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“HOLY WARRIORS” OF THE BARBARIAN SOCIETY? MYTHOLOGY AND REALITY CONCERNING THE GERMANIC “ANIMAL-WARRIORS”

Fábián István*

Abstract

The Germanic mythology has a very special character: the animal-warrior. Although present in many other indo-European and North-American mythologies, the wolfspetze and the berserker had some interesting individual features. Beyond mythology lies an entire web of historic sources (written and epigraphic) who stresses out the fact that these warriors were not only the fruit of a rich imagination. They actually were present in such “rational” institutions as the roman army or, later, in the armies of early medieval northern kings. This paper tries to emphasize a few aspects of this complex problem.

Keywords: Germanic, Auxilia, Mythology, Wolfspetze, Berserker

“In the Germanic ideology and practice war conquered everything and colored everything”, said rightfully Georges Dumézil¹ referring to the traditional Germanic society where war became a ritual justified by theology: primarily the assimilation of the battle with the idea of sacrifice, when both the victor and the defeated offered their sacrifice in blood, considering the fact that war and death brought an unique and privileged experience which made the warrior to get closer to the inspired poet or the visionary prophet². The mingling between warrior, prophet, poet was a characteristic feature of the god designed by Tacitus “*regnator omnius deus*”, identified later with Odin/Wotan³. Although, he was a god of war, Odin/Wotan seldom participated directly to battles, even so he used rather the powers of magic, blinding his enemies or inducing a state of paralyzing fear so they were not able to fight. Another magical feature was to induce to his warriors a state of blind, almost pathological, fury: “all his men were fighting without armor, like wild wolves or dogs. They were biting their shields and they were strong like bears or like bulls. They were killing everyone, and nor steel nor fire had no effect on them. It is what they call the *Berserkgang*”⁴. In the same order, Tacitus, speaking about the *Chatti*, he asserted that: “they are fierce, but they enhance the savageness of their

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¹ Georges Dumézil, *Mythes et dieux de germans. Essai de interprétation comparative*, Paris, Leroux, 1939, p. 103.

² Mircea Eliade, *Istoria ideilor și credințelor religioase*, București, Editura Univers Enciclopedic, 2000, p. 329.

³ Tacitus, *De origine et situ germanorum*, VI, București, Editura Didactică și Pedagogică, 1963, p. 41.

⁴ Ynglinga Saga, *apud* Mircea Eliade *op. cit.*, p. 329; Georges Dumézil, *Zeii suverani ai indo-europenilor*, București, Editura Univers Enciclopedic, 1996, p. 190.

nature by specific masteries: they paint their shields and bodies in black, and for attacks they choose the darkest nights. Just only the seeing of the army of ghosts (*exercitus ferralis*) puts you in all the fears of death... no enemy can withstand this infernal view: because in all battles the first things which are defeated are the eyes”⁵.

In any case, Iulius Cesar, Tacitus, or Snorri Sturlusson or even the pictures on the Trajan’s Column, describe a class of specialized warriors in missions of reconnaissance and guerrilla warfare. What is a common feature of all this sources is the uncommon savageness and cruelty of these warriors, especially of the ones called *berserker* or *wolfspetze* (“the wolf skinner”). This class of warrior induced their state of rage by consuming a potion made of a powerful psychotropic alkaloid - muscarinic - with strong hallucinogen effects. The induced state, especially in the case of young warriors, was a specific one, producing a “transmutation of their humanity in a state of aggressive, blind fury”⁶. That is why, Eliade considered that, in the case of these warriors, in order to become redoubtable fighters it was necessary to magically assimilate the animal behavior, especially of the wolf’s behavior. “So, he was dressed in the wolf’s skin in order to impart the way of this predator, or in order to symbolize his transformation in a wolf. As long as the individual was wearing this skin he was no longer human, but a predator: he was not only a fierce and invincible warrior, dominated by the *furor heroicus* but he became a beast. He no longer had to do with the ways of humans... The young warriors no longer were satisfied just with the war prays, but he behaved like animals, consuming for instance human flesh”⁷. This cannibalism originated from the idea that by consuming the flesh of the defeated enemy a part of his spirit was transmitted. In all cases, even we have some specific descriptions, it cannot be stated that we are dealing with a common practice. The transformation in animal-warrior was made after an initiatory fight during which the courage of the candidate was put to the test. The same Tacitus gives us the example of the *Chatti* tribes, where the solicitant never cut his hair or beard before killing an enemy or, at the *Thaifali* where he had to kill a bear or a boar or, in the case of the *Heruli* had to go to his first battle and fight empty handed. Saxo Grammaticus, much later in the 9th century, shows exactly the role of these *berserker* as elite troops of the king’s Army, beside their military role they were considered as protectors of the king’s court - and implicitly Odin’s favorite warriors - as guards of the sovereign function in the Germanic divine tripartite mythology⁸.

⁵ Tacitus, *De origine et...*, cit., p. 43.

⁶ Mircea Eliade, *De la Zalmoxis la Genghis Han*, București, Editura Humanitas, 1998, p. 16.

⁷ Georges Dumézil, *Gods of Ancient Northmen*, Los Angeles, University of California Press, 1973, p. 14.

⁸ Georges Dumézil, *Zeii suverani ai...*, cit., p. 190 sqq., characterized the Germanic society as a tripartite one (as any indo-European society): its most important manifestation is the presence of three elements of social hierarchy: the sovereign function (represented by local chieftains and royalty), the warrior function (represented by men at arms) and the function of fecundity (peasants).

The explanation of this warriors possessed by the *furor heroicus* resides in the concept that the Germanic tribes believed that in order to earn the favors of the warrior god (generically named as Odin/Wotan or Woden) it is not enough to be a good fighter, someone must be “chosen”. The battles on earth represent trials during which the fallen ones are chosen to enter the warrior heaven. The warrior god intervenes in the moment of the fight in the favor of the chosen one by inducing this state of intense fury and, on the other hand, ties the hands of the enemy with the so called *her-fjodur* (military bound). This induced state of rage made the *berserker* to feel relieved of all earthly things and concentrate only on his main purpose: to become an *einheiar* (“chosen warrior”), honored after his death to enter the Germanic heaven (generically called *Walhalla*⁹, a term which can be translated as “the hall of the chosen ones”) an there to spend his afterlife in training and feasting. In this way the Germanic tribes tried to explain one of the main features of their mythology: the ongoing menace of the Apocalypse. The warrior god gathers his troops for the Final Battle, *Ragnarok*, the moment in which the infernal forces will rise against the order instituted by the gods. The recruitment of the *einheiar* is made under the sign of this final battle. This class of beast-warriors made their initiation on the battle field, they must die heroically, enter *Walhalla* and in the *Ragnarok* he must fight fiercely and die on the side of his gods. This conception becomes a part of Germanic, and later Nordic warrior ideology in such a manner that is generally considered that: “the only real support of the human spirit is heroism... the fighter demonstrates who he is by dying in battle”¹⁰. The Germanic philosophy considered that the real power of the Good is not to smash Evil in a single blow, but to resist Evil as long as possible, accepting a certain defeat if it is necessary on the long term. Of course, there are great dozes of fatalism in the Germanic mythology and implicitly in their warrior ideology, grouped around the idea that no one can elude his destiny and the only way to live and die honorably is the way of the warrior.

This mythology, at the institutional level, created a class of specialized warriors whose prime goal was the protection of the ruler, the defense of the community, expansion toward new territories. This organization (whose Latin name is *comitatus*) was considered to be “the secret weapon that facilitated the expansion of Indo-European communities”¹¹.

But beyond the myths and legends lays an entire network of archeological, artistic and literary elements that underlines the existence of this class of “beast-warriors”. Their fighting technique, as Michael P.

⁹ Jan De Vries, *Altgermansiche Religionsgeschichte*, Berlin-Leipzig, Editura De Gruyter, 1970, p. 94; Georges Dumézil, *Zeii suverani ai...*, cit., p. 192.

¹⁰ *Ibidem*.

¹¹ Scott C. Littleton, *The New Comparative Mythology. An Anthropological Assessment of the Theories of Georges Dumézil*, Berkeley, University of California Press, 1982, p. 156, *apud* John C. Russel, *The germanisation of early medieval Christianity*, London-New-York, Longman, 1994.

Speidel emphasized, “link the Bronze, Iron, and Middle Ages, two thousand years of history seldom seen as belonging together”¹². The Germanic warrior stiles, founded during the Bronze Age, “gave way among classical Greeks and Romans to rational warfare. In middle and northern Europe, however warriors followed the ancient styles throughout the Iron Age and early Middle Ages”¹³. And here is the most interesting part: how this “rational warfare”, especially the Romans used this class of “holy warriors”. Tacitus, in his *De origine et situ germanorum*, emphasizes (as seen before) a few characteristics of the initiation of the chosen warriors and their way of waging a battle. Before considering Tacitus just a literary exaggeration, we should take a look to the concrete historical-archaeological evidence.

The most important in this perspective is emperor’s Trajan Column, an important work of art and propaganda who also can serve as vital source in the identification of ancient warrior types. Showing the Roman counterattack in Lower Moesia from of 101 A.D., the Column on scene 36 depicts the emperors horse guards the *Equites Singulare Augusti*, raised by Trajan himself, mainly from Batavi and other Germanic tribes allied to the Romans. What is more interesting is a row of foot soldiers wearing wolf and bear skins and using a mixed Roman-Germanic weaponry¹⁴. These two kinds of warriors (wolf- and bear- warriors) are very seldom met together, only in a description from 872 A.D. of Thorbjorn Hornklofi of the battle from Hafrsfjord, we meet this: *wulfhefnar* (wolf-hood bearers) and *bersekir* (bear hood bearers, but also the term was used as *furious warrior*)¹⁵. “It is astonishing to find in a work of Roman art the same two kind of animal warriors that, 800 years later stalk together in a skaldic poem”¹⁶. Anyway the presence of these warriors in the Roman Army in skirmishing operations or in counterattacks or as *exploratores* was an usual fact. The same Tacitus described them: “a wild show, frightening with animal skins and huge weapons”¹⁷. The only problem is the tribal status of these auxiliaries: were they young warriors during their combat initiation or were they champions, fully grown fighters, members of a *comitatus*? It is hard to answer due to lack of Germanic literary source for the specific period.

The Romans generally, and the Roman Army specially, had an interesting view toward the Germanic warriors. First they were conceived as brutal barbarians especially after the devastating invasions of the Cimbri and Teutons from the end of the 2nd century B.C., then merciless enemies of Rome, after the battle from the Teutoburg Forrest from the year 9 A.D. (when three Roman legions were entirely destroyed by a Germanic coalition led by Arminius). After the reign of Augustus, more and more

¹² Michael P. Speidel, *Ancient Germanic Warriors. Warrior Styles from Trajan’s Column to Icelandic Sagas*, London-New-York, Routledge, 2004, p. 2.

¹³ *Ibidem*.

¹⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 7.

¹⁵ *Ibidem*, p. 8.

¹⁶ *Ibidem*.

¹⁷ Tacitus, *Istoriî*, Book II, Paragraph 88, 3, Bucureşti, Editura Ştiinţifică, 1963, p. 94.

Germanic ethnic units were organized as *auxilia*, and took part in the Roman military campaigns. Their courage, loyalty was much appreciated by the Roman officers and moreover the Romans “borrowed” the one of the most specific signs of the Germans: the bear and/or wolf skins. Speidel presumes that in the beginning the Roman soldiers took these skins as a personal trophy from their vanquished enemies. It was a mark of courage: later, the bravest soldier of a unit, the *signifier* wore such skins (especially bear skin) as a mark of his rank and status¹⁸.

Finally, a few word about the presence of this special class of warriors in the Roman military presence in the province of Dacia. Between a large number of ethnic units (*alae*, *cohortes* and *numeri*), draws attention:

- *Ala I Batavorum miliaria* - recruited from Batavi, famous for their bravery, specialized in landing operations¹⁹, came in Dacia during the reign of Hadrian and stationed at Boroşneu Mare and Războeni-Cetate. Its presence is marked, among specific archeological proves, by a large number of inscriptions²⁰.
- *Ala I Tungrorum Frontoniana* - recruited from Tungri during the reign of Augustus, came in Dacia also in the time of Hadrian, and was stationed in Banat²¹ and Ilişua²².
- *Numerus Germanorum (Germanicianorum) exploratorum* - this unit participated occupation of Dacia and was stationed at Orăştioara de Sus. Its presence is marked by many epigraphic proofs. One of the most interesting is the tombstone of a Germanic soldier of this unit, Iulius Secundus: *Dis Manibus / Iulio Secundo / exploratory stipendiorum XXXII / Domo Agripinensis / Vixit annis LV / Heres faciendum curavit*²³.

The warrior cult and the myths linked to it are the most powerful heritages of the Germanic tribes in the Ancient world. The presence of wolf- and bear-warriors in the Imperial Army, but also in the Nordic Armies, creates a link that united the Ancient world with the Medieval one.

The institution of the *comitatus* changed its shape and “conquered” medieval Europe in the form of the knight orders. They had the same

¹⁸ Michael P. Speidel, *op. cit.*, p. 18.

¹⁹ Adrian Husar, *Celţi şi germani în Dacia romană*, Cluj-Napoca, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 1999, p. 111.

²⁰ *Inscripțiile Daciei Romane (I.D.R.)*, vol. I, *Introducere istorică şi epigrafică, Diplomele militare, Tăblițele cerate*, Bucureşti, Editura Academiei Republicii Socialiste România, 1975, DiplD XVI, pp. 118-121.

²¹ *Ibidem*, vol. III, *Dacia Superior*, t. 3, *Zona centrală (teritoriul dintre Ulpia Traiana, Micia, Apulum, Alburnus Maior, Valea Crişului)*, Bucureşti, Editura Academiei Republicii Socialiste România, 1984, 107, pp. 118-119.

²² *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum*, vol. III, *Inscriptiones Asiae, provinciarum Europae Graecarum, Illyrici Latinae*, Berlin, s.n., 1873, fragm. 798, *apud* Adrian Husar, *op. cit.*, p. 119.

²³ *I.D.R.*, vol. III, t. 3, *cit.*, 263, pp. 261-263.

ideology based on group loyalty, and loyalty toward the leader, the concept of “holy warrior” or chosen one. These all lead eventually to the expansion of European ideas in the form of the Crusades.

**FROM THE HISTORY OF READING. EXAMPLES FROM
THE ROMANIAN WORLD
(THE XVIITH AND THE XVIIITH CENTURIES)**

Corina Teodor*

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to analyze the manner in which the relationship between book and society has been delineated into premodern Romanian society. Succeeding François Furet, the French historian who turned the researches on the history of the books towards the receiver, we would like to emphasize the feminist practices of reading, as they were established at the level of Wallachia and Moldavia's elite.

Our analysis is based on a comparative perspective. It emphasizes some studies of case, as they are resulted after the enquiry of the official papers of the Court, the denotation on the books pages, correspondence, chronicles, travel diaries. We would like to find out which were the reading genres preferences of the feminine elite during the XVIIth and XVIIIth centuries, what kind of image the women attracted by reading were able to pass on and if the masculine power, as representing the dominant culture, did really perceived them as "becoming intellectuals" or, on the contrary, they were looked on hostile.

Keywords: Readings, Woman, Enlightenment, Romanian Society

“Că nu este alta și mai frumoasă și mai de folos în toată viața omului zăbavă decât cetitul cărților...” Miron Costin's reflection from the foreword of *De neamul moldovenilor*, towards which many of the historians of culture have turned to with admiration, almost became a typical collocation when the researchers interest pointed to the study of reading practices in Romanian society at the end of the Middle Age. But before making any cursory generalization, we have to ask ourselves if we could extend this meditation within the feminine universe. Especially considering that the way of living and the cultural horizon of the two halves, masculine and feminine, have been so dissimilar up to the XIXth century. It is only then, women having an intellectual formation according to the Romanticism canons, which means almost nothing less than masculine education, are starting to assert in cultural life, either to literary reunions, such as Livia Maiorescu, the critic's daughter, or having themselves involved in translating works, as Hermiona Asachi, Gheorghe Asachi's daughter, or in journalistic boom, where we meet C. A. Rosetti's wife, Maria Rosetti, which is considered to be the first Romanian female journalist in the literary historian's opinion.

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Succeeding François Furet admonition, who has assigned the coordinates of the relation book-society more than three decades ago, then considering the methodological suggestion offered by Roger Chartier, Guglielmo Cavallo or Robert Darnton¹, we intend to study the feminist practices of reading, as they were established within the elitist society from Wallachia and Moldavia in the second half of the XVIIth century and the first half of the XVIIIth century. As Răzvan Theodorescu² perceives it on artistic and cultural level, it is the age of transition between medieval and modern times. Our analysis does not include Transylvania because of its specific evolution as multiconfessional and multiethnic space, that has been connected to Mitteleuropa especially after the Habsburgic success of Reconquista and the Ecclesiastic Union of Romanians with the Catholic Church, when the transition to modernism has been accelerated; thus, there is nothing astonishing, neither in the chancellor Teleki's febrile activity to inaugurate a public library at Tirgu-Mureș in 1802, nor in his wife's interest for books; during two decades, the countess Susana Bethlen has been gathering 2000 volumes, especially editions printed during the XVIth-XVIIIth centuries and representing the same domains as the main library, religious and agricultural literature, educational books, sermons, paediatrics, philosophy, newspapers; after her death, in 1799 her library has been included in Teleki Collection and the books may be identified in the third of the four volumes library catalogue that has been published at Vienna between 1796-1819³.

Therefore, we will try to assign some of the reading coordinates, because if we consider Occidental historiography researches, it became clear that within the triad *author - creation - reader*, the last one is not at all seen as passive element. According to Michel de Certeau⁴, the text is important only through those who actually read it, it changes along with them and is systematized on other perception codes. During the last years, researches on the history of culture have brought a displacement of the interest from book to reading and some of

¹ Roger Chartier, *Lecturi și cititori în Franța vechiului Regim*, București, Editura Meridiane, 1997; Roger Chartier, Guglielmo Cavallo, *Histoire de la lecture dans le monde occidental*, Paris, Éditions du Seuil, 1997; Robert Darnton, *Marele masacru al pisicii și alte episoade din istoria culturală a Franței*, Iași, Editura Polirom, 2000.

² Răzvan Theodorescu, *Civilizația românilor între medieval și modern. Orizontul imaginii (1550-1800)*, vol. I-II, București, Editura Meridiane, 1987.

³ Mihály Spielmann, *Teleki Bolyai Library*, in "Transilvanian Review", IV, 2, 1995, p. 105.

⁴ Gerard Mauger, *Écrits, lecteurs, lectures*, in "Annales. Histoire, Science Sociales", 1999, no. 34, pp. 144-161.

the historians, such as Roger Chartier, have tried to retrace the way “the world of text” encounters “the world of readers”. But it is so difficult to investigate the practice of reading, because it leaves no tangible traces, but can only be perceived in an infinity of some other cultural gestures.

In this “reading file,” succeeding the hermeneut Paul Ricoeur, historians have also highlighted the role of the reader, without him the text having no real significance. Therefore, we intend to delineate the practice of reading in the feminine universe of Romanian elite, a sequential subject that is situated at the frontier between the history of books and that of woman’s.

If the history of book has initiate the investigation of the past practices of reading, the history of woman continues to be a subject that has been gradually delineated inside the European and American historiography, its study being accelerated by the women’s lib of the 70’s and its specific questions raised by the context. From time to time, there were certain historiographycal assessments, under the form of interrogation, that had been attached to the researches on the women’s role, her involvement in quotidian life, her relation with state authority, family etc. “Do women have a history?” is the question that Michelle Perrot, Fabienne Bock and Pauline Schmidt have asked in 1973, at the inauguration of the first university seminar on this subject; ten years latter, they asked another one “Is a history of women possible?” Finally, in 1998, at the colloquy from Rouen, the initial question has been transformed into “Is it possible to have a history without women?”⁵.

According to Michelle Perrot’s opinion, an eminent researcher of the subject, the history of woman has answered to a double will: that of crashing the silence surrounding women’s existence and, on the other side, that of making more visible their role in time. By recovering their traces, historiography enriches its discourse about the economical, social, political, cultural, simbolistical problematics⁶.

In a methodological and interpretative progress, the studies have delineated monographs or group portraits, have enlightened the relation between public and private, the woman’s role inside the community, fashion, travelling, the exile, reading, love, thus passing from meditations on the subject “what women are?” to answers for “what are women

⁵ Fabrice Virgili, *L’histoire des femmes et l’histoire des genres aujourd’hui*, in “Vingtième Siècle”, 2002, July-September, pp. 5-14.

⁶ Michelle Perrot, *La bibliothèque, mère de l’histoire des femmes*, in “Revue de la BNF”, 2004, no. 17.

doing”⁷. After *Histoire mondiale de la femme*, from 1965-1967, a synthesis coordinated by Pierre Grimal, a specialist in Roman history, who has admitted the scientific importance of the researches over the woman statute in history, passing through the challenges of the generation that has been defined itself as bearer of the discourse *La Nouvelle Histoire*, up to the *Storia delle Donne*, the synthesis of the 90’s, coordinated by Michel Perrot and George Duby⁸, that legitimates these days the history of women as a distinctive direction in historical researches, we may witness a passionate polemic between *gender studies* and *women studies*. Far from being finished, it proves the selfhood of European discourse of researches as compared to the American one, especially if we count that *women studies* partisans consider that a history of the gender would guise women again, by opposing the two words, *Her-story* and *Hi(s)-story*, in a concise formula and an untranslatable wordplay⁹.

Sounding the past practices of reading is an interesting means of understanding the cultural practices of that time. But the sources we might use to make such a historical reconstruction are quite few and fragmentary: in this case of feminine elite, most of the testimonies are indirect. However, we consider that the use of sources like these, may offer suggestions, hypothesis, approximations, interrogations.

In order to delineate the feminine reading features, we have chosen to strike out three different directions of investigating the Romanian society of the XVIIth-XVIIIth centuries: the patronage over the printing activities, feminine book donations and reading, as individual way of self-perfection.

Considering the patronage over the books, as recognition of the patron’s spiritual interest for that specific book, according to Professor Alexandru Duțu’s assertion¹⁰, we must point out the importance of Matei Basarab’s age. It has brought the resumption of typographic activity in Wallachia, which can not be considered as a temporary cultural success, but also in the terms of strengthening the monarchic authority¹¹. It is, in fact, a real typographical revulsion that may be noticed in the four typographic centres, Câmpulung (1635-1650), Govora (1637-1642), Dealu Monastery (1644-1647) and Târgoviște

⁷ *Ibidem*.

⁸ Italian edition, Laterza 1990, French edition, 1991-1992.

⁹ Fabrice Virgili, *op. cit.*, p. 12.

¹⁰ Alexandru Duțu, *Carte și societate în sec. XVIII*, in Idem, *Explorări în istoria literaturii române*, București, Editura pentru literatură, 1969, p. 48.

¹¹ Mircea Tomescu, *Istoria cărții românești de la începuturi până la 1918*, București, Editura Științifică, 1968, p. 65.

(1646-1652)¹². The typography of Câmpulung has replaced Matei Basarab's patronage on that of Melchisedec, the monastery superior, but the other centres have continued their activity as lordly typographies, by printing, at the same time, Slavonic, Slavo-Romanian and Romanian books. In this cultural climate, alongside lordly patronage, Udriște Năsturel has been asserted himself as a real spiritual coordinator of those times. The Voivode's brother-in-law, translator and author of some "coats of arms poems", he was representing the aulic Orthodox current and he was also member of the so-called "court culture"¹³. By his quill, as a representative figure of the nobility elite, we may foresee some of his sister's cultural profile, Elena, Radu Năsturel's daughter and Matei Basarab's wife.

Even if we do not know many of her education, we may presume that she could speak Greek; as the wife of the Wallachian voivode, she has been associated with Matei Basarab in his cultural patronage. Although the researches of women history have been for a long time tributary to some anecdotic and sententious reconstructions, even romanticized, the recent studies, as those signed by Violeta Barbu, Maria Magdalena Szekely, Sorin Iftimi, Dan Horia Mazilu¹⁴ are trying to pull out of the anonymity the women statute and their destiny in Romanian past history.

Therefore, we must point out the dedicatory verses that Udriște Năsturel wrote to his sister, laudable verses, when publishing the Romanian translation of *Imitatio Christi*, at Dealu Monastery, in 1647, which is more than an eulogistic canon, a possible reference concerning Elena Basarab's cultural horizon¹⁵.

In this stage of Romanian typographic activity, when the religious texts were quite prevailed, along with those of moral education, the praises dedicated to Elena Năsturel do not surpass the religious terms. According to the time mentality, women were strongly influenced by their readings, that is why

¹² Barbu Theodorescu, *Repertoriul cărții românești vechi*, in "Biserica Ortodoxă Română, 1960", no. 3-4, pp. 339-366.

¹³ Răzvan Theodorescu, *op. cit.*, vol. II, pp. 45-47; Dan Horia Mazilu, *Udriște Năsturel*, București, Editura Minerva, 1974, p. 110.

¹⁴ Violeta Barbu, *De bono coniugali. O istorie a familiei în Țara Românească în secolul al XVII-lea*, București, Editura Meridiane, 2003; Maria Magdalena Szekely, *Maria Asanina Paleologhina. O prințesă bizantină pe tronul Moldovei*, Mănăstirea Putna, 2006; Sorin Iftimi, *Curtea doamnei (I). Dregători și slujitori ai doamnelor Moldovei*, in "Anuarul Institutului de istorie A. D. Xenopol", 1995, vol. XXXII, pp. 423-440; Dan Horia Mazilu, *Văduvele sau despre istorie la feminin*, Iași, Editura Polirom, 2008.

¹⁵ Petre V. Năsturel, *Genealogia Năsturelilor*, in "Revista pentru istorie, arheologie și filologie", vol. XI, part I, 1910, p. 319.

we have to admit as undercurrent the men's surveillance over the texts women were about to read; but in Elena's case, considering that Matei Basarab was not an erudite person, this surveillance was not her husband's prerogative, but of her brother's, Udriște Năsturel, whose connections with the intellectual and Orthodox circles were already known¹⁶.

The feminine elite's involvement in endowing churches and monasteries with religious books, as we may conclude by studying the text's marginal inscriptions, is also due to the religious context of the time. Women's intention was to enrich the properties of the churches, as they were seen both as *res sacra* (the properly edifice and all those goods used for the religious services, including books), and as *res ecclesiastica* (meaning territorial possessions, financial goods, animals)¹⁷. During the last decades, historians have studied the act of founding as connected to religious mentality and it is seen as some kind of bridge between man and God; the founder tries this way to achieve the holy grace¹⁸.

Books and manuscripts donation surpasses the religious significance; there is also a cultural purport, because of the books circulation within the entire Romanian territory, even beyond state frontiers.

We will try to illustrate a few sequences of the books itinerary, in order to reveal the manner the feminine elite became part of such a cultural experience. There is a book, *Evanghelie*, at the Church of the Holy Sepulchre from Jerusalem, with the portraits of Matei Basarab and Elena, and the Greek denotation reminds us that it has been the voievod's donation¹⁹. Ecaterina, Vasile Lupu's second wife, has redeemed from the Kazahs a *Liturghier*, a manuscript ornamented by Anastasie Crimca with some miniatures. The manuscript has been taken away from Dragomirna Monastery, but it was brought back due to Ecaterina's initiative²⁰. Vasile Lupu's daughter, Ruxandra, is also mentioned in documents; she has offered two books, *Minei*, one for April, the other for May, to Agapia Monastery, during the times of the priest Nicanor²¹.

¹⁶ Virgil Căndea, *Umanismul lui Udriște Năsturel și agonia slavonismului cultural în Țara Românească*, in Idem, *Rățiunea dominantă*, Cluj, Editura Dacia, 1979, pp. 33-78.

¹⁷ Arcadie Bodali, *Semnificațiile actelor ctitoricești în evul mediu românesc*, in "Anuarul Institutului de istorie A. D. Xenopol", 2005, p. 19.

¹⁸ *Ibidem*.

¹⁹ Marcu Beza, *Urme românești în răsăritul ortodox*, second edition, București, Editura librăriei Pavel Suru, 1937, p. 111.

²⁰ George Popescu Vâlcea, *Școala miniaturistică de la Dragomirna*, in "Biserica Ortodoxă Română", 1968, no. 7-8, p. 961.

²¹ The researchers are identifying her as being Alexandru Lăpușneanu's wife - Radu Constantinescu and Virgil Căndea, Maria Magdalena Szekely, *Femei-*

Nasta, the former Moldavian voievod Alexandru Iliăș's daughter, has offered an *Octoih* to Șcheii Brașovului, in 1678, and so as Brâncoveanu's daughter, Maria, who has donated a *Liturghier* to the church of the village Bucerdea (Alba). Păuna Cantacuzino, Șerban Cantacuzino's wife, has offered a *Triod* to the village of Recea, "*pentru pomenirea Măriei sale*".

There is also another social level of nobility elite that can be noticed among the women who have made books donations. For instance, the book printed at Rădăuți, in 1745, *Ceaslov*, that "*l-au cumpărat dumneaei jupâneasa Ecaterina a răposatului Costachi Cantacuzino, biv vel spătar și l-au dat la schitișorul domniilor sale la Almaș*", in 1751. Or *Canonul Sf. Spiridon* (Iași, 1750), which "*l-au dat iubitul soțu meu Nastasia, fiica răposatului vornicului Dumitrașco Paladi, bisăricii noastre din Șerbești*", in 1771²².

Although the marginal notes do not allow us to make an analysis of the exterior features of women, we consider that these examples may demonstrate that, during the XVIIth-XVIIIth centuries, the interest for books has not been the men's privilege; this association of man and woman within a family, either lordly or noble, or the donations made of feminine initiative, proves the existence of the same inner impulse, based on the religious climate of the time.

We must also mention that a short regard over Movilă family thesaurus, that reveals both its possessions and the statute of the family heiress, brings out some books, along with the most valuable objects; there were Maria Movilă's books, Ieremia Movilă's daughter, who has been twice married, first to Ștefan Potocki, second to Firley, the Voivode of Sandomierz²³, both representing the Polonaise nobility: "*trei evangheliare legate în aur pur masiv, fiecare legătură valorând 3000 de scuzi de aur și cinci legate în argint masiv*"²⁴.

Finally, the feminine reading as a practice and modality of improving the intellectual horizon starts from the way the literacy could open the access to knowledge, at the elite level. If the feminine attendance to Romanian teaching remains quite

ctitor în Moldova medievală, in "Anuarul Institutului A. D. Xenopol", XXXII, 1995, p. 446.

²² Elena Chiaburu, *Carte și tipar în Țara Moldovei până la 1829*, Iași, Editura Universității "Al. Ioan Cuza", 2005, p. 171, p. 190.

²³ Marya Kasterska, *Les trésors des Movila en Pologne*, in "Revue historique du sud-est européen", vol. XIII, 1936, fasc. 1-4, January-December, pp. 69-77.

²⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 199; Lucian Predescu, *Udriște Năsturel și răspândirea romanului religios Varlaam și Ioasaf. Viața lui Udriște Năsturel*, in "Biserica Ortodoxă Română", 1965, no. 1-2, p. 75; Eufrosina Dvoicenco, *Un studiu necunoscut al lui Hașdeu despre traducerea cărții De imitatione Christi în 1647*, in "Revista istorică", 1932, no. 10-12, pp. 315-328.

hypothetical up to the XIXth century, the study of women correspondence and other documents - testaments, in the first instance, might give us indirect marks. Even if there were no women of letters in Romanian Countries outside the Carpathians, such as Queen Margot - whose celebrity in European historiography is due to Robert Muchembled's commentaries on her written memories²⁵, or Veronica Franco, Vittoria Colonna, Gaspara Stampa - poetess of the Renaissance, the feminine literacy was not lacking.

We can not omit the difficulty in revealing this phenomenon of feminine literacy from the multitude of documents, partly because of the writers, scribes the women were surrounded by, although there is no way of speaking about a "feminine chancellery"²⁶; in this way, women have left behind them only a few written signs. However, some examples allow us to complete the feminine "file" of literacy: thus, a document from 1627 mentions an older one, issued by Ion Vodă's wife, Marica, a "*zapis făcut de mâna ei și cu pecetea ei*"²⁷.

Elena, Matei Basarab's wife, as we mentioned before, has been appointed as regent, while the Voivode was going to the Ottoman Empire to receive his reign confirmation, in December 1632²⁸; according to her position, she had to get involved in coordinating the chancellery activity and to keep correspondence in Romanian and Latin; for instance, she has described the battle of Finta and has sealed the document with red sealing wax²⁹.

If we mention some other letters, such as Elisabeta Movilă's Latin letters, written in February 1614³⁰, or those written in Italian, in 1638 by her daughter, Ana Movilă, whose husband was Stanislav Potocki³¹, the Polonaise noble, or the Greek correspondence of Vasile Lupu's daughter, Ruxandra, the one married to Timuș Hmelnicki, whose letters were sealed and signed by herself³², and some others, they are all proving

²⁵ Robert Muchembled, *Pătimiri ale femeilor în vremea reginei Margot*, Chișinău, Editura Cartier, 2004.

²⁶ Sorin Iftimi, *op. cit.*, p. 435.

²⁷ *Ibidem*, p. 435.

²⁸ Nicolae Iorga, *Istoria românilor*, vol. VI, București, 1938, p. 36.

²⁹ Ștefan Meteș, *Contribuții nouă privitoare la familia boierească Buhuș din Moldova*, in "Analele Academiei Române. Memoriile Secției Istorice", series III, tom VII, 1927; T. G. Bulat, *O mărturie a doamnei Elina despre bătălia de la Finta*, in "Revista istorică", 1926, no. 1-3, pp. 18-19.

³⁰ Andrei Veresss, *Documente privitoare la istoria Ardealului, Moldovei și Țării Românești*, vol. IX, București, 1937, pp. 3-4.

³¹ Elena Eftimiu, *Relațiuni ceho-române în trecut*, in "Revista istorică", 1931, no. 10-12, pp. 294-298.

³² Vasile A. Urechia, *Biserica din cetatea Neamț și documente relative la Vasile Lupu și doamna Ruxandra*, in "Analele Academiei Române. Memoriile Secției

the same cultural horizon of the feminine elite of the XVIIth-XVIIIth centuries. Those letters are more than sequences of women's destinies, as the correspondence between Constantin Brâncoveanu's wife, Maria, and the ruler of Braşov, in 1717, concerning the doom of her daughters³³ proves to be, but also consignments of their educational level, of their knowledge on cultural languages, evidences of their self-image, of the contemporary state authority structure and mechanism.

Diplomatic documents, testaments, the correspondence and marginal notices, giving information about the feminine passion of reading, are all going to complete the image of the feminine elite. Following another feminine destiny, in fact an amount of asymmetric sequences that allow us to make a comparison between the XVIIth and the XVIIIth century, we consider a document from 1657, issued by Gheorghe Ştefan for Antimia, to strength one of her properties; the document specifies that "*şi ea singură cu mâinile sale le-a făcut lor zapis şi l-a scris, fiind în cărţi foarte învăţată. Aşadar şi domnia mea, văzând dania de-a ei bună voie, încă şi de la Domnia Mea am dat şi am întărit slugei noastre, lui Gavriil Jora sluger şi doamnei sale, să le fie lor şi de la domnia mea acel sat mai sus scris Măndreşti dreaptă ocină şi danie şi uric şi întăritură, cu tot venitul neclintit niciodată în veci*"³⁴.

Few decades latter, in 1719, while writing his testament in Greek, the Stolnic Matei Creţulescu spoke about the importance of his library, bought from Vienna; there is also an urge for his sons and emphasis his wife's role in their education: "*când am fost la Viena pentru treaba celor doi copilaşi, ca să înveţe greceşte şi mai vârtos italieneşte şi latineşte, de care mă rog Zoitei să-mi înveţe copilaşii şi să-i strunească pentru carte de se va putea ca să-i pedepsească să-i înveţe mai bine...*"³⁵.

At the end of the XVIIIth century, Tzigara, a man whose work was to take care of the horses, drivers and mail stoppages from Moldavian territory, gave us a few information about his family destiny; thus, he proves that, during the age of Enlightenment, even the families with a lower social statute were having access to education. However, we must not omit

Istorice", IInd series, tom XI, 1888-1889, pp. 112-132; Grigore Tocilescu and Ioan Bogdan, *Din legăturile cu Moscova*, in "Revista istorică", 1937, no. 1-4, pp. 73-79.

³³ Constantin A. Stoide, *Noi documente braşovene*, in "Revista arhivelor", VII, 2, 1947, pp. 296-297.

³⁴ Elena Eftimiu, *Antimia, fata vornicului Grigore Ureche. Contribuţie documentară*, in "Revista arhivelor", no. 1-3, 1924-1926, pp. 370-372.

³⁵ Alexandru Marcu, *Un student român la Pisa şi Paris, către 1820: Simion Marcovici*, in "Revista istorică", 1929, no. 1-3, p. 23.

that this man was of Greek origin, his mother was a Comnen, and she has been eulogized by his own son: “1794, februarie 4 și-a plătit neuitata mea mamă Zefirița obșteasca datorie, jertfă a ofitei și a fost îngropată la Iași, în Moldova în biserica Goliei. Și avea 33 de ani. Femeie vrednică de respect pentru virtuțile ei și pentru nașterea ei, pregătită foarte bine în elinească și împărtășită cu științele publice”³⁶.

The Pre-Enlightenment climate emphasis the interest in the triumph of rationality, education and intellectual instruction. If we are interested on an educational pattern, we will find more information about the cantemirian one; we may thus observe that, after his settling in Russia, in 1711, Dimitrie Cantemir, the scholar prince, has never forget the ideal of giving his children the chance of studying abroad, as we may read in his testament. His correspondence with Peter the Great, that has been commented by Ștefan Ciobanu, reveals the former Moldavian Voivode’s predilection for study and soliloquies and also his preoccupation for his children’s education³⁷, whose knowledge of Greek language, even for corresponding, is well-known.

Cantemir’s testament has foreseen the same kind of education for all his children, making no difference between the four sons of his first marriage - Matei, Constantin, Șerban and Antioh, and their sister, Maria. According to Russian and Romanian positivism historiography, it is presumable that Maria’s education begun within the family, having her mother Casandra for learning Greek; then, she has continued her education in Russia, with professor Kondoiti for learning Latin and Italian and Ivan Iliinschi, who thought her Russian³⁸.

Beyond the details about her private life, next to the biographical notes that reveals her privileged statute in Peter the Great’s eyes, the correspondence with Antioh Cantemir, her brother, unveils her intellectual neatness. Her sensibility, her literary horizon, her profound knowledge on Greek and Latin she used for corresponding, all those are revealed by the reflections based on her own reading; she has been provided with books due to her brother, Antioh. Maria used to read a lot, especially literary and classic, humanist historiography works, Horace, Cornelius Nepos, Flavius Josephus, Appian, Boccaccio, but she was also interested in some books that were quite appreciated in those times, such as the comedies of Juan Batista Diamante, the Spanish writer, and travel diaries.

³⁶ Nicolae Iorga, *Condica de menziluri a lui Scarlat vodă Callimachi*, in Idem, *Studii și documente*, vol. XIX, București, 1910, pp. 120-121.

³⁷ Ștefan Ciobanu, *Dimitrie Cantemir în Rusia*, București, Editura Elion, 2000, pp. 36-39.

³⁸ *Ibidem*, p. 82.

Certainly, the most important aspect is that Maria used to complete her written thoughts with personal assessments, which reveal both her sensibility and her intellectual horizon: “*cred că vă aduceți aminte - she wrote refering to Josephus Flavius - cum vă rugam încă de când erați la Moscova, să-mi găsiți această carte, după ce mi-ați tradus ceva din limba franceză; am presimțirea că ea va fi foarte interesantă, și întâi voi începe s-o citesc pe ea*”³⁹. She has done a bookish selection that proves her passion for literature, but also her craving in reading “*ceva din astronomie și geometrie*”⁴⁰. Thus, Maria Cantemir proves to be a brightly character of her age and it is quite difficult to appreciate her objectively, considering the default of other contemporary feminine figures; through her own epistolary confessions, she has recommended herself as representative of the feminine intellectual elite, a product of that age, when the humanism features have interfered with the Enlightenment critical spirit. Her correspondence seems to be more important as it proves her interest in improving her selfhood through reading, so as the yearning to speak about her cultural horizon. She is, in fact, representing a different generation of female readers. If we might speak about Elena Basarab in terms of an intellectual woman, whose interest was connected to an intensive way of reading, who has reduced her horizon to religious books to show respect for the church and sacredness’s authority⁴¹, we may state that Maria Cantemir represents the modern tendencies; she is, in fact, the product of the Pre-Enlightenment movement, that has been so brightly illustrated by her father, in both Romanian and South-East European culture. She has thus developed another way of reading, the extensive one, diversified, critical, that does reckon neither the number of pages, nor the domains.

But it has no sense to put everything under the sign of generalization; the sources we may study today can only reveal us the isolated portraits of some women of those times elite, whose passion for reading is well-known; we speak about teachable, educated women, that were able to write a letter, to copy a manuscript by themselves, to settle the structure of a testament, to sustain the typographic activity. The examples we have brought out, along with a future research over Transylvanian territory, although the differences between

³⁹ *Ibidem*, pp. 85-86.

⁴⁰ Dan Horia Mazilu, *Voievodul dincolo de sala tronului*, Iași, Editura Polirom, 2003.

⁴¹ Nicolae Iorga, *Doamna Elina a Țerii Românești ca patroană literară*, in “*Analele Academiei Române. Memoriile Secției Istorice*”, IIIrd series, tom XIII, pp. 57-67.

masculine and feminine level of reading in the XVIIth - XVIIIth centuries is quite obvious, cannot elide a question: is a history of reading possible without women?

**INTELLETTUALI, VIAGGIATORI E ARTISTI ITALIANI
ALLA “RISCOPERTA” DELLA GRECIA
FRA XVIII E XIX SECOLO**

Andrea Giovanni Noto*

Abstract

After a long period of oblivion and a series of great international events, Greece was rediscovered by Western Europe at the turn of the XIX century. Regarding this general context, not even Italy, that had always had a close relationship with the Hellenic world, thanks to remarkable cultural and historical affinities that bound the two peoples together, was an exception. This essay means to focus attention on the characters of the Italian intellectuals, travellers and artists of that time who favoured this great appeal for the Hellenistic civilization, developping in the Italian peninsula a strong philhellenic sentiment, useful for supporting the Greek Risorgimento and for binding the two nations together.

Keywords: Greece; Italy; Europe; Intellectuals; Travellers; Artists; Risorgimento; XVIII Century; XIX Century

La particolare visione prospettica dell'Occidente europeo ha conferito alla realtà storica della Grecia un inusuale destino: tanto studiata, ammirata, celebrata nel suo passato classico dalla millenaria tradizione, al punto da essere universalmente riconosciuta come perno fondante della cultura e dell'identità europea insieme al patrimonio della latinità romana, quanto dimenticata, ignorata, denigrata nelle sue vicende attinenti all'epoca moderna e contemporanea, per via della sua configurazione politica, religiosa e socio-culturale dalle molteplici e tutt'altro che univoche sfaccettature, “al tempo stesso frontiera dell'Europa ma parte dell'Oriente musulmano, minoranza cristiana ma di culto ortodosso, potenziale erede dell'impero ottomano ma elemento conflittuale delle lotte balcaniche”¹. Un aspetto quest'ultimo che, non a caso, ha giocato un ruolo assolutamente decisivo nell'ambito dei processi di *nation-building* e *state-building* vissuti dal Paese, finendo pesantemente per condizionarne il senso identitario e lo sviluppo storico mediante l'emergere di un rapporto ambivalente, sia a livello interno che esterno, con la tradizione e la cultura europea occidentale².

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¹ Stuart Joseph Woolf, “Prefazione”, in Antonis Liakos, *L'unificazione italiana e la grande idea. Ideologia e azione dei movimenti nazionali in Italia e in Grecia, 1859-1871*, Firenze, Aletheia, 1995, p. 5.

² Cfr. Paschalis M. Kitromilides, “Imagined communities” and the origins of the national question in the Balkans, in “European History Quarterly”, vol. 19, 1989, pp. 149-192; Victor Roudometof, *From Rum Millet to Greek Nation: Enlightenment, Secularization, and National Identity in Ottoman Balkan Society, 1453-1821*, in “Journal of Modern Greek Studies”, vol. 16, 1998, pp. 11-48;

Tra la seconda metà del Settecento e i primi due decenni dell'Ottocento, tuttavia, il Vecchio Continente fu indistintamente caratterizzato da una fase di intenso e rinnovato risveglio di interesse nei confronti del mondo ellenico, riscoperto inizialmente proprio a partire dal periodo aureo dell'Antichità classica e, tramite questo, indirettamente approcciato anche nella ben più trascurata realtà coeva, così da determinare la fioritura in quegli anni presso ampi strati della società europea e statunitense di un diffuso e duraturo sentimento filellenico, che si sarebbe rivelato un sostegno estremamente prezioso per le rivendicazioni libertarie avanzate con sempre maggiore vigore e frequenza dal popolo greco fino a riuscire a condizionare, almeno in una certa misura, gli esiti della Guerra di Indipendenza in funzione antiturca³.

A riaccendere il mito dell'Ellade, a lungo sopito con la rilevante eccezione rappresentata dall'età dell'Umanesimo e del Rinascimento, concorsero indubbiamente alcuni fattori di notevole portata come la diffusione della filosofia dei Lumi, la realizzazione di intense campagne di scavi archeologici (su tutte quelle attinenti ai siti di Ercolano e Pompei) e la moda di collezionare oggetti antichi a prezzo di qualsiasi sacrificio economico ed espediente più o meno lecito (come si evince dalla dolorosa vicenda dei "Marmi di Elgin" provenienti dall'Acropoli di Atene e traslati a Londra nel 1806⁴), il forte sviluppo del movimento neoclassico per merito,

Vangelis Kechriotis, "Lo stato ellenico, la nazione interna e la nazione esterna: rappresentazioni culturali e configurazioni politiche nel lungo XIX secolo", in Marco Dogo (a cura di), *Schegge d'impero, pezzi d'Europa. Balcani e Turchia fra continuità e mutamento. 1804-1923*, Gorizia, Libreria Editrice Goriziana, 1999, pp. 183-214; Ioannis K. Hassiotis, "La Chiesa greco-ortodossa e la formazione del nazionalismo neogreco durante la dominazione ottomana", in Luciano Vaccaro (a cura di), *Storia religiosa della Grecia*, Milano, Centro ambrosiano, 2002, pp. 219-238; Antonis Liakos, *La storia della Grecia come costruzione di un tempo nazionale*, in "Contemporanea", n. 1, gennaio 2001, pp. 155-170.

³ Sul filellenismo, vista la vastità dell'argomento, si rimanda, senza pretesa di esaustività a: William St. Clair, *That Greece might still be free. The Philhellenes in the War of Independence*, London, Oxford University Press, 1972; Gilles Pécout, "Une amitié politique méditerranéenne: le philhellénisme italien et français au XIXe siècle", in Maurizio Ridolfi (a cura di), *La democrazia radicale nell'Ottocento europeo*, Milano, Fondazione Giangiacomo Feltrinelli, 2005, pp. 81-106; AA. VV., *Indipendenza e unità nazionale in Italia ed in Grecia. Convegno di studio, Atene, 2-7 ottobre 1985*, Firenze, L. S. Olschki, 1987; *Risorgimento greco e filellenismo italiano: lotte, cultura, arte. Mostra promossa dall'Ambasciata di Grecia e dall'Associazione per lo sviluppo delle relazioni fra Italia e Grecia, Roma, Palazzo Venezia, 25 marzo-25 aprile 1986*, catalogo a cura di Caterina Spetsieri Beschi ed Enrica Lucarelli, Roma, Pubblicazione Edizioni del Sole, 1986; AA. VV., *Garibaldi e il filellenismo italiano nel XIX secolo*, Atene, Istituto italiano di cultura in Atene, 1985.

⁴ I "Marmi di Elgin" costituiscono un'importantissima raccolta di sculture e frammenti architettonici provenienti dall'Acropoli di Atene, acquistati dal diplomatico britannico Thomas Bruce, settimo conte di Elgin (1766-1841), tra il 1801 e il 1803, quando era ambasciatore presso il sultano di Costantinopoli. Il materiale fu trasportato in Gran Bretagna nell'arco di diversi anni e una parte della collezione fu mostrata per la prima volta a una ristretta cerchia di visitatori nel 1807, suscitando un enorme impatto dal momento che a Londra

soprattutto, del suo massimo teorico, il tedesco Johann Joachim Winckelmann. Apporti altrettanto importanti, inoltre, provennero dai clamorosi accadimenti connessi alla guerra russo-turca del 1768-1774 - segnati dall'emergere di un "caso greco" presso l'opinione pubblica internazionale in seguito alla sanguinosa repressione attuata da parte ottomana, per mezzo di bande irregolari di albanesi, di due rivolte scoppiate in Macedonia e nel Peloponneso nel 1770 dietro lo sprone di emissari della zarina Caterina II, intenzionata a liberare i fratelli ortodossi dal giogo degli "infedeli" e a riproporre una sorta di riedizione del defunto Impero bizantino, con la ricristianizzata Costantinopoli come capitale e con il suo secondo nipote Costantino nelle vesti di *basileus*⁵ -, dall'idealizzazione delle forme politiche repubblicane, dal contributo chiarificatore offerto da cospicui resoconti (descrittivi, storici, archeologici o letterari) dei visitatori stranieri che avevano compiuto dei viaggi nella terra di Platone, dall'emergere della sensibilità romantica e, naturalmente, dalle influenze dei grandi sommovimenti rivoluzionari d'America e di Francia⁶.

Rispetto a questo contesto generale, neppure l'Italia, da sempre polo privilegiato di relazione con il mondo ellenico, grazie alle notevoli affinità culturali, caratteriali e storiche esistenti fra i due popoli, fece eccezione. Anzi, per ciò che concerne la specificità italiana, va sottolineato come essa avesse mantenuto in buona parte intatti per tutto il Medioevo, nonostante il realizzarsi del drammatico scisma che nel 1054 aveva spaccato la Cristianità in una Chiesa d'oriente sotto il patriarca di Bisanzio e in una Chiesa d'occidente sotto il papa di Roma, e durante la prima età moderna, malgrado il crollo dell'Impero bizantino avvenuto il 29 maggio 1453, gli intensi vincoli di collegamento culturale, economico e

la scultura greca dell'età classica era rimasta fino ad allora praticamente sconosciuta, in quanto si aveva familiarità solo con copie romane e tardo-elleniche. L'intera collezione fu acquistata dal governo inglese nel 1816 e presa in custodia dal londinese British Museum, dove si trova ancora oggi in esposizione, nonostante le vivaci polemiche suscitate e le tante richieste, finora infruttuose, di restituzione avanzate dal governo greco e da molti membri della comunità internazionale.

⁵ In merito si vedano: Franco Venturi, *Settecento riformatore*, vol. III: *La prima crisi dell'Antico Regime (1768-1776)*, Torino, Einaudi, 1979, pp. 22-153; Edouard Driault, Michel Lheritier, *Histoire diplomatique de la Grèce de 1821 à nos jours*, 5 voll., Paris, Les Presses Universitaires de France, 1925-1926, vol. 1: Edouard Driault, *L'insurrection et l'indépendance (1821-1830)*, Paris, Les Presses Universitaires de France, 1925, pp. 19-24; Ariadna Camariano-Cioran, *La guerre russo-turque de 1768-1774 et les Grecs*, in "Revue des études sud-est européennes", III, 1965, 3-4, pp. 513-547; Francesco Cognasso, *Storia della questione d'Oriente*, 1. *Dalle origini al Congresso di Berlino*, Torino, Edizioni de "L'erma", 1934, pp. 21-36.

⁶ Fani-Maria Tsigakou, *Alla riscoperta della Grecia: artisti e viaggiatori dell'età romantica*, Milano, Edizioni di Comunità, 1985; Zeffiro Ciuffoletti, Luigi Mascilli Migliorini, "Il mito della Grecia in Italia tra politica e letteratura", in AA. VV., *Indipendenza e unità nazionale...*, pp. 43-60.

politico imbastiti nell'Antichità con la realtà ellenica da parte di Roma⁷, laddove la Grecia classica aveva esercitato una profonda influenza, in termini politici, culturali, sociali e religiosi, sulla nascente civiltà romana, ricevendo successivamente da questa, quasi come ideale restituzione, un enorme contributo nella diffusione del patrimonio dei saperi della grecità in tutto il mondo allora conosciuto attraverso l'egemonico ordine di potere instauratosi con il sistema imperiale⁸. Decisivi, in tal senso, anche sotto la dominazione ottomana, erano stati da un lato la città di Venezia, in virtù dello strategico ruolo di collante naturale esercitato verso l'altra sponda del Mediterraneo tramite la lunga presenza sia militare che politica nelle Isole Ionie, al punto da divenire uno dei massimi centri dell'Ellenismo sottomesso⁹, e, dall'altro lato, l'esistenza di grandi comunità elleniche in città quali Venezia, per l'appunto, Trieste, Padova, Genova, Livorno, Pisa, Ancona, Napoli, Messina¹⁰.

Un ulteriore *trait d'union* fu rappresentato, poi, in pieno XVIII secolo, dall'esplosione del Neoclassicismo, che vide l'Italia tra le zone di massima centralità e diffusione a causa della sua storia impregnata a un tempo di romanità e di grecità: qui furono effettuate le maggiori scoperte archeologiche del secolo, da Ercolano a Pompei, da Paestum a Tivoli, mentre a Roma, divenuta il centro di irradiazione di questo nuovo orientamento culturale, operarono i massimi protagonisti artistici e letterari del movimento come, solo per fare qualche nome, il già citato Winckelmann, lo scultore Antonio Canova e il poeta Vincenzo Monti.

Indubbiamente, però, al pari del resto d'Europa, anche per l'Italia un momento altamente topico, se non di vera e propria svolta, nella multiforme riscoperta neoellenica fu offerto nel 1768

⁷ Antonio Carile, "Italia e Grecia dalla conquista turca alla nascita del nuovo stato greco", in "Il Veltro", a. XXVII, nn. 1-2, gennaio-aprile 1983, numero monografico *Le relazioni tra l'Italia e la Grecia*, I, pp. 17-20.

⁸ Giuliano Balbino, "Prefazione", in Istituto nazionale per le relazioni culturali con l'estero, *Italia e Grecia. Saggi su le due civiltà e i loro rapporti attraverso i secoli*, Felice Le Monnier, Firenze 1939, pp. IX-X.

⁹ Antonio Carile, *op. cit.*, pp. 18-21; Gino Benzoni (a cura di), *L'eredità greca e l'ellenismo veneziano*, Firenze, L. S. Olschki, 2002; Maria Francesca Tiepolo, Eurigio Tonetti (a cura di), *I greci a Venezia. Atti del convegno internazionale di studio, Venezia 5-7 novembre 1998*, Venezia, Istituto Veneto di Scienze, Lettere ed Arti, 2002. Una cifra dell'estremo valore assunto dalla città lagunare per il mondo greco è offerto dal fatto che essa sia stata una delle pochissime, se non l'unica, realtà urbana dell'area occidentale a venire nominata insieme a Costantinopoli nei canti popolari neogreci. Cfr. Silvio Giuseppe Mercati, *Venezia nella poesia neo-greca*, in Istituto nazionale per le relazioni culturali con l'estero, *op. cit.*, pp. 307-340.

¹⁰ Cfr. Manoussos I. Manoussakas, "Le grandi comunità elleniche in Italia", in *Risorgimento greco e filellenismo italiano...*, pp. 43-48; Olga Katsiardi-Heiring, "Rapporti commerciali tra due paesi mediterranei", in *Risorgimento greco e filellenismo italiano...*, pp. 49-53. Una panoramica sulla situazione di alcune comunità greche italiane è visibile nei saggi raccolti in "Il Veltro", a. XXVII, nn. 3-4, maggio-agosto 1983, numero monografico *Le relazioni tra l'Italia e la Grecia*, II, pp. 421-468, 477-502.

dalla cruenta penetrazione russa nel Mediterraneo all'indomani delle frizioni avute con il governo di Istanbul e, nel dettaglio, dalle già ricordate rivolte greche del 1770, una data che viene considerata, a dispetto delle cocenti delusioni, l'inizio del moto nazionale ellenico, secondo la magistrale ricostruzione operata da Franco Venturi nel III volume del suo ponderoso studio *Settecento riformatore*¹¹. In tali frangenti, vivaci discussioni animarono il dibattito su scala nazionale, gettando luce su contesti politici e geografici all'epoca scarsamente conosciuti, in un susseguirsi e in un alternarsi di speranze, timori e valutazioni contrastanti man mano che l'impresa dei fratelli Aleksej e Fëdor Orlov andava allargandosi; in parallelo, tutto ciò incoraggiò una richiesta di informazioni più particolareggiate sulla Grecia da parte di un pubblico in continuo ampliamento, al punto da alimentare un vasto filone di viaggiatori stranieri - italiani inclusi - in direzione delle terre elleniche e stimolare la produzione di una ricca mole di studi e opere di taglio diverso (descrittivo, storico, politico, letterario, archeologico o naturalistico) incentrate o facenti riferimento al mondo greco, nei cui confronti venne espresso un giudizio variegato, derivanti in buona misura esattamente dall'esperienza odeporica vissuta dagli autori.

Sul fronte cospirativo Venezia, Trieste, Livorno, Napoli intrecciarono in vario modo la propria sorte a quella del moto di sollevamento greco, rappresentando luoghi di propaganda, incontro e organizzazione più o meno clandestini dello stesso: all'interesse e alla comprensibile preoccupazione nutrita dalla Repubblica di San Marco, direttamente minacciata nelle Isole Ionie e nei suoi traffici commerciali, corrispose un approccio totalmente antitetico da parte del Granducato di Toscana e del Regno di Napoli, per i quali si aprivano orizzonti nuovi verso il Levante.

Per ciò che concerne la città lagunare, grave fu lo sforzo che essa dovette compiere per non venire coinvolta nelle dispute dei tre grandi imperi, russo, ottomano e austriaco, e per contenere tanto le rivolte popolari quanto le ribellioni nobiliari scoppiate sulla scia del conflitto principale nelle isole di Cefalonia, Corfù, Zante. Essa spiccò, inoltre, come sede di una copiosa pubblicistica attinente agli eventi analizzati, in cui emergevano dei giudizi non entusiasmanti sui greci.

Innanzitutto la *Storia della guerra presente tra la Russia e la Porta Ottomana*, il principale testo scritto in quegli anni sull'argomento, pubblicato con enorme successo a partire dal 1770 presso la tipografia di Antonio Graziosi, basato in buona misura sulle notizie provenienti da un testimone diretto, tale Pietro Romanelli, un medico greco al servizio del pascià della Morea. Evitando accuratamente ogni menzione a fatti direttamente collegati alla Serenissima, come le insubordinazioni e le ribellioni verificatesi nelle Isole Ionie che venivano passate sotto silenzio o

¹¹ Franco Venturi, *op. cit.*, vol. III, p. 48.

accuratamente offuscate, ci si addentrava, al contrario, nel seguire i concitati avvenimenti, esprimendo ammirazione per le azioni dei russi e perplessità sui mainotti, i discendenti e successori dei lacedemoni, accusati di eccessiva indisciplinatezza militare e di “inumana barbarie”, fino a descrivere un’agghiacciante immagine finale della Morea “ridotta in estrema desolazione”, con raccolti distrutti, campagne calpestate, migliaia di abitanti uccisi o costretti alla fuga e chiosare emblematicamente: “non è possibile il presentare una giusta immagine dell’orrore che in quell’occasione compariva sotto Navarrino”¹².

A questa si aggiunsero il “Mercurio storico e politico”, edito nel 1770 dal libraio Luigi Panini, versione ritoccata e più contenuta della maggiore rivista politica di allora, l’olandese “*Mercure historique et politique*”; alcune *Descrizioni* di carattere geografico, politico e storico delle zone interessate dalla guerra, dell’Arcipelago, della Morea, corredate di pregevoli carte geografiche, per opera della stamperia Savioni e del già citato Graziosi; la *Storia dell’anno*, di durata trentennale e dall’impostazione ariosa, visto che raccoglieva informazioni globali dalle gazzette apparse in ogni angolo del continente, la quale per il 1770 narrava con tono diffidente degli insorti, definendoli “un ammasso di gente tumultuosa e rapace”; le *Osservazioni sopra le passate campagne militari della presente guerra tra’ russi e ottomani, sopra il militare dei turchi e la maniera di combatterli*, una traduzione parziale del 1772 di un’opera pubblicata l’anno prima a Breslavia dal generale Charles-Emmanuel de Varnéry incentrata sulle tattiche più efficaci per sconfiggere i musulmani, in cui si marcava in senso negativo la differenza esistente fra moderni e antichi elleni: “*Ce ne sont plus les mêmes Grecs, ils veulent être gouvernés à la turque. Une personne élevée parmi eux m’a assuré qu’ils sont incapables de le faire d’eux mêmes, ils sont lâches, fourbes et ont une ambition démesurée de primer sur leurs égaux*”¹³.

Un atteggiamento non dissimile da quello manifestato nell’*Elogio di Caterina II imperatrice delle Russie*, traduzione del 1773 di un’opera dello scrittore francese Ange Goudar, in cui la responsabilità dell’insuccesso era totalmente attribuita ai greci con la seguente motivazione: “La mala fede, la viltà, il genio avido di rapine e l’indisciplina de’ mainotti medesimi fecero che quell’impresa non procedesse con quella felicità ch’erasi aspettata”¹⁴.

Una visione scettica e incline a particolare durezza, in ultimo, animava la disamina del veneziano Giacomo Casanova nella continuazione della sua *Istoria delle turbolenze di Polonia*, apparsa in tre piccoli tomi a Gorizia nel 1774. Questi, ricordando con rancore come la Repubblica di San Marco avesse perduto Candia e la Morea per i tradimenti degli autoctoni “di rea e pessima natura”,

¹² *Ibidem*, pp. 20-21; 42-45.

¹³ *Ibidem*, pp. 42- 61 (la citazione si trova a p. 61).

¹⁴ *Ibidem*, pp. 63-68 (la citazione si trova a p. 66).

insisteva nel ritenere i discendenti degli antichi spartani abili a "far schiavi tanto turchi che cristiani", "perfidi" e propensi "alla libertà, al saccheggio, al latrocinio, come una dovuta remunerazione alla loro cattività", alla stessa stregua degli ebrei. I "mille esempi che l'istoria affaccia a chi la legge" avrebbero dovuto persuadere i russi a non fidarsi di "quella misera gente" sottoposta alla "scimitarra alzata" del turco da oltre tre secoli, una condizione da cui deduceva candidamente: "Dio li vuole in quello stato di dipendenza"¹⁵.

Il Granducato di Toscana, al contrario, si impose già dall'inverno 1769-1770 a perfetta base dell'iniziativa degli Orlov, potendo contare sugli ottimi rapporti che univano i russi ai commercianti toscani, soprattutto livornesi: a Pisa si trasferirono gli emissari dell'imperatrice tedesca dopo il loro passaggio veneziano; nella città pisana e a Livorno si attuò una notevole convergenza di esponenti del mondo insurrezionale ellenico e qui costoro raggiunsero un accordo con i moscoviti per l'elaborazione dei dettagli più concreti; nelle terre guidate da Pietro Leopoldo, allo scopo di intensificare il reclutamento di truppe, fu stampato un manifesto a nome di Caterina II finalizzato a "tutti i popoli ortodossi i quali gemono sotto il peso del giogo ottomano", degni "di un pronto soccorso per essere sì ragguardevoli" per antichità e religione; dal porto livornese Aleksej Orlov avrebbe raggiunto, per prenderne il comando, la flotta russa che nel febbraio 1770 lasciava Port Mahon per dirigersi verso Levante¹⁶.

Conseguentemente, ciò si rifletté sulla stampa regionale, dagli orientamenti apertamente filellenici. Le fiorentine "Notizie dal mondo", ad esempio, seguirono l'insurrezione non solo con interesse ma con una prudente benevolenza, accordando credito all'opera di supporto svolta con "fervore" e "militar disciplina" dai soldati greci, che, anzi, andavano paradossalmente frenati nel loro veemente impeto volto a rovesciare "tutte le mezze lune per inalberarvi le croci e le aquile russe" e a "procacciarsi la gloria antica". Sulle sue colonne, il 6 e 9 luglio 1771, venne pubblicato in due puntate quello che è stato valutato da Franco Venturi come "il più importante appello filellenico apparso allora non solo in Italia ma nella intera Europa, destinato a risuonare anche ben lontano dalle terre toscane": si trattava dei *Voti dei greci all'Europa cristiana*, frutto della penna dell'epirota Antonio Gicca, ufficiale a servizio dell'esercito russo, seppure venisse attribuito erroneamente a Giovanni Del Turco. Nella sua esortazione all'intero continente, e in special modo a Caterina II, perchè non abbandonasse la terra di Socrate a un terribile destino ma proseguisse la lotta contro i maomettani, Gicca richiamava alla

¹⁵ Giacomo Casanova, *Istoria delle turbolenze della Polonia*, a cura di Giacinto Spagnoletti, Napoli, Guida, 1974. Cfr. al riguardo Franco Venturi, *op. cit.*, vol. III, pp. 68-69.

¹⁶ *Ibidem*, pp. 33-36.

memoria tutto il patrimonio di doti presente nel DNA del popolo ellenico - i liberi governi, “la retta amministrazione della giustizia”, “la perizia delle armi”, “la cognizione delle scienze e delle arti più belle e più utili”, “l’esercizio di ogni pubblica e privata virtù” - che aveva permesso loro, pur trovandosi a vivere da lungo tempo in qualità di “vili istrumenti de’ loro signori” senza alcuna legge che li proteggesse, di non “avvezzarsi alla servitù” e di continuare a lottare per rompere i ceppi. Di fronte al drammatico bivio che si apriva davanti ai cristiani sottomessi, l’apostasia o la schiavitù, quando non la prospettiva si estrema ma non del tutto irrealizzabile dello sterminio totale voluto dai turchi, l’obiettivo dell’“infelice nazione de’ greci” - concludeva Gicca - era non di gloriarsi stucchevolmente del passato ormai andato ma di chiedere ai confratelli un’“unica grazia”: “il semplice loro consenso per non perire”. Degno di nota, in ultimo, che il foglio fiorentino, anche a guerra quasi ultimata, continuasse a informare i lettori sulle vicende degli attori coinvolti¹⁷.

Spostando l’attenzione al Regno di Napoli, esso brillò certamente quale uno dei versanti più attivi nel reagire agli avvenimenti del 1768-1774. La posizione di cautela e neutralità ostentata dal governo borbonico risentiva degli importanti rapporti commerciali con l’Impero ottomano che impedivano a Ferdinando IV di fornire un valido appoggio alla flotta russa, limitandosi tutt’al più - secondo la corrispondenza diplomatica del primo segretario di Stato del governo napoletano, Bernardo Tanucci, con Domenico Caracciolo, allora ambasciatore del Regno di Napoli e di Sicilia a Londra - a permettere “che nei porti delle Sicilie, in casi di necessità solamente”, venissero ricevute “una, due o tre navi per porto, pel tempo necessario a ristorarsi del disastro, pagando quel che lor bisognasse non potendo né dovendo il re disgustar la Porta Sua amica e non esistendo tralle [sic!] Sicilie e le Russie alcun trattato, come esiste tralle Sicilie e la Porta”¹⁸. Una diffidenza e una ritrosia condivise da Ferdinando Galiani, dominato dal pensiero dei tanti rischi inutili che i partenopei avrebbero corso se si fossero intromessi nella questione, così da suggerire di lasciare giusto qualche nave nell’arcipelago e ridurre al minimo le spese¹⁹.

A questo fece da contraltare la cultura napoletana degli anni Settanta caratterizzata da un misto di entusiasmi neoellenici, solidarietà con gli esuli, visioni neoclassiche, scoperta del mondo russo, ritrovabile unicamente in Toscana. Il “Foglio straordinario”, edito *in situ* dal 1769, pur non possedendo l’identica ricchezza di fatti e commenti delle “Notizie del mondo”, fin dal primo numero del 6 gennaio dedicò spazio ai preparativi bellici, esponendo le

¹⁷ *Ibidem*, pp. 40-42; 83; 100-104.

¹⁸ Salvatore Bottari, “Per il dominio sul Mar Nero: la guerra russo-turca del 1768-1774 nella corrispondenza diplomatica napoletana”, in Mirella Mafri, Luigi Mascilli Migliorini (a cura di), *Mediterraneo e/è Mar Nero. Due mari tra età moderna e contemporanea*, Napoli-Roma, Edizione Scientifiche Italiane, 2011 (in corso di stampa).

¹⁹ Franco Venturi, *op. cit.*, vol. III, pp. 129-132.

prime misure turche contro i greci dell'arcipelago e le precauzioni preventive di Venezia contro alcuni ribelli; altrettanto degni di nota i due fogli volanti intitolati "Copia di lettera" del 1770, che commentavano i primi successi dei greci nel Peloponneso, facendo risaltare il loro giuramento di fedeltà "con solenne promessa di mai abbandonarsi" e la loro eccellente unità di corpo nell'attaccare e nel difendersi dai nemici²⁰.

Sempre alle pendici del Vesuvio furono pubblicate due coeve raccolte poetiche celebrative di Caterina II e Aleksej Orlov²¹, che annoveravano fra i vari autori il conte Giorgio Corafà, comandante e storiografo del Reggimento Real Macedone del Regno di Napoli, artefice e ispiratore di molti brani poetici, nei quali il comune denominatore era rappresentato dalla Russia garante della "greca libertà", da Orlov "invitto" con le chiome cinte da Pallade e dalla zarina "redentrica della Grecia"²².

Sulla stessa scia si collocò il ventenne Francesco Maria Pagano, grande amante dell'Ellade fin dall'adolescenza, che dedicò all'amico Antonio Gicca il suo panegirico esaltante il conte Orlov, eletto a patrono dei greci per avere distrutto il 7 luglio 1770 la flotta ottomana nello stretto di Çeşme, in cui esprimeva la speranza che, sradicati i barbari, per la Grecia con sommo trionfo si aprisse una nuova era, celebrata da un nuovo Omero²³.

Circoscritta ma significativa estensione del dibattito all'area lombarda, infine, fu quella espressa da Pietro Verri nell'ambiente milanese. Il filosofo e illuminista ambrosiano, come appare dal carteggio con il fratello Alessandro, comprese con profondo acume la portata politica di quanto stava avvenendo e il suo inserirsi in una più ampia sfera europea di scontro tra visioni opposte (libertà tradizionali *vs* libertà di tipo nuovo, assolutismo *vs* afflitti di trasformazioni sociali). Se l'impresa moscovita suscitava in lui un sincero apprezzamento, al punto da fargli commentare che si trattava di qualcosa di "grande e di eroico", tuttavia egli manteneva la giusta lucidità nell'osservare i possibili rischi di prepotenza, dispotismo e barbarie insiti nell'impresa, dal momento che i russi si erano da troppo poco troppo tempo "inciviliti" e si trovavano esposti al "capriccio del sovrano". Criticando l'orientamento dello

²⁰ *Ibidem*, pp. 111-112.

²¹ Si trattava dei *Componimenti poetici di vari autori in lode di Caterina II, augustissima imperatrice di tutte le Russie*, editi nel 1771, e dei *Componimenti poetici di vari autori in lode di S. E. il signor conte Alessio Orlov, plenipotenziario e comandante supremo delle arme russe in Levante*, successivi di due anni rispetto alla prima opera.

²² Franco Venturi, *op. cit.*, vol. III, pp. 113-122; Arnaldo Di Benedetto, "Le rovine d'Atene": *Letteratura filellenica in Italia tra Sette e Ottocento*, in "Italice", vol. 76, n. 3, Autumn 1999, pp. 335-354.

²³ Il titolo completo era: *Francisci Marii Pagani Oratio ad comitem Alexium Orlov, virum immortalam, cictrici moschorum classi in expeditione in Mediterraneum mare summo cum imperio praefectum*, s.l., s.d. Cfr. in merito Franco Venturi, *op. cit.*, vol. III, pp. 124-127; Arnaldo Di Benedetto, *op. cit.*, p. 336.

Stato della Chiesa, incapace di superare le contrapposizioni con i cristiani ortodossi e accusato ironicamente di stare quasi dalla parte dei musulmani a causa del suo atteggiamento atto a conservare gli equilibri esistenti, rinnovava, ancora nell'ottobre del 1770, i suoi auspici affinché la risurrezione greca, a suo parere accostabile alla rivoluzione corsa, si indirizzasse verso un esito positivo: "Vorrei pure che la patria di Pericle, di Milziade, di Platone, e di tanti uomini venerabili cambiasse destino e che sulle loro ossa onorate non passeggiasse l'oppressore d'una avvilita e ingegnosa nazione"²⁴.

Parimenti, appare ineludibile il contributo chiarificatore fornito dai resoconti dei numerosi viaggiatori che si recarono in Grecia. In una cornice globale in cui l'esperienza del viaggio aveva assunto sin dagli albori del XVIII secolo una funzione di spicco nell'ambito del processo di formazione individuale e di sviluppo culturale complessivo delle élites europee, l'itinerario ellenico tardo settecentesco si situò in una condizione del tutto peculiare, risentendo della dilagante presenza dell'antico innanzitutto quale mito culturale e, secondariamente, quale *cliché* informatore, non di rado deformante, del giudizio sull'attualità, tanto da risultare irrimediabilmente sospeso in una duplice dimensione, "divisa tra itinerario nello spazio e viaggio nel tempo, fra ricognizione di luoghi reali ed evocazione di ombre dal passato", dove l'osservazione obiettiva di oggetti e circostanze veniva condizionata dal filtro delle rovine e dalla tensione emotiva del "contatto diretto"²⁵. Ciò si rifletté pure nella tipologia e nello spirito di chi si mise in cammino verso questi luoghi, non più esclusivamente mercanti, geografi, diplomatici o avventurieri, spinti da esigenze pratiche, come era accaduto fino a cent'anni prima, ma, in misura crescente, un consistente nucleo di intellettuali imbevuti della visione winckelmanniana, che lo concepirono quale "pellegrinaggio culturale", preparandolo con puntigliose letture²⁶. Ambivalente l'esito che ne scaturì: una porzione di essi manifestò una totale incomprensione per lo stato di difficoltà dei greci, non fornendo loro delle attenuanti o delle giustificazioni, bensì denigrandoli e ritenendoli corresponsabili dell'abbruttimento vissuto; un altro gruppo, di orientamento politico vario e numericamente di gran lunga più cospicuo, rivolse loro il suo benevolo sguardo, commiserandoli per le sofferenze patite e additandone al mondo intero i fremiti di risveglio, le doti e i mali, finendo per brillare come preziosa manifestazione di filellenismo *in nuce*²⁷.

²⁴ Franco Venturi, *op. cit.*, vol. III, pp. 133-136; Arnaldo Di Benedetto, *op. cit.*, p. 336.

²⁵ Fabrizio Cicoira, *Il silenzio dell'antico. La Grecia fra passato e presente nelle relazioni di viaggiatori italiani del tardo Settecento*, in "Studi Settecenteschi", n. 3-4, 1982-1983, pp. 270-271.

²⁶ *Ibidem*.

²⁷ Elena Persico, *Letteratura filellenica italiana 1787-1870*, Roma, Tip. Bondi e C., 1920, pp. 7-9.

In tal senso, alcune interessanti testimonianze vennero offerte proprio da degli scritti odeporici pubblicati in Italia e/o in lingua italiana. Nel 1761, nel corso di un viaggio che lo avrebbe condotto a Costantinopoli e ad attraversare i Balcani, l'abate, matematico e astronomo Ruggiero Giuseppe Boscovich visitò i resti di Troia, stendendone più in là negli anni una *Relazione*, che si esauriva in un "minuzioso inventario di architetture cadenti e di iscrizioni consunte". Tre anni dopo, durante una navigazione alla volta della capitale dell'Impero ottomano, l'attraversamento delle tante isole suggerì al conte Giuseppe Gorani la metafora di un "*vieillard caduc, accablé d'infirmités et impotent, qui a été un héros dans sa jeunesse*" per rendere il violento contrasto con la magnificenza antica. Nel 1773 l'irrequieto Giovanni Del Turco fu a lungo in Levante al seguito della flotta russa, approdando nell'Egeo, prima a Smirne, da cui ricavò impressioni sulla struttura urbana e sull'organizzazione sociale ottomana, e poi a Chio, dove il traduttore di Omero sembrò trovare una perfetta corrispondenza tra le immagini evocate dalle sue letture e la realtà che aveva di fronte agli occhi, al punto da affermare: "Non vi è villano greco tanto idiota che non vi additi il luogo dove la lavandaia madre di Omero su questo ramo del Melete lo partori: tanta è tuttavia dopo tremil'anni la celebrità di quel grand'uomo"²⁸.

Un altro viaggiatore, coinvolto anch'egli nella spedizione cateriniana, l'ufficiale di origine olandese Enrico Leopoldo Pash di Krienen si trovò a visitare metodicamente le Cicladi, tracciandone al suo ritorno una dettagliata *Descrizione*, che venne pubblicata a Livorno nel 1773²⁹. Uomo istruito e animato da spiccati interessi archeologici, l'autore mescolava notizie storiche, posizione e caratteristiche geografiche, aspetti demografici ed economici, attrattive artistiche delle diciotto isole, ricavandone una sensazione di desolante stridore rispetto al passato: grossolanità, grettezza e ignoranza regnavano ovunque in luoghi come Amorgos, Delo, Milo, Paro, un tempo adornati di ricche vestigia e adesso privati di ogni decoro e ridotti in penosa decadenza³⁰.

Notizie su Atene e sulla realtà ellenica si possono rintracciare nella *Relazione di un viaggio a Costantinopoli*, compiuto nel biennio 1788-1789 dal letterato Giambattista Casti, osservatore piuttosto superficiale, ma imparziale, molto attratto dall'esotico e pittoresco mondo ottomano. L'ignoranza dei turchi, "senza gusto e senza idee di utili e scienze ed arti", forniva l'occasione a costui per addentrarsi sulla situazione della "nazione greca" e specificamente

²⁸ Fabrizio Ciccoira, *op. cit.*, pp. 272-276.

²⁹ Questo il titolo completo: *Breve descrizione dell'Arcipelago e particolarmente dello diciotto isole sottomesse l'anno 1771 al dominio russo, del Conte Pash di Krienen con un ragguaglio esatto di tutte le antichità da esso scoperte ed acquistate e specialmente del sepolcro d'Omero e d'altri celebri personaggi*, Livorno, Tommaso Masi, 1773.

³⁰ Franco Venturi, *Settecento riformatore*, cit., vol. III: *La prima crisi...*, cit., pp. 105-106; Ciccoira Fabrizio, *op. cit.*, pp. 276-278.

della sua futura capitale, con un misto di rimpianto e di riprovazione morale. Nel centro dell'antica democrazia, lo spettacolo dei resti di tanti insigni monumenti, su cui spiccava il maestoso Partenone, e il pensiero di tante irripetibili venerabili opere d'arte lo spingevano a rendere omaggio a una terra comunque impareggiabile: "Io non sono entusiasta a segno di baciare la terra e pormi sotto l'origliere i pezzi di marmo, come fanno i fanatici dell'antichità... ma credo che qualunque animo per poco educato e ben formato che sia, non possa fare a meno d'interessarsi e di essere sensibile a questi oggetti e a queste riflessioni"³¹.

Il culmine più maturo di tale concezione si ritrova, probabilmente, nel *Viaggio in Grecia* dell'abate modicano Saverio Scrofani, opera in grado di varcare i confini delle Alpi per la risonanza raggiunta³². Questi, in qualità di sovrintendente all'agricoltura e al commercio con il Levante della Repubblica veneta, si mosse da Venezia nel luglio 1794 con l'incarico di osservare e relazionare al suo ritorno lo stato agricolo, economico e commerciale dei possedimenti veneti, protraendo la sua permanenza fino all'ottobre dell'anno successivo. Da questa gradita peregrinazione sarebbe scaturito un doppio frutto, la *Relazione sullo stato attuale dell'agricoltura e del commercio delle isole veneziane, della Morea e della bassa Romelia* del 1798 e, appunto, il *Viaggio in Grecia* datato 1799. In esso, strutturato secondo la settecentesca forma delle lettere-diario, prendeva corpo non un erudito commento intriso di dati minuziosi e maniacali ma un sentimentale accostamento a un mondo vagheggiato, studiato ed evocato artificiosamente persino in mezzo al silenzio, a oggetti comuni o a vuoti simulacri del tempo presente: "Questa è dunque la Grecia? Questa: e per essa ho navigato mille miglia di mare e lasciato l'Italia, i parenti, gli amici? Per essa. E non poteva io fare questo viaggio nel mio gabinetto, come l'autore del *Giovane Anacarsi*? Non poteva io leggendo gli antichi e moderni viaggiatori, sapere senza molto stento ciò ch'esiste oggi in Grecia, ciò che vi esisteva una volta? Sì... tutto è vero; ma io non avrei fatto allora altro viaggio che per istruirmi e voleva farne uno per sentire... Che importa se Sparta, Atene, Corinto non esistono più? Il terreno dov'esse erano conserva ancora sepolte le grandi idee che destavano un giorno: chi sa scavarlo, questo terreno vi troverà il segreto di vedere nel 1794 la Grecia di Pericle e di Licurgo. Ma il

³¹ *Ibidem*, pp. 278-280.

³² Saverio Scrofani, *Viaggio in Grecia*, introduzione, testo e nota filologica a cura di Claudio Mutini, Roma, Edizioni dell'Ateneo, 1965. Cfr. A. Salvatore, *Un viaggiatore siracusano alla fine del Settecento e la sua descrizione della Grecia*, in "Archivio Storico per la Sicilia Orientale", a. XIV, fasc. I, II, III, 1917, pp. 206-219; Roberto Zapperi, *Saverio Scrofani e i suoi biograf*, in "Rassegna Storica del Risorgimento", a. XLIX, fasc. III, luglio-settembre 1962, fasc. 3, pp. 447-484; Laura Pulejo, *Il viaggio in Grecia di un economista siciliano (1795)*, in Giovanna Motta, *Mercanti e viaggiatori per le vie del mondo*, Milano, Franco Angeli, 2000, pp. 289-306.

silenzio? Aiuterà il mio cuore a dilatarsi e godere in libertà il teatro di questi venerandi deserti"³³.

Fra i viaggiatori una delle categorie più particolari e influenti fu rappresentata dagli artisti che, con la loro presenza - episodica o continua - sul territorio greco, diedero una spinta consistente alla circolazione della questione ellenica, offrendone una rappresentazione visiva per mezzo delle arti figurative. In merito ai pochi artisti italiani che in questa fase storica contribuirono alla progressiva riscoperta culturale dell'Ellade, alcuni si distinsero per attività moralmente discutibili, altri per qualità e risultati non indifferenti.

Così, nel 1798, l'incisore senese Giovanni Battista Cipriani, per sottolineare quel legame con la Grecia, pur non avendola percorsa sotto i suoi passi, decise di produrre una serie di *Vedute di Atene e di altri siti*, rielaborazione semplificata e miniaturistica della celebre opera di Julien David Le Roy *Les Ruines des plus beaux monuments de la Grèce* di qualche decennio addietro.

Realmente attivo sul suolo ellenico fu invece Giovan Battista Lusieri, pittore capo di un gruppo di artisti e tecnici che Lord Elgin aveva composto in Italia con l'aiuto del dotto antiquario e collezionista Hamilton; giunto ad Atene dal 1800 per dipingere le antiche rovine architettoniche, il valido paesaggista si lasciò purtroppo progressivamente assorbire dagli "impegni di spoliazione" dell'Acropoli, lasciando come unico prodotto realizzativo il solo acquarello con *Monumento di Filopappo* (una cassa intera contenente altri suoi disegni di soggetto greco si sarebbe inabissata in mare nel 1828), proseguendo nella sua veste di scavatore-antiquario per circa un ventennio, fino a ricevere la conservazione della sua lastra tombale ad Atene nella via dei Filelleni, una paradossale ricompensa per chi si era macchiato di simili deprezzazioni del patrimonio culturale.

Nella primavera del 1805 giunse ad Atene il paesaggista romano Simone Pomardi, trovandosi al servizio dell'archeologo e collezionista Edward Dodwell, in un viaggio durato dal 2 ottobre 1804 al 18 settembre 1806 che li avrebbe portati dalle Isole Ionie a Patrasso, Lepanto, Delfi, in Beozia, Attica, Tessaglia, nel Peloponneso, fino a ritornare a Corfù e da lì nuovamente in Italia. Ne derivò un'imponente raccolta di materiali che, dopo una lunga elaborazione, Dodwell pubblicò a Londra nel 1819 sotto il titolo di *Classical and Topographical Tour*, testo dominato da vibranti proteste per il vandalismo di Elgin e da ripetute espressioni di solidarietà e simpatia con la popolazione oppressa, il cui apparato illustrativo poggiava quasi interamente sulle 41 incisioni di Pomardi.

In ultimo, va ricordata *La Grecia in catene*, tavola dipinta nel 1816 da Antonio Rancati, in cui veniva proposta la personificazione della Grecia come una matrona incatenata, afflitta

³³ *Ibidem*, Lettera XVII.

e pensosa, che si appoggiava al sarcofago di Leonida, l'eroe delle Termopili, in attesa dell'aiuto delle Potenze straniere per invertire il suo stato di avvilito. Un dipinto che veniva accompagnato da un commento scritto decisamente esplicito, vivo auspicio e testimonianza di un marcato filellenismo: "Colà finalmente vivono ancora i discendenti degli antichi Spartani, conosciuti sotto il nome di Maniotti, i quali non mai piegarono il collo sotto il giogo ottomano. E già sembra che su quelle infelici spiagge spuntino alcuni raggi di una bella aurora, da che i moderni Greci, specialmente della Ionia, cominciato hanno a coltivare la mente e il cuore colle letterature e colle scienze, unico retaggio dei loro avi. Possano essi riacquistare un giorno la primiera gloria e far rivivere que' grandi uomini, la cui sola memoria tanto le loro e le nostra anime infiamma!"³⁴.

Enorme capacità trainante ebbe, infine, l'ambiente letterario nel veicolare presso un'ampia opinione pubblica questa riscoperta della Grecia contemporanea e la passione verso le sue sfortunate genti. Alcuni fra i più grandi autori della letteratura mondiale si fecero cantori di questi sentimenti in opere consacrate dalla fama del pubblico - da Friedrich Schiller de *Gli dèi della Grecia* (1788) a Johann Christian Friedrich Hölderlin di *Hyperion (Iperione o l'eremita in Grecia, 1797-1799)*, da Chateaubriand dell'*Itinéraire de Paris à Jérusalem* a Lord Byron di *The Giaour* (1813), *The Bride of Abydos* (1813), *The Siege of Corinth* (1815) e *Don Juan* (1824), da Percy Bysshe Shelley di *Hellas* (1822) fino a Victor Hugo de *Les Orientales* (1829), giusto per citare i massimi protagonisti - toccando di persona il "sacro suolo" e ricavandone impressioni, ricordi, sensazioni che travasarono nei loro scritti o traendo ispirazione da situazioni, spunti, episodi raccontati da viaggiatori o da giornalisti per poi rielaborarli secondo la propria sensibilità artistica.

Il primo accenno filellenico nella letteratura italiana, al contrario, risale, secondo le ricerche compiute da Elena Persico³⁵, al 1787, anno di inizio della seconda guerra russo-turca ultimatasi nel 1792, nell'ambito della quale i mercanti greci di Trieste finanziarono una flottiglia capitanata da Lâmbros Katsônis che si schierò a fianco degli zar come dimostrazione della fiducia nutrita da parte ellenica verso i loro "protettori" slavi³⁶. In quell'occasione il poeta toscano Giovanni Fantoni compose l'ode *Su lo stato d'Europa nel 1787*, che mostrava una Grecia intenta a osservare con attenzione l'epica discesa di Caterina "dal freddo Ponto" con l'asta impugnata e il suo dirompente prorompere ai danni del "molle oriental tiranno", tutto tremante nelle sue bende in fronte.

³⁴ *Risorgimento greco e filellenismo italiano...*, cit. , pp. 151-152, 212-219, 274 (la citazione è relativa a p. 274) e Caterina Spetsieri Beschi, *Pittori italiani e la Grecia*, in *Le relazioni tra l'Italia e la Grecia*, II, cit. , pp. 351-355.

³⁵ Persico Elena, *op. cit.*

³⁶ Richard Clogg, *Storia della Grecia moderna: dalla caduta dell'impero bizantino a oggi*, Milano, Bompiani, 1996, p. 38.

Ancora il verseggiatore di Fivizzano, nel 1791, in pieno contesto bellico, si distinse per un'altra ode - poi rimaneggiata cinque anni dopo e adattata all'attualità italiana - dedicata ad Antonio Gennaro duca di Belforte in cui profetizzava un risveglio dell'Ellade dormiente, pronta a lottare nuovamente per riprendersi la propria libertà smarrita: "Dallo scosceso Taigeta scendono / Gli eguali agli avi Spartani intrepidi; / Grecia si desta, impugna / l'asta e corre alla pugna... / Salve, dell'arti madre palladia! / già i dissepoliti licei t'additano / gli archi e le tombe gravi / della gloria degli avi... / Grandeggia Sparta, Tebe rinnovasi, / Alfea risorge, Corinto il bimare, / Larissa, Argo, Micene / E la cecropia Atene... / Tornan gl'illustri giorni di Pericle, / ma ricchi d'opre guerriere e libere, / e ai fasti loro presiede / incolpabil la fede"³⁷.

A Torino, nel 1793, fu pubblicato dal gesuita Andrea Rubbi il trattato *I greci antichi e moderni*, veemente risposta al *Saggio sugli Ebrei e sui Greci* dato alle stampe l'anno prima a Venezia dall'abate Giuseppe Compagnoni, che vi aveva esplicitato una violenta requisitoria sull'imbelle acquiescenza ai dominatori mostrata dai moderni elleni, considerati spossati nel loro ingegno, passivi nelle loro abitudini e grossolanamente ignoranti, e vi aveva concluso un attacco frontale alla presunta vacuità della pratica periegetica condotta in un tale contesto³⁸. Riprendendo l'apostrofe del suo avversario, Rubbi ribadiva un'apologetica esaltazione del viaggio, nell'ottica di chi, come lui, si sentiva pervaso da un fervore classicista e beneficiava ugualmente dell'incontro magico con la greicità: "Viaggiatori filosofi, a che vi affrettate pur tuttavia a visitar con fatica e dispendio tante isole dell'oriente, e tanti lidi, e percorrere i vestigi di cento regni e di cento repubbliche greche? Voi mi risponderete, noi siam pieni la mente del mondo greco. Arti greche, scienza e legislazione greca, e marmi e bronzi e colonne e fregi e templi e medaglie e iscrizioni greche; anzi i codici e le pergamene e le manifatture e i vestimenti e il lusso medesimo e i ruderi greci ne occupano lo spirito in guisa, che siamo beati allor quando possiamo nei nostri scritti aver detto ai posteri: noi vedemmo le greche reliquie, noi baciammo i vestigi dei greci monumenti"³⁹.

³⁷ Elena Persico, *op. cit.*, pp. 18-19; Arnaldo Di Benedetto, *op. cit.*, p. 337.

³⁸ Questo è uno dei passi della *lettera* di Compagnoni al marchese Francesco Albergati Capacelli, sottotitolo del *Saggio sugli Ebrei e sui Greci*, in cui meglio si delineano tali concetti (riportato in Fabrizio Cicoira, *op. cit.*, p. 281): "Viaggiatori filosofi, voi che godete del brillante prospetto, che v'offre l'antica storia, v'affrettate curiosi verso le terre, nelle quali un giorno Atene, Sparta, e Corinto figurarono con sì fausti auspizj. Fermatevi. Che pensate mai di trovare oggi colà? Un mucchio di deplorabili ruine, e un popolo oppresso dalla più lurida decrepitezza, un popolo degradato dalla classe de' popoli. Se mai approdate a quei lidi, voi accuserete senza fallo il pilota, quasi che egli v'abbia traditi. Potete voi persuadervi d'essere fra i nipoti di Demostene, di Alcibiade, e di Epaminonda?"

³⁹ *Ibidem*.

Nel 1797 uscì sul “Termometro politico della Lombardia”, giornale della Milano “giacobina”, una lettera degli “Scolari di Demetriade città della Macedonia” intitolata *La prigioniera Grecia ai degni autori del Termometro politico della libera Milano*, zampillante di burrascosi propositi rivoluzionari simboleggiati dalla frase “vogliamo vulcanizzare l’anima del nostro tiranno, spezzando le catene ferree de’ nostri piedi”. I redattori del periodico, non insensibili alle mire napoleoniche sull’altra sponda dell’Adriatico, rispondevano enfaticamente ai giovani alunni, invitandoli ad avere fiducia nell’intervento liberatorio dei francesi, al pari di quanto si era verificato nel nord della penisola italiana: “La Francia è libera; l’Italia la siegue a gran passi; la Grecia ritornerà alla sua primiera grandezza. A voi giovani alunni di Minerva sarà serbata la gloria della greca rivoluzione... Attendeteci nelle campagne di Elide: là i novelli Flaminj proclameranno la vostra sorte, e un nuovo destino renderà formidabile al dispotismo il nome di Sparta, e terribile alla superstizione il nome di Atene”⁴⁰.

Nel 1804 apparvero a Milano i primi due tomi del *Platone in Italia* di Vincenzo Cuoco, già celeberrimo per il suo *Saggio storico sulla rivoluzione di Napoli*, particolare forma di romanzo epistolare che narrava il viaggio immaginario intrapreso dal giovane Cleobolo, discepolo di Platone, in visita nella Magna Grecia in compagnia del suo maestro, pieni di stupore per il valore eccezionale raggiunto da questa antica civiltà italica, maestra agli stessi greci nei campi delle istituzioni civili, delle scienze e delle arti. Nel rovesciare l’assunto dominante dell’antiorità della civiltà greca su quella italiana e nel tessere allegoricamente le lodi della supremazia culturale italica del Settecento rispetto alla Francia, Cuoco si serviva di un mondo, quello della Magna Grecia, per così dire “di confine”, a un tempo patrimonio della civiltà di matrice italiana e di quella greca, e implicitamente ravvisava nella gente ellenica un popolo fratello⁴¹.

Due anni dopo a Livorno apparve in forma anonima, forse per ragioni di prudenza politica, *La Grecia legalitaria ovvero Discorso sulla libertà*, un opuscolo battagliero rivolto a qualunque greco “non pronunci il nome della Grecia senza sospirare” allo scopo di suscitare in lui un’adesione alle idealità della nuova fede civica.

I drammatici casi di Suli, rasa al suolo nel 1803 dal feroce Ali Tepeleni, pascià di Giannina, artefice di una politica espansionista in contrasto con il sultano, malgrado l’eroica e strenua difesa tentata dagli abitanti del villaggio, e di Parga, venduta dai britannici per una grossa somma nel 1819 sempre ad

⁴⁰ Arnaldo Di Benedetto, *op. cit.*, p. 338.

⁴¹ Vincenzo Cuoco, *Platone in Italia*, a cura di Antonino De Francesco e Annalisa Andreoni, Roma-Bari, Laterza, 2006. Cfr. Giovanni Pugliese Carratelli, “Gli studi di greci e il filellenismo in Italia”, in *Risorgimento greco e filellenismo italiano...*, p. 114; Giuseppe Galasso, “E Platone creò il Risorgimento”, in *Corriere della Sera*, 6 aprile 2007, p. 49.

Ali Tepeleni dopo essere passata attraverso l'occupazione francese prima e appunto il protettorato inglese poi, con la spaventosa conseguenza di costringere i residenti del piccolo centro greco a portarsi con sé in esilio financo le ossa dei propri antenati pur di non lasciarli in mano ai nuovi occupanti, impressero nell'animo ellenico una consapevolezza ancora più forte e non tardarono a sollecitare ulteriormente l'impegno e la fantasia degli scrittori italiani.

Se ne fece promotore, ad esempio, un letterato del calibro di Ugo Foscolo, anche per ovvi motivi autobiografici, visti i suoi natali risalenti all'isola di Zante, affermando le sue aspettative di libertà e il suo entusiasmo per la causa ellenica già nel 1808, quando, in risposta al pessimismo manifestatogli dal diplomatico prussiano Bartholdy, ribatté di attenersi alle "lontane e forse vane illusioni della speranza". Nel 1810, da Milano, comunicò a Michele Ciliciani il proposito di scrivere un libro sui suoi sfortunati connazionali di Suli, in modo da rendere in maniera tangibile il suo trasporto emotivo per gli amati greci, "nobili sciagurati che sentono a prezzo di calamità la gloria de' loro antenati", progetto, però, rimasto nel concreto irrealizzato e destinato a essere immortalato invece nel 1823 dalla penna di Giovanni Berchet.

Foscolo tornò di nuovo a occuparsene nel periodo dell'esilio londinese allorché compose nel 1817 alcuni scritti lasciati inediti e poi raccolti nell'*Edizione nazionale foscoliana*, cioè lo *Stato politico delle Isole Ionie*, *Mémoire sur l'éducation publique aux Isles Ioniennes* e *Come ottenere modifiche alla Costituzione delle Isole Ionie*, che affrontavano aspetti specifici e fornivano indicazioni sull'assetto costituzionale da destinare al territorio insulare; l'ampio articolo *On Parga*, pubblicato anonimamente sull'*Edinburgh Review* nell'ottobre del 1819, in cui Foscolo tracciava la storia della sfortunata città, dei suoi fieri protagonisti e dei suoi selvaggi nemici; in ultimo, sempre sullo stesso tema e nello stesso periodo, l'opera *Narrative of events illustrating the vicissitudes and the cession of Parga*, rimasta incompiuta al terzo libro e tale da attirargli per queste ragioni le maligne accuse di codardia e di opportunismo da cui il poeta italo-ellenico di Zacinto cercò di scagionarsi nella *Lettera apologetica*⁴².

In conclusione, estremamente degna di nota è l'adesione agli orientamenti liberali e libertari dei greci da parte di uno dei massimi poeti della letteratura mondiale, Giacomo Leopardi, grande cultore della classicità, il quale nel periodo 1820-1821 abbozzò una *Canzone sulla Grecia*, attaccando a chiare lettere - come traspare anche dal *Supplemento* alla stessa - la detestabile politica dei principi europei che impediva "di recar soccorso così

⁴² Cfr. Achille Tartaro, "Letteratura filellenica in Italia", in *Risorgimento greco e filellenismo italiano...*, p. 118; Guido Muoni, *La letteratura filellenica nel romanticismo italiano*, Milano, Società editrice libraria, 1907, pp. 3-7; Elena Persico, *op. cit.*, pp. 21-25.

facile alla povera Grecia” e, al contempo, sopportava invece “l’indegna pirateria de’ barbareschi”, un testo abbastanza misconosciuto, ma dalla poetica ben chiara, come si evince dai seguenti stralci incompiuti: “Nostra amica, madre, nelle scienze ed arti e lettere maestra, è voce che siamo sua colonia ec. ec. si porti l’antica storia, è giusto che le siamo grati, le rendiamo quel che ci ha dato, sì ec. entusiasmo di compassione e di gratitudine, stato suo presente, stato antico, pittura delle principali gesta antiche in compendio giudizioso e veramente vivo e poetico, basta che risorgano in lei le buone discipline, non è morto il suo sacro fuoco, rivivrà la Grecia, apostrofe a quelli che ve le riconducono, sieno greci, sieno stranieri tutti parimenti obbligatissimi alla infelice...”⁴³.

⁴³ Giacomo Leopardi, “Canzone sulla Grecia” e “Supplemento”, in Idem, *Poesie e prose*, Milano, Hoepli, 1997, p. 216.

CLASSIQUES DE LA PEINTURE ROUMAINE DANS LE PATRIMOINE DU MUSEE D'ART DE TÎRGU MUREȘ

Cora Fodor*

Abstract

Classic Romanian paintings sheltered by the Art Museum of Mureș County

The paintings that are studied in this work are selected from the patrimony of the Art Museum of Mureș County and are representative both for the general artistic credo of the authors and for the plastic approach of the themes embraced by the painters studied: Theodor Aman, Sava Henția, the Moldavian Constantin Dumitru Stahi and Emanoil Bardasare, as well as for the classics that marked and distinctly contoured the 19th century: Nicolae Grigorescu, Ion Andreescu and Ștefan Luchian. Their role in the formation of the Romanian art school was a wholesome and highly decisive one. Their efforts were successfully made in order to find the best artistic formula to reveal our national sensitivity.

Keywords: Art Museum of Tîrgu Mureș, Romanian Art, Theodor Aman, Nicolae Grigorescu, Ion Andreescu, Ștefan Luchian

Les œuvres d'art roumain étudiées, représentent une sélection du patrimoine du Musée d'Arts de Tîrgu Mureș, un patrimoine assez peu étudié au regard de l'incalculable valeur de ces pièces et la parcimonie des écritures en leur référence. La sélection des œuvres, certaines inédites, permet de faire une succincte introduction dans la cristallisation de l'art roumain moderne, de coaguler une identité propre aussi dans le domaine de l'art, en identifiant les interférences et similitudes avec des tendances consacrées et stimulantes des grandes cultures occidentales. La physionomie de l'art roumain, une fois esquissée par les précurseurs du modernisme, s'assoit par le style, avec la création des trois piliers de l'art roumain: Nicolae Grigorescu, Ion Andreescu și Ștefan Luchian. Nicolae Grigorescu est le premier fondateur de la peinture roumaine moderne qui apporte une nouvelle¹ vision, consolidée par Ion Andreescu et anoblie par Ștefan Luchian.

Les œuvres étudiés sont représentatives pour la conception artistique de l'ensemble des auteurs et pour la manière de l'approche plastique des thèmes interprétés par les

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¹ Vasile Florea, *Theodor Aman*, București, Editura Meridiane, 1965, p. 12.

artistes en question: Theodor Aman, Sava Henția, les moldaves Constantin Dumitru Stahi et Emanoil Bardasare et les classiques qui marquent et clôturent avec distinction le XIX^{ème}² siècle: Nicolae Grigorescu, Ion Andreescu et Ștefan Luchian. Leur rôle dans la structuration de l'École d'art roumain a été bénéfique et déterminant. Leurs efforts se sont orientés vers la recherche d'une nouvelle formule artistique capable de refléter la sensibilité nationale.

L'histoire de la collection du Musée d'Art³ de Țirgu Mureș, débute avec les 68 œuvres d'art classique hongroise, "confiées"⁴ par le fond du Musée National d'Art de Budapest à la mairie de Țirgu Mureș qui a son tour, les confie au récent Palais de la Culture⁵ qui possédait aussi un espace dédié exclusivement à l'exposition des œuvres d'art. A ces 68 œuvres⁶ viennent se rajouter 15, achetées par le maire d'époque Bernády György, avec l'argent des contribuables de la ville. Au fil du temps, ce petit noyau se développe, la collection prenant un vigoureux revirement dans la quatrième décennie du XX^{ème} siècle, lorsque le destin de la collection était entre les mains du peintre Aurel Ciupe (1900-1988), en qualité de custode de la collection. La nécessité de créer un juste équilibre du patrimoine artistique⁷ le détermine d'appeler aux institutions d'État et d'initier une ample et réussite campagne⁸ parmi les artistes bucarestois en vue de cessation et de donation des œuvres⁹. Aussi, dans la période 1950-1970 il a été emprunté

² "Traité avec générosité" chronologique.

³ Jusqu'en 1949, nommée "pinacotecă" (terme dérivé de l'allemand "pinakothek").

⁴ Le terme "donation" n'est pas forcément celui utilisé à l'époque, lorsqu'on parlait plutôt de "cessation temporaire" ou de "gardiennage de certaines oeuvres" car la collection bénéficiait du statut de dépôt de l'état hongrois. Cfr. Arhivele Naționale ale României - Direcția Județeană Mureș (A.N.R.), Fond de la Mairie de Țirgu Mureș, Série du "Préfet de la ville", no. Acte 1108 du 1913, p. 1 *recto*.

⁵ La construction du Palais de la Culture s'est déroulée entre 1911-1913, selon les plans d'architectes Komor Marcell (1868-1944) et Jakab Dezső (1864-1932), secondés du peintre Aladár Körösfői Kriesch (1863-1920), le tout dans un style plutôt sécessionniste.

⁶ *Gazeta Mureșului*, II, nr. 29, 21 août 1932, p. 2.

⁷ Entre 1913 et 1934, la mairie a acquis 113 tableaux dont seulement 8 peints par des peintres roumains, cfr. "Gazeta Mureșului", IV, nr. 23, 10 juin 1934, p. 1.

⁸ Le 27 avril 1934 Aurel Ciupe avec Mihail Demetrescu, vont se déplacer à Bucarest pour obtenir des œuvres d'arts, par des donations, pour l'enrichissement de la collection. Suite à cette démarche, ils vont réussir à avoir 22 œuvres, soit données par des artistes soit empruntées auprès du Ministère de l'Instruction et des Arts.

⁹ Ainsi rentre dans le patrimoine *Peisaj la Muntele Athos*- Marius Bunescu, *Peisaj din Sudul Franței*- Paul Mișcovici, *Cap de expresie*- Aurel Kessler, *Ardeleana*- Mihai Onofrei, *Bustul lui Delavrancea*- Corneliu Medrea, *Bustul lui Octavian Goga*- Corneliu Medrea, *Cap de satir*- Corneliu Medrea (donné par

des œuvres de référence signées par des personnalités réputées¹⁰ de la scène roumaine, du patrimoine du Musée de l'Art de la République Socialiste Roumaine. L'emprunt a été facilité par le Ministère de l'Enseignement et de la Culture. Une partie de ces créations ont été données ultérieurement, en restant définitivement dans la collection du Musée d'Art de Tîrgu Mureş. Le nombre d'œuvres augmente progressivement en fonction des transferts, acquisitions et donations, en arrivant de 191 œuvres, soit la collection de 1944, à 2470 actuellement, comprenant outre les peintures et les sculptures, un riche fond de graphique et art décorative.

En revenant aux artistes et leurs œuvres mises en discussion, ils sont actifs spécialement dans la deuxième partie du XIXème siècle, mais le contexte de cristallisation de la peinture roumaine moderne est en pleine effervescence tout au long du XIXème siècle. C'est la période dans laquelle s'opère des mutations au niveau de la société roumaine entière, lorsque le mode de vie des bourgeois en pleine expansion apporte avec elle des formes et des institutions occidentales qui vont se mouler d'une manière hétéroclite, aux réalités locales. Progressivement, la condition du peintre et ses connotations prennent ses aises, la peinture au chevalet et la sculpture s'insèrent dans la pratique quotidienne.

Le passage de l'hiératisme et la spiritualité de l'héritage byzantin vers l'anthropocentrisme réaliste de type occidental, se fait assez brusquement, en récupérant plutôt l'aspect de la forme que son fond. La peinture murale et des icônes tel que pratiquée par les peintres d'église et d'icônes est abondante dans le domaine de la peinture de chevalet, la pratique du portrait étant le plus souvent utilisé au départ comme une immortalisation pour la postériorité des visages de ceux qui se sont rapidement affirmé sur l'échelle sociale, en s'éloignant de la précédente représentation votive.

La seconde partie du XIXème siècle apporte avec soi, un nouvel état d'esprit sur un fond historique des grands événements générateurs de changements radicaux, en entraînant la jeunesse intellectuelle aussi sur le plan culturel. C'est une période effervescente, avec des grandes ouvertures vers le monde occidental, lorsque se forge et se consolide l'identité culturelle et lorsque les Écoles de Beaux-arts arrivent:

Dimitrie Paciurea), *Bustul lui Bourdelle*- Mihai Onofrei, *Cântărețul din baladă*-Serova Medrea, auxquelles s'ajoutent deux œuvres données par Oscar Han et quinze autres obtenues du Ministère. Cfr. "Gazeta Mureşului", IV, nr. 23, 10 juin 1934, p. 1.

¹⁰ Il s'agit des œuvres des artistes Theodor Aman, Nicolae Grigorescu, Ştefan Luchian, Gheorghe Petraşcu, etc.

celle de Iassy en 1860 grâce à Gheorghe Panaiteanu Bardasare et celle de Bucarest en 1864 suite aux démarches des peintres Theodor Aman et Gheorghe Tătărăscu¹¹.

Ainsi, Theodor Aman (1831-1891) est celui qui par la synthèse des recherches de ses prédécesseurs, intègre définitivement la peinture roumaine dans le paysage européen correspondant. Par contre, malgré la diversité de techniques abordés: peinture, dessin, graphique et sa disponibilité comme professeur ou collectionneur d'art, en maîtrisant pleinement la technique de la peinture, se garde dans la sphère de certaines conventions. Il accélère et ferme une étape¹² - celle de l'académisme - en lui épuisant les moyens et les solutions. De valeur et recherche comme portraitiste, dans une période où ce style était populaire, Aman réalise un grand nombre de toiles dans lesquelles les personnages sont représentés dans une tonalité austère académique ou bien plus énigmatique spécifique au Romantisme. *Le Portrait de Pepica Aman*¹³ (*Portretul Pepicăi Aman*) - représentant la mère de l'artiste - a été réalisé vers 1856, donc dans la phase de début de sa création, nous dévoile un bon dessinateur, mais garde la teinte froide et enfermée des formes traditionnelles, avec une palette retenue qui souligne plutôt la dignité du personnage que l'approche maternelle. Une image beaucoup plus libre dans l'expression, dans une lumière beaucoup plus chaude, imprégnée discrètement par l'atmosphère locale, c'est dans le tableau *La Ronde (Hora)* dans lequel on ressent l'amour de la vie sans toutefois tomber dans le pathétisme. Malgré ceci, l'œuvre dégage un certain manque de naturalité et dénote le traitement du côté pittoresque de la vie à la campagne, sans soucis et avec des accents mis sur les attitudes et le costume populaire. Elle fait partie d'une suite beaucoup plus ample sur le même thème¹⁴, celui des jeux populaires, bucolique idéalisant. Par sa création, Theodor Aman ouvre seulement la voie¹⁵ de certaines reconsidérations esthétiques dans l'art roumain, sans pour autant être novateur. Son effort de modernisme est porté plus loin par Nicolae Grigorescu qui va proposer et imposé une nouvelle vision artistique.

¹¹ Des artistes missionnaires, des fondateurs des institutions et collections modernes, des initiateurs des salons d'arts.

¹² Vasile Florea, *Theodor Aman*, cit., p. 13.

¹³ Une autre représentation de Pepica Aman se trouve au Musée d'Art de Craiova.

¹⁴ Il existe de grandes similitudes avec l'œuvre *La Ronde de Aninoasa (Hora de la Aninoasa)* se trouvant dans le Patrimoine du Musée National d'Art de Roumanie, mais la manière de travail plus retenue, ainsi que la posture plus rigide des personnages, font penser que l'œuvre de Tîrgu Mures précède à celle-ci.

¹⁵ Vasile Florea, *Theodor Aman*, cit., p. 16.

Un des élèves d'Aman, Sava Henția (1848-1904), peintre de Transylvanie, va contribuer à l'enrichissement de la peinture roumaine au travers des portraits de son entourage, auréolés d'une valeur documentaire, résultant de l'habileté et le savoir faire des artisans. Attiré par le style pictural de Prud'hon¹⁶, du côté lyrique caractéristique de ses œuvres, à ses débuts il peut être considéré comme un bon disciple du peintre français¹⁷. Progressivement il va se forger sa personnalité artistique, caractérisée par un dessin et un coloriage vigoureux, mais parfois il est trahi par certaines réminiscences des hommes du maître français. Dès fois, il arrive à se détacher de l'appareillage artificiel et conventionnel, en prenant librement des thèmes de sa réalité proche. Après la Guerre d'Indépendance où il était attaché au niveau du quartier général, il se consacre presque complètement au portrait, aux tableaux historiques et les natures statiques, thèmes populaires à l'époque.

Faite en 1876, l'œuvre *Le Gibier (Vânat)* est caractéristique pour cette large période de l'artiste où il traite souvent des thèmes aux teintes cynégétiques. Ceci dérivé pas tant d'une passion pour les trophées de chasse que par la prédilection et la virtuosité de la réalisation des natures statiques¹⁸. Le sujet est abordé exclusivement comme exercice de style, sans profusion philosophique ou des allusions littéraires, et l'œuvre restitue les éléments de cette nature morte comme prétexte de l'exercice de forme et couleur. L'accent est mis sur l'habileté de la composition à la verticale sur laquelle les éléments sont minutieusement reproduits dans des touches académiques. La palette de couleur oscille entre l'harmonie des bruns et des gris cendrés avec des touches de vert bois sur fond neutre, non modulé. La lumière utilisée avec parcimonie vient renforcer l'ensemble. A Iassy, les professeurs de l'École de Beaux-arts formés dans la capitale bavaroise restent fidèles aux principes du courant académiste (dans sa forme classique ou celle du réalisme bourgeois) accumulés avec beaucoup d'application là-bas. Emanoil Bardasare (1850-1935) est convaincu par le lyrisme de l'école munichoise dans les scènes du genre ou les paysages mineurs dominés d'une lumière sentimentale. L'œuvre *L'Italienne (Italianca)* démontre une maîtrise rigoureuse de la technique en dépit de l'imagination, un esprit subtil qui, par la qualité picturale des

¹⁶ Pierre Paul Prud'hon (1758-1823) a été un peintre et dessinateur français, influencé à ses débuts par le Néoclassicisme avant de se dédier au Néoromantisme. Il est connu surtout pour ses portraits et ses peintures allégoriques. Il était en vogue à la cour de Napoléon.

¹⁷ Livia Drăgoi, *Sava Henția*, Bucureşti, Editura Meridiane, 1979, p. 16.

¹⁸ *Ibidem*, p. 22.

vêtements, par le traitement personnel du portrait vaguement flatté, tente de se détacher timidement de l'ancienne mentalité.

Toujours venant de Moldavie, Constantin Dumitru Stahi (1844-1920) a traversé toutes les étapes de l'enseignement, nécessaires à la préparation dans le système académique, en commençant par le compagnonnage chez un peintre d'église et arrivant à enseigner à l'École de Beaux-arts de Iassy. Il reste connu et apprécié, spécialement, comme auteur de minutieuses natures statiques¹⁹ et il est présent dans la collection avec un impeccable portrait, *Le Vieux (Bătrân)*. Celui-ci démontre la force et la précision du dessin, l'utilisation d'une technique juste, acquise pendant les études à l'école munichoise. Avec une virtuosité technique dans laquelle on retrouve la passion de la minutie du détail physique (dérivé aussi de sa pratique de la gravure) mais avec une vague émotion intérieure, le portrait est une excellente étude de physionomie. Il ne lui manque ni les jeux contrôlés des lumières ni l'ombre entre le visage du personnage et le fond non modulé.

Ces artistes, sont des fidèles disciples qui appliquent avec beaucoup d'habileté les formules académiques, sans accentuer une note particulière en mesure de les individualiser. L'attachement aux principes consacrés, transposés avec abnégation et foi, les rendent tributaires à la fidélité de l'aspect physique du modèle au détriment d'une profonde analyse.

La peinture roumaine pénètre dans l'ambiance des prérogatives modernes, avec Nicolae Grigorescu (1838-1907) dont son cursus implique le motif et l'atmosphère, en apportant un nouveau mode totalement inédit de la pensée plastique. C'est la conséquence du contact avec l'expérience et la peinture française, en exerçant à côté de ses collègues à Barbizon (parmi lesquels Jean François Millet²⁰), en pratiquant le plein air, qui par la suite, il va l'adopter et transposer à la réalité roumaine. L'option pour l'École de Barbizon, attiré par une nouvelle vision de l'art, qui lui ouvrait une peinture libérée des règles académiques strictes et fades, marque un tournant dans sa vision et sa création artistique.

Sans qu'il soit un vrai portraitiste²¹, par son tempérament, Grigorescu innove chez nous ce genre, en déplaçant l'accent de la description rigoureuse des attributs extérieurs vers une représentation fortement individualisée, axée sur les ressentiments intérieurs. *L'Intendant de Barbizon*

¹⁹ Valentin Ciucă, *Un secol de arte frumoase la Iași*, Iași, Editura ART XXI, 2005, p. 33.

²⁰ Jean François Millet (1814-1875) a été un peintre français, figure de proue de l'École de Barbizon. Il se dédie aux sujets d'un réalisme accru pour la restitution du travail au champ et la fatigue physique des paysans.

²¹ George Oprescu, *Nicolae Grigorescu*, București, Editura Meridiane, 1963, p. 38.

(*Intendentul de la Barbizon*) fait partie de la suite des portraits des personnages modestes, restitués avec réalisme dans une expression exquise, preuve d'une parfaite compréhension du modèle. Cette manière de faire, le place dans une descendance rembrandtienne dans le rendu de l'atmosphère de la lumière et des effets du clair-obscur. De la grande diversité de ses portraits, souvent les personnages sont placés dans la nature, dans la même atmosphère dominée par l'harmonie et le silence, tel que dans l'œuvre *La Jeune fille à cruche (Fata cu urcior)*. Elle appartient à la catégorie plus ample, celle de "la vie au village" dont l'interprétation très spécifique, lui apporta la célébrité. Légèrement idéalisé, dans une écriture raffinée et une colorisation impressionnante, il respire une grande fraîcheur, en rappelant un rythme d'un chant populaire. Il utilise une palette lumineuse des couleurs et il adapte la technique picturale pour surprendre l'instant, en étant inspiré du mouvement impressionniste²². Il transforme le paysage d'un simple décor, dans un cadre lyrique dans lequel il intègre ses personnages. Il est facile de reconnaître la silhouette féminine, spécifique à Grigorescu, celle d'une paysanne filiforme, dans un costume populaire. L'accent n'est pas mis sur les détails qui tiennent du folklore mais sur l'esthétisme de la peinture, le personnage devenant une sorte de médiateur entre le paysage et le contemplateur du tableau.

Un autre sujet favori est le paysage, plus particulièrement la forêt et les collines. Dans l'œuvre *Le Paysage (Peisaj)*, appartenant à la phase de pleine maturité, avec des longues touches, il présente une vision dans laquelle nous ne retrouverons plus des formes mais uniquement des bandes chromatiques horizontales et étroites, qui s'entremêlent toutefois dans un ensemble unitaire sans contrastes dramatiques. Il démontre ainsi, non seulement une évolution de la palette de l'artiste suite au contact avec les terres ensoleillées dominées d'une atmosphère calme et chaude, mais aussi d'une conception picturale basée sur une vision de synthèse, propre à la nature artistique de Grigorescu. Le résultat est un ensemble plein de saveur lyrique.

Le motif du "char à bœufs" fait partie d'une iconographie originale créée dans la peinture roumaine par Grigorescu, motif auquel il dédie beaucoup de tableaux dans sa période dite "blanche". De cette période de fin de vie, il appartient la toile *Parmi des côtes et des collines (Printre dealuri și muscele)* dans laquelle on ressent fortement son niveau de maturité; la lumière blanche, limpide des jours d'été répandue sur la

²² *Ibidem*, p. 60.

surface entière de l'œuvre lui rend un aspect lyrique, mélangeant repos et rêverie. Le bleu éteint du ciel, le vert poussiéreux des collines mélangé aux ombres lilacées, crée une atmosphère de rêverie, un vrai chant de joie face à la nature, en dévoilant la note caractéristique de son intériorité spécifique.

Sans faire une école de peinture à proprement parler, Grigorescu sera pour ses successeurs, un véritable menteur, en créant des émules, mais aussi des épigones.

En pendant à la valeur de Grigorescu, par son éclectisme et son degré de pérennité, se trouve Ion Andreescu (1850-1882) avec un tonus différent en ce qui concerne l'atmosphère des ses peintures. L'enthousiasme et l'exubérance "grigorescienne", il oppose une intonation grave du thème, du motif et du coloriage. Avec un talent précoce, il commence ses recherches avec un répertoire thématique restreint: natures statiques ou voisinages des habitations modestes, faisant un crayonnage distinct de l'image du village roumain de pleine plaine, dans une note austère, en pleine résonance avec son être. Au début, se trouvant sous l'influence directe de Grigorescu, il arrive progressivement de s'élaborer ses propres formules d'une vraie originalité.

L'œuvre *Les Jacinthes (Zambilele)* fait partie de la première période de création, lorsque sa palette réduite des tonalités de verts, des brunâtres et grisâtres, légèrement adoucies par le rose délicat des fleurs, rangés avec simplicité dans un verre avec des transparences aériennes qui dégage dans son ensemble, une modeste et conquérante émotion. Le contact avec la peinture française pendant son séjour à Paris et Barbizon, lui rafraîchit la colorisation qui va gagner en subtilité, grâce à des touches joyeuses, en devenant l'adepte d'une contemplation sereine. Sa technique se cisèle tel que prouvé dans la toile *Le Paysage (Peisaj)*. Malgré ses dimensions réduites, elle arrive à suggérer certains états d'âme provoqués par le frémissement de la matière vive et dévoile des indices de colorisation moderne, signe d'une émancipation de sa vision plastique.

L'œuvre d'Andreescu limitée à une décennie de création, est caractérisée par la profondeur du sentiment, restituée par des moyens d'expression bien clarifiés et assumés. Il bâtit des espaces avec désinvolture chromatique, le tout parcouru d'une onde de méditation grave.

La période de fin du XIX^{ème} siècle et le début de la Grande Guerre fut prolifique, ce qui va influencer et donner l'impulsion à la physionomie artistique entre les deux guerres, l'expression d'une prégnante continuité, en évitant les

manifestations polémiques radicales par rapport à ses prédécesseurs.

Si jusqu'au 1900 la physionomie de la peinture roumaine a été fortement influencée par l'impulsion occidentale, avec Luchian on arrive avoir une évolution d'émancipation par rapport aux schémas existants, par la synthèse proposée. Toutefois, le système de référence reste l'École française²³. Par contre, on fait aussi appel à la position esthétique antérieure au XIX^{ème} siècle, ses éléments étant adaptés et assimilés dans des expériences artistiques cultes. Le passage des siècles est caractérisé par une animation des tendances réformiste en fonction des influences des courants artistiques de l'extérieur, ramenés par les jeunes gens qui ont étudié dans les écoles européennes. C'est le moment des grandes expériences dans l'espace artistique européen, dans lequel l'autonomie du langage de type impressionniste, la grâce de l'Art Nouveau, la recherche analytique de la forme, de la surface et du volume d'une perspective cézannienne, rythment ensemble. La modalité dans laquelle se collecte ces influences est par contre, une modalité retenue, ayant comme source un vieil instinct de la mesure. Il convient de remarquer une transformation de la peinture roumaine d'une attitude lyrico-méditative à une plus dynamique, avec un penchement vers un filon en tension, sorte de renoncement à l'élément pur sensoriel. Malgré tout ça, aucun d'entre eux ne va pas adhérer aux formes extrêmes de manifestation de l'époque. C'est la période de la croissance de l'intérêt pour l'art populaire, pour les valeurs propres, locales, dans l'essai de définition d'un spécifique national. Sous l'influence du style de Grigorescu, il apparaît des successeurs mineurs du grand artiste, des représentants du "*semănătorism*", intéressés plutôt par le détail ethnographique que par la connaissance approfondie du monde rural.

Celui qui va savoir renoncer aux conquêtes et aux autres effets faciles, en captant en même temps toutes les provocations de l'époque, sans toutefois se borner à aucune d'entre elles, celui par lequel il existe un mouvement ascensionnel vers le nouveau et la modernité, c'est Ștefan Luchian (1868-1916).

L'intensité de la coloration et du sentiment, la synthèse chromatique spécifique, le refus du lyrisme conventionnel, font de Luchian un peintre à part.

Luchian met en valeur les sources et crée une synthèse entre l'esprit des formes et du langage compris dans l'art

²³ Idem, *Pictura românească în secolul al XIX-lea*, București, Editura Meridiane, 1984, p. 272.

traditionnel et les notions formelles de la pensée plastique européenne de fin de siècle, mais aussi il crée une synthèse entre deux attitudes distinctes de la culture roumaine: l'attitude rigoureuse-rationnelle et celle dramatique-expressive. Par l'œuvre de Luchian on prend conscience et on applique à une formule préexistante dans le filon de notre ancienne peinture, en mettant en valeur en même temps, un style contemporain avec une référence à la peinture de Manet²⁴, Degas²⁵ ou Cézanne²⁶. Progressivement il va quitter la manière de Grigorescu²⁷ et passant par la séduction de la ligne ondulatoire spécifique à l'Art Nouveau, en fin de comptes, il va bâtir définitivement sa propre vision. D'un point de vue de l'implication organisationnelle soutenue par la conviction de l'innovation dans le domaine de l'art, Ștefan Luchian fut un des initiateurs de l'Exposition des Artistes Indépendants du mai 1896 ouverte en total désaccord avec le Salon Officiel, en plaidant pour la liberté de l'expression dans l'art²⁸. En même temps il va participer à la fondation de la Société "Ileana"²⁹ et de la revue éponyme mais que ne va pas perdurer, fort probable en raison économique.

Un chapitre consistant de sa création est réservé aux natures statiques et plus particulièrement aux fleurs, dans lesquelles la suggestion de la forme par la couleur est l'expression d'un vibrant ressenti de son âme. Contenue dans l'enrobage sensible de la pâte et de la couleur, ses fleurs³⁰, soit *Les Anémones* (*Anemone*, titre d'une des œuvres dans le patrimoine de Tîrgu Mureș), les roses, les œillets communs ou bien des immortelles, se transforment dans un moyen de communication des mouvements d'états d'âme. Celle-ci sont posée le plus souvent dans des vases en terre traditionnelle, d'une beauté simple, avec des accord chromatiques inspirés par l'art populaire roumaine, car, tel que le maître l'affirmait en faisant référence aux fleurs peintes: "puisque'elle sont de chez nous, cela leur va bien dans un bocal fait toujours par nous". Pour équilibrer la composition, souvent, à la base de vases se

²⁴ Édouard Manet (1832-1883), peintre français, précurseur de l'Impressionnisme, par son œuvre il se place à la limite entre le classique et le moderne.

²⁵ Edgar Degas (1834-1917), peintre français qui s'est démarqué par son talent extraordinaire de dessin, spécialement dans le pastel, et par ses sujets préférés du monde des ballerines, des modistes et des courses de chevaux.

²⁶ Paul Cézanne (1839-1906), peintre français considéré le plus novateur de l'art moderne, qui fait la transition entre l'Impressionnisme et le Cubisme.

²⁷ Vasile Drăguț, *Luchian*, București, Editura Meridiane, 1962, pp. 10-13.

²⁸ George Oprescu, *Pictura românească în...*, cit., p. 275.

²⁹ Vasile Florea, *Pictura în secolul al XIX-lea*, București, Editura Meridiane, 1976, p. 212; George Oprescu, *Pictura românească în...*, cit., p. 276.

³⁰ Le choix de ce sujet est conséquent à la limitation du thème, due à la contrainte induite par la souffrance qui l'immobilise à la maison.

retrouvent, éparpillées sur la table, des pétales et des fleurs. Avec certitude, et non pas par hasard, Luchian a choisi parmi ses préférées, l'anémone dont ses racines légendaires ont bâti des aspects duaux: amour-mort, retrouvaille-séparation, ressuscitation-extinction. De ce point de vue, on peut faire des associations avec son destin. Luchian confère à la thématique des fleurs, une gamme infinie de nuances en reflétant sa propre sensibilité.

Aussi bien le blanc éclatant avec des variations tonale, les harmonies de rose et de gris, que la composition, font de la toile *Le pot à roses blanches (Vas cu trandafiri albi)* une œuvre d'une expressivité maximale et de témoignage de ses propres vibrations de son âme, malgré le fait que le sujet soit prosaïque. Soit en huile soit en pastel³¹, Luchian mène avec grande habileté, le tracé de ligne comme provocation du langage, mais plus particulièrement il manifeste d'une manière obsessionnelle l'intériorisation et les valences subtiles du domaine de la sensibilité.

Les années entre 1905 et 1910 sont considérées la période d'apogée de sa création artistique³², lorsqu'il peint avec prédilection, des portraits et compositions dans lesquelles il montre sa solidarité auprès des humbles. C'est la période qui met en évidence la purification de son style, qui parcourt le chemin du "spécifique vers générique"³³. En 1909, il passe l'été dans la petite bourgade de Moinești, où, à part le paysage, il recherche à approfondir les visages typiques des quelques juifs³⁴ qu'il fait connaissance et avec qui, il essaye de sympathiser³⁵ malgré le fait qu'ils ne se laissent pas "poser". De cette période nous présumons que l'œuvre *Le portrait du vieux (Portret de bătrân)* de la collection de Tîrgu Mureș, fait partie. Atypique dans la manière, par sa gamme de couleur très sombre et les notes rembrandtiennes de clair-obscur, le portrait se trouve plutôt dans la sphère d'influence de célèbres portraits de juifs appartenant à Grigorescu, avec un accent sur une analyse humaine très profonde.

Luchian n'apporte pas des nouveautés dans le sujet mais dans sa manière de résolution et de la profondeur du sentiment³⁶.

³¹ Technique moins chère et plus commode, préférée par l'artiste dans les dernières années de vie à cause de sa maladie et sa pauvreté.

³² Petru Comarnescu, *Luchian*, București, Editura Tineretului, 1965, p. 222.

³³ Theodor Enescu, *Ștefan Luchian și spiritualul modern în pictura românească*, București, Editura Meridiane, 2000, p. 228.

³⁴ Petru Comarnescu, *Ștefan Luchian*, București, Editura Tineretului, 1960, pp. 217-218.

³⁵ Vasile Drăguț, *op. cit.*, p. 64.

³⁶ George Oprescu, *Pictura românească în...*, cit., p. 276.

Même si dans l'époque persiste l'impact de Grigorescu, au travers de Luchian fait apparition une nouvelle conception de la peinture du début de siècle et se stabilise la modernité du langage dans l'art roumain. Ceux qui continuent et diversifient cette ouverture de chemin, dans le nouveau sens du message artistique sont, avec prédilection Tonitza, Petraşcu et Pallady d'entre les deux guerres. Avec eux, on ouvre un nouveau chapitre dans l'art roumain.

**CORRUPTION. NOTION AND THE HISTORICAL
EVOLUTION OF THE PHENOMENON.
EVOLUTION OF THE CRIME OF CORRUPTION IN
THE APPROPRIATE REGULATIONS OF THE 1821-
PRESENT PERIOD**

Adrian Vasile Boantă,*
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Abstract

If we relate strictly to the notion of corruption, it can be asserted that this phenomenon existed from ancient times. There are some opinions which argue that the human tendency to corruption has always existed. The phenomenon of corruption does not refer only to bribery, abuse, receiving undue benefits or other crimes related to corruption, being rather an illicit intersection of the public authorities sphere with private sector.

Keywords: *Corruption, Definition, Evolution, Law*

The crime of corruption is entered in the *Condica criminalicească* and its procedure, adopted in 1826, during the reign of Sturdza¹. The text applies only to a restricted category of persons, namely to officials who facilitate the escape of prisoners under their supervision².

Until the adoption of the Criminal Code of 1965, *Condica de Drept penal și procedura penală* is worth mentioning, which sanctions the active and passive forms of corruption in different ways, according to the concrete social danger that each illegal action represents. The official was considered more dangerous than the one, who gave the bribe, and was punished more severely³.

The 1884 Criminal Code

The 1884 Criminal Code⁴ incriminated influence peddling in Art. 146 and bribe taking (passive corruption) in

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¹ Viorel Pașca, *Drept penal. Parte generală I*, Timișoara, Editura WorldTech, 2006, p. 45.

² Vasile Dobrinou, Mihai Adrian Hotca, Norel Neagu, *et alii, Legea nr. 78/2000 pentru prevenirea descoperirea și sancționarea faptelor de corupție*, București, Editura Wolters Kluwer, 2009, p. 51.

³ *Ibidem*, p. 17.

⁴ The Code was republished in 1912, in what follows we will refer to this form.

Art. 144 and 145, but without incriminating the active form of corruption, the giving of bribe.

According to Art. 144, in Chapter II of Title VIII, entitled *Crimes and Offenses against Public Interest*: “Any public official belonging to the judiciary or administration, any agent of a public administration, which received or claimed gifts or presents, or which accepted promises of these, in order to do, or not to do, an act pertaining to his function, even if it is a rightful one, but for which there is no payment determined by law, shall be punished with imprisonment from two to three years and a fine double the amount received or promised, without this fine being less than 200 lei. The money or the gifts, or their value will be taken on behalf of the madhouses or charity houses of the locality where the bribery was committed.

They will not be able to occupy a public function in the future and they lose their pension rights. This same punishment will apply to any arbitrator or expert, appointed by the court or by the parties, which will accept promises or receive gifts or presents, to give a decision or emit an opinion favorable to one of the parties”.

According to art 145, “If the bribery was effectuated upon a judge or juror leading to a pronouncement in criminal matters for or against the accused, the punishment will be the maximum prison sentence, the loss of the right to ever be admitted to these kind of position again and also the loss of pension rights. If the bribing intervened upon a juror who pronounced in matters of expropriation, the punishment will be imprisonment from one to two years, the loss of the right to hold this position again and the loss of pension rights”.

This criminal code did not incriminate the giving of bribe, reason for why, it was considered in the doctrine⁵ that the legislature’s purpose was to facilitate the denouncing of such acts, however, in practice of the courts, the briber was condemned as an instigator⁶ to the crime of taking bribe.

The provisions of Art. 146 of the Criminal Code did incriminate influence peddling: “Any private person who, on his behalf or on behalf of any public official, administrative or judicial, with or without their knowledge, directly or indirectly, will ask, will take or will determine someone to promise gifts or other undue advantages in order to intervene to do, or not to do an act concerning the prerogatives of that official, the

⁵ Vasile Dobrinouiu, Mihai Adrian Hotca, Norel Neagu, *et alii*, *op. cit.*, p. 52; Ion Tanoviceanu, Vintilă Dongoroz, *Tratat de drept și procedură penală*, ed. a II-a, București, Editura Academiei, 1925, p. 565.

⁶ Vintilă Dongoroz, Siegfried Kahane, Ion Oancea, *et alii*, *Explicații teoretice ale Codului Penal Român. Partea Specială*, vol. IV, București, Editura Academiei, 1972, p. 145.

punishment is imprisonment from six months to 2 years and a fine double the value of the things taken or promised, without this fine being less than 200 lei.

The money or the gifts, or their value will be taken on behalf of the madhouses or charity houses of the locality where the bribery was committed.

And if the mediator is a public official, he will lose his right to ever again occupy a public function and his pension's rights".

Sanctioning influence peddling is how I showed before, a takeover of the legislature from *Pravilniceasca Conducă* and it is designed to fill the legal vacuum caused by the non-incrimination of the active form of corruption (bribe giving)⁷.

The 1936 Criminal Code

Bribe taking and bribe giving were incriminated in the 1936 Criminal Code, in Art. 250 and 251, influence peddling in Art. 252 and receipt of undue advantage in art. 240⁸.

According to Art. 250, "The individual who promises, offers or gives money or other benefits, directly or indirectly, to a public official in order to determine him to perform, not to perform or delay the performance of an act pertaining to his function, or to perform an act contrary to his duties, shall be punished by imprisonment from 6 months to 3 years and a fine of 5000 to 10000 lei.

If the bribery was effectuated upon a judge or a person holding an elected office, juror or a public official charged with the delivery, reception or supervision of supplies or public works, or with the assessment or collection of taxes, the punishment is correctional imprisonment from 1 to 5 years and a fine of 5000 to 15000 lei.

If the proposal was not accepted, the briber is punished with correctional imprisonment from 2 to 6 months.

It is not deemed bribery the act committed under the conditions of art. 238. No person shall be punished for bribery if the bribe was claimed and if by refusing the claim he would have suffered inevitable and important damages in relation with his material situation".

⁷ Vasile Dobrinoiu, *Corupția în dreptul penal român*, București, Editura Atlas Lex, 1995, p. 53.

⁸ Horia Diaconescu, *Infrațiunile de corupție și cele asimilate cu acestea*, București, Editura All Beck, 2004, p. 6.

The provisions have partial counterpart in the provisions of Art. 255 from the 1968 Criminal Code, in which the aggravations were not mentioned.⁹

According to Art. 240, the unfair remuneration was incriminated, which corresponds to the offense of receiving undue benefits.

According to Art. 251 “The public official, which, for the purpose showed in the preceding article, claims or gets, directly or indirectly, money or any other benefits, which are not appropriate, or accepts such a promise or does not rejects it, commits the offense of taking bribe and it is punished with correctional imprisonment from one to 5 years, a fine of 5000 to 15000 and correctional ban from 1 to 5 years.

The punishment is correctional imprisonment from 2 to 5 years, a fine of 5000 to 15000 lei and correctional ban from 2 to 5 years, in the case of paragraph 2, is correctional imprisonment from 3 to 8 years, a fine of 5000 to 15000 and correctional ban from 3 to 6 years, if the bribed one, committed an unlawful or illegal act because of this.

In all the other cases of bribe giving, the money, the gifts or their value is taken for the benefit if the fine.” The 1968 Criminal Code mostly takes over the objective side of the crime of bribery from the 1937 Criminal Code, with the exception of some aggravating circumstances”¹⁰.

The crime of influence peddling was incriminated in art. 252: “The receipt of or request of gifts, money or other benefits, or the acceptance of promises, gifts, be it directly or indirectly, for oneself or for another, committed by a person who is influential or who gives to believe that he/she is influential upon a clerk, in order to determine him/her to perform or not to perform an act included within his/her service prerogatives, commits the crime of influence peddling and shall be punished by correctional imprisonment from 6 months to 2 years, a fine of 2000 to 10000 lei and correctional ban from 1 to 3 years.

If the defendant receives directly or indirectly, or determines someone to give or promise, for oneself or for another, gifts, other benefits or money, under the pretext that he/she has to buy the favor of a clerk/public servant, the punishment is correctional imprisonment from 1 to 3 years, a fine of 2000 to 10000 lei and correctional ban from 1 to 3 years.

The things received or their value will be taken for the benefit of the fines fund. The provisions of paragraph 1 are taken by the subsequent criminal code, the aggravating version of paragraph 2 is not used subsequently and the act of

⁹ Vintilă Dongoroz *et alii*, *op.cit.*, p. 146.

¹⁰ *Ibidem*, p. 138.

paragraph 2 is no longer separately criminalized, which if committed would constitute another crime”¹¹.

The 1969 Criminal Code

*The 1969*¹² *Criminal Code* took substantially the concepts of the previous criminal code, in what concerns the acts of corruption, in what follows we will present the crimes of corruption in their actual form.

Art. 254 (bribe giving): The act of a clerk who, either directly or indirectly, claims or receives money or other undue benefits, or accepts the promise of such benefits or does not reject it, in order to perform, not to perform or to delay the accomplishment of an act with regard to his service duties or in order to perform an act that is contrary to these duties, shall be punished by imprisonment from 3 to 12 years and the prohibition of certain rights.

The act in paragraph (1), if it has been committed by a clerk having prerogatives of control, shall be punished by imprisonment from 3 to 15 years and the prohibition of certain rights¹³.

The money, values or any other goods that were the object of bribe taking shall be confiscated, and if they cannot be found, the convict shall be obliged to pay their equivalent in money.

Art. 255 Bribe giving: The act of promising, offering or giving money or other benefits in the manners and for the purposes shown in Art. 254, shall be punished by imprisonment from 6 months to 5 years.

The act in the previous paragraph shall not be an offence when the bribe-giver was coerced by any means by the bribe-taker.

The bribe-giver shall not be punished if he/she denounces the act to the authorities before the body of prosecution is notified for that offence.

Art. 254 paragraph (3) shall apply accordingly, even if the offer was not followed by acceptance¹⁴.

The money, values or any other goods shall be returned to the person who gave them, in the cases provided in paragraph (2) and (3).

¹¹ Respectively, the abuse of office, fraud, misappropriation of official qualities.

¹² Published in *Monitorul Oficial*, no. 79-79 bis/ 21.06.1968.

¹³ Introduced by Paragraph 1 of Law no. 65/1992.

¹⁴ Amended by Paragraph 2 of Law no. 65/1992.

Art. 256 (Receipt of undue advantage): The act, committed by a clerk, of receiving, either directly or indirectly, money or other benefits after having accomplished an act by virtue of his/her office and which was incumbent upon him/her because of this office, shall be punished by imprisonment from 6 months to 5 years¹⁵.

The money, values or other goods received shall be confiscated, and if they cannot be found, the convict shall be obliged to pay their equivalent in money.

Art. 257 (influence peddling): The receipt of or request of money or other benefits, or the acceptance of promises, gifts, be it directly or indirectly, for oneself or for another, committed by a person who is influential or who gives to believe that he/she is influential upon a clerk, in order to determine him/her to perform or not to perform an act included within his/her service prerogatives, shall be punished by imprisonment from 2 to 10 years¹⁶.

Art. 253 (1) introduced by Law No. 278/2006¹⁷ incriminates the conflict of interest in conformity with which: The deed of a civil servant who, in the exercise of service prerogatives, fulfills an act or participates in making a decision through which it was realized, directly or indirectly, a material benefit for himself or another person with who he/she had commercial or employment relationships in the past five years or from who he/she has received services or benefits of any kind, shall be punished with imprisonment from 6 months to 5 years and the prohibition to hold a public function. The provisions of paragraph (1) shall not apply in the case of the issuing, approval or adoption of laws.

Law no. 65/1992

The first changes after 1989 concerning the crimes of corruption were provided by Law no. 65/1992¹⁸ which amended and supplemented the criminal code regarding some facts of corruption.

Point 1 of Law no. 65/1992, introduces paragraph 2 in Art. 254 of the Criminal Code, through which it is worsen the criminal liability of public servants who also exercise control attributions.

Paragraph 2 of Law no. 65/1992 introduces Art. 255 Criminal Code “the provisions of art. 254 al. 3 apply properly, even if the offer was not followed by acceptance”.

¹⁵ Amended by Paragraph 3 of Law no. 65/1992.

¹⁶ Amended by Paragraph 4 of Law no. 65/1992.

¹⁷ Published in *Monotorul Oficial* no. 601 of July the 7th 2006.

¹⁸ Published in *Monotorul Oficial* no. 166/1992.

Point 3 and 4 change the content of Art. 256 and 257 respectively as we mentioned before.

The last change refers to the content of Art. 258 of the Criminal Code, whose scope was extended to other employees within the organizations provided by Art. 145 Criminal Code, including the autonomous companies, companies owed in full or majority by the state, and also to their directors and auditors. The provisions of Art. 254, 256, 257 regarding civil servants will also apply to servants working in the private sphere.

Law no. 78/2000 with ulterior modifications and completions

The legal regime of corruption infractions was determined by the enactment of Law no. 78/2000 which was substantially modified by Law no. 161/2003.

Art. 5 of Law no. 78/2000 distinguishes four categories of crimes: corruption infractions, infractions assimilated to corruption infractions, infractions directly connected to corruption infractions or with those assimilated to them and infractions against the financial interests of the European Communities¹⁹.

The New Criminal Code

Within the framework Criminal Code of 17th July 2009 approved by Law no. 286/2009 published in the *Monitorul Oficial* of Romania no. 510 of 24 July 2009, Title V, Chapter I called "Corruption Infractions" considers bribe taking (Art. 289), bribe giving (290), influence peddling (291), influence buying (292). The denomination of Title V, "Corruption and Workplace Infractions" is criticized by doctrine²⁰ since the pre-project phase of the Criminal Code as the denomination of a chapter cannot consist of a simple association of the names of the component infractions. It must reflect the common characteristics of the component groups of infractions, similar to the Criminal Code in force: "Infractions against the Public Interest".

¹⁹ Ioan Lascu, Laura Codruț Lascu, *O nouă reglementare în legătură cu infracțiunile de corupție*, in "Dreptul", no. 10, 2000, pp. 3-13.

²⁰ George Antoniu, *Observații cu privire la anteproiectul unui al doilea nou Cod penal*, in "Revista de Drept Penal", no. 1, 2008, p. 26.

Firstly, the crime of conflict of interests is considered to be a violation of a professional obligation and not as a form of corruption and secondly, the criminalization of abuse of function (Art. 292 of the project)²¹ proposed by the Project of the New Criminal Code has been dropped. Thus, we consider the solution proposed by this normative act to be reproachable under this aspect.

More so, the crime of receiving undue benefits is not only considered as a corruption infraction but it is decriminalized. We consider this position of the legislator to be a clear regression compared to the regulations in previous Criminal Codes. Foreign legislation has proceeded in criminalizing receipt of undue benefits in recent years, yet the new Criminal Code omits a crime which could have a well-established role. This way the act of taking bribe can be perpetrated before and after the action performed by the public functionary. The more reduced social danger of receiving undue benefits shall be appreciated by the courts by judicially individualizing the punishment in the new Criminal Code.

In *Chapter I*, in establishing the contents of corruption infractions, the current regulations in the Criminal Code in force on the one hand, and the provisions in Law no. 78/2000 with ulterior modifications and completions, including the ones by Law no. 161/2003, on the other hand were taken into account, without producing any significant substantial changes.

Bribe taking is criminalized in a typical form, with content similar to the one enshrined in the Criminal Code in force.

In its basic form, an element of the subjective side in the Criminal Code in force which imposes the active demeanor of the functionary in rejecting the promises made by the briber has been dropped.

Bribe taking when the perpetrator is holding a function in the public interest is incriminated in a separate paragraph, but only when committed with the aim of not fulfilling or delaying the fulfillment of an act regarding his legal duties or with the scope of not fulfilling an act contrary to those duties. By this disposition, the controversial problem of whether the

²¹ The abuse of function which cannot be found within the corruption infractions (Art. 292 of the project): "(paragraph 1) The act of a functionary of using his influence and authority in order to obtain for himself or for another an undue benefit is punished with a prison sentence of one to five years. (paragraph 2) If the act was perpetrated by a person who hold a leading position in a political party, syndicate or employer organisation or a non-profit legal person, the prison sentence ranges from 6 months to 3 years. (paragraph 3) Money, values and any other goods received are to be confiscated, according to art. 112".

public notaries, court enforcement officers or other persons holding functions in the public interest can be the authors of bribe taking.

In order to better realize general prevention, the criminalizing norm of bribe taking included the subsidiary punishment of being stripped of the right of holding a public function or exercising the profession or activity in connection of which the bribe was taken.

The crime of buying influence was included into the Code from Law no. 78/2000 with ulterior modifications and completions through Law no. 161/2003 in which the mandatory application of the subsidiary punishment of forbidding the exercising of some rights was stipulated.

In the end, the chapter includes a general text (Art. 294) from Law no. 78/2000 with modifications and completions according to which the regulations included in the 'Corruption Infractions' chapter are to be applied accordingly to acts of corruption perpetrated by foreign public officials or in connection to their activity.

Furthermore, following Romania's ratification of the Additional Protocol to the European Council's Criminal Law Convention on Corruption (Law no. 260/2004), the framework of corruption infractions has been extended to acts of taking and giving of bribes committed by persons involved in litigation by way of domestic or international arbitration. (Art. 2-4 of the Protocol).

Bribe taking (art. 288 of the Project of the new Criminal Code) is «(paragraph 1) The Act of a public functionary who, directly or indirectly, for himself or for a third party, requests or receives money or other undue benefits or accepts the promises of such benefits in connection with exercising, omitting or delaying the fulfillment of an act pertaining o his professional and legal duties or in connection with fulfilling an act contrary to such duties is punishable with a prison sentence of 2 to 7 years and forbidding the exercising of the right to occupy a public function or to exercise the profession or activity in the execution of which the act was committed.

Taking bribery (Art.288 of the draft of the new Criminal Code) consists of»(paragraph. 1) The deed of a public official, that, directly or indirectly, for himself or another, claims or receives money or other benefits that are not due to him, or accepts the promise of such benefits, in connection with the performance, the refrain or the delay of an act falling within its office duties or in connection with the performance of an act contrary to these duties, shall be punished with the

imprisonment for 2 to 7 years and the prohibition of the right to exercise a public function or of exercising the profession or the activity in which the deed was performed.

(Paragraph 2) The action referred to in paragraph (1) committed by a person shown in Art. 175 paragraph (2) is an offense only when committed in connection with the refrain, the delay or the fulfillment of an act regarding its legal office duties or in connection with the performance of an act contrary to these duties.

(paragraph 3) The money, the values or any other goods received will be confiscated and if they are no longer available, the confiscation by equivalent will be ordered”²².

Offences of corruption and of duty committed by other persons:

“(1) The provisions of art. 289-292 and of Art. 297-301 relating to civil servants apply properly to offenses committed by persons or in connection with persons who exercise temporarily or permanently, with or without retribution, a duty of any kind in the service of a natural person from those set out in Art. 175 paragraph (2), or within any legal entity.

2) In this case, the special limits of punishment are reduced by one third”²³.

Giving bribery (Art. 289) consists of

“(1) Promising, offering or giving money or other benefits, in the conditions set out in Art. 289, shall be punished with the imprisonment for 2 to 7 years”²⁴.

(2) The deed referred to in paragraph (1) is not an offence when the briber was coerced by any means by the one who took the bribe.

(3) The briber will not be punished if he denounces the deed before the prosecuting authority has been notified about it.

(4) The money, the values or any other goods given will be returned to the person who gave them, if they were given in the case referred to in paragraph (2) or given after the denunciation from paragraph (3).

The money, the values or any other goods offered or given will be confiscated and if they are no longer available, the confiscation by equivalent will be ordered”.

²² As in the form proposed in the project “The money, values or any other goods received”.

²³ As in the form proposed in the project (paragraph 3) If the deed stipulated at paragraph 1 was committed by another person than those set out in Art.175, the special limits of punishment are reduced by half.

²⁴ As in the form proposed in the project the offence was punished in lower limits from one to five years.

(5) The money, values or any other goods offered or data are subject to forfeiture, and when they are no longer available, the confiscation by equivalent.

Trading influence (Art. 290) consists of”(paragraph 1) Claiming, receiving or accepting the promise of money or other benefits, directly or indirectly, for himself or another, committed by a person who has influence or makes others believe that he has influence over a public official and promises that he will cause him to perform, to refrain, to hasten or to delay the execution of an act connected to his office duties or to perform an act contrary to these duties, shall be punished with the imprisonment for 2 to 7 years²⁵.

(paragraph 2) If the offense was committed in connection with a person other than those set out in art. 175, the special limits of punishment are reduced by half.

(paragraph 3) The money, the values or any other goods received will be confiscated, according to Art.112”

Buying influence (Art. 291) consists of: “(paragraph1) Promising, offering or giving money or other benefits, directly or indirectly, to a person having influence or that made others believe that he has influence over a public official in order to determine him to perform, not perform an act or to delay the performance of an act regarding its office duties or to perform an act contrary to these duties, shall be punished by imprisonment for one to five years and the prohibition of the exercise of some rights.

(2) The money, the values or any other goods received will be confiscated and if they are no longer available, the confiscation by equivalent will be ordered”.

Acts committed by members of arbitration courts, or in connection with them (Art. 293): “The provisions of art. 288 and 289 shall apply accordingly to persons who, on the basis of an arbitration agreement, are called to issue a decision upon a dispute that is given to them by the parties to this agreement, regardless if the arbitration proceedings shall be conducted under the Romanian law or on the basis of other laws.

Acts committed by foreign officials or related to them (Art. 294) “The provisions of this chapter shall apply, accordingly, to:

²⁵ In the draft version of the criminal cod project the offence was punished milder, from one to five years, and the objective side is completed through the possibility of “the hastening” that was not found in the project.

- a) officials or persons acting under a contract of employment or to other persons exercising similar functions within a public international organization to which Romania is party;
- b) Members of parliamentary assemblies of international organizations to which Romania is party;
- c) Officials or persons acting under a contract of employment or to other persons exercising similar functions within the European Communities;
- d) Persons exercising judicial functions in the international courts whose jurisdiction is accepted by Romania, and officials from the *office of the clerk* of these courts;
- e) Officials of a foreign state;
- f) Members of parliamentary or administrative assemblies of a foreign state”.

PRIMA CRISI D'ORIENTE: IL CONFRONTO NAVALE NEL MAR NERO

Antonello Battaglia*

Abstract

The Crimean War is the first international conflict following the Napoleonic Wars and it's the first crisis of the Continental order established in Vienna (1814-1815). The War opposed the Tsarist Empire which, under the pretext of defending the Orthodox Ottoman subjects, wants to disrupt the geopolitical order in the Eastern Europe gaining control over Bosphorus and Dardanelles, in order to have a coastal outlet in the Mediterranean Sea and fits in the main European trade routes to Ottoman Empire, and the coalition of Great Britain, France, the Habsburg Empire and the Kingdom of Sardinia, which want to maintain the status quo. In this war, a very strategic area is the Black Sea, which is the main theatre of the battles. Supremacy in this area soon becomes the key to victory in the conflict.

Keywords: *Crimean War, Tsarist Empire, Ottoman Empire, Dardanelles, Bosphorus, Black Sea*

“Origine ben presto dimenticata. Sebastopoli con i suoi traffici commerciali, il suo grano, e non Gerusalemme, era il centro della contesa... e così il teatro della guerra si spostò rapidamente là dove gli interessi europei si sentivano maggiormente minacciati”¹.

La prima Crisi d'Oriente ebbe origini geografiche e temporali molto distanti dal periodo preso in questione. Infatti agli albori la *querelle*, da un punto di vista meramente formale, scoppiò nella regione mediorientale, in Terra Santa, mentre le coordinate temporali risalgono alla metà XVIII secolo².

I privilegi relativi alla protezione dei cristiano-latini, accordati a Francesco I di Valois nel XVI secolo e rinnovati nel 1740, erano stati ulteriormente confermati nel Trattato di Kuciuk Kainargi del 1774³. In virtù di tale intesa il regno di Francia aveva ottenuto il diritto di tutela degli stanziamenti religiosi latini della Terra Santa, nonché il diritto di sorveglianza dei luoghi di pellegrinaggio della regione palestinese. Alla fine del XVIII secolo, a causa della crisi

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¹ Francesco Dante, *I cattolici e la Guerra di Crimea*, Cosenza- Roma, Periferia, 2005, p. 230.

² Luc Monnier, *Études sur les origines de la guerre de Crimée*, Librairie Droz, Genova, 1977.

³ *Ibidem*, p.33.

rivoluzionaria transalpina che non aveva permesso un impegno assiduo nell'amministrare e nell'esercitare tale prerogative, erano stati ridimensionati i privilegi della confessione latina e contestualmente ampliati i diritti dell'Impero russo, protettore per antonomasia dei cristiano-ortodossi. Il mutamento degli equilibri mediorientali aveva permesso allo zar di rivendicare nuovi diritti. Il pretesto fu l'aumento esponenziale dei pellegrinaggi ortodossi in Terra Santa. "Gli affronti tra cattolici e ortodossi, originati spesso da futili motivazioni, erano sfociati in diversi episodi di scontri violenti all'interno degli stessi santuari"⁴.

Nel XIX secolo a complicare ulteriormente la situazione fu il sultano ottomano Abdul Mejid I che, temendo ritorsioni da ambedue i contendenti, decise di accordare i medesimi diritti a entrambe le parti e tale condotta inasprì il livello dello scontro⁵.

La politica internazionale russa, mirante a dare massima rilevanza alla grave "questione dei luoghi Santi", era finalizzata al raggiungimento dello scontro - dapprima diplomatico, poi militare - con l'Impero ottomano, ma dietro il pretesto religioso si celava il reale obiettivo di Nicola I di espandere il territorio dell'Impero verso gli agognati Stretti del Bosforo e dei Dardanelli. La conquista di quest'area strategica divenne di fondamentale importanza. Il territorio sotto dominio russo era molto esteso ma tuttavia privo di porti su mari "caldi" che ne permettessero l'inserimento nelle tratte commerciali principali. Gli unici sbocchi erano Arcangelo, Odessa, San Pietroburgo e Riga⁶, alcuni dei quali ghiacciati per buona parte dell'anno, dunque poco utilizzabili e quindi di scarsa rilevanza strategica. L'eventuale conquista della zona a ridosso degli Stretti avrebbe permesso alla Russia di penetrare all'interno dei traffici mediterranei provocando la cesura della via delle Indie britannica e avrebbe garantito *l'escalation* commerciale russa.

⁴ Antonello Battaglia, *Crisi d'Oriente (1853-1856): le implicazioni del Regno di Sardegna e della Santa Sede*, in "Eurostudium", aprile-giugno, II, 2008, disponibile all'indirizzo internet:

<http://www.eurostudium.uniroma1.it/rivista/studi%20ricerche/numero%207/battaglia.pdf> (ultimo accesso 10/12/2011).

⁵ Il negoziatore francese La Vallette, l'8 febbraio 1852, ottenne dal sultano degli importanti privilegi: le chiavi della Chiesa di Betlemme e il diritto di officiare nella tomba della Vergine. Al ritorno a Parigi, La Vallette annunciò il risultato come un prestigioso trionfo sulla Russia e sugli ortodossi. Lo zar, a conoscenza dell'accaduto, inviò il proprio esponente Titov che, intimidendo il sovrano, riuscì ad ottenere la revoca dei privilegi appena concessi alla Francia. A Parigi l'irritazione fu notevole. Cfr. "La Civiltà Cattolica", 1, 1853, p. 106.

⁶ Neal Ascherson, *Mar Nero. Storie e miti del Mediterraneo d'Oriente*, Torino, Einaudi, 1999, p. 141.

La medesima strategia sarebbe stata fondamentale per il conseguimento di un ulteriore obiettivo: permettere di aprire la strada verso la penisola balcanica, favorendo l'eventuale inglobamento dei popoli di etnia slava in linea con i principi panslavisti e slavofili che da sempre avevano innalzato la Russia a madrepatria di tali popoli.

La direttrice d'espansione russa mirava dunque allo smantellamento dei territori dell'Impero ottomano, mentre gli interessi britannici erano concentrati sul mantenimento della propria *leadership* mondiale e dello *status quo* continentale. Da questo punto di vista il Mar Nero costituiva una zona strategica di grande importanza poiché il suo controllo avrebbe permesso di dominare in maniera incontrastata le sorti del conflitto. La neutralizzazione della flotta turca da parte della Russia divenne dunque un obiettivo di primaria importanza, mentre le potenze europee, conscie della valenza strategica del Mar Nero, decisero di organizzare l'invio delle proprie navi al fine di monitorare le acque ed evitare che lo zar potesse prendere il sopravvento. Nell'inverno del 1853, gli iniziali movimenti delle imbarcazioni di Nicola I costituirono i prodromi di un conflitto che sarebbe stato dichiarato ufficialmente l'anno successivo, il 27 marzo 1854, e che sarebbe divampato ulteriormente dopo la ratifica dell'alleanza delle potenze occidentali con la Turchia⁷, con la quale Francia e Inghilterra - *in primis* - avrebbero pianificato il blocco e l'assedio di Sebastopoli, principale base navale russa, proprio allo scopo di ridurre la potenza marittima dello zar e ottenere il controllo del bacino del Mar Nero, chiave di volta del conflitto.

Il 29 febbraio 1853 Nicola I inviò il generale Aleksandr Danilovič Menscikov⁸ a Costantinopoli, presso la corte del sultano, ma l'emissario ignorò volutamente la visita di protocollo al ministro degli Esteri turco Fuad Effendi⁹ e si recò al cospetto del sovrano in semplici abiti borghesi violando appositamente il rigoroso cerimoniale della diplomazia internazionale. La missione Menscikov ebbe il premeditato obiettivo di presentare condizioni inaccettabili alla Sublime Porta per creare, a priori, un alibi che giustificasse l'imminente dichiarazione di guerra. Lo zar richiese che venisse confermato

⁷ Franco Valsecchi, *L'unificazione italiana e la politica europea dalla Guerra di Crimea alla Guerra di Lombardia. 1854-1859*, Milano, Istituto per gli studi di politica internazionale, 1939, p. 109.

⁸ Ministro della Marina, esponente del Partito Conservatore russo, fu nominato generale durante la Guerra di Crimea. Intimo amico di Nicola I e suo uomo di fiducia, ne influenzò la politica.

⁹ Il ministro, invisato a San Pietroburgo, fu costretto a dimettersi e venne sostituito da un nuovo ministro filo-russo, Rifaat Pascià.

il riconoscimento della protezione di tutti i sudditi ortodossi dell'Impero ottomano e inoltre pretese di ottenere il diritto di *placet* sull'elezione del patriarca di Costantinopoli, da sempre prerogativa del sovrano turco¹⁰. In altre parole, come riconosce Antonello Biagini: “se il sultano avesse aderito completamente alle richieste russe, avrebbe ceduto i propri diritti sovrani su tre quarti della Turchia europea, mettendo una forte ipoteca sull'esistenza stessa dell'Impero ottomano”¹¹.

Altro scopo della visita del generale russo era confermare gli studi di fattibilità relativi alla possibilità di attaccare Costantinopoli via mare: “Le cose erano assai più innanzi di quanto il buon generale-diplomatico non supponesse. Lo zar aveva già preso le sue disposizioni per un attacco a Costantinopoli e a Gallipoli, via mare... In realtà, con tutti quegli ufficiali di terra e di mare, essa era anche missione militare, oltre che diplomatica: aveva il compito di assodare se e da qual parte la capitale turca potesse venire attaccata dal mare”¹². Bisogna puntualizzare che prima di recarsi a Costantinopoli, l'ambasciatore russo visitò la flotta ormeggiata al porto di Odessa. I segnali furono chiari: la determinazione dello zar si sarebbe spinta fino allo scontro armato qualora non fossero state accettate le sue richieste.

Dopo una lunga fase di stallo diplomatico, la marina britannica, a due settimane dal Consiglio che avrebbe deciso definitivamente la strategia politica da adottare, diede l'ordine a una propria squadra di spostarsi a ridosso della baia di Besikta, a sud dei Dardanelli. Dopo qualche giorno fu raggiunta dalla squadra francese, rimasta fino ad allora a Salamina¹³. “Le truppe russe occuperanno i principati danubiani”, annunciò il cancelliere Nesselrode; “è un pegno di cui vogliamo impadronirci, non una guerra che vogliamo incominciare”¹⁴.

Negli ultimi giorni della primavera del 1853, erano molti i segnali che facevano intuire il precipitare della grave situazione: parecchie navi da guerra turche incrociavano il Mar Nero per far scorta di carbone a Eraclea. Il 4 e 5 giugno due navi a vapore della compagnia ottomana, la *Medaci-Tigiaret* e la

¹⁰ Francesco Dante, *op. cit.*, p. 36.

¹¹ Antonello Biagini, *La Crisi d'Oriente del 1853-56 e del 1875-78, nel commento de "La Civiltà Cattolica"*, in “Annali della Facoltà di Scienze Politiche”, XI, vol. I, 1970, p. 205.

¹² Franco Valsecchi, *L'alleanza di Crimea. L'Europa e il Risorgimento*, Firenze, Vallecchi, 1968, p. 231.

¹³ *Ibidem*, p. 249.

¹⁴ *Circolare di Nesselrode ai rappresentanti russi presso le Corti europee*, 2 luglio 1853 cit. in Abdolonyme Ubicini, Emile Girardin, *La Questione d'Oriente innanzi all'Europa*, Milano, Ufficio del Cosmorama Pittorico, 1855, p. 71.

Vapitanci-Tigiaret, si diressero verso gli Stretti per imbarcare truppe, facendo ritorno il 6 e il 7 a Costantinopoli per poi proseguire per Varna, dopo aver imbarcato più di 2.000 uomini. Durante tutta la settimana successiva l'attività divenne frenetica: il 6 giunse nella capitale, proveniente dal Pireo, la fregata americana *Cumberland*, munita di 50 cannoni. A bordo c'era il comandante in capo delle forze navali degli Stati Uniti nel Mediterraneo: l'approssimarsi del conflitto si accompagnava a una progressiva internazionalizzazione. Tre giorni dopo tutta la delegazione americana fu ricevuta dal Gran Vizir Giritli Mustafa Naili Pascià.

Il 7 giugno la fregata a vapore *Foizi-Babri* trasportò munizioni nel Mar Nero, mentre contestualmente fu dato l'ordine di spostare truppe da Adrianopoli a Varna. L'8 la nave da guerra *Taif* partì per l'Albania, da dove prelevò truppe per Costantinopoli. L'11 giugno alti ufficiali del genio partirono per Silistria con il direttore della Scuola militare e vari ufficiali superiori francesi addetti alla scuola. Il 14 due navi da guerra partirono per Varna per trasportare altre truppe e armi. Alla fine del mese l'Impero ottomano aveva schierato in Silistria 150.000 uomini¹⁵.

Lo spostamento repentino di truppe in un arco di tempo relativamente breve fu garantito dall'utilizzo della flotta, poiché lo sfruttamento delle rotte del Mar Nero permetteva il trasporto di uomini e mezzi da una sponda all'altra con una tempistica certamente inferiore rispetto agli spostamenti effettuati via terra. Il mare era presto divenuto una frontiera divisa in due settori: quello settentrionale e orientale russo, e quello meridionale e occidentale ottomano; per tale motivo il predominio dell'area marittima divenne ben presto di primaria importanza per la riuscita delle operazioni militari, anche perché geograficamente il bacino si trovava proprio nel cuore dello scenario bellico.

Il 3 luglio l'armata russa varcò il Prut e l'esercito turco si ritirò senza opporre resistenza. Non si trattava ancora di una guerra guerreggiata, non era stata ufficialmente dichiarata, ma l'equilibrio continentale era stato definitivamente compromesso. Invano la diplomazia continentale si prodigò al fine di scongiurare lo scontro armato; a Vienna i rappresentanti delle grandi potenze riuniti in conferenze vararono una "nota" che cercava di ristabilire l'equilibrio tra le parti opposte. Gli sforzi delle cancellerie ebbero il solo effetto di ritardare la crisi bellica: ai primi di ottobre il generale ottomano Omar Pascià intimò al

¹⁵ Francesco Dante, *op. cit.*, pp. 52-53.

comandante russo il ritiro immediato dai territori turchi invasi. Il rifiuto russo rese inevitabile lo scoppio del conflitto e le potenze britannica e francese decisero di spostare la propria flotta dalla baia di Besikta, oltrepassando i Dardanelli, verso il Mar di Marmara per ormeggiare nel Bosforo.

A Vienna furono ripresi gli sforzi al fine di salvare *in extremis* la pace continentale imperturbata dalle guerre napoleoniche: il 5 dicembre venne elaborata una nuova nota in cui le potenze esprimevano “voto di contribuire al ristabilimento della pace, con un intervento amichevole volto al riavvicinamento dei contendenti”¹⁶, ma gli sforzi diplomatici tentati *in primis* da Francesco Giuseppe non prendevano in considerazione il realistico scenario che ormai si prospettava in Oriente. Alla fine di novembre, infatti, la squadra ottomana composta da sette fregate a vela (*Avni Illah* - 44 cannoni, *Fazl Illah* - 44 cannoni che in precedenza era stata la russa *Rafail*, catturata nel 1829, *Nizamieh* - 62 cannoni, *Nessin Zafer* - 60 cannoni, *Navek Bahri* - 58 cannoni, *Damiat* - 56 cannoni, *Kaid Zafer* - 54 cannoni) tre corvette a vela (*Nejm Fishan* - 24 cannoni, *Eyz Mabud* - 24 cannoni, *Kel Safid* - 22 cannoni) e due fregate a vapore (*Taif* - 12 cannoni, *Erkelye* - 10 cannoni), per un totale di 4.200 uomini, sotto il comando di Osman Pascià, lasciò il Bosforo inoltrandosi nel Mar Nero con l’obiettivo di portare provvigioni e rinforzi alla guarnigione di Batum - dove erano in corso scontri non particolarmente rilevanti - ma il cattivo tempo la bloccò nella rada di Sinope, antico porto militare che nel mese di dicembre ospitava 21 cannoni disposti su quattro batterie. Le navi russe intercettarono la squadra ottomana e la flotta zarista composta da sei navi di linea (*Veliky Knyaz Kostantin* - 120 cannoni, *Tri Sviatitelia* - 120 cannoni, *Parizh* - 120 cannoni, *Imperatriitsa Maria* - 84 cannoni, *Chesma* - 84 cannoni, *Rostislav* - 84 cannoni), due fregate (*Kulevtcha* - 54 cannoni, *Kagul* - 44 cannoni) e tre vapori (*Odessa* - 4 cannoni, *Krym* - 4 cannoni, *Khersones* - 4 cannoni), guidata dall’ammiraglio Nakhimov¹⁷, apparve in vista di Sinope il 27 novembre e tre giorni dopo, nella mattinata del 30, tutta la squadra russa entrava nella baia. Con una manovra repentina la flotta russa circondò le forze ottomane e improvvisamente venne issata la bandiera che intimava la resa. Osman Pascià a quel punto decise di provare a rompere l’accerchiamento e a disporsi a largo in modo da prendere la flotta russa tra due fuochi, ma non venne compreso dai comandanti delle altre navi

¹⁶ Cfr. il protocollo della conferenza in data 5 dicembre 1853, in “Nouveau Recueil des traités”, XV, p. 533.

¹⁷ Pavel Stepanovič Nachimov (Gorodok, 5 luglio 1802 – Sebastopoli, 12 luglio 1855).

che non assecondarono il movimento dell'ammiraglia. A quel punto, da solo con la propria nave, decise con una manovra azzardata di puntare contro la nave dell'ammiraglio russo provando a speronarne la fiancata, ma fu neutralizzato dal fuoco di altre due imbarcazioni russe: "Naviglio pesante, col quale le leggere navi turche non potevano stare a pari. Non fu una battaglia, fu un massacro. Quattro ore, quattromila uomini a fondo con le loro navi: un solo vapore scampato a portar notizia a Costantinopoli"¹⁸.

Le imbarcazioni russe, dotate di maggior potenza di fuoco, utilizzarono i proiettili esplosivi inventati alcuni anni prima dal generale francese Paixhans. Soltanto il *Taif* riuscì a fuggire e, inseguito dalla flotta russa, riuscì a raggiungere la capitale turca il 2 dicembre portando l'infausta notizia. I marinai turchi superstiti si lanciarono in mare e nonostante la flotta russa ne accogliesse molti sulle proprie imbarcazioni, le vittime furono circa 4.000. L'unico alto ufficiale a trarsi in salvo fu Osman Pascià, che venne fatto prigioniero, mentre il viceammiraglio morì annegato in un tentativo di fuga e un altro comandante, Ali Bey, dopo aver consegnato i marinai al nemico ed essersi assicurato di far conoscere la disfatta al sultano¹⁹, diede fuoco all'arsenale e saltò in aria con tutta la nave²⁰. Le batterie turche di Sinope aprirono il fuoco sulla flotta russa che reagì bombardando e incendiando buona parte della città.

L'11 dicembre, per telegrafo, via Vienna, la notizia raggiunse Londra e Parigi: "La lontana vicenda asiatica, all'eccitazione delle corrispondenze da Costantinopoli, si colorisce di patetici colori: la flotta turca che si inabissa, senza quasi potersi difendere, le migliaia di naufraghi nelle acque agitate, la città in fiamme, la popolazione in fuga sotto gli obici... Il massacro era avvenuto sotto gli occhi degli ammiragli delle due Potenze, in fazione sul Bosforo: il loro compito era di proteggere il territorio turco"²¹. "Il colpo vibrato a Sinope non colpisce soltanto la Turchia - scrisse Drouvn de Lhuvs a Castelbajac - il tempo delle parole e delle manifestazioni platoniche è finito. Ora è tempo di agire"²²

Nel gennaio del 1854 Napoleone III inviò una lettera allo zar, molto cordiale nella forma, ma dura nel rimproverare

¹⁸Franco Valsecchi, *L'alleanza di Crimea...*, cit., p. 257.

¹⁹ A tale scopo inviò una nave a Costantinopoli.

²⁰ Francesco Dante, *op. cit.*, p. 105.

²¹ Franco Valsecchi, *L'alleanza di Crimea...*, cit., p. 258.

²² Alfred Stern, *Geschichte Europas seit den Verträgen von 1815 bis zum Frankfurter Frieder von 1871*, Stuttgart-Berlin, J.G. Cotta'sche Buchhandlung Nachfolger, 1913-1923, p. 58.

l'attacco di Sinope ai danni della marina turca, soprattutto perché compiuto davanti alla flotta francese a largo del porto anatolico: "Malgrado la vicinanza del nostro naviglio - scriveva l'imperatore, fino a quel tempo semplice spettatore ma preannunciando un possibile cambiamento di atteggiamento - i vascelli russi con nostra sorpresa e rincrescimento andarono ad attaccare la flotta turca stanziata nel proprio porto di Sinope... Epperziò - attaccava l'imperatore - non solo la nostra politica, ma, che più conta, il nostro onore militare rimaneva sconfitto in quel doloroso avvenimento e i cannoni della battaglia di Sinope rimbombarono nel cuore di quanti, francesi o inglesi, sentono la dignità nazionale, ripetendo ciascuno seco stesso che, dovunque possono giungere le nostre artiglierie, ivi debbono essere rispettati i nostri alleati"²³.

Lo zar, nella sua risposta, utilizzò i medesimi toni formali dell'imperatore transalpino e sottolineò come l'attacco di Sinope non era stato la causa scatenante del conflitto, ma semplicemente una conseguenza inevitabile della politica occidentale ai danni dell'Impero russo: in particolare Nicola I rimproverava i precedenti arrivi della flotta inglese nei Dardanelli e di quella francese a Salamina, il che provava la vera diffidenza nei suoi confronti e l'incoraggiamento ai turchi di fare la guerra. Sinope era stata, dunque, la conseguenza dell'atteggiamento ostile di Francia e Inghilterra. Impedire, in seguito, l'accesso delle navi russe nel Mar Nero, non sarebbe stato certamente un atto di incoraggiamento alla pace: "Voi stesso, o Sire, - scriveva Nicola I con uno scatto di orgoglio - se foste in vece mia, accettereste voi tali proposte? Ve lo consentirebbe il vostro sentimento nazionale? lo rispondo arditamente che no. Concedete dunque a me il diritto di pensare come voi stesso. Checché decida V. M. io non indietreggerò per minacce"²⁴.

L'attacco di Sinope sancì il fallimento delle trattative di pace, pertanto i preparativi militari, già in atto da diverso tempo, furono velocizzati da parte di tutti i contendenti. Verso la metà di marzo partì alla volta del Baltico - considerato potenzialmente un ulteriore fronte - l'ammiraglio britannico Charles Napier²⁵, che affermava di non voler entrare in quel mare senza una dichiarazione formale di guerra nei confronti dell'Impero russo. Tra le indiscrezioni che circolavano nei concitati frangenti prebellici, pullularono false notizie tra le

²³ "La Civiltà Cattolica", 1854, VI, p. 114.

²⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 115.

²⁵ Sir Charles John Napier (6 marzo 1786 – 6 novembre 1860), ammiraglio della *Royal Navy*, comandò la flotta britannica nelle guerre napoleoniche, quelle di Siria e di Crimea.

quali quella che voleva l'ammiraglio inglese fermo all'ingresso del Golfo di Finlandia dopo aver attaccato e distrutto la fortezza di Gustassweren e aver catturato 1.500 russi. In realtà la notizia non fu confermata dalle fonti ufficiali, che lamentavano la difficoltà di contatto con la zona in questione, facendo ipotizzare la stasi delle operazioni a motivo dei ghiacci ancora persistenti che rendevano difficile la navigazione. In quei giorni il "Times" pubblicò il discorso di congedo dell'ammiraglio Napier: "So che si aspetta molto da questa flotta; non si aspetti troppo. Andiamo incontro al nemico comune, ad un nemico ben preparato. Son certo che ogni ufficiale, ogni marinaio del naviglio farà gloriosamente il suo dovere; tuttavia vi ripeto: non si aspetti troppo. Questa flotta è di nuova formazione: è nuovo il sistema di guerra che faremo e bisogna considerare assai per trovare il migliore partito che possa trarsi da una flotta a vapore"²⁶.

La flotta presente nella rada di Amburgo venne richiamata in Inghilterra per il rifornimento di armi e munizioni da trasferire nel Baltico, mentre una squadra francese composta da 23 bastimenti con 1.250 cannoni, guidata da Parceval Dechènes, si era mossa da Brest alla volta della Finlandia. Le forze anglo-francesi, forti di 70 navi, 30.000 uomini e 3.000 cannoni, si posizionarono all'imboccatura dei golfi di Botnia e di Finlandia per impedire l'uscita in mare del naviglio russo che in zona poteva contare su una forza 30 vascelli, 9 fregate e circa 34.000 uomini, di cui la maggior parte alloggiata nei porti di Revel e Kronstadt²⁷. In queste prime fasi la Russia decise di concentrare l'offensiva sul fronte danubiano, rallentando le operazioni sia sul Baltico che sul Mar Nero.

In Francia l'approssimarsi dello scontro era stato accolto con entusiasmo: i 238 membri del Parlamento votarono all'unanimità lo stanziamento di un prestito di 250 milioni di franchi per le spese di guerra. La legge venne riconfermata dal Senato, mentre il maresciallo Saint Arnaud²⁸ fu nominato capo dell'Esercito in Oriente e il principe Napoleone suo vice. Per quanto concerne la Sublime Porta, le forze rimaste in mare dopo il duro attacco subito a Sinope erano 51 navi a vela e 18 bastimenti a vapore, ma l'arrivo delle flotte alleate non

²⁶ In "La Civiltà Cattolica", 1854, VI, pp. 117-118.

²⁷ Francesco Dante, *op. cit.*, p. 113.

²⁸ Armand Jacques Achille Leroy de Saint-Arnaud (Parigi, 20 agosto 1801 - Mar Nero, 29 settembre 1854). Generale francese, Maresciallo di Francia dal 1852. Fu ministro della Guerra fino al conflitto di Crimea, quando fu nominato comandante in capo dell'esercito d'Oriente. Morì durante la campagna di Crimea a causa del colera il 26 settembre, a bordo della nave *Berthollet* diretta a Costantinopoli.

preoccupava il sultano ostinato, a non lasciar passo al nemico nel Mar Nero: “Tra le scaramucce di qualche importanza recentemente battagliate - scrive un cronista dell’epoca - è da registrare l’avvenuta or è un mese nelle vicinanze di Georgevo. Sedici barche di milizie musulmane ed albanesi dirigevansi verso Slobozia... quando, arrivate all’isola di Tcoroi e trovatala da una parte piena di russi, pigliando larga la volta vi si recarono sulla sponda opposta. Tre navi cannoniere e le batterie di Rutsuk protessero il maneggio dei turcheschi finché questi li ebbero avvertite rombando di essere pronte alla battaglia. Nello stesso tempo i cosacchi poterono gettare i ponti e trasmettere nell’isola altri due reggimenti di fanti... La zuffa durò cinque ore e colla peggio dei russi”²⁹.

Il 27 febbraio furono inviate allo zar le proposte delle potenze occidentali: il governo russo era invitato ad abbandonare entro il 30 aprile i Principati danubiani recentemente occupati. Il rifiuto o anche semplicemente una mancata risposta, sarebbero equivalsi all’apertura delle ostilità.

Il 13 marzo il messaggio arrivò a Pietroburgo, ma lo zar non diede alcuna risposta, ordinando al contrario alle sue truppe di riprendere l’avanzata in Dobrugia.

Il 27 marzo 1854 Francia e Inghilterra annunciarono la dichiarazione di guerra all’Impero zarista e il 10 aprile ratificarono la firma del trattato di alleanza in favore dell’Impero ottomano³⁰: “Non ci vengano a dire: che cosa andate a fare a Costantinopoli? Noi vi andiamo con l’Inghilterra per difendere la causa del sultano e nello stesso tempo proteggere i diritti dei cristiani. Noi vi andiamo per difendere la libertà dei mari e la nostra giusta influenza nel Mediterraneo... Noi vi andiamo infine con tutti coloro che vogliono il trionfo del buon diritto, della giustizia e della civiltà”³¹, si espresse l’imperatore Napoleone III.

Visti i nuovi venti di guerra, il 6 aprile la fregata inglese *Furious* giunse davanti al porto di Odessa per accogliere il personale diplomatico e i cittadini inglesi e francesi intenzionati a lasciare la città. Le imbarcazioni battevano bandiera parlamentare e quindi non sarebbero potute essere attaccate poiché l’inviolabilità era garantita dal diritto internazionale; invece furono oggetto di alcuni colpi di cannone che diedero avvio alla battaglia. Gli ammiragli alleati inviarono a Odessa otto fregate a vapore, cinque inglesi e tre francesi che il 22 aprile, alle sei di mattina, aprirono il fuoco contro la città fino

²⁹ In “La Civiltà Cattolica”, 1854, V, p. 707.

³⁰ Franco Valsecchi, *L’alleanza di Crimea...*, cit., p. 264.

³¹ *Ibidem*.

alle diciassette. Furono distrutti il palazzo del governatore generale, diverse batterie russe, una polveriera, che esplodendo danneggiò gravemente le strutture portuali e rese inagibile la zona militare del porto. Furono risparmiati, invece, la città e il porto mercantile³². Secondo le fonti russe, le batterie aprirono il fuoco contro l'imbarcazione inglese perché insospettite dalla lunga attesa di circa sei ore per il trasbordo dei passeggeri: ritenuto un atto di spionaggio relativo allo studio delle difese del porto, le batterie avevano deciso di reagire su ordine del sottotenente Séegotov³³.

Lo zar considerò positivo l'esito della battaglia per lo scarso numero di morti (quattro), per la rinuncia delle flotte nemiche al bombardamento della città e soprattutto perché nei pressi del porto di Odessa si era arenata una nave a vapore britannica, la *Tiger*, che era stata attaccata e saccheggiata dai russi nonostante la strenua difesa del capitano Giffard che, nel tentativo di contrastare i nemici, era caduto nello scontro³⁴.

Tra il 26 e il 27 agosto si presentarono nuovamente al largo di Odessa alcune imbarcazioni anglo-francesi, e il generale russo Kausenstern, temendo un imminente bombardamento seguito da uno sbarco in massa, il 30 agosto rese noto un proclama: "Perché non trovi ricovero il nemico, faremo la città un mucchio di rovine. Mal prenda a coloro i quali rimarranno indietro, o cercheranno di spegnere il fuoco"³⁵. Il proclama del generale, tuttavia, non ebbe seguito in quanto non si registrò alcun tentativo di sbarco da parte delle forze alleate.

A scontro inoltrato, dunque, gli sforzi militari si concentravano sempre più nel Mar Nero. Nonostante il Baltico fosse di grande importanza per ingaggiare le truppe russe anche sul fronte settentrionale, si decise di non dislocare cospicue forze navali in loco a causa della neutralità di Svezia e Prussia. Sul fronte balcanico l'Austria, determinata a imporre l'influenza sull'area, non avrebbe accettato l'ingresso degli eserciti di altre potenze, pertanto il Mar Nero, zona centrale tra l'Impero ottomano e quello russo, divenne in definitiva la soluzione maggiormente percorribile nel panorama europeo.

³² Francesco Dante, *op. cit.*, p. 137.

³³ Un proiettile si conficcò nel basamento della statua di Richelieu, dove si trova ancora oggi. Inoltre, un cannone della *Tiger* venne preso come trofeo e ancora oggi si trova alla fine del Primorskij bulvar, il maestoso viale che corre lungo la cresta delle scogliere e arriva fino in cima alla scalinata. Neal Ascherson, *op. cit.*, p. 143.

³⁴ Mariano D'Ayala, *I piemontesi in Crimea: narrazione storica*, Firenze, s.n., 1858, p. 20.

³⁵ *Ibidem*, p. 24.

Napoleone III si vantò della scelta della penisola di Crimea: “Semmai decideste di prendere la Crimea, sappiate l’origine dell’iniziativa non è vostra ma mia che già da tempo ho riconosciuto la sua importanza dal punto di vista strategico. La sua conquista è l’unico mezzo per portare un decisivo colpo alla Russia”³⁶.

Nell’estate del 1851 la squadra guidata dal contrammiraglio Brut, composta da 7.000 uomini, si preparava a sbarcare sulle coste della Crimea, mentre il 30 luglio il maresciallo Saint Arnaud allertò i propri uomini circa le difficoltà dell’imminente spedizione: “Noi stiamo per entrare nel territorio nemico. Malagevole è l’impresa cui ci accingiamo, giacché il nemico che andiamo ad incontrare è forte e numeroso... Noi entreremo nondimeno nel territorio nemico con ferma risoluzione di vincere: la nostra patria o non la rivedremo più, o la rivedremo da vincitori”³⁷.

La stampa del periodo dava pareri contrastanti: chi considerava certo l’attacco e la conquista della penisola, chi riteneva l’impresa ardua, chi un diversivo che avrebbe dovuto coprire il reale obiettivo che sarebbe stato Odessa e infine chi considerava il controllo del Mar Nero l’elemento essenziale per la risoluzione del conflitto.

L’Impero russo decise di rafforzare immediatamente il fronte della Crimea con l’arrivo di 7.000 uomini da Anapa, Rajevsji e Novorosijsk. L’ammiraglio russo stabilì di contrastare la potenza navale anglo-francese con azioni di assalto e sabotaggio e si cercò di dimostrare che, nonostante l’accerchiamento delle posizioni, le imbarcazioni sarebbero riuscite a uscire ugualmente dalla rada di Sebastopoli eludendo i controlli dei nemici.

Alla grossa fregata a vapore *Vladimiro* fu cambiato il nome in *Austerlitz*, *escamotage* che permise all’imbarcazione di uscire indisturbata senza incontrare alcuna resistenza. Una volta traversato il mare, bombardò e affondò diverse navi turche che trasportavano grano e approvvigionamenti militari. Dopo la prima scorreria, si diresse a Eraclea dove si sapeva ancorata la *Cyclops*, importante imbarcazione inglese che in quei giorni, trovandosi in acque sicure, aveva lasciato gran parte dei propri cannoni a Malta. La nave russa arrivò in ritardo e non riuscì a incrociare in tempo la *Cyclops*, ma ebbe comunque la possibilità di abbordare, saccheggiare - soprattutto facendo scorta di carbone - e affondare due imbarcazioni britanniche.

³⁶ In Alain Gouttman, *La guerre de Crimée, 1853-1856. La première guerre moderne*, Paris, Perrin, 1995, p. 127.

³⁷ In “La Civiltà Cattolica”, 1854, VII, p. 584.

Dopo l'azione militare, rientrò a Sebastopoli nuovamente indisturbata³⁸.

Oltre alla brillante sortita, il 4 agosto l'ammiraglio Nakimov riuscì a effettuare importanti spostamenti di imbarcazioni tra Odessa e Sebastopoli senza ingaggiare alcuno scontro con le forze anglo-francesi. In realtà, nonostante le dure critiche del "Times" e della stampa internazionale, le forze alleate non erano ancora confluite tutte in Crimea, ma erano ancora ferme a Baltchick, vicino Varna.

Lo spostamento, annunciato da tempo, iniziò il 5 settembre, quando la flotta francese si mosse da Varna e fu seguita, due giorni dopo, dal naviglio britannico proveniente da Baltchick, per un totale di 150 navi da guerra, di cui 80 a vapore, e un convoglio di altre 600 navi da carico. L'esercito era composto da 70.000 uomini, di cui 35.000 francesi, 25.000 inglesi e 10.000 turchi. La marina contava 25.000 effettivi, di cui 5.000 avrebbero fornito forza di completamento terrestre. Inoltre 5.000 cavalli, 80 cannoni con 1.000 colpi ciascuno, viveri e vettovagliamento sufficienti per due mesi. Uno sbarco notevole, come quello previsto, non si sarebbe potuto effettuare nell'arco di pochi giorni, pertanto molti consigliarono la fortificazione della zona da sbarco con il posizionamento di 15 navi da guerra all'ingresso del porto di Sebastopoli al fine di fornire copertura all'azione di sbarco. L'8 settembre un'*équipe* composta da ufficiali di esercito e marina effettuò l'analisi delle coste e lo studio di fattibilità ispezionando la costa in prossimità di Sebastopoli, da Capo Chersoneso fino a Eupatoria. Due giorni dopo quattro imbarcazioni controllarono ulteriormente la zona rilevando l'assenza di ulteriori postazioni militari tra Capo Chersoneso e Capo Lunul, mentre nuovi campi militari e artiglierie erano stati posti sulle rive della Katcha e dell'Alma, dove fu stimata la presenza di 35.000 russi. Il luogo più adatto alle esigenze di sbarco fu individuato nel tratto compreso tra il fiume Alma ed Eupatoria poiché, per la sua particolare geomorfia, avrebbe fornito una copertura naturale alle eventuali sortite nemiche.

Negli studi di pianificazione militare si decise che, dopo l'iniziale sbarco nei pressi di Eupatoria, si sarebbe marciato in direzione sud, verso Sebastopoli, procedendo lungo la riva, appoggiati nell'avanzata da 15 navi che avrebbero coperto il fianco. Prima di avvicinarsi a Sebastopoli si stabilì di raggiungere in marcia Balaklava per conquistarne dall'interno il porto, in modo da permettere l'arrivo e l'attracco sicuro delle

³⁸ Francesco Dante, *op. cit.*, p. 162.

navi che avrebbero potuto sbarcare ulteriori rinforzi e vettovagliamento. Il 13 settembre, dopo due notti di mare burrascoso, la flotta alleata arrivò a Eupatoria e il giorno successivo si spostò al Vecchio Forte, a circa sette miglia da Sebastopoli³⁹.

Il mattino, verso le ore otto, iniziarono le operazioni di sbarco e alle ore dodici erano sbarcati 18 cannoni e 8 divisioni. La notte seguente giunse da Katcha la 4^a divisione dopo aver attuato un diversivo per disorientare il nemico sulla strategia di sbarco. La marcia su Balaklava si rivelò più difficile del previsto a causa delle impervie condizioni geografiche: durante l'avanzata ci si imbatté in una boscaglia, la strada maestra fu lasciata per ragioni di sicurezza all'artiglieria e alla cavalleria, mentre la fanteria si addentrò cercando di aprire nuovi varchi, ma all'uscita si scontrò con un drappello di russi che nonostante l'attacco a sorpresa, fu costretto alla ritirata dopo aver perso diversi uomini catturati dagli inglesi. Il 26 settembre la guarnigione alleata arrivò nella poco difesa Balaklava, che si arrese dopo qualche colpo di cannone.

La conquista di questo porto fu strategicamente importante in quanto, situato a poche miglia da Sebastopoli accerchiata dalle flotte alleate, avrebbe permesso alle imbarcazioni di navigare in tutta sicurezza nelle acque del Mar Nero e approdare direttamente nel Chersoneso sbarcando, indisturbate, i propri uomini in prossimità di Sebastopoli. "Partite il 9 settembre dall'isola de' Serpenti tutte le forze marittime, andati avanti il Canrobert e i generali delle artiglierie e degli ingegneri a fare l'ultima ricognizione dello sbarco, avevano il 13 già valicati 400 e più chilometri di mare; ed il naviglio nemico, evitando ogni scontro, lasciava che si compiesse un'impresa, della quale era stato senza mistero annunciato il giorno della partenza e quello dell'arrivo. Le squadre, buttata l'ancora in tre linee, stando nella prima i vascelli di combattimento, calarono in mare barche, palischermi e schifi per isbarcare a Castelvechio, in inglese Old-fort, 50 a 60 chilometri sopra Sebastopoli... E tutto questo a 900 leghe di distanza, formando una città sulle acque ed una popolazione. Dopo quattro giorni dallo sbarco incontrastato, si fu al punto di muovere lungo il mare, protetti a destra dalle squadre per dar battaglia sul terreno che il nemico medesimo aveva scelto. La quale battaglia avvenne il giorno appresso, 20 di settembre 1854, sulle rive dell'Alma"⁴⁰.

³⁹ *Ibidem*, p. 166.

⁴⁰ Mariano D'Ayala, *op. cit.*, p. 24.

Davanti a una situazione di progressivo accerchiamento marittimo i russi decisero di attuare una strategia singolare che, come si evince dalle pagine del "Times", stupì il comando alleato: il 23 settembre, all'imbocco del porto di Sebastopoli, furono affondati dalle batterie russe alcuni bastimenti della marina zarista proprio per costituire intralcio e sbarramento e impedire che le imbarcazioni nemiche tentassero di penetrare all'interno del porto. Il segretario dell'ammiraglio inglese scriveva così, a proposito dell'espedito russo: "All'apparire delle flotte dinanzi Sebastopoli, tutti i vascelli russi che erano all'ancora davanti al porto, sono stati calati a fondo, rimanendo però i loro alberi più o meno fuori dell'acqua: io mi recai ieri sera alla bocca del porto per vedere questo singolare avvenimento. Il capitano Drummont esaminò questa mattina il porto e dice che la punta degli alberi è generalmente sopra l'acqua, che il passo è chiuso, eccetto forse uno stretto passaggio presso il baso fondo in vista della batteria del nord. Otto vascelli di linea sono ancorati ad est e ad ovest dietro le sbarre palizzate, dei quali tre sono molto chinati di costa per innalzare i loro cannoni che possano colpire a terra verso il Nord"⁴¹.

La marina britannica provò a inviare all'interno del porto piccole imbarcazioni con carichi esplosivi da applicare ai vascelli semi-affondati che ostruivano il passaggio, ma l'esito dell'operazione non fu dei migliori. Data l'impossibilità di una penetrazione efficace a ridosso di Sebastopoli e visto l'andamento degli scontri militari terrestri, l'accerchiamento del porto si prospettò un'operazione che sarebbe durata per diversi mesi. Tale possibilità preoccupò gli ammiragli a causa della prossimità della stagione invernale, non tanto per il ghiaccio, poiché non c'era il timore che le acque del Mar Nero congelassero, quanto soprattutto per le numerose tempeste che iniziavano a mettere in difficoltà le imbarcazioni: nei pressi del canale di Costantinopoli affondò, nel mese di ottobre la nave ammiraglia egiziana e un vapore con 300 malati a bordo.

La guerra continuava anche se con pochi spostamenti di fronte, mentre molto più attiva si dimostrava la diplomazia europea che cercava di coinvolgere ulteriormente nuovi protagonisti all'interno dell'alleanza antirussa. Già all'inizio della primavera del 1854 si era dato avvio ai contatti e alle trattative per un'eventuale alleanza con la potenza austriaca per scongiurare la minaccia di un paventato ingresso in guerra di Vienna a fianco di Nicola I e per aprire un altro fronte che avrebbe impegnato lo zar anche a occidente del proprio impero.

⁴¹ In Francesco Dante, *op. cit.*, p. 170.

Non solo la forza militare quindi, ma anche l'ubicazione geografica dell'Impero asburgico sarebbe stata strategica in uno scenario di guerra nell'estremo levante europeo. La politica di Napoleone III pertanto aveva mirato innanzitutto a guadagnarsi la fiducia e l'appoggio austriaci, in secondo luogo l'imperatore aveva cercato di non alienarsi l'eventuale intervento piemontese.

L'obiettivo principale era ovviamente quello di coinvolgere l'indecisa Vienna, che ai prodromi del conflitto si trovava in un'*empasse* notevole poiché era reduce dalle cruenti rivolte del 1848 che avevano minato profondamente le basi dell'Impero. Tuttavia era riuscita a uscirne indenne, seppure grazie all'intervento provvidenziale delle truppe inviate dallo zar. Il riconoscimento del salvifico intervento aveva permesso di consolidare ulteriormente i rapporti tra le due potenze e aveva rinvigorito l'antica Santa Alleanza. Proprio questo aiuto dello zar era divenuto, alle porte della guerra di Crimea, il motivo principale dell'imbarazzo austriaco, in quanto Francesco Giuseppe si sentiva costretto a ricambiare il favore mostrando fedeltà e riconoscenza, il che avrebbe comportato l'obbligo morale di intervenire in difesa della causa russa. Il *do ut des* era considerato ovvio e l'appoggio ormai preteso da Nicola I, che dava per certo il sostegno dell'aquila bifronte. La posizione austriaca tuttavia non era assolutamente decisa, né certa: da una parte c'era la necessità di onorare l'impegno e il debito contratto con Pietroburgo, dall'altra l'incompatibilità di tale decisione con le strategie internazionali di Vienna, ormai da qualche anno palesemente in contrasto con gli interessi russi⁴². "Di qui una politica che non riesce a prendere posizione e cerca di stare in bilico fra i contendenti, e si illude di potere, mantenendo una neutralità vigilante ed armata, essere al momento opportuno il fattore decisivo, l'arbitro della situazione. Era la politica di minore responsabilità... ma non di minore pericolo, a cominciare da quello, proprio di tutti i neutri, di essere a Dio spiacenti ed ai nemici suoi, di alienarsi la Russia

⁴² Soprattutto relativamente ai confini orientali dell'Impero austriaco, in quanto Francesco Giuseppe temeva che la costante crescita dell'influenza russa avrebbe potuto sottrarre l'area al controllo asburgico. Quindi l'intervento di Vienna a favore di Pietroburgo sarebbe andato contro gli interessi austriaci ridimensionando l'influenza sull'area danubiano-balcanica, sarebbe stata un'ammissione palese della superiorità russa, avrebbe comportato l'ammissione del paternalismo di Nicola I, avrebbe isolato l'Austria dalle potenze dell'Europa occidentale e avrebbe costituito, trattandosi di un intervento a difesa di uno Stato ortodosso, un duro smacco nei confronti della confessione cattolica di cui Vienna era antica peroratrice. Ma d'altra parte, l'entrata in guerra a fianco dell'alleanza antirussa, avrebbe implicato la difesa di un Impero musulmano contro uno cristiano.

senza guadagnarsi le Potenze occidentali. In fondo a questa politica v'era isolamento"⁴³.

Davanti all'esitazione di Vienna a entrare nell'alleanza, Napoleone III decise di intavolare le trattative con il Regno di Sardegna, *in primis* per mostrare che in caso di intervento in Crimea, Vienna non avrebbe dovuto temere di spostare le proprie truppe dal lombardo-veneto, in quanto anche Torino sarebbe stata ugualmente impegnata in un ingente sforzo militare a Oriente, *in secundis* per ribadire all'Austria come un piccolo regno fosse più risoluto di un grande impero. In cambio di una rassicurazione sul fronte italiano, Napoleone III chiedeva l'ingresso austriaco nella coalizione. Dell'iniziale rifiuto della Hofburg approfittò Cavour che, nel suo progetto di proiettare il regno sabauda nello scacchiere continentale, vide come favorevole la situazione venutasi a creare e aprì notevoli margini di intesa per intavolare le trattative con le potenze occidentali. Nell'aprile del 1854, infatti, i diplomatici britannici si recarono a Torino al fine di avviare i negoziati relativi all'alleanza piemontese⁴⁴. Se Parigi fosse riuscita a ottenere l'alleanza austriaca, e Cavour l'appoggio francese, si sarebbe venuta a creare una paradossale situazione di alleanza indiretta austro-piemontese sul fronte orientale, mentre sul fronte occidentale Vienna e Torino sarebbero state - come sempre - rivali in perenne conflitto⁴⁵. "Cavour era persuaso che l'alleanza con le potenze occidentali fosse questione di vita per il Piemonte... Bisognava quindi non far troppi calcoli, rischiare tutto, e intervenire a qualsiasi prezzo. Quel che importava, era intervenire: il resto aveva importanza secondaria. Una volta postisi a fianco delle grandi Potenze, si sarebbe ben trovato il modo di ricavare dalla situazione il ricavabile"⁴⁶.

Il 13 e il 14 dicembre 1854 due successive comunicazioni inglesi invitarono ufficialmente il Piemonte a partecipare all'alleanza fra le Potenze occidentali⁴⁷. Dopo numerosi dissidi e un acceso dibattito politico interno, Cavour decise di procedere, "con un atto veramente dittatoriale"⁴⁸ e scavalcando le direttive del ministro degli Interni Urbano Rattazzi, agli accordi d'alleanza⁴⁹. La convenzione franco-anglo-

⁴³ Franco Valsecchi, *Il Risorgimento e l'Europa. L'alleanza di Crimea*, Milano, Mondadori, 1948, pp. 11-12.

⁴⁴ Antonello Battaglia, *op. cit.*, p. 19.

⁴⁵ Cosa che di fatto avvenne nella guerra di Crimea.

⁴⁶ Franco Valsecchi, *L'unificazione italiana...*, cit., p. 17.

⁴⁷ Ottavio Barié et alii, *Storia delle relazioni internazionali. Testi e documenti. 1815-2003*, Bologna, Monduzzi, 2004, pp. 39-42.

⁴⁸ Franco Valsecchi, *L'unificazione italiana...*, cit., p. 101.

⁴⁹ *Ibidem*. Cfr. Ottavio Barié et alii, *op. cit.*, p. 41.

sarda, dopo alcuni rinvii, fu firmata il 21 gennaio 1855 e ratificata il 4 marzo⁵⁰. Il trattato risultò un vero e proprio schiaffo diplomatico all'Austria, la cui neutralità a conflitto ormai inoltrato deludeva le potenze occidentali. Napoleone III ritenne che le trattative con lo zar fossero ormai fallite e, rivolgendosi a Vienna, esortò al rispetto degli accordi siglati il 22 dicembre 1854 richiamandola altresì a un impegno concreto sia difensivo che offensivo⁵¹.

A Torino si decise di "allestire a gabarre" 17 navi da guerra, salvo la fregata a vapore *Carlo Alberto* che fu munita di 45 cannoni alla *paixhans* e marinai cannonieri⁵². La squadra sarda in Oriente annoverava 3.818 uomini in mare, e in Senato fu presentata una legge, approvata il 28 febbraio, relativa alla leva straordinaria di ulteriori 500 marinai⁵³. La forza totale fu di 18.061 unità⁵⁴. Una piccola parte degli uomini partì a bordo del vapore francese *Vaticano*, con destinazione Costantinopoli, il 20 marzo 1855 con un ufficiale ingegnere per la disposizione e l'organizzazione degli apprestamenti militari necessari alla spedizione piemontese. Il 22 aprile arrivarono altri ufficiali dello Stato Maggiore a bordo della fregata da guerra *Costituzione*. "Arrivavano intanto da Malta, dalla Spezia, da Tolone, da Costantinopoli in gran numero navi e da sopracollo, la massima parte a vapore, molte a elice, cioè a vite, nuovo modo trovato più sicuro e più celere delle ruote. Le batterie del porto di Genova rendevano ogni giorno il saluto di risposta agli spari delle navi appartenenti alle nazioni amiche e collegate; e tutti

⁵⁰ "Senza esitare affermiamo che non meno di Francia e d'Inghilterra avrebbe l'Italia a piangere amaramente quest'inausto avvenimento. L'Italia per la sua giacitura in seno al Mediterraneo troverà sempre la via d'Oriente più conveniente ai suoi traffici. Questa stessa strada dovrà fra non molto condurre per mezzo di una facile e pronta comunicazione alle Indie Orientali, emporio del commercio universale. Supponete ora lo Czar di tutte le Russie padrone delle chiavi del Mar Nero e la libertà di questo immenso traffico starà nelle sue mani... Una potenza colossale quale la Russia diverrebbe tra breve tal potenza marittima da dominare orgogliosamente entro e fuori dello stretto dei Dardanelli. Il suo naviglio guerresco solcherebbe minaccioso le acque del Mediterraneo...". *Relazione della Commissione composta dai deputati: Salmour, Farini, Lisio, Notta, Lanza, C. Cadorna, Valerio. Tornata I, febbraio 1855*, in Franco Valsecchi, *L'unificazione italiana...*, cit., p. 149.

⁵¹ Alain Gouttman, *op. cit.*, p. 142.

⁵² Mariano D'Ayala, *op. cit.*, p. 42.

⁵³ *Ibidem*, p. 43.

⁵⁴ Il colonnello dello Stato Maggiore Enrico Giustiniani, nella sua opera *Commentaires sur les opérations militaires en Crimée* pubblicata a Parigi nel 1857, afferma che la forza inviata in Crimea era superiore ai 15.000 uomini previsti negli accordi e cioè: 18.061 uomini, 3.963 cavalli ossia 692 per cavalleria, 932 per artiglieria e 2.339 per traino, e 36 cannoni campali.

cercavano visitare le maggiori e le più belle, fra le quali il *Giasone*, inglese, su cui fu data una sontuosa festa da ballo per ufficiali e altri cittadini la sera del 19 marzo”⁵⁵.

La data stabilita per la partenza fu il 20 aprile: i primi scaglioni della brigata di riserva furono imbarcati sulle navi da guerra *Authion*, *Carlo Alberto* e *Costituzione*, già ritornata dal Bosforo. Subito dopo la partenza, salutata da molta commozione, si registrò un inaspettato quanto tragico incidente marittimo: il 24 aprile - dopo aver fatto rientro da una tappa a Malta - era salpata da Genova la grande nave a vapore *Creso* con a bordo una compagnia di zappatori del genio, una di operai delle sussistenze militari, alcune Sorelle della Carità, diverse attrezzature sanitarie come letti, medicine, strumenti medici, ventiquattro muli necessari per il trasporto, più viveri e vettovagliamento sufficienti per un mese. Dopo aver solcato il mare per qualche miglio, all'altezza di Recco, non molto distante da Genova, si sprigionò un violento incendio interno. Il capitano di vascello diede inizialmente l'ordine di spegnere le fiamme, che però in poco tempo raggiunsero proporzioni notevoli, e dopo infruttuosi tentativi diede l'ordine di sganciare le gomene che univano il *Creso* al *Pedestrian*, carico di munizioni che furono gettate in mare. L'ordine impartito fu quello di navigare verso la spiaggia nella conca di San Fruttuoso per permettere agli uomini di abbandonare indenni l'imbarcazione su cui l'incendio era divampato con notevole violenza. Molti soldati - come racconta Mariano D'Ayala nella sua cronaca - si prodigarono nel contrastare le fiamme e altri si occuparono dell'organizzazione delle scialuppe di salvataggio, mentre altri, probabilmente preoccupati dalle fiamme crescenti e dalla difficoltà di approdare ai mezzi di fortuna, decisero di gettarsi inavvertitamente in mare che inghiottì diverse decine di soldati e ventisette sottufficiali. Il *Creso* affondò portando con sé l'intero carico di vettovagliamento e attrezzature appena fabbricate. Il danno stimato ammontò a circa tre milioni di lire⁵⁶. Nonostante il grande disastro avvenuto in acque sabaude, la marina continuò a organizzare le spedizioni per il Mar Nero, e infatti dopo qualche giorno salpò, a bordo del *Governolo*, il generale Alfonso La Marmora insieme a 4.000 soldati⁵⁷. “Le une dopo le altre partivan le navi verso Oriente; alcune, tenendosi più dappresso alla costa orientale della Corsica e della Sardegna, toccavano Malta; ed altre, vieppiù stringendosi alla costa occidentale d'Italia, salutavano Capraia

⁵⁵ Mariano D'Ayala, *op. cit.*, p. 46.

⁵⁶ *Ibidem*, p. 53.

⁵⁷ *Ibidem*, p. 55.

e la Gorgona, non più invocate a far *siepe all'Arno in su la foce*, e l'Elba e le isole Eolie con la Stromboli fumante, e Ponza e Nisida e Capri, poi Messina e Reggio; sulle cui rive i giovani ardenti del Faro e il popolo infelice salutavano col guardo e con lo sventolare di bianchi lini il passaggio di quelle gloriose bandiere, appena soffocando nel cuore il grido che correva sulle labbra di: *Viva l'Italia*, e augurando nella lontana onorevole impresa felice successo e glorioso alle armi italiane⁵⁸.

Dal diario del sottotenente *pro tempore* del I Reggimento di Guerra, Giuseppe Francesco Ceresa di Bonvillaret, si possono ricostruire i giorni immediatamente precedenti alla partenza da Genova e la rotta di navigazione per Balaklava. In particolare, il I reggimento si spostò da Torino a Frugarolo e Bosca la mattina di venerdì 13 aprile 1855. Appena giunti, i soldati si accamparono in attesa della consegna delle bandiere da parte del re Vittorio Emanuele II che avvenne il giorno successivo. Il 15 aprile si registrarono i primi casi di diserzione, mentre nei giorni seguenti alcuni soldati cercavano di dirigersi nella vicina Alessandria al fine di contrarre qualche malattia venerea per essere esonerati dalla partenza. Al di là di qualche sporadico caso, il sottotenente descrive uno scenario di attesa ottimistica diffusa tra le truppe⁵⁹. Il 2 maggio gli uomini furono trasportati da treni speciali a Genova, in attesa dell'imbarco che avvenne nel pomeriggio del giorno successivo a bordo del vapore inglese *Audes* che portava a rimorchio un bastimento a vela carico di materiale d'artiglieria, mentre i battaglioni della brigata Cuneo, 7° e 8° furono imbarcati sul piroscafo *Clyd*.

Nella ricostruzione della rotta, il 7 maggio, in condizioni meteorologiche piovose, ma con mare calmo, le imbarcazioni passarono in vista delle isole toscane di Capraia, Gorgona, Elba, Montecristo, Pianosa, Giglio, mentre a ovest si intravedevano le coste corse. Dopo il passaggio nell'arcipelago, la rotta di navigazione si allontanò dalla costa di circa 60-70 miglia e fu aumentata la velocità fino al successivo rallentamento e alla virata verso est nei pressi dell'arcipelago siciliano delle Eolie, in vista di Stromboli. Dopo tre ore di navigazione tra le Eolie e lo stretto di Messina, le imbarcazioni entrarono nello Ionio perdendo di vista la terra che venne lasciata dietro, a ovest. Dopo due giorni si giunse a Capo Matapan per poi proseguire, con rotta nord-est verso le Cicladi settentrionali e l'Eubea. Una volta giunti in Egeo il rimorchio

⁵⁸ *Ibidem*.

⁵⁹ Giuseppe Francesco Ceresa di Bonvillaret, *Diario della campagna di Crimea, tolto dal taccuino di un sottotenente del 2. reggimento di guerra: dal 1 aprile 1855 al 16 giugno 1856*, Torino-Roma, L. Roux e C., 1894, pp. 9-13.

cedette e il bastimento a vela rimase in balia delle onde rallentando la navigazione; infatti ci vollero circa dieci ore per ripristinare il collegamento tra le due imbarcazioni e riparare il danno. Il 12 maggio, dopo aver passato Negroponte e Andros, si arrivò in vista di Tenedos, davanti alle coste turche, e di qui si proseguì all'imbocco dei Dardanelli, dopo aver scorto Gallipoli e aver solcato le acque del Mar di Marmara, le imbarcazioni ormeggiarono nel porto di Costantinopoli dove le truppe alloggiarono per qualche giorno prima della partenza⁶⁰. Dopo quarantotto ore, nella tarda mattinata del 16 maggio, le imbarcazioni entrarono nel Mar Nero dove iniziano le prime lontane visioni di colonne di fumo, fiamme e si cominciarono a udire i primi colpi di cannone. Il 18 maggio, dopo due settimane di navigazione, la flotta arrivò nei pressi di Balaklava, dove ormeggiò e iniziò la fase di sbarco. "Entriamo nel porto di Balaklava, dove ci ancoriamo. Questo porto è destinato specialmente per le operazioni marittime del corpo piemontese in Crimea. È un porto sicuro, tutto circondato da montagne, sulle quali sorgono tutt'ora ruderi di castelli e notificazioni genovesi. Il porto non è grande, tutto circondato da scogli aridi e ora ingombro di navi mercantili con vettovaglie e viveri per la truppa. La prima impressione non è certamente splendida. Siamo divenuti tutti seri"⁶¹.

Dopo sette giorni, le operazioni di sbarco furono concluse e il corpo di spedizione, composto da cinque brigate, fu accampato vicino Balaklava, a Karani⁶². L'importanza delle rotte nel Mar Nero è evidente, poiché il controllo di questo vasto bacino permetteva l'arrivo celere, rispetto alle vie terrestri, di approvvigionamenti, munizioni e soprattutto assicurava il continuo ricambio di uomini⁶³ attraverso la partenza di numerose navi-ospedale e l'arrivo di vapori. Il predominio dei mari e in particolare del vasto bacino del Mar Nero divenne, fin dalle prime battute del conflitto, *condicio sine qua non* per la riuscita delle operazioni militari, un essenziale elemento che permise alla coalizione antirussa di avere la meglio sul nemico assediato da mesi a Sebastopoli, suo principale porto militare ormai paralizzato e privo di qualsiasi potenziale offensivo sul fronte marittimo.

⁶⁰ *Ibidem*, p. 17.

⁶¹ *Ibidem*, p. 18.

⁶² Balaklava era stato un porto mercantile genovese nel XIV e XV secolo e il nome fu proprio dato dai mercanti liguri che considerandolo gradevole e sicuro lo chiamarono appunto *Bella-chiave*.

⁶³ Molti malati di colera, altri feriti.

Per quanto riguarda propriamente la flotta sabauda, dunque, nelle acque del Mar Nero era presente una piccola squadra da guerra, comandata dal c.v. Di Negro e composta dalla nuovissima *Carlo Alberto*, *Governolo*, *Costituzione*, *Malfatano*; si trattava di naviglio a vapore che tuttavia non partecipò alle azioni di guerra in quanto, secondo le fonti ufficiali, non se ne presentò occasione⁶⁴.

Dopo le battaglie dell'Alma del 20 settembre 1854, di Balaklava del 25 ottobre 1854 e della Cernaia del 16 agosto 1855 con cui i russi cercarono di rompere l'accerchiamento, gli alleati aprirono il varco per Sebastopoli stremata da circa un anno di assedio, mentre le navi continuavano la loro preziosa opera di copertura e soprattutto di rifornimento di uomini e mezzi⁶⁵. "Il giorno 6, 7 e 8 di settembre raddoppiarono con insolito calore l'opera di distruzione vomitando spavento e morte sull'infelice Sebastopoli da ben settecento bocche di cannone, mentre la flotta alleata faceva grandinare senza posa le sue bombe specialmente sopra il forte in quarantena"⁶⁶.

La guerra, estenuante e interminabile, ebbe una svolta nei primi giorni del settembre 1855. Dopo gli scontri militari e il vano assedio di Sebastopoli (dal 9 ottobre 1854 all'8 settembre 1855), l'esercito alleato decise di sferrare l'attacco definitivo che permise l'espugnazione della roccaforte crimea. La caduta di Sebastopoli costituì la svolta definitiva del conflitto armato. Si trattò dell'atto finale di una guerra combattuta per due anni. Ai grandi assalti erano seguite repentine ritirate, a migliaia si erano scagliati contro l'artiglieria nemica e le cavallerie avevano caricato intere divisioni di fanteria. Gli scontri cruenti terminarono in uno scenario drammatico: in soli tre giorni circa 30.000 caduti russi e 8.000 caduti alleati. "Così rimanevano appagati gli intendimenti principali dell'impresa di Crimea; distruggere e annientare le ricchezze navali della Russia nel Mar Nero, l'arsenale marittimo, le officine, le costruzioni e le macchine e quanto apparteneva alla marineria moscovita; perloché venne minato anco tutto quel poco ch'era rimasto illeso"⁶⁷.

La supremazia russa nel Mar Nero era stata scongiurata dall'intervento delle potenze occidentali a fianco del "grande malato d'Europa". L'Impero russo perdette il confronto diretto con le potenze continentali e quindi l'opportunità di ottenere il controllo dell'Europa orientale e di raggiungere gli agognati

⁶⁴ Domenico Guerrini, *Come ci avviammo a Lissa*, Torino, Casanova, 1907, p. 148.

⁶⁵ Mariano D'Ayala, *op. cit.*, p. 102.

⁶⁶ "La Civiltà Cattolica", 1855, XII, p. 123.

⁶⁷ Mariano D'Ayala, *op. cit.*, p. 110.

Stretti, che avrebbero permesso l'inserimento nelle rotte mediterranee.

Anche nei trattati di pace venne ribadita la centralità del Mar Nero, scenario strategico non solo in guerra, ma ancora più importante nelle prospettive future. All'art. 11 fu sancito che: *“La Mer Noir est neutralisée: ouverts à la marine marchande de toutes les nations, ses eaux et ses ports sont, formellement, et à perpétuité, interdit au pavillon de guerre soit des Puissance riveraines, soit de tout autre Puissance, sauf les exception mentionnées aux articles 14 et 19 du présent Traité”*⁶⁸. L'art. 12 stabiliva invece: *“Libre de toute entrave, le commerce, dans les ports et dans les eaux de la Mer Noir, ne sera assujété qu'à des règlements de santé, de douane, de police, conçus dans un esprit favorable au développement des transactions commerciales... La Russie et la Sublime Porte admettront des Consuls dans leurs ports situés sur le littoral de la Mer Noir, conformément aux principes du droit international”*⁶⁹. L'art. 13, infine, recitava: *“... L'Empereur de toutes les Russies, et sa Majesté Impériale le Sultan, s'engagent à n'élever et à ne conserver sur ce littoral aucun arsenal militaire-maritime”*⁷⁰.

La paventata strategia dell'Impero russo di poter prendere il sopravvento sul Mar Nero, sferrare controffensive contro le coste turche e arrivare, attraverso gli Stretti, al Mediterraneo fu scongiurata tramite il dispiegamento di un numero ragguardevole di navi da guerra appartenenti alle diverse marinierie alleate. In particolar modo cruciale si era rivelata la scelta strategica di assediare Sebastopoli e paralizzare il più importante porto militare russo. La neutralizzazione delle imbarcazioni zariste e il controllo del mare permisero di monopolizzare i traffici marittimi e fecero delle marinierie elementi essenziali per la riuscita delle operazioni militari. Anche se la guerra fu condotta prevalentemente per vie terrestri, l'appoggio delle imbarcazioni - in azioni di copertura e operazioni offensive, nonché le continue “spole” per i rimpiazzi e i rifornimenti - si rivelò fondamentale per la risoluzione del conflitto. La centralità del vasto bacino interno, situato geograficamente proprio nel cuore del conflitto, era stata già compresa da Napoleone III ai prodromi del conflitto e l'invio di cospicue forze in loco era divenuto il fattore essenziale per la vittoria marittima, terrestre e politica. “Nella

⁶⁸ In Giuseppe Francesco Ceresa di Bonvillaret, *op. cit.*, p. 281.

⁶⁹ *Ibidem*, p. 282.

⁷⁰ *Ibidem*.

pace si prepara la guerra, e dopo la guerra meglio tornano in pregio le care e generose istituzioni della pace⁷¹.

⁷¹ Mariano D'Ayala, *op. cit.*, p. 118.

WOMEN AS TOPIC OF “INTELLECTUAL DEBATES” CASE STUDY: “AMICULU FAMILIEI”

Georgeta Fodor*

Abstract

The XIXth century is the witness of a real intellectual debate around women's role and position in the society. Both men and women (for the first time) will get involved in this debate and the written press is one of the media they used as a vehicle for their ideas, for or against women. Thus we chose as a study case to analyze the manners through which this gender discussion develops in the Transylvanian Romanian press of the second half of the XIXth century. Part of a major research project, we limited our analysis, for the timebeing, to a single review that is the Amiculu Familiei, as its declared aim is that of both educating and entertaining its readers.

Keywords: *Press, Gender, Women, Nation, National Ideas*

“They do not have a political career, they give birth to children, take care of their homes and pray to God; they are admired if they are honest and virtuous, thus seemingly becoming more beautiful; also, they must be appreciated as well as watch over the virtuosity of mother, wife and daughter that has consequences over the husband's honesty or, as the relatives, the neighbouring community or the social peer group in general think, in which the latter is integrated¹. According to the Christian morale, they still bear in their smile a reminiscence of the forbidden apple, of Eve's sin. Unfaithful. Misleading. Lacking mind. Passionate. But instigating”².

These are the real aspects that marked the Feminine profile in both the Medieval and Modern times. These are the very aspects that women were going to “fight” against, in their attempt to remove a conception deeply rooted in the over whole mentality and placing them in absolute inferiority as compared to men. Hence this paperwork aims at studying the way in which the feminine profile has been changing or actually adapting to the new social and intellectual background of the XIXth century. The work is focused on

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¹ Ionuț Costea, “Repere pentru o istorie a cuplului și a prostituției în Transilvania veacului al XVII-lea. Studiu de caz: «Cronica Transilvaniei» de Georg Kraus» in Ionuț Costea, Valentin Orga (coord.), *Studii de Istorie a Transilvaniei. Familie și Societate*, Cluj- Napoca, Ed. Clusium, 1999, p.17.

² *Ibidem.*

one of the Romanian titles in Transylvania's written press, namely *Amiculu Familiei* – the major argument lies in the fact that this weekly magazine makes a statement out of being “instructive and entertaining”, thus an echo of the preferences and tastes of society.

The written press was chosen as a documentary source, for the research of the way in which the discourse over women changes, out of two reasons. First of all, because it somehow represents an intermediary documentary support, a place where the official and the real meet – and this is exactly why it has tremendous importance in the history of women. Moreover, written press represented the main tool of the researcher in identifying a reality that is otherwise very difficult to see: that is the society's attitude towards women. While earlier centuries³ seldom allowed us to have a glimpse of the way in which women were perceived by society and the voices – when they existed – were exclusively masculine, written press radically changed this reality, making possible for us to become part in real intellectual “debates” over women's condition and role. Secondly, written press is significant also for the way in which it presents the engine that actuates women's voices to stand up. While for instance in the Middle Ages women failed in making themselves heard and then the early Modern Ages (the XVIth century) allowed that their voice become “whispering”⁴, it is the beginnings of the contemporary time that significantly changed women's role in society, allowing them to make themselves heard in public life too. In fact, up to the democratic revolutions, women did not react to the masculine dominant- patronizing discourse building their own identity. Only starting with the XIXth century, throughout promoting new values such as universalism, human rights etc., favourable conditions were created for women's emergence as a social actor⁵. Thus, women gradually stepped over the limited space of the family and actively got involved in social life. The written press shall record all the transformations that women's statute would undergo within this century of nations. Moreover, the second half of the XIXth century brought about the press published in large quantity⁶, whose mechanisms modelled women's image.

³ Reference is being made to the period between 15th and 17th centuries, on which we insisted within our former studies.

⁴ Madeleine Lazard, *Eva în oglindă. Viața femeii în Renaștere*, București, Ed.Saeculum, 2007, p. 30.

⁵ Ionela Băluță, “Apariția femeii ca actor social – a doua jumătate a secolului al XIX-lea”, in Ionela Băluță, Ioana Cîrstocea (coord.), *Direcții și teme de cercetare în studiile de gen din România. Atelier*, București, Colegiul Noua Europă, 2002, p.62.

⁶ Loredana Stepan, *Imagini ale femeii în literatura și presa românească arădeană la sfârșitul secolului al XIX-lea și începutul secolului XX* in “Caiete de Antropologie Istorică”, An II, No. 1(3), January-June, 2003, p. 47. The author researched in the Romanian written press of Arad in the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century and found various images of the woman: the image of mother as a

Amiculu Familiei was published on a regular basis in Gherla and Cluj under the supervision of Nicolae Fekete Negrutiu, editor. It represents only one of the papers that proved the society's interest in women, as a topic, both at "theoretical" level and as regards their actions in the social context. Generally, the Romanian written press in Transylvania regarding women is focused on two aspects: one which reveals the social, political, cultural and national significance of "women's issue" and the other which analyses, on a concrete level, the feminist trend as perceived by the Romanian society and its aspects related to women's emancipation.

Though there are plenty of topics related to women published by *Amiculu Familiei* (in 1878, for instance, there are 3 articles directly referring to women: their education, the habits and "customs" of certain European women, women's luxury and the bride's dowry), this paperwork shall consider for the moment only women's discourse as it is revealed by the written press, in an attempt to identify the actual modern definition of women, as well as the role that society attributed to them.

We can state with no shadow of doubt that it is a real "intellectual debate" over women we are handling with, a debate that integrates both men and women, "feminists" and antifeminists, all eager to define women out of referring them to the fundamental values they adhered to. There are voices that stand for women's right to access to education and for their becoming more than a décor object – right to education would give them the opportunity to be a valuable citizen. Women shall play a decisive role in this polemics from now on: they shall no longer be passive actors in the discussions about women's role in society, but shall be the ones trying to destroy the popular myth that they are exclusively subjected to men and consequently win an active place in the public space.

It is worth mentioning that the arguments used by both male and female authors in supporting the reconsidering and the re-evaluation of women's condition in society are identical: they build upon the virtues of maternity focusing mainly on mothers' educating role – thus extrapolating on women's educating role for the whole nation, consequently their quality of great citizens. Also, a good part of the articles underlie the progress that women made, as social actors, in their statute, within the 19th century, as opposed to the inferiority level that women had in former centuries⁷.

teacher; the civil status - the image of solitary unmarried women that were disapproved because they were not part of the pattern of being a mother and a wife; the adulterous, coquetish woman keen on fashion, as well as the cliché regarding the vanity and greediness of the woman, her misleading and trwachrous character.

⁷ *Amiculu Familiei*, no. 1, August 1st / 13th, 1878, p. 10.

1. Women as family founders

No doubt, the image of women as family founders and hence the idea that the specific space for women is the private space plays a representative role as far as the Romanian written press of the XIXth century is concerned. This idea resides in numerous patterns: be it the highlight on the virtuosity that maternity implies, the hygiene and breeding rules for children, or the right of women to be offered education (topic that shall be later approached), the women's representation as a mother is omnipresent. For instance the October 15th / 27th 1878 edition in the study on maternity signed by Legouv, member of the French Academy, clearly states that: for women "maternity is life itself"⁸. Similarly, the August 1st / 13th 1879 article signed by B. P. H. advocates the virtuosity that maternity means. The article seems to be part of a lecture and is actually homage to women and their quality as educators. According to the author, women as mothers are the ones that put the basis of the child's education. They are the primordial human beings, as successors of the Blessed Virgin Mary. Their role is a positive one; yet, the author does not forget about the original sin but minimizes it through the positive virtuosities women are at present "awarded": "oh, you, women's lips, you have seduced us to Adam.... And the God made you able to teach us the truth and reveal the very existence of God"⁹.

2. Women as intellectuals, utility of education offered to women

In the August 1st / 13th 1878 edition, "Social studies" column (where the majority of studies about women shall be published), there is an article that actually quotes a speech of Mrs. Paulina Zaharescu, principal of the vocational girls school in Bucharest, with the occasion of a prize awarding ceremony. It is a historic "anamnesis" of the evolution of women's right to education: the Ancient Ages – the women's access to knowledge is refused; the Christianity – women start being considered "human beings", that is they increase the degree of respect towards them but continue to be "slaves of the ignorance"; the Modern Age – women rise up and stand for themselves (late XVIIIth century)¹⁰. The whole discourse emphasizes the great utility of education offered to women. There is a peculiar idea highlighted, that shall be found in numerous other future articles too, according to which education for women is necessary for the present times but it shall not "change" the primordial meaning of women: that of being good mothers, virtuous

⁸ Legouv, *Maternitatea*, in "Amiculu Familiei", no. 6, October 15th /27th, 1878, p.63.

⁹ B. P. H., *Muma. Fragmentu dintr-o conferin*, in *Ibidem*, no. 1, August 1st / 13th, 1879, p.1.

¹⁰ ***, *La cestiunea educatiunei si instructiunei femeiei romane*, in *Ibidem*, no.1, August 1st / 13th, 1878, p.11.

and devoted wives¹¹. Interesting or perhaps duplicity bearing? – and thus making room for interpretations – is the mention that the article's author makes before quoting Mrs. Zaharescu, as the initial argument for inserting the extract of the above mentioned speech was: "the lines are presented for their value in literary terms"¹².

The same aspect regarding women's education shall be treated also in the edition of September 1st / 13th 1878. In fact it is about the same topic as the previous edition – only now the speech of King Carol I is quoted. It is worth noticing this tendency, perfectly anchored in the realities of the time otherwise, to take over the pattern from outside the Carpathians and implicitly to mould the debates on the Transylvanian feminist movement after the Romanian model in the Romanian Royalty. Made by the Romanian King, the speech increases in value also for the picture it contours for the Romanian woman of the 19th century: it is no wonder that the emphasis on the utility of women's education remains the same as in the previous article: the educated woman is nothing more than a corollary of her husband and family. An educated wife's role was first to increase the prestige of her husband and only as a second additional effect to get her considered as a citizen of the country. The very structure of the sentence obviously indicates the hierarchy of women's roles, as referred back to the private-public and family – society contexts: "only the Romanian daughters shall become founders of families, the Vestals goddesses of the Country, the happiness and treasure of our community, the hope of a future that is worth our industriousness as well as the sacrifices of the present generation"¹³.

Broadly speaking, the two aspects: maternity and the need of women to have access to education appear simultaneously in the articles published in *Amiculu Familiei*. Yet, so far the articles do not overtly assume the debate on women's condition; this situation comes to an end starting with 1879: the series of debates on the feminine profile is opened with November 13th / 25th 1879 edition in the article that Mrs. Emilia Lungu wrote related to the Romanian woman. As the first Romanian teacher in the region of Banat in Romania, she will get remarked due to the efforts made for winning the women's right to access education. Her activity in this respect shall be developed on several layers, an official one – whose aim was to obtain the permission to found an institute for girls – and another less formal – that of using the written press as a means to promote

¹¹ *Ibidem*.

¹² *Ibidem*.

¹³ ***, *La cestiunea educatiunei si instructiunei femeiei romane*, in "Amiculu Familiei", no.3, September 1st / 13th 1878, p. 34.

women and their right to education. The article we refer to starts from a fundamental question: “What are women and what would their mission be?”- this actually encompasses the essence of all debates on the feminine profile of the time. The article *per se* should not be considered a manifesto of the Romanian feminist movement, as the author is far from protesting or “rioting” against the dominant masculine movement – this is obvious even in the motto: “Give the woman the awareness of herself and soon she will learn how she should be!”¹⁴ The author does nothing but demand the woman’s right to be a good citizen, but not before being a good mother: the woman is first of all a mother, creator of the whole nation – the supreme argument actually standing for women’s right to education – and hence the need to grant her right to rise above ignorance and lack of knowledge. Quotes from J. J. Rousseau and Aimé Martin come to emphasize the importance that women play in the society: “Beware... the ideas that are born in the woman’s mind while taking care of her home are further brought by the man in the public arena, the Parliament and everywhere else!”¹⁵. The author advocates for women’s right to education using as major argument the fact that an educated woman shall be nothing more than added value to her husband. Thus the talk initiated in this end of XIXth century reminds of the similar debates back to Renaissance and Reforms period, when women were granted the right to education only in order to increase the prestige of their husbands. Emilia Lungu wrote: “how can anyone forget that women with no rational education, just in the primitive state similar to her ancestors, cannot forget to influence by cultivating and ennobling? How can anyone pretend that women should stay outside everything but household activities but still influence her family to conquer sciences...? What could she offer when her mind looks like a board with nothing written on it?”¹⁶ Yet, the present debate reports a real progress, as education does not only serve the family, but the whole nation, too. The author’s answer to the question in the title of the article, “it is the model which generations and peoples take after”, is representative for this idea: the woman is half the nation and the girl’s schools shall be able to model women “in respect of the blessing of her own, her family and the whole nation”¹⁷.

The effort to define women continues with a new article on the first page of the paper in the editions of November 20th / December 7th, November 27th / December 7th and December 4th / 16th 1879. The

¹⁴ Emilia Lungu, *Femeia română*, in *Ibidem*, November no. 8, 13th / 25th, 1879, p. 69.

¹⁵ *Ibidem*.

¹⁶ *Ibidem*, p.71.

¹⁷ *Ibidem*.

article is entitled "A few words on the issue of women" and, out of the tonality of the discourse, we presume the author is a man. The objective overtly declared by the author is to contour the social status of women appealing to historical evidence, as well as to rational arguments perfectly integrated in the contemporary time. The approach follows the rationale characteristic to historical research: the author synthetically presents the history of women's evolution between the Middle Ages and up to contemporary times (the 19th century). The analysis is also headed towards future: the obvious effort of the author to indicate the directions in which it was compulsory that the social status of women should improve. The value of the article is greater as it becomes the echo of the contemporary world's interest regarding women's status in society – another evidence that we can, as above mentioned, talk about the existence of a debate over women; the author places this debate among the issues of major importance of his time: "The motto of the XIXth century is: common effort for the freedom of conscience, between free will and divine power -. Yet, I personally consider that the current issue should be added to all the above mentioned: common effort between parallel development of men and women"¹⁸. Still, roles should not be mistaken for! The author does not talk about equality between men and women; he just stands for the uplifting of women so that they could serve mainly to their husbands and families¹⁹. It is about a desideratum, still hard to achieve, as the author reckons, while revealing the progress that women's status underwent within the XIXth century:

- Women's status got improved both as far as private and public contexts are concerned;
- The legal provisions got improved (the right to inheritance, annulment of absolute inferiority);
- Adjustment of customs, which stood for the issues that the legal system lacked.

As far as wide perception is concerned, progress is obvious. The woman does not define herself by reference to the familial context any longer, but the issue of her social position is approached. The author emphasizes on the discrepancy between the society's needs and the slow rhythm in which the feminine problematic evolves, signalling the fact that the issue of women as social human beings is not yet defined. This is the very context in which the same question in the article of Mrs. Emilia Lungu is reconsidered: "what are

¹⁸ ***, *Cateva cuvinte asupra cestiunei femeiloru*, in "Amiculu Familiei", no. 9, November 20th / December 2nd, 1879, p. 77.

¹⁹ *Ibidem*, *I do not want that the woman should be the man, but the man could become complete with the help of the woman.*

women?” As above mentioned already, this is the essence of the whole point and the answer to this question is nothing but the solution of the most acute aspects related to the position and role that women should have within society, all grouped around a dilemma: “what place is the woman worth having in our century?”²⁰ The progress recorded in women’s status are actually the consequences of a “long historical process” and the author, just like Mrs. Paulina Zaharescu, renders details of the woman’s profile over previous historical ages²¹. It is interesting to note the way in which opinions of famous contemporary intellectuals on women are briefly presented while encompassing the general view on the matter:

- Diderot – the woman is a courtesan
- Montesquieu – the woman is the doll worth loving
- Rousseau – the woman is the object of pleasure for the man
- Voltaire – the woman is “nothing”

There are voices that stand for women too – the abbot Sieyès or Condortet, and yet, the voices against-women shall triumph (Mirabeau, Danton, Robespierre).

Reflecting over the past times determines the author to signal on the shortcomings of the social system of whose the most serious is the absence of public schools for girls. In fact, this is the very source of all the other lacking aspects which bring about the inferiority of the woman of modern age. The shortcomings of the educational system do not give women other alternative:

- In order to be able to ensure her subsistence, the woman must get married and thus become dependant on her husband;
- She is not allowed to take care of her inheritance;
- As a mother, she is not allowed to take care of the education of her offsprings, she does not have any authority on the latter;
- As a “citizen”, she is not allowed to be tutors or witnesses to the writing of wills.

Women are inferior in their families as well as in society. Society is rejecting change. As far as the society’s perception over the different hypostases of the feminine profile is concerned, the article underlies the fact that society shall be forced to “integrate” (as it will actually happen) the idea that women are equal to men in terms of their rights. The woman is a human being too and hence it is compulsory that she be granted her rights as a human being – it is no longer

²⁰ *Ibidem*.

²¹ Starting with Creation. The vision that the author renders is the one that has marked the debates over women for centuries: Adam and Eve, two parts of the same whole, but Eve create out of Adam and so implicitly dependant on him and inferior to him.

about an innate inferiority, so “the women’s spirit is not dead, only suffocated”.

The article undoubtedly belongs to those that are favourable to women’s emancipation movement without contesting the man’s authority: the woman and the man cannot be equal, they are different; yet, this difference cannot justify for subordination²². It is cautiousness that characterizes the author’s approach, but this does not reduce the historical value of his article. At the same time, it is worth noticing that in standing up for women, he uses the same arguments that were previously stated to entitle for refusing the woman’s access to the public life: tradition, nature – “studying tradition, I can conclude that progress and gender difference do not exclude social equality. History is fundamental argument for this, our conscience and even nature; history imposes that women strive their way towards freedom, so it is natural that her way towards freedom, totally different from the man’s, be opened for her!”²³ The author emphasizes on the importance of the issue of the feminine profile while advocating the equality between genders: “In my personal opinion, the woman is a significantly different human being as compared to the man, but I don’t see the slightest reason for her subordination, but her need to uplift. – It should be one out of two options: we could either restrain the woman’s life to her family space and thus have them reign only inside the borders of her space; in other words, exactly as a result of the difference between men and women we should keep the woman around her home and family... or, on the contrary, we should extend their influence over the social-political life too – and I personally think that this is better... women, if welcome in the social-political life, do not destroy men, but get the available places and improve their spirit to its actual value ”²⁴.

The debates in the Romanian written press of the XIXth century shall thus make a contribution to the complete contour of the feminine profile; this had for centuries been dominated by the roles of daughter, wife and mother. A new dimension has gradually been developed, through successive add-ons – that of the woman as a social actor, and by extension, as a citizen with limited rights for the moment. Women become gradually topics of history, they become directly involved in this debate over the role that they should have in society. The whole debate is recorded in the written press; actually the written press is one of the favourite environments of the XIXth

²² ***, *Cateva cuvinte asupra cestiunei femeiloru*, in “Amiculu Familiei”, no. 11, December 4th / 16th 1879, p. 94.

²³ *Ibidem*.

²⁴ *Ibidem*.

century's intellectuals that got involved in the feminine profile problematic.

URBAN MODERNIZATION AND GOVERNMENT POLICIES. THE EXAMPLE OF THE TOWN OF REGHIN (THE SECOND HALF OF THE 19TH CENTURY)

Maria Dan*

Abstract

Transylvania enters the 19th century on a path of deep reforms, which will erase the medieval legacy and will consecrate, in terms of urban evolution, a modern model. The guidelines of this evolution are outlined by State policies but, at the same time, the variety of local and regional forces generates different rhythms, producing different versions. Between the Revolution of 1848 and World War I, the town of Reghin, founded in the 13th century by a Saxon population, adheres to an urban model through industrialisation, demographic growth, town planning and diversification of cultural and social activities. However, the major challenge and, concurrently, the materialisation of modernity in this area are the change of the ethnic and social structure.

Keywords: *Modernization, Urban Evolution, State Policies, Local Diversity*

Modernity is a slippery concept, with no firm base in time or place and with no clearly defined characteristics; its features differ with each authority¹. All theories and perspectives upon its definition, periodization, characteristics and consequences substantiate there is no single modernization theory. Recent approaches to this problem are even talking in terms of "alternative modernities". These ways of thinking stress the variety of local, regional, and global forces whose combination shapes the particular histories of modernity, producing different versions in different places². In this context, each study on the modernity of local or regional communities could enrich the overall picture, reflecting the extent to which the major processes of modernity have affected daily life of common person.

Our study, which is part of a broader research on the modernization process of a local community that is representative for Transylvania of the 19th century through its character and structure, deals with one of the fundamental characteristics of modernization: urbanization. My intention is to capture the impact of State policies on the modern evolution of urban areas.

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¹ Jack Goody, *The European Family. An Historico-Anthropological Essay*, Oxford, Blackwell Publishers Ltd, 2000, p. 12.

² Timothy Mitchell (ed.), *Questions of Modernity*, Minneapolis, University of Minnesota Press, 2000, p. XII.

Urban development has depended and still largely depends on the interconnection of geographical environment, traditions and economic potential, social and cultural developments, developments that are outlined by the Government policies. Nevertheless, the cosmopolitan, multi-ethnic and multi-denominational structure of the Transylvanian province often triggered inconsistencies as far as the priorities of the Government policies and those of the ethnic communities were concerned, which led to the diversity of the modernization project, which surpassed from numerous points of view the options of the Governments³.

Founded by a Saxon population in the 13th century, in the context of the colonization policy practiced by the Hungarian Kings, the town of Reghin became in the next centuries an important trade centre in the area. The privileges enjoyed by the Saxons have greatly contributed to its economic development and prosperity. Although surrounded by strong Romanian and Hungarian communities, in the spirit of medieval tradition, the town had remained closed to the outsiders for centuries.

The Austrian conquest and Vienna's policy of integration opened the road to profound transformations. Undoubtedly, the practice of the 18th century Habsburg's reformism triggered a process, which, in spite of Metternich's absolutism could not be stopped. The existing political and social order was strongly contested by the Revolution of 1848. In terms of urban evolution, the period between 1848 and the World War I marks the entry on the path of deep reforms, which will erase the medieval legacy and will consecrate the modern urban model.

Considerably affected by the conflicts in the year 1848 and 1849⁴ Reghin owes its subsequent development mainly to Government policies. The government loan amounting to 210,000 florins granted to the town in 1850 represents the first impetus towards economic and social recovery after the tragedy in the year 1848. The economic liberalism promoted in Vienna in the era of neo-absolutism, the dissolution of guilds, the regulation of ownership, as well as the laws governing the protection of national capital, create a favourable environment for the development of the market economy and production. In addition to the traditional artisans, the merchants are more and more

³ Liviu Maior, "Asociaționismul transilvan (sfârșitul secolului al XIX-lea și începutul secolului al XX-lea)", in Ioan Bolovan, Sorina Paula Bolovan (coord.), *Schimbare și devenire în istoria României*, Cluj-Napoca, Centrul de Studii Transilvane, 2008, p. 92.

⁴ On November 1st, 1848, the town of Reghin was assaulted and burned to the ground by the Seklers.

present, the growing activity of whom results in the creation of the first associations and businesses. Indeed, at first, the factories in the town are small since the owners work with few employees and use a small number of machines, but their activity develops systematically and the signs of industrialisation are more and more conspicuous. In this way, a strong argument is the “inventory” of the inhabitants earning their living by working in the industrial sector. Thus, if in 1885, 21.65% of the overall population were employed in industry, within five years this percentage reached 56.40%. In this manner, at the beginning of the 20th century, there were 36 factories in Reghin that produced timber, parquetry, slats for furniture; there were also 2 steam mills, 4 spirits factories, leather factories, tanning houses, one carriage factory, one joinery shop, which had 30 employees in 1905, one hatters shop, one foundry, one brick factory. The growth of the industrial activity led to the establishment of a power plant, which was ready in 1911 when there were 42 operating electric engines in town⁵.

The city is gradually connecting to the economic life of the Dualist State since the factories in Reghin export their products outside the boundaries of the Province, and even of the Monarchy⁶. At the beginning of the 20th century, the entrepreneurs in Reghin participate in international fairs in Bucharest, Budapest, London, and they even organise the first local industrial fairs⁷.

The development of the industrial activity is supported by town planning through training of the Mureş and Gurghiu rivers, the development of the Reghin-Toplița road and the commissioning of the Tirgu-Mureş-Reghin-Deda-Ciceu-Braşov railway⁸ and the Reghin-Lăpuşna narrow gauge railway⁹. In addition, the town planning criteria in Reghin are enriched by organisation and development works: the streets are paved, the power and water supply and sewerage systems are built, and the town is connected to the telephone circuit. The Town Hall and the Law Court are built and so are the first post office and the first

⁵ See Mihai Szabo, *Reghinul în a doua jumătate a secolului al XIX-lea și începutul secolului al XX-lea (1848-1849)*, in “Marisia”, vol. XV-XXII, 1992, pp. 206-213.

⁶ At the end of the 19th century, the factories in Reghin were exporting especially lumbers in countries such as Germany, Bulgaria and even Egypt.

⁷ See Mihai Szabo, *op. cit.*, p. 213.

⁸ This railway was built and commissioned by sections: Tirgu Mureş-Reghin in 1885, Reghin-Deda in 1906, and finally Deda-Ciceu in 1909.

⁹ Mihai Szabo, *op. cit.* p. 214.

railway station¹⁰. All this constitutes the framework of a modern urban structure.

This economic development influenced the dynamic of the human factor. Between the Revolution of 1848 and World War I, the population in the area of Reghin grew with 82.41% - i.e., 5323 people¹¹. Comparing, the area under analysis to the Province and the Monarchy it was part of, one may note that demographic growth exceeds the general recorded figures. Within the same time frames, Transylvania registers a growth of 47.40%, whereas in the Habsburg Monarchy (the Austro-Hungarian Monarchy after 1867), there is a 58.20% growth¹². The demographic evolution in Reghin indicates the dynamic of the Transylvanian population, which was not at all linear as the specificity of the economic and social development generated variations and different growth rates even within the same area¹³.

Economic progress, urban development, the growth of the human factors led to a different meaning of leisure. Gradually, the bourgeois culture is arising. The theatre, the press, the choirs, the orchestras, the amateur theatricals, different associations are all an indication of a new urban lifestyle¹⁴.

Unlike other small provincial towns, in which, until the 1860s, the cultural life was limited to the activities organised by schools and the rare performances of the strolling players¹⁵, in Reghin, the first cultural societies are created at the end of the 18th century; in 1788, the first “reading hall” is created and attended by intellectuals of different nationalities. On the eve of the Revolution of 1848, the Saxon community, as well as the Hungarian community benefit from reading clubs that are annually increasing their collections: in the second half of the 19th century, there were 1,000 volumes and subscriptions registered for the current newspapers¹⁶. In the second half of the 19th century, the number of these societies considerably increases and

¹⁰ At the beginning of the 20th century, four trains (two passenger trains and two goods trains) were arriving at and departing from the Reghin railway station daily.

¹¹ See the 1850 and 1910 censuses,

URL: <http://varga.adatbank.transindex.ro/?pg=3&action=etnik&id=601>, Accessed: September 17th 2011.

¹² Ioan-Aurel Pop, Thomas Năgler, Magyari Andras (coord.), *Istoria Transilvaniei*, vol. III, Cluj-Napoca, Centrul de Studii Transilvane, 2008, p. 481.

¹³ *Ibidem*, p. 479.

¹⁴ Păl Judith, *Procesul de urbanizare în scaunele secuiești în secolul al XIX-lea*, Cluj-Napoca, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 1999, p. 361.

¹⁵ *Ibidem*.

¹⁶ Marin Șara, “Contribuția la cunoașterea istoriei bibliotecilor reghinene”, in *Reghinul Cultural*, Reghin, Biblioteca Municipală ”Petru Maior”, 1992, p. 94.

they have a more and more active role in the life of the town. In 1867, the first casino is established, followed by a second one in 1894. In 1860, a choir of the German inhabitants is created, followed by the “Hungarian Citizens Music Society” in 1883¹⁷. These societies organise different types of performances, some of which for the purpose of raising funds for their own upkeep. Moreover, they participate in the organisation of different anniversary events. For example, in 1905, “The Hungarian Citizens Choir” opens the ceremony of the 15th of March by solemnly interpreting the *Himnusz*, singing kuruc songs and closing the evening with the famous *Szózat*¹⁸. Towards the end of the century, the sports activities also developed. As of 1895, as part of the leisure park of the town, there was a swimming pool, a swimming school and a playing field. The sports associations participated in the cultural and social life of the town by organising different balls and feasts. In 1905, the “Reghin Association of Cyclists” organised a ball in the main hall of the town hotel where different types of dance were presented on bicycles, which were adorned by the members of the association¹⁹.

For the Romanian community, the event that had a major impact on the cultural and political life was the creation of the *Despărțământul Reghin al Astei*. Before this local institution was created, the intellectuals of Reghin took part in cultural activities by attending the Hungarian and Saxon cultural societies’ events or by collaborating with Romanian magazines, such as *Gazeta Transilvaniei*, *Foaia școlastică*, *Telegraful Român*²⁰. At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, in the context of a more and more hostile policy in terms of national affirmation, the cultural societies allowed the maintenance and affirmation of a shared identity. *Despărțământul Reghin al Astei* together with other societies established by the Romanians in Reghin (*Reuniunea învățătorilor greco-catolici*, *Societatea pentru un fond de teatru românesc*, *Reuniunea meseriașilor români*) had a leading role in educating the Romanian population in the area

¹⁷ Mihai Szabo, *op.cit.* p. 220.

¹⁸ *Morosvölgy*, no. 10, March 5th, 1905, p. 3.

¹⁹ *Ibidem*, no. 21, May 2nd, 1905, p. 5.

²⁰ The Romanians of Reghin are among the subscribers to the first Romanian cultural periodicals: the merchant Ioan Marinovici to *Biblioteca românească*, the first literary review published in the Romanian by Zaharia Carcalechi in Buda, the archbishop Mihai Crișan and the landowners Ioan Pop Maior and Șerban Lupu to *Gazeta Transilvaniei* and *Organul Național*. Also, the Romanian school of Reghin is among the first subscribers to *Organul Național*.

through frequent cultural actions (theatre performances, public speeches, folklore socials), and also through the libraries set up.

The expansion of cultural life, the propagation of mass culture is evidently based on the development of modern schools. Between the Revolution of 1848 and World War I, the evolution of the Transylvanian schools was guided by the Government policies of Vienna and then Budapest, the aim of which was to transform the schools in supportive instruments for political systems. Despite the limitations of the Viennese school policies, which promoted centralism and absolute control of educational institutions, the reform initiated by Leon Thun led the Transylvanian education towards modernity and provided more practical and pragmatic features.²¹ The new current social context generated by industrialisation imposed in the Reghin area the necessity of establishment of vocational schools, and thus, in 1884, the first vocational school was founded²². Moreover, denominational schools continued to function and expand together with the vocational schools. Starting with the end of the 18th century, there was a Greek Catholic school, the first on the Mureş Valley. The Roman Catholics coordinated two schools, out of which one girls' school since 1860; however, it was only in the year 1875 that these two schools had their own place of residence. A Reformed denominational school was founded in 1860 and, at the end of the 19th century; the developing Jewish community opened its own private school²³. The renovations and the expansion of these schools towards the end of the century are an indication of the growing interest for education of the urban population.

However, the major challenge and, concurrently, the materialisation of modernity in the Reghin area are, in our opinion, the change of the ethnic and social structure. The roots of these transformations are to be found in the Habsburg conquest. The Austrian policy in terms of subjection by counteracting the position of the three nations and four religions led to the creation of the Greek Catholic Church, thus generating a new alteration of the denominational structure, after that of the Reformation. The major consequence of Habsburg reformism for the Reghin area was the fact that the town became "opened" to the "others" and so, the Romanian and Hungarian population

²¹ Nicolae Albu, *Istoria școlilor românești din Transilvania între 1800-1867*, București, Editura Didactică și Pedagogică, 1971, p. 159.

²² Mihai Szabo, *op.cit.* p. 217.

²³ *Ibidem*, pp. 213-217.

progressively gained access to the structures of the town. These profound transformations were strongly felt by the traditional inhabitants. A perfect example of these emotions is a description made by one of the most representative figures of the 19th century in Reghin, Joseph Haltrich²⁴. "Reghin as it is today is the creation of modernity and perhaps no other place throughout the country has changed so much in the last hundred years, in all its relations and in all its aspects"²⁵.

A new alteration of the ethnic and social structure of the area takes place under the dualist regime in the context of the policy of the Hungarian State to create a single nation, the Hungarian nation. The censuses conducted by the authorities in the second half of the 19th century prove the proportion of these changes. Thus, at the beginning of the 1850s, there were 644 Romanians, 556 Hungarians, 2,805 Saxons, and 159 Germans in town. There were also a small Jewish community of 40 people, 6 Armenians, 2 gipsies and 15 other nationalities. The census of 1880 reveals that the number of Hungarian people tripled, whereas the Romanian and the German population increased with 10%, as compared to the 430.03% percentage of growth of the Hungarian population²⁶. The Magyarisation of towns during the dualist regime through the assimilation of the German bourgeoisie, the settlement and the Magyarisation of Jewish people, is a general phenomenon in the entire Transylvanian province. The effects of the economic laws, freedom in what trades are concerned and the dissolution of guilds have strongly shaken the economic power of the Saxons and triggered their massive emigration²⁷. In the Reghin area, even though the German population was still economically dominant (out of the 980 houses in 1910, 598 are owned by the Saxons (61%) and 382 by other inhabitants of different ethnic groups (39%)²⁸), their supremacy was more and more disputed by the rise of the

²⁴ Joseph Haltrich was a Saxon philologist, best known as a folk collector.

²⁵ The excerpt is part of a monograph written by J. Haltrich in 1858, entitled *Zur Geschichte von Sächsisch-Regen seit dem letzten hundert Jahren*. *apud.* Marian Zăloagă, "Scriind istoria urbei în secolul al XIX-lea transilvan - Cazul Reghinului Săsesc", in *Reghinul Cultural*, Reghin, Biblioteca Municipală "Petru Maior", 2004, p. 133.

²⁶ See the 1850 and 1880 Censuses,

URL: <http://varga.adatbank.transindex.ro/?pg=3&action=etnik&id=601>, Accessed: September 17th 2011.

²⁷ See Ioan-Aurel Pop, Thomas Năgler, Magyari Andras (coord.), *op. cit.*, pp. 494-501.

²⁸ See the 1910 Census.

URL: <http://varga.adatbank.transindex.ro/?pg=3&action=etnik&id=601>, Accessed: September 17th 2011.

Romanian and Hungarian bourgeoisie. The Government policies in Budapest corresponding to their own interests favoured the expansion of the Hungarian element, but they also allowed a strong activity of the non-Hungarian communities by the right of association, which became one of the main means of supporting national identity. The 19th century is the century of cultural exchanges and transfers, but also of cultural competitions on account of the awareness that culture derives from politics²⁹.

To conclude with, between the Revolution of 1848 and World War I, the town of Reghin adhered to an urban model through industrialisation, demographic growth, town planning and diversification of cultural and social activities. The guidelines of all these transformations were outlined by State policies but, at the same time, the rhythm of these evolutions was strongly influenced by local specificities. The penetration of Hungarians and Romanians in the town, which was a major consequence of the 18th and 19th century reforms, generated progress in the long term as ethnic diversity, despite inherent tensions, favours competition and mutual productive exchanges.

²⁹ See Liviu Maior, *op. cit.* pp. 90-100.

NATIONAL IDENTITY. CONFESSIONAL IDENTITY. ROMANIANS IN TRANSYLVANIA IN THE SECOND HALF OF THE NINETEENTH CENTURY

Oana Habor*

Abstract

Inside deeply religious bounds, such as Transylvania, confession plays an important role in the effort to emphasize the identity phenomenon. Within the same nation, two Churches competed for the title of National Church. The relationship between the two faiths was not infrequently affected, in part because each Church attempted by various means to prove its own identity. The Romanians' position of inferiority compared to the other ethnic groups in Transylvania and the possible threat coming from "the other" are elements that also drafted the definition of identity. The two Romanian Churches engaged in the struggle to preserve national identity and they gradually evolved from a Church autonomy into a political one. The Romanian identity discourse outlines into a point where the confessional and political elements become thoroughly intertwined. At the end of the nineteenth century and given the political context, national identity is preserved with the joint effort of both ecclesiastical and political elites despite the differences. Although the secular spirit gains ground, the Church has undoubtedly its extremely important role in preserving and defending a, not only religious but also national right.

Keywords: *National Identity, Confessional Identity, the Romanian Orthodox Church, the Romanian Greek Catholic Church*

Inside deeply religious frames, such as Transylvania, confession plays an important role in the effort to emphasize the identity phenomenon. Transylvania and the Romanian Churches: the Orthodox and the Greek Catholic Church. For the Romanians, these two represented not only the frame of the spiritual life, but also the relationship with the Nation. Being *Orthodox* or *Uniate* meant... *being Romanian*.

Key moments such as the Revolution of 1848, the liberal regime of the 60s', raising the rank of the dioceses to the one of Metropolitan See and implicitly the emancipation from the foreign jurisdiction, the establishment of the dualist regime, the project of the Hungarian Catholic autonomy (seen as a real danger by the Greek Catholic Church) provided a significant contribution to the identity discourse maturation.

The Revolution of 1848 would gradually change the concept about the identity discourse from mainly religious bases to those of a more lay nature. Then, in 1848, national solidarity would prevail at

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the expense of the religious one¹. The generation after 1830 shares a lay spirit, Barițiu's papers being an excellent way of spreading the new ideas².

Barițiu is the one demanding, in order to annihilate the differences upon dogmatic themes, the clergy not to enter into polemics that generate arguments, the priest keeping away from "deceivers that the sanctimoniously cheat people, or over fanatics that fight for decades for a single word, for an and or another, equally misunderstood from Greek or Hebraic or Chaldean language". August Treboniu Laurian would advocate for the "Romanian law" against religious disunion³.

National solidarity is what prevails. Although the authorities tried religious disunion by confirming meetings based only on religious criteria, the national assemblies gain ground. Barițiu thought that, "arguing on earth about things that have not even been defined in Heaven does not solve the nation's problem"⁴. The political context of 1848 did not allow religious dissensions. Therefore, it called for a Romanian Church and a Romanian Metropolitan See, without specifying any details about being Uniate or Orthodox. At 1848 The Metropolitan See appeared rather independent, both The Greek-Catholic Metropolitan See and The Orthodox Metropolitan See being part of it, but without mentioning, for example, which ecclesiastical forum it obeys⁵.

Religion, Nation and "the good emperor myth" intersect. Over the years expressing a sense of affiliation to the throne played not an insignificant role. Romanians regarded the emperor as a Catholic, it is true, but Christian, while the idea of a supposed Hungarian emperor, Calvin, was denigrated. Romanians threatened that "the church steeple rooster would come down and be replaced with the cross"⁶.

The powerful symbol of nationalism now said its word. In fact, this was the most serious disagreement between intellectuals and ecclesiastical hierarchy. Intellectuals saw the religious disputes as the key of division. A society based on reason rather than superstition and mysticism⁷.

¹ Ladislau Gyémánt, *Mișcarea națională a românilor din Transilvania între anii 1790-1848*, București, Editura Științifică și Enciclopedică, 1986, p. 455.

² *Ibidem*, p. 456.

³ Ciprian Ghișa, *Biserica Greco-catolică din Transilvania (1700-1850). Elaborarea discursului identitar*, Cluj-Napoca, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 2006, p. 271.

⁴ Ladislau Gyémánt, *op. cit.*, p. 461.

⁵ Sorin Mitu, *Geneza identității naționale la românii ardeleni*, București, Editura Humanitas, 2007, p. 373.

⁶ Liviu Maior, *Habsburgi și români. De la loialitate dinastică la identitate națională*, București, Editura Enciclopedică, 2006, p. 191.

⁷ Keith Hitchins, *Conștiința națională și acțiune politică la românii din Transilvania 1700-1868*, Cluj-Napoca, Editura Dacia, 1987, pp. 134-136.

Bărnuțiu's words summarize in a striking manner the new spirit that prevailed: "what water is for fish, air is for birds and for all living things, what sun is for plant growth, word for thinking, this is the nationality of each nation... through it we communicate today with our parents who lived thousands of years before, through it our great-grandchildren and posterity will know us over thousands of years..."⁸

In defining the identity, the speech of the ecclesiastical hierarchy and the one of the political elite intercross more and more. The election of the new bishop, after the death of Vasile Moga gives the laymen the opportunity to claim the laics' right to be a part in the appointment, leaving the impression that this act has not only a religious significance but a national one too. Moreover, the demand to improve the synodal institution is frequently found as a necessity to impose a democratic line in the life of both Orthodox and Uniate Churches. The regular convening of the council is a rule of the Eastern Church⁹. The Synod was considered a collective organization, the only one able to certify issues related to Church¹⁰. Similarly, the desire of the Karlowitz hierarchy to impose in the school field would meet rather strong resistance from the secular elements¹¹.

The Revolution of 1848 represented the triumph of the modern idea of nation, a solidarity based upon the uniform ideology imperative in the national program. The political leaders of the time understood it¹². The liberal and democratic idea of national states comes into its own, for the first time, being present in the shape of national unitary state imperative and therefore peoples' right to self-determination¹³.

But the ecclesiastical hierarchy's and the political leaders' opinions concerning the importance of the Church mission were not the same. While religion gave the Church the dominant role in supporting the identity discourse, intellectuals no longer trusted the primary role played by the bishops, seeing the Church as a tool that

⁸ Camil Mureșanu, "Reflecții despre Simion Bărnuțiu- gânditorul politic", in Sorin Mitu, Rudolf Grăf, Ana Sima, Ion Cârja (coord.), *Biserică, Societate, Identitate. In Honorum Nicolae Bocșan*, Cluj-Napoca, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 2007, p. 245.

⁹ George Em. Marica, Iosif Hajós, Călina Mare, Constantin Rusu (coord.), *Ideologia generației de la 1848 din Transilvania*, București, Editura Polirom, 1968, pp. 254-255.

¹⁰ Simion Retegan, *Reconstrucția politică a Transilvaniei (1861-1863)*, Cluj-Napoca, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 2004, p. 41.

¹¹ Ladislau Gyémánt, *op.cit.*, p. 458.

¹² Nicolae Bocșan, *Ideea de națiune la românii din Transilvania și Banat. Secolul al XIX-lea*, Cluj-Napoca, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 1997, p. 134.

¹³ *Ibidem*, p. 192.

contributes to national emancipation¹⁴. However, the bishops were recognized as leaders of the nation, they stood at the head of delegations, negotiated with the Hungarian government, signed memoranda and petitions on behalf of the people.

The petitions and memoranda were drafted by representatives of both the religious sphere, (e.g. Alexandru Șterca Șuluțiu, Andrei Șaguna), and the rural *intelligentia* including priests and teachers, but also the new elite dominated by the secular spirit. They were educated in Romanian schools (Sibiu, Blaj, Arad or Năsăud) that propagated national ideas¹⁵.

In the petitions and memoranda advocating religious and political autonomy there were claims based on the same grounds. Thus it is raised the noble origin of the people, the fidelity to the dynasty and, for example, the proof of loyalty to the emperor during military clashes in the revolution. The political and religious administration based on the national argument, the National Congress and the National Assembly are claims that were included in the petition to the emperor on 25 February 1849¹⁶.

In the Christmas pastoral (1849), the loyalty to the throne is clearly expressed: "Today, every Romanian is proud and high-minded about his nation because he is a member of the nation pleasant to the other just and fair compatriot nations. Be glad that you could prove our good Emperor and country that you are a nation and you know your place as a nation..."¹⁷ Until 1867, the dynastic loyalty continued to play an important role. Alexandru Dobra stated: "with me every Romanian Greek-Catholic, and also all those who have a national sense, even if they chose another religion, for the crown woven of His Majesty for the church and our nation is his monarchy"¹⁸.

Șaguna saw a special connection between Orthodoxy and Nation. The values preached by the Church are to be followed by the nation. Although convinced by the growing impact of nationalism, Șaguna refused to regard the Church as a mean of promoting the national interests. The Church respected the government policy and laws, but it was the duty of the authorities to respect its rights. It did not agree with the priestcraft, as it did not allow the intellectuals to

¹⁴ Keith Hitchens, *Conștiință națională și acțiune politică...*, p. 132.

¹⁵ Ladislau Gyémánt, *op. cit.*, p. 477.

¹⁶ Ion Cârja, "Românii ardeleni și puterea imperială austriacă în perioada 1849-1851. Considerații privind ideologia mișcării petiționare românești", in Nicolae Bocșan, Sorin Mitu, Toader Nicoară (coord.), *Identitate și alteritate. Studii de imagologie*, vol. II, Cluj-Napoca, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 1998, pp. 249-251.

¹⁷ Liviu Maior, *op. cit.*, pp. 199-200.

¹⁸ Nicolae Bocșan, Camelia Vulea, *La începuturile episcopiei Lugojului. Studii și documente*, Cluj-Napoca, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 2003, p. 351.

engage in spiritual matters, except those related to economy and education. The canon law was a matter depending on the clergy¹⁹.

But the secular spirit began to gain ground even to some members of the Church. Chosen to be editor of the *Telegraful Român*, Nicolae Cristea supported the land reform and the idea of a middle class²⁰.

When realizing the complicated political situation and the need to compose a delegation representing its interests in Vienna, the Orthodox Metropolitan also writes to Șuluțiu about the need for “understanding, care and cooperation”²¹. National solidarity seems to triumph, the Uniate Church’s representative responds: “we hope, in fact we expect from the children of our Church and nation, full agreement, full obedience, we would not work in secret without the agreement and permission of our nation’s children of both faiths”. Alexandru Șterca Șuluțiu and Andrei Șaguna address to the Transylvania province Government requesting approval for a meeting in Sibiu in order to set up the frames of a Romanian cultural society.

The Uniate Metropolitan congratulates Andrei Șaguna for his work in the Imperial Senate: “So, for this nationalist truth and patriotic zeal shown, the unshaken sincere and ardent love for our common nationality and language, so beautifully demonstrated a merge...”²²

But in late 1861, the relations between Blaj and Sibiu seriously deteriorated due to religious conflicts. Differences in view occurred on the background of sending delegations to the National Conference, the program and its regulations, but also inconsistencies regarding the Diet of 1863. Requests for cooperation were renewed after the dissolution of the Diet in 1865, when both metropolitans were advised to resume talks for a united front for the national problem²³.

The two Romanian Churches invoked their own identity trying to argue that political unity is not equal to the hierarchical order. Subordination to the Karlowitz hierarchy is considered to be non-canonical.

For each Church, the Metropolitan See is a historical truth. The Metropolitans’ voices are eloquent. The Metropolitan See of Alba

¹⁹ Keith Hitchens, *Conștiință națională și acțiune politică...*, pp. 138-142.

²⁰ *Ibidem*, p. 145.

²¹ Simion Retegan (coord.), *Mișcarea națională a românilor din Transilvania între 1849-1918. Documente*. Vol. III, 30 iulie 1859-26 februarie 1861, București, Editura Academiei Române, 2006, p. 185, p. 360.

²² *Ibidem*, p. 136.

²³ Nicolae Bocșan, Ioan-Vasile Leb, Gabriel Gârdan, Pavel Vesa, Bogdan Ivanov (coord.), *Andrei Șaguna, Corespondență*, vol. I/1, Cluj-Napoca, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 2005, p. 75.

Iulia is claimed by both sides as an identity mark: both religious and national. From here to the proselytizing accusations there is little. The competition between the Orthodox and the Uniate people appears to be open, especially given that the Greek Catholics are the first to profit by the Metropolitan See restoration. For the Uniate Church, this event is an extra opportunity to assert its strong connection with Rome, the center that maintains the links between religion and nation.

Between 1860 and 1864, the Romanian metropolitans played a leading role in the national movement. Intellectuals were still convinced of Șaguna's prestige. However, after the dissolution of the Diet, the differences of opinion were obvious and the intellectuals decided to act by themselves in the autumn of 1866. The new religion was now nationalism, the one justifying the basic principles of society. The Orthodox Metropolitan was replaced (being the president of *Astra*), and the National Church Congress held after raising to the rank of Metropolitan See of the Orthodox diocese have expressed a desire to have a stronger voice when it came to decide on Church matters. Hierarchy would lose their influence more and more²⁴, but the political system after 1867 brought together the laity and clergy to support the school and the Church as the two key elements of national identity.

The Catholic autonomy is seen as a threat to the national and religious identity. The two parties: the Hungarians and the Romanians have different views not only about the religious principle but also the national one. If the term *schismatic* had been so far applied to the religious disputes between the Orthodox and the Greek-Catholics, Hungarians are now those who called both the Uniate and the Orthodox, *schismatics*. Magyarization entered on the fields belonging to the Church and this was inconceivable.

The Florentin Council, the Union with Rome, the establishment of Metropolitan Sees, the law of 1868, are arguments that come to strengthen their own identity. Rome is seen not only as the center of the faith but also of the nation. Against Hungarian, the Romanian language is viewed as a mean of preserving the individuality.

At that time, National Congresses convened by the political elite stressed the special connection between the Church and Nation. The desire for a Uniate Church joint synod reunion remains a mark of individuality of this Church.

Since 1867, in the context of new policy measures, confessionalism earns a political tinge too. The attitude towards the Budapest government's passivism is symbolized by those who revolved towards Blaj, while activism revolved around the interests

²⁴ Keith Hitchens, *Conștiință națională și acțiune politică...*, pp. 147-151.

promoted by Șaguna. A clearer separation of the religious and political issues will be achieved in the moment the political parties had established. The assembly in Miercurea Ciuc, assembly held without the participation of bishops declared itself against activism.

After the installation of Ioan Vancea in the Metropolitan See, there was an attempt to persuade the two Metropolitans in terms of cooperation. The Committee of Sibiu, in memory of the past and national solidarity, addressed to Sibiu and Blaj to this effect. But the different visions of the two Metropolitans said their word again²⁵.

After the death of Andrei Șaguna and Alexandru Șterca Șuluțiu there is an increasing involvement of the politicians in the affairs related to the Church. Therefore, those who expressed their willingness to actively participate in the life of the Church supported Timotei Cipariu as a candidate. As for the Orthodox, the national club run by Vincențiu Babeș supported Miron Romanul. The Metropolitan Miron Romanul involved in politics. He founded the Constitutional or Moderate Party, criticized the policy pursued by the National Party, the passivism promoted by the latter, as National Party members, in turn, blamed him for not sufficiently supporting the political struggle. In 1896, he advised the Romanians not to participate in celebrations dedicated to the Millennium of the of the Hungarian State foundation²⁶. The National Congress members were led by Miron Romanul to Vienna voting against the Trefort Law. In 1883, the same Metropolitan protested against introducing Hungarian language in secondary schools and the establishment of kindergardens in Hungarian²⁷. He felt that: “widening in all parts the instruction and popular culture, moralizing and disciplining the clergy and our people and staying away this from foreign influences, the eradication of many abuses in the Church, in elections and in our autonomy, avoiding any influences that would jeopardize the legal right, as good a relationship as possible with the brothers compatriots of other confession...”²⁸

The magyarization policy, the Budapest government’s wish to introduce Hungarian and religious education led again the efforts of the two Churches to combine. Thus, in 1909, the Orthodox Metropolitan Ioan Mețianu together with Ioan Micu Moldovan and

²⁵ Nicolae Bocșan, Ioan-Vasile Leb, Gabriel Gărdan, Pavel Vesa, Bogdan Ivanov (coord.), *op.cit.*, pp. 84-86.

²⁶ Keith Hitchins, *Afirmarea Națiunii și mișcarea națională a românilor din Transilvania 1860-1914*, București, Editura Enciclopedică, București, 2000, p. 167.

²⁷ Mircea Păcurariu, *Istoria Bisericii Ortodoxe Române (secolele XIX-XX)*, vol. III, București, Editura Institutului Biblic și de Misiune al Bisericii Ortodoxe Române, 1994, p. 217.

²⁸ Liviu Maior, *op. cit.*, pp. 205-206.

Augustin Bunea took a stand on this political approach²⁹. In fact, Miron Romanul and Ioan Vancea formed delegations in regard of Hungarian language problems. But they have not appeared together in Vienna.

Vasile Mangra participated in the political life in Arad and was a former Member of Parliament in Budapest in the government led by Tisza. Mangra supported the involvement of the Church members in politics, highlighting the priest's vocation and its implications vis a vis the Church and State³⁰.

The importance of the memorandum is underlined by Mangra at a meeting which he convened in front of a cathedral in Arad. The Orthodox and Uniate clergy was called to inform parishioners about the movement's direction and to draw attention to the Vienna court on the effects of the Hungarian government. Accused on the bases of participating in the Memorandum movement, Vasile Mangra summarized the religion-nation relationship in the late nineteenth century: "I went into Parliament under my desires and rights and as a citizen and member of the Romanian Orthodox Church whose national character and independence, every Romanian Orthodox Christian is obliged to sustain and to defend on all legal and moral grounds"³¹.

The liberal era enabled many Romanians to access to public functions. This, along with the increasing number of intellectuals and the growing importance of the press has helped to crystallize a political elite that, by its connections to Vienna and Budapest facilitated the process of secularization³². In one of the circulars, Bishop Ioan Alexi speaking about the importance of secular and sacred functions condemned the participation of the priests in the political actions³³.

Controversies appeared in the educational field too: mixed schools, object of dissension between the two Churches (seen as a possible attempt against identity through the religious proselytism). Then, the divisions between clergy and laity, the latter being against the participation of the clergy in the matter of education. Although for the representatives of the Church "education should not confine to transforming the child into a man and citizen ready to contribute with all his means to society's interests, willing to sacrifice his interest for the general happiness", still the state's duty is

²⁹ Keith Hitchens, *Afirmarea Națiunii și mișcarea națională...*, pp. 208-209.

³⁰ Marius Eppel, *Un mitropolit și epoca sa - Vasile Mangra (1850-1918)*, Cluj-Napoca, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 2006, p. 436.

³¹ Idem, *Vasile Mangra. Activitatea politică 1875-1918*, Cluj-Napoca, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 2004, pp. 65-68.

³² Nicolae Bocșan, Ioan-Vasile Leb, Gabriel Gârdan, Pavel Vesa, Bogdan Ivanov (coord.), *op.cit.*, p. 77.

³³ Simion Retegan (coord.), *op. cit.*, pp. 191-194.

particularly to solve the material issues³⁴. For the intellectuals, school must be a modern environment dominated by the secular spirit. But the dualist era established a different role for school. Loyal citizens had to be good Hungarians too and the government in Budapest made a target of its policy out of this matter³⁵.

National identity is seen from different angles by the two Romanian Churches. From the Orthodox point of view, identity was compromised when the Union with Rome took place, in fact, at the moment of the covenant with the "enemy nation" under certain advantages. On the other hand, the Greek Catholics are those who argue that the Union had just saved the people from national death, unlike those who had fallen once in the hand of "Fanar and Caloviț". Through the connection with Latin, with the Catholic universalism, the Uniate Church is directed towards progress, while, under the auspices of Byzantium by the twinning with the Greeks and Slavs, the Orthodox Church is doomed to decay. Not only the Orthodox Church in Transylvania but also the Romanian Kingdom is accused of serving the interests of the state exclusively, promoting itself according to the state policy³⁶. Both Churches, therefore, accuse each other at the expense of denationalization. The Orthodox people blame Rome, the Uniate behalf, "the powerful tool of denationalization... The Orthodox Church whose head is the Holy Tsar"³⁷.

In 1856, Șaguna sends a letter to Metropolitan Nifon highlighting the uniate danger that "quietly meddle in our flock, parade with Romanian nationality to gain the trust of those who do not know them, cursed the Greeks, Serbs and others that are related through the Church and then began to graft their venom to deceive the Romanians to hate their Church and to deny it"³⁸.

As the basis of national consciousness the connection with Rome is always emphasized: "our great people the Romans, our ancestors the Romans, our grandchildren once the Romans"³⁹.

Iosif Pop Sălăjean summarizes the benefits of the Union: "The advantages of the Union are based on the returning to the primary

³⁴ Biblioteca Academiei Române, Filiala Cluj, Fond *Blaj*, Ms. rom. 151, *Catehism și catehetică*, Blaj, ff. 58-68.

³⁵ Paul Brusanowski, *Învățământul confesional ortodox din Transilvania între anii 1848-1918 între exigențele statului centralizat și principiile autonomiei bisericești*, Cluj-Napoca, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 2005, p. 594.

³⁶ *Ibidem*, p. 73.

³⁷ Augustin Bunea, *Cestiuni din dreptulu și istoria bisericeii românescei unite, studiu apologeticu din incidentulu invecivelaru Gazetei Transilvania și a dlui Nicolae Densușanu aupra Mitropolitulu Vancea și a biserice unite*, I, Blaj, 1893, p. 326.

³⁸ Pavel Cherescu, *Contribuții la studiul Istoriei Bisericii Ortodoxe Române*, Oradea, Editura Adsumus, 2001, p. 209.

³⁹ *Ibidem*, p. 343.

source, in Rome, whence springs life and truth, better knowledge of law and faith, more pleasure and gifts from God, where awakening, enlightenment, culture, morality, holiness, soul salvation, reunion of the nations, Romanians' love towards each other, their peace and happiness, help and relief, Romanian episcopacies, seminaries, clever priesthood with time spent in Hungary and Romanian Metropolitan See, and from here raising the nation, and honor and prestige⁴⁰.

In the disputes between the two Churches, the alphabet problem remained an important religious and national identity matter. The Latin alphabet was supported by the promoters of the Union, an argument in favor of people with Latin names and roots. But the letters were considered a characteristic of the Eastern heritage⁴¹.

In his *Catechism*, Iosif Papp-Szilághi mentioned the advantages of the transition to the Union with Rome (are not only of a spiritual but also the national nature, so, the religious disputes can be set aside)⁴². The religious differences that affect the nation's interest are also mentioned by Alexandru Dobra: "the unfortunate fate of our nation... not just in the same country, in the same town or village, but also in the same home and family, are divided in faith for which they argue"⁴³.

The Uniates only share with the Hungarian Roman Catholics issues related to Catholicism. Solidarity is stated in some issues (as was the resistance to the laws considered by the Wekerle Government), but not in the national liberation movement of Romanians⁴⁴. "But nor can it be about a conflict between religious belief and between national feeling in our hearts, when our blood and faith have nothing to do with those who come against us, when enemy fire is downloaded against our religion and against our nationality... We are and we want to be Romanian and nothing else. We form a Church that is united with that of Rome, which however is not the Roman Catholic and not Hungarian". And there is the threat: "The Hungarian Catholic propaganda should push us finally towards the Orthodoxy"⁴⁵.

⁴⁰ *Ibidem*, pp. 363-364.

⁴¹ Sorin Mitu, *op. cit.*, p. 346.

⁴² Ion Cârja, *Biserică și societate în Transilvania în perioada păstoririi mitropolitului Ioan Vancea (1862-1892)*, Cluj-Napoca, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 2007, p. 240.

⁴³ Nicolae Bocșan, Camelia Vulea, *op. cit.*, p. 197.

⁴⁴ Daniela Mârza, "Identitate și alteritate: românii greco-catolici despre ei înșiși în revista «Unirea» (sfârșitul secolului al XIX-lea, începutul secolului XX)", in Nicolae Bocșan, Sorin Mitu, Toader Nicoară (coord.), *Identitate și alteritate. Studii de istorie politică și culturală*, vol. III, Cluj-Napoca, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 2002, p. 69.

⁴⁵ Lucian Bolcaș, *Chestia autonomiei Bisericii Române Unite în șirul luptelor noastre pentru existența națională*, București, Editura Minerva, 1900, pp. 56-60.

But this religious solidarity with the Hungarians brings huge reproaches from the Orthodox. Thus, in various articles in *Gazeta Transilvaniei* or *Telegraful Român*, the Uniates are blamed that, through communion with the Hungarians, who first let themselves caught in the trap of the advantages and implicitly in that of Magyarization⁴⁶. In his dispute with Nicolae Densușianu, Augustin Bunea argued that as in the official and liturgical language of the people, they are Orthodox allies similarly the United are in communion with the Roman Catholic faith, but not diplomatically.

On the other hand, Bunea argues, while faith may not be national, “true for a nation and not for the other”, the institution of the Church may be national “in this respect in our united Church keeping united the faith with the entire Catholic world in five continents, in its manifestation among the people is however the national Church, with its national ranking, its national institutions and national language”⁴⁷.

The national paradigm gains ground at the expense of religion. Even if they are united with Rome, the Hungarian Roman Catholics consider themselves true Catholics. Communion with the Orthodox rite and language makes them Romanians first, so “schismatics”⁴⁸.

Solidarity efforts did not miss when required: “We, Uniates Romanians, we have nothing against our Romanian Orthodox brothers as such, given that we love them, as persons as Christians, as Romanians” But tensions were often obvious, and not only in the religious field but also in the national one. Each Church tries to demonstrate its superiority and comes with plausible arguments as to certify the contribution offered to the nation’s history⁴⁹. Religious rivalries culminated on the educational realm too, even in villages where we could barely maintain an educational institution, both confessions urging their own school⁵⁰. Augustin Bunea stated: “Those who love their Church and feel happy that they are members in it should not only be satisfied with doing the priestly duty with piety, but warmly embrace all cultural and even the economic and material interests of the people”⁵¹.

Within the same nation, two Churches competed for the title of National Church. The relationship between the two faiths was not infrequently affected, in part because of the fact that each church

⁴⁶ *Ibidem*, p. 70.

⁴⁷ Augustin Bunea, *op. cit.*, pp. 47-49.

⁴⁸ Ion Cârja, *Biserica și societate în Transilvania...*, p. 252.

⁴⁹ *Ibidem*, p. 71.

⁵⁰ Vasile Netea, *Lupta românilor din Transilvania pentru libertatea națională (1848-1881)*, București, Editura Științifică, 1974, p. 138.

⁵¹ Liviu Maior, *op. cit.*, p. 218.

has tried by various means to outline its own identity⁵². The Romanian position of inferiority compared to the other ethnic groups in Transylvania, but also the possible threat from “the other” are elements that drafted the identity definition.

The Uniates build a rather defensive identity discourse, while the Orthodox consider that they have nothing to defend, their confession descending along with the nation. It is undisputed that the two Romanian Churches, engaged in the struggle to preserve national identity, and gradually from a church autonomy they have evolved into a political one. We are dealing with the nationalization of confession, with emphasis on the national character⁵³. The ability to elaborate their own image, the Romanian identity discourse reveals into a point where the confessional and political elements become thoroughly intertwined.

Let's not forget the fact that the ecclesiastical elite who participated in the political emancipation project in the second half of the nineteenth century was very well educated and succeeded in improving the theological education⁵⁴. Church involvement in the political realm was also shown in supporting the election method for candidates for the Diet and for the National Church conventions, or synods held every three years.

In the late nineteenth century, we confront with a decrease illiteracy rate. On the other hand the number of trained is continuously growing, cultural associations and societies are multiplying in villages, priests in turn propagate nationalistic ideas after 1867 with increasing fervor⁵⁵.

For the two Romanian Churches, the identity discourse was formulated around the basic elements such as faith, ritual, and contribution to national history, tradition, national consciousness.

Tradition and ritual were important pillars. The efforts of the two Romanian Churches were highlighted in the struggle for autonomy, both religious, but which takes a national affiliation with the appeal to history. The identity discourse was promoted both by the ecclesiastical elites (then hierarchically towards the clergy and social strata), and the new political class increasingly consistent.

The issue of a possible overlap between ethnicity and religion in defining the Romanian identity was rejected by the Transylvanian

⁵² Nicolae Bocșan, Ioan-Vasile Leb, Gabriel Gărdan, Pavel Vesa, Bogdan Ivanov (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 56.

⁵³ Liviu Maior, *op. cit.*, pp. 197-198.

⁵⁴ Cornel Sigmirean, “Elita ecleziastică românească din Transilvania în epoca modernă. Formarea universitară”, in ***, *Slujitor al Bisericii și al Neamului. Părintele Prof. Univ. Dr. Mircea Păcurariu membru corespondent al Academiei Române la împlinirea vârstei de 70 de ani*, Cluj Napoca, Editura Renașterea, 2002, pp. 599-600.

⁵⁵ Liviu Maior, *op. cit.*, p. 207.

School and Romantics⁵⁶. There were certainly controversies and differences between clergy and laity, different ways of understanding the role of the Church in building the national identity. But the importance of the Orthodox and Uniate Church's voice will not be denied ever. The political elite saw the Church as a national institution and it should not be forgotten that many ministers of the Church shared as citizens the ideology of a party or another⁵⁷.

The regime promoted by Budapest led the priests to get involved in politics to protect the interests of the Church. At the end of the nineteenth century and given the political context, the national identity is preserved with the joint effort of both ecclesiastical and political elites⁵⁸.

Secular spirit would influence ever more. The Romanian law had, in the intellectuals' opinion, to be placed above religious divisions. Although they had their sacred symbols, the National Assembly provides a good example. While nationalism warned by its power a multinational Habsburg empire, the myth of the good emperor loses importance. Now the nations claimed self-determination.

Church saw the confession as the element which defended the national consciousness over time. Here are Andrei Șaguna's words: "... what should I devote you, dear clergy and faithful people of the Greek-Eastern Romanian National Metropolitan See in Hungary and Transylvania... may you recreate the religion, religiosity and morality of your ancestors..."⁵⁹ Similarly, Vasile Erdely talks about "advance of the true Religion to happiness and blossom of the faithful Romanian Nation"⁶⁰. Political elites saw things from another angle. The Church's role was to serve the national emancipation. The Church autonomy gradually moved to political autonomy. The Church pastors and politicians combined their efforts to this effect.

Differences of opinion between the clergy and political elite, and differences between the representatives of the two Romanian Churches. However, the common front was strengthened when national interest demanded it. The policy of Budapest after 1867 gathered together the clergy and laity to support the school and

⁵⁶ Sorin Mitu, *op. cit.*, p. 364.

⁵⁷ Keith Hitchins, *Afirmarea națiunii și mișcarea națională...*, pp. 161-166.

⁵⁸ Valeria Șoroștineanu, "Raporturile dintre greco-catolici și ortodocși în arhiepiscopia Transilvaniei la sfârșitul secolului al XIX-lea", in Nicolae Bocșan, Sorin Mitu, Toader Nicoară (coord.), *Identitate și alteritate. Studii de istorie politică și culturală*, vol. III, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 2002, p. 76.

⁵⁹ ***, *Euchiridionu, adeca Carte manuale de canone ale unei, sântei, sobornicești și apostolesci Biserici cu Comentariu de Andrei Baronu de Șaguna*, Tipografia Arhiepiscopozană, Sibiu, 1871, pp. V-VI.

⁶⁰ B.A.R., Fond *Blaș*, Ms. rom. 694; Vasile Erdely, *Discurs la instalarea ep. Al. Dobra*, Lugoj, s.n., 1856, p. 1.

church as the basis of the national identity. Politicians increasingly involved in church life and part of the ecclesiastical elite increasingly took part in politics (Miron Romanul, Vasile Mangra, etc.).

A society inside which illiteracy is declining, the cultural associations in the traditional village became increases, secular spirit gains ground. It's a new force, a new religion, the one of nationalism, which defends its rights. It is spread by a group of intellectuals who defend national identity, sometimes separately or together with the ecclesiastical elite. But the latter, had undoubtedly its extremely important role in preserving and defending a not only religious but also national right.

THE ELECTIVE REPRESENTATION OF THE ROMANIANS IN THE HUNGARIAN PARLIAMENT

Vlad Popovici*, Ovidiu Iudean**

Abstract

The paper analyses the presence of Romanian representatives in the lower chamber of the Hungarian Parliament between 1869 and 1892. It starts with the prosopographical description of the Romanian MPs and their political affiliation, presented for each elective cycle of the given period. Next, following Adalbert Toth's method, the authors grouped the represented parties in three tendencies (slightly different from Toth's original ones): government parties, Hungarian opposition parties and Romanian national parties. The results show that most of the Romanian MPs (73%) were elected on the lists of the Hungarian government parties, and many of them migrated from the Parliament to bureaucracy during the 1870s. Under such circumstances - given the elective passivity that spread among the Romanians after 1875 and the lack of cohesion inside the national movement - the number of Romanian MPs regressed constantly, from 31 (1869-1872) to 9 (1887-1892). A projection of the geographical distribution of their mandates also shows how the area in which the Romanian MPs were elected grew smaller, from the entire Banat, Western Parts and Maramureş in 1869 to a few scattered colleges in 1892. This regressive process was mainly a result of the violent tactics used by the Tisza government during the elections and of the Romanian elite's withdrawal inside county administration. But it can also be regarded as a sign (among many others) of the Romanian elites' lack of trust in the Hungarian political system, announcing the radical movement of the 1892 Memorandum.

Keywords: Politics, Elective Representation, Parliament, Hungary, MPs, Electoral Geography

Romanian historiography dwelled at length on the significance of year 1869 in the history of Romanians in Hungary and the creation of the first modern national parties in Transylvania and Banat¹. The participation (and also lack of participation) in the political life of Dualist Monarchy on the part of representatives of these parties was also discussed extensively; the topic generated thousands of works but their approach was rather rhetorical than thorough. The numerous collections

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¹ Valeriu Moldovan, *Conferințele Naționale ale românilor de dincoace de Carpați*, Sibiu, Editura "Asociațiunii", 1937, pp. 6-10; Bujor Surdu, *Conferința națională de la Mercurea (1869)*, in "Anuarul Institutului de Istorie din Cluj", VIII (1965), pp. 173-211; Miodrag Milin, *De la autonomism la memorandum. Din problematica vieții politice la românii bănățeni. 1860-1895*, Timișoara, Tipografia Universității din Timișoara, 1986, pp. 16-21.

of documents and correspondence and the large quantity of biographical studies could not compensate for the lack of primary tools for the creation of a prosopographic register of Romanian political elite members (MPs, members of the Chamber of Magnates, leaders of national parties). Teodor V. Păcățian's study remains the only reference work in the field; it is a useful synthesis research, which nevertheless includes inaccuracies and lacunas inherent to the historical period when it was written².

No ethnically circumscribed list of Romanian MPs in the Hungarian Parliament is available to the present state of research. T. V. Păcățian gives relatively complete data on each elective cycle, but he does not always add details on the platform the future MPs candidate and won with, not to mention biographical elements that are so necessary in understanding the motifs behind decision-making processes.

A. Toth's prosopographic effort³ gave Romanian researchers a priceless tool: the list of all MPs in the Hungarian Diet between 1848 and 1892, brief biographic data and an exhaustive analysis of local elective dynamics and behaviour down to the level of colleges. This ample work, though bibliographically outdated, remains an essential tool for those researching political life in Austria-Hungary. Yet A. Toth's analysis does not touch upon the ethnic element, with the exception of general-context references to nationalities' parties; Romanian MPs on the lists of Hungarian political formations are (correctly) associated to the platform they represented. Their nationality can be identified in the prosopographic table, where most of them feature with both Romanian and Hungarian onomastic forms.

Gabriella Ilonszky⁴ extended A. Toth's analyses for the period between 1848 and 1892, focusing on the interval after 1884. In her latest book, Ilonszky offers an exhaustive database including all MPs in the Hungarian Parliament from 1884 until nowadays; she also gives complex data on elective statistics and dynamics. Though focusing on the post-dualist period, this work makes available for researchers the amplest tool for the analysis of the Romanian political elite in Hungary between 1884 and 1918, surpassing through size and methodology all similar initiatives from Romania in the field of political elite collective biography.

Despite their qualities, the above-mentioned works do not guarantee infallible information. For example, A. Toth mentioned Ilie Măcelariu's election and the fact that he did not confirm his mandate in the college of Hațeg, but the author only mentioned this happening in

² Teodor V. Păcățian, *Cartea de aur sau luptele politice-naționale ale românilor de sub coroana ungară*, vol. I, 2nd edition, Sibiu, Tipografia Iosif Marschall, 1904; vol. II, Sibiu, Tipografia Iosif Marschall, 1904; vol. III, Sibiu, Tipografia Iosif Marschall, 1905; Vol. IV, Sibiu, Tipografia Arhidiecezană, 1906; vol. V, Sibiu, Tipografia Arhidiecezană, 1909; vol. VI, Sibiu, Tipografia Arhidiecezană, 1910; vol. VII, Sibiu, Tipografia Arhidiecezană, 1911.

³ Adalbert Toth, *Parteien und Reichstagswahlen in Ungarn 1848-1892*, München, R. Oldenbourg Verlag, 1973.

⁴ Ilonszki Gabriella, *Képviselek és képviselőlet Magyarországon a 19. és 20. Században*, Budapest, Akadémiai Kiadó, 2009.

1872, not in 1869 as well⁵. Dumitru Suciu, Ilie Măcelariu's main biographer, completed the information⁶. In his turn, D. Suciu⁷ mentioned the intense campaign led by the passivists in Năsăud in 1869, writing that "the boycott of the elections was successful" though this "success" still meant that Sigismund Victor Popp, a Romanian activist and deákist MP was elected with 2 votes (and the Diet confirmed it despite the fact that the law required a minimum of 10 votes for the election of each MP)⁸!

Among the contemporary contributions to the topic from Romania, one could also mention one of Eugen Glück's studies on Romanian MPs in the Hungarian Diet between 1848 and 1849⁹ and an article signed by Stelian Mândruț on elective dynamics in post-Memorandum Transylvania - meant to complete A. Toth's research with data on the inner Carpathian area¹⁰.

Starting from these pre-requisites, our research aims at recreating from a prosopographical perspective a less researched elite group, i.e. the Romanian MPs in the Parliament of Budapest, and at analyzing it statistically. Historians focused so far on representatives of the national parties in Transylvania and Banat, usually presenting them in a favourable light, while most of their co-nationals entering the Diet on the lists of Hungarian parties were undeservingly forgotten. When their strong and influential personalities did bring them to the attention of biographers, the nature of the platform they candidated with was neglected or minimized. There are no studies in Romanian historiography focusing on this topic, only tangential mentions and brief biographic references.

We will thus start with a scholastic and rigid but most necessary presentation of each electoral cycle, continuing with an overview analysis of the period between 1869 and 1892 that will allow us to formulate primary conclusions on this elite group and its presence in the political life of Hungary. A number of supplementary details can be found in the Annexes (table 1 and 2). Such details are not discussed in the main text in order to prevent it from becoming overloaded. We believe that we managed to recreate the full picture of Romanian MPs in Budapest between 1869 and 1892, and even if other such MPs will be identified by future studies, their small number cannot modify the general conclusions of the present research.

⁵ Adalbert Toth, *op. cit.*, p. 169.

⁶ Dumitru Suciu, *Mișcarea antidualistă a românilor din Ungaria și Ilie Măcelariu (1867-1891)*, București, Editura Albatros, 2002, pp. 261-262.

⁷ *Ibidem*, pp. 257-258.

⁸ *Albina*, IV (1869), no. 54, June 15th-27th, p. 1.

⁹ Eugen Glück, "Deputați români în Parlamentul Ungariei în 1848-49", in Maria Berényi (ed.) *Simpozion. Comunicările celui de al VIII-lea simpozion al cercetătorilor români din Ungaria*, Giula, Editura "NOI", 1999, pp. 46-63.

¹⁰ Stelian Mândruț, *Dinamica electoral-politică în Transilvania între anii 1892-1910*, in "Anuarul Institutului de Istorie « George Barițiu » din Cluj-Napoca", XLII (2003), pp. 313-323.

Remaining in the methodological section, we must also explain the relevance of the selected time span. Despite the fact that Romanian MPs had been present in Budapest before¹¹, the 1869-1872 electoral cycle was the first in the history of dualist Hungary to include representatives of Romanian national parties. These national parties were organized during the conferences held in Timișoara and Miercurea. The 1887-1892 electoral cycle had a double meaning: it marked the end of the Tisza Kálmán government and the introduction of new forces on the Hungarian political scene¹², but also the entry of the Romanian National Party from Transylvania and Hungary (RNP) in a stage of complete passivity for the following decade¹³. In fact, the entire period between 1869 and 1892 was special for the political life of Romanians in Hungary, starting with the foundation of national parties and ending with a major crisis that disintegrated the organizing structures of the national movement and left the parliamentarians elected on the lists of Hungarian parties as the only representatives of the nation. It is for these reasons that we selected this period as focus of the present analysis, since the elective dynamics of the Romanian national MPs held a key role in the understanding of the general trends of parliamentary representation of Romanians in Hungary.

a. The dynamics of elective representation according to parliamentary cycles

31 Romanian MPs were elected in the Parliament of Budapest for the 1869-1872 elective cycle, among whom 17 held full mandates, 12 partial mandates, while 2 failed to appear for their confirmation¹⁴. The 17 MPs with full mandates were Vincentiu Babeș, Vicențiu Bogdan, Sigismund Borlea, Iosif Hodoș, Dimitrie Ionescu, Lazăr Ionescu, George Ioanovici, Vasile Jurca, Aurel Maniu, Petru Mihály, Alexandru Mocsonyi, Anton Mocsonyi, Eugeniu Mocsonyi, George Mocsonyi, Sigismund Victor Papp, Iosif Pop and Alexandru Roman. The 12 partial mandates went to Vasile Buteanu, Ioan Eugen Cucu (deceased), Lazăr Gruescu (deceased), Iosif Hoszu, George Ivacicovici, Sigismund Popovici (replaced by Dimitrie Bonciu), Miron Romanul (replaced by Mircea B. Stănescu), Mihail Pavel, and Aloisiu Vlad de Săliște (replaced by Iuliu Petricu). Ilie Măcelariu and Ioan Antonelli, the Vicar of Făgăraș, did not confirm their mandates, complying with the general passivity imposed by the conference in Miercurea¹⁵.

¹¹ Dumitru Suci, *Antecedentele dualismului austro-ungar și lupta națională a Românilor din Transilvania (1848-1867)*, București, Editura Albatros, 2000, pp. 254-255.

¹² István Barta, Iván T. Berend, Péter Hanák, Miklós Lackó, László Makkai, Zsuzsa L. Nagy, György Ránki, *Histoire de la Hongrie des origines à nos jours*, Budapest, Éditions Corvina, 1974, pp. 370-372.

¹³ Teodor Pavel, *Partidul Național Român și acțiunea memorandistă*, Cluj-Napoca, Editura Daco-Press, 1994, pp. 26-52.

¹⁴ Teodor V. Păcățian, *op. cit.*, vol. V, p. 132; A. Toth, *op. cit.*, pp. 216-343, passim (see the entries dedicated to these MPs).

¹⁵ Dumitru Suci, *Mișcarea antidualistă...*, pp. 261-262.

28 colleges from 13 administrative units were represented (see annexes). Among them, only 4 were in Transylvania (Mociu-Clujul de Jos, Rodna, Hațeg and Făgărașul de Jos), the other 24 covering the entire area of the western-Carpathian territories with Romanian majority: Banat, Partium, Zarand, Chioar, Bihor and Maramureș. Most mandates came from the counties of Caraș (6), Arad (4), Maramureș and Torontal (3 each).

The Romanian MPs were elected on the lists of 4 political formations: the Deákist governmental Party (DP - 16 MPs), The Center-Left Party (the main Hungarian opposition force, CLP - 2 MPs), the Romanian National Party from Banat (RNPB - 11 MPs) and the Romanian National Party from Transylvania (RNPT - 2 MPs who failed to appear). The situation differed in those colleges where elections were held in order to fill in vacant positions: MPs representing the same party were selected in two cases (DP and RNPB), while in a third case DP lost its mandate in favour of CLP.

Over the 1872-1875 elective cycle, a number of 25 Romanian MPs were elected in the Parliament of Budapest, among whom 17 held full mandates, 7 had partial mandates and 1 failed to appear¹⁶. The 17 MPs with full mandates were Mihai Bejan, Vicențiu Bogdan, Dimitrie Bonciu, Sigismund Borlea, Partenie Cosma, Ioan Gozman, Iosif Hodoș, George Ioanovici, Vasile Jurca, Petru Mihály, Anton Mocsonyi, Petru Nemeș, Iuliu Petricu, Gheorghe Pop de Băsești, Alexa Popescu, Alexandru Roman, and Mircea B. Stănescu. The 7 partial mandates went to Vincențiu Babeș, Alexandru Buda (deceased), Alexandru Mocsonyi (replaced by Ioan Popovici-Desseanu), Vasile Buteanu, Traian Doda, Ioachim Mureșan (he initially failed to appear, but then reconsidered). Ilie Măcelariu failed to appear and confirm his mandate.

24 colleges from 12 administrative units were represented. 2 of these colleges were located in Transylvania (Mociu-Clujul de Jos and Rodna), while the other 10 lay in the western parts. The counties of Arad, Caraș and Bihor were the administrative units with the most numerous mandates (5, 5 and 3 respectively).

The Romanian MPs were initially elected on the lists of 5 parties: DP - 11, CLP - 2, The 1848 Party (48P - 2), RNPB - 8 and RNPT - 2 among whom one MP failed to appear. A new party was created towards the end of this elective cycle, as consequence of the regrouping of political forces in Hungary: The Liberal Party (LP), formed through DP merging with CLP on March 1st 1875. The new party, led by Tisza Kálmán, formed a parliamentary majority and it was obvious it was going to win the summer elections and form the new cabinet¹⁷. In such conditions, most Romanian MPs who had candidated on the lists of DP and CLP rallied to the new party, with two exceptions: Alexa Popescu from Sasca college who returned to the national platform of the RNPB and Vicențiu Bogdan from Sânnicolau Mare college who remained a member of the Right Wing

¹⁶ Teodor V. Păcățian, *op. cit.*, vol. VI, p. 5, pp. 102-103; Adalbert Toth, *op. cit.*, pp. 216-343, passim (see the entries dedicated to these MPs).

¹⁷ István Barta *et alii*, *op. cit.*, pp. 357-359.

Opposition (RWO) - a political formation created from the remaining members of the DP and CLP who did not accept the merging¹⁸. The 1848 Party also went through reorganizing phases and name changes, but the two Romanian MPs who candidated on its lists (Mircea B. Stănescu and Gheorghe Pop de Băsești) maintained their orientation by joining, successively, the United Constitutional Opposition (UCO) and the Independence Party (IP)¹⁹. Romanians took part in the filling of vacant positions in a single elective college, managing to preserve the RNPB mandate in Radna.

21 Romanian MPs were elected during the 1875-1878 elective cycle in the Parliament of Budapest, among whom 16 had full mandates, 6 had partial mandates and 3 failed to appear²⁰. The 12 MPs with full mandates were Ștefan Antonescu, Sigismund Borlea, Sigismund Ciplea, Partenie Cosma, Traian Doda, Constantin Gurban, Petru Mihály, Ioan Misici, Iosif Nistor, Alexandru Papp, Gheorghe Pop de Băsești and Alexandru Roman. The 6 partial mandates belonged to Ioan Balomiri, Iosif Hodoș (resigned), Vasile Hoszu, George Ioanovici, Iuliu Petricu (replaced by George Szerb). Laurean Berceanu, Ioan Axente Sever and Avram Tincu, all from Orăștie college failed to appear in Diet meetings, refusing to confirm their mandates. The latter was replaced by Ioan Balomiri, who took part for ca. 6 months in the proceedings of the Parliament.

17 colleges, from 10 administrative units, were represented. The county of Caraș provided the largest number of Romanian mandates (5). A special situation occurred in the college of Orăștie where 3 Romanian candidates renounced their mandates successively, thus cumulating 4 mandates during this elective cycle²¹. Hungary went through an administrative reform in 1876, with the result that some old units disappeared while others were reorganized or given new names²². Romanian historiography lacks studies on the effects of this reorganization of the elective geography in the areas inhabited by the Romanians. Despite the fact that the basic units - the colleges - remained largely the same²³, a detailed study on the redistribution of people with the right to vote in Transylvania and the Western Parts as a result of the administrative reform of 1876 is still needed.

The Romanian MPs were elected on the lists of 4 parties: LP - 12, IP - 1, RNPB - 4 and RNPT - 4. Considering the special situation in Orăștie, RNPT actually had a single candidate thus the large majority rested with the government party. One can note, inside this party, Iosif Nistor's

¹⁸ Adalbert Toth, *op. cit.*, pp. 141-143.

¹⁹ *Ibidem*, p. 301, 315.

²⁰ Teodor V. Păcățian, *op. cit.*, vol. VI, p. 519; Adalbert Toth, *op. cit.*, pp. 216-343, *passim* (see the entries dedicated to these MPs).

²¹ Valentin Orga, *Grupul neoactivist de la Orăștie. Premise. Constituire. Activitate (1885-1914)*, PhD dissertation, "Babeș-Bolyai" University, Cluj-Napoca, 2002, pp. 198-199.

²² Anton Dörner, *Administrația Transilvaniei în perioada anilor 1867-1876*, in "Anuarul Institutului de Istorie « George Barițiu » din Cluj-Napoca", XL (2001), pp. 116-121.

²³ Adalbert Toth, *op. cit.*, pp. 150-154.

desertion. He enrolled the Independent Liberal Party (ILP) and then the United Opposition (OU). We must also mention the situation in Zorlențu Mare college, where two governmental Romanian MPs succeeded each other, i.e. Iuliu Petricu and George Szerb.

14 Romanian MPs were elected in the Parliament from Budapest during the 1878-1881 elective cycle. 11 of them had full mandates²⁴: George Constantini, Partenie Cosma, Traian Doda, Vasile Jurca, Petru Mihály, Ioan Misici, Alexandru Papp, Gheorghe Pop de Băsești, Alexandru Roman, George Szerb and Nicolae Străvoiu. George Ivacicovici died shortly after the elections, Atanasiu Racz did not finish his mandate and George Ioanovici only started his in the autumn of 1878. 14 elective colleges were represented, from 8 counties, the largest number of mandates coming from Caraș-Severin (4). Romanian MPs candidated on the lists of 4 political formations: LP - 10, OU - 2, IP - 1 and RNPB - 1. We must note Nicolae Străvoiu's desertion (in the college of Brașov II). He returned to the platform of RNPT after entering the Parliament on the lists of the governmental party²⁵.

11 Romanian MPs were elected in the Parliament of Budapest during the 1881-1884 elective cycle. 7 of them had full mandates: George Constantini, Traian Doda, Iosif Gall, Vasile Jurca, Alexandru Roman, George Szerb and Végshö Gellért. Ioan Misici died during his mandate. Ștefan Antonescu resigned and entered the administration, being replaced by Leontin Simonescu. Atanasiu Racz was elected, for a few months, towards the end of the cycle²⁶. 11 colleges from 5 counties were represented. The largest number of mandates came from the counties of Caraș-Severin (4) and Timiș (3). With the exception of Traian Doda, elected in Caransebeș on the lists of the RNP, all 10 other Romanian MPs candidated for the Liberal Party.

12 Romanian MPs were elected in the Parliament of Budapest during the elective cycle 1884-1887, all of them with full mandates: Vincențiu Babeș, Ioan Beleş, Sigismund Ciplea, Traian Doda, Iosif Gall, Constantin Gurban, Petru Mihály, Atanasiu Racz, Alexandru Roman, George Szerb, Petru Truț(i)a and Végshö Gellért²⁷. 12 colleges from 5 counties were represented: Caraș-Severin (3 mandates), Arad, Bihor, Maramureș, Timiș (2 mandates) and Hunedoara (1 mandate). Among these, the Liberal Party held 8 mandates, RNP 3 mandates and the Moderate Opposition (MO) one mandate.

9 Romanian MPs were elected in the Parliament of Budapest during the elective cycle 1887-1892. Among them, 6 had full mandates: Ioan Beleş, George Constantini, Petru Mihály, Silviu Rezei, George Szerb and

²⁴ Teodor V. Păcățian, *op. cit.*, vol. VI, pp. 667-669; Adalbert Toth, *op. cit.*, pp. 216-343, *passim* (see the entries dedicated to these MPs).

²⁵ Adalbert Toth, *op. cit.*, p. 315.

²⁶ Teodor V. Păcățian, *op. cit.*, vol. VII, pp. 49-50; Adalbert Toth, *op. cit.*, pp. 216-343, *passim* (see the entries dedicated to these MPs).

²⁷ Teodor V. Păcățian, *op. cit.*, vol. VII, p. 207; Adalbert Toth, *op. cit.*, pp. 216-343, *passim* (see the entries dedicated to these MPs); G. Ilonszki, *op. cit.*, CD-Rom (Történeti_Képviseelő_Adatbázis_1884_1947.xls).

Véghsö Gellért. Atanasiu Racz died in 1891, while Traian Doda and Mihail Popovici failed to appear in order to confirm their election. 8 colleges from 5 counties were represented: Caransebeş (3 mandates), Arad, Bihor (2 mandates), Timiș, Maramureș (1 mandate). 6 Romanians candidate on the lists of the Liberal Party, RNP obtained two unconfirmed mandates in the same college, and a Romanian MP decided to candidate on the platform of the Moderate Opposition, continuing the same platform direction as member of count Appanyi's National Party (NP)²⁸.

We have presented the overall attendance of Romanian MPs in the Parliament from Budapest, according to elective cycles, between 1869 and 1892. Even from this simple and dry presentation, one can observe some of the major trends of that period, such as the dominance of the governmental parties and the constant regress of MPs elected on the basis of their national program until their complete disappearance after 1892. Over the following paragraphs, we will attempt to analyze this period in its entirety, detailing and refining the previous general observations.

b. General development during the period between 1869 and 1892

62 Romanian MPs were present in the Hungarian Parliament between 1869 and 1892, sharing a number of 123 mandates. Among these, 82 were full mandates, while the other 41 were interrupted or taken by others. Among the latter, in 8 cases the candidates failed to appear and in 6 cases death prevented the respective MPs to finish their mandates.

It is difficult to analyze the geographic-elective representation due to the changes triggered by the administrative reform of 1876. Graph no. 1 shows the distribution of Romanian MPs' mandates according to their distribution on counties, including also the administrative units dissolved in 1876 (marked in red). Mandates from the colleges included in such units were given to the counties to which they were annexed after the reform. Since the former Caraș County overlaps almost entirely the 1876 Caraș-Severin, one can state that in this case our elective presentation is not distorted by the administrative reform; for this reason, we did not mark this case with different colour. Most of the seats in the Diet were won in the colleges of Caraș-Severin (30), Arad (22), Bihor (15), Maramureș (13) and Timiș (12). The county of Zarand is special due to the fact that 3 of the 22 mandates from Arad came from there. 10 mandates came from the county of Hunedoara, but 4 of them were due to the special situation in the district of Orăștie (1875-1878), other 4 were obtained in the former Zarand, while the last 2 were not confirmed. Taking into consideration also the mandates obtained between 1878 and 1892 in the college of Iosășel (Hălmagiul Mare), the total number of Romanian mandates in Zarand (before and after 1876) raises to 11, placing it in the upper half of the hierarchy grouping areas where Romanian MPs were elected.

²⁸ Teodor V. Păcățian, *op. cit.*, vol. VII, p. 357; A. Toth, *op. cit.*, pp. 216-343, passim (see the entries dedicated to these MPs); G. Ilonszki, *op. cit.*, CD-Rom (Történeti Képvisező Adatbázis 1884-1947.xls).

Much lower figures correspond to the counties of Solnoc-Dăbâca (4), Sălaj (4), Satu Mare (3) and Torontal (4). All 7 mandates from the counties of Solnoc-Dăbâca and Satu Mare came from the former district of Chioar, while the mandates in Sălaj were all obtained in the colleges of the former Solnocul de Mijloc County. Historical Transylvania totals 12 mandates (9.5%) from Hunedoara (6), Năsăud (2), Cluj (2), Braşov (1) and Făgăraş (1) - 5 of them were not confirmed and one was confirmed later.

Graph no. 1. Distribution of mandates held by Romanian MPs according to administrative and territorial units.

Overall, Romanian MPs represented 38 elective colleges distributed in 14 administrative units (during the period between 1869 and 1876) and 8 such units respectively (during the 1876-1892 period). The elective geography can be explained, at first glance, by the tactics adopted by the Romanian parties: activism in Banat and passivism in Transylvania. The significant difference between the governmental Romanian MPs elected in the Western Parts and those in historical Transylvania is yet to be interpreted. One could think of several explanations: the imposed passivity on one hand and the difference in elective legislation (more restrictive in Transylvania) on the other hand; and from one moment onward the construction of an activist “tradition” in the western counties. Since not all data is available at this point, we tend to explain this difference also through an increased conservatism of Romanians in Transylvania, through a certain “local patriotism” that prevented them from entering a Parliament they did not consider as their own. Another possible explanation, even a plausible one, is the emergence in Transylvania of financially powerful Hungarian parliamentary elite that few of the Romanian candidates for the Diet could rival.

Romanian MPs represented 15 political formations and groups between 1869 and 1892. One could group them according to three tendencies: government parties (I), Hungarian opposition parties (II) and Romanian national parties (III). This taxonomy differs from the classical one created by A. Toth who placed some Hungarian opposition groups

(48P, UCO, IP) in the same radical tendency, labeled “C”, as the parties of the nationalities²⁹. This does not mean we reject his analytical model; on the contrary, we acknowledge its merits and believe it fits his approach on the scale of entire Hungary perfectly. But the much more focused topic of our study and the present state of research (almost nothing is known on the actual doctrinal position of several Romanian MPs) determine us to use, for the time being, a less detailed delimitation among parliamentary parties in Hungary, even with the risk of assuming ethnocentric tendencies. In the future, if the topic will grow and the state of research will allow it, we are certain researchers will also pay attention to the needed differentiations among Romanian MPs in the ranks of the Hungarian opposition.

Tendency I includes the two government parties, DP and LP, grouping 73 mandates, i.e. 59.35% of the total. Tendency II includes no less than 10 opposition formations (MO, RWO, UO1, UO2, UCO, 48P, CLP, IP, ILP, NP), totaling 12 mandates (9.75%). Tendency III includes the three national parties (RNPB, RNPT, RNP), with 38 mandates (30.90%). Graph no. 2 shows the development of these tendencies.

Tendency I slightly decreased in 1872 and then remained stable until 1884, when the number of Romanian governmental MPs started to decrease again, significantly. The causes of this regress relates to a complex of both natural and ideological factors. We would be tempted to say that governmental parties felt less and less attracted, over a couple of decades, by the idea of promoting Romanian MPs as the internal situation stabilized after the *Ausgleich* and the Magyarization policy gained momentum. The fact is possible, but no documents support this explicitly.

There are nevertheless documents attesting the fact that some of the Romanian MPs were attracted into bureaucratic structures, occupying more secure positions that were sometimes also financially more profitable. The following were in such a situation between 1869 and 1872: M. Romanul (appointed school inspector, he went on to become bishop and metropolitan)³⁰, A. Vlad de Săliște (appointed judex of the *Tabula Regia Judiciaria* in Budapest)³¹, S. Popovici (appointed court chairman)³² and G. Ivacicovici. Between 1872 and 1875 V. Butean was appointed royal judge in Șomcuța Mare³³ and between 1875 and 1878 I. Petricu and V. Hoszu were appointed college judges³⁴. The case of G. Ivacicovici was special: in 1869 he was elected Deákist MP, gave up his mandate in 1871 in order to enter the administration and became *comes* of Caraș. After the

²⁹ Adalbert Toth, *op. cit.*, p. 143.

³⁰ Antonie Plămădeală, *Lupta împotriva deznaționalizării românilor din Transilvania în timpul dualismului austro-ungar în vremea lui Miron Romanul 1874-1898, după acte, documente și corespondență*, Sibiu, Tiparul Tipografiei Eparhiale Sibiu, 1986, p. 27.

³¹ Vasile Iuga de Săliște, *Aloisiu Vlad de Săliște. Viața și activitatea*, Cluj-Napoca, Editura Societății Culturale Pro Maramureș Dragoș Vodă, 2003, pp. 41-47.

³² Teodor V. Păcățian, *op. cit.*, vol. V, p. 132.

³³ *Ibidem*, vol. VI, p. 103.

³⁴ *Ibidem*, vol. VI, p. 519.

1876 administrative reform and the reorganizing of the county of Caraș he returned to parliamentary life but died shortly after the elections³⁵.

Graph no. 2. Development of political tendencies among the Romanian MPs (1869-1892)

MPs movements from administration to Parliament continued during the 80s, probably according to the local strategies of the government and the desire for self-accomplishment of those involved. During the 1881-1884 cycle, MP Șt. Antonescu was elected president of the Orphans' Court in the county of Lugoj; he then resigned and his seat was taken by L. Simonescu, former *vice-comes* in Lugoj. Another Romanian, A. Racz, former *vice-comes* in Timiș, exchanged places with the Hungarian MP Ormós Zsigmond, took his mandate, and the latter became *vice-comes* instead of Racz³⁶. By the time he was elected member of the Parliament in 1884, C-tin Gurban was arch-priest of Buteni and temporary director of the Theological and Pedagogical Institute in Ara³⁷, thus clerk in the autonomous administration of the Orthodox Church. I. Gall³⁸ and Vêghsö G.³⁹ also came from the administration and both temporarily gave up their pensions in favour of the MP allowance. In the same manner, in 1892, P. Vuia promoted from college proprietor to MP⁴⁰.

As one can note, there were several cases of Romanian MPs migrating to-and-from Parliament and bureaucracy (either of the state or the church) between 1869 and 1892. It is possible that this also triggered a decrease in the total number of Romanian governmental candidates who preferred safer and less turbulent positions. The fact that in at least one

³⁵ *Ibidem*, vol. VI, p. 669.

³⁶ *Ibidem*, vol. VII, p. 50.

³⁷ "Luminătorul", IV (1884), no. 49, June 16th-28th, p. 1.

³⁸ Teodor V. Păcățian [?], *Iosif Gall*, f. 40-41. Anonymous manuscript, probably written by T.V. Păcățian, preserved in Ovidiu Emil Iudean's personal archive.

³⁹ "Telegraful Român", XXIX (1881), no. 69, June 16th, p. 1.

⁴⁰ Ovidiu Emil Iudean, *The involvement of Romanian candidates in the parliamentary elections in Hungary during the last decade of the 19th century, as reflected in the Romanian press in Transylvania*, in "Transylvanian Review", XX (2011), Supplement no. 1/2011. Edited by Oana Mihaela Tămaș, Romanian Academy, Center for Transylvanian Studies, Cluj-Napoca (under print).

case a Romanian took over a Hungarian mandate and that some of the people who left were also replaced by Romanians indicate that the government rather chose its people according to political than nationalistic considerations. As possible explanation for this phenomenon, we note that administration work was much easier and on the long run more profitable; since major investments were no longer needed during election periods, pensions were ensured and any high clerk was able to directly support the promotion of a number of people who were close to him or were members of his family in the lower ranks of administration. Not least, the boom of Hungarian bureaucracy after 1867⁴¹ certainly created an attractive context for the Romanian elite, diminishing the political leaning of those who wished to enjoy certain prosperity without major financial efforts. The fact that migration took place in both directions reflects the complex motivation that determined such behaviour and the need to study it at an individual level in order to reach fully acceptable explanations.

Turning to the causes of the decrease in the number of governmental Romanian MPs, one must mention that throughout the period under analysis, out of the 6 who died during their mandate, 5 were governmental and 3 died after 1881, thus naturally reducing the number of Romanians in the Parliament. Paradoxically, political migration rather had a negative impact on the government parties, as we will subsequently show. Not least, the legislative actions of the Tisza government against the nationalities⁴² seem to have undermined the support of a pro-government inclination among the Romanians. The failed attempts of 1881 and 1884-1885⁴³ indicate the impossibility of maintaining a moderate Romanian party. The unification of Romanian national parties⁴⁴ and the relative solidarity that characterized the period between 1881 and 1892 contributed to their rejection of collaborating with the government.

Taking into consideration this complex system of factors and the descending trend between 1869 and 1875, T.V. Păcățian's assertion that the elective legislation of 1875 had a major influence on the decrease in numbers of Romanian MPs can be detailed; we believe that the modification of elective norms was only a reason among many in the support of a development that was descendent from the beginning⁴⁵.

⁴¹ Alan John Percival Taylor, *The Habsburg Monarchy 1809-1918. A History of the Austrian Empire and Austria-Hungary*, London, Hamish Hamilton, 1948, pp. 185-186; István Barta *et alii*, *op. cit.*, pp. 350-359, 365-372.

⁴² Paul Lucian Bruslanowski, *Învățământul confesional ortodox din Transilvania între anii 1848-1918: între exigențele statului centralizat și principiile autonomiei bisericești*, Cluj-Napoca, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 2005, pp. 272-285.

⁴³ Vlad Popovici, *Publicații activiste progubernamentale românești din Ungaria dualistă. Discursul politic al ziarelor «Patria» și «Viitorul»*, in "Revista Bistriței", XX (2006), pp. 296-297.

⁴⁴ Bujor Surdu, *Conferința de constituire a Partidului Național Român din Ungaria (1881)*, in "Anuarul Institutului de Istorie din Cluj", XI (1968), pp. 307-325; Liviu Maior, *Constituirea Partidului Național Român. Conferința din 12-14 mai 1881*, in "Studia Universitatis Babeș-Bolyai. Seria Historia", XV (1970), fasciculus 1, pp. 91-107.

⁴⁵ Teodor V. Păcățian, *op. cit.*, vol. VI, p. 501.

If there is one reason to contribute significantly to the lowering number of Romanian nationalist MPs, it is not connected to legislation but to the elective procedures of that time. Ever since 1869, Romanian correspondents noted the violent clashes during the elections, especially in Hungary and less in Transylvania⁴⁶. During the Tisza period, elective violence and pressure extended at the level of the entire country, as a means of controlling elections aimed against the entire opposition, not only the nationalist one: “Supporters of the government, who voted for its candidates, enjoyed all favour and were forgiven all sins, while supporters of the opposition, both Hungarian and nationalist, were terrorized and persecuted until they despaired. It is thus no wonder that even the few Romanians who had the courage to enter elective struggle in such conditions came out disillusioned and, with few exceptions, defeated by our own Romanian people”⁴⁷. Even if this fragment, belonging to T.V. Păcățian, was written several decades after the events, this is how a member of the Romanian political elite presented the situation in 1881, in an internal correspondence of the RNP: “Romanian leaders lack from all colleges, the priests are either not interested or afraid to take interest in such matters, the few college people do not dare intervene, and most Romanian electors vote for the mandate of the praetor who takes them by carriage to the election place, pays for their travelling expenses and feeds them for free - in Aiud for example they show up with feathers in the colours of the Hungarian flag at their hats and are unwilling to know of any national action, nor do they ask for any advice; in such conditions, all national action is completely paralyzed”⁴⁸.

We cannot end the analysis on TI without discussing political migration. In the beginning of 1875, with the dissolution of the DP and the coalition of the LP, out of the 11 Romanian Deákists only 9 joined the new formation. V. Bogdan chose to join the RWO, while A. Popescu supported the RNPB during the few remaining months of his mandate. Over the 1875-1878 elective cycle, MP I. Nistor went from the LP to the ILP and then the OU. In 1878, P. Mihály did not candidate on the lists of the LP but those of the OU, maintaining this orientation (OU, MO, NP) over his subsequent mandates as well. The same is true for G. Ioanovici. During the same year, N. Străvoiu was elected MP in Transylvania, in the college of Braşov II, on the lists of the LP, later abandoning this formation and assuming a national platform (RNPT). A total of 6 Romanian MPs left the governmental camp between 1869 and 1892. Only 3 of them were attracted by the LP, none during the elective cycles but on the occasion of elections: D. Bonciu gave up the lists of the RNPB for those of the CLP in 1872, joining the LP in 1875; C-tin. Gurban returned to the Parliament on

⁴⁶ Alexandru Onojescu, Vlad Popovici (ed.), *Correspondențe politice peste Carpați. Visarion Roman - colaborator la ziarul «Românul» (1868-1870)*, Cluj-Napoca, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 2010, pp. 130-132.

⁴⁷ Teodor V. Păcățian, *op. cit.*, vol. VI, p. 502.

⁴⁸ Central National Historical Archives Bucharest, Romanian National Party Font (National Committee Sibiu), file 2, f. 5-6.

the lists of the LP in 1884-1887, after a RNPB mandate in 1875-1878; A. Roman represented the LP between 1875 and 1887, after several national mandates, including 2 for the RNPB (1869-1875).

The report on political migration is thus negative for TI: twice the number of Romanian MPs left the governmental camp than the number of those whom it attracted from other formations. The motivation behind such migrations was probably a mix between personal and doctrine-related elements, difficult to grasp since the biographies of the large majority of Romanian governmental members of the Parliament have not been written. We can suspect that N. Străvoiu's Tisza platform was only a pretense, in order to ensure the support of the government and of part of the Saxons, since the lawyer from Braşov was well known for his pro-activism⁴⁹. Such data is available in the case of Al. Roman who joined the governmental camp in the context of certain incompatibilities between his status as university professor and as MP; the Tisza government agreed to accept such incompatibilities in this particular case on the condition Al. Roman rallied to its platform, though the Romanian MP maintained, in some cases, his explicitly nationalist orientation and even stood up against the founding of the Romanian Moderate Party in 1884⁵⁰.

Tendency II (TII) went through a fluctuating development over the period under discussion, reaching peaks of popularity during the intervals of 1872-1875 and 1878-1881. The first interval represents the years when DP disintegrated in the conditions created by corruption and the ascension of the CLP⁵¹, while the second marks the coalition of opposition forces against the Tisza government whose power preservation tactics grew increasingly stronger⁵². Analyzing graph 3, one can note that TII is not represented in historical Transylvania, except for the border regions (Cehu Silvaniei college). There are nevertheless two areas where the Romanians strongly supported TII: Arad (Ineu-Buteni, Chişineu-Criş and Radna colleges) and Maramureş (Vişeu and Şugatag colleges). Isolated mandates were obtained in Beiuş (BH) and Bocşa (CS). One must not forget that among the 12 Hungarian opposition mandates, 2 were won on the lists of the CLP and transferred to the LP in 1875, thus changing tendency. Among the Romanian MPs of explicitly opposition orientation one can mention M.B. Stănescu (CLP 1870-1872; 48P, UCO, IP 1872-1875) and Gh. Pop de Băseşti (48P, UCO, IP 1872-1881), besides the above mentioned P. Mihályi. M.B. Stănescu and Gh. Pop de Băseşti getting closer to the 1848 Party can also be related to the negotiations between RNPB-48P during 1870-1871⁵³. Though such negotiations failed at top level, the persistence of personal ties, and the need for allies against the ascension

⁴⁹ Teodor V. Păcăţian, *op. cit.*, vol. VI, pp. 668-669.

⁵⁰ Gelu Neamţu, *Alexandru Roman, marele fiu al Bihorului 1826-1897*, Oradea, Fundaţia Culturală "Cele Trei Crişuri", 1995, pp. 125-127.

⁵¹ István Barta *et alii*, *op. cit.*, pp. 358-359.

⁵² *Ibidem*, pp. 369-371.

⁵³ Ioan Chiorean, *Mişcarea Naţională Română din Austro-Ungaria (1867-1918)*, Tîrgu Mureş, Editura Universităţii "Petru Maior", 2000, pp. 21-23.

of those in support of the government, triggered collaborations at the level of the elective colleges. TII dropped suddenly after 1875 since it “melted” into TI; during subsequent parliamentary cycles TII remained at the value of 1-2 units. Better-known Romanian MPs who chose to candidate on the lists of Hungarian opposition parties were, or seem to have been, nationalists and probably preferred this solution for elective tactical reasons (financial support, ensuring the majority etc.). The hypothesis is also supported by the lack of political migration between TII and TIII among Romanians.

Tendency III (TIII) constantly lost favour. It seemed to go through a slow regress in the beginning, between 1869 and 1875, but taking into consideration the 4 mandates in Orăștie that disturb the statistical picture, one can state that in 1875 the number of Romanian national MPs was half of what it was in 1872, reaching just 1 in 1878. A slight revival can be noted after 1884, but the failure in the 1887 elections pushed RNP to complete passivity and lead to the two successive mandates in Caransebeș be left unconfirmed⁵⁴. T.V. Păcățian explains the decrease of 1872 through the first attempts of the government party to use governmental Romanian candidates in colleges with Romanian majority, where representatives of the RNPB also candidated⁵⁵. The next descending phase, in 1875, can be explained by the lack of unity that characterized the RNPB, in the context of previous failures but also as a side effect of the coalition of the LP. Not even a single central elective conference was held in 1875 and members were allowed to proceed at will, most local branches choosing the path of passivism⁵⁶. It was the elective tactics of the Tisza government and not the elective legislation that lay at the core of the total regress marking the post-Memorandum decade; the decrease in number of the Romanian nationalist MPs corresponds to the general regress of the entire opposition in Hungary. One must not forget the hybrid platform of the RNP that maintained the duality of the elective tactics for Banat and Transylvania, thus preventing unity of action (either in the direction of activism or passivism) and implicitly diminishing the force of its candidates.

c. Conclusions

The fourth indicator in graph 2 (the general development of the number of Romanian MPs - marked in violet) needs no deeper analysis in context of the increasingly lower representation of Romanians in all three political tendencies. One can nevertheless note the steep descending development of this indicator, only interrupted by the slight increase in 1884 mentioned above. Analyzing graph 3, the fact that the strongest all-nationalist college (that of Caransebeș) is still less significant than the strongest all-governmental college (that of Zorlențu Mare) seems symptomatic. It is also not by chance that the disappearance of MPs

⁵⁴ *Tribuna*, XII (1895), no. 151, July 6th-18th, p. 601.

⁵⁵ Teodor V. Păcățian, *op. cit.*, vol. VI, pp. 102-103.

⁵⁶ M. Milin, *op. cit.*, pp. 24-25.

belonging to TIII in the Hungarian Parliament coincides with the Memorandum: the lack of parliamentary representation was meant to generate new forms of political expressions - more radical and with an increased impact on public opinion in Hungary and especially outside its borders.

Over two decades, under the balanced influence of political, ideological and natural factors, the number of Romanian MPs in the Hungarian Parliament decreased constantly, independent of the elective platform they candidated with. Many of those willing to collaborate with the government stepped down during the 1870s to enter bureaucracy and occupy more stable and less demanding positions. The other activists, supporters of the national program or of the opposition, faced the elective tactics meant to ensure for the government majority in the Chamber. In Transylvania, the debate between activists and passivists paralyzed all significant elective initiatives. The election of Romanian candidates was usually followed by their not confirming of these mandates.

The administrative units conferring the largest number of Romanian mandates were located, as expected, in the territory west of the Carpathians. 6 counties [AR(+ZR), BH, CS (CR), MM, TM] together granted 97 of all 123 Romanian mandates during the period under analysis (79.35%). Among these, 59 belonged to governmental parties, 30 to national parties and 8 to Hungarian opposition parties. Nationalist MPs were obviously never as numerous as governmental ones. The fact that many of the latter seemed to stand on rather national and governmental positions in the Diet is equally true. But studies on the parliamentary activity of Romanians in Budapest during this period are either related to biographical reconsiderations or significant moments in the national struggle, almost completely ignoring what we might call the history of parliamentary life. The latter issue thus remains as many others, undecided. In such conditions, beyond the general character of the conclusions in this study, we are left to signal the need for future deeper analyses of aspects related to the elective implication of Romanians in Hungary and the parliamentary activity of Romanian MPs in Budapest, as a needed segment of the history of the national movement and that of Romanian political elites.

Graph no. 3. Distribution of mandates on elective colleges according to the three political tendencies

ANNEXES

Table 1. List of Romanian MPs in the Parliament in Budapest (1869-1892)

Elective Cycle	Name	Adm. unit	Elective college	Party
1869-1872	Antonelli, Ioan	FG	Arpaşul de Jos (Făgăraş de Jos)	RNPT
	Babeş, Vincentiu	CS (CR)	Sasca	RNPB
	Bogdan, Vicențiu	TO	Comloş	DP
	Bonciu, Dimitrie	AR	Ineu (Buteni)	RNPB
	Borlea, Sigismund	AR (ZR)	Iosăşel (Hălmagiul Mare)	RNPB
	Buteanu, Vasile	SD (CH)	Îleanda Mare (Mesteacăn)	DP
	Cucu, Ioan Eugen	SJ (SMj)	Tăşnad	DP
	Gruescu, Lazăr	TO	Zitişte	RNPB
	Hodoş, Iosif	HD (ZR)	Brad	RNPB
	Hoszu, Iosif	CJ	Teaca (Mociu-Cluj de Jos)	DP
	Ionescu, Dimitrie	BH	Beiuş	DP
	Ionescu, Lazăr	AR	Radna	CLP
	Ivacicovici, George	TM	Ciacova	DP
	Ioanovici, George	CS (CR)	Bocşa	DP
	Jurca, Vasile	MM	Şugatag	DP
	Maniu, Aurel	CS (CR)	Făget	DP
	Măcelariu, Ilie	HD	Haţeg	RNPT
	Mihályi, Petru	MM	Vişeu	DP
	Mocsonyi, Alexandru	CS (CR)	Lugoj	RNPB
	Mocsonyi, Anton	AR	Şiria-Pâncota (Şiria)	RNPB
	Mocsonyi, Eugeniu	TO	Sănnicolau Mare	RNPB
	Mocsonyi, George	TM	Moraviţa	RNPB
	Pavel, Mihail	MM	Sighetu Marmăţiei	DP
	Petricu, Iuliu	CS (CR)	Zorlenţu Mare	DP
	Papp, Sigismund Victor	BN (NS)	Rodna	DP
	Popovici, Sigismund	AR	Ineu (Buteni)	RNPB
	Pop, Iosif	SM (CH)	Şomcuţa Mare	DP
	Roman, Alexandru	BH	Ceica	RNPB
Romanul, Miron	AR	Chişineu-Criş	DP	
Stănescu, Mircea B.	AR	Chişineu-Criş	CLP	

Elective Cycle	Name	Adm. unit	Elective college	Party
	Wlad de Săliște, Aloisiu	CS (CR)	Zorlențu Mare	DP
1872-1875	Babeș, Vincentiu	TM	Biserica Albă	RNPB
	Bejan, Mihai	CS (CR)	Făget	DP, LP
	Bogdan, Vicențiu	TO	Sănnicolau Mare	DP, RWO
	Bonciu, Dimitrie	AR	Ineu (Buteni)	CLP; LP
	Borlea, Sigismund	AR (ZR)	Iosășel (Hălmagiul Mare)	RNPB
	Buda, Alexandru	SM (CH)	Șomcuța Mare	DP
	Buteanu, Vasile	SD (CH)	Ileanda Mare (Mesteacăn)	DP
	Cosma, Partenie	BH	Beiuș	CLP; LP
	Doda, Traian	CS (CR)	Caransebeș	RNPB
	Gozman, Ioan	BH	Aleșd	DP, LP
	Hodoș, Iosif	HD (ZR)	Brad	RNPB
	Ioanovici, George	CS (CR)	Bocșa	DP, LP
	Jurca, Vasile	MM	Șugatag	DP, LP
	Măcelariu, Ilie	HD	Hățeg	RNPT
	Mihályi, Petru	MM	Vișeu	DP, LP
	Mocsonyi, Alexandru	AR	Radna	RNPB
	Mocsonyi, Anton	AR	Șiria-Pâncota (Șiria)	RNPB
	Mureșan, Ioachim	BN (NS)	Rodna	RNPT
	Nemeș, Petru	CJ	Teaca (Mociu-Cluj de Jos)	DP, LP
	Petricu, Iuliu	CS (CR)	Zorlențu Mare	DP, LP
Pop de Băsești, Gheorghe	SJ (SMj)	Cehu Silvaniei	48P, UCO, IP	
Popescu, Alexa	CS (CR)	Sasca	DP, RNPB	
Popovici-Desseanu, Ioan	AR	Radna	RNPB	
Roman, Alexandru	BH	Ceica	RNPB	
Stănescu, Mircea B.	AR	Chișineu-Criș	48P, UCO, IP	
1875-1878	Antonescu, Ștefan	CS (CR)	Sasca	LP
	Axente Sever, Ioan	HD (OR)	Orăștie	RNPT
	Balomiri, Ioan	HD (OR)	Orăștie	RNPT
	Berceanu, Laurean	HD (OR)	Orăștie	RNPT
	Borlea, Sigismund	AR (ZR)	Iosășel (Hălmagiul Mare)	RNPB
	Ciplea, Sigismund	MM	Șugatag	LP

Elective Cycle	Name	Adm. unit	Elective college	Party
	Cosma, Partenie	BH	Beiuș	LP
	Doda, Traian	CS (CR)	Caransebeș	RNPB
	Gurban, Constantin	AR	Ineu (Buteni)	RNPB
	Hodoș, Iosif	HD (ZR)	Brad	RNPB
	Hoszu, Vasile	SD (CH)	Ileanda Mare (Mesteacăn)	LP
	Ioanovici, George	CS (CR)	Bocșa	LP
	Mihály, Petru	MM	Vișeu	LP
	Misici, Ioan	TM	Timișoara	LP
	Nistor, Iosif	AR	Șiria-Pâncota (Șiria)	LP, ILP, OU
	Papp, Alexandru	SM (CH)	Șomcuța Mare	LP
	Petricu, Iuliu	CS (CR)	Zorlențu Mare	LP
	Pop de Băsești, Gheorghe	SJ (SMj)	Cehu Silvaniei	IP
	Roman, Alexandru	BH	Ceica	LP
	Szerb, George	CS (CR)	Zorlențu Mare	LP
	Tincu, Avram	HD (OR)	Orăștie	RNPT
1878-1881	Constantini, George	AR	Iosășel	LP
	Cosma, Partenie	BH	Beiuș	LP
	Doda, Traian	CS	Caransebeș	RNPB
	Ivacicovici, George	CS	Sasca	LP
	Ioanovici, George	CS	Bocșa	OU
	Jurca, Vasile	MM	Șugatag	LP
	Mihályi, Petru	MM	Vișeu	OU, MO
	Misici, Ioan	TM	Timișoara	LP
	Papp, Alexandru	SD	Ileanda Mare	LP
	Pop de Băsești, Gheorghe	SJ	Cehu Silvaniei	IP
	Racz, Atanasiu	TM	Moravița	LP
	Roman, Alexandru	BH	Ceica	LP
	Szerb, George	CS	Zorlențu Mare	LP
	Străvoiu, Nicolae	BV	Brașov II	LP, RNPT
1881-1884	Antonescu, Ștefan	CS	Bocșa	LP
	Constantini, George	AR	Iosășel	LP
	Doda, Traian	CS	Caransebeș	RNP
	Gall, Iosif	TM	Recaș	LP
	Jurca, Vasile	MM	Șugatag	LP
	Misici, Ioan	TM	Timișoara	LP
	Racz, Atanasiu	TM	Becicherecul Mic	LP

Elective Cycle	Name	Adm. unit	Elective college	Party
	Roman, Alexandru	BH	Ceica	LP
	Simonescu, Leontin	CS	Bocşa	LP
	Szerb, George	CS	Zorlenţu Mare	LP
	Véghsö, Gellért	BH	Beiuş	LP
1884-1887	Babeş, Vincentiu	CS	Sasca	RNP
	Beleş, Ioan	AR	Radna	LP
	Ciplea, Sigismund	MM	Şugatag	LP
	Doda, Traian	CS	Caransebeş	RNP
	Gall, Iosif	TM	Recaş	LP
	Gurban, Constantin	AR	Iosăşel	LP
	Mihályi, Petru	MM	Vişeu	MO
	Racz, Atanasiu	TM	Becicherecul Mic	LP
	Roman, Alexandru	BH	Ceica	LP
	Szerb, George	CS	Zorlenţu Mare	LP
	Truţ(î)a, Petru	HD	Baia-de-Criş	RNP
	Véghsö, Gellért	BH	Beiuş	LP
	1887-1892	Beleş, Ioan	AR	Radna
Constantini, George		AR	Iosăşel	LP
Doda, Traian		CS	Caransebeş	RNP
Mihályi, Petru		MM	Şugatag	MO, NP
Popovici, Mihail		CS	Caransebeş	RNP
Rezei, Silviu		BH	Ceica	LP
Racz, Atanasiu		TM	Becicherecul Mic	LP
Szerb, George		CS	Zorlenţu Mare	LP
Véghsö, Gellért	BH	Beiuş	LP	

Table 2. Distribution of mandates and parties according to elective colleges

	Ad m. uni t	Elective college	186 9- 187 2	1872 - 1875	187 5- 187 8	187 8- 188 1	188 1- 188 4	188 4- 188 7	188 7- 189 2	T o t a l
1	AR	Ineu (Buteni)	2 RNP B	1 CLP, LP	1 RNP B					4
2	AR	Chişineu- Criş	2 DP, CLP	1 48P, UCO, IP						3
3	AR (ZR)	Iosăşel (Hălmaşgiul Mare)	1 RNP B	1 RNPB	1 RNP B	1 LP	1 LP	1 LP	1 LP	7
4	AR	Radna	1 CLP	2 RNPB				1 LP	1 LP	5
5	AR	Şiria- Pâncota (Şiria)	1 RNP B	1 RNPB	1 LP, ILP, OU					3
6	BH	Aleşd		1 DP, LP						1
7	BH	Beiuş	1 DP	1 CLP, LP	1 LP	7				
8	BH	Ceica	1 RNP B	1 RNPB	1 LP	7				
9	BN (NS)	Rodna	1 DP	1 RNPT						2
1 0	BV	Braşov II				1 LP, RNP T				1
1 1	CJ	Teaca (Mociu-Cluj de Jos)	1 DP	1 DP, LP						2
1 2	CS (CR)	Bocşa	1 DP	1 DP, LP	1 LP	1 OU	2 LP			6
1 3	CS (CR)	Caransebeş		1 RNPB	1 RNP B	1 RNP B	1 RNP	1 RNP	2 RNP	7
1 4	CS (CR)	Făget	1 DP	1 DP, LP						2

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)									
15	CS (CR)	Lugoj	1 RNP B							1
16	CS (CR)	Sasca	1 RNP B	1 DP, RNPB	1 LP	1 LP		1 RNP		5
17	CS (CR)	Zorlențu Mare	2 DP	1 DP, LP	2 LP	1 LP	1 LP	1 LP	1 LP	9
18	FG	Arpașul de Jos (Făgăraș de Jos)	1 RNP T							1
19	HD	Baia-de-Criș						1 RNP		1
20	HD	Hațeg	1 RNP T	1 RNPT						2
21	HD (OR)	Orăștie			4 RNP T					4
22	HD (ZR)	Brad	1 RNP B	1 RNPB	1 RNP B					3
23	MM	Sighetu Marmației	1 DP							1
24	MM	Șugatag	1 DP	1 DP, LP	1 LP	1 LP	1 LP	1 LP	1 MO, NP	7
25	MM	Vișeu	1 DP	1 DP, LP	1 LP	1 OU, MO		1 MO		5
26	SD (CH)	Ileanda Mare (Mesteacăn)	1 DP	1 DP	1 LP	1 LP				4
27	SJ (SM j)	Cehu Silvaniei		1 48P, UCO, IP	1 IP	1 IP				3
28	SJ (SM j)	Tășnad	1 DP							1
29	SM (CH)	Șomcuța Mare	1 DP	1 DP	1 LP					3
30	TM	Becicherecu					1 LP	1 LP	1 LP	3

0		1 Mic								
3 1	TM	Biserica Albă		1 RNPB					1	
3 2	TM	Ciacova	1 DP						1	
3 3	TM	Moravița	1 RNP B			1 LP			2	
3 4	TM	Recaș				1 LP	1 LP		2	
3 5	TM	Timișoara			1 LP	1 LP	1 LP		3	
3 6	TO	Comloș	1 DP						1	
3 7	TO	Sănnicolau Mare	1 RNP B	1 DP, RWO					2	
3 8	TO	Zitiște	1 RNP B						1	
		Total mandates	31	25	21	14	11	12	9	1 2 3
		Total colleges	27	24	17	14	10	12	8	1 1 2

List of abbreviations

1. Abbreviations of administrative units¹

AR	Arad
BH	Bihor
BN	Bistrița-Năsăud
BV	Brașov
CH	<i>Chioar (Cetatea de Piatră)</i>
CJ	Cluj
CR	<i>Caraș</i>
CS	Caraș-Severin
FG	Făgăraș
HD	Hunedoara
MM	Maramureș
NS	<i>Năsăud</i>
OR	<i>Orăștie</i>
SD	Solnoc-Dăbâca
SJ	Sălaj
SM	Satu Mare
SMj	<i>Solnocul de Mijloc</i>
TM	Timiș
TO	Torontal
ZR	<i>Zarand</i>

2. Abbreviations of political formations²

48P	The 1848 Party (January 1869 - 24 March 1874)
CLP	The Center-Left Party (January 1866 - 1 March 1875)
DP	The Deákist Party (January 1866 - 1 March 1875)
ILP	The Independent Liberal Party (19 May 1876 - 11 April 1878)
IP	The Independence Party (17 May 1874 - September 1884)
LP	The Liberal Party (1 March 1875 - 1906)
MO	The Moderate Opposition (March 1881 - December 1891)
NP	The National Party (7 January 1892 - 1899, 1904-1905)
RNP	The Romanian National Party Transylvania and Hungary (12-14 May 1881 - 1896)
RNPB	The Romanian National Party from Banat (26 January/7 February 1869 - 3/15 May 1881)
RNPT	The Romanian National Party from Transylvania (7 March 1869 - 3/15 May 1881)

¹ Administrative units in italics disappeared or were reorganized through the 1876 reform.

² Cf. A. Toth, *op. cit.*, pp. 142-145.

RWO	The Right Wing Opposition (7 March 1875 - 11 April 1878)
UCO	The United Constitutional Opposition (24 March 1874 - 17 May 1874)
UO1	The United Opposition (12 April 1878 - 20 November 1880)
UO2	The Club of Constitutional Opposition Detached Persons (20 November 1880 - March 1881)

3. Other abbreviations

- TI Tendency I - Hungarian governmental parties: DP, LP
TII Tendency II - Hungarian opposition parties: RWO, MO, UO1-2, UCO, 48P, CLP, DP, IP, LP, ILP, NP
TIII Tendency III - Romanian national parties: RNPB, RNPT, RNP

THE COMMUNIST CENSORSHIP AND THE WAR FOR INDEPENDENCE (1877-1878) A CENTURY SINCE ITS ACHIEVEMENT

Gabriel Moisa*

Abstract

In the second half of the years 1970s, under a communist regime in which the censorship was at her home, in Romania was given free for celebrating the centenary of the State Independence, that under the terms in which the recovery of the past was made selectively and in the areas useful for the regime. So as in 1968 came the time for "declassification" of the moment 1918, celebrating for the first time, after half of century, the unification of Transylvania with Romania in the terms and conditions imposed by the regime, the year 1977 meant the celebration with pomp of 100 years of independence. The present study tries to capture the concrete relationships associated with the censorship which accompanied this phenomenon.

Keywords: *Eastern Crisis, Romania, Russia, Independence, Historiography*

The reopening of the "Eastern crisis" in the years 1875-1876, together with the riots and the anti-Ottoman wars from Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia and Montenegro, helped the fight for independence in Romania. All these riots and wars were backed by Russia, which aspired to achieve the hegemony in the area. Romania wanted to gain its independence through diplomatic channels, but the new Ottoman constitution of 1876 maintained Romania's status. Under the circumstances, the only way of achieving its goal was the military one. The negotiations between Romania and the Tsarist Russia that began in 1876, at Livadia, on April 4th 1877 ended up with the Romanian-Russian Convention which stipulated that, in the context of the war outbreak in the Balkans, Russia was allowed to cross the Romanian territory with its the army, on its own expense and on a route that avoided Bucharest, Russia also had to maintain Romania's territorial integrity and to respect its political rights. On April 12th 1877, Russia declared war on the Ottoman Empire, and the Turks bombed villages on the North of the Danube. The Romanians responded by bombing Vidin.

On May 9th 1877, the Foreign Minister, Mihail Kogălniceanu, proclaimed Romania's independence in the Chamber of Deputies. Romania expressed its intention to participate to the Russo-Turkish war through the voice of its Prime Minister, I. C. Brătianu, but the Russians turned its offer down. However, after the Tsarist armies began to lose ground, Grand Duke Nicholas, head of the Russian troops in the Balkans, asked support from Carol I. Carol I accepted becoming commander of the Romanian-Russian troops at Plevna. After Turkey's

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capitulation, the Great Powers recognized Romania's independence in the treaties signed at San Stefano (February 1878) and Berlin (June-July 1878). At the Congress of Berlin, Romania gained its independence, received Dobrogea, with the Danube Delta and the Snake Island (previously held by Turkey), but it was forced to give Russia the counties from Southern Bessarabia (Cahul, Bolgrad and Ismail). On November 14th 1878, Dobrogea became a Romanian territory.

A century later, under the conditions of a Communist regime where censorship was at home, Romania was free to celebrate 100 years of independence in the context of a highly selective redeeming atmosphere of its historic past and only on segments that were useful to the interests of the Communist regime. As 1968 was the year of "the declassification" of the moment of 1918¹, celebrating for the first time half a century since the union of Transylvania to Romania, in the terms and under the conditions imposed by the regime, the year 1977 celebrated with luxury the 100 years of independence. A veritable avalanche of moments dedicated to the event appeared on the Romanian landscape, from artistic, cultural, film shows (movies and television series with this subject), to symposiums, scientific sessions and exhibitions in museums.

Historiographical works were assigned a special place in order to mark the moment. Although many of them appeared because of the political momentum, they were carefully controlled and checked before being published due to our "big brother from the East" who was also involved and who had to be spared in the context of its not quite friendly attitude towards the young Romanian state at the time of 1877-1878.

The smooth running of the affairs in this respect was supervised by the Committee for Press and Publications, the descendent of the General Directorate of Press and Publications, the main institution of the Communist censorship after the installing of the Communist regime in Romania. Before 1949, the censorship body was represented by the Directorate of Press and Publications which was operating within the Ministry of Arts and Information. In 1949, by a Decree of the State Council, the Directorate was transformed into the General Directorate of Press and Publications (GDPP), subordinated to the Council of Ministers and organized on directorates and departments. Representative commissions² also activated in the territory. The institution was directly subordinated to the Central Committee of the Communist Party and to the Council of Ministers³. A Decree of 1975 ordered the establishment of the Committee for Press and Publications, which was later dissolved in 1977. The dissolution of the General Directorate of Press and Publications was closely linked to the consolidation of the Romanian

¹ Gabriel Moisa, *Istoria Transilvaniei în istoriografia românească 1965-1989*, Cluj-Napoca, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 2003, pp. 54-55.

² Ion Zănea, *Cenzura istoriei. Istoria cenzurată, documente (1966-1972)*, Oradea, Editura Universității din Oradea, 2006, p. 1.

³ Marin Radu Mocanu, *Cenzura comunistă*, București, Editura Albatros, 2001, p. 13.

totalitarian regime and to the political ideological changes that took place in the country in the early '70s. That is why the dissolution of the institution at the Plenary of the Central Committee of the Romanian Communist Party of June 28-29th 1977 did not mean the practical abolition of censorship in Romania. The place of institutionalized censorship was taken by "a more elaborate system of checking carried out at several levels: that of the publisher – through the book editor and reviewers (as till then); that of the Socialist Culture and Education Council, including the composition of the editorial plans (a work negatively viewed by the officials was not included in the editorial plan or was postponed from a year to another); that of the Central Committee, where a special commission worked, especially for the works of history, sociology, etc. furthermore, printing houses were ordered not to receive any text unless it bore a special stamp and signature of the publisher (institution) that had sent the work. Censorship - dominated by political interests - became, after 1975 and especially in the '80s, much more restrictive"⁴.

Thus, as shown in the data provided by the Committee for Press and Publications, the supreme body of censorship, Romanian historians and censors attempted and succeeded to perform a true expediency in order to be able to write about this event so that the Soviet Union be spared of any considerations that were inadequate to its address. This is more so because, after a period of "rebel" attitude from Nicolae Ceaușescu's part against the Soviet Union, in the summer of 1976, the visit to Crimea where he met Leonid Brezhnev, followed by the latter's visit to Bucharest in the autumn of the same year, seemed to have led to a renewal of the relationships between the two parts. Nicolae Ceaușescu needed the Soviet Union in a Romanian economic context increasingly precarious which required the shift to the USSR and Council for Mutual Economic Assistance (CMEA)⁵ as a result of the so-called Comprehensive Economic Program of CMEA issued by the Soviet Union that was meant to ensure the "flourishing of the national economy of each member country"⁶. At the same time, in the context of a totalitarian regime controlled by the political leader in Bucharest and of the increasingly evident impoverishment of the population together with other unpopular measures such as the systematization of villages, the appeal to the national feeling was one of the few possibilities of the regime to preserve some popular adherence. The anniversary of a century since the declaration of the country's national independence, in a time when

⁴ Dinu C. Giurescu (coord.), *Istoria României în date*, București, Editura Enciclopedică, 2007, p. 660.

⁵ Nicolae Ceaușescu, "Pe drumul luminos al socialismului și comunismului, al progresului și păcii", in Idem, *România pe drumul construirii societății socialiste multilateral dezvoltate*, vol. XV, București, Editura Politică, 1978, pp. 169-183; article also appeared in the Communist Party of the Soviet Union (CPSU) officious, *Pravda*, on October 29th 1977, on the occasion of celebrating 60 years since the Great Socialist Revolution of October.

⁶ *Ibidem*, p. 173.

Nicolae Ceaușescu wanted to pose to the Romanians and to the West as an independent political leader in the Communist Bloc, represented a very good opportunity to support his own projects. Accordingly, historiographical works had to be carefully monitored, focusing mainly on two objectives: the first, to spear the Soviet Union of any inadequate considerations, which, in its turn, kept a close eye on all historiographical productions regarding the Russian space; and, the second, to support the image of Nicolae Ceaușescu as an authentic national leader as well as the image of the political regime he was head of.

To achieve this purpose, each scientific paper, be it a newspaper article, a specialized study, or a book on the events of the years 1877-1878 was carefully assessed by the censorship before passing the proof for press. Not even those considered as very confident by the regime escaped the ordeal of the Committee for Press and Publications. A report carried out by this institution on January 31st 1977 mentioned the suggested objections and corrections to the work "Romania in the War of Independence 1877-1878"⁷ that was included in the editorial plan of the Military Publishing House for 1977 and whose main coordinator was Col. Ion Coman. The members of the coordinating committee were Ștefan Pascu, C. C. Giurescu, General Major Dr. Constantin Olteanu, col. Dr. Ilie Ceaușescu, col. Dr. Al. Gheorghe Savu, General Major C. Antip and General Major Dr. Eugen Bantea. As one can see, the fact that Nicolae Ceaușescu's own brother was one of the members of the coordinating committee did not exempt the work of careful checking from the part of the censors in the Committee for Press and Publications.

The conclusions of their report specified that "at our suggestion, the management of the Centre of Historical Studies and Research and Military Theory performed, in the title and the text of the paper, a number of reformulations and changes..."⁸ Absolutely all adjustments suggested to the coordinator team by the censor institution had connotations intended to protect the Soviet Union. Thus, all expressions of "regaining the independence" and "gaining the independence"⁹ had to be and, in the end, were replaced. They also asked the elimination of any references to territorial exchanges between Romania and the Tsarist Russia after the war of 1877-1878, with the emphasis on the idea of reformulating all references to the "territorial annexations" of the Tsarist Russia after the conflict in the Balkans¹⁰. At the end of the note they specified that the volume "had passed the proof for press" since all required changes had been completed.

⁷ The work was published under the title *România în războiul de independență 1877-1878*, București, Editura Militară, 1977, 675 p.

⁸ Central Historical National Archives (C.H.N.A), Fond *The Committee for Press and Print*, no. 30, 1977, f. 5.

⁹ *Ibidem*.

¹⁰ *Ibidem*.

The same types of assessments are to be found in other reports issued by the Committee for Press and Publications. Numbers I-II of the "Review of History" of 1977 published Vasile Maciu's study, *The Recognition of Romanian's Independence*. The article had been given for publication in journal number 7 from 1976, but it passed the proof for press just on February 1st 1977¹¹ and only after a series of interventions brought to the text. Absolutely all changes referred to Vasile Maciu's references to Russia. Thus, a number of sentences on the territorial exchanges discussed during the diplomatic negotiations of 1878 were reformulated. There were phrases such as: annexation, taking over, stealing, occupancy, restitution of the counties in Southern Bessarabia to the Tsarist Russia¹², avoiding possible historiographical or even political disputes on the subject. However, such formulations were accepted in quotes from the time documents or memorialistic works. In the same way we can also interpret the censors' acceptance, on almost every page, of general references to the policy led by the Tsarist Russian government which wanted to reintegrate the three counties from South-Western Bessarabia, to the diplomatic activity (speeches and press articles, memoirs) of the members of the Romanian political circles with the Great Powers in order to prevent territorial exchanges and to restore the rights on the Romanian territories, to the Romanian public opinion's reaction of resistance to these changes reflected in the time press, and to the position of the Great Powers on the changes under discussion¹³. The time politicians' position on Dobrogea was also not censored, position which, in fact, represented a hostile point of view on Russian policy in the area. In this respect, certain politicians' opinions that supported the "reunion of Dobrogea" to Romania were accepted for publication. At the same time, V. A. Urechia, G. Misail, N. Ionescu, P. P. Carp, Em. Costache Epureanu, Dimitrie A. Sturdza or C. A. Rosseti's position in the discussions of the Conservative Legislative Bodies was also reproduced in detail. They were "against getting back Dobrogea, for it (Romania) does not mean to consent to the loss of Bessarabia and to an eternal alliance with Russia"¹⁴. Vasile Maciu ingeniously assigned to the "retrograde" conservatives the idea that the cession of Southern Bessarabia in exchange for Dobrogea was not fully accepted and the censors overlooked this aspect.

The message was sent with all the imposed reformulations to the text, but the authorities in Bucharest adopted a neutral position since only the documents and the memoirs of the time talked about the loss of a part of Bessarabia to the Tsarist Russia, territories belonging to the USSR even at the moment when the article was published.

On February 28th 1977, the Committee for Press and Publications approved the monograph entitled *Independența României a*

¹¹ *Ibidem*, f. 7.

¹² *Ibidem*.

¹³ *Ibidem*, f. 8.

¹⁴ *Ibidem*.

work of many historians, published under Ștefan Pascu's editorial. Right in the censor's preamble we find out that the volume was included in the measure plan regarding Romania's anniversary of 100 years of state independence, plan approved by the Political Executive Committee of the Romanian Communist Party (R.C.P). The monograph was issued, as specified in the same preamble, under the aegis of the Academy of Social and Political Sciences, Centre of Historical Studies and Research and Military Theory, Ministry of Foreign Affairs and General Directorate of the State Archives, and included 31 studies on gaining our state independence. Although it appeared under the aegis of these institutions of the totalitarian regime, the work needed the approval of the Committee for Press and Publications. Perhaps that is why the approval, covering more than four pages, had to be given following a very careful examination of the material. A significant area was allotted, as the censor emphasized from the first pages, to "present the situation of the Romanians in the Romanian provinces under foreign domination - particularly of those in Transylvania and Bukovina - of their struggle to maintain and develop their national consciousness and to escape the domination of absolutist empires"¹⁵. References to the actions of the Romanians from Bessarabia for unity and independence lay several lines below. The censor's conclusions to the presentation of these aspects in the volume are quite interesting. He believes that "in our opinion, they can be approved"¹⁶ for publication, corresponding to the ideological requirements of the moment.

The censor or censors' opinion to some of the formulations that could have affected the Soviet sensitivity regarding Bessarabia is quite surprising, especially since the volume of studies entitled *Independența României* (Romanian's Independence) stated the regime's official position to the events of the years 1877-1878 and appeared under the aegis of the above mentioned institutions. Moreover, the fact that the Ministry of Foreign Affairs was one of these institutions meant that the volume was also intended for foreign countries which could thus become aware of Communist Romania's official position to Bessarabia.

The approval note insisted mainly on two studies in the volume. One, signed by the same Vasile Maciu, entitled "Romanian Diplomacy and the Recognition of Independence"¹⁷, and the second, signed by Mircea Mușat and Ion Ardeleanu, entitled "The Great Union of 1918 and Its International Confirmation"¹⁸. Both studies were considered models to be followed by those who would deal in the future with this theme and not an issue that was meant to become a subject to censorship,

¹⁵ *Ibidem*, f. 16.

¹⁶ *Ibidem*.

¹⁷ Vasile Maciu, "Diplomația românească și recunoașterea independenței", in Ștefan Pascu (coord.), *Independența României*, București, Editura Academiei, 1977, pp. 400-422.

¹⁸ Mircea Mușat, Ion Ardeleanu, „Marea unire din 1918 și confirmarea ei pe plan internațional”, in Ștefan Pascu (coord.), *Independența României*, București, Editura Academiei, 1977, pp. 611-662.

although the text indicated a number of sensitive formulations from the authors' part. It was almost impossible for the situation to be otherwise since the authors' names, especially those of Mircea Mușat and Ion Ardeleanu, were under close surveillance from the part of the censors in the Committee for Press and Publications.

The censor of Vasile Maciu's study mentioned in his note situations, historical data and formulations that, in other times, would have certainly been amended. The note referred to the fact that the author insisted, based on a comprehensive research, on the intense activity carried out by Romania on diplomatic channels for the recognition of its independence and for the defence of its territorial integrity¹⁹. In connection with this aspect, the censor emphasized the fact that Vasile Maciu talked in his study about Russia's intention to take Southern Bessarabia from Romania, in exchange for which, as compensation, Romania would receive the Danube Delta and Dobrogea till Constanța, fact that would have "stirred spirits in Romania"²⁰. Another sensitive issue for the Romanian - Soviet relationships reported in Vasile Maciu's study was I. C. Brătianu's intervention in the Chamber of Deputies, intervention that led to the passing of a motion of protest which expressed the determination to "maintain the country's territorial integrity and not to allow any cession from the land, under any name and for any compensation or reparation"²¹. The reference was clear to the loss of Southern Bessarabia in exchange for Dobrogea and to the fact that the Chamber of Deputies of that time did not agree with this. In the same thematic trend, the censor mentioned that Vasile Maciu insisted on several pages on the provisions referring to Romania at the preliminaries of peace between Russia and the Ottoman Empire that were signed at San Stefano (including those referring to the territorial exchange), the author showing, according to the censor, that these provisions imposed Romania the loss of a part of its territory (Southern Bessarabia) in exchange for another territory, which was also Romanian and which was inhabited mostly by Romanians (Dobrogea). The author's reproductions from the statement submitted by the Romanian Government to the Peace Congress of Berlin were also discussed, including among others: Russia's territorial claims against Romania, the Russian representative's position and unconvincing arguments, the opinion of some Western diplomats and politicians who felt that Bessarabia should be "sacrificed", as well as the debates on Article 45 of the Treaty of Berlin which established the cession to Russia of Southern Bessarabia²². According to the censor's opinion, the author insisted too much on I. C. Brătianu's protest at the Peace Congress of Berlin that made direct reference to Russia: "to deprive us of a part of our heritage

¹⁹ C.H.N.A., Fond *The Committee for Press and Print*, no. 30, 1977, f. 16.

²⁰ *Ibidem*.

²¹ *Ibidem*.

²² *Ibidem*.

would not only cause deep sorrow for the Romanian nation, but it would also break down its trust in the power of the treaties...”²³

The study signed by Mircea Mușat and Ion Ardeleanu²⁴ seemed even more straightforward to the censor. Since from an ideological point of view, the two were the most authorized voices of the Romanian historiography at the time, the censor mentioned only some aspects that seemed to be susceptible. It was obvious that the points of view of the two authors were not anything else but the regime’s official position on the matter. Among the most complex historiographical issues with political aspect on which both made considerations, according to the censor’s opinion, was “the proclamation, on the Leninist principle of peoples’ right for self-determination, of the province’s autonomy and then of the independent Moldavian Democratic Republic”²⁵. Introducing a Leninist principle was interesting and difficult to refute even by the Soviet historiography and made the authors’ arguments stronger. To make things more sensitive, the authors quoted from the decision of union “forever with its mother Romania”²⁶, adopted on March 27th 1918 by the State Council from Kishinev (Chișinău) and presented data about the meetings that took place throughout the whole province to express the enthusiasm to the act of union. The censor considered as belonging to the same spectrum Mircea Mușat and Ion Ardeleanu’s concerns to report in detail the events that led to the “union of Bukovina with Romania by decision of the Constituent Assembly in Chernivtsi (Cernăuți), November 28th 1918, Ukraine’s reaction to this decision”²⁷. Finally, the censor showed concerns about the fact that the idea of the union of Bessarabia to Romania appeared in too many places as a result of the free will expressed by the popular masses of this province, under the right to self-determination.

Taking into account the names involved and the institutions under the aegis of which the volume appeared, the censor limited himself to say that such sensitive issues presented in the two studies were well-documented and therefore could not be confuted. However, he came with the proposal that the “the editor in charge, Comrade Academician Ștefan Pascu, should review in the light of the existing guidelines the mentioned pages, avoiding, if possible, the insistent repetitions and some of the inappropriate formulations”²⁸. The censor’s position was still very timid as compared to other occasions when he punctually would propose the elimination of one passage or another.

Several similar works meant to celebrate the events of 1877-1878 were carefully screened by the Communist censorship²⁹. In absolutely all of them, censors proved to be very careful in the references to Tsarist

²³ *Ibidem*.

²⁴ Mircea Mușat, Ion Ardeleanu, *op. cit.*

²⁵ C.H.N.A., Fond *The Committee for Press and Print*, no. 30, 1977, f. 17.

²⁶ *Ibidem*.

²⁷ *Ibidem*.

²⁸ *Ibidem*, f. 18.

²⁹ *Ibidem*, f. 19.

Russia's attitude towards Romania in those years. In fact, these are, with few exceptions, the only issues raised by the censorship, showing a great concern to protect the Soviet Union. The report on the collection of *Documente privind războiul pentru independența României, 1877-1878* (Documents Regarding Romania's War for the Independence, 1877-1878)³⁰ showed a real obsession for this question. There were doubts from the censors' part on the necessity of the large number of documents introduced in the volume that referred to "Russia's intentions to take the three counties from Southern Bessarabia"³¹, emphasizing the protest of the Romanian politicians of the time against the decisions of the Peace Congress of San Stefano and of Berlin, which "alienated our ancestral land"³² to Russia. Other sensitive issues raised by the documents that would be printed referred, according to the censors, to the "information about the imminent Russian invasion, then about the actual entry of the Tsarist troops in Romania, about the disagreements between the Romanian and the Russian armies, the last document (no. 317, pages 953-964), dated 1884, made the inventory of the damages suffered by Romania as a result of the Russian troops crossing through Southern Bessarabia, Greater Wallachia (Muntenia) and Lesser Wallachia (Oltenia) (about 18 million lei, recognized only partially, but not paid by the Russians)"³³. This last assertion was very interesting and exciting for the historian of that time and of the present having in view the fact that the same phenomena repeated with the same players at the end of World War II. Since nothing could be said about those last events, the consequences of Russians' crossing Romania in 1877 were noted for the first time after 1948. Although the publication of these documents seemed a little bit imposed according to the censor's opinion, he concluded that "since they make reference to the time documents, we suggest they be approved"³⁴.

The same censors, however, were very harsh with Prince Carol who, in their opinion, was presented in positive colours in too many places. "In some of the documents there are passages praising Prince Carol and claims according to which, once embarked on the land of Romania, he became Romanian"³⁵, says the censors' note. These assertions were considered totally inappropriate, therefore they proposed their disposal from the texts presented in the volume.

The censor's point of view on the other major player in the independence war, the Ottoman Empire, is also interesting. Although, at least theoretically, the Ottoman Empire had to be blasphemed since not only then (1877) but also in the present (1977) it belonged to enemy camp, this did not happen, at least in the case of the present volume.

³⁰ Ionel Gal (coord.), *Documente privind războiul pentru independența României, 1877-1878*, vol. I, București, Editura Academiei, 969 p.

³¹ C.H.N.A., Fond *The Committee for Press and Print*, no. 30, 1977, f. 19.

³² *Ibidem*.

³³ *Ibidem*.

³⁴ *Ibidem*.

³⁵ *Ibidem*, f. 18.

Although the time documents were extremely harsh with the Turks, the author of the note proposed to publish them, but only after the elimination of the invectives against Turkey³⁶.

Since 1977 till the dissolution of this Committee, several other studies, articles, volumes of documents or books of author on Romania's war for independence 1877-1878 were published. They were all carefully censored by the Committee for Press and Publications until its dissolution at the Plenary of the Central Committee of the Romanian Communist Party of June 28-29th 1977, occasion on which it was pompously announced that censorship had been abolished in Romania. In fact this never happened since the Committee's place was taken by an invisible institutional censorship present at several levels, from book editors, referents, editorial plans of institutions that did not include inconsistent ideological works, printing houses, which were ordered not to include works unless they bore a special stamp and signature from the publishing house (institution) that had sent the manuscript, to the Central Committee, where a special commission was analyzing historical works. The fact is that censorship became harsher and more restrictive.

³⁶ *Ibidem.*

ALL'OMBRA DELLE RIFORME. COSPIRAZIONE, DOPPIOGIOCHISMO E RIVOLUZIONE NELLA RUSSIA DI PËTR STOLYPIN

Francesco Randazzo*

Abstract

In 1911 a double agent working for the Okhrana assassinated Stolypin, and Finance Minister Vladimir Kokovtsov replaced him. The cautious Kokovtsov was very able and a supporter of the Tsar, but he could not compete with the powerful court factions that dominated the government. Historians have debated whether Russia had the potential to develop a constitutional government between 1905 and 1914. The failure to do so was partly because the Tsar was not willing to give up autocratic rule or share power. By manipulating the franchise, the Government obtained progressively more conservative, but less representative, Dumas. Moreover, the regime sometimes bypassed the conservative Dumas and ruled by decree. During this period, the Government's policies waivered from reformist to repressive. Historians have speculated about whether Witte's and Stolypin's bold reform plans could have "saved" the Russian Empire. But court politics, together with the continuing isolation of the Tsar and the bureaucracy from the rest of society, hampered all reforms. Suspensions of civil liberties and the rule of law continued in many places, and neither workers nor the Orthodox Church had the right to organize themselves as they chose. Discrimination against Poles, Jews, Ukrainians, and Old Believers was common. Domestic unrest was on the rise while the empire's foreign policy was becoming more adventurous

Keywords: *Russian Empire, Stolypin, Revolution, Agrarian Disorders*

L'uccisione di Stolypin il primo settembre 1911, fu uno dei tanti assassinii politici che dal 1878 funestarono la vita politica russa. Vittima illustre ne era stato lo stesso “zar liberatore” Alessandro II, colui che tante speranze aveva fatto nascere in Russia all'indomani del Manifesto del 19 febbraio 1861 con cui affrancava il lavoro servile. Condannato a morte nella tarda estate del 1879, i terroristi avevano eseguito la sentenza soltanto due anni più tardi. Un gesto estremo da cui i cospiratori si attendevano uno sfaldamento della compagine statale che in realtà non ci fu. Al contrario, il terrore poliziesco continuò a essere utilizzato come l'unico strumento possibile per controllare il Paese alle prese con i drammatici risvolti della questione sociale esplosa dopo la *debâcle* di Crimea. I congiurati che avevano partecipato al regicidio, per la maggior parte studenti e studentesse, ma anche figli di contadini, erano riusciti a infiltrarsi perfino nelle fila della polizia segreta e, nonostante l'alta sorveglianza, colpirono ripetutamente funzionari, burocrati e membri della famiglia imperiale.

Molti Romanov seguiranno la sorte di Alessandro II e con loro uomini politici in vista quali i ministri degli Interni Dmitrij Sergeevič Sipjagin (1853-1902) lo “sciocco”, e Vjačeslav Konstantinovič [von] Pleve (1846-1904) la “canaglia”, il ministro dell'Istruzione Nikolaj Pavlonič

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Bogolepov (1846-1901) e il principe Aleksej Vasil'evič Obolenskij (1819-1884) che, come governatore di Mosca, aveva represso nella Russia meridionale alcune rivolte contadine negli anni tra il 1881 e il 1884.

I tredici anni di regno di Alessandro III (1881-1894) furono contrassegnati da una relativa calma; l'attesa ondata rivoluzionaria parve ridimensionarsi. Ridotta al silenzio la stampa, costantemente controllati i pochi circoli liberali, dispersi o deportati in Siberia i rivoluzionari, il governo sembrò proseguire lungo la più dura reazione, ignorando le pulsioni sociali e cercando appoggio nuovamente nella nobiltà, a cui affidò ampi poteri di controllo sugli *zemstva*. Il disastro ferroviario del 1887, in cui lo zar e il principe ereditario Nicola per poco non rimasero uccisi, dimostrò al contrario che le forze rivoluzionarie erano attive: il treno imperiale deragliò a Borki e ventuno persone perirono. Non si trattò di un incidente, ma di un attentato "inetto e pazzesco" - dice Wolf Giusti - organizzato da studenti universitari¹, progenie del circolo studentesco moscovita capeggiato da Nikolaj Vladimirovič Stankevič (1813-1840), giovane hegeliano pieno di talento morto prematuramente. Alcuni anni dopo, in Giappone, un fanatico, impugnando una spada da samurai, si avventò contro il granduca Nicola, che sfuggì ancora una volta miracolosamente alla morte². Il primo novembre del 1894 morì Alessandro III, appena cinquantenne, a causa delle numerose complicazioni seguite alle lesioni riportate nell'incidente ferroviario del 1887. L'erede, Nicola II (1894), educato dal padre e dal procuratore del Santo Sinodo a credere che fosse suo dovere mantenere il principio dell'autocrazia, suscitò la vana speranza di una svolta politica in senso liberale. In realtà, prevalse una linea politica conservatrice ben rappresentata dall'azione del ministro degli Interni Pleve, che ebbe l'ambizione di trasformare la Russia in uno Stato di polizia, ancor più di quanto non lo fosse in passato. Autocrazia e reazione frenarono i rivoluzionari, i quali volevano a tutti i costi lo smantellamento dello zarismo e auspicavano l'instaurazione di un nuovo ordine sociale.

Per un certo periodo l'azione rivoluzionaria si limitò a colmare il *gap* esistente tra *intelligencija* e contadini, ma tale divaricazione non fu mai realmente superata e, quando le due classi si mossero all'unisono, la

¹ Wolfgang Giusti, *Storia della Russia, 988-1974*, Roma, Abete, 1975, p. 33. Sul ruolo degli studenti universitari nella lotta armata si veda il celeberrimo contributo di Franco Venturi sul populismo russo e l'efficace sintesi di Dmitrij Tschizewskij nella sua *Storia dello spirito russo* (Sansoni, 1965). In entrambi i casi viene richiamato il ruolo del mito decabrista presente negli studenti universitari appartenenti alle future correnti populiste. In russo, un buon lavoro sull'argomento è quello degli autori Крутов В.В., Швецова-Крутова Л.В., *Белые, пятна красного цвета. Декабристы*, [Bianchi, macchie di colore rosso. Decabristi] (*В двух книгах*). Новости прошлого. Москва, 2001.

² Lev Tikomirov, grande teorico de "La libertà del popolo" rendeva noto, intorno alla metà degli anni Ottanta, che "*le terrorisme eu tant que système de lutte politique est soit impuissant, soit superflu... Sous l'aspect des changements politiques, la terreur ne signifie à peu près rien*". Si veda Hélène Carrère D'Encausse, *Le malheur russe. Essai sur le meurtre politique*, Paris, Fayard, 1988, p. 307.

rivoluzione divenne ancora più esplosiva³. Così, mentre l'ala più moderata dei gruppi rivoluzionari decise di basare la lotta su programmi politico-economici, abbandonando la strategia del terrore, il partito socialrivoluzionario, nato in Russia come una versione più radicale dei gruppi populistici, unì alla propaganda di massa un ritorno alla politica del terrore e degli attentati. Gli anni tra il 1902 e il 1907 furono funestati così da una speciale organizzazione combattente i cui capi vanno identificati in Georgij Andreevič Geršuni (1870-1908), Boris Viktorovič Savinkov (1879-1925) ed Evno Fišelevič Azev (1869-1918). L'ultimo dei tre era, come fu più tardi Dmitrij Grigor'evič Bogrov (1887-1911), l'uccisore di Stolypin, un "doppiogiochista" introdotto dal Pleve nelle file rivoluzionarie e autore del suo omicidio (1904). I delitti politici continuarono senza sosta con l'uccisione di importanti personaggi politici tra cui il governatore di Ufa e quello generale della Finlandia.

Il meccanismo di collaborazione tra rivoluzionari e polizia segreta zarista, l'*Ochrana*, si rivelò tuttavia un'arma a doppio taglio per l'autocrazia. A farne le spese fu il ministro "riformatore" Pëtr Stolypin (1862-1911), vittima della rete di spionaggio da lui stesso ammessa per prevenire i crimini interni. La sua morte, la cui matrice è chiaramente di natura terroristica, lascia aperti ancora oggi molti quesiti. Avvenuta durante uno spettacolo teatrale a Kiev per mano di Dmitrij Grigor'evič Bogrov (1887-1911)⁴, l'uccisione del primo ministro russo fu accolta con entusiasmo dai gruppi rivoluzionari più estremisti, che videro nell'assassino la figura dell'eroe-liberatore. Tutta la vicenda però si tinge di giallo poiché l'"esecuzione", a prima vista inquadrata come atto di vendetta nei confronti del ministro dal polso duro, contiene un'eterogeneità di elementi che inducono a piste di indagine nettamente divergenti tra loro.

Quella più accreditata dagli stessi contemporanei condusse direttamente ai movimenti rivoluzionari e trovò vasta eco non solo all'interno dell'Impero, ma anche al di fuori dei suoi confini. Come dimostrò un articolo apparso sul quotidiano socialista "l'Avanti", il 16 settembre 1911, la morte del primo ministro era stata ben organizzata e prevista anzitempo dal momento che venne scoperta dalla polizia segreta una tipografia nella quale erano preparati i manifesti nichilisti diretti al popolo, per informarlo che Stolypin era stato raggiunto dalla vendetta

³ Alan Moorehead, *La rivoluzione russa*, Milano, Mondadori, 1959, p. 5.

⁴ Un ebreo, socialista rivoluzionario, ma anche agente di polizia che proprio nella duplice veste di agente-doppiogiochista aveva avuto facilmente accesso a teatro. Di lui si ebbero notizie confuse e contraddittorie. La sua azione, ritenuta da molti storici un atto di vendetta per i *pogromy* antiebraici organizzati sotto il governo di Stolypin, può esser stata agevolata da una serie di fattori ostili al primo ministro, una trama complicata nella quale si intrecciano più motivazioni e più ordini gerarchici. Dal suo interrogatorio subito dopo l'arresto, il 1 settembre 1911, si evince che egli fu nel 1905 un simpatizzante del gruppo socialdemocratico russo, poi nel 1906 entrò a far parte del gruppo anarchico di Kiev e dall'anno successivo iniziò a collaborare con i servizi segreti della capitale ucraina con l'identità "Alenskij", dal 1910 nel reparto investigativo di San Pietroburgo con il nome in codice "Nadeždin".

popolare. Accanto a tale ipotesi vi fu la corresponsabilità degli elementi conservatori vicini allo zar Nicola II il quale, per sua natura, nutriva sentimenti di diffidenza nei confronti dei suoi ministri, nella cui scelta, però, almeno durante la prima metà del suo regno, diede prova di giudizio sensato. Nella scelta dell'ex governatore di Saratov a primo ministro aveva certamente visto la possibilità di dare realizzazione pratica a una politica più repressiva. Era giunto a tale decisione ricordando l'attacco sferrato in un governatorato del territorio di Samara da Stolypin il quale, oltrepassando i limiti delle sue competenze, era riuscito a sedare la rivolta, realizzando ciò che al governatore del luogo non era riuscito di fare. Ma il giudizio positivo dello zar sul suo capo di governo si tramutò nel tempo in aperta ostilità. Per alcuni storici, ciò fu dovuto in parte alla sistematica azione dei militanti dell'Unione del Popolo Russo (U.P.R.) i quali, avendo libero accesso alla corte, "approfittavano delle violenze che lo zar accordava loro per criticare la politica di Stolypin e provocare la sfiducia contro i suoi disegni"⁵. Fomentatori di odio contro i rappresentanti più liberali del governo Stolypin, essi affermavano davanti a Nicola II che "la popolarità del primo ministro cresceva a scapito di quella dello zar stesso", e che "un movimento rivoluzionario in Russia non era mai esistito; per conseguenza, Stolypin non aveva sventato e non aveva potuto sventare alcuna rivoluzione. Al contrario i piccoli movimenti rivoluzionari che si erano prodotti nel paese si esplicavano unicamente attraverso la debolezza inammissibile del potere"⁶. Accusato di un liberalismo eccessivo, dannoso per l'autocrazia, di avere a disposizione una Duma la cui istituzione era puramente rivoluzionaria, di accrescere il suo potere a dispetto di quello dello zar, di aver creato l'alibi della lotta controrivoluzionaria per la smania di fama personale, e soprattutto di aver allontanato dalla corte l'uomo prediletto della zarina, il monaco Grigorij Rasputin, Stolypin cominciò a essere guardato con sospetto dall'intera corte zarista.

L'assassinio del primo ministro è collegato anche con il risentimento ebraico per la politica antisemita in atto nell'Impero dalla fine del XIX secolo, resa ancora più dura da Pleve durante il suo ministero. Dmitrij Bogrov era infatti un ebreo e non è da escludere che il suo atto fosse anche da porre in relazione con i risentimenti alimentati nell'animo degli ebrei russi dai *pogromy* del 1907 voluti da Stolypin in risposta ai continui attentati dinamitardi di cui lui e la sua famiglia furono destinatari. Lo storico Wolf Giusti, collega l'uccisione di Stolypin con gli esiti e le contraddizioni della riforma agraria da lui portata avanti dal novembre 1906 al giugno 1910. Egli si riferisce a quel meccanismo che, attraverso le riforme agrarie, generò tensione tra coloro che andarono a costituire, arricchendosi, una solida borghesia agraria e coloro che rimasero senza terra e mezzi di sostentamento. "Stolypin, con freddo

⁵ Aleksandr Gerasimov, *Tsarisme et terrorisme. Souvenirs du général Guérassimov ancien chef de l'Okhrana de S. Péterbourg 1909-1912*, Paris, Librairie Plon, 1934, p. 253.

⁶ *Ibidem*.

calcolo, voleva insomma destare l'invidia tra i vari strati contadini per indebolirne la forza di ribellione, voleva creare dei nuclei operai che avrebbero trovato il proprio tornaconto nell'appoggiare il regime zarista" contro le agitazioni dei loro compagni di lavoro⁷.

La genesi della lotta rivoluzionaria, brevemente delineata, si conclude con un passaggio fondamentale: quello relativo cioè alla nascita di sodalizi interclassisti, che era stata anticipata dai *narodniki*. Da questo ultimo anello della catena rivoluzionaria "venne fuori la figura dell'uomo nuovo, il rivoluzionario di professione, un essere che si considerava sacrificabile, che seguiva ciecamente il capo e la linea del partito e che, se necessario, mentiva, truffava e assassinava pur di conseguire lo scopo. Non era dominato né da patriottismo né da pietà, riponeva fede esclusivamente nella rivoluzione e in questa sua fede era un fanatico... Un personaggio davvero sinistro nella mutevole scena..., l'uomo che tradisce gli amici, la spia al soldo della polizia, l'*agent provocateur*"⁸. Si faceva largo nella mente del rivoluzionario russo l'idea che il male incarnato dall'autocrazia dovesse essere sradicato con tutti i mezzi, comprese le bombe.

All'epoca di Alessandro II esistevano persino scuole clandestine in cui si insegnava a costruire e a far detonare le bombe. Tra la fine del XIX secolo e l'inizio del XX i terroristi non esercitavano il terrore per professione, non erano nobili, né ufficiali della Guardia, ma studenti universitari calati in un mondo di appassionato idealismo e di odio. Il permesso, concesso a un numero sempre più crescente di elementi derivanti dalle classi più povere, di giungere all'istruzione superiore, faceva sì che numerosi fossero tra gli studenti coloro che lottarono contro condizioni economiche difficili e spesso misere. I disordini recenti, soprattutto nella capitale, avevano dimostrato come lo spirito di corpo degli studenti fosse sempre forte e attivo⁹. Il rivoluzionario di fine XIX secolo, incarnava diverse qualità e interessi: provava un sentimento di avversione nei confronti dell'apparato statale e, sull'onda delle idee liberali europee, si poneva come forza nuova a dispetto di una folla di uomini impauriti e tradizionalmente schierata dalla parte dello zar.

Nei primi anni del XX secolo un ruolo importante nella lotta ebbe il sodalizio, quanto mai insolito, tra le frange estremiste dei partiti di sinistra, alcuni esponenti anarchici e i contadini. Secondo Franco Venturi infatti "un anello di congiunzione esiste tra socialisti-rivoluzionari e la campagna, che un tempo aveva fatto fallire i populisti. È di là che il movimento seppe trascinare i contadini sulla sua scia e avviare un'azione terrorista completamente nuova, poiché fondata sulla comprensione e l'appoggio popolare"¹⁰.

⁷ Wolfgang Giusti, *op. cit.*, p. 209.

⁸ *Ibidem*, pp. 51-53.

⁹ Franco Venturi, *Il populismo russo*, 3 voll., Torino, Einaudi, 1977-1979, vol. III, *Dall'andata nel popolo al terrorismo*, p. 286.

¹⁰ Hélène Carrère D'Encausse, *op. cit.*, p. 318.

Bisognava evitare la formazione di una “borghesia contadina”: questo era il fine dei rivoluzionari. Conservare la proprietà comunitaria, l'*obščina*, evitando la proprietà privata della terra, divenne per i socialisti rivoluzionari un imperativo categorico. Ma era necessario incanalare la spontaneità dell'indignazione contadina che si rivelava negli incendi delle proprietà private, negli assassinii di proprietari, nei saccheggi dei loro beni, in un movimento organizzato.

Prese così piede tra i socialisti rivoluzionari, eredi del movimento populista, il ricorso agli attentati. La loro strategia non era solo diretta a colpire il sovrano e la sua famiglia: “la violenza occupava, nella politica russa, un posto decisivo anche se gli attentati non prendevano più di mira il vertice del sistema, ma quelli che circondavano il sovrano”¹¹.

Il partito socialista rivoluzionario, dall'inizio del secolo fino al giorno dell'attentato al primo ministro russo (1911), non del tutto correttamente a esso attribuito, uccise circa 150 persone. Un numero esiguo ma indicativo, se inserito nel contesto di una violenza sempre più crescente, soprattutto nelle campagne e nella periferia del Paese, “dove si assisteva al moltiplicarsi degli assassinii di agenti di Stato e di proprietari terrieri”¹².

Ecco il quadro degli assassinii eccellenti e degli attentati politici compiuti per destabilizzare lo Stato russo agli inizi del XX secolo: nel 1901, Nikolaj Pavlonič Bogolepov (1846-1901), ministro dell'Istruzione, viene ucciso dallo studente Pëtr Vladimirovič Karpovič (1874-1917); Kostantin Petrovič Pobedonoscev (1827-1907), procuratore del Santo Sinodo, viene ferito in un attentato; nel 1902; Dmitrij Fëdorovič Trepov (1855-1906), prefetto della polizia di Mosca, subisce tre attentati ai quali sfugge miracolosamente; Dmitrij Sergeevič Sipjagin (1853-1902), ministro degli Interni, viene ucciso a Pietroburgo dallo studente Sergej Bolmakov; il governatore militare di Vilno è ferito da un colpo di pistola sparato da un terrorista lituano; il principe Aleksej Obolenskij, governatore di Char'kov, sopravvive a due attentati perpetrati contro di lui nello spazio di due mesi; nel 1903, Nikolaj Modestovič Bogdonovič (1856-1903), governatore di Ufa, viene ucciso a Kiev dallo studente Igor Dulebov; nel 1904, Nikolaj Ivanovič Bobrikov (1839-1904), governatore generale della Finlandia, è ucciso da uno studente; nello stesso anno i terroristi mettono a segno l'uccisione del governatore del Caucaso G. Bogoslovskij; Vjačeslav Konstantinovič [von] Pleve (1846-1904), ministro degli Interni, rimane ucciso da una bomba piazzata nella capitale; nel 1905, il granduca Sergej Aleksandrovič (1857-1905), figlio dello zar Alessandro II e zio di Nicola II, governatore generale di Mosca, viene assassinato il 4 febbraio con una bomba lanciata dal rivoluzionario Ivan Platonovič Kaliaev (1877-1905); il conte Pavel Kuvajlov, prefetto della polizia di Mosca, viene assassinato; nel 1906, Michail Jakovlevič Gercenštejn (1859-1906), membro della I Duma e docente di economia all'Università di Mosca, cade sotto i colpi di un antisemita; Pëtr

¹¹ *Ibidem*, p. 321.

¹² *Ibidem*.

Stolypin, primo ministro, sfugge a un attentato che produce decine di morti e feriti¹³; nel 1911, lo stesso viene ucciso nel teatro dell'Opera di Kiev in presenza dello zar e della famiglia reale. Come risulta evidente, dopo l'attentato a Stolypin del 1906, gli atti terroristici subirono una recrudescenza per via delle dure misure repressive volute dal primo ministro a cui seguirono esecuzioni e deportazioni in Siberia. In molte di quelle circostanze, fu comprovata la presenza di studenti, la quale stava a dimostrare la tipologia della nuova organizzazione rivoluzionaria.

Mentre per molti omicidi si è trattato di attentati terroristici voluti dalle frange estreme dei partiti di sinistra, per ciò che riguarda la morte di Stolypin pesanti sospetti si abbattano sugli organi di sorveglianza e sulla corte zarista, rea di aver abbandonato il ministro al proprio destino. Se da un punto di vista processuale è chiaro chi sia stato l'autore materiale del reato, ovvero l'ebreo Bogrov, lunga appare la lista dei possibili mandanti del delitto. I socialisti rivoluzionari, tirati in ballo dallo stesso attentatore, furono i principali indiziati per la strategia del terrore che avevano enunciato di fatto, portando a segno colpi spettacolari ripetuti allo Stato. Secondo Hélène Carrère D'Encausse, dopo il 1905-1906, "allorché il potere piegò politicamente e accettò di intraprendere un processo costituzionale, il movimento si assopì e l'unico omicidio strepitoso rimase quello di Stolypin"¹⁴. Sarà proprio tale modalità strategica, tanto temuta da Alessandro II, a catturare le coscienze dei contadini-proletari nell'era stolypiniana. Così, all'idea della sacralità del potere pian piano si sostituì quella della inefficienza e della corruzione del potere autocratico.

Accanto a una folla di contadini, proletari, rivoluzionari, *pomeščiki*, *kulaki*, imprenditori-commercianti, cominciarono a prendere forma raggruppamenti politici che portarono in breve tempo alla costituzione dei primi partiti: cadetti, liberali, socialisti rivoluzionari, socialdemocratici (divisi dopo il Congresso del Partito Operaio Socialdemocratico russo del 1903 in bolscevichi e menscevichi), ognuno con un proprio programma politico, una propria idea di sviluppo sociale e una propria "ricetta" per le questioni più scottanti, tra cui quella agraria. Il pluripartitismo, come fenomeno nuovo nel panorama nazionale, si era rivelato palesamente dopo la rivoluzione del 1905 con il Manifesto d'ottobre. Da allora, fino alle elezioni delle prime Dume, la lotta rivoluzionaria assunse una posizione più pragmatica rispetto al passato cercando di trovare una valvola di sfogo nei primi circoli politici di sinistra. Spaventata dalle bande dei "Cento Neri" e dalla mano forte della restaurazione autocratica, essa fermentò nelle

¹³ Il numero dei morti in quell'attentato varia, a seconda delle testimonianze, tra le trenta e le cinquanta unità. In quell'occasione una delle figlie di Stolypin rimase gravemente ferita e disabile per tutta la vita. Riporta James Billington che dopo quell'attentato i "massimalisti" autori dello stesso ribadirono che "la vera causa del cordoglio pubblico era che lo stesso Stolypin... fosse ancora vivo". Si veda James H. Billington, *Con il fuoco nella mente. Le origini della fede rivoluzionaria*, Bologna, il Mulino, 1986, p. 713.

¹⁴ Hélène Carrère D'Encausse, *op. cit.*, p. 323.

cantine, nei locali clandestini della capitale nordica per sfuggire al regime poliziesco inaugurato dalla nuova stagione reazionaria di Stolypin. Nonostante la profonda crisi in cui si ritrovarono catapultati i rivoluzionari, alcune idee sulle metodologie di lotta vennero fatte conoscere ai circoli più progressisti e “se gli attentati conobbero un declino dopo il 1906, ciò non fu a causa di un legame tra l’evoluzione politica e la strategia terrorista ma per il fatto che il movimento socialista-rivoluzionario e soprattutto i suoi agenti più attivi, attraversarono una profonda crisi”¹⁵.

I gruppi di sinistra più oltranzisti, in effetti, percepirono l’involuzione reazionaria inaugurata dallo zar che, passata la bufera rivoluzionaria, si era affrettato a ritrattare l’apertura alle istanze costituzionali. Per alcuni storici, soprattutto per quelli di area marxista, piuttosto che un atto “illuminato” il Manifesto d’ottobre nascondeva la solita dietrologia monarchica. Afferma Lev Trockij, a tal proposito, che lo zarismo “cedette tutte le volte che vi fu costretto dalle sue esigenze di conservazione. Dopo la disastrosa guerra di Crimea, Alessandro II procedette a una semiemancipazione dei contadini e ad un certo numero di riforme liberali sul piano degli *zemstva*, dei tribunali, della stampa, dell’istruzione ecc. Sotto la spinta della prima rivoluzione, Nicola II concesse una mezza costituzione. Ma tutte queste riforme avevano un senso per la monarchia solo nella misura in cui concessioni parziali salvavano l’essenziale, le basi di una società di casta e della monarchia stessa. Quando le conseguenze delle riforme cominciarono a straripare oltre i limiti, la monarchia inevitabilmente ripiegava”¹⁶. Alessandro II nella seconda metà del suo regno aveva così soppresso, secondo Trockij, le riforme concesse nella prima metà. Alessandro III, spaventato dalla morte del suo predecessore per mano terroristica, aveva spinto l’acceleratore sulle controriforme. Nicola II, costretto a piegarsi di fronte alla rivoluzione del 1905, in un secondo momento fu sostenitore dello scioglimento delle Dume che egli stesso aveva ammesso col Manifesto d’ottobre e, non appena la rivoluzione si indebolì, riprese con autorità e fermezza le redini del Paese¹⁷.

Dopo il 1907, che vide la condanna a morte di tre dei 28 terroristi, giudicati davanti alla corte marziale di San Pietroburgo e accusati di tentato omicidio contro il sovrano e il granduca, il movimento rivoluzionario parve subire una brusca battuta d’arresto. Troppo tardi ci si accorse invece che, sornione, esso si stava organizzando per colpire un bersaglio di alto profilo governativo, il ministro Stolypin. Egli era l’uomo “designato da abbattere, ciò in ragione del fatto che il suo desiderio di trasformazione del mondo rurale tagliava l’erba sotto i piedi di tutto il movimento socialista-rivoluzionario”¹⁸. La sua dura politica interna, e

¹⁵ *Ibidem*, p. 325.

¹⁶ Lev Trotsky, *Storia della rivoluzione russa*, Milano, Sugar, 1964, pp. 117-118.

¹⁷ *Ibidem*.

¹⁸ Hélène Carrère D’Encausse, *op. cit.*, pp. 328-329.

l'utilizzo di corti marziali istituite in diverse regioni dell'Impero, rese ancora più risoluti gli ultimi gruppi di rivoluzionari alle prese con la riorganizzazione interna dopo le numerose sentenze di condanna a morte e di esilio forzato dei suoi affiliati. A onor del vero, bisogna anche dire che se da una parte Stolypin veniva accusato di recepire e dar seguito con durezza ai desideri dello zar mettendo a tacere le masse rivoluzionarie, secondo i circoli più liberali, egli aveva il merito di aver spezzato gli ultimi vincoli feudali che legavano la Russia del tempo a quella arcaica. Aveva chiesto venti anni perché la sua riforma portasse frutti, i terroristi gliene concessero molti di meno.

I rivoluzionari, con cui Bogrov diceva di essere stato in contatto, smentirono tramite uno degli esponenti di spicco del partito socialista-rivoluzionario, Egor Egorovič Lazarev (1855-1937), la loro responsabilità nell'omicidio. Dalla sua residenza in Svizzera quest'ultimo inviò al dottor I. I. Dobrovolskij una lettera, datata 22 settembre 1911, nella quale smentì categoricamente l'implicazione dei rivoluzionari nell'omicidio del primo ministro e accusò il capo della polizia Nikolaj Nikolaevič Kuljabko (1873-1920)¹⁹ di aver strumentalizzato l'attentatore di Stolypin per rivoltare l'opinione pubblica contro il suo partito. Nella stessa lettera, oltre ad affermare che Bogrov non era affatto conosciuto nei circoli rivoluzionari parigini da dove si diceva che provenisse, Lazarev affermò che l'eliminazione rapida e a porte chiuse dell'ebreo lasciava molti quesiti aperti e non sollevava Kuljabko dalle tante responsabilità che egli aveva avuto quel giorno a Kiev²⁰. Nelle memorie pubblicate da Lazarev nel 1926 su "Volija Rossii", così raccontò il suo incontro con Bogrov nel luglio del 1910: "Egli dichiarò che aveva deciso di uccidere Stolypin e che, per dare al suo atto un valore politico più grande, desiderava ottenere il consenso e l'approvazione stessa del partito socialista-rivoluzionario"²¹. Lazarev, al contrario, "si sforzò di persuadere il giovane a rinunciare al suo progetto, ma quello lo supplicò di prenderlo sul serio, di raccogliere su di lui tutte le informazioni necessarie e dargli una risposta una settimana dopo". Dopo qualche tempo Lazarev avrebbe incontrato nuovamente Bogrov il quale avrebbe confidato ai rappresentanti dei socialisti-rivoluzionari: "fino alla morte stessa, io non coinvolgerò il partito". Il leader dei socialisti-rivoluzionari non fece mai capire chiaramente a Bogrov che il partito non avrebbe potuto accettare la sua proposta; infatti "se il partito riteneva che la soppressione di un uomo come Stolypin fosse indispensabile, avrebbe dovuto incaricarsene esso stesso e non appoggiarsi agli anarchisti e a gente di cui esso non avrebbe potuto controllare la condotta. Lazarev

¹⁹ Kuljabko fu un ufficiale di polizia. Nel 1897 era ispettore a Mosca. Dal 1907 al 1911 fu Capo del Dipartimento di Polizia di Kiev e dopo l'assassinio di Stolypin fu rimosso dal suo incarico. È stato poi condannato al carcere con l'accusa di appropriazione indebita di denaro pubblico.

²⁰ La lettera si trova presso l'Archivio di Stato russo (G.A.R.F.), Fondo DP, op. 265, d. 497. L. 21-24, alla voce di repertorio "Perljustracija".

²¹ Nikolaj Savickij, *L'assassinat de Stolypin*, in "Le Monde slave", IV (1927), p. 318.

rifiutò dunque categoricamente di essere l'intermediario tra Bogrov e il partito"²².

Stando alle memorie di Lazarev, una terza volta Bogrov si recò da lui con la stessa proposta ricevendo definitivamente una risposta negativa, dopo di che egli non lo rivide mai più e si trovava all'estero quando apprese della morte di Stolypin. Tale versione escluderebbe dunque l'implicazione del partito socialista-rivoluzionario nell'omicidio. Bogrov, in una deposizione del 10 settembre, alla vigilia della sua esecuzione, raccontò che "su ordine degli anarchici di Kiev, davanti ai quali voleva riabilitarsi, egli aveva a due riprese tentato di assassinare Kuljabko [capo della polizia e suo diretto superiore]. Fino all'ultimo minuto, insomma, egli avrebbe esitato e solo quando si trovò nel teatro egli avrebbe definitivamente deciso di uccidere Stolypin". Nell'interrogatorio del Capo del Dipartimento di polizia di Kiev, avvenuto il 2 settembre, subito dopo l'attentato, Kuljabko affermò che Bogrov era un informatore sicuro e attendibile al servizio dell'*Ochrana* dal 1906, anno in cui egli lo aveva conosciuto. Da allora in poi, grazie alle informazioni ricevute, si era riusciti ad arrestare molti terroristi e a sequestrare diverse officine clandestine dove si preparavano bombe e si mettevano a punto piani criminali. Lo stesso agente di polizia parlò del suo incontro a Kiev nei giorni precedenti con Bogrov, il quale aveva messo in allerta l'*Ochrana* per l'arrivo colà di tale Nikolaj Jakovlevič, un attivista rivoluzionario, che voleva informazioni dettagliate su Stolypin e sul ministro dell'Istruzione Lev Aristidovič Kasso (1865-1914)²³. Dunque la polizia conosceva bene Bogrov e la deposizione fatta da quest'ultimo contro Lazarev "gli fu ispirata dall'*Ochrana*, che cercava innanzitutto di diminuire la responsabilità di Kuljabko nel dramma di Kiev"²⁴. Veniva così chiamata in causa la polizia segreta zarista, la quale avrebbe costretto l'autore dell'omicidio a confessare il falso, cioè l'intenzione di voler colpire il tenente colonnello Kuljabko, dirigente del servizio speciale di pubblica sicurezza in Kiev, e non Stolypin. Bisogna entrare nella psicologia di un personaggio così particolare, quale fu il rivoluzionario russo degli inizi del secolo, per comprendere meglio l'atmosfera in cui venne concepito l'assassinio di Stolypin. Infatti, la rete di spionaggio messa in campo dalla polizia zarista, con la conseguente comparsa di personaggi ambigui e doppiogiochisti, rese ancor più arduo il lavoro degli inquirenti alle prese con identità contraffatte, giochi di ruolo assai complessi e false attestazioni. Nonostante tale premessa, i capi di

²² *Ibidem*.

²³ Al primo interrogatorio di Kuljabko ne seguirono altri nei giorni e nei mesi successivi. In seguito al tragico evento egli fu destituito dal suo incarico. Il documento in questione si trova presso il G.A.R.F., Fondo 271, Op. 1, d. 1, l. 27-29 in copia autenticata.

²⁴ *Ibidem*, p.318. Già condannato a morte, Bogrov, il quale non avrebbe avuto più niente da perdere, avrebbe dichiarato che era Kuljabko e non Stolypin che egli aveva avuto realmente l'intenzione di uccidere. Se questa deposizione risultasse vera, verrebbero a cadere una ad una le affermazioni di Lazarev e le prime rilasciate da Bogrov.

imputazione attribuibili al partito socialrivoluzionario russo, di cui Bogrov si considerava affiliato, furono molto deboli. La morte di Stolypin, anche se fortemente auspicata dai gruppi rivoluzionari, difficilmente può essere loro attribuita. A questo punto, le indagini portano a riconsiderare il ruolo dell'ex governatore di Saratov alla corte di Nicola II e qualche aspetto delle relazioni intrigate di corte, senza dubbio, potrà rivelarsi interessante per la verità sull'accaduto.

La figura di Nicola II, così come la storia ce la propone, è quella di uno zar debole e assai diffidente nei confronti dei suoi ministri: “quando li ereditava da suo padre, come Pobedonoscev, riteneva che ben presto il tempo sarebbe finito e quando si rendeva conto che erano indispensabili, il suo amor proprio ne risultava irritato”²⁵. Un aneddoto riportato da Ferro narra che “un giorno, prima di scegliere un ministro, Nicola II consultò il vecchio Pobedonoscev, il quale gli disse: Plevè è una canaglia, Sipjagin un imbecille. La sua scelta cadde sull'imbecille”²⁶. Lo zar da questo punto di vista non brillò nelle sue scelte, ma ebbe la fortuna di lavorare con uomini di grande spessore culturale e con ministri che avevano l'ambizione di costruire un nuovo modello di Stato monarchico. Molti di loro avevano studiato in Europa, parlavano correntemente il francese e il tedesco e avevano una visione dinamica della Storia. Stolypin può senz'altro essere annoverato nella generazione che traghettò la Russia “analfabeta” e “povera” verso quella che “sapeva leggere” e cominciava a dotarsi di più efficienti strumenti scientifici. Ma non sempre a corte tali qualità potevano riscontrare ammirazione e stima. Il più delle volte i Romanov si dimostrarono insofferenti verso coloro che dimostravano di possedere qualità pratiche e teoriche ben superiori alle loro ma, soprattutto, cercarono di circondarsi di uomini malleabili e privi di ambizione personale e da questo punto di vista alcuni atteggiamenti verso il primo ministro meritano un'analisi più attenta. Il peso del primo ministro dal 1906 era andato sempre più scemando e tale sensazione la ebbe Stolypin stesso che, incontrando Vladimir Nikolaevič Kokovcov (1853-1943) a Kiev, in occasione dell'inaugurazione del monumento ad Alessandro II nell'agosto 1911, confessò: “Da ieri ho l'impressione di essere di troppo”. Gli esponenti di corte lo avevano quasi ignorato: “non c'era posto per lui in nessuna carrozza del corteo, né sul battello imperiale nella gita a Černigov per venerare la reliquie di un monaco, di recente santificato”²⁷.

La sera del primo settembre 1911, cosciente di avere la corte contro, per molti motivi disse a Kokovcov di “avere i nervi a pezzi” per il disagio che provava in quell'ambiente ostile. Di questa ostilità Stolypin stesso ne percepì la portata già nel maggio dello stesso anno quando, a

²⁵ Marc Ferro, *Nicola II. L'ultimo zar*, Bari, Laterza, 1990, p. 72.

²⁶ *Ibidem*, p. 73.

²⁷ Laura Satta Boschian, *La tragedia dello statista Stolypin, vecchia Russia alla deriva*, in “*Studium*”, LXXXII (1986), p. 29.

seguito di un ennesimo scontro col Consiglio di Stato²⁸, vistosi senza appoggi, presentò le dimissioni che non furono accettate, sentendosi lui, il grande “statista” dell’epoca, un uomo sconfitto²⁹. Sconfitta più che altro morale, dato che il sistema da lui avviato in campo economico stava portando notevoli contributi al miglioramento dell’economia nazionale; in politica aveva smorzato le forze d’opposizione e riconsegnato allo zar un “*primatus*”, la cui precarietà era stata palese all’indomani della domenica di sangue del 1905.

Il rapporto di Nicola II con Stolypin, tutto sommato, si rivelò diverso da quello che lo zar aveva avuto con i precedenti ministri. Infatti, dopo che la sua scelta ricadde sull’ex governatore di Saratov, lo zar scrisse alla madre: “Non so dirti fino a che punto io abbia finito con lo stimare e rispettare quest’uomo”³⁰.

Poiché il primo ministro dava dimostrazione di lealtà estrema al conservatorismo assolutista, c’erano tutte le premesse per stringere, almeno con lui, un sodalizio di grande importanza. Invece, e la storiografia degli ultimi cinquant’anni ne prende atto, Nicola II non si dimostrò tanto disponibile: “è stato a volte paragonato al suo trisavolo semipazzo, Paolo I, strangolato da una camarilla con il consenso del figlio, Alessandro I, il *benedetto*”³¹. Trockij dice che “un ministro incantato dall’accoglienza che aveva avuto a Corte trovava, rientrando a casa, una lettera di destituzione. Era per lo zar un modo di vendicarsi della propria nullità”³². Tra l’altro Nicola II ci viene descritto da altri storici come un “fatalista”³³. Aveva un’attrazione particolare per il misticismo. A un certo punto del mandato governativo, nei rapporti tra lo zar e Stolypin subentrano questioni personali allorché Rasputin³⁴, monaco, pseudoguaritore e taumaturgo, gradito alla zarina, fu ostacolato e infine allontanato dal primo ministro

²⁸ Creato nel 1906, quest’organo era come una specie di Camera alta, composto in massima parte da conservatori con gli stessi poteri della Duma. La sua presenza doveva controbilanciare l’azione di un’eventuale Duma rivoluzionaria e quindi un contrappeso indispensabile alla monarchia in tempi così turbolenti quali furono gli anni delle prime dume.

²⁹ I ministri non avevano il diritto di dare le dimissioni, poiché in questo modo avrebbero dimostrato di avere un’opinione personale e di usare il libero arbitrio in contraddizione con il servizio dovuto allo zar. Cfr. Marc Ferro, *op. cit.*, p. 75. Ciò conferma che lo zar non respingeva le dimissioni poiché credeva nella efficienza dei suoi ministri, ma per una questione di orgoglio personale.

³⁰ Alan Moorehead, *op. cit.*, p. 96.

³¹ Lev Trotsky, *op. cit.*, p. 73. Effettivamente questi due Romanov si assomigliavano per la diffidenza verso tutti derivante dalla diffidenza verso se stessi, e da un atteggiamento da onnipotenti nullità.

³² *Ibidem*, p. 74.

³³ Hélène Carrère D’Encausse, *op. cit.*, p. 74.

³⁴ Gregorio Efimovič Rasputin, lacero contadino di statura media dalla lunga barba arruffata e dagli sporchi capelli che gli cadevano sulle spalle, arrivato a Pietroburgo fu ospitato dai monaci ai quali si rivolse chiedendo un tetto. Giunse in città nel 1903 con la fama di preveggenete. Conobbe la granduchessa Anna Vyubova, che ben presto lo introdusse a corte.

Stolypin, che lo riteneva un truffatore pericoloso per la stessa corte. “Non furono né Lenin, né Trotcky, né alcuno degli altri rivoluzionari ad ostacolare Stolypin, in questo periodo colmo di speranze; nel 1909, la più grande, o almeno la più insidiosa opposizione, gli venne dal lato più inatteso, dalla stessa imperatrice Alice... La causa diretta dell'odio dell'imperatrice contro Stolypin, era Rasputin”³⁵. La zarina, a cui stava a cuore la sorte del piccolo figlio emofiliaco, unico discendente maschio, riservava parole di riguardo quando si trattava delle capacità taumaturgiche di Rasputin e non comprendeva l'ostilità del primo ministro nei suoi confronti. Un giorno lei stessa scrisse allo zar: “accusano Rasputin di baciare le donne e così via. Leggi gli apostoli: baciavano tutti come una forma di saluto”³⁶. Così Rasputin venne allontanato dalla corte; né la zarina, né lo zar osarono opporsi alle decisioni di Stolypin. L'ex governatore di Saratov aveva tollerato, poiché non direttamente collegata agli eventi politici, l'influenza di Rasputin negli affari privati della famiglia zarista, ma, quando il monaco “cominciò ad esprimere le proprie idee anche in campo politico, idee che venivano accettate dall'imperatrice come un'ispirazione divina - tanto più che Rasputin badava bene a sostenere il principio dell'autocrazia - Stolypin scorse in questo falso taumaturgo un grave pericolo”³⁷.

All'inizio del 1911, il nome di Rasputin era diventato motivo di aperto scandalo a Pietroburgo e Stolypin gli ordinò di lasciare la città. “Erano ancora i primi tempi dell'ascesa di Rasputin al potere e l'imperatrice, pur odiando Stolypin a causa di tale gesto (tanto che non glielo perdonò mai) non si sentì forte abbastanza per far revocare il bando. Lo *starec* tornò al suo natio villaggio in Siberia”³⁸.

Stolypin fu assassinato, ma se così non fosse stato e la sua opposizione nei confronti di Rasputin fosse continuata, avrebbe certamente seguito la sorte del suo successore Kokovcov che, reo di aver consentito l'inchiesta ufficiale sul monaco-guaritore, nel febbraio del 1914, “seguì il destino di tutti i primi ministri di Nicola ch'erano stati così fortunati da sfuggire agli attentati: cordialmente, affettuosamente e bruscamente venne congedato”³⁹.

³⁵ Alan Moorehead, *op. cit.*, pp. 97-99. Dopo la nascita del figlio emofiliaco, nel 1904, l'imperatrice si dimostrò sempre più fredda verso gli altri e distaccata dalla vita pubblica. Cominciò a stringere un buon rapporto con Rasputin allorché si scoprì che questo presupposto santone possedeva strani poteri sul bambino; bastava che lo guardasse negli occhi mormorando parole tranquillizzanti o anche soltanto che gli parlasse al telefono e tutto andava bene, i dolori cessavano e il piccolo si addormentava. Si vedano a riguardo le pagine 101-102.

³⁶ *Ibidem*, p. 100.

³⁷ *Ibidem*.

³⁸ *Ibidem*, pp. 102-104.

³⁹ *Ibidem*, p. 107. Nell'ottobre del 1912 vi fu un incidente che convinse più che mai l'imperatrice a far tornare Rasputin a corte: lo zarevič scivolò salendo sulla barca, e subito incominciò un'acuta emorragia interna. Il ragazzo soffriva molto e Anna Vyubova, la quale era rimasta in contatto con Rasputin anche dopo il suo

Michail Vladimirovič Rodzjanko (1859-1924), presidente dell'ultima Duma, osò dire allo zar il 7 gennaio 1917, mentre la rivoluzione batteva alle porte: "Sire, attorno a voi non resta un solo uomo sicuro ed onesto; i migliori sono stati allontanati o se ne sono andati spontaneamente. Restano solo coloro che hanno una cattiva reputazione"⁴⁰.

Nonostante Nicola II in più di una circostanza si fosse mostrato favorevole alle iniziative riformatrici di Stolypin, poiché esse "avevano un senso per la monarchia solo nella misura in cui concessioni parziali salvavano l'essenziale, le basi di una società di casta e della monarchia stessa"⁴¹, egli stesso, nel momento in cui sentì alleggerirsi la pressione "dal basso", cominciò a stancarsi del suo ministro. La zarina aveva in odio Stolypin per via di Rasputin, le forze conservatrici di destra vedevano nel primo ministro un decentralizzatore e lo definivano "il mini-Bismarck russo"⁴², la corte mal vedeva le aperture di Stolypin ai moderati e così Nicola II rafforzò la sua decisione di sbarazzarsi un giorno o l'altro di Stolypin⁴³.

L'atteggiamento per altro ostile della corte nei confronti del primo ministro trova conferma nelle parole pronunciate dalla zarina, di origine tedesca⁴⁴, in un colloquio avuto con Kokovcov, dopo la morte di Stolypin: "Non dobbiamo compiangere troppo coloro i quali ci hanno lasciato... Se qualcuno se n'è andato vuol dire che ha esaurito la propria funzione... Stolypin è morto per cedere a voi il suo posto"⁴⁵. Il comportamento di Nicola II, l'indole subdola, il carattere debole e le sue convinzioni autocratiche, nonché l'atteggiamento assunto all'indomani della morte di Stolypin nei riguardi di quello che era stato il grande ministro riformatore, il "combattente di ferro" (*železnyj boec*), gettano ombra sull'intera corte e sugli uomini vicini allo zar nell'omicidio di Kiev. Il generale Pavel Grigor'evič Kurlov (1860-1923), a cui, per desiderio di Stolypin, era stata affidata la sicurezza della persona del primo ministro, fu accusato di

allontanamento da corte voluto da Stolypin, gli telegrafò la notizia in Siberia. La risposta di Rasputin fu: "la malattia non è pericolosa come sembra. Non permettete ai medici che lo spaventino"; secondo Moorehead fu "un brillante salto nel buio". Subito dopo l'arrivo del telegramma il ragazzo cominciò a ristabilirsi e una volta di più apparve chiaro all'imperatrice "che Rasputin era lo strumento di Dio". Ecco perché il rancore della zarina Alice ora si appuntò contro il nuovo primo ministro Kokovcov, che seguiva una linea stolypiniana, dato che era un collaboratore del defunto Stolypin.

⁴⁰ Lev Trotsky, *op. cit.*, p. 74.

⁴¹ *Ibidem*, p. 118.

⁴² Martin Malia, *Comprendre la Révolution russe*, Paris, Edition du Seuil, 1980, p. 85.

⁴³ *Ibidem*.

⁴⁴ Il primo ministro russo era favorevole a un riavvicinamento della Russia con la Francia e l'Inghilterra e nel 1908 si pronunciò energicamente contro l'annessione della Bosnia e dell'Erzegovina all'Impero asburgico.

⁴⁵ Marc Raeff, *La Russia degli zar*, Roma-Bari, Laterza, 1989, p. 144.

essere stato “responsabile di quella sciagura”⁴⁶. L'inchiesta ordinata da Nicola II venne poi sospesa per ordine dello zar stesso⁴⁷.

Il giorno del funerale, Nicola II partì con la famiglia per le vacanze a Jalta. La freddezza con cui venne trattato tutto *l'affaire* Stolypin a corte, la naturalezza con cui Kokovcov venne nominato nuovo primo ministro non passarono certo inosservate. Detto ciò, nessuno ha mai pensato di attribuire allo zar la responsabilità dell'uccisione del suo primo ministro, “ma - secondo Satta Boschian - l'indifferenza di quella corte, se non il compiacimento, sembrò fin troppo evidente”⁴⁸. Implicazioni e corresponsabilità monarchiche vanno di pari passo con l'importante funzione ricoperta dalla polizia segreta alle prese con il torbido meccanismo di spionaggio dei primi anni del Novecento. Il sistema di infiltrazione poliziesca tra i rivoluzionari e le correnti di sinistra, la cosiddetta “simbiosi degli estremi”⁴⁹, divenne più efficace della “Terza Sezione” della Cancelleria imperiale russa, nata come diretta conseguenza della sollevazione decabrista del 1825 e dipendente direttamente dalla burocrazia zarista. Molti dei più alti funzionari di polizia erano tedeschi, baltici disciplinaristi come Pleve, che divenne direttore del dipartimento di polizia nel 1881, viceministro degli Interni dal 1884 al 1892 e ministro degli Interni a capo della gendarmeria dal 1902 fino alla morte sopraggiunta due anni dopo.

La Russia meridionale, da dove fu importata a Pietroburgo la violenza terrorista negli anni Settanta, divenne il principale scenario della controviolenza governativa negli anni Ottanta. Kiev era chiamata *Skorpion* (lo Scorpione) nel sistema in codice dell'*Ochrana*. Il generale Vladimir S. Strel'nikov, che diede inizio ai rastrellamenti, agli arresti e ai *pogromy* a Kiev, fu assassinato nel marzo del 1882 da Stepan Nikolaevič Chalturin (1856-1882), il quale aveva in precedenza tentato di minare il Palazzo d'Inverno e divenne, con l'assassinio di Strel'nikov, l'ultimo martire di *Volontà del Popolo* a cogliere nel segno. Per contro, “la polizia sviluppò un nuovo tipo di professionalità sotto la guida del tenente colonnello Georgij Sudejkin dell'*Ochrana* pietroburchese”⁵⁰. La sua azione consisteva nel trasformare i prigionieri politici in doppi agenti, come avvenne con Sergej Petrovič Degaev (1857-1920), agente di polizia infiltrato in ciò che rimaneva di *Volontà del Popolo*. Come Dmitrij Bogrov, uccisore di Stolypin,

⁴⁶ Aleksej Tihonovič Vassiljev, *La polizia segreta degli zar: l'Ochrana*, Milano, Mondadori, 1930, p. 59. Sposano questa tesi altri storici come Miljukov, Radinkij, Satta Boschian.

⁴⁷ *Ibidem*.

⁴⁸ Laura Satta Boschian, *op. cit.*, p. 30.

⁴⁹ James H. Billington, *op. cit.*, p. 702. La più importante fra tutte le analogie possibili fra l'epoca del primo impero francese e quella dell'ultimo impero russo è l'interazione degli estremi. In Russia, ancor più che in Francia, i gruppi di estrema Sinistra e quelli di estrema Destra si influenzarono l'un l'altro profondamente; e la simbiosi degli estremi sarebbe divenuta una caratteristica fatale e duratura della tradizione rivoluzionaria russa.

⁵⁰ *Ibidem*.

così pure Degaev, quasi come un gesto di espiazione per i suoi tradimenti, assassinò Georgij Porfir'evič Sudejkin (1850-1883): si venne a creare così "il precedente per la futura confusione delle identità fra gli imperi clandestini rivali della Destra e della Sinistra all'interno del cosmo russo"⁵¹.

All'epoca in cui l'*Ochrana* acquisì un quartier generale proprio al numero 16 di Fontanka a Pietroburgo, nel 1898, la Russia poteva ormai disporre di un'organizzazione controrivoluzionaria di professione "con schedari molto dettagliati basati sui rapporti degli agenti e sulla scrupolosa censura postale che veniva diretta dal *Gabinetto nero*"⁵². La polizia raccolse più di centomila documenti nel 1900; tramite i resoconti delle spie esterne (*fileri*, dal francese *fileurs*) e quelli degli infiltrati (*sotrudniki*) venivano sistematicamente condotti rastrellamenti ed effettuati arresti di massa nei periodi di alta tensione sociale. James Billington riferisce che sotto molti aspetti la polizia controrivoluzionaria sembrava l'immagine speculare dei rivoluzionari. I poliziotti adottarono propri *klički* (pseudonimi), compresa la distinzione tra "anziani" e "giovani" usata dai rivoluzionari negli anni Novanta. Un'importanza particolare fu attribuita agli agenti tipografi in riconoscimento del ruolo centrale che le tipografie clandestine svolgevano come punto di collegamento fra i rivoluzionari. L'impiego di metodi "legali" per estorcere la confessione dell'accusato sarebbe ben presto risultata un'arma a doppio taglio per l'*Ochrana*. Risultava difficile infiltrarsi negli ambienti della Sinistra senza assorbirne gli ideali e le aspirazioni. Si venne a creare così, nel tardo periodo imperiale, un mondo in chiaroscuro di alleanze e identità dagli incerti confini. Sebbene in linea di principio contrapposti, l'*Ochrana* e i rivoluzionari praticarono una subcultura di intrigo, anonimato e cospirazione. Essi rappresentavano le forze dinamiche in una società statica ed era senz'altro più facile cambiare schieramento che abbandonare del tutto tale seducente mondo.

Le più importanti forme di simbiosi tra Destra e Sinistra furono quelle realizzate dai due più famosi funzionari dell'*Ochrana* infiltrati nel movimento rivoluzionario: Sergej Vasil'evič Zubatov (1864-1917) e il già citato Jevno Azev. Anche se non riuscirono nell'intento di distruggere entrambi i movimenti di Sinistra, "questi due celebri provocatori di Destra riuscirono per molti versi a legare i due estremi in un nuovo genere di interdipendenza"⁵³.

La campagna condotta da Zubatov per strappare i lavoratori all'*intelligencija* sovversiva fu estesa alla comunità ebraica di Minsk, Vilna e Odessa, dove furono creati partiti operai indipendenti ebrei, con più o meno successo, per contrastare il *Bund*⁵⁴ socialdemocratico. Ma il 9

⁵¹ *Ibidem*, p. 703.

⁵² *Ibidem*.

⁵³ *Ibidem*, pp. 704-707.

⁵⁴ Con tale termine si indica un movimento socialista ebraico fondato a Vilnius nel 1897 e raggruppante i lavoratori della Polonia, della Lituania e della Russia (tutte

gennaio 1905 fu proprio una folla guidata da un'organizzazione generata dal movimento di Zubatov, con a capo padre Gabon, a Pietroburgo, a finire nel tragico massacro passato alla storia come la famigerata "domenica di sangue".

Il ministro Pleve, che si era distinto, nei primi anni del regno di Nicola II, nella caccia agli assassini di Alessandro III, intensificò, a partire dal 1903, la politica antisemita già in atto nell'Impero quale diversivo di fronte alle difficoltà del Paese: i *pogromy* assumevano così la funzione di orientare e scaricare sugli ebrei il malcontento popolare. Il risentimento per i *pogromy* di Kišinëv e di Gomel' tra il 1904 e il 1905 avrebbero portato all'uccisione, nel luglio del 1905, del ministro dell'Interno. L'assassinio fu organizzato quale "atto di vendetta da un ebreo chiamato Azev, la cui storia è un'illustrazione della ramificazione dell'amministrazione poliziesca"⁵⁵.

Con Jevno Azev a capo della sezione combattente del partito socialrivoluzionario nel 1903 in sostituzione di Geršuni, l'*Ochrana* mise a segno un colpo importante. Non evitò l'uccisione di Pleve ma, in compenso, questo tipico rappresentante del nuovo modello di agente-spia aiutò l'*Ochrana* a compiere "i suoi due arresti di massa più cospicui dell'era rivoluzionaria: quello di quasi tutti i delegati al primo Congresso del partito Sr a Imatra nel gennaio del 1906 e quello della sezione combattente del partito nel marzo dello stesso anno a Pietroburgo"⁵⁶.

Ciò che avvenne con il "caso Azev" si ripeté sette anni più tardi con Bogrov, collaboratore dei servizi segreti zaristi. Questa pratica di infiltrazione poliziesca nelle file dei rivoluzionari traeva origine da una più "machiavellica" idea zarista, quella di istituire sindacati governativi noti alla fine del XIX secolo col nome di *Zubatov*, i quali misero in pratica il piano di aggregare il movimento dei lavoratori alla macchina della polizia. La situazione degli ebrei si era aggravata all'indomani delle drastiche misure prese dal sovrano alla fine degli anni Ottanta del XIX secolo. Infatti proprio in quegli anni venne vietato agli ebrei l'esercizio della professione

nazioni che facevano parte dell'impero zarista). Il Bund cercò l'alleanza con il movimento socialdemocratico russo per la realizzazione di una società democratica e socialista e per ottenere il riconoscimento giuridico degli ebrei come minoranza nazionale. Appoggerà le armate rosse durante la guerra civile negli anni 1918-1922.

⁵⁵ Evno Azev era un agente di polizia e quando i torbidi dei contadini del 1902 incoraggiarono la formazione di un partito socialrivoluzionario che doveva succedere ai populisti nella difesa dei diritti dei contadini, la polizia si assicurò la sua nomina come capo della nuova organizzazione socialista (1904). Per anni egli ondeggiò tra i rivoluzionari e i loro naturali nemici, tradendo e disilludendoli entrambi alternativamente e simultaneamente.

⁵⁶ James H. Billington, *op. cit.*, p. 712. Ma il terrorismo, anche se perse molti dei suoi affiliati, si era svincolato dal controllo degli Sr ancor prima della rivoluzione del 1905. "L'agente incendiario dell'anti-disciplina sistematica fu il dirompente anarchismo dei *bezmotivniki*, il gruppo dei «senza motivo» inserito nel movimento largamente ebraico di «Bandiera Nera» a Bjalistok e nel più piccolo gruppo chiamato degli «Intransigenti» a Odessa".

forense. Lionel Kochan così descrive la condizione degli ebrei russi di quel periodo: “Concentrati nelle province occidentali e meridionali dell’impero, nella così detta riserva, e conducendo un’esistenza miserabile come proletari industriali o inserendosi con difficoltà ai margini della vita economica (erano piccoli venditori, locandieri, cocchieri, sarti, usurai, ciabattini, ebanisti) gli ebrei costituivano un comodo bersaglio per lo zarismo agonizzante”⁵⁷. L’antisemitismo aveva da secoli in Russia un carattere endemico, ma gli ebrei vi avevano rappresentato una esigua presenza. Il problema si era rivelato in tutta la sua portata nel XVIII secolo, dopo la spartizione della Polonia, quando ben 600.000 persone entrarono a far parte dello Stato russo. Tuttavia il fenomeno antisemita esplose dopo l’assassinio di Alessandro II. Infatti “il governo si valse della *canaille* nella lotta di classe in un modo che tornerà a verificarsi soltanto col fascismo nel secolo XX. Una ragazza ebrea, Hessia Helfmann, era stata fra gli assassini dello zar”⁵⁸. Fu dato così il via alla caccia all’ebreo, alla lotta feroce e sfrenata contro il popolo semita. Di qui il pretesto per un’ondata di *pogromy* che si abbatté su più di cento località della Russia meridionale abitate da ebrei, seminando terrore, morte e violenza di ogni genere fra la primavera e l’estate del 1881. Le peggiori atrocità furono commesse a Kirov e a Kiev. Verso la fine di quell’anno e per i primi mesi di quello successivo il movimento antisemitico si estese a Varsavia e alla Podolia... seguirono le cosiddette *leggi di maggio*”⁵⁹. Nel decennio successivo le persecuzioni raggiunsero il loro culmine con l’espulsione, nel 1891 e nel 1892, “durante un rigido inverno e senza preavviso, di migliaia di artigiani ebrei da Mosca e da una larga striscia di terra sul confine occidentale e la loro risistemazione nei ghetti dell’interno”⁶⁰.

Tutto questo influì sugli avvenimenti successivi. Divenne una regola quella che “ogni volta che si verificava un attentato, veniva accusato un rivoluzionario ebreo; poi ci si faceva il segno della croce dicendo: *Non poteva essere un russo*”⁶¹. Così, per Alessandro III e per i suoi ministri, “gli ebrei divennero un comodo capro espiatorio... e l’antisemitismo, per la prima volta, uno strumento di governo”⁶². Addirittura negli strati popolari il pretesto per violenze e uccisioni era fornito dall’accusa, rivolta agli ebrei,

⁵⁷ Lionel Kochan, *Storia della Russia moderna dal 1500 a oggi*, Torino, Einaudi, 1971, p. 218.

⁵⁸ Si veda a tal riguardo Jonathan Frankel, *Gli ebrei russi, tra socialismo e nazionalismo (1862-1917)*, Torino, Einaudi, 1990, pp. 215-249; Hans Rogger, *La Russia pre-rivoluzionaria 1881-1917*, Bologna, Il Mulino, 1992, pp. 324-335.

⁵⁹ Con le “Leggi di maggio” infatti veniva interdetto agli ebrei di fermarsi nei distretti rurali, anche se essi si fossero trovati nella zona della Riserva. Vedi anche Hugh Seton-Watson, *Storia dell’impero russo (1801-1917)*, Torino, Einaudi, 1971, pp. 450-453.

⁶⁰ Ad esempio fu limitato il numero di studenti ebrei ammessi a frequentare le università, l’esclusione dall’esercizio della professione forense, dei medici ebrei dagli incarichi pubblici, la perdita dei diritti di suffragio per l’elezione degli *zemstva* e delle giunte comunali.

⁶¹ Marc Ferro, *op. cit.*, pp. 105-106.

⁶² *Ibidem*, p. 106.

di commettere omicidi rituali. Questi *pogromy* si nutrivano sempre di nuove accuse, soprattutto di ordine religioso; “il pope [ad esempio], insegnava ai bambini, sin dall’infanzia, che gli ebrei avevano ucciso Gesù e commesso il crimine infame”⁶³. Altre accuse contro di essi si riferivano alle loro attività, quella di agenti della nobiltà terriera, responsabili della gestione dei mulini, del sale, delle taverne, quella di usurai, responsabili della miseria dei contadini, della loro ubriachezza e delle loro agitazioni. Agli occhi del potere, gli ebrei diventavano fomentatori di disordini. La reazione ai *pogromy* con l’impassibilità e la non violenza degli ebrei, era dovuta al “timore che ciò stroncasse le prime manifestazioni di presa di coscienza politica dei contadini, i quali successivamente, a loro giudizio si sarebbero rivoltati contro i proprietari ed il regime”⁶⁴.

I Romanov temevano i complotti ebraici e così, per tenere a bada il malumore semita e nello stesso tempo renderlo pericoloso agli occhi di quegli elementi conservatori che volevano il mantenimento sociale dello *status quo*, nel 1903 venne redatto dalla polizia zarista “un falso, i *Protocolli dei Savi di Sion*, nel quale si poteva leggere che i fondatori del *Bund*, il Partito socialdemocratico ebraico, nel 1897, avevano ideato a Basilea un piano di rivoluzione mondiale, di cui questo testo costituiva il fondamento”⁶⁵.

Per quello che riguarda gli omicidi rituali, nei russi si andò consolidando l’idea che gli attentati ne costituivano la forma più moderna. Alla domanda posta allo zar da Pobedonoscev che gli chiedeva in che modo sperava che si sarebbe risolta la questione ebraica in Russia, questi rispose: “Un terzo degli ebrei emigrerà, un terzo si convertirà e un terzo morirà”⁶⁶.

Durante il regno di Nicola II tutto ciò che accadeva di nefasto era colpa degli ebrei, veniva loro addebitata perfino la difficoltà di ottenere prestiti dalla Francia. Persino Guglielmo II si era persuaso di quest’ultima motivazione a tal punto che spiegò allo zar che “il motivo per cui la Francia aveva rifiutato un prestito alla Russia aveva a che vedere, più che con gli affari marocchini, con le notizie inviate dagli ebrei russi, capi della rivoluzione, ai loro parenti in Francia, di cui tutta la stampa subiva l’esecrabile influenza (gennaio 1906)”⁶⁷.

Ad aggravare ancor più la già precaria situazione degli ebrei fu quel meccanismo di collaborazione tra la nascente *Unione del popolo* e le

⁶³ *Ibidem*.

⁶⁴ *Ibidem*. Si veda anche Heiko Haumann, *Storia degli ebrei dell’Est*, Milano, SugarCo, 1990, pp. 72-95.

⁶⁵ Marc Ferro, *op. cit.*, p. 107.

⁶⁶ *Ibidem*. L’antisemitismo serviva da fondamento a un’ideologia premoderna dato che per gli antisemiti gli ebrei erano l’avanguardia di un movimento capitalistico che avrebbe portato a una democratizzazione del Paese. Di conseguenza, mentre Vitte, che auspicava lo sviluppo economico (e per tal motivo si rese invisibile allo zar il quale temeva ogni forma di cambiamento), frena le misure antisemite, il ministro degli Interni, che rappresenta l’ordine costituito, le provoca.

⁶⁷ Marc Ferro, *op. cit.*, p. 105.

autorità che diedero vita a *pogromy* antiebraici e antiliberali. Proprio all'*Unione del popolo*⁶⁸ “si può attribuire l'*affaire* Bejlis: Bejlis infatti era quel rabbino accusato, a torto, dell'assassinio rituale di un bambino”⁶⁹.

Stolypin, il quale suo malgrado doveva accettare le disposizioni di Nicola II, nella sua politica filo-autocratica non privilegiò per nulla la linea antisemita esasperata dal Pleve, anche se a lui vengono attribuiti i *pogromy* del 1907. Il fatto che Nicola inviasse di propria mano all'*Unione del popolo russo* (organizzazione antisemita e repressiva sconfitta alle elezioni della prima Duma), il seguente telegramma: “Che l'Unione del popolo russo sia il mio sostegno e un esempio di fronte a tutti, e a ciascuno, di ciò che rappresentano l'ordine e la legalità (giugno 1907)”⁷⁰, chiarisce la posizione dello zar di fronte alla linea conservatrice, ma non antisemita, della politica del primo ministro. Agivano in Russia forze governative che sfuggivano al controllo di Stolypin; forze conservatrici e controrivoluzionarie alimentate dagli stessi esponenti di corte, che vedevano nella nuova fase della *perestrojka* russa una spada di Damocle sempre incombente.

Ciò non esclude la responsabilità di Stolypin nei *pogromy*, ma quanto meno ne limitano la colpa. I *pogromy* erano ormai in Russia una valvola di sfogo per lo zarismo e certo non fu Stolypin a inventarli. La sua uccisione per mano del giovane avvocato ebreo Dmitrij Bogrov conferma l'odio di una razza, quella ebraica, sottoposta a ogni tipo di discriminazione. Emarginati, relegati nel loro mondo di “diversi”, tacciati di deicidio, gli ebrei si ritrovarono in una situazione di incompatibilità con le esigenze dello Stato zarista. L'uccisione di Stolypin avvenne in questo clima di disperazione, ma i fatti storici fin qui enunciati non forniscono elementi di giudizio tali da poter ritenere valida l'ipotesi di una congiura ebraica contro il primo ministro. Lo stesso Bogrov, nelle sue deposizioni, cadde più volte in contraddizione e il suo atto, alla fine, sembra essere espressione di un gesto del tutto individuale, che si può giustificare con quel senso di autoimmolazione che egli stesso provava per aver fatto

⁶⁸ Gruppo reazionario e antisemita, di cui già detto, che assieme alle *Centurie Nere* riprendevano le idee di Durmont in Francia provocando per di più i *pogromy*. Addirittura nel febbraio del 1907 si parlò di un probabile attentato, ordito da questa organizzazione, ai danni del Vitte. La stampa dell'Unione del Popolo Russo, “aveva condotto una lotta senza sosta contro Vitte, designandolo come il principale responsabile di tutti i problemi che si erano abbattuti sulla Russia”. Cfr. Aleksandr Gerasimov, *op. cit.*, p. 242. Dalle minacce all'azione il passo fu breve. Gerasimov, autore del libro da cui sono tratte queste informazioni, dice che recatosi egli stesso la sera dell'attentato a casa dell'ex presidente del Consiglio dei ministri, Sergej Vitte, gli fu sufficiente gettare un colpo d'occhio sulla macchina infernale che vi era stata collocata per rendersi conto ch'essa “non era l'opera di rivoluzionari (...) poiché solo la sezione combattente dell'U.P.R. era capace di una esecuzione così maldestra (nel senso che i materiali usati per la fabbricazione dell'ordigno risultarono così antiquati)”. Per certi aspetti, questo comitato reazionario richiama alla mente quello istituito più di tre secoli prima quando Ivan IV il Terribile, nel 1565, diede vita all'*opričnina*.

⁶⁹ *Ibidem*, p. 109.

⁷⁰ *Ibidem*.

giustiziare alcuni suoi compagni rivoluzionari o anarchici durante il periodo in cui aveva collaborato con l'*Ochrana*. Non appena si venne a sapere che l'assassino di Stolypin si chiamava Dmitrij Bogrov, nell'"Istoričeskij Vestnik" ("Messaggero Storico") dell'ottobre 1911 si scrisse che "dato che l'assassino era ebreo, vi sarebbero stati dei *pogromy*"⁷¹.

L'uccisione di Stolypin, nella sua doppia natura di omicidio politico e di Stato, segna una tappa decisiva per la caduta dello zarismo. Subito dopo, Nicola II si ritrovò sempre più solo e in compagnia di Rasputin, passato alla storia come un uomo astuto, pronto al momento giusto ad accattivarsi il potere per avere il potere. Lo storico e pubblicitista Pavel Miljukov nei suoi *Vspominanija (Ricordi)*, disse che Stolypin "votato a salvare la Russia dalla rivoluzione terminò con il ruolo di un Thomas Becket russo"⁷², anche se in questo giudizio la tendenziosità di partito pare avere il sopravvento sull'obiettività storica.

Stolypin, al contrario di quello che sosteneva Lenin, era solo nella sua battaglia. "Se la borghesia gli fosse stata vicina come Lenin trovava opportuno far credere, Stolypin avrebbe potuto agire con più sicurezza"⁷³. I cadetti, cioè gli aderenti al partito costituzionale democratico, negli anni che precedettero la morte di Stolypin, volevano che la Russia si liberasse dalle misure prese "dall'alto", imparasse a partecipare alla vita politica. Stolypin non poteva quindi rappresentarli. Il primo ministro era attaccato anche dai socialisti polacchi, i quali, subito prima della rivoluzione russa del 1905, "si mossero rabbiosamente contro l'*Ochrana*, uccidendo senza pietà tutti i collaboratori segreti di cui riuscivano a sapere il nome"⁷⁴. Anche i conservatori erano ostili a Stolypin. Dapprima lo avevano appoggiato nella lotta contro i rivoluzionari, ma, quietato il paese, "non vedevano ragione per mantenere in piedi il pericolo sempre latente della Duma e delle previe elezioni. Né comprendevano la fretta, la febbre della Riforma Agraria"⁷⁵. Inoltre i conservatori, come gli slavofili, erano legati all'*Obščina* e difficilmente avrebbero ceduto allo smantellamento di questa atavica tradizione russa. Fra gli errori che Martin Malia attribuisce alla politica stolypiniana c'è anche quello relativo al fatto che "Stolypin non aveva fatto nulla per la classe operaia allorché invece una politica conservatrice ragionevole, come mostrò l'esempio prussiano, aveva

⁷¹ *Ibidem*, p. 140.

⁷² Pavel Nikolaevič Miljukov, *Vspominanija 1859-1917. Ubijstvo Stolypina, svidetel'stva i dokumenty*, Riga, Kooperativ "Kursiv", 1990, p. 293. Nella nota riportata a fondo pagina dell'estratto di Miljukov si chiarisce questo parallelo tendenzioso tra Stolypin e Becket. In sostanza Thomas Becket, nel 1155 cancelliere del regno inglese, dal 1162 arcivescovo di Canterbury, nel 1173 canonizzato dalla Chiesa cattolica, difendeva l'indipendenza della Chiesa dal potere regio. Fu assassinato sui gradini dell'altare per ordine del suo protettore. L'articolo proposto in questi documenti mostra come, facendo intendere che nell'omicidio di Stolypin fosse coinvolto il suo protettore, cioè lo zar, abbia prevalso nel giudizio dello storico la tendenziosità e non l'obiettività.

⁷³ Laura Satta Boschian, *op. cit.*, p. 24.

⁷⁴ Aleksej Tihonovič Vassiljev, *op. cit.*, p. 59.

⁷⁵ Laura Satta Boschian, *op. cit.*, p. 25.

articolato a sua volta una repressione dei partiti politici rivoluzionari e una politica sociale in favore degli operai⁷⁶. In questo modo Stolypin si alienò le simpatie degli intellettuali e degli operai i quali, secondo Georgij Valentinovič Plechanov (1856-1918), erano i rappresentanti di una tradizione rivoluzionaria, frutto del processo di europeizzazione della Russia. Cosicché le riforme, a vantaggio dell'elemento tradizionalmente conservatore della realtà russa cioè quello rurale, avrebbero inevitabilmente rallentato quel processo di trasformazione in senso moderno.

Inspiegabile, o piuttosto oscura, è la storia dell'autore materiale dell'attentato, l'ebreo Bogrov, entrato a teatro armato senza destare sospetto alcuno. Si disse che un agente governativo avesse compiuto l'attentato o che elementi di destra, lo stesso capo della polizia fra questi, lo avessero organizzato. La difesa dell'attentatore come uomo di assoluta fiducia avvalorò i sospetti. Si disse anche che lo Stato Maggiore russo fosse contrario a Stolypin, perché lo sapeva contrario a ogni guerra e per questo volesse liberarsene.

Sin dalle prime deposizioni di Bogrov, si era compresa la complessità della sua personalità. "Non c'è alcun interesse verso la vita. Niente eccetto un vassoio pieno di polpette"⁷⁷, aveva detto Bogrov in una sua lettera del primo dicembre 1910. Lo storico sovietico Avrech giustifica questo atteggiamento nichilista affermando che "simili stati d'animo, in quel periodo, impazzavano in una parte della gioventù intellettuale e dipendeva dal temperamento, dalla visione del mondo, dalle circostanze: ognuno di questi ragazzi si prefiggeva di compiere uno stravagante atto eroico; qualcuno finì col suicidarsi, qualcun'altro al contrario uccise l'amante ed ecco che Bogrov pensò di «risolvere la questione» uccidendo Stolypin... per lui, quelli che egli ricordava nelle sue deposizioni era *gente di mezza tacca* e la sua morte nella gloria per lui sarebbe stata più importante della sofferenza degli altri"⁷⁸.

Non tutti gli storici sono comunque concordi con questa interpretazione. Vladislav Krasnov, autore dell'articolo *Voskresenie Stolypina* (la resurrezione di Stolypin), sostiene che "Bogrov non smise di essere un rivoluzionario e fino alla fine perseguì il suo importante scopo: vendicare la mortificazione e i *pogromy*, che i suoi connazionali avevano subito in Russia"⁷⁹. Ragion di Stato e risentimento razziale avrebbero alimentato quindi l'azione fanatica di Bogrov. Stolypin, nazionalista convinto, interprete fedele delle aspirazioni dei gruppi nazionalisti russi eredi della scuola slavofila ottocentesca, monarchico spietato e autoritario pronto a intervenire a favore delle minoranze russe nei territori occidentali,

⁷⁶ *Ibidem*, p. 84.

⁷⁷ Aron Avrech, *P.A. Stolypin i sud'by reform v Rossii*, Moskva, Izd.vo Političeskoj Literatury, 1991, p. 218.

⁷⁸ *Ibidem*.

⁷⁹ Vladislav Krasnov, *Voskrešenie Stolypina*, in "Grani. Žurnal literatury, iskusstva, nauki i obščestvennoj mysli", 1986, nr. XLI, p. 167.

nella mente di Bogrov “rappresenta gli interessi nazionali russi, la rappresentanza russa alla Duma, lo Stato russo. Egli edifica un paese non universalmente libero ma una monarchia nazionale... Lo sviluppo stolypiniano non promette prosperità agli ebrei ed ecco perché Stolypin deve essere rimosso”⁸⁰.

Nonostante i notevoli sforzi portati avanti da Stolypin con il progetto delle riforme agrarie, egli “non poteva pretendere di salvare la Russia in nome di uno zar davanti al quale si faceva il segno della croce [come avvenne nel teatro di Kiev subito dopo che fu colpito a morte da Bogrov] come davanti all’incarnazione di Dio”⁸¹. I tempi erano però cambiati e, mentre Stolypin intendeva seguire la via della modernizzazione, la Russia voleva rimanere sostanzialmente quella che era ovvero un Impero extraeuropeo. In circostanze diverse Stolypin sarebbe forse riuscito a portare a termine con successo i suoi progetti riformistici.

Riguardo alla morte di Stolypin resteranno molti dubbi e lati oscuri; il solo fattore di certezza resta Dmitrij Bogrov, l’autore materiale della cui identità qualcosa sappiamo. Nel momento in cui compì l’attentato era solo e solo resterà nel ricordo di quell’omicidio, abbia egli rappresentato un partito, una razza, uno Stato o semplicemente se stesso.

Il redattore del “Pravitel’stvennij vestnik” (“Il Messaggero governativo”), Bašmakov, scrisse subito dopo la morte di Stolypin: “È chiara la differenza tra le grandi personalità della storia e quelle più opinabili. Stolypin è un personaggio indiscutibilmente di prima grandezza insieme a figure come Pietro I, Lomonosov, Suvorov, Alessandro II e Mendeleev”⁸².

L’omicidio di Stolypin attirò su di sé l’attenzione di tutto il mondo russo e non solo. Nonostante la sua incrollabile fede nella monarchia, nello zar e nel suo *primatus potestatis*, Stolypin diede prova di grande temperamento e forte autoritarismo, riuscendo a imporsi tra altri *leader* della storia moderna, quali il cardinale Richelieu o il cardinale Mazzarino, o ancor meglio il cancelliere tedesco Bismarck, a cui fu avvicinato per il suo ruolo di *iudex in partibus*.

In fondo Stolypin sapeva che prima o poi sarebbe stato ucciso: infatti egli diceva: “Ogni mattina prego e considero il giorno che viene come l’ultimo..., talvolta, ho la sensazione netta, che verrà il giorno in cui il disegno dell’omicida si realizzerà”⁸³.

Conformemente ai suoi presentimenti, egli morirà dopo cinque giorni di crudeli sofferenze: la sua volontà, di essere seppellito proprio nel luogo in cui sarebbe morto, fu rispettata. Presso la chiesa del più vecchio monastero della Russia di Kiev-Pečerskij a Kiev, fondato nel secolo XI, il 6 settembre fu sotterrato “l’uomo forte” di Nicola II. Subito dopo la morte del primo ministro, i delegati degli *zemstva* e i membri della Duma, riuniti a

⁸⁰ *Ibidem*, p. 168.

⁸¹ Laura Satta Boschian, *op. cit.*, pp. 30-32.

⁸² Aron Aavrech, *op. cit.*, p. 237.

⁸³ Vladislav Krasnov, *op. cit.*, p. 161.

Kiev, proposero un monumento al grande ministro. Nicola II rimase entusiasta dell'iniziativa e il monumento fu inaugurato un anno dopo l'assassinio. Sulla scultura fu scolpita la frase cardine del pensiero politico di Stolypin: "A voi occorrono forti scossoni, a noi una grande Russia".

Durante la tempesta rivoluzionaria, il "grande scossone" del 1917, il monumento fu abbattuto e per moltissimi anni la figura di Stolypin sarà tenuta nell'oblio. Solo alla fine degli anni Ottanta del nostro secolo, è ritornato l'interesse per la figura di Stolypin. Non è da escludere che il risorto interesse attorno a questo "assolutista illuminato"⁸⁴ dell'epoca zarista derivi da quello suscitato per un altro riformatore dello scorso secolo, Michail Sergeevič Gorbačëv.

⁸⁴ Hugh Seton-Watson, *op. cit.*, p. 575. In effetti questo epiteto venne attribuito a Stolypin da Aleksandr S. Izgoev, uno dei suoi critici più acuti.

L'ULTIMO CONFLITTO PRIMA DELLA GRANDE GUERRA: L'ITALIA DEL RISORGIMENTO CONTRO L'IMPERO OTTOMANO (1911-1912)^{***}

Antonello Biagini^{*}, Andrea Carteny^{**}

Abstract

In 1911 Italy was an important partner of Turkey for the Army officials' training of the Empire, but in the international "equilibrium" Rome wanted to catch the last possibility to extend the power of the "young Italian nation" to his "fourth side". So in Autumn 1911 the Italian military expedition in Tripolitania and Cyrenaica opened a new season of hope for Balkan nations to conquer national territory and freedom against Turks. Bulgarians, Greeks, Serbians and Montenegrins are mobilized to launch an new war against the Ottoman power with the help of the Italian attack in Africa and in the Aegean area. Italy of "Risorgimento" is for the Balkan young nations and their public opinions a good sample of national independence. But the Italian policy against Turks didn't want to be too stronger against the Ottoman Empire, mainly to damage the Turkish "status quo" in Balkans. In Summer 1912 began the negotiations for peace, in September at Ouchy the Turkish negotiators – face to the national mobilizations in Montenegro, Serbia, Bulgaria, Greece – accepted the Italian peace conditions, signed on 18th October, recognizing the autonomy of Tripolitania and Cyrenaica. But finally, in that same time, the 1st Balkan war exploded between Balkan countries and the Ottoman Empire, as the premise of a "Great" war of "young" nations against "old" empires.

Keywords: Italy, Risorgimento, Ottoman Empire, Military Expedition, National Struggle

1. Introduzione: i rapporti italo-turchi agli inizi del Novecento

È un contesto straordinario quello nel quale si inquadra, a livello interno e internazionale, la guerra italo-turca, detta comunemente "guerra di Libia". L'Italia infatti tentava allora di trovare una propria dimensione di Potenza nel consesso delle grandi nazioni europee, cercando proprio nel rilancio della propria vocazione mediterranea questo "posto al sole", anche per celebrare degnamente il primo mezzo secolo dall'unificazione della Penisola nel Regno d'Italia. Sono le fasi finali del "lungo Ottocento", di un secolo iniziato al Congresso di Vienna e che avrebbe proseguito nell'età "degli imperi" e sarebbe sopravvissuto a se stesso fino agli esiti della Grande Guerra: che vide dunque nel conflitto italo-turco l'*ouverture* dell'ultimo atto di questo periodo storico, scandito dalle guerre balcaniche e dal primo conflitto mondiale.

È pur vero che le premesse storico-internazionali sono date fondamentalmente dalle condizioni dell'Impero ottomano nel 1911, che presenta le proprie origini e caratteristiche nella "rivoluzione dei Giovani Turchi" del 1908. Sfruttando il malessere delle guarnigioni e le tensioni con le nazionalità non turco-musulmane, infatti, nell'estate 1908 un

^{***} Il paragrafo 2 è da attribuire ad Antonello Biagini; i paragrafi 3, 4 e 5 ad Andrea Carteny; i paragrafi introduttivo e conclusivo (1 e 6) sono da attribuirsi ad entrambi gli autori.

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gruppo di ufficiali - che avevano frequentato le scuole europee e che erano stati influenzati dalla cultura occidentale - aveva marciato su Istanbul e deposto il sultano tentando di dare una svolta “moderna e occidentale” al declino politico della “Turchia” imperiale. L’atteggiamento fortemente critico dell’Italia verso la politica assolutistica del sultano costituiva un elemento costante degli ambienti governativi di Roma e rifletteva gli articolati giudizi presenti nei rapporti italiani inviati dagli *attachés* diplomatici e dagli addetti militari in missione all’estero¹. La simpatia chiaramente mostrata verso il movimento giovane-turco, seppure determinata dalla massiccia presenza degli ufficiali che erano stati i principali sostenitori dell’attività e della struttura del movimento stesso, nasceva tuttavia anche dall’obiettiva visione della situazione politica interna dell’Impero ottomano così come allora si presentava. Certo, l’Italia continuava a essere per l’Impero ottomano un *partner* importante anche e soprattutto per i tentativi di riforma delle strutture portanti dello Stato: si realizza così, nel corso del primo decennio del Novecento, il coinvolgimento di ufficiali italiani nella riorganizzazione della gendarmeria turca in alcuni *vilayet* turchi e in particolar modo in Macedonia². Nei rapporti inviati a Roma vengono delineate luci e ombre dell’attività italiana, soprattutto per quanto riguardava le relazioni non sempre facili con le autorità ottomane. È pur vero che i Giovani Turchi accentuarono la loro politica nazionalistica accelerando oggettivamente la disgregazione di quell’Impero che volevano salvare: di fatto, ai dirigenti del movimento costituzionale mancò una visione obiettiva della situazione così come la volontà di realizzare un’effettiva convivenza tra etnie e nazionalità rilanciando un comune sentimento ottomano, che solo avrebbe potuto salvare l’Impero. Questa contraddizione fondamentale - propugnare un Impero liberale senza però intaccarne i presupposti monarchici e religiosi che ne facevano uno Stato teocratico - non permise ai Giovani Turchi di realizzare una vera rivoluzione: tuttavia questi ufficiali rappresentarono, con il loro movimento, l’ultimo generoso sussulto di vitalità interna dell’Impero.

La crisi della Sublime Porta coincise con l’inizio della guerra italo-turca per proseguire poi con le due guerre balcaniche e concludersi con il primo conflitto mondiale: la Turchia come Stato moderno sarebbe nata quindi solo grazie alle capacità e al carisma di un uomo della statura di Mustafà Kemal “Atatürk” che, pur avendo partecipato al movimento dei

¹ Cfr fondamentalmente Antonello Biagini, *L’Italia e le guerre balcaniche*, Roma, Ufficio Storico SME, 1990; Idem, *Momenti di storia balcanica (1878-1914): aspetti militari*, Roma, Ufficio Storico SME, 1981; Idem, *Note e relazioni di viaggio nei Balcani: (1879-1898)*, Roma, Ufficio Storico SME, 1979.

² Cfr Idem, “Italia e Turchia (1904-1911): gli ufficiali italiani e la riorganizzazione della gendarmeria in Macedonia”, in ***, *Memorie storiche militari. 1977*, Roma, Stato Maggiore Esercito - Ufficio Storico, 1977, in seguito pubblicato come “La riorganizzazione della gendarmeria turca in Macedonia (1904-1911)”, in Antonello Biagini, *Momenti di storia...*, pp. 123-144.

Giovani Turchi, comprendeva fin dall'inizio i limiti e le profonde ragioni che ne avrebbero causato il fallimento³.

2. I Balcani, anti-turchi e filo-italiani

Nell'aprile del 1911 il tenente colonnello Prospero Marro, nuovo addetto militare a Costantinopoli, scrivendo allo Stato Maggiore confermava che la Turchia avrebbe avuto tutto l'interesse a mantenere gli ufficiali stranieri nella riorganizzazione in atto, anche se questi trovavano la propria capacità d'azione limitata dal fatto di essere al servizio turco come ispettori o consiglieri⁴. Se da una parte dunque l'Italia e il suo esercito continuavano ad avere negli ambienti turchi ottima considerazione, dall'altro l'inizio della guerra italo-turca nell'autunno del 1911 aveva riaccessato mai sopite speranze per una forte azione antiturca nelle nazioni e nei popoli ancora sottoposti al potere del sultano. In particolare nella regione balcanica ci si preparò a sfruttare l'impegno militare turco sul fronte libico ed egeo per mobilitare gli ambienti nazionali (per lo più intellettuali, degli ambienti nobiliari e soprattutto dei ceti borghesi nazionali emergenti dei Balcani) e internazionali (le cancellerie dell'Europa occidentale e le corti imperiali dell'Europa centro-orientale) contro l'"Uomo malato" d'Europa, il "Turco". A conferma di ciò il tenente colonnello Merrone, addetto militare a Costantinopoli, nell'ottobre del 1911 informava lo Stato Maggiore che il re Nicola del Montenegro aveva dichiarato al console d'Italia a Cetinje, barone Squitti, che era giunto il momento per un'azione "concorde di tutti gli stati balcanici con l'aiuto dell'Italia"⁵.

È il caso della Bulgaria, dove la proclamazione dell'indipendenza, avvenuta il 5 ottobre 1908, all'indomani della rivoluzione dei Giovani Turchi e accettata dal governo ottomano (che sanciva d'altronde uno stato di fatto già esistente), non sopì le lotte che opponevano i bulgari alla Turchia. I Giovani Turchi non avevano in realtà risolto i gravi problemi delle province europee né tanto meno di quelle asiatiche, lasciando aperte questioni complesse come quella macedone. Da Sofia, in effetti, il tenente colonnello Enrico Merrone, addetto militare italiano, segnalava allo Stato Maggiore un'intensa attività giornalistica e pubblicistica nazionalista⁶, da cui emergeva la grande impressione prodotta in Bulgaria dalla guerra italo-turca⁷. In particolar modo, ma non esclusivamente, i partiti dell'opposizione indicavano quel frangente bellico come il contesto più favorevole per attaccare la Turchia poiché, in caso contrario, si sarebbe

³ In una vasta bibliografia cfr. in generale Antonello Biagini, *Storia della Turchia contemporanea*, Milano, Bompiani, 2007.

⁴ Cfr. Antonello Biagini, "La riorganizzazione della...", in Idem, *Momentidi storia...*, p. 143.

⁵ Cfr. Antonello Biagini, "Simeon Radev, le nazioni balcaniche e la guerra italo-turca", in Idem, *Momenti di storia...*, p. 196.

⁶ L'attenzione si concentra su alcuni personaggi particolarmente versatili e attivi del panorama pubblico bulgaro: è in particolar modo il caso di Simeon Radev, giornalista e attivista "stambulista", già con ruoli militari e diplomatici.

⁷ *Ibidem*, p. 191.

vanificata un'altra buona occasione, dopo quella (persa) del 1908. Nello stesso tempo si consolidava l'opinione che l'azione italiana a Tripoli fosse il preludio di un completo disinteressamento dell'Italia per le vicende balcaniche, con la conseguenza di facilitare un'ulteriore espansione austriaca nella penisola⁸. È pur vero che la Bulgaria, dall'entusiasmo iniziale per l'azione italiana contro l'Impero ottomano, sarebbe presto passata a un atteggiamento più cauto - anche in seguito alla delusione per il modo con cui l'Italia aveva condotto le operazioni militari - facendo attenzione a non provocare pericolose estensioni del conflitto nelle province balcaniche. Gli "enigmi maggiori" della condotta italiana risultavano facilmente identificabili (tra cui la mancata distruzione della flotta turca, la parata dimostrativa ai Dardanelli e l'incongruenza della politica dello *status quo* balcanico con le sperate insurrezioni, che ricadevano così nelle mani di russi e austriaci) ed evidenziavano un'impreparazione "diplomantica" di fondo che era stata la maggior debolezza dell'impresa. Ciò aveva fatto sì che l'Italia di fronte al mondo assumesse il ruolo di ingiusto provocatore da cui ne era conseguito lo sfavore di tutta l'opinione pubblica europea e perfino lo scherno per le difficoltà dell'esercito di quella che si prometteva come una "passeggiata militare". Inoltre, più concretamente, la Tripolitania rappresentava per il popolo bulgaro la massima espressione dell'oppressione, visto che in quella inospitale regione venivano inviati i rivoluzionari più pericolosi del movimento bulgaro-macedone: la conquista italiana "civile e liberale" avrebbe posto fine a questo stato di cose. A questo si aggiungeva un generale sentimento di simpatia verso l'Italia del Risorgimento - risultato di un difficile processo di lotta per l'unificazione e l'indipendenza nazionale - in cui i popoli balcanici identificavano la massima espressione del "diritto di nazionalità", di quel diritto soggettivo che tutti i popoli della regione danubiana e balcanica anelavano a vedersi riconosciuto e per il quale lottavano⁹. Il fatto che l'Italia si fosse trasformata in uno "Stato egoista" e alleato delle grandi potenze europee cambiava solo relativamente i termini della visione a favore di Roma. Il timore per i popoli balcanici era per lo più dato dal fatto che la resistenza all'armata italiana su un territorio dove i turchi avevano "il deserto per alleato" aveva convinto la Sublime Porta di aver praticamente vinto e l'aveva resa più pericolosa nei Balcani e più "tirannica" verso le popolazioni non musulmane. In effetti però i dati specifici della resistenza araba provano che l'azione italiana nei confronti della popolazione aveva riscosso un insuccesso non solo per la presenza del deserto, ma anche per le capacità combattive degli stessi arabi, che avevano ritardato l'avanzata italiana e imposto al generale Carlo Caneva una tattica sostanzialmente attendista¹⁰: contrariamente a quanto propagandato dalle corrispondenze da Tripoli di interventisti (che

⁸ *Ibidem*, p. 196.

⁹ Si veda Angelo Tamborra, *Cavour e i Balcani*, Torino, ILTE, 1958.

¹⁰ Si veda Francesco Malgeri, *La guerra libica 1911-1912*, Roma, Edizioni di storia e letteratura, 1970.

assicuravano che gli italiani non avrebbero incontrato opposizione nell'elemento arabo), questo svolse un ruolo proprio e autonomo dalle stesse truppe ottomane, non previsto dai politici e dagli esponenti delle gerarchie militari italiane. Per gli ambienti balcanici e in particolare bulgari, quindi, risultava chiara anche la superficialità con cui l'azione italiana su Tripoli era stata preparata e condotta, non tanto dal punto di vista militare quanto da quello politico (nei fatti, la dimostrazione navale effettuata ai Dardanelli e l'occupazione delle isole del Dodecaneso, di scarso valore strategico, dovevano rivelarsi come due errori). In questi stessi ambienti, invece, non si capiva che c'erano condizionanti elementi di politica internazionale che avevano peso nella determinazione della politica italiana. Fin dall'inizio dunque Vienna e Berlino avevano sollecitato una rapida conclusione del conflitto: d'altronde il timore (non ingiustificato) che dalla guerra italo-turca gli Stati balcanici potessero convincersi che l'esercito ottomano non fosse imbattibile e condurre quindi una "guerra balcanica" contro la Turchia che potesse degenerare in un conflitto europeo, insieme alla tradizionale politica filoturca della Germania, erano tra i motivi fondamentali che animavano l'iniziativa austro-germanica. L'Italia d'altra parte doveva limitare il conflitto sia per evitare un'azione austriaca a Durazzo e Valona, sia per l'opposizione delle altre potenze europee a un eventuale allargamento della guerra. Questi elementi, che muovevano la politica italiana e determinavano quelle incertezze che si ripercuotevano sulla situazione balcanica, si basavano su due grandi errori di prospettiva commessi dall'Italia: l'aver sopravvalutato la possibilità che il solo timore di complicazioni nella penisola balcanica avrebbe reso la Turchia disponibile alla pace e il non aver coinvolto (né tentato di coinvolgere) gli Stati balcanici. È così che nell'autunno 1912, in ulteriori rapporti da Sofia, si sottolineava come la stampa bulgara, dopo aver "sfogato il malumore per la doccia fredda della nota italiana circa il mantenimento dello *status quo*", tornava a proporre almeno il conseguimento di concessioni per i connazionali di Macedonia in cambio della neutralità¹¹.

La questione della neutralità, di fatto, era un problema esclusivamente bulgaro, dal momento che la Serbia si era immediatamente dichiarata per la neutralità, come anche la Grecia e la Romania, che pure (come aveva scritto l'addetto militare a Bucarest, capitano Carlo Papa di Costigliole, prima dello scoppio del conflitto) in precedenza era stata attratta nell'orbita della Triplice Alleanza proprio dalla presenza dell'Italia, che aveva rappresentato fino a quel momento "una salvaguardia per gli interessi di questo paese nella penisola balcanica, una garanzia per il mantenimento dello *status quo*, un freno alle aspirazioni dell'elemento tedesco verso il sud"¹². Alla deflagrazione della guerra italo-turca di fatto l'interesse della Romania era focalizzato esclusivamente sui riflessi che

¹¹ Cfr Antonello Biagini, "Simeon Radev...", pp. 196-197.

¹² *Ibidem*, p. 197.

questo poteva avere sul comportamento della Bulgaria, che avrebbe potuto tentare di estendersi verso sud e provocare così degli “avvenimenti di fronte ai quali” il governo romeno “non crede di poter rimanere indifferente”¹³ (proprio per il timore che a un’espansione bulgara verso sud non avrebbe corrisposto un compenso territoriale per la Romania). Nell’autunno 1911 la stampa romena risultava così complessivamente poco favorevole all’azione italiana o, più esplicitamente, tendente anche a “simpatizzare per il governo turco”¹⁴. A giudizio del capitano italiano Carlo Papa, tuttavia, il linguaggio della stampa non rispecchiava i reali sentimenti dell’opinione pubblica romena, anche se in pratica la Romania mostrava simpatia verso la Turchia in tutte le occasioni che sembravano mettere in discussione lo *status quo* balcanico, magari con la speranza di ottenere dalla Sublime Porta un diverso trattamento in favore dei “cutzovalacchi” (di etnia balcano-romanza, affine a quella daco-romena) di Macedonia¹⁵. La regione macedone, di fatto, era al centro dell’attenzione, dei problemi politici e dei rapporti tra gli Stati balcanici e tra questi e l’Impero ottomano.

All’inizio del secondo decennio del XX secolo esplodeva anche un’altra questione nazionale, quella albanese, rimasta in sordina per decenni ma mai realmente sopita. Gli albanesi, maggioritariamente musulmani e ben inseriti in molti ambienti governativi e militari turchi, come ultimo popolo balcanico avrebbero proclamato la propria indipendenza dall’Impero ottomano il 28 novembre 1912. Naturalmente anche in questo caso la competizione tra l’Italia (che si considerava una sorta di “protettore” del “Paese delle aquile”, anche per la presenza in Italia dell’antica comunità albanofona degli *arbëreshë*) e le grandi potenze, *in primis* l’Austria-Ungheria, risultava la chiave di lettura per la comprensione della politica italiana nei confronti di questi territori adriatici. Al centro dell’analisi politica che emerge nell’estate 1911 su questo tema dai rapporti dell’addetto militare a Costantinopoli Marro restava comunque la presenza di Vienna, mostratasi dapprima “grande amica della Turchia”, quindi protettrice dei ribelli - come nazione cattolica - con lo scopo di appoggiare i cattolici albanesi e di impedire che slavi e albanesi, abbandonati a se stessi, facessero causa comune con il Montenegro su incoraggiamento della Russia¹⁶. Lo scopo principale dell’Austria-Ungheria (come dimostrato nel 1908 nel caso della Bosnia-Erzegovina) era l’annessione, poiché “quando un popolo piccolo, povero, privo dei conforti della civiltà è in comunanza di vita con un altro popolo colto, forte, intraprendente e ricco è, per legge di natura, da questo assorbito”: di fronte a questa nuova minaccia la Turchia avrebbe sempre più cercato e ottenuto l’appoggio germanico¹⁷. La questione albanese, così

¹³ *Ibidem*.

¹⁴ *Ibidem*, pp. 197-198.

¹⁵ *Ibidem*, p. 198.

¹⁶ Cfr. Idem, “L’indipendenza albanese (1911-1912)”, in Idem, *Momenti di storia...*, p. 210.

¹⁷ *Ibidem*.

come quella macedone, si legava dunque direttamente alla crisi dell'Impero ottomano sin dall'inizio del Novecento: la debolezza del potere centrale, la propaganda di mobilitazione nazionale, la penetrazione economica e l'ingerenza degli Stati europei, le velleità dei piccoli Stati balcanici con il loro particolarismo, il fallimento della politica dei Giovani Turchi, tutti questi elementi avevano causato uno stato di anarchia endemica manifestatosi con un lungo susseguirsi di insurrezioni spesso sanguinose, le quali avevano accentuato le stesse rivalità tra le differenti "nazionalità oppresse". In principio la rivoluzione e il tentativo costituzionale dei Giovani Turchi era stato appoggiato dalle tribù albanesi, nella speranza della concessione di una reale autonomia amministrativa e dell'uguaglianza delle etnie all'interno dell'Impero. Il programma di "ottomanizzazione" (di fatto di "turchizzazione") e di islamizzazione messo in atto dal regime costituzionale, invece, così come la proibizione a costituire società politiche e la nuova legge sul servizio militare (che aveva posto fine agli stessi privilegi di cui gli albanesi avevano goduto con i sultani, in quanto loro fedeli servitori), furono le cause determinanti della definitiva e insanabile rottura con il movimento giovane turco.

3. Debolezza turca in Africa: l'intervento italiano

Non soltanto nella "Turchia europea", cioè nei Balcani, ma anche negli altri territori periferici rispetto alla penisola anatolica erano attivi movimenti tribali antiottomani: in particolare nel Vicino Oriente, in Arabia e in Africa settentrionale. In quest'ultima regione, tra la Tunisia francese e l'Egitto inglese, rimanevano le province indicate comunemente con la denominazione imperiale romana (*Libya*): la Tripolitania, a est, la Cirenaica, a ovest, oltre alle zone desertiche orientali chiamate Fezzan. Elevate a *vilayet* ottomani fin dalla prima metà del XIX secolo e abitate da popolazione araba (concentrata per lo più nei centri costieri, mentre poche migliaia di nomadi si muovevano nell'entroterra), queste regioni erano all'inizio del Novecento organizzate intorno al potere degli emiri senussiti. Le confraternite islamiche dei Senussi vantavano la propria discendenza direttamente da Fatima (l'ultima figlia di Maometto) e gestivano la vita politico-sociale e religiosa delle regioni libiche in autonomia rispetto al governo ottomano. La rivendicazione di totale indipendenza dal potere centrale, però, si univa alla lotta contro i nuovi regimi coloniali (in Tunisia, Egitto e Sudan): in seguito all'occupazione italiana, i Senussi avrebbero organizzato la resistenza dietro la guida di valorosi guerriglieri e capi religiosi (come Omar al-Mukhtar, eroe della resistenza anti-italiana, giustiziato nel 1931).

Nonostante la debolezza del potere ottomano in queste province ottomane fosse un indubbio elemento favorevole a un eventuale intervento da parte di una potenza straniera, nell'iniziale cautela del capo del governo Giovanni Giolitti si ritrova però la conferma del timore di una crisi europea dalle conseguenze inaspettate. È così che Roma, di fronte alle tensioni tra Parigi (appoggiata da Londra) e Berlino nel Mediterraneo occidentale,

attende il consolidamento di un accordo franco-tedesco ritardando la spedizione almeno fino alla metà di settembre. La “brutalità” dell’ultimatum italiano (di sole ventiquattro ore!) del 28 settembre al governo ottomano prima dell’occupazione determina il resto: Giolitti intende gestire l’intervento come una pura scelta di politica estera e una semplice “guerra coloniale” (quindi una guerra “periferica”, e non “europea”) che non deve influire sulla politica interna. Il 29 settembre avvenne il primo scontro navale con le navi turche nel Mediterraneo: la guerra era esplosa. L’Italia mobilitò un Corpo d’armata organizzato in due divisioni al comando del generale Carlo Caneva e portò la mobilitazione nel corso del conflitto da 20.000 unità fino quasi a raddoppiare il numero di uomini.

4. Campagna di Libia: Italia “liberale” o “imperiale”?

La campagna di Libia divenne un punto controverso nella lettura critica della storia dell’Italia liberale, legata strettamente alla figura di Giovanni Giolitti e all’applicazione di concetti quali “liberalismo” e “imperialismo” alla storia patria. In generale si possono identificare tre principali interpretazioni¹⁸: una prima evidenza il superamento del liberalismo in declino attraverso un impegno funzionale a favorire fattori emergenti di ordine economico-industriale (o, secondo la formula togliattiana, all’avvento del “capitale monopolistico finanziario”¹⁹) o di ispirazione politico-“nazionalista”. Una seconda, complessa, raccoglie coloro che vedono nell’avventura libica un’ultima espressione del “trasformismo” giolittiano, che apre a sinistra (come sul suffragio universale) e che guadagna il sostegno anche dell’opinione pubblica dei “nazionalisti” (con il nuovo settimanale *L’Idea nazionale*) e dei cattolici (come nelle testate finanziate dal Banco di Roma, che notoriamente faceva pesanti pressioni per l’intervento), adattandosi al desiderio di “guerra” da parte degli ambienti conservatori così come dell’Italia “proletaria” e di conquista della “quarta sponda” italiana²⁰. La terza (accreditata anche da Benedetto Croce²¹ e che risulta la chiave di lettura più adatta al contemporaneo contesto internazionale) dà infine risalto alle specifiche condizioni della situazione internazionale in cui l’Italia, dopo lo scacco di Tunisi, si trova nel 1911 ad assistere alla seconda crisi marocchina tra Parigi (supportata da Londra) e Berlino e quindi a non poter evitare di procedere ad assumere il proprio ruolo nel Mediterraneo con l’intervento in Libia, come già concordato nella conferenza di Algeiras del 1906.

¹⁸ Cfr. Bruno Vigezzi, “Il liberalismo di Giolitti e l’impresa libica”, in Lucia D’Ippolito (a cura di), *Fonti e problemi della politica coloniale italiana. Atti del Convegno, Taormina-Messina, 23-29 ottobre 1989*, 2 voll., Roma, Ministero per i Beni Culturali, 1996, vol. II, pp. 1230 e sgg.

¹⁹ Cfr. Palmiro Togliatti, “Discorso su Giolitti (1950)”, in Idem, *Momenti della storia d’Italia*, Roma, Editori Riuniti 1963; cfr. anche Bruno Vigezzi, *op. cit.*, p. 1230.

²⁰ Si veda in generale Sergio Romano, *La quarta sponda. La guerra di Libia, 1911-1912*, Milano, Bompiani, 1977.

²¹ Cfr. in generale la sua opera e nello specifico Benedetto Croce, *Storia d’Italia dal 1871 al 1915*, Bari, Laterza, 1928 e seguenti edizioni.

D'altronde quest'ultima è la prospettiva che emerge anche dal promemoria del ministro degli Esteri San Giuliano del 28 luglio, che prospetta la necessità di intervenire (in adempimento dell'accordo franco-italiano 1902, che prevedeva mano libera in Marocco per Parigi e in Libia per Roma) come pure il timore di un'accelerazione della crisi dell'Impero ottomano in particolare nei Balcani, rispetto al quale s'intravedono anche soluzioni intermedie (con una presenza italiana che limiti il potere ottomano alla sola sovranità, come nel caso di una restaurazione della dinastia indigena dei Karamanli o del modello della Bosnia-Erzegovina del 1878)²².

5. La guerra italo-turca come "primavera italiana"

Per l'Italia era dunque l'occasione per vivere una "primavera italiana": il governo, la marina mercantile e le forze armate avrebbero elaborato l'evoluzione del conflitto attraverso rapporti ben documentati negli anni a seguire²³, anticipati da relazioni brevi subito dopo la fine delle ostilità²⁴. La mobilitazione "speciale" per il conflitto fu così "il primo esperimento, dopo le campagne per l'unità d'Italia, di mobilitazione preordinata su scala piuttosto estesa" ma rispettando la "necessità di non compromettere un'eventuale mobilitazione generale dell'esercito". Fu costituito il corpo di spedizione con reparti organici tratti da diversi corpi d'armata, insieme con mezzi (ambulanze e ospedali da guerra) forniti dall'associazione Croce Rossa, con cui si sarebbe arrivati a un totale di circa 34.000 uomini, 6.300 quadrupedi, 1.050 carri, 48 cannoni da campagna e 24 cannoni da montagna: 2 divisioni (di fanteria, con sezione mitragliatrici, cavalleggeri, artiglieria da campagna, zappatori e servizi di carreggio leggero), truppe suppletive (tra cui erano presenti anche bersaglieri, con sezione mitragliatrici, artiglieria da montagna e da fortezza, e 4 stazioni telegrafiche da campo), intendenza e servizi della Croce Rossa. Come principale porto d'imbarco fu scelto quello di Napoli, con l'impiego di piroscafi noleggiati. L'ordine di mobilitazione fu diramato il 25 settembre 1911, fissando come primo giorno il 28, e fu rivolto agli individui della classe 1890 sotto le armi e ai richiamati della classe 1888.

²² Cfr *Documenti Diplomatici Italiani (D.D.I.)*, IV serie, 1908-1914, voll. VII-VIII (30 marzo 1911-18 ottobre 1912), pp. 121-125, documento n. 108, *Il Ministro degli Esteri, Di San Giuliano, al Re Vittorio Emanuele III e al Presidente del Consiglio e Ministro dell'Interno, Giolitti (Promemoria riservato)*, Fiuggi, 28 luglio 1911.

²³ I riferimenti più completi sono: Direzione Generale della Marina Mercantile, *Atti della R. Commissione delle prede: guerra italo-turca 1911-'12*, 5 voll., Roma, Officina Poligrafica Italiana, 1912-1915; Ministero della Guerra - Ufficio Storico dello Stato Maggiore del Regio Esercito, *Campagna di Libia*, 5 voll., Roma, Stabilimento poligrafico per l'amministrazione della guerra, 1922-1927.

²⁴ Si veda: ***, *La marina nella guerra italo-turca (1911-12). Esposizione sommaria delle operazioni compiute durante la guerra*, Roma, Ministero della Marina, 1912; Ufficio Coloniale del Comando di Corpo dello Stato Maggiore, *L'azione dell'esercito italiano nella guerra italo-turca (1911-1912)*, Roma, Lab. tip. del Comando del Corpo di Stato Maggiore, 1913. Per quest'ultimo documento, si veda anche Andrea Carteny, "Il 1911 e l'intervento italiano in Libia: dalla relazione breve dello Stato Maggiore Esercito Italiano", in Antonello Biagini, *C'era una volta la Libia. 1911-2011, storia e cronaca*, Torino, Miraggi, 2011.

Le condizioni che si delineavano in Libia richiedevano forze superiori a quelle previste: si avviò così, da metà ottobre a fine dicembre, la mobilitazione di ulteriori effettivi (fanteria, bersaglieri), armamenti e mezzi, per un numero complessivo di 55.000 uomini, 8.300 quadrupedi, 1.500 carri, 84 cannoni da campagna, 42 cannoni da montagna, 28 bocche da fuoco da assedio. Ancora nei primi dieci mesi del 1912 si mobilitarono per la Libia e l'Egeo ulteriori battaglioni alpini, ascari eritrei e meharisti, reparti dirigibili e flottiglie d'aviazione. Con la massima attività impiegata dalla Regia Marina e con i servizi postali e telegrafici, la mobilitazione fu realizzata con il massimo impiego delle ferrovie italiane, sui cui convogli nei soli mesi di ottobre e novembre 1911 furono trasportati oltre 250.000 uomini. Dalla fine di settembre 1911, dunque, il Ministero della Guerra aveva posto in essere tutto il necessario per un intervento armato se non fosse stato raggiunto un accordo diplomatico con l'Impero ottomano²⁵. Oltre alla successione delle operazioni sul campo nei differenti scenari, in queste relazioni si sottolinea come "con l'opera civile compiuta in Libia durante la guerra, si raggiungeva evidentemente anche lo scopo di mostrare agli arabi i nostri intendimenti benefici nei riguardi della nuova colonia: il paragone fra il vecchio ed il nuovo non poteva che riuscire grandemente vantaggioso per noi, dato lo squallore cui erano state ridotte quelle terre e quelle popolazioni. Naturalmente i maggiori effetti politici si raggiunsero mercé la nostra larga assistenza sanitaria per gli indigeni e mercé il rispetto delle loro tradizioni, dei costumi, delle credenze religiose; cose queste di più immediato beneficio e meglio tangibili". Si fa riferimento alla concessione di "salve d'onore nelle maggiori ricorrenze musulmane; si fecero distribuzioni di montoni per la pratica delle funzioni di rito; e si restaurarono anche le moschee danneggiate dai bombardamenti". Si evidenziò la necessità del coinvolgimento dei capi-tribù locali, e quindi "s'intavolarono anche trattative con i capi, perché si era compreso che il volere di costoro era ciecamente seguito dalle turbe; e si allettarono con la promessa che sarebbero stati mantenuti del loro rango, e si sarebbero conferite loro anche cariche amministrative"²⁶.

6. Conclusioni: la fine del "lungo Ottocento"

Dal punto di vista diplomatico, il negoziato di pace era stato avviato già nel luglio 1912 (trattative italo-turche di Losanna) e ripreso ad agosto a Caux. A settembre i negoziatori si trasferivano a Ouchy: qui il peggioramento della situazione militare dei turchi - anche a causa delle diserzioni nella Turchia europea - portò al precipitare delle tensioni nei Balcani, con la mobilitazione di Serbia, Montenegro, Bulgaria e Grecia contro l'Impero ottomano. E l'Italia impose la pace dietro la minaccia di blocco al trasporto via mare di truppe turche verso i territori ottomani in Europa: il trattato di pace fu siglato il 18 ottobre. Si sancì così l'autonomia

²⁵ *Ibidem*, pp. 22-24.

²⁶ *Ibidem*, p. 43.

di Tripolitania e Cirenaica dal governo ottomano, si emanò un'amnistia per la popolazione araba che aveva partecipato al conflitto, si garantì nei due territori la presenza di un rappresentante del Califfo, mentre l'Italia s'impegnò a versare all'Impero ottomano una somma di indennizzo per la perdita dei territori. La restituzione delle isole dell'Egeo occupate, condizionata dal ritiro delle truppe ottomane da Tripolitania e Cirenaica, rimase inattuata.

Contestualmente alle ostilità sul fronte libico si erano articolate dunque le lotte nazionali nei Balcani: quella per l'indipendenza albanese e la prima guerra balcanica (ottobre 1912), dove di fronte ai soldati balcanici si trovavano a combattere eroici personaggi anche del mondo turco (come Enver pascià, uno dei massimi esponenti del movimento dei Giovani Turchi e leggendario condottiero della guerra di Libia, delle guerre balcaniche e ministro della Guerra durante la prima guerra mondiale). La Bulgaria, che sosteneva il peso maggiore della lega balcanica contro i turchi, non ritenne soddisfatte le proprie rivendicazioni sui territori ceduti dall'Impero ottomano in seguito alla pace di Londra (maggio 1913). L'azione bulgara contro i serbi indusse gli altri Stati a coalizzarsi a favore di Belgrado: fu così che le guerre balcaniche, iniziate con una lega preludio di una più ampia collaborazione, si sarebbero concluse con violenti contrasti tra gli Stati alleati che non si erano preoccupati di chiarire prima della pace di Londra i limiti delle loro pretese territoriali. La Macedonia rimaneva al centro degli interessi e dei contrasti tra bulgari e serbi, così come tra bulgari e greci, per la Macedonia egea. I romeni dal canto loro rivendicavano, in cambio della neutralità, quella parte della Dobrugia assegnata alla Bulgaria dal Congresso di Berlino. Nello spazio di un mese (luglio-agosto 1913) la ripresa delle ostilità della coalizione antibulgara, rapidamente formatasi tra Serbia, Romania, Grecia, Montenegro e perfino Turchia ottomana (l'"eterno nemico"), costrinse la Bulgaria a firmare la pace di Bucarest (10 agosto 1913). La Serbia otteneva la Macedonia settentrionale e centrale con la città di Monastir, la Grecia quella egea con Salonico e Cavala, la Romania un'ulteriore parte della Dobrugia mentre l'Impero ottomano, con il trattato di Costantinopoli (29 settembre 1913), recuperava gran parte della Tracia compresa la città di Adrianopoli. Il dominio turco in Europa era stato drasticamente ridotto, così come la presenza in Africa settentrionale.

L'Italia, nella campagna di Libia, aveva testato l'efficienza dell'esercito e della marina militare a mezzo secolo dalla sua unificazione. Quello libico fu inoltre lo scenario dove si registrarono notevoli progressi tecnologici applicati a operazioni e azioni belliche: *in primis* l'uso dell'aeroplano, che dopo due anni dal primo volo, veniva impiegato sia come mezzo di offesa sia per ricognizione. Nell'ottobre 1911 il capitano Carlo Maria Piazza guidò un apparecchio sulle linee turche nella prima missione di ricognizione delle forze armate italiane, e il 1° novembre l'aviatore Giulio Gavotti da un velivolo lasciò cadere una bomba a mano sulle truppe ottomane. Quindi ci fu l'impiego della radio, con un servizio

regolare di radiotelegrafia campale organizzato dall'arma del genio (con la collaborazione di Guglielmo Marconi) e il primo utilizzo di vetture automobili in un conflitto, prodotte dall'azienda torinese Fiat.

La campagna di Libia era stata sì l'ultimo conflitto del "lungo" secolo decimonono dell'Italia risorgimentale, ma risultava anche incontrovertibilmente il primo conflitto novecentesco (per tecnologia e propaganda) del "nazionalismo" italiano.

THE REBIRTH OF POLAND. POLISH APPLICATION OF SELF-DETERMINATION AT THE END OF THE FIRST WORLD WAR

Giuseppe Motta*

Abstract

After the end of the first world war Versailles' peace negotiations defined the new settlement of Central-Eastern Europe on the principle of self-determination. The application of this concept, anyway, was not easy and peaceful and was many times entrusted to the factual conditions of the disputed regions and to conditions of the States claiming them. In the case of Poland, the new State was reshaped according to the strange combination of diplomacy and conflicts, as the definitive extension of the State depended on the fate of the campaigns in which Polish troops were involved after the Great War. Poland, thus, showed the particular situation of Central-Eastern Europe, where many little conflicts accompanied the development of diplomatic negotiations.

Keywords: Poland, Self-Determination, National Minorities

“An independent Polish state should be erected which should include the territories inhabited by indisputably Polish populations, which should be assured a free and secure access to the sea, and whose political and economic independence and territorial integrity should be guaranteed by international covenant”¹.

The American president Wilson openly recognized among his famous “fourteen points” the independence of Poland as one of the most outstanding pieces of the future European settlement, which had to be developed in the name of self-determination principle².

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¹ “Under his scepter Poland will come together, free in faith, in language, and in self-government”. *Proclamation of 14th August 1914*, in R. Leslie (ed.), *The History of Poland since 1863*, Cambridge, Harvard University Press, 1983.

² On the influence of American diplomacy at the peace negotiations of Versailles, Wiktor Sukiennicki, *East-Central Europe during World War I: From Foreign Domination to National Independence*, Vol. II, New York, East European Monographs, 1984; Inga Floto, *Colonel House In Paris. A Study of American Policy at the Paris Peace Conference 1919*, Aarhus, Universitetsforlaget i Aarhus, 1973; Ray Stannard Baker, *Woodrow Wilson and World Settlement*, New York, Doubleday, Page&Co., 1922; Lawrence Emerson Gelfand, *The Inquiry. American Preparation for Peace, 1917-1919*, New Haven, Yale University Press, 1963; Victor Samuel Mamatey, *The United States and East Central Europe, 1914-1918. A Study in Wilsonian Diplomacy and Propaganda*, Princeton University Press, New Jersey, 1957; George Cipăianu - Vasile Vesa (sous la dir.), *La fin de la première Guerre Mondiale et la nouvelle architecture géopolitique européenne*, Presses Universitaires de Cluj, Cluj-Napoca, 2000; August Heckscher (ed.), *The Politics of Woodrow Wilson. Selections from his speeches and writings*, New York, Harper&Brothers, 1956; Jean-Baptiste Duroselle, *De Wilson à Roosevelt. La politique extérieure des Etats-Unis, 1913-1945*, Paris, Armand Colin, 1960; Charles Seymour, *The Intimate Papers of Colonel House*, 4 voll., New York, Houghton Mifflin, 1926-1928.

The Crown of Poland had been one of the most important States of Central-Eastern Europe for many centuries, until the State anyway was gradually dismantled: the internal instability due to the elective monarchy weakened the central power while enforcing the different confederations formed by the nobles (*szlachta*); the other States as Prussia, Russia and Austria, on the contrary were strengthening their power. These States signed the Treaty of the Three Black Eagles, reaching an agreement to consult reciprocally in order to manage the Polish destiny. Poland was partitioned in 1772, 1793 and 1795, after that the last king Stanisław II August Poniatowski had tried to reform the State, also through one of the first and more advanced constitutions, the Constitution of May 3rd, 1791³.

The Congress of Vienna in 1815 confirmed the death of old Poland - for some it was her fourth partition - and during the XIX century Polish patriots were one of the most lively and committed in fighting for the liberty of the nationalities. In all the territories of former Poland, a strong Polish national consciousness emerged, as showed by the rebellions of 1830 and 1863 against Russia, as well as by the great participation of Poles in the unification of Italy, in the secession war in the United States and in other places where Poles fought "For Your Freedom and Ours"⁴.

Even if in 1914 Gran Duke Nicholas talked about the union of the Polish people "under the scepter of the Russian Emperor", things evolved in a different way, as the First World War gave Poland the opportunity to resume her independence. During the war a Regency Council was formed (*Rada Regencyjna Królestwa Polskiego*) to administer the country under German auspices, and in 1916 a first independent puppet Poland was

³ The May 3 Constitution responded to the increasingly perilous situation of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, which only a century earlier was a major European power and indeed the largest State on the continent. Already two hundred years before the May 3 Constitution, King Stanisław August supported a new wave of reforms. The most important included the establishment, in 1773, of a commission for National education and, in 1776, the draft of a legal code commissioned to the Chancellor Zamoyski. The Constitution remained in effect for only a year before being overthrown, by Russian armies allied with the help of the Targowica Confederation. Richard Butterwick, *Poland's Last King and English Culture: Stanisław August Poniatowski, 1732-1798*, Oxford-New York, Oxford University Press, 1998; Norman Davies, *God's Playground: A History of Poland in Two Volumes*, 2 voll., Oxford-New York, Oxford University Press, 2005; Joseph Kasperek-Obst, *The Constitutions of Poland and of the United States: Kinships and Genealogy*, Miami, American Institute of Polish Culture, 1980; Adam Zamoyski, *The Polish Way: a Thousand-Year History of the Poles and Their Culture*, New York, Hippocrene Books, 1994. On the Polish relations with Italy during the times of the Reign, Gaetano Platania (a cura di), *L'Europa centro-orientale e gli archivi tra età moderna e contemporanea*, Viterbo, Settecittà, 2003; Idem, (a cura di), *L'Europa di Giovanni Sobieski*, Viterbo, Settecittà, 2005.

⁴ Andrzej Tadeusz Bonawentura Kościuszko went to America and on 1776 he presented a Memorial to the Congress. He initially served as a volunteer, but in October 18, 1776, Congress appointed him Colonel of Engineers in the Continental Army. Alex Storozynski, *The peasant prince: Thaddeus Kosciuszko and the age of revolution*, New York, St. Martin's Press, 2009; James S. Pula, *Thaddeus Kosciuszko: The Purest Son of Liberty*, Hippocrene Books 1999; Gary B. Nash, Graham Russell Gao Hodegs, *Friends of Liberty: Thomas Jefferson, Thaddeus Kosciuszko, and Agrippa Hull. A Tale of Three Patriots, Two Revolutions, and a Tragic Betrayal of Freedom in the New Nation*, New York, Basic Books, 2008.

created. Shortly after the armistice signed with Germany in November 1918, its full independence as the Second Polish Republic (*II Rzeczpospolita Polska*) was recognized.

In October a new Government began the conscription into the army and in November Jozéf Piłsudski returned to Warsaw, where he was appointed commander in chief of the Polish Army and began his rise towards the most important positions of the newborn State. On 18th November he clearly declared that: “the political situation in Poland and the shackles of occupation made it possible for the Polish nation freely to decide about its own fate... Poland’s revived independence and sovereignty have now become an accomplished fact”⁵. But, after independence, the size of the State had to make its way through chaos and instability, just thanks the military intervention which was necessary to repress the short-lived Republic of Tarnobrzeg and to consolidate the frontiers on the Western and the Eastern fronts.

The first clashes between Polish and Ukrainian units occurred in December 1918 and were not very severe. The West Ukrainian People’s Republic was proclaimed on November 1st, 1918, and soon started a controversy with Poland for the city of Lviv and Eastern Galicia. The city of Lviv (Lwów or Lemberg) became the center of this bloody dispute, which occurred while on the Eastern part of Ukraine the People’s republic had to face the bolshevik Red Army and Denikin’s White troops⁶.

On November 1st, 1918 Ukrainian soldiers occupied Lviv’s public utilities and military objectives, raising Ukrainian flags and proclaiming the birth of the West Ukrainian People’s Republic. But the Polish residents, constituting the majority of Lviv’s inhabitants, were shocked to find themselves in a proclaimed Ukrainian State and organized a small group of resisters in a school. The defenders were joined by hundreds of volunteers, mostly teenagers and students, the “Lwów Eaglets” (*Orlęta Lwowskie*), and started a fight in the streets of the city. Although numerically superior and well-equipped, the Ukrainian Sich Riflemen, the former Ukrainian division of the Habsburg army, was stopped by the Polish resistance, which soon received the help of more troops sent by

⁵ Decree of 18th November 1918. For the process reconstruction of Poland, Paul Latawski (ed.), *The Reconstruction of Poland, 1914-1923*, London, MacMillan, 1992; R. F. Leslie, *The History of Poland Since 1863*, Cambridge-New York, Cambridge University Press, 1983, Cesare La Mantia, *Polonia*, Milano, Unicopli, 2006.

⁶ Galicia had already experienced two Russian occupations in 1914-15 and in 1916-17. During these periods, the conflict between the occupation forces and the Uniate Church emerged as one of the leading feature of the relations between Russians and Rusyns (Ruthenes). The latter showed to be not Russians separated by their mothercountry, as thought by V.A. Brobinskij’s Galician-Russia Beneficent Society, or hereditary subordinates of the Poles. Mark von Hagen, *War in a European Borderland. Occupations and Occupation Plans in Galicia and Ukraine*, Seattle-London, University of Washington Press, 2007; Chris Hann, Paul Robert Magocsi, *Galicia: A Multicultural Land*, Toronto-Buffalo, University of Toronto, 2005; Aviel Roshwald, *Ethnic Nationalism and the Fall of Empires: Central Europe, the Middle East and Russia, 1914-1923*, London-New York, Routledge, 2001.

Warsaw. The city resisted under siege for some months, with the Ukrainian forces continuing to surround Lviv from three sides.

Even if an armistice was signed on November 18th, chaos during the Polish take-over of the city culminated in about two day-long riot, in which mostly Polish criminals and soldiers started pillaging the city; over the course of the riots, many Ukrainians and Jews were murdered (November 21st-23th). Heavy fighting for other cities continued and the situation did not change either after that on February 24th, 1919, a short-lived armistice was signed under the pressure of the Entente.

Positional skirmishes between entrenched sides lasted till May, 1919, when Polish offensive on the Eastern-Galician front forced the Ukrainians to withdraw, ending the six-month battle for the control over Lviv. After the creation of a commission for the negotiation of an armistice between Poland and Ukraine was created in Paris under the presidency of General Louis Botha, in the summer of 1919 Polish forces took over most of the territory claimed by the West Ukrainian People's Republic and reached an agreement with Petljura, the leader of Russian Ukraine. Part of the defeated army found refuge in Czechoslovakia, where it kept on acting under the name of *Ukrajinská brigáda*, while most of the army, continued the struggle for Ukrainian independence in the Russian part of the country.

In July 1919 the West Ukrainian People's Republic established a government-in-exile headed by Evgeny Petrushevich, who strongly adversed any compromise with Poland. In April 1920 Poland and the Kiev-based Ukrainian People's Republic agreed at Warsaw to fix a border, officially recognizing Polish control over the disputed territory of Eastern Galicia⁷. But the end of the defense of Lwów - which was called by Polish

⁷ The history of the Ukrainian minority in Poland dates back to the mid-14th century, when King Casimir III annexed Ruthenia, whose population was predominantly Ukrainian (Ruthenian). In 1340, Poland annexed other Przemysł lands and in the following years, Polish rule was extended further east. After the Union of Lublin (1569), more ethnic Ukrainian lands were incorporated into the Kingdom. Timothy Snyder, *The Reconstruction of Nations: Poland, Ukraine, Lithuania, Belarus, 1569-1999*, New Haven, Yale University Press; Paul Robert Magocsi, *A History of Ukraine*, Toronto-Buffalo, University of Toronto Press, 1996; Orest Subtelny, *Ukraine: a History*, Toronto-Buffalo, University of Toronto Press, 1988. The relations between the exiled Western Ukrainian government and that of Kiev-based government continued to deteriorate, in part because the Western Ukrainians saw the Poles as the main enemy (with the Russians as a potential ally) while the Kiev-based Ukrainian government considered to negotiate with the Poles against their Russian enemies. In response to Kiev's diplomatic talks with Poland, the Western Ukrainian government sent a delegation to the Soviet 12th Army, but ultimately rejected Soviet conditions for an alliance. In November the government of the West Ukrainian People's Republic left for exile in Vienna. Michael Palij, *The Ukrainian-Polish Defensive Alliance, 1919-1921. An Aspect of the Ukrainian Revolution*, Edmonton, Canadian Institute of Ukrainian Studies Press, 1995; Oleksandr Derhachov (ed.), *Ukrainian Statehood in the Twentieth Century: Historical and Political Analysis*, Kiev, Political Thought, 1996; Dennis P. Hupchick, *Conflict and Chaos in Eastern Europe*, New York, St. Martin's Press, 1995; Norman Davies, *White Eagle, Red Star: The Polish-Soviet War 1919-20*, London, Macdonald&Co., 1972; Manuela Pellegrino, *Ucraina: invenzione geografica o Stato sovrano? La rivoluzione del 1917 nella documentazione militare*

historians *the last civilized conflict* because both sides were too weak to create regular front lines and lacked of heavy weapons, the civilian casualties were low and did not exceed 400, moreover, both sides tried to avoid destroying the city's facilities and the most important buildings were declared *de-militarized zone* - the traditional hostility between Poles and Ukrainians resurfaced. In the past the two people had coexisted inside the same State, at least until Poland kept its stability. In the XVII century, in fact, the rebellion of Bohdan Zynoviy Mykhailovych Khmelnytsky (1648) addressed the Ukrainians towards Russia, which made an important step towards unification of the three East-Slavic countries (Ukraine, Belarus and Russia) with the Treaty of Andrusovo (1667). This conflict had also religious and cultural implications, as the Ukrainians were subjected to policies which they considered as an attempt of Polonization. Also the Orthodox believers were pushed towards the union with the Church of Rome, after the creation of an Uniate confession which entered under the sphere of Roman Catholic Church while keeping Eastern rites. The importance of religion for the Polish-Ukrainian conflict was clearly detachable studying the documents of the Holy See, which noticed not only the violence of the bolsheviks. As in the first postwar phase the Catholics of those regions suffered for the chaos and the fights following the Revolution of 1917, at the end of 1918 the conflict for Eastern Galicia took a second wave of violence. Ratti, the apostolic representative of the Pope in Poland, expressed the sadness of Benedict XV for the tragical effects that the war had on the relationships among the Catholic Poles and the Ukrainian Uniates⁸.

The connection between political and religious questions was testified also by other sources, for example the press. In 1919, the "New York Times" published an article reporting the protests generated by the internment of the Ruthenian primate, Archbishop Szeptycky, and of 200 Ukrainian priests in Lemberg, which was to add to the closure of "nearly all of the Ukrainian Catholic churches". The article also mentioned other cases of imprisonment and shooting without trial, the assassination of a priest during the celebration of the mass in Bortne, as it was reported by

italiana, Roma, Stato Maggiore dell'Esercito - Ufficio Storico, 2006; Michael Hrushevsky, *A History of Ukraine*, Hamden, Archon Books, 1941; John Stephen Reshetar, *The Ukrainian Revolution, 1917-1920. A Study in Nationalism*, Princeton, Princeton University Press, 1952; Basil Dmitryshyn, *Moscow and the Ukraine, 1918-1953. A Study of Russian Bolshevik National Policy*, New York, Bookman Associates, 1956; E. Revyuk, *Polish Atrocities in Ukraine*, New York, Svoboda Press, 1931; Adam Żoltowski, *Border of Europe. A study of the Polish Eastern Provinces*, London, Hollis&Carter, 1950.

⁸ "Per questo il Ss.Padre alza un'altra volta la sua voce ed ai suoi figli che tra loro si uccidono grida pace, pace...". Document of 27th December 1918. Roberto Morozzo della Rocca, *Le nazioni non muoiono. Russia rivoluzionaria, Polonia indipendente e Santa Sede*, Bologna, il Mulino, 1992, p. 123; John Stephen Reshetar, *Ukrainian Nationalism and the Orthodox Church*, in "American Slavonic and East European Review", X, 1951, pp.38-49; J. Mirtshuk, *The Ukrainian Uniat Church*, in "Slavonic Review", X, 1931-1932, pp. 377-385.

the memorial presented by the religious authorities to the American Hierarchy⁹.

The success of Polish Army inevitably took to a whole of repressive measures against the Ukrainians, for example against those clergymen who were considered the moral and national benchmark of the Ukrainian people. Church had a very important position and a great influence on both national movements, as it was realized in Paris by Stephen Bonsal, an advisor of President Wilson, who received the visit of a delegation from the “former Crown land of Galicia in Austria” protesting against the addition of the Ukrainian territories of Cholm, Podlachia, and Wolhynia to the Kingdom of Poland which was in process of formation. Any compromise sounded to the Ukrainian people “as a violation of its historic rights and a mockery of the principle of self-determination of peoples”¹⁰. As a consequence, the exiled Western Ukrainian Government fiercely opposed the Treaty signed in 1920 and continued pressing for its interests during the postwar negotiations and the following years. Clearly Polish point of view was totally different, as Warsaw regarded the minorities almost as an integral part of historical Poland and stressed the role played in the past to reconcile the different ethnic groups under the same rule.

While the peace talks continued through the protests of many big and small delegations, also the struggles for the Eastern territory reached a new peak some months later, when Piłsudski thought to put into practice his *Międzymorze* project, also known as *Intermarum* because it aimed at forming a unique political unity between the Baltic and the Black Sea. This proposed federation was meant to emulate the old Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, but it was not sustained by the Allied Powers and openly rejected by the Soviets and the other peoples of the region, as it was perceived by Lithuanians and Ukrainians as a threat to their independence¹¹. Piłsudski’s dreams, anyway, were not shared by his

⁹ *Catholics Accuse Poles*, in “New York Times”, 28th September 1919; Gaetano Platania, “La pace polono-russa del 1920 nella documentazione del generale Romei-Longhena conservata presso l’Archivio dello Stato Maggiore dell’esercito italiano”, in Waclaw Wierzbienic (a cura di), *Polska, Europa, świat XX wieku. Studia i szkice ofiarowane profesorowi Włodzimierzowi Bonusiakowi w czterdziestolecie Jego pracy twórczej*, Wydawn. Uniw. Rzeszowskiego, Rzeszów 2005, pp. 347-371.

¹⁰ Stephen Bonsal, *Suitors and Supplicants. Little nations at Versailles*, Port Washington, Kennikat Press, 1969, p. 185.

¹¹ In his book, *Essai sur la diplomatie*, completed in 1827 but published only in 1830, Czartoryski observed that, “Having extended her sway south and west, and being by the nature of things unreachable from the east and north, Russia becomes a source of constant threat to Europe”. He argued that she would have done better, cultivating “friends rather than slaves”. He also identified a future threat from Prussia and urged the incorporation of East Prussia into a resurrected Poland. Jonathan Levy, *The Intermarium: Madison, Wilson, and East Central European Federalism*, Dissertation.com, Boca Raton, 2006; Marian Kamil Dziewanowski, *Czartoryski and His Essai sur la diplomatie*, in “Slavic Review”, XXX, 3, 1971; M. K. Dziewanowski, *Joseph Piłsudski: a European Federalist, 1918-1922*, Stanford, Hoover Institution, 1979.

greatest rival Roman Dmowski, leader of the national democracy, who did not want to endanger the numerical hegemony of the Poles¹².

This project took Warsaw to interfere in the Ukrainian affairs. In 1920 the agreement reached with Symon Vasylyovych Petljura's Ukrainian government recognized Poland's right to Galicia but in exchange for military aid against the bolsheviks. According to Italian military sources, Petljura was the most convenient neighbor for Poland, who hosting and helping him, could subordinate his actions to Polish will¹³.

The Polish and Ukrainian armies, under Piłsudski's command, launched a successful offensive and in May 1920 they captured Kiev. But the bolsheviks soon launched a counter-offensive and strengthened their ambitions to export the revolution until Germany. Poland formed a Council for the Defense of the Nation against Mikhail Nikolayevich Tukhachevsky's advance and entrusted its leadership to Piłsudski¹⁴. Even if he was criticized for his ambitious and unconventional strategy, in August 1920 Piłsudski got a revenge on his detractors halting the Soviet advance in the battle of Warsaw¹⁵. Even if it was considered "amateurish", Piłsudski's plan was successful and stopped the Soviet advance; the "Miracle at the Vistula" (*Cud nad Wisłą*) was soon followed by the start of peace talks. An armistice was signed on October 12th, while in Riga the delegations drawn in detail the new border, which did not take to a great extension of Polish territory. The Peace of Riga was signed on March 18th,

¹² Adam Zamoyski, *The Polish Way. A Thousand-Year History of the Poles and their Culture*, London, Murray, 1987; Kay Lundgren-Nielsen, *The Polish Problem at the Paris Peace Conference: A Study of the Policies of the Great Powers and the Poles, 1918-1919*, Odense, Odense University Press, 1979.

¹³ Note sent to the Army General Staff from Warsaw, 10 January 1920, "Notiziario politico", Archivio dello Stato Maggiore dell'Esercito, Rome, (A.U.S.S.M.E.), E11, 57, 13. The agreement reached by Piłsudski and Petljura was instead opposed by Petruschey, leader of the People's Republic of Western Ukraine who did not accept the frontier at Zbrucz and Horyn. Also Dmowski, the chairman of the Polish National committee, had expressed contrasting opinions, preferring to extend Polish borders towards East. The choice, moreover, was conditioned also by the Polish-Soviet relations and by choice Poland had to do between an alliance with Russia or Ukraine in a very complicated context. Peter J. Potichnyj (ed.), *Poland and Ukraine. Past and Present*, Edmonton-Toronto, Canadian Institute of Ukrainian Studies, 1980; Andrei S. Markovits, Frank E. Sysyn (eds.), *Nationbuilding and the Politics of Nationalism. Essays on Austrian Galicia*, Cambridge, Harvard University Press, 1982; Taras Hunczak (ed.), *Ukraine and Poland in Documents, 1918-1922*, New York, Shevchenko Scientific Society, 1983; Andrea Romano, Silvio Pons (eds.), *Russia in the Age of Wars 1914-1945*, Milano, Feltrinelli, 2000.

¹⁴ Naturally, during the war many radio-telegrams of the bolsheviks were addressed to Polish soldiers, inviting them to constitute soviets and stop war in the name of international proletarian solidarity. Some examples of these messages are kept in the historical archive of the Italian Army, A.U.S.S.M.E., E11, 57, 46.

¹⁵ Some suggested that the bolshevik defeat was caused by the Stalin's refusal to transfer the armies from the South-Western front, as ordered by Tukhachevskij. Besides Norman Davies, *White Eagle, Red Star...*, cit.; Adam Zamoyski, *Warsaw 1920: Lenin's Failed Conquest of Europe*, London, HarperPress, 2008, pp. 80-81.

1921, partitioning the territories disputed between Poland and Russia and ending the conflict¹⁶.

Another parallel conflict was involving also the Lithuanians, who had to face Polish uprising in Sejny in August 1919 and in Kaunas, where they discovered the planning of a coup against their government. Finally, Poles succeeded in getting the city of Sejny, where they started a strong repression of Lithuanian cultural life, but later they had to withdraw due to the bolshevik pressures. Lithuanians got the occasion to gain the territories lost in the previous phases and were thus accused of having broken their policy of neutrality.

When the Poles stopped the bolsheviks, the things changed once again and Polish Army started to move towards East. In September 1920, the Battle of the Niemen River drastically altered the balance of power: Vilnius, in Lithuanian hands since August, was exposed to a Polish attack. While negotiations for a peaceful settlement of the dispute continued, in October 1920, Polish General Lucian Żeligowski deserted the Army with his troops and carried out a “mutiny”, taking the control of the city and region of Vilnius (Wilno). Żeligowski’s forces defeated the Lithuanian Infantry Regiment, and on October 9th the Lithuanian forces evacuated the city: on October 12th, Żeligowski proclaimed the independence of the area as the Republic of Central Lithuania, with Vilnius as its capital.

The Polish-Lithuanian war had not been fully studied and analyzed and, thus, is subjected to different interpretations, as some considered it part of the Polish-Soviet war, other as a separate conflict. Also Żeligowski’s mutiny, which was generally interpreted as a Polish strategic move, was considered by some as a sincere attempt made to safeguard at least the independence of a part of Lithuania, in front of the pressures of Germany and Russia. What could be surely affirmed is that the takeover of Wilno was not disliked by Piłsudski, who thought Vilnius (Wilno) was a part of historical Poland and the Poles and Lithuanians were to be considered as brothers¹⁷.

The settlement of the new frontier was very sensitive and complicated, also as a consequence of the creation of a German volunteer

¹⁶ The Terms of the treaty created a huge difference between the Curzon line requested by the Allied Powers and the effective borderland which would be recognized by France, Great Britain, Italy, and Japan, only in 1923. Galicia was first assigned to Poland for 25 years and only later, in 1920, the Supreme Council of Paris abandoned that hybrid solution which was *de facto* modified by the events of 1920-1921 and by the treaty of Riga. The Treaty of Riga abrogated the agreement reached in Warsaw in 1920 and disregarded the ambitions of Belarus and Ukraine to constitute autonomous States. Moreover, the loss of the territories won during the war was strongly criticized in Poland and meant the failure of Piłsudski’s plans to create a Polish-led federation. For Belarusian history, see Jan Zaprudnik, *Belarus. At a Crossroad in History*, Boulder, Westview Press, 1993; Ivan S. Lubachko. *Belorussia under Soviet Rule, 1917-1957*, Lexington, University Press of Kentucky, 1972; Nicholas P. Vakar. *Belorussia. The Making of a Nation*, Cambridge, Harvard University Press, 1956.

¹⁷ In a meeting with the Italian general Romei, the Polish marshal officialy stated that the occupation of Wilno was not against the policy of the Polish government. A.U.S.S.M.E., E11, 57, 52, *Note of 21st October 1920*.

force to defend the Eastern Baltic regions of the former Reich. The Republic of Weimar created a special militia to fight bolshevism and consolidate the presence of Germans along the Baltic shores, for some even to maintain these regions under the authority of Berlin. As a consequence, in the postwar years German divisions fought in Latvia, Estonia and in other areas where German population lived. This experiment, however, was destined to fail disappointing the wishes of many Germans, who saw in the retirement of the troops from the Baltic regions the loss of a land which was historically, economically and culturally connected with their mother country. It was a tragic moment for Germany, which was going to lose other important regions and economic sources, acquiring in exchange the burden of protecting the German communities living in Poland and in the Baltic States.

The result of the complicated postwar situation, however, was that Poland succeeded in acquiring huge portions of territory inhabited by ethnic minorities and claimed by her neighboring States: this extension was not always accomplished in a pacific way. The work of the League of Nations underlined the dangerous effects that Polish attitude could have, refusing to accept the convention proposed by the conference on 12th May on the general military grounds that the safety of the Polish State precluded the acceptance of any armistice which did not allow a Polish military occupation of Eastern Galicia. With her action and her refusal to obey the Conference as regards Galicia, Poland could create "serious results upon other States in stimulating their resistance to the authority of the Conference in local areas, where the armies of the Great Powers could not make their influence felt"¹⁸.

Even if generally the behavior of Polish Government was not contrasting with the directives of the Peace Conference, the cases of Galicia and Lithuania generated many negative appreciations, as well as the case of Korfanty in Upper Silesia, where many riots accompanied the postwar settlement and the relationships among the ethnic groups of the region: Poles, Czechs and Germans. On the other side, the occupation of Prussian territories was in accordance with the decisions of the Conference, which made Poland obtain many territories inhabited by Germans and the creation of a corridor to get an access to the sea through the Free City of Danzig.

A Slask-Pomorze-Poznan (Silesia-West Prussia-Posen) Congress was organized by the National Democrats on December 6th, 1918, and it attempted to seize control of the German eastern provinces in the hope of presenting the Peace Conference at Paris with a *fait accompli*. Ignaz Paderewski arrived at Poznan a few weeks later on a journey from London to Warsaw, and a Polish uprising broke out while he was in this city.

¹⁸ Harold William Vazeille Temperley, *History of the Peace Conference*, 6 voll., London, Frowde, Hodder & Stoughton, 1920, vol. I, p. 338.

Afterwards the Poles, in a series of bitter battles, drove the local German volunteer militia out of most of Posen province.

On January 12th, the Paris Peace conference opened, resulting in the draft of the Treaty of Versailles (June 28th 1919). Articles 27 and 28 of the Treaty ruled on the territorial shape of the Corridor, while articles 89 to 93 ruled on transit, citizenship and property issues. As a consequence of the Versailles Treaty, which was put into effect on January 20th 1920, the corridor was established as Poland's access to the Baltic Sea from 70% of the dissolved province of West Prussia¹⁹. As a memorandum on Polish claims to Danzig and West Prussia argued (Paton's one of February 27th 1919), the question of West Prussia affected Prussian more than German prestige, as its cession could be interpreted as "the symbol of the defeat of *Junkerdom* rather than of Germany".

In the case of Danzig (Gdańsk), anyway, the self-determination principle could not justify the assignment of this German-speaking seaport to Poland, and so the Free City of Danzig was established and placed under the protection of the League of Nations without a plebiscite. After the dock workers of Danzig harbor went on strike at a critical moment during the Polish-Soviet War, refusing to unload ammunition, the Polish Government decided to build a new seaport in the territory of the Corridor, and connected this seaport to the Upper Silesian industrial centers by the newly constructed railways.

At the end of this phase, Poland gained many regions with important German minorities, not only in the Corridor, but also in East Prussia, Poznanian and Upper Silesia. Since the end of 1918, in Poznanian the Polish growing forces of the *Polska Organizacja Wojskowa*, were opposed by the *Heimatschutz-Ost* and later by other special forces, *Deutsche Vereinigung*, in order to keep Prussian Poland in Germany. When Poles took power, Germans counter-demonstrated and at the end of December 1918 were repressed with the martial order and the arrests of the German officers. Polish insurrection spread to the province, confiscating German weapons, imposing curfew and removing Germans signs, expelling Germans when they resisted as at Hohensalza-Inowroclaw.

Germans tried to react also with other volunteers, as the Rossbach Corps, until the ceasefire imposed by the Entente in February 1919. After the definitive failure of the creation of an Ost-Staat, the German population of Polish Prussia started a massive process of emigration, which was a reasonable consequence of the Polish policies. The latter were targeted at inverting the old Germanization of this region, which had been

¹⁹ Greater Poland or Great Poland (*Wielkopolska, Polonia Maior*) together with the Corridor and Pomerania, hosted some particular minorities as the Slavic ethnic groups Kociewiaczy, Borowiacy, Krajniacy and the Kashubians. The problem of the minorities went side by side with the geopolitical value of the region; Kay Lundgren-Nielsen, *op. cit.*; Anna M. Cienciala, Titus Komarnicki, *From Versailles to Locarno. Keys to Polish Foreign Policy, 1919-1925*, Lawrence, United Press of Kansas, 1984.

sponsored in the past by Fredrick the Great and continued in the XIX century.

After the pacification of the Baltic region, in some areas the Polish-German dispute was resolved thanks to a plebiscite, which had to assign some cities in accordance with the will expressed by their population. The plebiscites, however, were held in a climate that was still conditioned by the post-war chaos and lack of stability. The areas of Allenstein and Marienwerder were placed under the authority of two Inter-Allied Commissions of five members appointed by the Principal Allied and Associated Powers representing the League of Nations. Both sides started a propaganda campaign. Yet in March 1919 a delegation headed by the Lutheran Paul Hensel brought to Versailles a collection of more than 100.000 signatures to protest against the planned cession. The Germans founded several regional associations under the title of the *Ostdeutsche Heimatdienst* and put their emphasis on Prussian history, also recalling traditional prejudices against Polish culture and Poland's economical backwardness²⁰.

The Commissioners in the region generally noticed the sympathies of the population for Germany, stressing the pressures of Polish authorities, which managed to present the situation under different terms: they disrupted the railway, telegraphic and telephone system, and created the greatest difficulty with many expedients, for example presenting complaints and establishing an unofficial Masurian Plebiscite Committee. The latter argued that the Masurians were ethnic Poles who had been subjected to a long process of Germanization and protested against the decision thanks to which those who were born in the plebiscite area but were not living there any more could return to vote.

The plebiscites asked all inhabitants older than 20 years of age or those who were born in this area before January 1st 1905, whether they wanted their homeland to remain in East Prussia or become part of Poland. The consultations took place in July 1920, in a season when Poland seemed to have lost any hope for the success in the war against Soviet Russia. German Prussia was able to organize a very successful propaganda campaign and so the plebiscite ended with a majority voting for Prussia. Only a small part of the territory was awarded to Poland, for example the area where the railway Danzig-Warsaw passed, which was renamed Dziąldowo²¹.

²⁰ For the history of Germans outside Weimar Republic, Richard Blanke, *Orphans of Versailles: The Germans in Western Poland, 1918-1939*, Lexington, The University Press of Kentucky, 1993.

²¹ The results in Allenstein (11 July 1920) and Marienwerder (11 July 1920) were with no doubts in favour of Germany (363.159 against 7.924 votes and 96.895 against 7.947 votes) while in the Silesian district, where the solution was finally achieved through an international compromise as the results gave rise to many controversies, German majority was less evident: 707.393 against 479.365. *Annuaire statistique de la République Polonaise, I-ère année 1920/22, Partie II*, Warszawa, Nakładem Głównego Urzędu Statystycznego, 1923.

Besides Allenstein and Marienwerder, another plebiscite had to take place in Upper Silesia, which was a very troublesome region, claimed by Poland, Germany and by Czechoslovakia, whose troops invaded the lands of Cieszyn Silesia in January 1919. Historically, Silesia had been part of Bohemia, of the Habsburg lands and of Prussia, after that Frederick II the Great conquered it in the War of the Austrian Succession (1740-1748). The province of Teschen was disputed by Poland and Czechoslovakia, and it was initially divided in two parts, following as much as possible an ethnic criteria.

On July 28th 1920, at the Spa Conference, Cieszyn Silesia was divided between Poland and the Czech Republic, leaving a sizable Polish minority on the Czech side and dividing the town of Cieszyn between the two States. In the other part of Silesia, things were not easier. Yet in August 1919, a bloody massacre complied by the German border guards (*Grenzschutz*) in the Mysłowice mine, where the Silesian Polish workers revolted against German authorities. Several Polish leaders were arrested and the troops of the Weimar Republic quickly suppressed the uprising. The troubles continued with the strike in the minery centre of Ratibor (Racibórz), at the end of 1919, which was followed by the activity of the Spartakists and by the continuous clashes between Germans and Poles²². In May the Polish authorities forbade the publication and sell of the "Deutsches Zeitung", while in August the Germans burnt the building of the Polish electoral committee in Cosel. The reprisal of the Poles lasted all the night in the city and was even stronger in the surroundings, where they had already replaced German police and kept on attacking the former members of German *Polizei*. A real battle was fought between the villages of Kochłowitz and Bismarckhütte with deaths and hostages, while the troubles continued in September 1920 at Nikolai and Orontowitz²³.

In August 1920, a German newspaper in Upper Silesia printed a false announcement about the fall of Warsaw against the Red Army, provoking the start of celebrations among the German community. Celebrations degenerated into violence which continued even after the discovery of the salvation of Warsaw. Poles reacted with an uprising, which quickly took control of government offices in the districts of Kattowitz, Pless, Beuthen. Between August 20th and 25th, the rebellion spread to Königshütte, Tarnowitz, Rybink, Lublinitz and Gross Strehlitz. The uprising was slowly brought to an end in September, when the Poles obtained the creation of a new police. Also in Silesia, Polish turbulence was noted by the international observers, who followed with apprehension the initiatives of the full-blooded Wojciech Korfanty.

Finally, in March 1921 the Silesian plebiscite was carried out and in the aftermath of the event, while the International Commission was discussing about the interpretation of the results, another uprising

²² Notes sent from the Italian military command in Upper Silesia on 23rd November 1919 and on 28th April 1920, in A.U.S.S.M.E., E3, 219, 1.

²³ Note sent from Cosel on 15th September 1920, in A.U.S.S.M.E., E3, 219, 3.

occurred. Local partisans and forces from Poland took control of over half the area, while the Germans responded with volunteer paramilitary units from all over Germany. In late April 1921, elements on the Polish side announced the third popular uprising, which began on May 2nd–3rd, 1921, with Polish destruction of German rail bridges. Germany could count on some paramilitary groups, the *Freikorps*, which had ostensibly been created to support the German border-protection police (the *Grenzschutz*) and to defend the large estates. After an initial success of the insurgents, who controlled a large portion of the area of Upper Silesia, the German *Grenzschutz* several times resisted the attacks of Polish troops²⁴.

The parts arrived at fighting a real battle in Annaberg and, after the end of hostilities and the intervention of the Allies, a new border was finally drawn dividing the region, which had an outstanding industrial importance. In July, the British troops arrived in Upper Silesia while the Inter-Allied Commission pronounced a general amnesty for the illegal actions committed during the insurrection. A solution was found by turning the question over to the Council of the League of Nations. The appeals issued by both sides, as well as the dispatch of six battalions of Allied troops and the disbandment of the local guards, contributed markedly to the pacification of the district. On the basis of the reports of a League Commission and those of its experts, the Council awarded the greater part of the Upper Silesian industrial district to Poland. Later, the German and Polish Governments, under a League of Nations recommendation, agreed to enforce the protections of minority interests with a special convention concluded in Geneva on May 15th, 1922.

Another territory that was included in the new Poland was the Lithuanian zone of Vilnius, including the city which was occupied by Żeligowski's troops. The latter was considered as a menace to the peace by the international observers, who anyway had to tolerate the occupation of Vilnius and let the question be solved by the elections of January 1922²⁵. The elections were held "in a perfect order" and were won by the Polish Central Committee, which pressed for the independence of Wilno and its simple union with Poland, while the people's councils opted for a federation. The candidates of the Polish Committee signed a special

²⁴ "Groups of irregular soldiers were quartered on the large estates. An officer was attached to each frontier county and charged not only with supervising the active members of the frontier guard but also with keeping the rolls of those men who were to join it in an emergency"; see Hajo Holborn, *A History of Modern Germany*, vol. III, 1840-1945, Princeton, Princeton University Press, 1982, p. 588.

²⁵ Many attempts of reconciliation were managed by the League in 1921, when many critical appreciations were addressed towards Poland: "It is not only the Polish mark but the Polish honor and good name, which have depreciated". Harold William Vazeille Temperley, *Second year of the League. A Study of the Second Assembly of the League of Nations*, London, Hutchinson, 1921, pp. 94, 101-103.

declaration, according to which they promised to limit the work of Wilno's Assembly to the only accomplishment of this union²⁶.

The union of Vilnius to Poland was the last act of troublesome phase, when the Governments of postwar Poland oscillated between the construction of a wide State along the lines of historical Poland and the moderation of a smaller State with a stronger national cohesion. As in many similar cases, the final result was due to the contingency of that particular moment, when diplomatic negotiations were juxtaposed to small or great conflicts, which proved to be as conditioning as the former to draft the new frontiers of Central-Eastern Europe. Consequently, the European empowerment of Wilson's self-determination was destined to be conditioned by a set of different factors, which went side by side with the international diplomacy, but not always coincided with it.

After the end of the First World War, Poland gained more than her independence; Polish troops occupied many disputed territories, and the final result of this process made the State stronger in territorial extension, but weaker in terms of political stability. Interwar Poland became one of the most extended States of the region and gained relevant territories and consistent minorities. According to the dates of 1931, which were collected after the emigrations of many Germans and a decade of assimilationist policies, the Poles represented a percentage of the whole population included between the 68.9% of the Polish-speakers and the 64.8% of the Roman Catholics. The rest of the population was constituted by Ukrainians (13.9% of the total, while 10.4% of the total were Uniates), by Jews (9.8% by religious affiliation), Belarusians (5.3%), Germans and other nationalities as Russians and Lithuanians²⁷.

²⁶ The informations about the elections of Wilno are taken from the report sent by General Romei from Warsaw, on 30th January 1922. A.U.S.S.M.E., F3, 6, 4. Alfonsas Eidintas, Vytautas Zalys, *Lithuania in European Politics. The Years of the First Republic, 1918-1940*, New York, St. Martin's Press, 1998.

²⁷ Piotr Eberhardt, *Ethnic Groups and Population Changes in Twentieth-Century Central-Eastern Europe. History, Data, and Analysis*, Armonk-London, M. E. Sharpe, 2001, p. 113.

SOLUZIONI ALLA CRISI ECONOMICA DEL 1929: I “CENTO GIORNI” DI FRANKLIN DELANO ROOSEVELT

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Abstract

The New Deal represents a change of such magnitude that its ramifications continue to influence American policy. The importance of the New Deal is in being the union of different trends of government in one state. The Roosevelt Revolution is the key to modern American politics; his influence was profound for the use made of the state and that it represented the fusion of four periods of policy development and design of the state. Franklin Delano Roosevelt was a strong president, his power was conditioned by the energetic and determined to public policy. The Roosevelt Revolution was not accomplished in a single year, a hundred, however, were the days that impressed a decisive impact on the economic crisis.

Keywords: *Great Depression, USA, New Deal, Roosevelt*

Il *New Deal* rappresenta un cambiamento di tali dimensioni che le sue ramificazioni continuano a influenzare la politica americana. L'importanza del *New Deal* è nell'essere stato l'unione di diverse tendenze di governo in un unico Stato. La rivoluzione rooseveltiana è la chiave della politica americana moderna, la sua influenza fu profonda per l'uso che essa fece delle istituzioni pubbliche e rappresentò la fusione di quattro periodi di sviluppo politico e di concezione dello Stato. Franklin Delano Roosevelt fu un presidente forte, la sua forza fu condizionata dall'ambiente energico e deciso verso le politiche pubbliche. La rivoluzione rooseveltiana non si compì in un solo anno, cento però furono i giorni che impressero una svolta decisiva alla crisi economica. Roosevelt fu duramente criticato da molti durante la campagna elettorale, ed egli fece ben poco per rassicurare chi lo definiva un politico insicuro. Quel che colpisce, alla luce degli eventi successivi, sono i programmi che egli non menzionò nel 1932: la politica di forte disavanzo di bilancio, il gigantesco programma federale di lavori pubblici, la *National Recovery Administration*, la *Tennessee Valley Authority*, il forte aumento delle imposte dirette sui redditi dei ricchi, i programmi di assistenza pubblica e via a seguire.

I quattro mesi d'intervallo fra l'elezione di Roosevelt, nel novembre 1932, e il suo insediamento nel marzo del 1933 furono i più tormentosi di tutta la Grande Crisi. Il fallimento di cinquemila banche aveva spazzato via nove milioni di libretti di risparmio, i disoccupati erano più di quindici milioni. Una serie di scioperi si susseguirono, vennero organizzate manifestazioni spettacolari come quelle dei contadini, del *Bonus Army* e di disoccupati vari. In tale clima, il

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neoeletto presidente metteva silenziosamente a punto un vasto programma legislativo¹.

Gli uomini del *New Deal* formarono la loro cultura politica attraverso migliaia di libri, un intero patrimonio d'esperienze politiche del passato fu consultato; come gli illuministi seguaci di Montesquieu, i *new dealers* pensavano che la società ideale fosse quella dove nessun elemento abbia una forza preponderante².

Roosevelt passò rapidamente ad affrontare la malattia finanziaria che paralizzava la nazione, ordinò al segretario del Tesoro del primo mandato, Woodin, di redigere un disegno di legge d'emergenza sulle banche, e gli diede meno di cinque giorni per prepararlo. Il pomeriggio del 5 marzo 1933 approvò l'emanazione di due editti presidenziali: il primo convocava il Congresso in sessione speciale per il 9 marzo, l'altro, basato sull'autorità del *Trading with the Enemy Act* del 1917, sospendeva il commercio dell'oro e proclamava una vacanza bancaria nazionale. Il 9 marzo, la sessione si aprì con le misure d'emergenza, che consistevano nell'estendere l'assistenza governativa ai banchieri privati e autorizzavano l'immissione di nuove banconote della *Federal Reserve*; con voto unanime la Camera approvò il disegno di legge. L'attività dei "cento giorni" era dunque iniziata; seguirono i provvedimenti sulle economie e l'invito del neopresidente a porre fine al proibizionismo.

Il proibizionismo, con particolare riferimento al periodo 1919-1933, fu costituito da un insieme di provvedimenti che vietarono la produzione, la vendita e il trasporto degli alcolici in tutti gli Stati della Federazione. Roosevelt, il 22 marzo 1933, firmò la legge e le fabbriche di birra riattivarono la loro produzione; il 7 aprile, per la prima volta dal 1919, la bevanda fu venduta legalmente in America. Roosevelt, in due sole settimane, attraverso i primi provvedimenti, aveva cambiato lo spirito americano, meno depresso che mai.

Un altro punto di estrema importanza delle politiche del nuovo presidente degli Stati Uniti d'America fu la disoccupazione, Roosevelt, per riuscire a prevenirla voleva creare un esercito forestale, un programma di lavori pubblici e di sovvenzioni federali agli Stati per l'assistenza sociale. Il numero dei disoccupati era spaventoso: quindici milioni di individui. Il Congresso impiegò solo otto giorni per creare il *Civilian Conservation Corp.* Infine il presidente condusse in porto il terzo punto del suo programma assistenziale, i lavori pubblici, con il *National Industrial Recovery Act*.

Il Congresso, in giugno, approvò la legge per la concessione dei mutui ai proprietari di case, *Home Owener's Loan Act* (HOLC), che finì con il finanziare un quinto di tutti gli alloggi privati urbani soggetti a ipoteca. Il presidente Roosevelt, il 10 aprile, chiese al Congresso di creare la *Tennessee Valley Authority*, che aveva il compito di costruire

¹ Theodore J. Lowi, *The End of Liberalism. Ideology, Policy, and the Crisis of Public Authority*, New York, Norton, 1969.

² Idem, *La scienza delle politiche*, Bologna, il Mulino, 1999.

dighe che servissero da laghi serbatoi, per impedire inondazioni e nello stesso tempo produrre energia elettrica a buon mercato. La Camera approvò il disegno di legge, a maggio, invece, Roosevelt poté presentare al Congresso un progetto omnibus che conteneva qualcosa per tutte le categorie economiche, gli imprenditori erano autorizzati a *codici d'intese* senza ricorrere a leggi antitrust, la Camera approvò la legge mentre al Senato seguì un iter un po' più faticoso. Il Congresso, quando si aggiornò il 16 giugno, cento giorni dopo l'apertura della sessione speciale, aveva scritto nella legislazione USA la più straordinaria pagina di riforme della storia nazionale³.

Il programma federale di natura sociale ed economica attuato da Roosevelt, inteso a fronteggiare gli effetti della grande depressione, istituì numerosi organismi e agenzie federali, soprattutto durante i "cento giorni", per creare nuovi posti di lavoro e regolare l'economia⁴. Roosevelt aveva alimentato la collaborazione fra Governo e iniziativa privata, aveva promesso di distribuire somme fantastiche agli agricoltori, si era assunto la responsabilità di assistere milioni di disoccupati, aveva stanziato miliardi di dollari per salvare dalla vendita all'asta le grandi fattorie, aveva dato il via a una politica di grandi lavori pubblici e infine aveva ridotto Wall Street sotto il controllo federale. Il neopresidente Franklin Delano Roosevelt aveva visto andare in porto quindici leggi storiche, la nazione finalmente aveva trovato un capo.

Il compito più importante del *New Deal*, durante l'estate del 1933, fu quello di negoziare con le principali industrie i codici previsti dalla legge sulla rinascita industriale. Il presidente, nel mese di agosto, aveva in mano l'adesione di metà delle dieci grandi industrie, quella cantieristica, laniera, elettrica, dell'abbigliamento e cotoniera. Successivamente, Roosevelt convinse l'industria petrolifera, siderurgica e quella del legname; il 27 agosto 1933, anche tutti i magnati dell'industria automobilistica, a eccezione di Henry Ford, arrivarono a un'intesa con l'amministrazione. In settembre, anche i produttori di carbone si allinearono e Johnson aveva guadagnato nella *NRA*, in tre mesi, tutte le principali grandi industrie. All'inizio la *NRA* aveva tutti contro, e i repubblicani progressisti la denunciavano come uno strumento d'oppressione sulle piccole imprese; lo stesso presidente Roosevelt dovette successivamente riconoscere che molti meccanismi non funzionavano bene nella nuova agenzia da lui creata. Ma essa ebbe anche dei meriti, soprattutto se si tiene conto di quanti posti di lavoro creò, offrendo a circa due milioni di lavoratori un impiego; fece invece poco per accelerare la ripresa, e soprattutto gli interessi delle grandi compagnie finirono con il prevalere sull'interesse pubblico. Ma la vera debolezza del primo *New Deal* consisteva nella mancanza di una strategia diretta a elevare il potere d'acquisto dei

³ Cfr. Arthur M. Schlesinger jr., *L'età di Roosevelt*, Bologna, il Mulino, 1980.

⁴ Cfr. James MacGregor Burns, *Roosevelt. The Lion and the Fox*, New York, Harcourt, 1956.

cittadini e a stimolare gli investimenti. Il *new dealer* Jones, nell'ottobre del 1933, creò la *Commodity Credit Corporation*, con il compito di concedere prestiti a quegli agricoltori che avessero accettato, anno dopo anno, di escludere una parte del suolo per la produzione. Grazie anche alla creazione dell'*Agricultural Adjustment Administration*, il programma agricolo di Roosevelt diede buoni risultati.

Il primo *New Deal*, nel 1934, iniziava ad assumere una precisa fisionomia; il principale obiettivo era quello di rappresentare tutte le classi e i vari gruppi sociali. Il presidente Roosevelt aveva scelto i suoi collaboratori in modo da incorporare nel governo una vasta gamma di idee e concezioni: il vicesegretario dell'Agricoltura, Rexford Guy Tugwell, propugnava per esempio forti spese governative per i lavori pubblici e l'assistenza sociale, mentre il direttore del bilancio Douglas era invece contrario a forti spese pubbliche. L'unica stonatura del primo *New Deal* fu l'ira di Roosevelt contro i banchieri, tuttavia inevitabile se si voleva disciplinare le attività finanziarie.

Nella primavera del 1934, gli Stati Uniti si erano ormai sollevati dalla grave recessione dell'autunno dell'anno precedente, ma sino alla primavera del 1935 il Paese rimase all'ancora, e soprattutto i disoccupati erano ancora diversi milioni. Il 12 maggio 1933, il Congresso approvò uno stanziamento di mezzo miliardo di dollari per l'assistenza sociale⁵. Roosevelt annunciò di avere scelto, come direttore della *Federal Emergency Relief Administration*, l'assistente sociale Harry Hopkins. Questi creò in seguito la *Civil Work Administration*, che aveva il compito di arruolare i disoccupati per svolgere lavori pubblici di vario genere. Hopkins diede lavoro a 4.230.000 disoccupati e consentì alla nazione di superare il duro inverno⁶.

Il presidente Roosevelt, tornata la primavera, sciolse, allarmato dagli ingenti costi, la CWA, così l'onere dell'assistenza sociale tornò a ricadere sulla *FERA*. Questa istituzione finanziò cinquemila edifici pubblici, costruì settemila ponti, ripulì torrenti, dragò fiumi, insegnò a leggere e a scrivere a un milione e mezzo di adulti, aiutò molti studenti a frequentare l'università. Nel 1935, Roosevelt propose un nuovo, gigantesco programma per l'occupazione pubblica, poiché un terzo della popolazione viveva ancora tramite sussidi⁷. Il programma prevedeva lavoro per tre milioni di persone; la WPA costruì 2.500 ospedali, 6.000 edifici scolastici, 1.000 aeroporti e circa 13.000 campi di gioco. Il *Federal Theatre Project* della WPA impiegò registi, attori e tecnici per allestire varie commedie. La *National Youth Administration*, un altro ente, si proponeva di aiutare milioni di giovani americani. La

⁵ Cfr. D. R. Mayhew, *Congress: The Electoral Connection*, New Haven, Yale University Press, 1974.

⁶ Cfr. Michael E. Parrish, *L'età dell'ansia. Gli Stati Uniti dal 1920 al 1941*, Bologna, il Mulino, 1986.

⁷ Cfr. William E. Leuchtenburg, *Roosevelt e il New Deal, 1932-1940*, Bari, Laterza, 1968.

WPA, tuttavia per quanti sforzi furono fatti, non riuscì mai a offrire un impiego a tutti coloro che erano in grado di lavorare.

Il 15 agosto 1935, il Senato approvò il disegno di legge in materia di sicurezza sociale, il *Social Security Act*, che creò un sistema nazionale di previdenza per la vecchiaia, obbligatorio per la maggior parte dei lavoratori. La legge garantì anche un conguaglio federale agli Stati per l'assistenza alle madri e ai bambini, agli invalidi e ai ciechi, nonché per i servizi della sanità pubblica. Questo provvedimento, però, provocò ingenti danni economici e molte categorie ne furono escluse; pur così, rappresentò una pietra miliare nella storia politica americana⁸.

In base al *National Housing Act* del 1934, un nuovo ente, la *Federal Housing Administration*, garantì inoltre, prestiti a famiglie di medio reddito perché potessero riparare o modernizzare le loro abitazioni e costruirne di nuove. Durante il *New Deal* furono costruite circa un migliaio di comunità, per lo più colonie agricole; inoltre, in base al *Farm Tenancy Act* del 1937, un nuovo ente, la *Farm Security Administration*, sostituì la RA concedendo agli agricoltori prestiti per il risanamento agricolo. La rivoluzione rooseveltiana⁹ non si compì in un solo anno. Le proposte più efficaci furono quelle nel campo dell'agricoltura, laddove i compiti dell'*Agricultural Adjustment Administration* erano di natura regolatoria. Ci fu anche il *Security Act* e il *Glass-Steagall Banking Bill*, che separò le attività bancarie d'investimento da quelle commerciali. Con queste iniziative, tutte concentrate in un breve periodo, era inevitabile che differissero le interpretazioni circa il senso del "nuovo corso".

Roosevelt fu, al tempo stesso, il salvatore del capitalismo e il suo più importante nemico. Molti sono tentati di definire il *New Deal* uno Stato mediatore, ma si sentono in contraddizione nel momento stesso in cui utilizzano questo termine. William Leuchtenburg, ad esempio, autore politicamente avveduto, propone per molto tempo questa nozione, per poi esprimere serie riserve, suggerendo che il presidente Roosevelt avrebbe desiderato guidare un governo aperto alle diverse forze sociali, e che questo desiderio si scontrò con il fatto che egli, volente o nolente, fu un agente di forze riformatrici che il mondo degli affari considerava inaccettabile¹⁰. La grande influenza dell'ideologia del liberalismo dei gruppi d'interesse si può scorgere facilmente nel gran numero di provvedimenti approvati, durante e dopo i "cento giorni", che esprimono diversi e nobili sentimenti. Politiche pubbliche senza regolamentazioni sono il principio comportamentale del liberalismo europeo, la loro grande influenza sul processo legislativo è il motivo principale cui il sistema politico americano è oggi poco ricettivo nei confronti delle attività più importanti. Così Roosevelt fu

⁸ Cfr. Sergio Fabbrini, *Il presidenzialismo degli Stati Uniti*, Bari, Laterza, 1993.

⁹ Cfr. James MacGregor Burns, *op. cit.*

¹⁰ Cfr. William E. Leuchtenburg, *op. cit.*

davvero un presidente forte, seppure giocò un ruolo di mediatore e rinunciò a una quota consistente di potere governativo e presidenziale¹¹.

¹¹ Cfr. Furio Colombo, *America e libertà: da Alexis De Tocqueville a George W. Bush*, Milano, Baldini Castoldi Dalai, 2005.

LA NEUTRALITÀ JUGOSLAVA NELLE RELAZIONI DEL SERVIZIO INFORMAZIONI MILITARE ITALIANO (1939-1941)

Alberto Becherelli*

Abstract

In 1939-1941, the Third Reich was at its peak and temporarily allied with Soviet Union. At the beginning of World War II, Yugoslavia remained neutral but Hungary, Romania and Bulgaria were forced to join the Tripartite Pact and pressure on Belgrade's Government became irresistible, while Italy had already occupied Albania and was fighting in Greece. After several months of German pressure, Yugoslavia finally signed, on March 25th, 1941, the Tripartite Pact but a group of pro-British officers made a coup and on April 6th the Axis Powers invaded Yugoslavia. The Italian Military Intelligence Service provided a valuable record of the period in question allowing detailed analysis.

Keywords: World War II, Yugoslav Neutrality, 1939-1941, Tripartite Pact, Italian Military Intelligence Service

Il 1° settembre 1939 Hitler avviò l'invasione della Polonia e Francia e Gran Bretagna dichiararono guerra alla Germania: iniziava così il secondo conflitto mondiale. La sopravvivenza della Jugoslavia dipendeva ora dai suoi rapporti con i due vicini, l'Italia e la Germania, confinante con il regno dei Karadjordjević dopo l'*Anschluss*. La questione fondamentale che si poneva agli Stati danubiano-balcanici era la posizione da assumere nei confronti del conflitto. Berlino contava sulla loro neutralità, che li avrebbe di fatto allineati agli interessi politici ed economici tedeschi senza assumere posizioni apertamente antibritanniche e antifrancesi¹. L'Europa sud-orientale rappresentava per la Germania una preziosa riserva di materie prime e di risorse indispensabili alla vittoria: qualsiasi mutamento dello *status quo* nell'area avrebbe messo a rischio un settore essenziale, danneggiando per di più le relazioni con l'Unione Sovietica. L'intenzione di Berlino era monopolizzare il commercio di esportazione jugoslavo, ma Belgrado tentava di opporsi mirando all'industrializzazione dello Stato, in particolare nella produzione bellica. Sicuramente per tale ragione i notabili jugoslavi apparivano assai meno preoccupati di quanto si credesse dell'influenza russa che si andava profilando nei Balcani: tra i due mali, a quello tedesco era preferito il russo².

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¹ Per la ricostruzione delle dinamiche interne e del quadro politico internazionale nel quale maturò la politica di neutralità jugoslava nei primi due anni della Seconda guerra mondiale si veda Alfredo Breccia, *Jugoslavia 1939-1941. Diplomazia della neutralità*, Milano, Giuffrè, 1978. Sul Servizio Informazioni Militare (S.I.M.) durante il conflitto si veda Carlo De Risio, *Generali, servizi segreti e fascismo. La guerra nella guerra 1940-1943*, Milano, Mondadori, 1978; Giuseppe Conti, *Una guerra segreta. Il SIM nel secondo conflitto mondiale*, Bologna, il Mulino, 2009.

² Archivio dell'Ufficio Storico dello Stato Maggiore dell'Esercito, (A.U.S.S.M.E.), fondo I-4, Carteggio Stato Maggiore Generale – Comando Supremo – Stato Maggiore Difesa, anni 1924-1948, b. 6, fasc. 5, Ufficio di S.E. il Capo di Stato Maggiore Generale, *Promemoria per S.E. il*

L'Italia avrebbe approfittato di un collasso jugoslavo ma era da escludersi una sua azione di forza diretta, poiché avrebbe assorbito un tal numero di forze che, ove il collasso jugoslavo non fosse stato completo e repentino, avrebbe complicato anche la semplice sorveglianza della frontiera occidentale³. Bisognava attendere l'evoluzione degli eventi, sperando in rivolgimenti favorevoli, mentre la Jugoslavia, nonostante le dichiarazioni di serenità, intensificava i richiami alle armi e avviava una vera e propria mobilitazione⁴. Le voci di un'azione più o meno imminente delle potenze dell'Asse circolavano infatti comunemente nel Paese, accolte con malcelata rassegnazione dalla popolazione, mentre l'ambiente militare serbo sembrava deciso a difendere l'integrità statale⁵. Il timore era relativo a una prossima occupazione della Slovenia e della Dalmazia, ma non mancavano allarmi di un'azione italiana contro la Grecia⁶. Le autorità jugoslave aumentarono il richiamo di riservisti, accelerarono la preparazione dell'aviazione e disposero l'allontanamento dal confine degli oriundi istriani e degli italiani espatriati per motivi politici e residenti in Jugoslavia⁷. Le alte sfere jugoslave ufficialmente si mantenevano riservate: in varie manifestazioni e negli articoli dei più importanti giornali, era posta all'ordine del giorno la necessità di riorganizzare lo Stato su base corporativa e di riesaminare a fondo la stessa costituzione. La *leadership* di Belgrado era alla ricerca di una formula per l'organizzazione sociale dello Stato con indirizzo totalitario, quale estremo tentativo di riorganizzare il pericolante edificio statale su più solide basi e conquistare le simpatie dell'Asse; l'orientamento del governo jugoslavo per l'applicazione della riforma incontrava tuttavia l'opposizione crescente delle classi popolari⁸.

Capo di Stato Maggiore Generale, oggetto: Informazioni sulla Jugoslavia, Roma, 13 ottobre 1939-XVII.

³ Antonello Biagini, Fernando Frattolillo (a cura di), *Verbali delle Riunioni tenute dal Capo di S.M. Generale, vol. I (26 gennaio 1939-29 dicembre 1940)*, Roma, Stato Maggiore dell'Esercito – Ufficio Storico, 1983, verbale n. 3, seduta del 9 aprile 1940-XVIII, *Norme strategiche emanate dal Duce*, Ufficio del Capo di Stato Maggiore Generale, presieduta dall'Eccellenza il Capo di Stato Maggiore Generale, p. 33.

⁴ A.U.S.S.M.E., fondo H-3, Servizio Informazioni Militari – Notiziari Stati Esteri – Bollettini – 2^a Guerra Mondiale, b. 59, fasc. 2, Jugoslavia notizie situazione militare 1940, Ministero della Guerra, S.I.M., al Comando del Corpo di Stato Maggiore-Ufficio Operazioni I, prot. n. z/38485, oggetto: *Jugoslavia-situazione militare*, f.to Generale di Brigata Capo Servizio G. Carboni, Roma, 1° maggio 1940-XVIII.

⁵ *Ibidem*, b. 80, fasc. 1, Informazioni sulla Jugoslavia (1940), Comando Gruppo Armate-Ufficio Informazioni, Jugoslavia, Informazioni della 2^a Armata, Situazione descrittiva settimanale, Comando della 2^a Armata-Ufficio I, *Situazione descrittiva d'oltre confine n. 22*, Deduzioni, 23 luglio 1940-XVIII.

⁶ Antonello Biagini, Fernando Frattolillo (a cura di), *Diario Storico del Comando Supremo, Vol. I (11.6.1940 – 31.8.1940)*, Tomo I, *Diario*, Roma, Stato Maggiore Esercito – Ufficio Storico, 1986, II – *Comunicazioni e richieste dei comandi dipendenti*, f.to il Generale Addetto Q. Armellini, 2 agosto 1940, p. 307; II – *Comunicazioni e richieste dei comandi dipendenti*, b) Jugoslavia, f.to il Generale Addetto Q. Armellini, 7 agosto 1940, pp. 339-340.

⁷ A.U.S.S.M.E., H-3, b. 80, fasc. 1, Comando Gruppo Armate-Ufficio Informazioni, Jugoslavia, Informazioni della 2^a Armata, Situazione descrittiva settimanale, Comando della 2^a Armata-Ufficio I, *Notiziario giornaliero d'oltre confine n. 57*, Varie, Gorizia, 9 agosto 1940-XVIII; *Situazione descrittiva d'oltre confine n. 26*, Sintesi, 20 agosto 1940-XVIII.

⁸ *Ibidem*, b. 60, fasc. 4, Carteggio del Servizio Informazioni Militari (S.I.M.) relativo ai vari Stati, Jugoslavia, *Stralcio bollettino situazione settimanale n. 140*, Jugoslavia, 18 luglio 1940.

L'attesa dei risultati dell'intesa in corso tra le potenze dell'Asse e Ungheria, Romania e Bulgaria, era febbrile: negli accordi che andavano maturando si intravedeva la creazione di una barriera che, posta tra Unione Sovietica e Jugoslavia, avrebbe reso difficile col conseguente isolamento l'aiuto sovietico sul quale andava contando parte dell'opinione pubblica e i comunisti jugoslavi⁹. La propaganda di questi ultimi, che assumeva spesso toni panslavisti, era aumentata dopo l'acquisizione sovietica della Bucovina e della Bessarabia e andava diffondendosi anche tra le forze armate¹⁰. L'attività comunista faceva proseliti anche tra i nazionalisti, che nell'avvicinamento all'Unione Sovietica vedevano la possibilità di conservare l'integrità del territorio jugoslavo¹¹.

Crebbero le dimostrazioni antiitaliane e soprattutto nei dintorni di Zara la popolazione slava si abbandonò ad aperte manifestazioni di ostilità¹². Formazioni irregolari e volontarie andavano formandosi in tutta la Jugoslavia, e anche se il reclutamento avveniva principalmente nel Kosovo e nel Dibrano, il fenomeno del volontarismo andava diffondendosi anche tra la popolazione croata del litorale, mentre l'immissione di *četnici* nelle forze armate jugoslave era stata ufficialmente sanzionata e intorno al nucleo fondamentale, rappresentato dai reduci, si andava raggruppando un buon numero di volontari, nella quasi totalità serbi¹³.

Intanto in Croazia gli *ustaša* del separatista croato Ante Pavelić (in esilio in Italia) erano strettamente sorvegliati, arrestati e tradotti a Belgrado per il minimo motivo¹⁴. A luglio a Sušak una manifestazione in favore di Pavelić e dell'indipendenza croata, che aveva visto la partecipazione di circa cinquecento persone, si era conclusa con l'intervento della gendarmeria e numerosi arresti¹⁵. Il movimento separatista continuava l'attiva propaganda antigovernativa facendo circolare insistentemente la notizia di un imminente

⁹ *Ibidem*, b. 80, fasc. 1, Comando della 2^a Armata-Ufficio I, *Situazione descrittiva d'oltre confine n. 23*, Sintesi, Premessa, 30 luglio 1940-XVIII.

¹⁰ *Ibidem*, b. 60, fasc. 4, *Stralcio bollettino situazione settimanale n. 140*, Jugoslavia, 18 luglio 1940.

¹¹ *Ibidem*, *Jugoslavia*, Roma, 10 luglio 1940-XVIII.

¹² *Ibidem*, b. 59, fasc. 2, Carteggio del Servizio Informazioni Militari (S.I.M.) relativo ai vari Stati, Jugoslavia, Ministero della Guerra, Gabinetto, P.N.F., *Zara: mattinale novità Situazione Jugoslavia*, Appunto per il Duce, Roma, 19 maggio 1940-XVIII.

¹³ *Ibidem*, Ministero della Guerra, S.I.M., prot. n. Z/314894, oggetto: *Jugoslavia-Attività di formazioni irregolari e volontaristiche*, al Comando del Corpo di S.M.-Ufficio Operazioni, f.to il Generale di Div. Capo Servizio G. Carboni, Roma, 21 giugno 1940-XVIII. *Četnik*, al plurale *četnici*, significa propriamente "guerrigliero", dal termine *četa*, "compagnia" o "banda", denominazione attribuita alle formazioni irregolari serbe che sotto il dominio dell'Impero ottomano avevano mantenuto viva la resistenza contro i turchi; nel periodo fra le due guerre con tale appellativo venivano chiamate anche le associazioni di veterani usate da Belgrado come forza di polizia ausiliaria nelle regioni in cui l'elemento serbo era minoritario. Il termine, diventato sinonimo di "nazionalista serbo", è stato abbondantemente utilizzato durante la Seconda guerra mondiale e nel disfacimento jugoslavo degli anni Novanta.

¹⁴ L'Organizzazione Rivoluzionaria Croata Ribelle (*Ustaša Hrvatska Revolucionarna Organizacija*, U.H.R.O.), più semplicemente nota come movimento *ustaša* ("ribelle", "insorto", dal verbo *ustati*, "insorgere", "alzarsi") si proponeva come fini, da perseguire con la lotta armata, l'insurrezione della Croazia e la sua erezione a Stato indipendente.

¹⁵ A.U.S.S.M.E., H-3, b. 60, fasc. 4, Carteggio del Servizio Informazioni Militari (S.I.M.) relativo ai vari Stati, Jugoslavia, *Jugoslavia*, Roma, 20 luglio 1940-XVIII.

attacco italiano in suo supporto¹⁶. Gli eventi confermavano le ripercussioni politiche ed economiche delle eccezionali misure militari adottate dallo Stato jugoslavo, che non avevano tra l'altro attenuato il malcontento diffuso tra i soldati croati e sloveni, dovuto alla lunga durata dei richiami, al pessimo trattamento da parte degli ufficiali serbi, al vitto insufficiente e ai ritardi nei pagamenti¹⁷. Reggimenti costituiti da croati erano rinforzati da elementi serbi e da soldati bosniaci e lo stesso avveniva per alcuni reparti di gendarmeria operanti alla frontiera¹⁸, anche se, peraltro, sintomi di insofferenza andavano crescendo anche tra i bosniaci musulmani in correlazione al riaccendersi della propaganda autonomista per la Bosnia musulmana guidata dall'Organizzazione musulmana jugoslava (*Jugoslavenska Muslimanska Organizacija*, JMO)¹⁹. Per eliminare la possibilità di insurrezioni nelle zone abitate da albanesi il governo jugoslavo aveva accentuato il richiamo dei soggetti validi allontanandoli dal Kosovo per avviarli verso la frontiera ungherese e bulgara (viceversa l'elemento serbo di immigrazione ne era stato largamente dispensato)²⁰.

Andavano infine consolidandosi le milizie organizzate dal Partito Contadino Croato (*Hrvatska Pučka Seljačka Stranka*, HPSS), la "Protezione contadina croata" (*Hrvatska Seljačka Zaštita*), guardia armata formata da volontari inquadrati militarmente²¹. A luglio Vladko Maček, *leader* del partito, ispezionò la "Protezione contadina croata" accompagnato dagli addetti stampa dei consolati tedesco, russo e bulgaro a Zagabria.²² A ottobre la milizia contava già 180.000 iscritti tra i sostenitori del partito: l'utilizzo delle formazioni era previsto in caso di gravi circostanze, al fine di sopperire alle impossibilità della forza pubblica²³.

Con l'accordo serbo-croato (*Sporazum*) dell'agosto 1939 e la concessione dell'autonomia amministrativa ai croati, lo Stato jugoslavo sembrava aver assunto sempre più un carattere federativo; in Croazia, tuttavia, il concetto di autonomia tendeva definitivamente a evolversi verso l'aspirazione all'assoluta indipendenza²⁴. I dissidi continuarono con le riforme politico-sociali a carattere corporativo inaugurate dal governo e fortemente ostacolate dai croati, che considerarono i provvedimenti un espediente per privare la

¹⁶ *Ibidem*, *Stralcio della situazione settimanale del S.I.M. n. 142*, 1° agosto 1940-XVIII, Jugoslavia.

¹⁷ *Ibidem*, *Jugoslavia*, Roma, 30 luglio 1940-XVIII.

¹⁸ *Ibidem*, *Jugoslavia*, Roma, 12 luglio 1940-XVIII.

¹⁹ *Ibidem*, Ministero della Guerra, S.I.M., *Notiziario giornaliero*, Jugoslavia, Roma, 4 settembre 1940-XVIII; b. 80, fasc. 1, Informazioni sulla Jugoslavia (1940), Comando Gruppo Armate-Ufficio Informazioni, Jugoslavia, Informazioni della 2ª Armata, Situazione descrittiva settimanale, Comando della 2ª Armata-Ufficio I, *Situazione descrittiva d'oltre confine n. 23*, Sintesi, Premessa, 30 luglio 1940-XVIII.

²⁰ *Ibidem*, b. 60, fasc. 4, *Stralcio notiziario informazioni del S.I.M. n. 147*, Parte III, gli Stati danubiani e balcanici, 1° - Jugoslavia (s. d.).

²¹ *Ibidem*, *Jugoslavia*, Roma, 18 luglio 1940-XVIII.

²² *Ibidem*, *Jugoslavia*, Roma, 27 luglio 1940-XVIII.

²³ *Ibidem*, b. 80, fasc. 1, Comando Gruppo Armate-Ufficio Informazioni, Informazioni della 2ª Armata, notiziario giornaliero 1940, *Situazione descrittiva d'oltre confine n. 36*, Elementi informativi, *Organizzazioni paramilitari: Protezione contadina croata*, 30 ottobre 1940-XVIII.

²⁴ *Ibidem*, *Stralcio notiziario settimanale del S.I.M.*, 25 luglio 1940.

Banovina Hrvatska della propria autonomia amministrativa²⁵. Il 25 e 26 agosto 1940, in occasione della ricorrenza dello *Sporazum*, il Consiglio dei ministri jugoslavo si riunì a Zagabria dando particolare solennità e rilievo all'evento, ma la riunione dimostrò tutta la debolezza della dirigenza serba dinanzi alla persistente volontà separatista dei croati, e il governo fu costretto a rimandare a un secondo momento l'approvazione del testo di legge sulla riforma sociale e del lavoro, anticipando comunque la garanzia dell'estraneità della Croazia ai provvedimenti e riaffermandone in pieno l'autonomia²⁶.

Contemporaneamente in Italia venivano fornite le direttive per il perfezionamento dell'operazione contro la Jugoslavia (8 agosto). Mussolini stabilì l'inizio dell'offensiva per il 20 settembre e ordinò di prendere contatto con lo Stato Maggiore di Germania e Ungheria onde accertare la disponibilità ad attuare l'operazione con il concorso di truppe tedesche e ungheresi²⁷. I generali tedeschi tuttavia comunicavano allo Stato Maggiore Generale italiano la contrarietà di Hitler a effettuare operazioni militari nei Balcani, onde evitare di perturbare l'area da cui la Germania traeva materie prime fondamentali all'esito del conflitto e scongiurare il pericolo che l'Inghilterra ne approfittasse per crearsi basi aeree in Jugoslavia²⁸. Arrivava dunque il veto tedesco all'attuazione del piano italiano e Mussolini lasciò da parte per il momento lo scacchiere balcanico, allineandosi agli interessi tedeschi per il mantenimento della stabilità nell'area²⁹.

Si accentuò la sensazione di isolamento della Jugoslavia, nonostante il governo di Belgrado ostentasse un atteggiamento di assoluta neutralità sia nei riguardi dell'agitazione italo-greca, sia in merito alle trattative ungaro-romene nell'ambito del secondo arbitrato di Vienna per la rassegnazione all'Ungheria

²⁵ *Ibidem*, Comando Gruppo Armate-Ufficio Informazioni, Jugoslavia, Informazioni della 2^a Armata, Situazione descrittiva settimanale, Comando della 2^a Armata-Ufficio I, *Situazione descrittiva d'oltre confine n. 26*, Sintesi, 20 agosto 1940-XVIII.

²⁶ *Ibidem*, Comando della 2^a Armata-Ufficio I, *Stralcio stampa jugoslava*, 20 agosto 1940-XVIII; *Stralcio stampa jugoslava*, 27 agosto 1940-XVIII.

²⁷ Antonello Biagini, Fernando Frattolillo, *Diario Storico del Comando Supremo...*, Vol. I, Tomo I, II – *Comunicazioni e richieste dei comandi dipendenti*, Jugoslavia, f.to il Generale Addetto Q. Armellini, 2 e 7 agosto 1940, pp. 307 e 339-340; III – *Direttive ed ordini dati*, f.to il Generale Addetto Q. Armellini, 8 agosto 1940, p. 343; X – *Note personali dell'Eccellenza il Capo di S.M. Generale*, f.to il Capo di Stato Maggiore Generale P. Badoglio, 11 agosto 1940, p. 361.

²⁸ *Ibidem*, V – *Attività informativa*, f.to il Generale Addetto Q. Armellini, 15 agosto 1940, p. 382; X – *Note personali dell'Eccellenza il Capo di S.M. Generale*, f.to il Capo di Stato Maggiore Generale P. Badoglio, 20 agosto 1940, p. 411; IX – *Note dell'Eccellenza il Capo di S.M. Generale*, f.to il Capo di Stato Maggiore Generale P. Badoglio, 21 agosto 1940, p. 416.

²⁹ *Documenti Diplomatici Italiani (D.D.I.)*, Nona serie, 1939-1943, vol. V, doc. 431, *L'Ambasciatore a Berlino, Alfieri, al Ministro degli Esteri, Ciano*, Berlino, 17 agosto 1940, pp. 414-415; doc. 435, *Il Ministro degli Esteri, Ciano, all'Ambasciatore a Berlino, Alfieri*, Roma, 17 agosto 1940, pp. 418-419; doc. 467, *Il Capo del Governo, Mussolini, Appunto segreto*, Roma, 22 agosto 1940, pp. 452-453; doc. 484, *Il Capo del Governo, Mussolini, al Cancelliere del Reich, Hitler*, Roma, 24 agosto 1940, pp. 469-470; doc. 506, *L'Ambasciatore a Berlino, Alfieri, al Ministro degli Esteri, Ciano*, Berlino, 27 agosto 1940, pp. 490-491. Si veda anche: Giorgio Perich, *Mussolini nei Balcani*, Milano, Longanesi, 1966, pp. 13-15; Alfredo Breccia, *op. cit.*, pp. 306-325.

della Transilvania del nord³⁰. Proprio in conseguenza degli incidenti con la Grecia la diffidenza nei riguardi dell'Italia era cresciuta e alla frontiera italo-jugoslava fu intensificata la vigilanza con particolari misure restrittive per la disciplina del transito di persone attraverso i valichi di confine³¹. Anche la lenta ma graduale soggezione della Romania alla Germania destò viva preoccupazione e portò ai lavori di fortificazione sulla frontiera romena³².

Il partito comunista jugoslavo, con un discreto seguito tra i contadini della Croazia e della Bosnia-Erzegovina, diede vita a nuove proteste per il crescente carovita e agitazioni di piazza in diverse località: Zagabria, Belgrado, Mostar, Spalato. In quest'ultima l'intervento della polizia aveva provocato morti e feriti e numerosi arresti. Anche nell'ambito militare una sempre maggiore insofferenza caratterizzava sloveni e croati nei confronti degli ufficiali serbi, mentre gli ambienti governativi jugoslavi apparivano turbati sia dai progressi che andava facendo il movimento *ustaša* di Pavelić, sia dalla tendenza germanofila del partito contadino di Maček. In campo economico le requisizioni e le esportazioni in contropartita di forniture belliche pesavano sempre più sulle scorte alimentari, compromettendone la regolare distribuzione, mentre la produzione industriale e i mercati interni vivevano una crisi quasi totale. Il governo jugoslavo cercava di calmare l'opinione pubblica esasperata dall'aumento dei prezzi verificatosi tra il luglio e l'agosto del 1940 e la mancanza di generi di prima necessità. Le dimostrazioni e gli scioperi si allargarono rapidamente anche ai centri di Maribor, Sebenico, Sarajevo e Lubiana³³.

Negli ambienti responsabili di Belgrado la possibilità che la controversia italo-greca potesse sfociare in un atto di forza delle potenze dell'Asse destava viva inquietudine e si andava precisando la tendenza a una soluzione di compromesso con i croati di Maček. La situazione era stata oggetto d'esame a Belgrado in un incontro tra il reggente Pavle e il *leader* del partito contadino, che tornato a Zagabria aveva riunito i senatori e i deputati croati. Era inoltre da rilevare ancora la campagna antiserba condotta dagli *ustaša*, la cui attività continuava però a essere sorvegliata, contenuta e repressa³⁴.

³⁰ A.U.S.S.M.E., H-3, b. 80, fasc. 1, Comando Gruppo Armate-Ufficio Informazioni, Jugoslavia, Informazioni della 2ª Armata, Situazione descrittiva settimanale, Comando della 2ª Armata-Ufficio I, *Situazione descrittiva d'oltre confine n. 27*, Sintesi, 27 agosto 1940-XVIII.

³¹ *Ibidem*, b. 67, fasc. 4, Informazioni sulla frontiera jugoslava (1940), Ministero della Guerra-Gabinetto, allo Stato Maggiore R. Esercito, prot. n. 144628, oggetto: *Attività terroristica alla frontiera orientale*, f.to il Sottosegretario di Stato Soddu, Roma, 23 settembre 1940-XVIII.

³² *Ibidem*, b. 80, fasc. 1, Comando Gruppo Armate-Ufficio Informazioni, Jugoslavia, Informazioni della 2ª Armata, Situazione descrittiva settimanale, Comando della 2ª Armata-Ufficio I, *Situazione descrittiva d'oltre confine n. 31*, Sintesi, 24 settembre 1940-XVIII.

³³ *Ibidem*, *Situazione descrittiva d'oltre confine n. 29*, Situazione morale e politica (dalla stampa), 10 settembre 1940-XVIII; *Situazione descrittiva d'oltre confine n. 30*, 17 settembre 1940-XVIII; *Situazione descrittiva d'oltre confine n. 31*, Sintesi, 24 settembre 1940-XVIII. Le notizie sulle agitazioni a sfondo comunista sono riportate anche in b. 60, fasc. 4, *Stralcio notiziario informazioni del S.I.M. n. 147*, Parte III, gli Stati danubiani e balcanici, 1°-Jugoslavia (s.d.); *Stralcio della situazione settimanale del S.I.M. n. 148*, Parte III, gli Stati danubiani e balcanici, 1°- Jugoslavia (s.d.).

³⁴ *Ibidem*, b. 80, fasc. 1, Comando Gruppo Armate-Ufficio Informazioni, Informazioni della 2ª Armata, Situazione descrittiva settimanale, Comando della 2ª Armata-Ufficio I, *Situazione descrittiva d'oltre confine n. 32*, Sintesi, Premessa, 1° ottobre 1940-XVIII; *Situazione descrittiva d'oltre confine n. 33*, Sintesi, 8 ottobre 1940-XVIII.

I circoli politici jugoslavi si sforzarono di eliminare cause d'attrito con Italia e Germania. Il Ministero degli Interni sciolse le federazioni degli emigrati slavi e l'associazione irredentistica "Trieste-Istria-Gorizia-Rijeka" sequestrandone i beni; gli ebrei furono esclusi da ogni tipo di attività commerciale e industriale e dalle università, seguendo i decreti tedeschi; dirigenti e capitali francesi e inglesi vennero progressivamente sostituiti da tedeschi nelle imprese industriali e minerarie. In particolare con il provvedimento contro gli ebrei non solo si era trovato un capro espiatorio all'impresario del governo nell'arginare il crescente caroviveri, ma si colpivano gli ebrei magiari della Vojvodina, uno dei principali obiettivi, facendo passare in mano serbe le loro aziende³⁵.

Al tempo stesso a Skopije il premier Dragiša Cvetković e il generale Milan Nedić, ministro della Guerra, confermarono la decisa volontà jugoslava di difendere il proprio territorio a qualunque costo (ottobre 1940)³⁶ e fu quindi accelerato il trasferimento delle industrie dai territori croati a quelli serbi, destando notevole malumore tra la popolazione croata. Negli ambienti militari permaneva la profonda convinzione che qualsiasi cenno di debolezza del governo centrale avrebbe segnato il crollo dell'unità statale jugoslava (erano da escludersi nel modo più assoluto revisioni delle frontiere)³⁷. Ciò nonostante la penetrazione tedesca andava estendendosi alle più importanti attività industriali ed economiche jugoslave, superando non senza difficoltà la residua resistenza degli ambienti anglofili³⁸. Belgrado sembrava orientarsi verso la necessità di cedere alle pressioni tedesche almeno nell'ambito economico e culturale e alcune dichiarazioni ed eventi più o meno ufficiali confermavano la sensazione. A Novi Sad Cvetković si era dichiarato deciso ad accogliere le richieste avanzate dalla minoranza tedesca, concedendo, insieme con i consigli comunali e distrettuali, la lingua tedesca nei rapporti d'ufficio e l'ammissione di funzionari tedeschi nei comuni e nelle *banovine*; l'ambasciatore tedesco aveva organizzato l'esposizione di architettura tedesca a Belgrado, alla cui inaugurazione erano intervenuti il principe Pavle, l'intero gabinetto jugoslavo ed eminenti personalità del mondo politico e culturale della capitale; la principessa Olga e diversi ministri avevano visitato i posti di sosta e ristoro a Belgrado e Zagabria per gli emigrati tedeschi che rimpatriavano dalla Bessarabia passando per la Jugoslavia; infine era stato tenuto un ricevimento

³⁵ *Ibidem*, Comando Gruppo Armate-Ufficio Informazioni, Informazioni della 2^a Armata, Comando della 2^a Armata-Ufficio I, *Stralcio stampa jugoslava*, 13 ottobre 1940-XVIII. Sulle leggi antisemite del 1940 si veda Ivo Goldstein, *Anti-Semitism in Croatia*, in Ivo Goldstein, Narcisa Lengel-Krizman (a cura di), *Anti-semitism, Holocaust, Anti-Fascism*, Zagreb, Jewish Community, 1997, pp. 43-44; Idem, "Dva antisemitska zakona u Kraljevini Jugoslaviji 1940. Godine", in Damir Agić (a cura di), *Zbornik Mire Kolar-Dimitrijević: zbornik radova povodom 70. rodendana*, Zagreb, Filozofski fakultet, Odsjek za povijest, FF Press, 2003, pp. 395-405.

³⁶ A.U.S.M.E., H-3, b. 80, fasc. 1, *Stralcio stampa jugoslava*, Discorso del Presidente del Consiglio jugoslavo Cvetković a Skoplje (*sic*), 13 ottobre 1940-XVIII.

³⁷ *Ibidem*, b. 60, fasc. 4, Carteggio del Servizio Informazioni Militari (S.I.M.) relativo ai vari Stati, Jugoslavia, Ministero della Guerra, S.I.M., *Notiziario giornaliero*, Jugoslavia, Roma, 19 ottobre 1940-XVIII.

³⁸ *Ibidem*, b. 80, fasc. 1, Informazioni sulla Jugoslavia (1940), Comando Gruppo Armate-Ufficio Informazioni, Jugoslavia, Informazioni della 2^a Armata, Situazione descrittiva settimanale, Comando della 2^a Armata-Ufficio I, *Situazione descrittiva d'oltre confine n. 34*, Sintesi, 15 ottobre 1940-XVIII.

presso la Legazione tedesca a Belgrado in onore dei ministri e di personalità intellettuali jugoslave.

L'ingerenza tedesca era però solo parzialmente soddisfacente per l'economia jugoslava, che permaneva in condizioni difficili. La propaganda comunista era ampiamente diffusa in Croazia e Dalmazia con manifestini e volantini distribuiti di preferenza tra le truppe³⁹. Una serie di volantini diffusi dagli *ustasha* avevano invece riaffermato il diritto all'indipendenza croata e la speranza di un intervento dell'Asse in suo favore. I volantini contenevano violenti attacchi a Maček, accusato di essere uno strumento del governo di Belgrado e di tradire il popolo croato. Contemporaneamente gravi incidenti fra soldati cattolici e ortodossi avvenivano a Knin, con morti e feriti: questioni di carattere religioso erano presto degenerare in rissa per questioni di nazionalità⁴⁰.

Gran parte della popolazione serba era comunque convinta che, malgrado le iniziali vittorie tedesche, l'Inghilterra alla fine avrebbe vinto la guerra, opinione peraltro largamente condivisa dallo Stato Maggiore e dal principe Pavle. Se Belgrado cercava di non comprometersi con la Germania ingegnandosi in campo economico, nei confronti dell'Italia si dimostrava diffidente, anche a causa della presenza dei contingenti italiani alla frontiera slovena e albanese. L'influenza italiana raggiunta con gli accordi Ciano-Stojadinović del 1937 era ormai perduta, mentre la Germania stava progressivamente assorbendo l'economia jugoslava con un'azione che non si limitava all'esaurimento di gran parte delle risorse alimentari del Paese, ma penetrava in profondità, procedendo all'acquisto di stabili e istituti economici. L'attività tedesca non teneva in alcuna considerazione gli interessi italiani e lo Stato jugoslavo, fornitore di materie prime, era ormai decisamente inquadrato nello spazio vitale del *Reich*⁴¹.

Il 28 ottobre 1940 l'Italia dichiarò guerra alla Grecia, informando l'alleato tedesco a fatto compiuto. La politica di amicizia di Belgrado nei riguardi dell'Italia rimaneva invariata, ma malgrado i vari comunicati ufficiali e ufficiosi della stampa jugoslava, l'opinione pubblica e il contegno delle popolazioni serba, croata e slovena si mantenevano ostili al vicino italiano. L'atteggiamento jugoslavo sembrava decisamente collegato all'esito delle operazioni militari italiane in Grecia e non pochi si auguravano che la lenta e difficile avanzata italiana fosse arrestata del tutto. In tal caso era probabile che la Jugoslavia riesaminasse la propria posizione per schierarsi apertamente con l'Inghilterra, che aveva intensificato la propaganda contro l'Italia in Dalmazia tramite il consolato inglese a Spalato⁴².

Da parte tedesca la neutralità jugoslava iniziava a non essere più sufficiente e si richiedeva ora un pronunciamento esplicito pro o contro l'Asse.

³⁹ *Ibidem*, *Situazione politica e morale* (dalla stampa), pp. 12-13.

⁴⁰ *Ibidem*, Stralcio stampa jugoslava, Comando della 2^a Armata-Ufficio I, *Stralcio stampa jugoslava*, 16 ottobre 1940-XVIII.

⁴¹ *Ibidem*, b. 67, fasc. 4, Informazioni sulla frontiera jugoslava (1940), Comando della 2^a Armata, oggetto: *Conversazione con un italiano proveniente da Belgrado*, 20 ottobre 1940-XVIII.

⁴² *Ibidem*, b. 59, fasc. 2, Carteggio del Servizio Informazioni Militari (S.I.M.) relativo ai vari Stati, Jugoslavia, Ministero della Guerra, Contro-spionaggio militare e servizi speciali, all'Ecc. il Sottocapo di S.M. dell'Esercito, Roma, 4 novembre 1940-XIX, Jugoslavia, *Notizie di fonte fiduciaria attendibile*, Zara, 2 novembre 1940-XIX.

A Berlino continuava a prevalere la tendenza a ottenere il favore di Belgrado senza ricorrere alla forza, dal momento che un'azione spregiudicata avrebbe trasformato i Balcani in un focolaio di guerra, attirando nella zona l'Unione Sovietica e provocando una solidarietà anglo-russa compromettente per i piani tedeschi. Il principe Pavle avrebbe incontrato sempre maggiori difficoltà nel resistere alle pressioni tedesche per l'adesione al Patto Tripartito firmato nel settembre del 1940 da Germania, Italia e Giappone per la creazione di un "nuovo ordine" euro-asiatico. Berlino progressivamente isolò la Jugoslavia: nel novembre del 1940 l'Ungheria e la Romania aderirono al Tripartito, la Bulgaria avrebbe completato l'accerchiamento aderendovi pochi mesi dopo. Pavle continuò a dimostrarsi incerto, confuso da ministri e generali divisi tra coloro che, convinti dell'impossibilità delle potenze occidentali di inviare un aiuto nei Balcani, erano propensi ad accordarsi con la Germania e quanti continuavano invece a sostenere un'aperta presa di posizione favorevole a inglesi e francesi. Alti ecclesiastici fra cui il patriarca ortodosso, uomini d'affari e ufficiali dell'esercito ritenevano che le potenze occidentali avrebbero sconfitto la Germania: accettare la protezione dei tedeschi non soltanto sarebbe stato inconciliabile con la tradizione serba, ma alla lunga si sarebbe dimostrato svantaggioso. Il governo di Belgrado e il principe reggente in occasione di pubblici discorsi riaffermarono la volontà di pace, ma l'opinione pubblica jugoslava continuava a essere agitata dai partiti estremisti, che miravano a scalzare il prestigio del governo e nell'esercito rappresentavano con la loro propaganda la principale causa delle diserzioni, soprattutto tra i soldati croati⁴³.

La conclusione del Patto di Amicizia Perpetua con l'Ungheria, firmato a Belgrado il 12 dicembre 1940, fu preceduta da una favorevole propaganda tra i rappresentanti dell'Asse, anche se il patto, oltre ad affermazioni generiche di amicizia, non conteneva impegni che potessero collegare la Jugoslavia al Tripartito⁴⁴. L'avvicinamento jugoslavo all'Unione Sovietica era invece confermato dalla conclusione di trattative per la fornitura bellica, dall'inizio di scambi commerciali e dalle visite dell'addetto militare sovietico alle guarnigioni e ai lavori di fortificazione alle frontiere. Se il governo di Belgrado si proclamava disposto a proseguire sulla via della collaborazione con l'Asse, la quasi totalità dei circoli belgradesi coltivava la speranza di un maggiore impegno dei russi per il mantenimento dello *status quo* nei Balcani occidentali⁴⁵.

Iniziarono gli incontri per legare concretamente la Jugoslavia al sistema di alleanze tedesco e alla fine di dicembre vi fu un primo incontro tra Hitler e il ministro degli Esteri Aleksandar Cincar-Marković. Gli obiettivi urgenti che si poneva la Germania erano sottrarre l'Italia all'umiliazione in Grecia e garantire al *Reich* un'alleanza strategica per la guerra all'Unione Sovietica. Entrambi

⁴³ *Ibidem*, b. 60, fasc. 4, Stato Maggiore R. Esercito - S.I.M., Situazione generale Jugoslavia (politico-militare), 30 maggio 1940-28 dicembre 1940, *Stralcio situazione settimanale n. 160*, Jugoslavia, 5 dicembre 1940.

⁴⁴ *Ibidem*, *Stralcio situazione settimanale n. 162*, Jugoslavia, Situazione politico-militare, 19 dicembre 1940-XIX. Sul Patto con l'Ungheria si veda Alessandro Vagnini, *L'Ungheria nella guerra dell'Asse (1939-1943)*, Cosenza, Periferia, 2007, pp. 118-120.

⁴⁵ A.U.S.S.M.E., H-3, b. 60, fasc. 4, *Stralcio situazione settimanale n. 163*, Jugoslavia, Situazione politico-militare, 28 dicembre 1940-XIX.

non potevano assolutamente prescindere dall'adesione del governo di Belgrado al Patto Tripartito.

All'inizio del 1941 in Jugoslavia l'attenzione era inevitabilmente attirata dalla grave situazione internazionale, che aveva imposto una tregua ai dissensi e alle divisioni politiche interne⁴⁶. I circoli politici e militari seguivano con preoccupazione lo sviluppo della situazione in Romania, ove erano segnalati continui arrivi di truppe e materiale dell'esercito tedesco. Belgrado tentò di persuadere la Germania della propria volontà di svolgere una politica filo-Asse di neutralità, nella certezza che la già forte pressione tedesca fosse destinata ad aumentare e celando a stento un vivo senso di inquietudine (l'addensarsi di forze tedesche nel Banato romeno aveva confermato le apprensioni)⁴⁷. Le relazioni con l'Italia continuavano invece apparentemente normali, sebbene il Servizio Informazioni Militare italiano segnalasse una vivace e aperta campagna antiitaliana a Belgrado e Zagabria e in generale da parte della stampa, compresa quella slovena e croata. In alcuni centri della Dalmazia erano state anche tenute manifestazioni irredentistiche per la Venezia-Giulia e tra le forze armate la propaganda di ostilità all'Asse era svolta in termini sempre più decisi. La condizione di incerta attesa vissuta dallo Stato jugoslavo era aggravata dalla persistente crisi dei generi di prima necessità, ma il momentaneo stallo militare dell'Asse in Albania e in Africa, la speranza in un favorevole atteggiamento dell'Unione Sovietica e la propaganda inglese sembrarono creare un lieve miglioramento e un'atmosfera di maggiore sicurezza, che determinarono un rafforzamento della compagine governativa, alla quale si era stretta con una sempre più chiara adesione anche il partito contadino di Maček. Una ripresa delle agitazioni dei nazionalisti croati, cui andava collegato l'attentato contro il circolo inglese di Zagabria, fu repressa con l'arresto degli attentatori; al tempo stesso veniva segnalata una ripresa della propaganda comunista, specie tra i contadini⁴⁸.

Il 2 febbraio gli ambasciatori a Belgrado di Gran Bretagna, Stati Uniti, Grecia e Turchia chiesero esplicitamente al governo jugoslavo di precisare il proprio atteggiamento nell'eventualità che la Germania avesse chiesto il transito di truppe dell'Asse in territorio jugoslavo⁴⁹. Il colonnello americano Donovan promise l'aiuto statunitense qualora la Jugoslavia si fosse impegnata a resistere alle pressioni tedesche, assicurando che anche la Turchia non sarebbe rimasta passiva nel caso la Germania avesse agito attraverso i territori jugoslavi evitando la Bulgaria. La psicosi di guerra determinatasi nei circoli militari serbi indusse lo Stato Maggiore a prendere una serie di disposizioni e di misure precauzionali tali da consentire la rapida mobilitazione delle forze armate in vista della primavera: i circoli militari,

⁴⁶ *Ibidem*, b. 66, fasc. 2, Carteggio del Servizio Informazioni Militari (S.I.M.) relativo ai vari Stati, Notiziari politici militari ed economici sulla Jugoslavia (1941), 9 gennaio-5 aprile 1941, *Stralcio della situazione settimanale n. 1*, Jugoslavia, Situazione politico-militare, 4 gennaio 1941-XIX.

⁴⁷ *Ibidem*, *Stralcio della situazione settimanale n. 2*, Jugoslavia, Situazione politico-militare, 9 gennaio 1941-XIX; *Stralcio della situazione settimanale n. 3*, Jugoslavia, Situazione politico-militare, 16 gennaio 1941-XIX.

⁴⁸ *Ibidem*, *Stralcio del bollettino settimanale n. 6*, Jugoslavia, Situazione politico-militare, 6 febbraio 1941-XIX; *Stralcio della situazione settimanale n. 7*, Jugoslavia, Situazione politico-militare, 13 febbraio 1941-XIX.

⁴⁹ *Ibidem*, *Stralcio del bollettino giornaliero n. 40*, Jugoslavia, 9 febbraio 1941-XIX.

infatti, continuavano - solo apparentemente in contrasto con gli ambienti governativi - a opporsi a qualunque pressione dell'Asse nella certezza della vittoria finale inglese⁵⁰.

Il 14 febbraio, mentre la notizia della rottura delle relazioni diplomatiche tra Inghilterra e Romania destava nuove preoccupazioni, Cvetković e Cincar-Marković si recarono da Hitler e Ribbentrop in Austria per chiarire la posizione jugoslava nell'eventualità di un passaggio delle truppe tedesche in Bulgaria⁵¹. I circoli politici e militari belgradesi erano convinti che la Bulgaria non si sarebbe opposta al passaggio tedesco e che l'Unione Sovietica e la Turchia non avrebbero reagito se i loro territori e i loro più vicini interessi non fossero stati direttamente minacciati⁵². I colloqui si conclusero con la netta affermazione tedesca di voler eliminare qualsiasi ingerenza inglese nei Balcani e l'invito più o meno chiaramente esplicito ai ministri jugoslavi ad aderire al Tripartito. Con gli avvenimenti di politica interna in secondo piano dinanzi agli eventi internazionali, poco risalto ebbero alcuni tentativi di attività irredentistica in Macedonia e la propaganda *ustaša* in Croazia, peraltro subito represse dalle autorità jugoslave⁵³.

Il 1° marzo l'adesione della Bulgaria al Tripartito e la conseguente penetrazione delle truppe tedesche nel Paese accelerarono la messa in atto da parte di Belgrado di misure difensive alla frontiera sud-orientale, in attesa della decisione dell'atteggiamento politico da adottare. Il reggente Pavle si recò in incognito a Berghof (4 marzo) per continuare le conversazioni con i tedeschi. L'obiettivo era guadagnare tempo, ma la situazione non permetteva di dilazionare ulteriormente la presa di una chiara posizione, che peraltro sembrava sempre più propendere per l'adesione jugoslava alla politica dell'Asse, come confermato dalla partenza di elementi britannici da Belgrado e dall'intervento del governo presso gli ambienti militari per modificarne le note simpatie filoinglesi⁵⁴. I tedeschi avevano chiaramente ribadito al reggente jugoslavo che intendevano al più presto creare nei Balcani una situazione di assoluto e definitivo predominio militare, che consentisse loro la completa disponibilità delle forze e la piena libertà di azione, e con l'adesione della Bulgaria al Tripartito avevano di fatto completato l'accerchiamento politico e militare della Jugoslavia⁵⁵. Per la dirigenza di Belgrado si trattava di trovare una formula di adesione apparentemente negoziata e non apertamente imposta, che salvasse l'orgoglio nazionale agli occhi dell'opinione pubblica e dei militari⁵⁶. Con l'adesione al Tripartito, al regno dei Karadjordjević sarebbe stata garantita l'integrità territoriale senza chiedere un impegno in ambito

⁵⁰ *Ibidem*, *Stralcio del bollettino giornaliero n. 32*, 1° febbraio 1941-XIX.

⁵¹ Cfr. Giorgio Perich, *op. cit.*, pp. 49-51.

⁵² A.U.S.S.M.E., H-3, b. 66, fasc. 2, *Stralcio del bollettino settimanale n. 8*, Jugoslavia, Situazione politico-militare, 20 febbraio 1941-XIX.

⁵³ *Ibidem*, *Stralcio della situazione settimanale n. 10*, Jugoslavia, Situazione politico-militare, 6 marzo 1941-XIX.

⁵⁴ *Ibidem*, *Stralcio del bollettino giornaliero n. 68*, Jugoslavia, 9 marzo 1941-XIX.

⁵⁵ *Ibidem*, *Stralcio della situazione settimanale n. 11*, Jugoslavia, Situazione politico-militare, 13 marzo 1941-XIX.

⁵⁶ *Ibidem*, *Stralcio della situazione settimanale Stati esteri n. 12*, Jugoslavia, Situazione politico-militare, 20 marzo 1941-XIX.

militare o pretendere il passaggio delle truppe dell'Asse attraverso il territorio jugoslavo.

Per trovare una soluzione alle lotte e agli irredentismi interni jugoslavi, si faceva intanto insistente la possibilità di un rimaneggiamento governativo con la costituzione di un "gabinetto di guerra" che inaugurasse una politica d'intransigenza verso l'Asse fino alle estreme conseguenze o in alternativa con la formazione di un governo di "concentrazione nazionale" - con il compito di aderire al Tripartito - presieduto ancora da Cvetković ma comprendente anche i capi dell'opposizione⁵⁷. Il grave momento che la Jugoslavia stava attraversando aveva provocato nel Paese una netta divisione tra due correnti, l'una rappresentata dai croati, che manifestava cautamente una tendenza conciliatrice verso l'Asse, l'altra impersonata dai nazionalisti jugoslavi e dai serbi, che difendevano invece l'integrità territoriale e ostentavano la propria ostilità alla politica di potenza tedesca⁵⁸. Continuava inoltre la pressione britannica su Belgrado per influenzare l'atteggiamento da assumere nei confronti dell'Asse. Secondo le indiscrezioni di alcune personalità diplomatiche, sembrava che Eden avesse promesso larghi aiuti al reggente e, al termine del conflitto, l'Istria, le isole dalmate e parte dell'Albania; il principe Pavle non aveva però risposto al messaggio del ministro inglese, con grave disappunto degli ambienti jugoslavi filobritannici⁵⁹.

Il 13 marzo Pavle autorizzò Cincar-Marković a trattare con i tedeschi sulla base delle proposte ricevute pochi giorni prima a Berghof. Particolari clausole che secondo Belgrado avrebbero asservito all'Asse l'economia jugoslava rallentarono le trattative, ma si giunse comunque a un accordo di massima: con l'adesione al Tripartito la Jugoslavia avrebbe ottenuto la garanzia dell'inviolabilità del proprio territorio senza l'obbligo di aiutare le potenze dell'Asse nello sforzo bellico⁶⁰. Rimanevano però in sospeso la questione dell'eventuale passaggio di truppe sul suolo jugoslavo e forti le correnti contrarie all'adesione: a Lubiana e in tutta la Slovenia venivano diffusi manifestini che accusavano il governo di aver ceduto alle pressioni dell'Asse e incitavano alla ribellione⁶¹.

Il 22 marzo arrivò quasi un *ultimatum* di Ribbentrop a Cincar-Marković: la decisione definitiva in merito all'adesione jugoslava sarebbe dovuta pervenire a Berlino nei giorni successivi, altrimenti Belgrado avrebbe perso l'occasione di sistemare vantaggiosamente le proprie relazioni con l'Asse. Difficoltà ancora opposte agli accordi erano dovute alla preoccupazione jugoslava di coinvolgere il Paese in un eventuale allargamento del conflitto. Al tempo stesso l'adesione al Tripartito era quasi obbligatoria per garantire l'integrità dello Stato: la

⁵⁷ *Ibidem*, 13 marzo 1941-XIX.

⁵⁸ *Ibidem*, 20 marzo 1941-XIX.

⁵⁹ *Ibidem*, *Stralcio del bollettino giornaliero n. 70*, Jugoslavia, 11 marzo 1941-XIX.

⁶⁰ *Documents on German Foreign Policy 1918-1945, (D.G.F.P.), Series D (1937-1945)*, Vol. XII, *The War Years, February 1-June 22, 1941*, London, Her Majesty's Stationery Office, 1962, No. 156, 230/152555-56, *The Minister in Yugoslavia to the Foreign Ministry*, Telegram, Most Urgent, Top Secret, No. 216 of March 12, Belgrade, March 12, 1941, pp. 281-282; No. 165, 230/152558-62, *The Foreign Minister to the Legation in Yugoslavia*, Telegram, Most Urgent, Top Secret, No. 183 of March 14 from Fuschl, No. 281 of March 14 from the Foreign Ministry, Ribbentrop, Fuschl, March 14, 1941, pp. 291-294.

⁶¹ A.U.S.S.M.E., H-3, b. 66, fasc. 2, *Stralcio bollettino giornaliero n. 73*, Jugoslavia, 14 marzo 1941-XIX.

previsione ultima era di limitare la concessione di transito attraverso il territorio jugoslavo al solo materiale sanitario e commissariato. La residenza reale divenne sede di una serie di consultazioni sull'adesione o meno: il principe reggente sottopose l'argomento al consiglio della corona, composto dai principali ministri e dai comandanti militari. I membri del consiglio si dimostrarono favorevoli ad accettare l'accordo con la Germania, tre ministri invece si dimisero dichiarando che l'adesione al sistema di alleanze dell'Asse era estremamente pericolosa per l'indipendenza dello Stato⁶². Nella decisione jugoslava ebbe un ruolo determinante lo schieramento, quello stesso giorno (22 marzo), delle truppe tedesche lungo la frontiera bulgaro-jugoslava⁶³.

Infine il 25 marzo Cvetković e Cincar-Marković firmarono l'adesione al Patto Tripartito. L'accordo prevedeva espressamente l'impegno tedesco a non violare i confini jugoslavi, salvo il diritto di transito delle truppe tedesche per raggiungere la Grecia⁶⁴. Il viaggio a Vienna dei due ministri era stato tenuto in gran segreto, ma il 26 marzo al rientro a Belgrado la notizia dell'adesione jugoslava al Tripartito si diffuse rapidamente e la situazione in Jugoslavia diventò critica: nella capitale e nelle principali città serbe ebbero luogo manifestazioni ostili al governo, che dispose un largo spiegamento di forze di polizia, la chiusura delle scuole e severe disposizioni per evitare attentati e atti di sabotaggio⁶⁵. L'adesione della Jugoslavia al Tripartito, dopo lunghe esitazioni e contrasti interni, poneva la popolazione e l'esercito dinanzi al fatto compiuto⁶⁶. Sulla decisione avevano influito, tra l'altro, le aspirazioni revisioniste ungheresi e bulgare e la convinzione dell'impossibilità di concreti aiuti da parte della Gran Bretagna. Alla fine l'allineamento alle potenze dell'Asse era stato considerato l'inevitabile compromesso per non partecipare alla guerra. Disposizioni di sicurezza continuarono a essere prese per impedire manifestazioni di disapprovazione all'operato del governo⁶⁷.

La notte tra il 26 e il 27 marzo a Belgrado il generale Dušan Simović, ex capo di Stato Maggiore, e il generale Bora Mirković, comandante dell'aviazione, sostenuti dai servizi segreti britannici e dalle forze armate jugoslave, con il beneplacito dei circoli politici serbi e del clero ortodosso, attuarono un colpo di

⁶² *Ibidem*, *Stralcio al bollettino giornaliero n. 82*, Jugoslavia, 23 marzo 1941-XIX.

⁶³ Giorgio Perich, *op. cit.*, p. 63.

⁶⁴ Si veda lo scambio di note tra i governi jugoslavo, italiano e tedesco, in *D.G.F.P.*, Series D (1937-1945), Vol. XII, No. 205, F11/0070, *The Reich Foreign Minister to the Yugoslav Minister President*, Vienna, March 25, 1941, p. 353; No. 206, F11/0069, *The Yugoslav Minister President to the Reich Foreign Minister*, Vienna, March 25, 1941, pp. 353-354; No. 207, 67/47456-64, *Memorandum by an Official of the Foreign Minister's Secretariat*, Vienna, March 25, 1941, Record of the conversation between the Führer and Yugoslav Minister President Cvetković in the presence of the Reich Foreign Minister and Yugoslav Foreign Minister Cincar-Marković in Vienna in the Hotel Imperial on March 25, 1941, Schmidt, pp. 354-357; No. 208, 67/47445-55, *Memorandum by an Official of the Foreign Minister's Secretariat*, Vienna, March 25, 1941, Record of the conversation between the Führer and Count Ciano in the presence of the Ambassadors von Mackensen and Alfieri in the Hotel Imperial in Vienna on March 25, 1941, Schmidt, pp. 357-361. Anche *D.D.I.*, Nona serie, 1939-1943, vol. VI, doc. 778, *Colloquio tra il Cancelliere del Reich, Hitler, ed il Ministro degli Esteri, Ciano*, Vienna, 25 marzo 1941, pp. 744-746.

⁶⁵ A.U.S.S.M.E., H-3, b. 66, fasc. 2, *Stralcio del bollettino giornaliero n. 87*, Jugoslavia, 28 marzo 1941-XIX.

⁶⁶ *Ibidem*, *Stralcio della situazione settimanale n. 13*, Jugoslavia, 27 marzo 1941-XIX.

⁶⁷ *Ibidem*, *Stralcio al bollettino giornaliero n. 85*, Jugoslavia, 26 marzo 1941-XIX.

Stato incruento che pose fine alla reggenza del principe Pavle e investì del potere regio il giovanissimo Petar II, ancora diciassettenne. Il governo Cvetković venne destituito e il primo ministro, insieme al ministro degli Esteri Cincar-Marković e ad altri alti funzionari statali, furono momentaneamente posti agli arresti. Il giorno dopo il giovane Petar nominò alla guida del governo il generale Simović, il quale si affrettò a comunicare a Berlino e a Roma il mantenimento degli impegni presi dal precedente governo con l'adesione al Tripartito. Il governo Simović era deciso a non intraprendere iniziative che ai tedeschi potessero apparire provocatorie, nel tentativo di evitare la guerra o per lo meno di guadagnare tempo, nella speranza che nuovi imprevedibili eventi potessero arrestare la discesa tedesca nei Balcani⁶⁸.

Lo Stato Maggiore Generale italiano avvertì i comandi supremi di Esercito, Marina e Aviazione di tenersi pronti a ogni eventualità alle frontiere giuliana, adriatica e albanese, nel caso le intenzioni tedesche fossero aprirete le ostilità contro la Jugoslavia⁶⁹. Alle prime ore del 28 l'ambasciatore tedesco a Roma Hans Georg von Mackensen consegnava a Mussolini il testo di una lettera di Hitler in cui, senza accennare all'utilizzo dei separatisti croati, erano espresse le decisioni prese in merito alla Jugoslavia e si comunicava di aver chiesto per l'offensiva il concorso bulgaro e ungherese. Fu Mussolini, nella risposta, a ricordare all'alleato tedesco di tener presente, nel conflitto che si andava delineando, anche gli *ustaša* di Pavelić⁷⁰.

Il 29 marzo il governo insediatosi a Belgrado proclamò lo stato d'assedio, chiuse le frontiere e ordinò la mobilitazione generale, contando sui croati presenti nel gabinetto quali elementi moderatori. Costituito con rappresentanze di tutti i partiti, il governo intendeva evitare l'accerchiamento del Paese e prospettava gli avvenimenti dei giorni precedenti come il risultato di uno sforzo delle correnti che si erano proposte di salvare l'onore nazionale. Il Servizio Informazioni Militare riteneva che il colpo di Stato fosse stato attuato con la connivenza dell'esecutivo precedente e del reggente, partito per Atene. Prove in tal senso erano state l'immediata costituzione del nuovo governo, l'assoluta mancanza di reazione agli avvenimenti dei giorni precedenti e la partecipazione al gabinetto Simović di alcuni esponenti del precedente esecutivo⁷¹. Il cambiamento di governo e ancor più l'entusiasmo popolare che lo aveva accolto dimostravano chiaramente che i sentimenti jugoslavi erano profondamente contrari all'Asse e dominati dal timore dell'accerchiamento. Il colpo di Stato aveva suscitato un diffuso consenso tra la popolazione di Belgrado: le masse e i soldati scesero in piazza e ricomparvero in pubblico le bandiere del partito comunista.

⁶⁸ Giorgio Perich, *op. cit.*, pp. 71-74.

⁶⁹ A.U.S.S.M.E., I-4, b. 18, fasc. 5, Operazioni alla frontiera jugoslava dall'8 marzo al 14 maggio 1941, Comando Supremo Stato Maggiore Generale-Ufficio Operazioni, a Superesercito, Supermarina, Superaereo, Ministero della Guerra-Gabinetto, oggetto: *Situazione in Jugoslavia*, f. to il Capo di Stato Maggiore Generale, 27 marzo 1941-XIX.

⁷⁰ D.G.F.P., Series D (1937-1945), Vol. XII, No. 224, F1/0458-61, *An Official of the Foreign Minister's Personal Staff to the Embassy in Italy*, Closed Circuit Secret Teletype, Most urgent, No. 678, Hewel, Berlin, March 27, 1941, pp. 397-398; No. 226, F1/0455-57, *The Ambassador in Italy to the Foreign Ministry*, Teletype, Top Secret (No. 698 of March 28), For the Foreign Minister personally, Mackensen, Rome, March 28, 1941, pp. 399-400.

⁷¹ A.U.S.S.M.E., H-3, b. 66, fasc. 2, *Stralcio del bollettino giornaliero n. 88*, 29 marzo 1941-XIX; id., *Stralcio bollettino giornaliero n. 90*, Jugoslavia, 31 marzo 1941-XIX.

Svanito l'entusiasmo iniziale, il governo Simović si trovava però a dover fronteggiare la decisa reazione delle potenze dell'Asse, l'ostinata ostilità dei croati che temevano la revoca di ogni autonomia e la propaganda comunista e della piazza che attendevano ormai l'aggressione della Germania e dei suoi alleati e il coinvolgimento jugoslavo nel conflitto⁷². Aumentò l'attività insurrezionale croata: numerosi croati risultavano renitenti alla leva - soprattutto nella zona della Lika, centro delle tendenze *ustaša* - e le truppe intorno a Zara venivano ulteriormente rinforzate con elementi bosniaci e macedoni. Anche tra la popolazione dei maggiori centri urbani l'iniziale entusiasmo dei giorni precedenti lasciò il passo al panico diffuso: nella capitale, priva di ricoveri contro i bombardamenti e di particolari servizi di difesa, fu vietata l'evacuazione della popolazione⁷³.

Il Comando militare jugoslavo tentava di completare i preparativi di guerra. Il richiamo alle armi era stato progressivamente esteso sino alle classi più anziane e i riservisti erano stati richiamati fino a oltre i sessant'anni di età per essere adibiti a incarichi territoriali. Formazioni paramilitari e di volontari erano state mobilitate, mentre i reparti di frontiera, la marina e l'aviazione avevano già assunto lo stato d'emergenza. Le requisizioni e gli acquisti erano compiuti su vasta scala e senza più riguardi ai bisogni della popolazione, mentre venivano minate le acque territoriali, fluviali e marittime. Lo Stato Maggiore jugoslavo si preoccupò prima di affrontare possibili minacce tedesche dall'Ungheria, dalla Bulgaria e dalla Romania, rafforzando i dispositivi difensivi esistenti; in seguito rivolse l'attenzione alle frontiere giulia, tedesca e al litorale⁷⁴. Anche la frontiera giulia veniva rinforzata con soldati macedoni e bosniaci e il giorno seguente nuovi rinforzi di fanteria assumevano la dislocazione d'emergenza nel settore Alta Sava e Alta Kupa. Un nucleo considerevole di elementi serbi e bosniaci affluiva inoltre alla frontiera tedesca all'altezza di Jesenice (Alta Sava), mentre nuove forze completavano le unità schierate sulla frontiera albanese⁷⁵. La popolazione di Sušak residente in prossimità del ponte sull'Eneo riceveva il preavviso di sgomberare le proprie abitazioni per il pericolo che il ponte fosse fatto saltare, e dalla città venivano trasferiti archivi e valori governativi e postali.

Il governo jugoslavo non era solo consapevole della pressione militare che le potenze dell'Asse andavano esercitando alle frontiere ma anche del pericolo sempre più concreto rappresentato dalla loro influenza sulle tendenze separatiste croate⁷⁶. Se il colpo di Stato aveva diffuso entusiasmo tra i serbi, la destituzione di Pavle e Cvetković fu vissuta dai croati come una condanna dello *Sporazum* e una riaffermazione dell'egemonia di Belgrado. I croati finirono col collegare autonomia e adesione al Patto Tripartito, ma Maček

⁷² *Ibidem*, *Stralcio della situazione settimanale Stati esteri n. 14*, Jugoslavia, Situazione politico-militare, 3 aprile 1941-XIX. Nella regione di Zagabria, dove i richiami alle armi erano assai limitati, si segnalavano nei primi giorni di aprile nuove formazioni armate costituite da esponenti del partito contadino. *Ibidem*, *Stralcio bollettino giornaliero n. 94*, Jugoslavia, 4 aprile 1941-XIX.

⁷³ *Ibidem*, *Stralcio della situazione giornaliera n. 93*, 3 aprile 1941-XIX.

⁷⁴ *Ibidem*, *Stralcio della situazione settimanale Stati esteri n. 14*, Jugoslavia, Situazione politico-militare, 3 aprile 1941-XIX.

⁷⁵ *Ibidem*, *Stralcio bollettino giornaliero n. 95*, Jugoslavia, 5 aprile 1941-XIX.

⁷⁶ *Ibidem*, *Stralcio del bollettino giornaliero n. 91*, Jugoslavia, 1° aprile 1941.

nonostante le insistenze degli emissari tedeschi rimase fermo nella volontà di non separare la Croazia dalla Jugoslavia ed entrò nel governo solamente quando fu certo che sarebbe stato rispettato lo *Sporazum* e confermata l'alleanza con la Germania. Il 4 aprile accettò la vicepresidenza del governo nel tentativo di garantire l'autonomia croata all'interno dello Stato jugoslavo e rifiutò il ruolo offertogli dai tedeschi di "premier-fantoccio", dichiarandosi al più disponibile a sostenere l'indipendenza croata senza avervi parte attiva. Le assicurazioni di Belgrado alle potenze dell'Asse si rivelarono vane: il 5 aprile il governo jugoslavo strinse un inutile patto di amicizia e di non aggressione con l'Unione Sovietica, nella speranza che un avvicinamento a Stalin potesse scongiurare l'imminente attacco, ma Hitler era ormai convinto che la questione jugoslava non ammettesse altra soluzione che quella militare e il 6 aprile 1941 le truppe dell'Asse invasero la Jugoslavia, che incapace di opporre una seria resistenza, sarebbe stata sconfitta in pochi giorni⁷⁷.

⁷⁷ *D.G.F.P.*, Series D, Vol. XII, No. 281, 100/65260-65, *Adolf Hitler to Benito Mussolini*, Berlin, April 5, 1941, Hitler, pp. 475-478; No. 289 100/65269-70, *Benito Mussolini to Adolf Hitler*, Rome, April 6, 1941/XIX, Mussolini, p. 485; *D.D.I.*, Nona serie, 1939-1943, vol. VI, doc. 865, *Il Cancelliere del Reich, Hitler, al Capo del Governo, Mussolini*, Berlino, 5 aprile 1941, pp. 812-816; doc. 868, *Il Capo del Governo, Mussolini, al Cancelliere del Reich, Hitler*, Roma, 6 aprile 1941, p. 818. Sull'accordo sovietico-jugoslavo si veda Giorgio Perich, *op. cit.*, pp. 97-99.

STANDPOINTS OF SOME JEWISH MEMORISTS AND HISTORIANS REGARDING THE MEANING OF THE ACTIONS ORGANIZED BY ROMANIAN INHABITANTS (IN 1944) TO SAVE THE JEWS FROM HUNGARY AND NORTHERN TRANSYLVANIA

Antonio Faur*

Abstract

The author updates the points of view expressed by some Jewish intellectuals (in memorial and scientific texts, interviews, occasional accounts) in reference to the rescue actions carried out by the Romanian inhabitants from Transylvania, at the border between Hungary and Romania. Certain important truths have been emphasized since more perseverance was needed in order to recover them. The same desideratum is also valid in the case of the existing, factual material, which represents a talking point of the finding in the final report on the Holocaust, that is the fact that the Romanian territory has become, especially in the year 1944, "a refuge place for the Jews" who managed "to cross the border (with the help of some guides, through channels organised by Romanian inhabitants - n.n.) from Hungary and Northern Transylvania.

Keywords: *Standpoints, Jewish Memoirists, Saving Jews, Hungary, Northern Transylvania*

A historical problem of great interest, the solidarity and rescue actions of some Jews from a certain death, beyond compassion for those who were the victims of an unparalleled collective tragedy, have been invoked and evoked by publicists and historians, by memoirists and other personalities of the international cultural-scientific life. The Romanian chapter depicting these experiences, of certain significance, can undoubtedly be placed next to the one that happened on the French-Spanish border where the clandestine manner took precedence. In European context, Spain and Romania were, for many Jews, areas of freedom because they offered real chances to save the Jews from the European countries occupied or under the domination of Nazi Germany.

When drafting the present paper, we guided after the assertion made by the historian from Iași, Alexandru Zub, in the preface of the first issue of a magazine meant to recover some aspects of the Jewish community life on the Romanian territory: "If history, as a speech, usually begins by answering about the majority population of an area, in time it starts to do recovering gestures for smaller communities they lived together with and who naturally become part of the ineffable fabric of the history in that area"¹. The academician Nicolae Cajal subscribed to this interpretation, arguing that "writing the Jewish history cannot be imagined outside the Romanian

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¹ Alexandru Zub, *În loc de prefață*, in "Studia et acta historiae iudaeorum Romaniae", no. I, 1996, p. IX.

history”². A position of common sense and responsibility in relation to the realities of the past, as there are no parallel histories (unless for teaching reasons) but a common history with all its avatars.

We should mention that historians are the best informed on the historical sequence of the Holocaust, as there has been a constant concern for the actions to rescue the Jews over the Romanian-Hungarian border in Romania. There has also been the phenomenon of denial or minimization of the Jews’ rescue by their crossing the border into Romania, starting precisely with individuals. Such example is provided by Eszter Görö, who - in her testimony (1992) - states the following: “For decades after August 23, 1944, the entire rescue action of the Jews has been passed over in silence in Romania. There has never been any writing connected with it anywhere”³. And still, there have been some extremely honest and significant references in the book written by the journalist Katona Béla, published in Oradea in 1946, with the title *Várad a Viharban*⁴ (Oradea in the Storm). It was written and published in Hungarian, so the author of the above statements⁵ had the chance to read it, if she were interested in the truth⁶ regarding the actions to rescue some Jews from Hungary and Northern Transylvania by the Romanian diplomats from the General Consulate of Romania in Oradea⁷, and by other people (especially Romanian peasants from the settlements near the Romanian-Hungarian border who played the risky part of guides).

From this point of view we should keep in mind that, at the Conference of the Jewish Democratic Union (held in Cluj on March 3, 1945), dr. Leon Goldenberg presented a report containing also a subchapter entitled Escape actions from Northern Ardeal and Hungary, from where we write down

² Nicolae Cajal, *Cuvânt înainte* for the first issue of the magazine “Studia et acta historiae iudaeorum Romaniae”, no. I, 1996, p. VIII.

³ See Zoltán Tibori Szabó, *Frontiera dintre viață și moarte. Refugiul și salvarea evreilor la granița româno-ungară (1940-1944)*, Cluj-Napoca, Editura Compania, 2005, p. 120.

⁴ See the excerpt (from the book) reproduced in “Magazin istoric”, no. 6, 1976, p. 38, explaining the way in which the members of the General Consulate in Oradea drafted a memorial (on the Jews’ situation in the Transylvanian ghettos, emphasizing the tragic events in the one from Oradea), later sent to the International Red Cross (with its headquarter in Berne).

⁵ Undoubtedly, there were other comments on this theme, which means that before criticizing a reality (in categorical terms) it is better to carry out a “minimum” documentary of the issue in question and the historical context which was decisive, since the Soviet occupiers established - in the first post-war decades - what could be published in Romania, with a special reference to Jews.

⁶ It seems that, in this case, it is about a political reaction and not about a useful scientific evaluation.

⁷ Béla Katona, *Várad a viharban*, Nagyvárad, 1946. He, who was in Oradea (in 1944) and therefore knew -first handedly - everything that had happened, makes the following comments about the role of the Romanian diplomatic staff in Oradea in order to save some Jews from death: “The Romanian [General] Consul in Oradea (dr. Mihai Marina-n.n.) and almost every member of the Consulate tried to help the Jewish fugitives run away from town. Not once the car (in fact three cars belonging to the members of the Consulate -n.n.) crossed rapidly the border, loaded with Jews who had escaped from the ghetto in Oradea” (subl.ns.-A.F.). Therefore, after August 23 1944, such points of view appeared in Romania (that had been seized by the Soviet Union, together with other Central European countries).

an edifying fragment: “what has been done to save the [Jewish]refugees remains a heroic page forever..., there were some people who, by endangering their lives before the eyes of the ruthless Gestapo, brought people over the border in daylight but especially at night”⁸. Undoubtedly, the inhabitants of the settlements near the border had rather strong and fresh memories of their actions to rescue the Jews.

Thirteen years later, the secretary of the Jewish community in Turda (in 1944), David Arnold Finkelstein, published in Haifa a memorial book with an undisputable documentary value as it contains the testimony of one of the most important participants in the rescue actions of the Jews and their providing with documents (fake, of course) and guiding most of them to Bucharest. From this local Jewish leader (with official positions and within “the Jewish church in Turda”⁹), we have left some touching lines which we write down in full, yet also mentioning the fact that, in our opinion, they are under the sign of truth and honesty:

“One evening in June 1944, in front of the Jewish church in Turda, a short, thin peasant was walking impatiently on the pavement, wearing clothes typical of the region of the Apuseni Mountains. He was surprised by my asking him:

«What are you doing here? »

«I...I...you know...I am looking for the Jewish priest», he mumbled.

«Well, come with me, I am the priest»

I led him straight into the «laboratory».

«Now, tell me why you are looking for the Jewish priest - I said after I invited him to sit».

The peasant from Apuseni Mountains told me that he was from a remote village in the mountains, at the border. 7-8 days before, five men knocked on the gate and told him that they were Jewish refugees from Hungary and asked him to let them hide inside his house. And he welcomed them: «Well, they told him - they are only people with God’s soul». They had been living in the stall attic ever since. He also fed them. This is what he had and what they wanted to eat: some polenta, milk, eggs, onion, radishes and some beans...

But he is a poor man, he has many children and he is running out of the little corn he has. Neither he nor his guests have any money to buy a few things from the village. He offered to come to Turda to get them some food because he knew there were some Jews here. He came on foot, over the mountains for three days and three nights for more than 120 km. He took a little cloth bag hanging from his neck, from underneath his shirt, revealing a letter... which he handed me in... The small letter was written in Hebrew and was addressed to the Rabi in Turda. It followed that the people who had written it were from Sălaj. Two of them were the Rabbi’s sons-in-law from

⁸ See Gheorghe I. Bodea, *Tragedia evreilor din nordul Transilvaniei*, Cluj-Napoca, Editura Hiperion, 2001, p. 315.

⁹ *Ibidem*, p. 163.

Jibou, Reb Mose Frenkel. They stayed hidden for eight weeks, until they reached this little village concealed in the mountains...

Moreover, the letter fully confirmed the things told by the peasant from the Apuseni Mountains... my heart was filled with joy and my eyes with tears of gratitude, and I was about to hug him and kiss his unshaven, prickly face.

Here he was, as I said to myself, a simple, ancestral peasant who had grown up in the immensity of the mountains, far away from any modern human civilization and culture and yet he was above tens and thousands of contemporary, civilised and cultured people.

He is not interested in law or danger. He does not reckon or hesitate. He welcomes Jews in his house, Jews who are hiding; he provides them shelter, a hiding place. He takes the meagre food from his own mouth and that of his children's and shares it with them.

He walks for hundreds of kilometres in order to help them. And all of these simply because they «are also people with God's soul».

Where is that man with the highest degree of culture, the bearer of the honourable order scarf, of the Nobel Prize who would do all these just as he does them?

If I were a sculptor, I would carve the statue of man after him!
How different this globe called the Earth would beif it was inhabited by simple peasants living in the Apuseni Mountains and not by cultural, civilised beasts..."¹⁰

This episode left a strong mark on Finkelstein's memory, by the example given by a simple man, animated by a genuine Christian spirit ("Love your fellow man"!), capable of risks and sacrifices to help his peer in an extremely difficult situation. This homage paid to the peasant from the Apuseni Mountains honours its author, being one of the most convincing testimonies regarding the actions carried out by the Romanian villagers (and not only), to save the refugee Jews from Northern Transylvania and Hungary.

Referring to other Jews in the mentioned area, the same memoirist makes two more comments that deserve our attention. In the former he mentions that some of them, "by risking everything" (in other words, even their life), "headed towards the Romanian border and most of them succeeded, after long and great difficulties, in reaching the Romanian territory", whereas some of them had disappeared "in a bold attempt"¹¹.

It is also remarkable the manner in which Finkelstein, expresses his gratitude towards those Romanian intellectuals who showed their discreet or open support for the Jewish refugees: "Fortunately, it happened (in Romanian.n.) in a quite significant number, really well-meant officials, with a humanistic thinking, who acted as such ...I still must add, for the sake of the truth, that among these officials ... there were, indeed, some who were led by humanitarian noble feelings, by an extremely sincere good-will, acting (in the case of the Jewish refugees -n.n.) in way that deserves all our gratitude"¹².

¹⁰ *Ibidem*, pp. 315-317.

¹¹ *Ibidem*, p. 151.

¹² *Ibidem*, p. 156.

A victim of the Holocaust (confined in the ghetto of Cluj and later deported to the Auschwitz-Birkenau camp), Oliver Lustig tried to reveal, through some literary writings, the terrible tragedy lived by the Jews who had the same fate as he did. Moreover, he wrote a mostly memorial book in which he also appeals to documentary information worthy of interest, focussing on some facts that belong to the issue we are dealing with. Thus, in a passage of his book, he offers us true explanations regarding the psychological impact of the ghettoization, the disorientation and inability of some people to make decisions that would lead to saving solutions. It is true that some of the situations were impossible, like the one the mentioned author refers to: "The Romanian friends of Nora Dimantstein's family wanted to help them save themselves, to escape to Romania. But her parents were elderly. Moreover, her father was ill. That is why she could not think of such an adventure: «At least, let your daughter help them» their friends insisted.

Nora was struggling day and night. She could not decide. She asked her father what to do. «He neither prevented me nor encouraged me to do it». «Do as you wish, he said, I am old, who knows how long I live...» I kept silent. I was about to cry. Suddenly my father told me: «Could you leave your mother? » I kept silent again, trying to choke back my tears (...) and I stayed. The rebellion, aversion and fear had urged me to leave. My conscience and love for my parents prevented me from doing so. The latter ones were stronger.

Now that I have lost my family, I would not have peace if I had left them. I would never forget that I had abandoned them in difficult moments. Yet I cannot forget the kindness of so many Romanians who tried to protect us from the misfortune that was about to happen to us. It would be hard to enumerate their names, as they were countless¹³. From the perspective of this paper, such statements of a certain moral probity are strong arguments¹⁴, which cannot be challenged by any history fan or its interested interpreter.

One should notice the insistence of the Chief-Rabi (of the Neolog Community) in Cluj, Moshe Carmilly-Weinbeger, when he talked about the ways in which the Jews were rescued in 1944 and about the necessity of them being researched from a historical point of view. He was wondering, for good reasons, (in 1988), "why was it written or discussed so little about the Romanian action to help the Jews? Why hasn't history been written as it is yet?"¹⁵ In an interview published by *Magazin istoric*, the same personality considered that "it is an elementary moral duty not to forget and to emphasize

¹³ Oliver Lustig, *Jurnal însângerat*, București, Editura Militară, 1987, p. 220.

¹⁴ We agree, as a supporting reasoning, with the following remark made by a Jewish Rabi: "Not even God can undo some facts that have happened" (as cited by Gheorghe Bodea, *op. cit.*, p. 334).

¹⁵ *Almanahul Luceafărul* 1989, p. 132; Gheorghe I. Bodea, *op. cit.*, p. 332. A year earlier, Itzak Artzi was convinced that one would find "a historian that would deepen in all the details in order to retell this extraordinary epic (of the Jews-n.n.), because of which 4,000 Jews were saved from deportation (and total destruction - n.n.)" (Gheorghe I. Bodea, *op. cit.*, p. 343).

the fact that, during those years in Romania, there was a ray of humanity that the Jews benefited from". It is unfortunate that "a serious, comprehensive book on the rescue operations that took place in Romania and with the Romanians' help is still missing"¹⁶. This is the more as "there have been two ways to save the Jews in Romania: through Romania or through the Pyrenees in Spain"¹⁷. We bear in mind one of the conclusions of the mentioned interview: "In any case, there was undoubtedly a single possibility for the Jews to escape the iron circle of the Nazi terror, a single hope to save themselves in the space of the Central and South-Eastern Europe... Romania was willing to receive Jewish refugees... and we, the Jews, are grateful for this"¹⁸.

Few Jewish personalities have persisted in showing the true meanings of the actions to rescue the Jews which were organised by the Romanian inhabitants. In another interview given in October 1992, Moshe Carmilly-Weinberger genuinely praised the rescuers: "Since the history of the Holocaust starts with the first labour camps, the history of survival starts with the first actions against the Nazi policy. From the simple people - the guides who provided illegal border crossing - to the intellectuals and public personalities, most Romanians showed a brave attitude, as opposed to the Nazi extermination plans, in Transylvania during 1940-1944"¹⁹.

In his turn, the historian Randolph Braham expressed, in 1989, relevant opinions regarding the actions to save "the Hungarian Jews", which, to his mind, represent "a special aspect of the Jewish issue in Romania"²⁰ at the end of the World War II. "After March 1944 - as the author of the most reliable studies and books on the effects of the Holocaust on the Jews from Horthy Hungary points out - the Nazi measures to exterminate the Jews were introduced in Hungary while Romania became - as I have shown in one of my books - a real oasis for the thousands of Jews hunted and led towards the gas chambers and crematoria of Auschwitz"²¹. The American specialist, originally from Transylvania, also concluded that the solidarity between the Jews from Hungary and Northern Transylvania was due "first and foremost to the

¹⁶ Moshe Carmilly-Weinberger, *1940-1944. În acele vremuri grele, poporul român și-a păstrat demnitatea și omenia*, in "Magazin istoric", 1989, no. 10, pp. 40-41.

¹⁷ *Ibidem*.

¹⁸ *Ibidem*.

¹⁹ Manase Radnev, *Poporul român și-a salvat credința în omenie*, in "Magazin istoric", 1992, no. 10, p. 27. On another occasion, the former Chief-Rabi of the Jewish Neolog Community in Cluj confesses in these precise terms: "Today I have a perspective that allows me to appreciate the significance of rescuing the Jewish refugees...in a bloody and inhuman world. Let me state that we would have been incapable to do this operation (of saving the Jews from Hungary and Northern Transylvania -n.n.), unless we had been helped by some Romanian with a humanist thinking. The words of the Talmud come to my mind: "Whoever saves a man saves an entire world". It is the thought I send wholeheartedly to the Romanian people, when I want to thank them for the help given to the Jews from Northern Transylvania", (Constantin Mustață, *Reconstituiri*, București, Editura Militară, 1991, p. 66).

²⁰ Randolph L. Braham, *România - o adevărată oază pentru evrei în cel de-al doilea război mondial*, in "Magazin istoric", 1989, no. 3, p. 36.

²¹ *Ibidem*.

Romanian people and their traditional humanity”²². As a natural conclusion to these considerations, Randolph L. Braham considers that “the Romanians did their best to help as many Hungarian Jews as possible cross the border. Once in Romania, they were not subjected to any unreasonable constraints. Thousands of Hungarian Jews fraudulently crossed the border in Romania, since the date Hungary started their massive deportation. Most of them settled down in Bucharest, Arad and Timișoara”²³.

A special place in our selection of representative texts, signed by Jewish intellectuals, is held by Elie Wiesel’s assertions, a world class writer who was offered the Nobel Prize for literature. In one of his books, published in Romanian as well (with the title *All Rivers Run to the Sea... And the Sea is Never Full*), one can find, besides many anthological pages, an exceptional account on “Brave Maria”, a peasant from Maramureș, who behaved with such kindness and warmth that impressed him deeply, for the rest of his life. Here is the portrait made by this great novelist to this Romanian peasant woman: “... there is also Maria. She again, always she. I have spoken about her, I come back to her. Brave, courageous, faithful, God-fearing, always pleased with her fate... She joined us whenever we went on holiday. She took part in our celebrations and our mourning.

She left us only when the government (the Hungarian one - n.n.) forbade the non-Jews to work for the Jews. That day, she cried and swore she would come back as soon as «all these would end».

She often sneaked in the ghetto passing through barriers and barbed wire in order to bring us cheese, eggs, vegetables and fruit. This Sunday night, she will also come. How did she manage to slip through the reinforced security cordon, placed by the gendarmes around the half empty ghetto? «Oh, no big deal», she said in a broken voice. «One can enter and get out. I know a safe place».

I wanted to tell you... to beg you... the cabin in the mountains... is ready... come to my place, there is nothing to be afraid of... you will live in peace... there are no Germans where we live. No villains to drag you after them. Come on...

Brave Maria... So, I rejected Maria’s miracle. I sometimes think of her with affection and gratitude... with perplexity as well.

This simple woman, completely devoid of culture, rose, from the moral standpoint, high above the intellectuals, the notables and clergy in the town ...

My father had many connections and even friends in the Christian community, yet none of them could manifest the spiritual force of this peasant woman with her wounded heart...

²² *Ibidem*.

²³ *Ibidem*, p. 37. In another place, the same American historian concluded that “Romania has provided shelter to the Jewish refugees from neighbouring countries, including several thousands of Jewish refugees from Hungary”, See Gheorghe I. Bodea, *op. cit.*, p. 351.

At that time, a naive and bigoted Christian woman, lacking in pretensions or grandiloquence, was the one who saved the soul of our city”²⁴.

As the president of the International Commission for the Study of Holocaust in Romania, Elie Wiesel has signed an important message, in which, among other things, he noticed the involvement of the Romanian inhabitants in the actions to rescue the Jews and concluded with a justified question: “... why were there so few ? those who were «brave and courageous», risking «their own lives», thus saving «the honour of their nation» by opposing the fascist oppression and murder of «their Jewish fellow citizens». All those who showed such «virtues» deserve our deepest gratitude”²⁵, concluded this contemporary of ours who knew the horrors caused by the Holocaust, as well as some realities in connection with the phenomenon in question, specifically the one of the real contribution brought by some Romanians to the rescue from a certain death of some Jews living in Hungary and Northern Transylvania, by their fraudulent crossing over the border in Romania. Originally from the small town of Sighet, Elie Wiesel maintained, also by these reflections, the relationship with his homeland, praising the spirit of human solidarity shown by its inhabitants, among which Maria is an emblematic figure.

I recalled, on this occasion, some of the standpoints expressed in various places (memorial and scientific tests, interviews and occasional accounts) by reputable Jewish intellectuals in reference to the rescue actions carried out by the Romanian inhabitants from Transylvania, at the border between Hungary and Romania. The authorised voices of these personalities are unanimous when emphasizing some little known facts, which must be investigated with more perseverance in order to discover a consistent factual material, as an unbeatable argument of the finding in the same final report that the Romanian territory has become, especially in 1944, “a refuge place for the Jews” who managed to “cross the border (with the help of some guides, through channels organised by the Romanian inhabitants -n.n.) from Hungary and Northern Transylvania”²⁶.

The only way to explore the past in order to actively maintain the memory of some facts, whether with a positive or negative impact on the present, is by systematically bringing into actuality the historical testimonies of this nature.

²⁴ Elie Wiesel, *Toate fluviile curg în mare... și marea nu se umple*, București, Editura Hasefer, 1997, 2000, pp. 69-70; Gheorghe I. Bodea, *op. cit.*, pp. 18-19.

²⁵ Elie Wiesel, “Mesajul președintelui Comisiei Internaționale pentru studierea Holocaustului în România”, in Tuvia Friling, Radu Ioanid, Mihail E. Ionescu (ed.), *Raport final*, Iași, Editura Polirom 2005, p. 15.

²⁶ Tuvia Friling, Radu Ioanid, Mihail E. Ionescu (ed.), *op. cit.*, p. 293.

THE SOVIET UNION AND THE TRANSYLVANIAN ISSUE (1944-1947)

Cornel Sigmirean*

Abstract

The agreements between the Allies at Tehran, Moscow and Yalta gave Russia the initiative in concluding the treaties with the East European countries. Thereby, the Soviet political and military authority became the decisive factor of the implementation of communism in the Eastern countries. Significant for the subordination policy led by Russia is the way in which it managed to handle the national issues and the territorial disputes. From this point of view, the study presents the role played by General Susaïkov, the head of the Allied Control Commission in Romania, in the Romanian-Hungarian disputes in the period 1945-1947.

Keywords: *Romanian-Hungarian Relations, Soviet Union, Paris Peace Conference*

The “Transylvanian issue” was unquestionably of prime concern to the Romanian diplomacy during the period preceding the Paris Peace Conference¹.

At the Potsdam Conference, the Council of Foreign Ministers representing the four great Powers (the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics, the United States of America, the United Kingdom and France) was formed for the purpose of drawing up the peace treaties with Italy, Romania, Finland, Hungary and Bulgaria. Nonetheless, the peace in Eastern Europe was directed by Moscow. By rejecting Churchill’s plan regarding the landing of the Anglo-American troops in the Balkans, which was presented at the Tehran Conference in 1943, Stalin was assured of the subjection of Eastern Europe at the end of the war. The Moscow Conference in October 1944 simply admitted a de facto state of affairs. This also applied to the eastern border of Romania. At the Tehran Conference, it was agreed that the territories conquered by the Soviet

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¹ For the history of foreign relations of Romania between 1944 and 1947, see: Nicolae Baciş, *Agonia României. 1944-1948. Dosarele secrete acuză*, Editura Dacia, Cluj-Napoca, 1990; Valeriu Fl. Dobrinescu, *România și organizarea postbelică a lumii (1945-1947)*, Editura Academiei Republicii Socialiste România, Bucureşti, 1988; Idem, *România și Ungaria de la Trianon la Paris (1920-1947). Bătălia diplomatică pentru Transilvania*. Bucureşti, Editura Viitorul Românesc, 1996; Valeriu Fl. Dobrinescu, Doru Tompea, *România la cele două Conferințe de pace de la Paris (1919-1920, 1946-1947). Un studiu comparativ*, Focşani, Editura Neuron, 1996; Ion Enescu, *Politica externă a României în perioada 1944-1947*, Bucureşti, Editura Științifică și Enciclopedică, 1979; Ștefan Lache, Gheorghe Țuțui, *România și Conferința de pace de la Paris din 1946*, Cluj, Editura Dacia, 1978; Liviu Țirău, *Între Washington și Moscova. Politicile de securitate națională ale SUA și URSS și impactul lor asupra României (1945-1965)*, Cluj-Napoca, Editura Tribuna, 2005.

Union between 1939 and 1940 would remain all under the control of the latter.

There was genuine uncertainty about the situation of Transylvania. Article 19 in the Armistice Agreement of 13 September 1944 concluded by Romania and the Allied Powers stipulated the return of Transylvania to Romania.

“The Allied Governments regard the decision of the Vienna Award regarding Transylvania as null and void and are agreed that Transylvania (or the greater part thereof) should be returned to Rumania, subject to confirmation at the peace settlement, and the Soviet Government agrees that Soviet forces shall take part for this purpose in joint military operations with Rumania against Germany and Hungary”².

The ambiguous message of the article referring to Transylvania, “or the greater part thereof”, constituted a reason for hope in Budapest, but it gave rise to concern in Bucharest. In a series of programmes, the *Kossuth* radio station presented the idea according to which Hungary should follow the example of Romania, that is to say breaking off the alliance with Germany³. In the commentary regarding the Agreement, the Hungarian B.B.C. drew attention to the article about Transylvania indicating that “Definite frontiers will be established at the Peace Conference”. The B.B.C. broadcaster, Candidus, set forth that “it is in the best interest of Hungary to come close to the Allies”, as Romania did, “to make a step forward to its salvation”⁴.

The uncertainty regarding the future of Transylvania also stemmed from the decision made on 14 November 1944 by the Allied Control Commission, i.e. the Soviet Union, settling that Transylvania would be under Soviet administration until a democratic Government was established in Bucharest⁵. The Soviets used thus Transylvania as blackmail against Bucharest. It was only after the establishment of the pro-Communist government of Petru Groza that Stalin submitted his approval to the Soviet Government regarding the Romanian administration in Northern Transylvania.

The manner in which the Soviets formulated Article 19 in the Agreement and the manner in which they managed the “Transylvanian issue” reveal the real political standpoint of Moscow: using Transylvania as an element of compulsion and subjection of Romania to the U.S.S.R. hegemony in the region⁶. There is no doubt that the Soviets tried to put

² *Apud.* Mihnea Romalo, *România în al doilea război mondial (1941-1945)*, Editura Vestala, Bucureşti, 2001, p. 140.

³ Valeriu Fl. Dobrinescu, *România și organizarea postbelică a lumii (1945-1947)*, Editura Academiei Republicii Socialiste România, Bucureşti, 1988, p. 55.

⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 56.

⁵ Marcela Sălăgean, *Administrația sovietică în Nordul Transilvaniei (noiembrie 1944-martie 1945)*, Cluj-Napoca, Fundația Culturală Română, 2002, pp. 71-146.

⁶ See T.M. Islamov, T.A. Pokivailova, Onufrie Vințeler, *Din culisele luptelor pentru Ardeal*, Cluj-Napoca, Editura Eikon, 2003; more recently, Alexandru Ghișa, *Adevărul despre*

Transylvania into play as compensation in favour of Romania for the loss of Bessarabia and Northern Bukovina.

Moscow officially disagreed with the decision of the Vienna Award according to which Northern Transylvania was ceded to Hungary. In July 1946, a Report of the Romanian Ambassador in Warsaw, I. Raiciu, which was submitted to the Vice-President of the Council of Ministers, Gheorghe Tătărescu, reproduced the dialog with the Soviet Union Ambassador. At some point during the visits of the Hungarian Prime Minister in Washington, London and Paris in order to obtain some promises regarding the modification of the borders with Romania, the Soviet Union Ambassador told I. Raiciu that “the viewpoint of U.S.S.R. regarding the rights of Romania concerning Northern Transylvania is not of recent date, but it dates back to 1941. When your troops were fighting against us on the territory of our country, I heard Generalissimo Stalin saying that the Vienna Award must be nullified and Northern Transylvania returned in its entirety to Romania”⁷.

The statement of the U.S.S.R. Ambassador is incompatible with other standpoints of Moscow. During the war, Stalin also considered the possibility to obtain neutrality of Hungary in exchange for Transylvania⁸. In 1944, according to the American historian L. Watts, a commission headed by M. Litvinov was created in Moscow in order to analyse the post-war issues. On 5 June 1944, in a document entitled *Despre Transilvania*, which was sent to Stalin, Molotov, Voroșilov and Visinski, the commission stated that “the recognition of the independence of Transylvania, apart from all alliances and federations, was the best solution”⁹.

Moscow agreed with the return of Transylvania to Romania, but it also cunningly gave the impression that it might change its attitude. Furthermore, Budapest and the ethnic Hungarians of Transylvania might have understood that Moscow could have been the most trustworthy guardian of the Hungarians in Romania.

Thus, on 17 July 1946, following the numerous memorials submitted by the Government of Budapest¹⁰ to the Council of Foreign Ministers, General I.Z. Susaikov, the head of the Allied Control Commission in Romania, sent a “Note” to the Vice-President of the Council of Ministers of Romania and Minister of Foreign Affairs, Gh.

cedarea Ardealului. 30 august 1940: Transilvania și iar Transilvania, in “Istorie și civilizație”, no. 12, September 2010, pp. 35-42.

⁷ Archive of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, *Conferința de pace de la Paris din 1946*, Dosar 61, p. 41.

⁸ Larry L. Watts, *Ferește-mă, Doamne, de prieteni. Războiul clandestin al Blocului Sovietic cu România*, Editura RAO, București, 2011, p. 141.

⁹ *Ibidem*, p. 147.

¹⁰ See Cornel Sigmirean, Corneliu Cezar Sigmirean, *România și Ungaria în fața Conferinței de Pace de la Paris: 1945-1947*, Editura Universității “Petru Maior”, Tîrgu Mureș, 2010.

Tătărescu¹¹. The said “Note” included severe accusations against the policy of the Romanian Government concerning the Hungarians in Transylvania: the plants, land and movable and immovable properties that were owned by the Hungarians and that were under the control of CASBI were in most cases sold; the land reform affected 300,000 Hungarians, the majority of which were smallholders; abuses were committed in the application of the Law on the annulment of deeds concluded in Northern Transylvania after the Vienna Award; late payment or failure to pay salaries to Romanian teachers etc.

Following the address of General I.Z. Susaikov, Gheorghe Tătărescu sent a comprehensive “Note” including a reply to each and every accusation made indicating that: “All complaints made by the Hungarians and referred to you are groundless and are made for the sole purpose of propaganda in relation to the works at the Peace Conference”¹².

The complaints referred to the Allied Control Commission in Romania have been made in response to the stipulation in the Draft Peace Treaty with Romania drawn up at the Meeting of Foreign Ministers of the great Powers in Paris on 7 May 1946: “The decision of the Vienna Award of August 30, 1940, is declared null and void. The frontier between Roumania and Hungary existing on January 1, 1938, is hereby restored”¹³.

Thus, the Hungarian Minister of Foreign Affairs, Gyöngyösi János, requested the U.S.S.R. Ambassador in Budapest to arrange an unofficial meeting with Molotov, the Minister of Foreign Affairs of the Soviet Union, but his request was denied. Despite that, a delegation headed by the Prime Minister, Nagy Ferenc, left for Washington, London and Paris¹⁴. The decision of 7 May 1946 was final and it was incorporated in the Peace Treaty concluded by Romania and the Allied and Associated Powers on 10 February 1947.

The approach of the Soviet Union concerning the Transylvanian issue, beginning with the Armistice Agreement in September 1944 and ending with the peace treaties signed, proves that Moscow, profiting from the passiveness of the Anglo-American leaders, played a substantial role in what the political decisions pertaining to Eastern Europe were concerned.

¹¹ Archive of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, *Conferința de pace de la Paris din 1946*, Dosar 63, p. 32.

¹² *Ibidem*, f. 63, pp. 35-42.

¹³ Cornel Sigmirean, Corneliu Cezar Sigmirean, *op. cit.* p. 16.

¹⁴ Valeriu Fl. Dobrinescu, Ion Pătroi, *Selecție și studiu introductiv, Documente franceze despre Transilvania*, Editura Vremea, București, 2001, p. 51.

Annexes

Translated from Romanian. The original document is available in Russian.

MINISTRY OF FOREIGN AFFAIRS
ALLIED CONTROL COMMISSION
17 June 1946
No. Iu-748
Bucharest
TO THE ATTENTION OF G. TĂTĂRESCU,
VICE-PRESIDENT OF THE COUNCIL OF
MINISTERS OF ROMANIA

I have been informed on the following:

1. The plants, land, movable and immovable properties that are owned by the Hungarians and that are under the control of CASBI are in many cases sold by auction.

2. Under the pretext of the housing crisis in Northern Transylvania, the Hungarians are evicted from their homes. Moreover, the Hungarians are evicted from the homes they have lived in for a long time so that the Romanians be able to settle therein.

3. The ruling of the People's Court (*Tribunalul Poporului*) of Cluj is biased.

4. The Land Reform of 1945 has affected approximately 300,000 Hungarians, the majority of which are smallholders. The expropriation is proved to be made with no written orders, and consequently no appeal may be filed against illicit expropriations. Furthermore, the local Hungarian peasants are excluded from the Committees for the allotment of land ownership, and thus they cannot benefit from the land reform.

5. The Courts ruling on the actions for annulment of deeds concluded in Northern Transylvania after the Vienna Award immediately seize the movable properties in order to sell them by auction. In Northern Transylvania, pursuant to this law, the Romanians enter upon the property they owned before, as opposed to the Hungarians in Southern Transylvania, despite the fact that their properties have been taken away under the same circumstances.

6. For all companies and cooperatives, commercial and industrial enterprises, trading companies and farms that are owned by the Hungarians, there have been appointed administrators.

7. The fiscal authorities collect taxes three or five times higher based on the businesses and ledgers of the Hungarian companies. Furthermore, the activity of the Hungarian cooperatives in Transylvania is limited because they do not receive any commodities upon the common distribution of the funds.

8. The Hungarian teachers are not paid or they are paid two to three months later than the Romanian teachers; the Hungarians meet with difficulties in their attempt to obtain certificates; the existence and activity of the Hungarian schools are not recognised.

I would be grateful if, in the shortest time frame possible, maximum 2-3 days, you could establish the legitimacy of the detailed and precise information I have received, and if you could explain the measures that the Government takes or will take to solve the deficits and settle the issue of the Hungarian nationality.

Vice-President of the Allied Control Commission in Romania
General-Colonel of Tank Troops

/ss/ I. Susaikov
15/06/1946.-

I hereby certify that the above text is a true and accurate translation of the original text:

A. Goian

AMAE [Archive of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs], File 63, f. 32

Bucharest, 19 July 1946

Nr.28.139
General,

Following your address no. Iu-748 of 17 June 1946, I am honoured to inform you on the following:

All complaints made by the Hungarians and referred to you are groundless and are made for the sole purpose of propaganda in relation to the works at the Peace Conference.

The Allied Control Commission is aware of the sincere policy adopted by the Romanian democratic Government in sympathy with the cohabiting nations, especially the Hungarian population in Transylvania. Pursuant to this policy, all measures have been taken in order to ensure full equality of treatment of the Hungarians that are Romanian citizens, and support for their cultural, religious and economic institutions. The demands of this population have been always thoughtfully considered and met to the greatest extent possible by the Romanian Government. Therefore, the Government has always maintained close contact with the representatives of the Hungarian People's Union (*Uniunea Populară Ungară*).

Moreover, the heads of this Union and the Hungarian press in Romania have always expressed their satisfaction with the measures taken by the Romanian Government and their willingness to cooperate with the latter.

Please find below the answers to the matters detailed in your address:

1. Stating that plants, land, movable and immovable properties that are owned by the Hungarians and that are under the control of C.A.S.B.I. are in most cases auctioned is absolutely erroneous.

You are already aware of the fact that the goods owned by the enemy (Germans and Hungarians) are managed by C.A.S.B.I. in compliance with the provisions of article 8 of the Armistice Agreement and according to the instructions of the Allied Control Commission. None of the goods that are owned by the enemy and that are under the administration of C.A.S.B.I. has been sold by auction, and cannot be sold since the Armistice Agreement and the law on the organisation of C.A.S.B.I. stipulate solely the preservation of these goods. Until now, none of the goods that are owned by the enemy and that are under the administration of C.A.S.B.I. has been leased; the Allied Control Commission has not approved leasing yet.

I must underline that, throughout the entire Transylvania, the properties owned by Hungarians that are Romanian citizens are not subject to the provisions of article 8 or the law on the organisation of C.A.S.B.I. These provisions apply only to Hungarian citizens, to enterprises in which Hungarian citizens have over 20% interest, and to all persons of any ethnic origin who allied themselves with the Fascist, German and Hungarian armies, who enrolled as volunteers or who showed solidarity with these armies. The properties owned by these persons remain under their provisional custody until final directions, if the said persons came back, or under the custody of their relatives, if any.

In order to examine the claims of the persons entering this category, a special commission has been formed. If this commission notes that the said persons have left for the enemy countries for reasons different from those mentioned above, their claims are approved and the General Commissioner of the Government for the relations with the Allied Control Commission decides the restoration of the property.

The Prefectures together with the democratic political organisations, including the Hungarian People's Union, carry out investigations into this matter.

2. It is not at all true that, in Northern Transylvania, under the pretext of the housing crisis, the Hungarians are evicted from their homes. The provisions pertaining to the commandeering of houses for refugees or deported persons returning to the country uniformly apply throughout the entire country, and no difference is made from the point of view of ethnicity of the persons concerned. No Hungarian in Northern Transylvania has been evicted from his home because he is Hungarian. Nevertheless, no privileges may be created for the Hungarians. Article 33 of the prevailing Law on rents (which also applies in Northern Transylvania) stipulates that the owners, who have been deported or refugees, shall comply with the provisions of the lease agreements that have not been concluded in the presence of the said owners by local

authorities, or by the administrators appointed by them, and the validity of the said agreements shall be extended as of right. The owners or the former tenants, who are deported or refugees and who return, may request that the current tenant be evicted so that they can move back in their former homes. However, the courts have the right to rule on the partitioning of the house between the owner, or the former tenant, and the current tenant, should the latter justify his staying in town and should this solution be deemed most equitable. The interests of the current tenants are thus fully guaranteed.

Furthermore, in Northern Transylvania, many Romanian civil servants and teachers, who have been refugees, have no homes particularly because the Hungarians occupying them could not be evicted. For this very reason, many refugees have not been able to return to Northern Transylvania, yet.

It is also incorrect to state that Hungarians have been evicted from the homes they have lived in for a long time so that the Romanians be able to settle therein. No resettlement has been organised in Romania. A great number of Hungarian citizens and former civil servants of the Hungarian State are still living in Northern Transylvania, even though they have no right to live in Romania, and a part of whom should have been withdrawn by the Hungarian Government, in compliance with the provisions of the Armistice Agreement concluded by Hungary and the Allied Powers on 20 January 1945 in Moscow. Nonetheless, it is natural and fair that the Romanian peasants, smallholders, who have been banished from their lands and expelled by the Hungarian authorities during the occupation of Northern Transylvania, return to their homes and that the Hungarians, who have unlawfully settled in the properties of the Romanians, be forced to leave. Yet, in this extraordinary situation, it is not about homes that have been occupied "for a long time" by the Hungarians, but about recent and abusive occupancy.

3. The People's Court of Cluj has been created to try cases of war crimes committed in Transylvania during the Hungarian Horthyst occupation in the north, and the Romanian Fascist dictatorship in the south. Considering the fact that most of the crimes, such as deportation in concentration camps in Germany of the entire Jewish population and the assassination and torture of a great number of Romanian inhabitants, have been committed in Northern Transylvania, where all civil servants and especially the officers and gendarmes were Hungarian, it is natural that the majority of the persons heard by this court be Hungarian nationals.

Moreover, most of the Hungarian war criminals have fled to Hungary and have been convicted in absentia by the People's Court of Cluj. This is why none of the death sentences ruled against those criminals could be enforced.

On the other hand, the People's Court of Cluj has also convicted Romanian war criminals and guilty defendants, who have been actually arrested. The People's Court of Bucharest has been declared competent regarding the cases concerning the main Romanian war criminals, and has ruled numerous convictions. This court has not heard any Hungarian.

It will be noted that among the judges and public prosecutors of the People's Court of Cluj, there were also Hungarian persons. No complaint has been formulated by the political representatives of the Hungarians in Romania, or their press, against the sentences ruled by the People's Court of Cluj.

4. The land reform has been implemented in the same manner and following the same rules throughout the entire country. No difference has been made from the point of view of nationality of the expropriated owners or peasants who have been apportioned land. It is not at all true that 300,000 Hungarians are affected by the land reform and that a large number of them are smallholders. The truth is that, throughout the entire Transylvania, the total number of expropriated Hungarian owners does not exceed 5,000. This figure is thus 60 times smaller than that notified to the Allied Control Commission.

It is true that out of the 5,000 Hungarian owners, a small part of them are peasants, smallholders who are subject to the provisions of article 3 of the property law according to which the collaborationists, those who fled to enemy countries after 23 August 1944 and those who volunteered to fight against the United Nations are expropriated regardless of their ethnic origin. This system applying to Hungarian smallholders in the abovementioned cases was subsequently modified by the provisions of the Ministry of Agriculture, according to which properties less than 5 hectares cannot be expropriated in such cases. The provision regarding the expropriation of collaborationists that are smallholders applies only to the Germans in Transylvania.

Stating that expropriation is made without written orders, which would not allow the owners to bring an appeal, is incorrect. All the decisions of the communal Committees are drawn up and posted at the town hall, so that the Hungarian and the Romanian owners be able to bring an appeal.

Last, but not least, it is not at all true that the Hungarian peasants are excluded from the Committees for the apportionment of land, and thus they do not benefit from the land reform. In all communes, the rural Committees for the application of the land reform have been constituted proportionally to the ethnic distribution of the population. The Ministry of Agriculture ensured that these provisions were appropriately enforced. In this way, in the communes inhabited only by Hungarians, the entire committee included Hungarians. Moreover, the chairmen of the appeal committees in each rural district have been appointed according to the

proposals of the county council of the democratic parties, including the representatives of the Hungarian People's Union. Thus, Hungarian chairmen of rural district commissions have been appointed in many multiethnic rural districts. In the three Transylvanian counties where the majority of the inhabitants are Hungarians, all the chairmen and members of the rural district commissions are Hungarian. The same rule applied to the creation of the county commissions for counselling regarding the land reform; therefore, in the commissions that have been formed in the counties inhabited only by Hungarians or in multiethnic counties work Hungarian chairmen or members. Finally, even in the Central Commission for land reform affiliated with the Ministry of Agriculture, a Hungarian member has been appointed, who participates in all works regarding the apportionment of the Hungarian peasants.

The following figures prove that the Hungarian peasants are fully benefiting from the land reform. In Odorhei, Trei-Scaune and Ciuc counties, where the majority of the population is Hungarian, 85-95% of the peasants who have been apportioned land are Hungarians. This percentage exceeds even the percentage of Hungarian inhabitants in the said counties. In the other Transylvanian counties, the proportion of Hungarian peasants who have been apportioned land is just. For example, it will be noted that 8,000 Hungarian peasants have been apportioned land in Cluj County, and 3,700 in Mureş County.

5. Regarding the law on the annulment of deeds concluded in Northern Transylvania after the Vienna Award, I would like to mention that, when the Courts seize the properties subject to proceedings, this measure acts only as a guarantee. These properties have never been auctioned. Furthermore, almost none of the cases under this law have been tried. Meanwhile, the Ministry of Justice examines the opportunity to implement a similar law in favour of the Hungarians in Southern Transylvania who are dealing with the same issues.

6. The statement that, for all commercial and industrial enterprises owned by Hungarians and also for cooperatives and farms, there have been invariably appointed administrators is not accurate and tendentious. With the exception of the industrial and commercial enterprises that are owned by German or Hungarian citizens and that are under the administration of C.A.S.B.I., pursuant to article 8 of the Armistice Agreement, the Romanian State has appointed supervising administrators for a number of enterprises that, regardless of the nationality of the owners, have carried out activities to the detriment of the State politically or economically speaking. Out of 2,000 enterprises in this category, only approximately 30 are owned by Hungarians. The rest of them are enterprises that are owned by Germans that are Romanian citizens, or even Romanian enterprises.

No supervising administrator has been appointed by the State for a Hungarian cooperative. Furthermore, although the law on cooperation

stipulates that, for all cooperative federations, the Ministry of Cooperation shall appoint three members in the Board of Administration, the State has used this right only in what the Romanian cooperatives are concerned, and not in relation to the two Hungarian cooperative federations in Transylvania, in order not to affect the Hungarians.

As far as the Hungarian farms are concerned, administrators have been appointed only for those whose owners were absent. Point 1. above regarding the implementation of the C.A.S.B.I. law is hereby clarified.

7. The taxes and financial laws in Romania are applied regardless of the ethnic origin of the taxpayers. The Ministry of Finance is not aware of any complaint filed against the method of taxation of Hungarians in Romania.

The tax laws uniformly apply throughout the entire country and do not establish different categories of taxpayers. Both Hungarians and Romanians are thus subject to the same taxes.

As for the higher levels of taxation of ledgers that are not filled out in Romanian, this is a provision of a law of 1941 in order to cover the expenses related to the translation of these ledgers. This measure, which did not apply only to Hungarian ledgers, was abrogated by the law of 6 April 1946; therefore the translation fees are currently born by the State.

The complaint that the cooperatives in Transylvania do not receive any commodities from the authorities is groundless. The truth is that, because of the insufficient amounts of commodities, they have to be distributed very rationally. Considering the organisation of the Romanian State, the most rational method is the distribution of commodities per county, proportionally to the rural population. In the Transylvanian counties, the Hungarian cooperatives, including those that are not registered under the National Institute for Cooperation (*Institutul Național al Cooperăției*), not only have they not been excluded from the distribution of commodities, but they have received special amounts. Since the Hungarian cooperatives are grouped in regional federations irrespective of the administrative division in counties, the distribution cannot be made through these cooperative federations, but directly to each Hungarian cooperative unit.

8. I shall clarify each item under this point in your letter as follows:

a) It is true that, in the first months following the reinstatement of the Romanian administration in Northern Transylvania, payment of both Hungarian and Romanian teachers was inevitably delayed because of the fact that these teachers have not been considered when the budget was established, and they could not be immediately included. However, the Romanian and Hungarian teachers have received important advance payments. By the end of April 1946, all remainders and differences in salaries owed to Hungarian teachers and schoolmasters following their inclusion were paid, which is confirmed by a written declaration of the Hungarian People's Union of Romania made on 19 June 1946 stating that

“as of 1 April 1946, since the Hungarian education is part of the State’s budget, the Hungarian teaching staff from public and denominational schools in Northern Transylvania receive their salaries in the same manner as the Romanian teaching staff. In Southern Transylvania, the Hungarian teachers are paid without considering degrees because their inclusion has not ended yet”. Moreover, for 1946/1947, the Ministry of National Education allocated a budget of 25,919,507,900 lei for the Hungarian schools of all grades and categories, out of which 23 billions represent salaries. This budget has been established in compliance with all the requirements of the representatives of Hungarian schools.

b) Regarding the difficulties met by the Hungarians in obtaining the degrees, it will be noted that, as far as the certificates of the teachers and the degrees of the students are concerned, the Romanian Government has not discriminated the Hungarians in Romania. I hereby quote from the abovementioned declaration of the Hungarian People’s Union of Romania: “we note that the schoolmasters in Northern Transylvania have been granted tenure without undergoing examination, and the tenure of public school teachers is granted after undergoing proficiency examination in front of a Hungarian commission, as provided by law. Even though all bachelors holding a university degree in Romania must undergo this examination, even if they were granted tenure in 1940-1944, those holding Hungarian teacher degrees have been granted tenure without undergoing proficiency examination, as provided by ministerial decisions”. As far as the degrees and certificates of the Hungarian students are concerned, I hereby quote the statement of the union of the Body of Teaching Staff (*Corpul Didactic*) of Cluj, organisation including Hungarian teachers: “We are not aware of any actions of the Romanian Government impeding the grant of degrees. On the contrary, generous measures have been taken. Among others, all school certificates granted to public school or private school students and the high school degrees, even though, formally, they do not comply with the standards provided in the Romanian education law, grant the same rights as those issued by the Romanian schools”. These testimonies prove that the complaints notified are groundless.

c) The statement that the existence and activity of Hungarian schools is not recognised is absolutely incorrect. In Northern Transylvania, there are 1,649 Hungarian elementary schools and 170,571 pupils. Out of the 1,649 schools, 780 are public schools, 650 denominational schools, 234 public elementary schools and 30 denominational elementary schools. There are 4,108 schoolmaster jobs, 2,567 of which in public schools and 1,541 in denominational schools; that is to say one schoolmaster to 40 pupils, whereas in Romanian schools in Northern Transylvania, there is only one schoolmaster to 60 pupils. In order to occupy these jobs, approximately 1,000 retired persons, substitute teachers or even schoolmasters, who are not

Romanian citizens, have been employed because of the shortage of qualified teachers. The Hungarian inspectors are in charge of the administrative organisation, management and control of these schools.

In what the secondary schools are concerned, the following Hungarian schools with Hungarian teachers, who are paid by the Romanian State, are operational in Northern Transylvania: 77 academic high schools, 15 teacher training schools, 8 secondary business schools and 6 technical or vocational schools, totalling 106 secondary schools with 22,997 students. These schools issue certificates that are approved by the Romanian State and granting the same rights as those issued by the Romanian schools. The high school degree is issued after undergoing examination in front of commissions including Hungarian teachers. Furthermore, the proficiency exams for Hungarian secondary school teachers are validated by commissions formed by Hungarian members. The Hungarian inspectors are in charge of the administrative organisation and control of Hungarian secondary schools, as it is the case of the elementary schools.

I must add that, in order to ensure complete education for the Hungarian population, the Romanian State has founded a Hungarian University in Cluj with four schools: Law, Literature, Medicine and Science. 68 departments have been created in this University, 15 Seminars/ Forums, and 202 jobs for auxiliary teaching staff. The courses are attended by 2,244 students who benefit from the same support from the State as the Romanian students. The University includes clinics, laboratories, a large library and a pedagogical seminary.

In order to occupy the created jobs, Hungarians who are not Romanian citizens have been employed.

To conclude with, I may say that Hungarian education in Romania is ensured in an appropriate manner and that the situation of the Hungarians is at least as good, if not better than that during the Hungarian regime. Considering all the above, the union of the Body of Teaching Staff of Cluj states: "Both Hungarian and Romanian schools are organised and treated in the same manner. The obligations undertaken by the Romanian State towards the Hungarian schools are fulfilled in the same manner as those regarding the Romanian schools".

Regarding the nationality matter referred to at the end of your address, please consider the following:

The Law of 4 April 1945 on the regulation of citizenship of the inhabitants of Northern Transylvania stipulates that Romanian citizenship is granted to all persons who were Romanian citizens before the Vienna Award. Thus, the majority of the Hungarians in Transylvania have been granted again Romanian citizenship.

There are only two exceptions:

a) the inhabitants who, as of 30 August 1940 (date of the Vienna Award) and until 4 April 1945, chose a citizenship different from the Hungarian citizenship;

b) the inhabitants in Northern Transylvania who voluntarily enrolled in the army of an enemy state or in a foreign military or paramilitary organisation.

Thus, in the first category are not included the Hungarians in Northern Transylvania who, together with the Romanians living in that territory, obtained Hungarian citizenship as of right after the Vienna Award, but the Hungarians who, leaving for Hungary from Southern Transylvania, have formally and voluntarily chosen Hungarian citizenship.

Moreover, point b) above does not apply to the Hungarians from Northern Transylvania who were forced to serve the Hungarian army. The Regulation of 4 April 1945 stipulates that it is about the "inhabitants of Northern Transylvania who voluntarily enrolled in the military service of a state fighting against Romania after 23 August 1944, or those who voluntarily left the territory of Northern Transylvania during the retreat of the enemy armies and who showed solidarity with these armies." I believe these provisions are fully compliant to the democratic principles and the anti-fascist position on which the policy of the Romanian Government is based. I also believe that the Romanian Government cannot be requested to grant Romanian citizenship to the persons who have voluntarily chosen the citizenship of a foreign state or to the former Romanian citizens who adopted the fascist ideas and left the Romanian territory when the Romanian army was fighting together with the Soviet army against the invading Fascist armies.

It stands to reason that Romanian citizenship cannot be granted to the persons who settled in Northern Transylvania during the Hungarian occupation and who were not Romanian citizens before the Vienna Award.

Respectfully yours,

VICE-PRESIDENT OF THE COUNCIL OF MINISTERS

and

MINISTER OF FOREIGN AFFAIRS

To the attention of

General-Colonel of Tank Troops

S. S u s a i k o v

Vice-President of the Allied Control Commission
in Romania.

BUCHAREST.

AMAE, File 63, f. 35-42.

BUCHAREST IN THE PERCEPTION OF A BRITISH DIPLOMAT (ERIC TAPPE, 1944-1946)

Maria Costea*

Abstract

This article aims to present the perception that a British diplomat had on the political, social and everyday life of Bucharest in 1944-1946. The diplomat wrote personal letters to his parents, explaining them the situation of the Romanian capital city and evaluating the Romanian realities by using British standards. Many dimensions of the Romanian social and cultural life had their correspondent in Great Britain, and at the same time, some Romanian specific characteristics were enjoyed by the British diplomat.

Keywords: Bucharest, Image, Diplomat, Tappe, Elite, British

This article studies the image of the capital of Romania from a British perspective at the end of the World War II from a historical perspective¹. It is focused on the perception that a British diplomat had on the political, social and daily life of Bucharest in 1944-1946. The Diplomat Eric Tappe was a well-prepared philologist and he knew Romanian well. As a military, he trained for a parachuting mission in Romania. But after 23rd August 1944, he joined the British military mission in Bucharest as a diplomat. The letters to his family have a number of interesting perceptions on the daily life in the capital of Romania².

The British diplomat's letters to his parents have the advantage that they are different from the diplomatic and intelligence reports. These letters provide details on the impact the

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¹ See also relevant works as: ****Călători străini despre Țările Române*, București, Editura Științifică, vol. 1-5, 1968-1973, vol 6-8, 1976-1983, București, Editura Academiei Române, vol 9, 1997; Nicolae Bocșan și Valeriu Leu, *Identitate și alteritate. Studii de imagologie*, Reșița, Editura Banatica, 1996; Simona Nicoară, *Istorie și imaginar*, Cluj-Napoca, Editura Presa Universitară Clujeană, 2000; Ștefan Borbely, *Experiența externă*, Iași, Editura Institutul European, 2011; Carmen Andras, *Călătorind între metafore: reprezentări ale Bucureștiului la britanici*, in "Anuarul Institutului de Cercetări Socio-Umane „Gheorghe Șincai” al Academiei Române”, nr 10, 2010, pp. 77-88; Keith Hichins, *România în 1866-1947*, București, Editura Humanitas, 1996.

² Eric Tappe, *Scrisori din București / Letters from Bucharest (1944-1946)*, Cluj-Napoca, Editura Limes, 2006 (Preface by Brian Davis).

political life in Bucharest had on the residents and important perceptions on daily life in Romania. The details are significant and give a nuanced and emphasized image on what the Soviet occupation meant and the specific methods of repression of the democratic opposition. The letters contain the personal opinions and perceptions of Eric Tappe, which he sent to the members of his family, being honest, humanizing the political history and giving it colour. Such issues confirm, deepen and give detailed and nuanced accounts of the official reports of the time, or of the press. Tappe's comments are of great value, since their author is still a professional diplomat and representative of the British Army, with special training and experience.

Bucharest under the Soviet military occupation in the British diplomat's opinion

On 4th July 1945, at the concert given on the occasion of the "American Independence Day", the British diplomat met Prime Minister Groza and Deputy Prime Minister Tătărescu: „close-up I thought they looked awful crooks”. At the same concert, the democratic opposition leader, Iuliu Maniu, “looks definitely old and low”³. The description that the British press gave for Deputy Prime Minister Tătărescu: “boneless wonder” is excellent, in Tappe's opinion. In September 1945, Groza and Tătărescu returned from Moscow by plane, ordering that the “citizens” meet them at the airport “with joy”. The Communist Party gathered groups of workers and took them there by trucks to organize the demonstration which eventually lacked excitement. In the first of the 20 official cars column, Petru Groza represented the smiling face of a “detestable regime”⁴.

The pro-communist regime organized groups of violent activists who brutally attacked the protesters who demonstrated in honour of King Michael's birthday in front of the Royal Palace and of the Athénée Palace Hotel on 8th November 1945. The regime used about eight trucks with workers who attacked the pro-monarchist crowd with stones. Then the “Tudor Vladimirescu” Division and other pro-government forces fired guns at citizens, killing even students. Despite the repression, the scale of the demonstration proves the citizens' commitment to the constitutional monarchy, to democracy and the pro-Western policy. Concerning the enthusiastic crowd, the British diplomat noted: “The crowd demonstrating in honour of the King's birthday received us with rapture and carried us shoulder high to the Palace door. When we came out it was the

³ *Ibidem*, p.102.

⁴ *Ibidem*, p 126. See also Joseph Rotschild, *Întoarcerea la diversitate. Istoria politică a Europei Centrale și de Est*, București, Editura Antet, 1997.

same thing...When I came back the scene was fantastic. In front of the Athénée Palace, the crowd was dancing national dances to the band, while at the far end the Communists were firing from the Ministry of the Internal Affairs)"⁵.

About the brutality of the repression, Tappe noted: "Finally about 8 lorries formed up and drove abreast into the crowd... the Communists were throwing stones from the lorries... In the course of the afternoon the Russian-trained Tudor Vladimirescu troops (traitors from the Romanian point of view) barred all approaches to the square. They certainly fired down the crowds. The whole thing was revolting. The crowds were demonstrating peacefully on behalf of the King, who is their bulwark of liberty. The communists came and provoked incidents and made the crowd more furiously anti-Government than ever. The victims of the firing were all sorts of people, including schoolboys and students. I have always detested this quisling Communist Government, and I do so more than ever now"⁶.

Daily life in Romania represented by the British military diplomat

The British diplomat was very impressed by the traditional Romanian food, the hospitality of the people, the climate, the natural scenery, the prices of the goods and the relatively good supply, the cultural life. "I cannot imagine any other country in Europe where I could do so well", Tappe wrote⁷. His intellectual Romanian friends often invited him to have a meal either at home or at restaurants where there were Gypsy musicians who would sing to the customers on each table individually. In wartime, the Romanian elite had more abundant food than Tappe's parents, who lived in England.

The supply of goods in Romania in 1945 was of interest to a Westerner. In Romania, Tappe bought some things his family in England needed. The prices in Romania were profitable for the British buyer, although relatively high for the Romanians. Comparatively, the prices were higher in Turkey, too high even for the British standards. For the weekend trips Tappe and his Romanian friends used the cars of the British Embassy. Snagov and Sinaia were among the favourite destinations of the Romanian elite and foreign diplomats, due to the landscapes and comfortable accommodation. The weekend trips were opportunities to enjoy the Romanian fruit and vegetables, which he received plenty as a gift on his rural visits. "The grapes and the tomatoes are the best things I've struck in this country". The British diplomat wished that his parents had been able to taste the Romanian grapes, which were "like the

⁵ Eric Tappe, *op cit*, p. 146.

⁶ *Ibidem*, p 146.

⁷ *Ibidem*, p.91.

very best hothouse grapes in England”⁸. Also, the Romanian intellectuals had given him so many books regularly, that the Englishman had an impressive library.

During the war, the British diplomat was surprised to find a high standard of living in the elite circles in Bucharest: abundant food, the luxury in the Athénée Palace Hotel where he was staying, the number and size of the parties organized in this city. In the British diplomat’s opinion, the Romanians ate a lot and liked meat in large hunks, instead of thin slices. In restaurants, they served delicacies and huge meals, just as before the war, and the frequent and prolonged parties were on the agenda. The only product that did not exist in Bucharest was coffee, instead of which they had “ersatz”.

He noticed that there were no buses, and for this reason the trams were always crowded. In general, he wrote towards the end of 1944: “There are not many things that can be sent from Great Britain”, because all the necessary goods could be found in Bucharest as well.

Fond of the family values, the British diplomat could find direct evidence that family life was as real in Bucharest as it was in London or Sheffield. He was excited about the Christmas traditions, which he observed in December 1944.

The religious life is important in Romania. He was surprised to see that in Romania taking the veil was an option even for some “very young and pretty girls”⁹. He visited, among others, the Plumbuita Monastery, that it did not have artistic value, in his view.

Most of the roads in Romania were far from the standards the Englishman was accustomed to. He finds that: “The suburban roads are awful; mud and stones. Even in the cities the paving is often very bad”¹⁰. The roads in the country (e.g. Bucharest-Pitești-Craiova) were destroying the cars and punctured tires were the most common events. “No English car could last any time in Romania, except on one or two asphalt roads...Fortunately the American cars are built for this sort of thing”.¹¹ In 1945, in the suburbs of Bucharest there were outbreaks of typhus, which he had to go around and change his schedule of visits.

The suburbs of Bucharest and many villages in Wallachia and Oltenia were characterized by “oriental squalor” in the mind of the English officer. Instead, he was delighted by the level of civilization in the Saxon cities and villages of Transylvania (Brașov, Sibiu, Prejmer, Hărman, etc.), the “fortified churches”, the nobles' mansions. “This clean, prosperous „Saxon” towns and villages are a

⁸ *Ibidem*, p.122.

⁹ *Ibidem*, p.70.

¹⁰ Eric Tappe, *op cit*, p.70.

¹¹ *Ibidem*, p.118.

delight after the oriental squalor of the Wallachian villages”, Tappe wrote¹². (On the same line, after several decades, one of his illustrious compatriots, Prince Charles, was so fascinated by the same region that bought several Saxon homes in Transylvania¹³, expressing his commitment to the region in a programme of great impact on Travel Channel in 2011¹⁴.) As for the urban areas of Wallachia, most of them were not notable for spectacular cultural sites. He considers Curtea de Argeş as “the only attractive town in Wallachia; most of the towns are very dull”¹⁵.

He noted that Bucharest had an intense artistic-cultural life, numerous opera performances of the highest quality, theatre and parties with folk dances. The books seemed very cheap to him and the newspapers - abundant. He appreciates the quality of the children's books which were illustrated. The records with western music met the English standards, but they were cheap. Herăstrău lake area was comparable to certain areas in Brussels.

In Bucharest and in other cities, in January 1945, there were “old fashioned” theatres where, among others, French films were on, with subtitles in Romanian¹⁶. The theatres and concert halls were always packed¹⁷.

The Institute of History in Bucharest organized conferences, which the British diplomat considered similar to and of the same quality level in organization as the events of the same kind in England. Such was the lecture on topics of prehistory, supported by professor and archaeologist Nestor in February 1945¹⁸. Tappe had the opportunity to visit the archaeological site at Glina, where Nestor worked. A new “English Library” was opened in Bucharest, attended by the British diplomat. The Romanian Academy, which he visited, was considered similar to the “Bodleian reading room” or to the “British Museum reading room”, on a smaller scale, of course¹⁹. But he also noted a striking difference: “The one thing that would tell you at once that you’re not in England is the smell of garlic! My

¹² *Ibidem*, p.96.

¹³ Damien Gayle, *Blue bloods: Prince Charles joins campaign to save Transylvania's forests - because of his family connections to 'Count Dracula'*, in <http://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-2054061/Prince-Charles-joins-campaign-save-Transylvanias-forests-inspired-family-connections-Count-Dracula.html#ixzz1gA48Xibu>

¹⁴ *Prince Charles: I have a stake in Transylvania's future*, 11.10.2011, in <http://www.independent.co.uk/news/people/news/prince-charles-i-have-a-stake-in-transylvanias-future-2376584.html>

¹⁵ Eric Tappe, *op cit*, p.140.

¹⁶ *Ibidem*, p.51.

¹⁷ *Ibidem*, p.131.

¹⁸ *Ibidem*, p.55.

¹⁹ *Ibidem*, p.55.

British soul was shocked to find garlic in such a scholarly atmosphere”²⁰.

The Romanian elite spoke excellent French and English, at least in the circles he frequented. However, the journalists did not really know English and kept on spelling the English names incorrectly. Some intellectuals conversed in English with the Anglo-Americans²¹. Many ladies played the piano at home for their guests²².

He was impressed by the sympathy which the Romanian elite had for Great Britain. Both the elite and the crowd expressed their sympathy and support for the representatives of the Western powers, even though they were under the terror of the Soviet occupation.

Tappe was delighted with the rural nobles' mansions of Wallachia, Oltenia and Transylvania, which he visited. He had the feeling that in these mansions, an idyllic nineteenth century life was being lived, amidst the general political tragedy triggered by the Soviet occupation that overwhelmed Romania, which will end the beautiful aspects of the life he described²³. The history confirmed that²⁴.

In conclusion, the diplomat evaluates the Romanian realities, by using British standards. He describes the Romanian elite as a European one, with good standards and local color. So the British author was easily integrated in the social, cultural and daily life of the European Romanian elite. Many dimensions of the Romanian social and cultural life had their correspondent in Great Britain, and in the same time, some Romanian specificities were delighting for the British diplomat. However, the Soviet occupation brutally stopped this European way of life in Romania and also its beautiful local specificity.

²⁰ Eric Tappe, *op cit*, p.58.

²¹ *Ibidem*, pp.71-73.

²² *Ibidem*, p.83.

²³ *Ibidem*, p.131.

²⁴ Mihai Bărbulescu, Dennis Deletant, Keith Hitchins, Șerban Papacostea Pompiliu Teodor, *Istoria României*, București, Editura Enciclopedică, 1998, pp. 468-496; Gheorghe Măndrescu, Giordano Altarozzi, editori, *Comunismo e comunismi. Il modello Rumeno*, Cluj-Napoca, Editura Accent, 2004.

RUSSIAN-FRENCH CONTRADICTIONS CONCERNING THE POSSIBILITY OF ROMANIAN ARMY'S EVACUATION IN RUSSIA IN THE YEAR 1917

Hadrian Gorun*

Abstract

This study deals with the possibility of the Royal Romanian Army's evacuation in the Russian territory for reorganization. This problem generated tension in the relations between the Allies, especially between France and Russia. During 1917, this represented a key-problem of the discussions between the three diplomacies (French, Russian and Romanian) and the military representatives. Of course, each party wanted to promote its own interest. These interests were influenced by the situation on the front, by the evolution of the military operations. There were also disputes and different points of view on this matter, which altered the quality of the cooperation. The Russian proposal concerning the evacuation of the Romanian Army, authorities and population was rejected from the very beginning by France. General Henry Mathias Berthelot, Chief of the French Military Mission in Romania, expressed a strong point of view against the withdrawal to Russia. The psychological condition of the Romanian troops would have been seriously affected. For French diplomacy and French officers, the reorganization of the Romanian Army on the Moldavian territory represented a guarantee of its utility. Romania's King, Ferdinand energetically rejected the idea of the evacuation. The French Minister from Iași, Count Charles de Saint Aulaire also persuaded the Romanian Government led by Ion I.C. Brătianu that the evacuation had been a hazardous operation. On the other hand, the Russians insisted for the solution of withdrawal. It is possible that they attempted to subordinate the Romanian Army. Finally, the Romanian Army and authorities remained on the national ground.

Keywords: Army, Evacuation, Reorganization, Russia, France, Ferdinand, Berthelot, Saint-Aulaire.

In 1917, one of the most important aspects of the political, diplomatic and military relations between France and Romania represented the possibility for Romanian Royal Army to go in Russia. It was to be reorganized on Russian territory. An intense correspondence took also place on this topic and the Romanian-French-Russian negotiations were very assiduous. Of course, each part wanted to promote its own interest. There were also disputes on this topic and dissensions as in the previous autumn concerning the army from Salonic or the military and material Russian aid. This year, the misunderstandings influenced negatively the quality of the co-operation between Romanian and Russian Armies.

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At the beginning of January 1917, The Russian General Headquarters considered the organization of the Romanian troops at the back of the army of operations impossible and too dangerous. Thus, it recommended this action should take place in Russia in order to remove any danger for Romanian Army, facilitating its training and its supply¹.

Confronted with Russians' claims who intended to impose to Romanian authorities the place of the reorganization for the army, Romania's King expressed his will that his troops should remain as long as possible in the current zone and leave for Basarabia only in the case of major force situations. There they were to be quartered in the region Bălți - Chişinău. Cautious, the Chief of the Romanian General Staff, Constantin Prezan negotiated with Russian Government the right of the Romanian Army to pass and to establish itself there.² Even French Military Mission was reluctant to the idea of a withdrawal in Russia for the Romanian Army, Commander Henri Mathias Berthelot expressing strong arguments in the favour of its keeping in Romania. From military point of view, such an action would mean a delay more than two months. Then one must also take into account the difficulties of instruction and material reorganization in a new country in which the relations between administrative, governmental and military centres would hardly be established. General Berthelot also emphasized moral arguments, insisting on the risk of a possible depression of the Romanian Army after its crossing the border. The political arguments added to those already mentioned. Romanian population felt fear towards Russians. These fears were amplified by the incidents on the front and on the back of the front. On the other hand, the event that King Ferdinand leaves his kingdom could negatively influence neutral countries and the opinion of the other Allies³.

However, on January 4th, 1917, the Russian Government took seriously into account the possibility of transferring the diplomatic body and Romanian authorities in Russia. As a

¹ Arhivele Militare ale României (A.M.R.), Fond *Marele Cartier General*, Dosar (D.) 286, fila (f.) 97.

² *Ibidem*, ff. 65 - 66.

³ Archives du Ministère des Affaires Etrangères Français (A.M.A.E.F.), Série *Guerre*, Sous-Série *Opérations Stratégiques-Militaires*, D. 1026, ff. 229-230; Jean-Noël Grandhomme, Michel Roucaud, Thierry Sarmant, *La Roumanie dans la Grande Guerre et l'Effondrement de l'Armée russe*, Paris, L'Harmattan, 2000, p. 146; Dumitru Preda, *România și Antanta 1916-1917. Avatarurile unei mici puteri într-un război de alianțe*, Iași, Institutul European, 1998, p. 183.

reply to Russian intents, Count Charles de Saint-Aulaire, the France's Minister plenipotentiary to Iași proceeded to sustained efforts together with his English and Italian colleagues, Sir George Barclay, respectively Baron Carlo Fasciotii. He also informed Russia's Minister to Iași, Mossolov that the refuse of the Russian troops to defend at least Moldavia placed the Empire of the Czars in a humiliating hypostasis⁴. Unfortunately the insufficiency of the means of transportation, a matter never improved, did not allow the bringing of strong reinforcements in good time⁵. In their competition with the French for influence in Romania, it seemed that the Russians have made some advance in the winter of 1917 when General Vladimir Sakharov became King Ferdinand's nominal deputy. Then General Berthelot was appointed to a position apparently without importance, namely the Inspector of the Romanian troops. Thus, Sakharov began to insist that all Romanian units undergoing rehabilitation under the supervision of General Berthelot should cross the Prut river in order to be quartered on Russian territory.

The Russian General had similar discussions with the Romanian Chief of Staff, Constantin Prezan. Romanian Government and King Ferdinand energetically rejected Russian demands. Ferdinand declared that he would never separate himself of his army. In fact, the Romanian authorities realized that Petrograd had planned the subordination of the Romanian Army, the limitation of the King's prerogatives, although he was the Supreme Commander. The Russian political and military officials wanted to gain for their army all the war materials sent by France to Romania, via Arhanghelsk harbour⁶.

A little time after the transfer of the Romanian General Headquarter to Bârlad, the Commander of the Russian Military Mission from Romania, General Mikhail Beleaev, required, on the behalf of the state he represented that Romanian and Russian Armies be commanded by General Sakharov. In his opinion, the Romanian General Headquarters should be eliminated and absorbed by the Russian one. This inadmissible request could not be fulfilled,

⁴ Service Historique de l' Armée de Terre (S.H.A.T.), Série *Cabinet du ministre*, Carton 5N 200, telegram no. 9, January 4th, 1917, signed Saint - Aulaire; A.M.A.E.F., *Guerre, Roumanie*, D. 345, f. 16.

⁵ A.M.A.E.F., *Guerre, Roumanie*, D. 345, f. 16.

⁶ *Ibidem*, p. 102; Constantin I. Stan, *Regele Ferdinand I „Întregitorul” (1914-1927)*, București, Editura Paideia, 2003, p. 82.

because there were also difficulties of legal nature. According to the Constitution, the Supreme Commander of the Army was the King, while according to the law of the siege state, the Romanian General Headquarters assumed a few of the prerogatives of the Council of Ministers⁷. Trying to subordinate the Romanian Army, the Russian military authorities projected its division in two components: one of them was to go to Poltava and the other one to Caucaz. The Romanian Minister to Paris, Lahovari informed French Government about the dangerous situation that would have been created if Russian projects had been materialized⁸.

With the aim of determining a more energetic action of Russian troops on the Romanian territory, which has often withdrawn without fighting, Romania's Prime-Minister Ion I.C. Brătianu and the Prince Successor Charles visited Petrograd in January 17th, 1917. On his way to Russia's capital, General Berthelot halted for a day in Iași, where he met Mossolov. He attempted to demonstrate him the necessity of the reconstitution for the Romanian Army the national territory⁹. If King Ferdinand energetically disagreed the sending of the Romanian Army and officials in Russia, the Government and the General Staff tended somehow to assume the point of view of the Russian authorities arguing that it was the sole solution for the salvation in the event of Moldavia's invasion. Maybe a few political and military officials wanted to prevent new sacrifices. The Minister plenipotentiary Saint-Aulaire and General Berthelot were aware that the reorganization of the Romanian Army on the national territory had represented the only one viable solution for the perpetuation of the French influence in Romanian Kingdom and in Balkans¹⁰. That is why they did their best to rally to their point of view all the decision makers from Romania. Due to these efforts, the president of the Council of Ministers, Ion I.C. Brătianu decided to plead for the reorganization of the Royal Army on the Romanian soil at the Petrograd Conference¹¹.

⁷ Ion G. Duca, *Memorii*, vol. IV, București, Editura Machiavelli, 1994, p. 133, *apud*. Constantin I. Stan, *op. cit.*, p. 82.

⁸ A.M.A.E.F., *Guerre, Roumanie*, D. 345, f. 25.

⁹ *Ibidem*, telegram no. 32, January 17th, 1917 and telegram no. 7, January 17th, 1917, signed Saint -Aulaire.

¹⁰ *Ibidem*, telegram no. 65, January 31th, 1917, signed Saint - Aulaire; See also Carton 5N 140.

¹¹ *Ibidem*, Carton 5N 200, telegram no. 66, January 31th, 1917, signed Saint - Aulaire.

Every step taken by France and England to Russia for the keeping of the Romanian Government and Romanian Army on the Moldavia's territory had to be followed by a collective demarche to the Government from Iași for an immediate evacuation of many refugees in Russia. General Gurko suggested this solution as a condition for the maintenance of the Royal troops during his discussions with the commander of the French Military Mission. The fulfilment of this issue was very important for French diplomacy. The refugees had to be evacuated. Otherwise, Moldavia's supply would have become impossible¹². The issue concerning the keeping of Romanian Army on the national territory or its evacuation to Russia represented also one of the topics of the Allies' Conference from Petrograd. In the first decade of February 1917, France attempted to do its best to negotiate successfully the reorganization of the Romanian troops in Moldavia. At the beginning, General Berthelot was not invited to these conferences. That was a real blow for his authority and his presence was necessary because he knew very well the Romanian Army¹³.

The French diplomacy has always insisted for the reorganization of the Romanian troops in Moldavia. This represented a guarantee of its efficiency.

In order to facilitate the transports of war materials and provisions for Romanian troops Generals Berthelot and Gurko agreed on February 9th, 1917 that 200,000 refugees should be evacuated in Russia. Subsequently, the Romanian Army should remain on the national territory. Its supply should be provided by the Russian railways¹⁴. The lack of provisions required a decision making as soon as possible¹⁵. The evacuation of the civilians represented a difficult process because of the inefficiency of the assigned trains. There were many sick people and wounded and starvation, typhus and cholera as well. The lack of coaches made impossible the evacuation of the civilians using the roads¹⁶.

¹² *Ibidem*, Carton 5N 140, coded telegram no. 73, February 3th, 1917, signed Saint-Aulaire.

¹³ *Ibidem*; Constantin I. Stan, *Regele Ferdinand I „Întregitorul” (1914-1927)*, București, Editura Paideia, 2003, p. 82.

¹⁴ A.M.A.E.F., *Guerre, Roumanie*, D. 345, ff. 88-91.

¹⁵ S.H.A.T., *Cabinet du ministre*, Carton 5N 140, coded telegrams no. 858-860 of the Commander of French Military Mission to the War Minister to General Commander-in-Chief.

¹⁶ *Ibidem*, coded telegrams of the French military attache from Petrograd to the War Minister and to General Commander-in-Chief, February 25th, 1917.

At the end of February 1917, the matter of the evacuation was still unsolved. The prime-minister Ion I.C. Brătianu disagreed with the evacuation of the civilians and of the army as well¹⁷. But Quai d'Orsay considered that the departure of the weak elements from the army and of a part of civilians was necessary¹⁸. In Odessa, General Berthelot had to adopt all the measures to make the transportation of the civil population practically possible. Unfortunately, the available train cars had no heating, and the temperatures were still quite low at the end of the winter. France's Ambassador at Petrograd, Paléologue emphasized to Russian Minister of Foreign Affairs, Nikolai Pokrovski, the political and humanitarian reasons for Romania's supply, keeping its army on the national territory¹⁹.

As a matter of fact, Moldavia's alimentary situation was much more difficult than it seemed to the authorities from Petrograd. The evacuation of the 200 000 civilians (number already mentioned) and of all army did not represent a viable solution. The lack of provisions would have led to a disaster. Saint-Aulaire noticed realistically: "If I insisted together with General Berthelot for the evacuation of a part of civilians... I did like this to make Russian General Staff give up its main reason for the evacuation of the army. This measure would mean the departure of the King and of the Government being more dangerous than ever... This would also mean the renunciation of the aid of a 200 000 people army, that was to be reorganized and Germany would have a decisive argument for the conclusion of a separate peace of Bucharest"²⁰. King Ferdinand represented a national symbol, and if he had left the country together with his government, the Central Empires would have been able to achieve their political and military objectives.

The correspondence between Romania's Queen Mary and the members of the Russian Imperial family proved that the King had never taken into consideration the hypothesis of leaving his country, even if the army had been transferred in Russia. The Romanian Royal House expressed its firm will to remain in Moldavia²¹. Although the Russian Government

¹⁷ *Ibidem*, *Attachés militaires en Roumanie*, Carton 7N 1457, coded telegram no. 1140 of the Commander of the French Military Mission from Russia to War Minister and General Commander-in-Chief, February 27th, 1917.

¹⁸ A.M.A.E.F., *Guerre, Roumanie*, D. 345, f. 161 bis.

¹⁹ S.H.A.T., *Cabinet du ministre*, Carton 5N 140, coded telegram no. 266, February 28th, 1917, signed Paléologue.

²⁰ A.M.A.E.F., *Guerre*, D. 345, ff. 162-163.

²¹ *Ibidem*, f. 185.

insisted for the evacuation of the Romanian Army in Russia, it did not adopt a similar attitude concerning Romanian Royal family, its presence on the soil of the homeland being perceived as a guarantee for the salvation of the dynasty. The authorities from Paris acted in the same way²².

If in March 1917, the authorities from Petrograd refused energetically the evacuation of the civil population, on contrary they insisted on the transportation of the army on the Russian territory²³. Nevertheless, at least, a few French military officials, leaded by General Berthelot began to subordinate the principle of evacuation to a set of measures that involved the regeneration of the Romanian Army. However, the Russian Empire had to send the necessary supplies²⁴.

The revolution, which broke out on February 28th – March 13th, 1917, put an end to the Russian plans and, subsequently, the independence and the identity of the Royal Army were preserved²⁵. So, at least at that moment, the matter of the evacuation of the Romanian Army and authorities was solved according to the French opinion strongly expressed by the Chief of the Military Mission, Berthelot.

General Berthelot emphasized the state of mind of the officials, of the Russian and Romanian Commanders and of the population as well. The Romanian King decided to remain loyal to the alliance and to withdraw the army, if necessary, in Russia. Although he did not express the same determination, the President of the Council of Ministers, showed his solidarity with the King and the Army. He could not be suspected that he had not continued to keep his loyalty to the Entente.

At the end of July 1917, the question of a possible withdrawal in Russia became again the most important topic of the discussions between Iași, Paris and Petrograd. The Government from Iași and King Ferdinand were reluctant to admit this eventuality. The Romanian diplomacy made its best to avoid the abandonment the national territory by the

²² *Ibidem*, f. 203, f. 207; S.H.A.T., *Cabinet du ministre*, Carton 5N 140, coded telegram no. 283, March 6th, 1917, sent from Rome and signed Barrère.

²³ S.H.A.T., *Cabinet du ministre*, Carton 5N 140, telegram no. 367, March 7th, 1917, sent from London and signed Paul Cambon.

²⁴ *Ibidem*, Carton 5N 200, telegram no. 162, March 24th, 1917, signed Saint - Aulaire.

²⁵ Glenn E. Torrey, *Russia, Romania and France: The Reorganisation of the Romanian Front 1916 - 1917*, in "Revue Roumaine d' Histoire", 1992, no. 1-2, p. 101, p. 63.

army. France had to support Romanian cause at Petrograd. The Central Empires' troops would invade Moldavia and could march to Odesa. On July 28th, the King reiterated his strong loyalty for the Entente and told that the withdrawal in Russia represented a desperate action, an ultimate solution. In this case, Ferdinand requested all the rights due to a Commander-in-Chief, a special military zone and even a temporary territorial sovereignty. The Foreign Affairs' Minister of the provisional government, Terescenko declared that the respecting of all the royal prerogatives would be guaranteed in this eventuality²⁶.

In August 7th, 1917, the Russian provisional government suggested the settlement of the Romanian authorities in the town of Kerson, but the Prime-Minister Brătianu preferred Ekaterinoslav or Poltava. In Terescenko's opinion, Poltava presented disadvantages because the material organization was impossible²⁷.

The Minister from Iași, Saint-Aulaire and General Berthelot expressed similar points of view concerning the matter of the evacuation. The first suggested a collective guarantee given to the King to remove any hesitation of the Romanians and keep them in the alliance in any circumstance. Russia had to make all the possible military efforts²⁸. The leader of French diplomacy, Alexandre-Félix Ribot feared that a withdrawal would provide strategic, moral and material advantages to the enemy. The Central Empires could seize the stocks of war materials constituted by France that would mean a disaster. To avoid it, the Russian troops had to resist at all costs in Bucovina, trying to protect Moldavia. Ribot gave explicit instructions to the Petrograd Ambassador, Noulens²⁹.

In the summer of 1917, Paris continued to put pressure on Petrograd. The Russians should not insist on the Moldavia's abandonment. A campaign for a separate peace appeared in Romanian public opinion and in a few military circles. This was a sign that the internal situation had become worse and

²⁶ A.M.A.E.F., *Guerre, Roumanie*, D. 347, ff. 77-80, f. 98.

²⁷ A.M.A.E.F., *Guerre, Roumanie*, D. 347, f. 119, ff. 126-128, ff. 146-147; S.H.A.T., *Cabinet du ministre*, Carton 5N 201, telegram no. 417 of the Commander of French Military Mission in Romania to War Minister at Paris, August 13th, 1917; Constantin Argetoianu, *Pentru cei de mâine. Amintiri din vremea celor de ieri*, vol. III, București, Editura Humanitas, 1991, pp. 125-126.

²⁸ A.M.A.E.F., *Guerre, Roumanie*, D. 347, *Ibidem*, f. 82, f. 98.

²⁹ A.M.R., *Fond Marele Cartier General*, D. 1035, f. 1; A.M.A.E.F., *Guerre, Roumanie*, D. 347, f. 88, f. 93.

worse. Russia represented a *terra incognita* for the army and the population. That is why Berthelot proposed the defense of the existing front and Moldavia's keeping³⁰. Moreover, an exodus would have been financially very expensive³¹.

Russia tried to persuade France that it had never given up Moldavia's defense and if necessary, the Russian General Staff would study the possibility of a withdrawal in the north of Bucovina³². General Brusilov was replaced by General Kornilov. In fact, the Russian troops began to refuse fighting and the growing anarchy made worst the military co-operation. They became very sensitive to the pacifist ideas and German propaganda. The Russian troops were unable to defend neither Prut line, nor that of Nistru. Moreover, the Russians were unpredictable seizing all the means of conveyance to facilitate their own run³³.

On August 3th, 1917, the news concerning the abandonment of Cernăuți provoked a deep emotion and a profound panic at Iași. Russia's agony will involve Romanian Kingdom's agony, because its fate depended geographically, strategically and military on the fate of its neighbour. Romania will remain isolated. Romania's Council of Ministers decided to maintain in Moldavia only the local authorities if the departure had been unavoidable. A government imposed by the Germans could conclude a separate peace or even an alliance with Germany³⁴.

On the other hand, the departure of the diplomatic body was delayed again, although the members of Parliament and those of the Court of Cassation had been already evacuated³⁵. In Constantin Diamandi's opinion, if the provisional government adopted a fair attitude to Romania, the Russian soldiers on the front did not show a similar one. Ion I.C. Bratianu considered that the Entente should "take in its hands Romania's fate and adopt Romanian Army"³⁶.

³⁰ Glenn Torrey (ed.), *General Henri Berthelot and Romania. Mémoires et correspondance 1916 - 1919*, New York, Columbia University Press, 1987, p. 92.

³¹ A.M.A.E.F., *Guerre, Roumanie*, D. 347, f. 147.

³² *Ibidem*, ff. 77-80 f. 99.

³³ Arhivele Naționale ale României, Fond *Microfilme, Anglia*, r. 257, c. 30; Contele de Saint - Aulaire, *Confesiunile unui bătrân diplomat*, București, Editura Humanitas, 2003, p. 154.

³⁴ Contele de Saint - Aulaire, *op. cit.*, pp. 153-154.

³⁵ S.H.A.T., *Cabinet du ministre*, Carton 5N 201, telegram no. 473 of the Commander of the French Military Mission to the War Minister, at Paris, August 23th, 1917.

³⁶ A.M.A.E.F., *Guerre, Roumanie*, D. 347, f. 198.

Therefore, the Allied Powers should respect and reaffirm the commitments assumed towards Romania.

The discussions concerning a possible departure in Russia continued in the fall of 1917. The Russian disorder and anarchy became deeper and deeper and therefore, the Romanian Kingdom was not able to fructify the brilliant victories of the summer and it had to combat without the necessary support and military means.

The Russian authorities tended to control and to subordinate the Romanian Army. That is why they insisted so much on the principle of the evacuation for the Romanian Army, Government and population.

General Henri Mathias Berthelot and Count Auguste Charles de Saint-Aulaire have always militated for the Romania's cause, warning Brătianu government about the disadvantages and risks involved by the evacuation of the army and of the authorities in Russia. Of course, this would have represented a military adventure and the costs for such an action would have been huge.

THE NATIONAL ISSUE IN THE COMMUNIST INNING

Lucian Săcălean*

Abstract

This article addresses the issue of ethnic relations in a complicated period of Romanian history onset of communism. The evolution was somewhat similar for Romania and Hungary, taking into consideration the setting up of the red power, from the alliance/independence fronts till the gradual buying up of the whole power and the increasing of the communist effectives' force, but in a short period of time¹. Even though the presence of the minorities in the party overtakes in some areas that of the population's percentage, the subsequent events, the merging with PSDR, the tendency of PMR of keeping the ethnical balance in the representation led to the increasing of the ethnical Romanians' weight both within the political party and at the level of decision². But there is much suspicion, the structures are not unitary, the conflicts between the Hungarian communists and the Romanian ones are frequent.

Keywords: Minorities, Nationalism

If the 1918 events signified the rising of the national minorities' weight to about 28% of the whole population³, the most numerous ones having a very well articulated political and social-cultural institutional system, the end of the Second World War and the loss of Bessarabia and Bucovina, show a changed situation, namely diminutions regarding the percentage of the majority of nationalities, but increases for Romanians, Hungarians or Ukrainians⁴. The industrialization contributes as well to the change of ethnical composition in the case of some towns and the collectivization leads to the change of a whole *modus vivendi*, not only for the minority but also for the majority. Regarding the structure of RCP, the presence of a high percentage of the minorities, inclusively at its leadership level, has to be mentioned, the ethnical composition being rather a heterogeneous one.

Through King Michael's decision of changing the political direction, August 23rd 1944 not only marks the future of

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¹ Gheorghe Gheorghiu-Dej, *Lupta pentru pace*, Bucureşti, Editura Politică, 1950, p. 12.

² See Virgiliu Tărău, *Problema naţională în politica PCR în anii 1944-1946. Consideraţii preliminare*, in "Anuarul Institutului de Istorie George Bariţiu", no. 36, 1997, pp. 223-239.

³ Ioan Scurtu, Liviu Boar (coord.), *Minorităţile naţionale din România*, vol. I, 1918-1925. Documente, Bucureşti, Arhivele Naţionale ale României, 1995, p. 8.

⁴ ***, *Recensământul populaţiei din 1956*, p. 18.

Romania, but also affects a series of other states. According to some evaluations, the decision led to the curtailment of the conflict with about six months, opening the way for the soviet advance towards Vienna and Prague⁵. This way, Romania can retrieve Transylvania, but its statute of co-belligerent country, leaving to Moscow a precious instrument of pressure against the Romanian communists, the minority issue. As a matter of fact, the Central and the Eastern Europe is left in the soviet influence and decision area, the relationships between the different actors being conditioned by the affiliation to the same political-military coalition. The party will radically transform, from this turning point Gheorghiu-Dej announcing the opening towards new members⁶. Even though the presence of the minorities in the party overtakes in some areas that of the population's percentage, the subsequent events, the merging with PSDR, and the tendency of PMR of keeping the ethnical balance in the representation led to the increasing of the ethnical Romanians' weight both within the political party and at the level of decision⁷. But there is much suspicion, the structures are not unitary, the conflicts between the Hungarian communists and the Romanian ones are frequent.

The evolution was somewhat similar for Romania and Hungary, taking into consideration the setting up of the red power, from the alliance/independence fronts till the gradual buying up of the whole power and the increasing of the communist effectives' force, but in a short period of time. The setting up of the communist regime in this part of the continent signified as a matter of fact the setting up of a *pax sovietica*, amity, co-operation and mutual assistance treaties being concluded between USSR and the satellite states, under the pressure of Moscow. Romania and Hungary were no exceptions, the amity, co-operation and mutual assistance treaty being concluded between the two states in January 24th 1948, as a result of Petru Groza's visit in Budapest, the treaty being signed by the prime-minister Lajos Dinnyés from the Hungarian party, both being authorized by the Temporary Presidium of the Romanian People's Republic, namely by the president of the Hungarian Republic. The treaty was affirming the two parties' wish to strengthen the reciprocal contacts; to take mutual

⁵ Iosif Constantin Drăgan, *Istoria Românilor*, București, Editura Europa Nova, 1999, p. 255.

⁶ Gheorghe Gheorghiu-Dej, *Lupta pentru pace*, cit., p. 12.

⁷ Virgiliu Țărău, *op. cit.*

counsel regarding the international issues, important for their interests; military support or other sort of assistance in case of a possible German attack, not concluding any alliance or action that could aim the other party. Both countries would be acquainted with the mechanism of the soviet example from the economical, political and social point of view. In August 31st 1944, the new Romanian government reinstates the Constitution from 1923, which had been suspended by Carol II in 1938⁸. The setting up of the Sănătescu government was followed by the struggle for power. In October 12th, in order to be more efficient, the left parties such as PCR, PSD, The Ploughmen's Front and The Patriotic Union create the coalition called "The National Democratic Front", later joint by The Hungarian People's Union, the only acknowledged political body of the Hungarian minority from Romania⁹. The Sănătescu Government (May 4th-December 6th 1944) was followed by the Rădescu government (December 6th 1944-February 28th 1945), meanwhile the left forces managed to gain the control over various district administrations. The appointment of the Groza government¹⁰, implicitly the entrance of "the historic parties" in the opposition marked an ultimate step towards the communization of Romania. The elections in November 19th 1946, even though disputed, bring a crushing victory to the left coalition¹¹, being followed by the liquidation of the historic parties, further to that of their own partners. In November 12th 1947 the merging of PSD and PCR is accepted, namely the establishment of The Romanian Workers' Party. After king Michael's abdication in December 30th 1947, through the proclamation number 393/147, Romania is declared People's Republic¹², and the PCR-PSD merging convention, taking place between February 21th-23th 1948, chooses Gheorghe Gheorghiu-Dej as the first secretary of the PMR¹³. The Romania's new direction is established at the plenary session of the PMR in July 10th-11th 1948, Dej already speaking about the building of a new state: "the new state will be the state of the country and town workers and intellectuals, where the state power comes from the

⁸ Ioan Scurtu, Gheorghe Buzatu, *Istoria românilor în secolul XX*, București, Editura Paideia, 1999. p. 487.

⁹ Andrea Süle, "România politikatörténete 1944-1990", in Gábor Hunya *et alii*, *România 1944-1990. Gazdaság- és politikatörténet*, Budapest, Atlantisz, 1990, p. 202.

¹⁰ Ioan Scurtu, Gheorghe Buzatu, *op. cit.*, p. 495.

¹¹ *Ibidem*, p. 512.

¹² *Ibidem*, p. 516.

¹³ Andrea Süle, *op. cit.*, p. 218.

crowd and will also be exercised by the crowd through the chosen authority”¹⁴. Following the soviet example, the nationalization policies aim more and more sectors, the checking and repression authorities are founded, being directly supervised by the PCR (Militia and Security). In 1949, the system of The Workers’ Councils is introduced, a checking and exclusion of “the exploitative and hostile elements”¹⁵ process is launched and through the Education Reform, in August 3rd, the confessional education is suppressed. As for the policy in the minorities’ domain, in May 22nd 1947, a first signal is recorded through Vasile Luca’s article “The Hungarians’ way in Romania”, published in the Hungarian newspaper called “Igazság”, in which the author insists on the need of struggle against “the insider enemy”, emphasizing the idea of solving the minority issue through the individual integration into the socialism¹⁶. The resolution of PMR regarding the national question is structured in six chapters, the first one introducing the theoretical part and the importance of solving the national issue, having the basis of the soviet example. The “detrimental” nationalism is seen as a product of the capitalist system: “the nationalistic, racist, chauvinist policy used by the imperialists undermines the international solidarity of the working people in the struggle against the imperialism for democracy and socialism and leads to the loss of the people’s independence and national sovereignty”¹⁷. The second chapter stresses the attachment to URSS and to the soviet example, condemning the Yugoslav Communist Party. The third chapter presents the achievements of the PCR concerning the policy for the nationalities, emphasizing the importance of the reforms and that of the legislation which “had suppressed all the national and racial discriminations and had granted equal rights to the nationalities, founding pecuniary possibilities for the exercising of these rights¹⁸”. Both the nationalism of the majority and that of the minority was being condemned, returning to the impulse of the class struggle within the own ethnicity. “The comrades who act within the co-inhabiting nationalities do not

¹⁴ Gheorghe Gheorghiu-Dej, *Általános politikai jelentés a Román Munkáspárt kongresszusán (1948 február 21-23)*, Bukarest, Román Munkáspárt, 1948, p. 21.

¹⁵ Dennis Deletant, *România în perioada comunistă*, Editura Fundația Academică Civică, București, 1997, p. 67.

¹⁶ Mihály Zoltán Nagy, Ágoston Olti, *Érdekképviselet vagy pártpolitika. Dokumentumok az MNSz történetéből 1944-1953*, Csíkszereda, Pro-Print Könyvkiadó, 2009, pp. 25-28.

¹⁷ *Ibidem*.

¹⁸ *Ibidem*.

struggle enough against their own nationalistic bourgeoisie, which defames the working people. The comrades who act within the mass organizations or in the nationalists' democratic committees have to consider themselves as party activists within those organizations and committees, unhesitatingly guiding them under the leadership of the party, towards the vision of the class struggle¹⁹. We can say that it is a return to the loyalty theme, to the loyalty towards the country, obviously not under an inter-war formula, the return being attributed to the party now, having also the loyalty expression towards the state. The fifth chapter presents the policy of the party towards each important minority in the country. In the case of the Hungarians, the theory of "national unity" and the "isolation tendencies" from the Hungarian bourgeoisie in different economical and cultural institutions was criticised. Not even the Jews were getting off from the same censure of the "national unity", the Zionist movement being considered detrimental to the cause of socialism. In the case of the German minority, the adjustment of rights was being stressed, as well as the importance of educating the young in the vision of the socialism. As far as the Ukrainians and the Russians are concerned, their attachment to the socialist assertions was pointed out, as well as the danger represented by the rich men. In the case of the Serbians, the danger coming from Yugoslavia was being reminded, while in the case of the Greeks, the detrimental effects of the civil war in Greece²⁰. The PMR's resolution becomes a programmatic document for the next years, founding the basis of the new policy regarding the national matter. The document denounces the "collective fault" of the minorities, stating that the co-inhabiting nationalities issue always has to be subordinated to the most important tasks of the proletariat. In consequence, the maintaining of some proper institutions, irrespective of their nature, becomes an attempt of isolation and resistance, pointing out the individual integration and by no means the collective one²¹.

In 1948, the Department for the Issues of the Co-inhabiting Nationalities around the Presidency of the Council of Ministers is founded, having the following prerogatives: it studies the co-inhabiting nationalities' issues on the territory of the Romanian

¹⁹ László Vörös, 1948. nr. 6

²⁰ *Ibidem*.

²¹ Mihály Nagy, *Protejarea intereselor etnice sau urmărirea liniei PCR. Funcția de reprezentare a intereselor a Uniunii Populare Maghiare*, in Olti Ágoston, Attila Gidó (eds.), *Minoritatea maghiară în perioada comunistă*, Cluj-Napoca, Institutul pentru Studierea Problemelor Minorităților Naționale, 2009, p. 144-157.

People's Republic; it keeps the accounts of these matters and proposes solutions in order to solve them from the political, juridical and administrative point of view; it checks and supervises the equitable use of the measures concerning the whole social life of the co-inhabiting nationalities, corresponding to the Constitution and to the rules of the nationalities and coordinates these measures²². Lajos Takács is named at the leadership of the department, being helped by four departmental counsellors. The department reminds of the similar structures from the inter-war period, having the same most of the prerogatives. It has no decision right, this being another characteristic kept from the previous organizations, but it has the right to propose solving measures to some issues. 1948-1949 brought purges within all the organizations, that is to say the naming of some cadres close to the leadership of the party and state, removing all those who were still believing the proper institutions as being necessary. The UPM, in the case of the Hungarians and CDE, in the case of the Jews, are not avoided by these measures, the minorities' democratic committees becoming gradually simple instruments of the communist party²³. In January 14th 1953, the "Report concerning the situation and the future measures that would be adopted in the present existing conditions regarding the organization of the Ploughmen's Front, UFDR, UPM and the democratic committees of the national minorities". The Jewish organizations, as a consequence to the anti-Semitic tendencies recorded in URSS are considered to be among the most dangerous ones, especially from the point of view of their Anglo-American spying. The leadership of the PMR was considering The Hungarian People's Union, The Jewish Democratic Committee and The German Antifascist Committee as being organizations which had become hiding places for the reactionary elements. In consequence, the ceasing of the activity of the above mentioned organizations and besides, that of The Russian, Ukrainian, Albanian, Bulgarian, Greek, Serbian, Tatar and Turkish Democratic Committees and that of the cultural organizations such as the Polish and the Czechoslovak House had been decided. Their suppressing, initiated and under the patronage of the Communist Party, has a very simple explanation. After the purges and the expulsion from the organizations of those who were sharing other ideologies, such as the Zionists, the bourgeois, the Jews, the rich men and the

²² *Ibidem*.

²³ Mihály Zoltán Nagy, Ágoston Olti, *op. cit.*, p. 170.

Hungarian reactionary priests²⁴ and after the naming of some men, loyal to the party, the above mentioned organizations still remain “otherness islands”; the Party does not need intermediates anymore in its relation with the minorities and the existence of a parallel space cannot be accepted. A similar process happens in other socialist countries, except Yugoslavia. Gradually, in Hungary, Bulgaria and Czechoslovakia the mass organizations were suppressed in favour of a more and more obvious centralization policy. As a matter of fact, the communist party acts upon the whole society, a whole set of values, customs and habits being changed in a sternly way in the name of a new society. It was impossible for the national minorities not to be exceptions in this huge gearing that was aiming at the profound change of the society and its paradigms.

It is not simple to solve the ethnical issue. For many times the various solutions that people had found in the course of time were compromises that could not assure the peace and the closing of this topic for a longer period of time. The inter-war period was marked by the Romanian authorities' attempts in assuring a minimum existence of some political topics such as loyalty towards the state; by the expressed discontents of the minorities and through the petitions directed to the international authorities, but the situation changes on the international arena with the ending of the Second World War, conflict that has brought new solutions. Just under the flag of the socialist internationalism, the conflicts between the Hungarian communists and the Romanian ones raise problems to the central authorities. The solution, at least for a while, is the mobilization against the common enemy, Vasile Luca being the one who advises us to the maintaining within our own ethnicity of the critical vision, namely of the exposure of the inconsistent elements, the Romanian communists being willing to attack the Romanian fascists and the Hungarian communists to attack the Hungarian fascists, this way avoiding the possibility of a conflict between the two ethnicities²⁵. The presence of numerous minority elements, at least in the first years among the Romanian communist party, can be explained taking into account more aspects. For the Jews, the safety valve of the internationalism could represent the way to integrate, for the Hungarians, the

²⁴ Liviu Rotman, *Evreii din România în perioada comunistă 1944-1965*, Iași, Editura Polirom, 2004, p. 88.

²⁵ Arhivele Naționale Istorice Centrale, Fond CC al PCR, Cancelarie, dos. 32/1945, f. 60.

hope of a new order, nourished as well by the fact that during the inter-war period the Trianon Treaty was not recognized by the communist movement and the presence of the Red Army in Transylvania, as a matter of fact, the “protection” offered by it, led to the increasing of the regard from the Hungarian part for the communist movement.

APPELLATION OF ORIGIN VS. GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS. TERMINOLOGICAL DEBATES DURING THE LISBON TREATY 1958

Mihaela Daciana Bolos*

Abstract

The paper studies the debates that took place during the Lisbon Conference of 1958 regarding the international protection and registration of appellation of origin. In particular, the bases of the research are the discussions that took place during the Lisbon Conference regarding the notion of appellation of origin, and that of geographical indication. All the opinions and positions took by different states regarding this particular problem are collected in the book entitled "Actes de la Conférence de Lisbonne" published by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO).

The debate is highly important nowadays because of the reforms intended to be made in the geographical indications protection system. Also the positions expressed during the Conference are relevant for the future of the international act adopted: the "Lisbon Agreement".

Keywords: *Appellations of Origin, Geographical Indications, International Treaties, Diplomatic Conferences*

Introduction

The Lisbon Agreement for the Protection of Appellations of Origin and their International Registration was adopted in October 31, 1958. The propose of the Agreement is to enlarge the provisions of the Paris Convention of 1883 regarding the Protection of Industrial Property and the Madrid Agreement of 1891 for the Repression of False or Deceptive Indications of Source on Goods, by introducing a new formula of protection and the creation of an international registration system, similar to the one developed by the Madrid Agreement 1891 regarding trademarks.

"The Lisbon Agreement was and still is much debated. Francis Gurry, General Director of WIPO, mentioned three important aspects regarding the Agreement, in a speech made in occasion to the 50 years anniversary of its adoption¹.

The three aspects are:

- that the issue of geographical indications had already been hotly debated in the international arena since the late 19th century without multilaterally agreed tangible results concerning the protection of geographical indications going beyond what is laid down in the Paris Convention and the Madrid Agreement for the Repression of False or Deceptive Indications of Source in 1891

- the negotiators did not only manage to agree on a definition on the basis of which geographical indications should be measured as being

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¹ Francis Gurry, Director General WIPO, speech held on occasion of the 50 years anniversary of Lisbon Agreement, URL: http://www.wipo.int/aboutwipo/en/dgo/speeches/gurry_lisbon_08.html.

capable for international registration under the Agreement, but also on the level of protection that Member States should provide in respect of such geographical indications

- In all respects, the negotiators found a way to lay down a large degree of flexibility in the provisions of the Agreement without impinging on the effectiveness of the protection to be accorded to geographical indications registered internationally”.

Francis Gurry discourse held on October 31, 2008

The Conference of Lisbon

The Lisbon Conference that has generated the Agreement was scheduled on October 6th 1958, in Portugal, organised by the Office of International Union of Intellectual Property, fact proved by several addresses² sent during the process. At the conference were invited to attend member states of the Union, non-member states, and international governmental and non - governmental organizations. From the state international actors present to the Conference we mention: Germany, Australia, Austria, Belgium, Brazil, Bulgaria, Canada, Cuba, Denmark, Spain, SUA, Finland, France, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Japan, Luxemburg, Morocco, Mexico, Monaco, Norway, New Zealand, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Anglia, Sweden, Switzerland, Czechoslovakia, Turkey, South African Union, Viet-Nam, Yugoslavia. In total there are 40 participants, 10 states non - member to the Union, among which URSS, Vatican and Iraq, eight governmental organizations like the Council of Europe, and seven non - governmental organizations³.

Romania was present to the Conference and was represented by delegates of the Foreign Affairs Ministry, and two directors of the State Office of Inventions as can be seen in the image below⁴.

ROUMANIE (République Populaire Roumaine) :

S. E. M. STEFAN CLEJA, Envoyé extraordinaire et Ministre plénipotentiaire de la République Populaire Roumaine, Ministère des Affaires étrangères.

M. LIVIU TRUFINESCU, Directeur technique à l'Office d'Etat pour Inventions.

M. LEO KAPPEL, Ingénieur principal à l'Office d'Etat pour Inventions.

² Union International pour la Protection de la Propriété Intellectuelle, *Actes de la Conférence Reunie à Lisbonne du 6 au 31 octobre 1958*, Imprimerie Paul Attinger Société anonyme, Suedia, 1963, p. 33-54

³ *Ibidem*, pp. 55-68

⁴ The image is part of the official text deposited at WIPO regarding the states delegates present at the conference. In *Ibidem*, p. 62

The Conference was divided into 5 commissions, the fourth being entirely dedicated to the adoption of the Agreement for the Protection of Appellations of Origin and their International Registration⁵.

The term appellation of origin

The term appellation of origin was debated mainly in the fourth commission concerning the revision of some Paris Convention articles. The legal provision concerning our research can be found in the first article paragraph two of the Paris Convention which presents the meaning of the phrase industrial property. In this article the Convention formulates those as follows: “*The protection of industrial property has as its object patents, utility models, industrial designs, trademarks, service marks, trade names, indications of source or appellations of origin, and the repression of unfair competition*”⁶. In the preliminary considerations the Office of the Intellectual Property Union submitted the reasons why the changes were needed. So they underlined that the two terms as presented in the Convention and considered initially as synonyms, have to be distinguished due to evolutions in the jurisprudence and juridical literature of some countries members of the Unions for the protection of industrial property⁷.

L'évolution de la législation et de la jurisprudence, ainsi que de la littérature juridique de plusieurs pays unionistes en matière de propriété industrielle, nous impose d'admettre désormais une distinction entre les indications de provenance et les appellations d'origine. Il y a lieu de souligner également leur diversité dans la Convention de Paris qui suit l'évolution du droit.

Excerpt from the paper presented during the Lisbon Conference⁸

From the view point of the document presented there, it was a clear difference between “appellations of origin” and “indications of sources”. The “appellation of origin” designated every geographical indications corresponding to a country, region or another place that give the name of a product originating in the zone from where it takes its name, and who has some special and renowned qualities due exclusively or essentially to the geographical environment, and the method of production. On the other hand the “indication of provenance” simply indicated the place of production.

⁵ The structure results from the informations presented in *Ibidem*

⁶ Paris Convention text, on WIPO website, URL: www.wipo.int.

⁷ Union International pour la Protection de la Propriété Intellectuelle, *Actes de la Conférence Reunie a Lisabonne du 6 au 31 octobre 1958*, Imprimerie Paul Attinger Société anonyme, Suedia, 1963, p. 771

⁸ The original text from where the image is taken can be found in *Ibidem*, p. 771

L'appellation d'origine désigne toute dénomination géographique correspondant à un pays, une région, une contrée ou un autre lieu quelconque servant d'appellation à des produits qui en sont originaires et qui présentent, selon les règlements établis à cet effet ou les usages locaux, loyaux et constants, des qualités typiques et renommées, dues exclusivement ou essentiellement au lieu et à la méthode de production et de fabrication, d'extraction ou de groupement de ces produits.

L'indication de provenance est la désignation géographique indiquant tout simplement le lieu de production, de fabrication, d'extraction ou de groupement afin d'identifier la marchandise.

Excerpt from the paper presented during the Lisbon Conference⁹

The present day appellation of origin definition is based on this reasons expressed in the preliminary text presented to be debated in the Conference¹⁰.

The analysis was not only made from the view point of the revision opportunity, or of the legal aspects implied by the two terms one (indication of provenance) regarding some public international law and the other (appellation of origin) private law, but also from the perspective of terms semantics.

Cependant, nous observons que, même au point de vue linguistique, si les mots « provenance » et « origine » peuvent être considérés comme synonymes, « indication » et « appellation » ne le sont jamais dans l'usage commun. Le premier donne l'idée d'un renseignement, le deuxième d'une dénomination ou d'un qualificatif. Il est donc bien clair que le langage juridique a voulu souligner cette différence essentielle entre le simple fait d'indiquer la provenance de la marchandise et celui d'en désigner la qualité par une dénomination géographique.

Excerpt from the paper presented during the Lisbon Conference¹¹

Contradictory positions

As already mentioned the terminology problem was first raised during the discussions regarding the Paris Convention revision, and afterwards in the process of adoption of the Agreement concerning the appellations of origin. Oppositions, to the use of the "appellation of origin" terminology, were raised by Germany, Denmark, Israel, Sweden, Yugoslavia, and USA. Modifications to the agreement were demanded by Italy, Romania and Czechoslovakia. Last but not least Japan, England, Morocco and Norway decline any interest towards the agreement¹².

⁹ The original text form where the image is taken can be found in *Ibidem*, p. 771

¹⁰ This fact it's obvious if we compare the text presented in the conference and the definition presented in the Lisbon Agreement. WIPO, Agreement for the Protection of Appellations of Origin and their International Registration, WIPO Publications, Geneva, 2004, p 3, art. 1

¹¹ The original text form where the image is taken can be found in Union International pour la Protection de la Propriété Intellectuelle, *op. cit.*, p. 772

¹² *Ibidem*, p. 824-829

Some of the motives for rejecting the use of “appellation of origin” term are the followings:

- “appellation of origin” as a juridical term is not sufficiently clear, because it implies a broader significance, referring not only to the geographical indication but also to some product characteristic¹³;
- the Agreement tries to introduce a new term and a new type of protection, a special one¹⁴;
- It was brought in front of the delegates the issue of changing an accepted term “geographical indications” with a new one “appellation of origin”. The later one cannot be applied in some countries due to some domestic legislations that do not recognize neither this notion, nor an equivalent¹⁵;

fallacieuses. Mais il craint que la proposition du Bureau international de remplacer la notion d'« appellations de provenance » par celle d'« appellations d'origine » ne puisse en fait aboutir à un affaiblissement de cette protection. A ce propos il se permet de faire remarquer, en particulier, que le droit allemand ne connaît pas la notion d'appellations d'origine, comprise dans le sens d'une indication se rapportant non pas seulement à la provenance, mais aussi à certaines qualités du produit. Le droit allemand protège n'importe quelle indication géographique de provenance, c'est-à-dire même celles qui n'impliquent aucune indication relative à des qualités particulières des produits ; il suffit que l'indication géographique constitue une simple indication relative à la provenance du produit.

*Excerpt from the Delegation of Germany position during the Lisbon Conference*¹⁶

- The appellation of origin can be considered a special type of geographical indication¹⁷. Nowadays the official documents regarding the differences between geographical indications and appellations of origin lean towards this position¹⁸.

¹³ Germany's position, *Ibidem*, p. 825

¹⁴ This motive can be found in Germany, Sweden, and Denmark's position *Ibidem*, pp. 798, 803, 800

¹⁵ In Germany the legislation does not requests that the geographical indications should have some characteristics related to the place of production. *Ibidem*, p. 799

¹⁶ The original text form where the image is taken can be found in *Ibidem*, p. 799

¹⁷ Denmark and Germany's position *Ibidem*, p. 800, 774. This view point is accepted also by Austria

¹⁸ WIPO, *What is intellectual property?*, WIPO Publications, Geneva, p. 15, WIPO, *Understanding industrial property*, WIPO Publications, Geneva, p.14-15

La proposition concernant l'article 4 de l'Arrangement de Madrid semble être fondée sur la prétendue différence entre les *indications de provenance* en général, — c'est-à-dire toutes dénominations géographiques, — et un groupe d'indications dites *appellations d'origine* et s'appliquant à des produits dont les qualités sont dues essentiellement au climat ou aux conditions du sol.

*Excerpt from the Delegation of Denmark position during the Lisbon Conference*¹⁹

- The new term is unknown in many states and there are many states in which the term has not an equivalent. This casts a shadow of doubt over the clarity of the Agreement provisions²⁰.

La Délégation de la Suède observa que la distinction entre les deux termes, inconnue dans de nombreux pays, n'est pas claire et que dans les pays de langue anglaise une traduction uniforme n'existe pas. Une convention internationale ne peut se baser sur des conceptions vagues.

*Excerpt from the Delegation of Sweden position during the Lisbon Conference*²¹

France declared, in support to the new term that this is used in its legislation, as well as in other legal systems as Spanish, Italian or Hungarian²². So appellation of origin was not such a novelty as it may seem.

The present definition that can be found in the Agreement text was adopted during the discussions in the commission and it was proposed by the delegates of Israel²³. The difficulties were related to the need to formulate a definition wide enough to give states the possibility to adapt it in their domestic laws, but at the same time restrictive enough to leave as little as possible room for bad-faith interpretations.

« Appellation d'origine signifie une dénomination géographique indiquant le pays, la région ou la localité d'où le produit considéré provient et impliquant en outre la notion de qualité ou de nature du produit particulière à ce pays, cette région ou cette localité. »

*Excerpt from the Delegation of Israel position during the Lisbon Conference*²⁴

Conclusions

The discussions that took place during the Conference are very important for the international development of regulations in the field of

¹⁹ The original text form where the image is taken can be found in Union International pour la Protection de la Propriété Intellectuelle, *op. cit.*, p. 800

²⁰ Sweden position, *Ibidem*, p. 773

²¹ The original text form where the image is taken can be found in *Ibidem*, p. 773

²² France position *Ibidem*, p. 775

²³ *Ibidem*, p. 832

²⁴ The original text form where the image is taken can be found in *Ibidem*, p. 832

intellectual property. This Conference proves the way in which the system of international organizations works and the need to negotiate in order to reach a common ground favourable to everybody. The Lisbon Conference did exactly that: it has brought together members of the Union regarding Intellectual Property and non-members, but with a keen interest in this field, in order to develop the existing system of international laws - in that case the Paris Convention of 1883, and the development of new laws and concepts – the Lisbon Agreement regarding appellations of origin.

The mere presence to negotiations is not as relevant as the political interest of each country for the particular case debated. If we look at the act of accession to a treaty as an international political act of a state than, certainly, we may identify a pattern by which states operate in order to have their interests protected.

Expressing their point of view during the International Conference is the first step. In the particular case of the Lisbon Agreement from the data presented we may draw the conclusion that each interested state expressed the position that best suited their country. So if we look at the Germany's positions we may directly conclude that it was in its interest to avoid altering their internal legislation, in base of a new term that is foreign for the German legal system and people. A modification of this sort does not imply a mere revision of the German law regarding intellectual property but also campaigns of public information in order to make the general population aware of the new rights that they could benefit of, but also the punishments they may undergo if they break this new regulations.

The fact that other states rallied to similar positions shows that the problem is not a singular one, and that other states are in similar situations.

Another way is the refusal of joining a treaty that is not in accordance to one's interests. From this perspective we should look back to Francis Gurry's speech that we presented in the beginning. The main idea is that the Lisbon Treaty is necessary in the contemporaneous era. But the need to reinforce this belief comes from the number of contracting parties that the international act has: 26. This number fades if we take a look to the 173 members of the Paris Convention or the 84 members of the Madrid Protocol regarding the international registration of marks. The evolution of the accession can be seen in the chart below²⁵.

Maybe one of the reasons can be identified in the debates of the

Conference. Clearly some states did not agree with the appellation of origin and the system of protection they impose. These states are not party to the agreement. So Germany, Sweden, Denmark, England, Japan and others participants never ratified the Agreement. So if we look at the total numbers of 40 participants form the Union members and that till the early 90's only 15 states become members to the international act, one can certainly state that an 36% of the participating states signed the act.

Regarding the terminology problem, today the problem is still debated internationally. Anyway in the EU, the system of appellation of origin is used so a part of the initially rejecting states are applying the system today.

DILEMMAS OF ROMANIAN POST-DECEMBER FOREIGN POLICY. RELATIONS WITH RUSSIA

Miruna Mădălina Trandafir*

Abstract

This attempted research tries to detect under punctual and rigorous arguments the preliminary stage of the Romanian post December Foreign Policy, demonstrating the increased attention assigned to the Romanian-Russian relationship at the level of the main action directions carried on externally. In the introductory part of the study, we propose a close radiography of the external portrait of Romania, emphasizing the atypical trajectory recorded together with the sudden fall of the communist structure and the beginning of coagulation of new post-communist political structures and systems. In the second part of the paper, we shall emphasize the Romanian-Russian bilateral tandem specific to recent or immediate history segment, locating the "privileged" statute this complex relation detains at the level of the defining options of Romanian post December foreign policy. In its integrity, the paper dissociates itself from the unanimously accepted tendency in the academic circle, according to which the fundamental option of Romanian post December foreign policy was made up by the affiliation of Romania to Euro-Atlantic structures and mechanisms, inserting a distinct research direction, that starts from a contrasting premise: Romania of year '90 perpetuated the relationships with the Soviet Union, being particularly preoccupied with the recalibration in a mutual advantageous manner of the new juridical-bilateral framework.

Keywords: *Post-Communism, Foreign Policy, Russia, Romania*

Currently, a succinct indicative incursion at the level of the Romanian post-communist historiographical register, otherwise worthwhile for the interest shown in the problematisation of the transition and the reconstruction of the post-communist Romanian society under its different aspects, is more than eloquent in order to perceive the insufficient scientific approach due to themes of primordial meaning for the academic and intellectual Romanian environment: the dimension of Romanian post December foreign policy. In an incontestable manner, the instability of the informational sources and the inaccessibility of consulting archivist documents from well-known reasons, attest this reality, becoming difficult to exactly presume the format in which Romania resized its parameters of foreign policy together with the implosion of the communism. However, contradictorily to the impediments encountered alongside this subject, the contingent efforts in the direction of framing hypothesis and research requirements allotted to this themes sphere were not delayed in taking shape.

In such a referential optic, this attempted research plans itself the theoretical-conceptual construction, daring a notable completion subsumed to the debated themes, with the intent to retrace from a particular perspective the stage and the preliminary orientations in the Romanian post December foreign policy. In a complementary manner, this scientific paper dissociates itself from the unanimously accepted tendency in the academic circle, according to which the fundamental option of Romanian post December foreign policy was made up by the affiliation of Romania to Euro-Atlantic structures and mechanisms, inserting

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a distinct research direction, that starts from a contrasting premise: Romania of year '90 perpetuated the relationships with the Soviet Union, being particularly preoccupied with the recalibration in a mutual advantageous manner of the new juridical-bilateral framework.

As a consequence, in the introductory part of the study, we propose a synthetic radiography of the external portrait of Romania, emphasizing the atypical evolution recorded externally, together with the sudden fall of the communist structure and the beginning of coagulation of new post-communist political structures and systems. In the second part of the paper, we shall have in view to emphasize the Romanian-Russian bilateral tandem specific to recent or immediate history segment, locating the “privileged” statute this complex relation detains at the level of the defining options of Romanian post December foreign policy. In its integrity, the paper proposes itself on the grounds of solid and synthetic options, without having the claim of exhaustive presentation, to point out the official trend promoted by the new political leadership in the activity carried on externally by Romania together with the formalizing of transition, of passing from communist system to democratic and lawful state regime.

Introducing in the debate circuit a theme enclosed in the category “immediate history or recent history”¹ implies the presentation of those research methods and instruments specific to this historiographic typology. But we must specify from the very beginning the fact that such a research is not and cannot be built up on archivist documents from objective reasons. The situation of diplomatic archives is the same. However, this distinct type of historiography presents other advantages than those derived from knowledge based upon use of archives. As an alternative, our research is underlain on the accession of studies dedicated to transformations in post-communist Europe, to which, on the basis of an interpretative analyse, we impartially allotted working hypothesis essential to understand the debated themes. Secondly, by the historical comparative method, we balanced the historiographic visions and the contradictory reference materials, sifting the information through sources critique. Finally, by making an appeal to the methodological support specific to the oral history, which is the structured interview, we expressly aimed at reconstituting through the oral history instruments this complex subject from the statements of participants or ocular eyewitnesses, in our case major political decision makers. As a consequence, by interviewing important personalities of Romanian politics, we asked for answers to a set of pre-established questions, with the aim to gather information necessary for the aimed problems, investigations that we subsequently interpreted, integrating them in the foundation of the paper. As for the bibliography, it is mainly underlain on consultation of speciality literature, as well as studies and articles, memoirs, documents and media sources.

Starting from the “National Salvation Front’s statement to the country”² drafted in the context of deep changes occurred after the victory over

¹ Florin Abraham, *Transformarea României: 1989-2006. Rolul factorilor externi*, București, Institutul Național pentru Studiul Totalitarismului, 2006, p. 26.

² The statement to the Country is the first programmatic document issued by the National Salvation Front, the new political party that took the lead after the revolution in December

communism of the Romanian Events in December '89, it may be seen that the only references dedicated to Romanian foreign policy are purely by conjunction, imposed by the highlights of the moment, aiming at "promoting a good neighbour policy, friendship and world peace, coming under the process of rebuilding a united Europe, a common abode for all peoples of the continent, as well as respecting Romania's international commitments arising from the membership to the Warsaw Treaty"³. Besides, an even more complex analyse in the frame document designates the clarification of a much too evasive, inexact and ambiguous subject, revealing, without a doubt, the lack of a clear and pragmatic strategy concerning the priority option of Romania's foreign policy.

Absolutely, the above objection does not deliberately invalidate in any way the rally recorded by Romania in the external dimension, but it prefigures the purpose to present as fair as possible the preliminary mechanism, elaborated at government level in the field of foreign policy. In brief, the idea that we wish to emphasize is that, considering the unprecedented outlined systemic context after the fall of communism and the beginning of the transition period in Romania, the major political decision makers canalized all their constructive energy into the most urgent emerging issues, pre-eminently economic and political, ignoring, by default, or even by immobility, a major aspect, such as that reflecting Romania's image and identity in international relations. The absence of an intuitive vision and the incapacity to foresee with accuracy the most suitable partnerships for Romania influenced the subsequent trajectory of Romania's foreign policy. At an official level, it was insisted upon a policy of forms without substance, relying upon the interference of purely assertive projections and prerogatives; the famous phrase "openness to the world"⁴ is very relevant evidence in this respect.

Under this axiomatic dictum, Romania desired a beneficial co-operation with all other states of the world "based on understanding, equality and mutual respect, eliminating the obstructing barriers set by the former regime in the way of international collaboration"⁵. Foreign policy commandments, tributary to this objective, stated the defining desire to "express the democratization process of the Romanian society, ensuring the connection of Romania to the new trends emerging in Europe and around the world, with the intent to consolidate new relations among states and to directly participate to the international forum debates, starting with the fundamental interests of the country"⁶. In short, a number of bold goals rallied to "a policy conceived as a complete circle, in which there are no major holes left"⁷. In other words, a policy of high aspirations, directed towards all horizons, but lacking substance. Praised by the extent of the

1989. The document attests the fundamental change of the political system and regime in Romania. For further details related to this document, see: Ion Iliescu, *Revoluția trăită*, București, Editura Redacției publicațiilor pentru străinătate, 1995, pp. 125-128; Idem, *Revoluția Română*, București, Presa Națională, 2001, pp. 50-56, and others.

³ Specification referring to the changes in Romanian foreign policy, stipulated in section 9 of the N.S.F. Statement.

⁴ Ion Iliescu, *Momente de istorie. Documente, interviuri, comentarii*. Vol. II. *Iunie 1990-Septembrie 1991*, București, Editura Enciclopedică, 1996, p. 29.

⁵ *Ibidem*, pp. 42-43.

⁶ "Jurnal Internațional", February 18th, 1990.

⁷ Sergiu Celac, *De vorbă cu... Sergiu Celac*, București, Editura Enciclopedică, 1996, p. 43.

estimated results, this strategy did not record any substantial external progress. An acute need was felt to elaborate alternative methods meant to activate and boost Romanian foreign policy. "It became vital to change the angle, as Romania had to gain a redefined legitimacy on the scene of international relations"⁸.

"The completely changed international situation as opposed to the Cold War period"⁹, demanded this. The beginning of 1990 announced a notable retreat with respect to international relations, the idea of bipolar order being gradually substituted by the idea of unipolarity and the supremacy of the United States of America, "the entire subsystem of international relations in the Central and Eastern Europe underwent a deep restructuring process"¹⁰. The old economic security and collaboration mechanisms, respectively "the Treaty of Warsaw"¹¹ and the "Council for Mutual Economic Assistance"¹², "became anachronistic in the context of the disappearance of the ideological tie and the definitive renunciation to force and force threat in international relations"¹³, which determined a unanimous dissolution of these obsolete organizations. Certainly, the process of gradual destruction of such structures also generated a "security vacuum, characterized by an accentuated instability and a powerful destabilizing current in the South-Eastern part of the European continent"¹⁴, impossible to counteract on the short term.

How did Romania receive these substantial changes in the sphere of international relations? With a lot of confusion, actually, prevailing with an imprecision in establishing a well articulate program, adjusted to the new requests. Even the apprehension that Romania might hypothetically remain incorporated in that "buffer or grey area, in which there was no credible security guarantee, in case of possible conflicts or other peace disturbing events"¹⁵, was minimized. A much too simple approach may be seen, which lacks content in relation to the delicate situation of international relations. Nevertheless, the intentions to offer efficient solutions in order to build a pan European security system cannot be contested. A conclusive example in this respect lies in the

⁸ Adrian Severin, Gabriel Andreescu, *Locurile unde se construiește Europa. Adrian Severin în dialog cu Gabriel Andreescu*, Iași, Editura Polirom, 2000, p. 192.

⁹ Constantin Hlihor, *România și vecinătatea sa după încheierea Războiului Rece*, in "Analele Universității Creștine «Dimitrie Cantemir»", no. 1, 2010, p. 186, URL:<http://istorie.ucdc.ro/7.%20Revista%20PDF%20files/Analele%20UCDC%20Istorie%201%202010%20Pdf%20autori/20%20Hlihor.pdf>, (Accessed: March 12th 2011).

¹⁰ Luciana Alexandra Ghica, Marian Zulea, *Politica de securitate națională. Concepte, instituții, procese*, Iași, Editura Polirom, 2007, pp. 162-163.

¹¹ The Treaty of Warsaw Organization, created in 1955, represented the military alliance that united the communist States, set up with the purpose of counterbalancing N.A.T.O.

¹² C.A.E.R. (Council for Mutual Economic Assistance) was created through the initiative of the Soviet Union in 1949 as an economic organization of communist States, in order to represent the equivalent of the European Economic Community, with the purpose of stimulating commerce between communist countries.

¹³ Ion Iliescu, *România și lumea la confluența secolelor XX și XXI*, București, Editura Tehnică, 2009, p. 187.

¹⁴ Ioan Mircea Pașcu, *Extinderea Nato: Cazul României. Raport personal*, 2007, URL: <http://ioanmirceapascu.ro/media/pdf/extinderea-nato-ioan-mircea-pascu.pdf>, Accessed: December 12th, 2010.

¹⁵ Adrian Năstase, *România după Malta: 875 de zile la Externe*, vol. V, 1 Mai - 30 Iunie 1991, București, Fundația Europeană Titulescu, 2007, p. 292.

attempt to set up a “Central and Eastern European Union, acting as a political-economical authority, destined for states within the Central and East European area, as well as the initiative to legitimise a complex network of bilateral treaties, dispersed throughout European continent. This initiative was directed towards very open constructive and co-operation actions, promoting good relations, respect and understanding among all European states”¹⁶.

Unfortunately, these intentions, concerted with the actions of Romanian diplomacy were not managed in a manner that would give rise to tangible actions, able to efficiently finalize the set objectives, being placed rather in the ideological area. In the same time, multiple prolific opportunities were missed, occasions not exploited accordingly. While most ex-communist states defined their complete foreign policy strategy, pursuing as main objective the affiliation to Euro-Atlantic structures and organizations, Romania showed a serious hesitation in its external demarche. Surely, this intrinsic exploration, characteristic to the beginning of actions is also justified by an “obvious policy of separation practiced with Romania in relation with the other Central and East European states.”¹⁷ This policy was fully justified based on political reasons.

“The reluctance of the West towards the new political power, suspected to have neo-communist orientations and affinities”¹⁸, represented the main cause for which Romania was excluded from the preliminary adherence process of ex-communist states in the Euro-Atlantic security structures. The incertitude referring to the institution of an authentic and believable democracy for the Romanian society, and the failure to fulfil, in the short term, the obligations and criteria stipulated by Western partners, delayed Romania’s preliminary actions to affiliate both to NATO, and the European Community. Moreover, “the degradation of Romania’s image in the world due to the violent bursts during Tîrgu Mureş events, as well as during the miners’ riots”¹⁹, generated an ineluctable regression with respect to the initiatives to accede in the exclusive club of Western democracies. The incontestable idea was embraced that Romania was not eligible to take part in the Euro-Atlantic security organizations, as the democracy process was not linear, but rather abrupt and discontinuous. Consequently, the initiative to reconnect Romania to the Euro-Atlantic constellation was obstructed by the completely unfavourable domestic political situation, and, in subsidiary, by the recurrent fluctuation, characteristic to the entire foreign policy strategy. In short, the foreign policy profile shaped at the beginning of 1990 does not specifically stand out, which eloquently entitles the label that bears the temporality valence.

What kind of role occupies the Romanian-Russian bilateral relation in this atypical scene of Romanian post December foreign policy? Taking into consideration the chronology of the dates and of the events carried on during the

¹⁶ Idem, *România și noua arhitectură mondială: studii, alocuțiuni, interviuri: 1990-1996*, București, Editura Monitorul Oficial, 1996, pp. 129-130.

¹⁷ “Jurnal Internațional”, February 30th, 1990.

¹⁸ Armand Gosu, *Politica răsăriteană a României: 1990-2005*, in “Contrafort. Revistă de literatură și dialog intelectual”, no. 1 (135), 2006. URL: <http://www.contrafort.md/2006/135/958.html> (Accessed: November 13th, 2009).

¹⁹ Marcel Dinu, *42 de ani în diplomatie. Ambasador sub patru președinți*, București, Editura C.H. Beck, 2009, p. 159.

first months of 1990, we may suppose that the Romanian-Russian relation detained a statute more than privileged, even foreground at the level of the options of Romanian post December foreign policy. Even “the visit at a high level officiated by the Minister of Foreign Affairs of the Soviet Union, Eduard Şevardnadze on January 6th, 1990 in Romania is a proof more than eloquent in this sense”²⁰. Otherwise, this visit marked a precedent at the level of bilateral relations by the size and the amplitude of the objectives traced under its different aspects, both politically and economically and technical-scientifically. On the agenda of the official debates “the issues of bilateral relations had been examined in a stringent way, expressing the mutual decision to develop them on a healthy, efficient basis, in the interest of both parties, starting from observing the principles of independency, sovereignty, rights equality, non-interference with the internal affairs, mutual confidence, liberty of option and territorial integrity, with the aim to propel the bilateral collaboration both on the world scene and within international organisations”²¹.

In short, a multitude of notable actions meant to regenerate the bilateral relations and by analogy a first step in resetting the relationships. Besides, if we take into account the official statements given by the Romania former Minister of Foreign Affairs in that period, Sergiu Celac, who asserted during an interview that “together with the official visit of Şevardnadze, it was agreed to revise the juridical frame of the bilateral relations”²², we dispose of the complete scene concerning the amplitude and the implications of the visit on January 06th, 1990.

Beyond doubt, the dialogue at a high level was reiterated, and the most decisive example in this sense was “the working visit of Romanian Minister of Foreign Affairs Sergiu Celac in the Soviet Union upon the invitation of Eduard Şevardnadze on March 08th, 1990, with the explicit purpose to grant substance and gravity to bilateral relations on new and solid grounds, of real convergence concerning both states”²³. The debates remarked by the “working character allotted to practical objectives and of tangible results recorded on short term, marking thus a moment of reconsiderations in bilateral relations”²⁴. The ambivalent desideratum of co-operation at the level of all stages of mutual interest prevailed, but the foreground component was the economical one. “Starting from the premise that the economics trains the politics, intense and efficacious actions meant to stimulate the commercial changes at the bilateral level were activated”²⁵. Besides, contacts between heads of government and ministers were perpetuated for a better bilateral receptivity. Last but not least, a series of preliminary stages meant to assure a pragmatic co-operation and a durable partnership were initiated, confirming the availability of both parties to grant gravity and substance to their relations.

²⁰ Ion Calafeteanu, *Istoria politicii externe româneşti în date*, Bucureşti, Fundaţia Europeană Titulescu, 2002, p. 605.

²¹ “Adevărul”, January 7th, 1990.

²² Interview with the Ambassador Sergiu Celac, Romanian former Minister of Foreign Affairs between December 28th, 1989 and June 28th, 1990, realised on March 5th, 2011.

²³ *Lumea azi*, March 11th-15th, 1990.

²⁴ “Adevărul”, March 13th, 1990.

²⁵ *Ibidem*, March 15th, 1990.

Still, the real synergy bilaterally materialized was detected, together with the “visit of the counsellor of Romanian presidency, Ioan Mircea Pașcu at Moscow, on February 09th, 1991, with the purpose to transmit a personal message to Mihail Gorbaciov”²⁶. The meaning of the visit, otherwise emblematic, hypostatized in the most eloquent manner, the consensual desideratum “to institute a new formula of interaction, as organic as possible, at the level of both states”²⁷ with the view to increase the bilateral process. On this monumental occasion, the parties involved corroborated their efforts by establishing a solid relationship in the benefit of both parties. The central objective was centred on the “reconstitution of a security system under the patronage of the Soviet Union in Eastern Europe”²⁸, Romania showing an unconditioned support in favour of concretisation of this demarche. Besides, both parties harmonized their initiatives with the view to reconceptualise in a mutual advantageously manner of the new juridical-bilateral format, demarche also required by the international context. On the grounds of a well-articulated strategy, the two states proposed a reshape of the juridical frame as a new treaty; this document was due to define the legal ground of mutual co-operation, stimulating the expansion of bilateral co-operation actions and starting new possibilities of dialogue and rapprochement between the two States; synthetically, an amplitude demarche adequate to mutual exigencies, demarche that approved a remarkable evolution and an ascendant trend at a bilateral level.

By an ascertaining analyse of the events trajectory characteristic to 1990-1991, it may be concluded that Romania showed an increased interest concerning the elaboration of the best modalities and procedures of re-establishing a *modus vivendi* in a bilateral dimension, adopting a particular strategy related to Moscow. At the level of Romanian foreign policy equation, prevailed the unchangeable desideratum of an open, pragmatic and constructive bilateral relation with the Kremlin homologues. The official statements of the former President in that period, which reflects the conviction that “it was a matter of natural, normal relations”²⁹, attests this unanimously expressed will. Synthetically, Romania was aiming to perpetuate the bilateral relationships, distinguishing itself actively and tacitly in the scene of reconfiguration efforts of the entire policy destined to Kremlin. The most eloquent testimony in this sense was represented by the perseverance with which intense demarches were began on the edge of negotiation and signing of the new bilateral treaty. Subsumed to the entire strategy dedicated to the Eastern neighbour, the treaty represented the legal guarantor of bilateral relations recalibration based upon new and modern

²⁶ Armand Gosu, Sabina Fati, *Iliescu a acționat pentru apărarea intereselor URSS-ului*, in “Evenimentul Zilei”, July 26th, 2004, URL: <http://www.hotnews.ro/știri-arhiva-1262128-iliescu-acționat-pentru-apararea-intereselor-urss-ului.htm?cfym>, Accessed: September 18th, 2009.

²⁷ Șerban Papacostea, *Sfârșitul unei tiranii și începutul unei mistificări istorice. Revelațiile unui document ignorat*, in “Revista 22”, XXI (1085) (December 21th, 2010-January, 3th, 2011), p. 12.

²⁸ Idem, *Post-scriptum la o controversă*, in “Revista 22”, XXII (1097) (March 15th-21th, 2011), URL: <http://www.revista22.ro/post-scriptum-la-o-controvers259-10158.html>, (Accessed: March 25th 2011).

²⁹ Interview with Ion Iliescu, Former President of Romania during 1990-1996/ 2000-2004, realised on May 11th 2011.

principles according to the norms of the international law. In such a referential optic, “Romanian diplomacy was undertaking, by the voice of the president, to sign on April 5th, 1991, during a tour officiated in the Soviet Union, the Treaty of Collaboration, Good Vicinity and Amity”³⁰, “a document eminently positive that reflected both the metamorphosis carried on publicly, economically and socially in both states, and the processes devolved in the European dimension and the international relations”³¹.

Contrary to the “Old Treaty of Friendship, Collaboration and Mutual Assistance, signed between the Socialist Republic of Romania and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics, which was visibly impregnated with the ideological component, the new Romanian-Soviet treaty, meant to replace the one of 1970, presented a flexible and new structure, on the basis of 23 articles prefiguring the main action directions, as well as the primordial objectives that were underlying the relationships between the two states”³². The stages of mutual interests were primarily centred on the economical, social, cultural and scientific co-operation, by an intensification of changes at a high level. Integrally, the treaty aimed at “reshaping the normative frame of the bilateral relations with the will to get out of the restraint of military alliance and to insert European values and the political transformations regionally started within the document”³³. Incontestably, the Romanian-Soviet agreement was perceived as a “European stage of the bilateral dialogue, approving a frame of good vicinity, expression of geopolitical situation and of economical imperatives”³⁴. According to the statements of Vasile Buga, collaborator of the mixed Romanian-Russian committee of history, “the treaty represented the most adequate instrument of regulation of bilateral relationships and the express modality to denounce the old treaty of mutual assistance”³⁵. One must not neglect the relevant information provided by the Ambassador Ion Porojan who considers the treaty as “consubstantial to the securitization strategy of the Romanian people, having in view the unfavourable geopolitical situation where Romania placed during that period”³⁶.

How can the gesture of signing the Treaty of Collaboration, Good Vicinity and Amity be interpreted in its subtle dimension? Eminently, as one that reflects the signal of contiguity on a bilateral level, both parties were promoting a policy of substantial proximity. Complementary, it also denotes the “voluntary option of Romanian political decision makers to perpetuate the relations”³⁷ under all

³⁰ Iulian Chifu, *România-Rusia: lungul drum de la dialog la cooperare*, in “Occasional Papers”, no. 2, 2003, p. 27.

³¹ Ion Iliescu, *Momente de istorie...*, cit., pp. 251-252.

³² Adrian Năstase, *România după Malta: 875 de zile la Externe*, vol. IV, (1 Martie-30 Aprilie 1991), Bucureşti, Fundația Europeană Titulescu, 2007, p. 149.

³³ *Ibidem*, p. 230.

³⁴ Idem, *România și noua arhitectură mondială...*, cit., p. 115.

³⁵ Interview with University Professor Vasile Buga, collaborator of the mixed Romanian-Russian committee of history and former diplomat within the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, realised on March 08th 2011.

³⁶ Interview with Ambassador Ion Porojan, realised on February 17th 2011.

³⁷ Ruxandra Ivan, *L'ombre de l'Empire. Les Rapports de la Roumanie à la Russie, 1991-2006*, in “Romanian Political Science Review”, vol. VIII, no. 3, 2008, p. 521.

possible aspects and in the benefit of the parties involved. The clues are various in this sense. For example, the intransigency of the Romanian party concerning the necessity of signing the document unquestionable attests this thing. Besides, if we take into account the fact that “Romania was the first state aroused by the idea of signing the Romanian-Soviet treaty”³⁸ we fully have the necessary data to remark the obedient conduct of Romania in relation with Moscow. Adrian Cioroianu, former Romanian minister of Foreign Affairs during April 5th 2007 and April 15th 2008, has the same opinion and considers the treaty as “part of the pact between the new management in Bucharest and the officials in Moscow, a real vassalage document of the new management in Bucharest towards the management in Moscow.”³⁹ Related to the complexity of bilateral topos, nothing is more probative that the “clause inserted in article 4, clause by which both parties are interdicted from participating in any military alliance perceived as hostile by any of the signatory parties”⁴⁰. This clause hypostatizes in a manner more than obvious, the veridical interests of the Soviet Union towards Romania, interests associated to the regimentation of Romanian state within its area and influence sphere, by concretising thus the foreseen organic mechanism of interaction. Confronted with the probability of having its legitimate right “of choosing for the security arrangements in compliance with the national interest”⁴¹ obstructed, Romania showed an impassive attitude, which is not surprising at all, having in view the simplistic and superficial approach with which this matter had been treated. Undeniably, the ease allotted to this stringent matter denotes the insistent will of Romania concerning the perpetuation of relations no matter what. With the same ease, the territorial claims towards “Bessarabia, North of Bucovina and Herta region, old Romanian regions attached to the Soviet Union on the grounds of secret protocol of Ribbentrop-Molotov pact”⁴² were dropped out. Despite the effusions and the unionist movements coagulated in the Republic of Moldavia, “the treaty laid a lead slab over the incipient efforts of the unionist supporters”⁴³, preferring a policy of economical and cultural interference proved by the existence of two Romanian states. “Praising the importance of the treaty by the simple fact that it granted the possibility of a direct contract with the federal republics, Romania consented in a tacit manner both the abdication from territorial claims and the independency and the sovereignty of the second Romanian state”⁴⁴. Contrary to the ambivalent enthusiasm, the treaty did not reach its stipulated objectives, the issues of internal order of the Soviet Union, “ended in the putsch in August 1991 and then in the dissolution of the heterogeneous conglomerate of USSR,

³⁸ “România Liberă”, April 3th, 1991.

³⁹ Interview with Adrian Cioroianu, Former Romanian Minister of Foreign Affairs between April 5th 2007 and April 15th 2008, realised on March 07th 2011.

⁴⁰ Janusz Bugajski, *Pacea rece: noul imperialism al Rusiei*, București, Casa Radio, 2005, p. 284.

⁴¹ Vasile Buga, *Romanian-Russian Relations: Stage and Perspectives*, in “Occasional Papers”, no. 2, 2003. Casa Nato, p. 9.

⁴² “România Liberă”, April 13th, 1991.

⁴³ Adrian Cioroianu, *Geopolitica Matrioșkăi: Rusia postsovietică în noua ordine mondială*, București, Editura Curtea Veche, 2009, p. 263.

⁴⁴ Dragomir Eminescu, *Diplomație și politică: note de jurnal*, Iași, Editura Junimea, 2010, p. 96.

supervened in December 1991”⁴⁵, irretrievably hindering the ratification of the international document. However, the Treaty of Collaboration, Good Vicinity and Amity marked a precedent at a bilateral level, reflecting the preliminary strategy of recalibration of bilateral relations, but also an emblematic intent statement of Romania in its relationship with Moscow, the intent to range and to maintain in its strategic proximity. As a matter of fact, the entire demarches specific to 1990-1991 converge in the same direction: Romania was systematically sustaining the bilateral co-operation, opting for a substance and gravity dialogue with the Eastern neighbour.

The atypical portraiture of Romanian post December foreign policy reserves a privileged statute to Moscow. Having in view the relatively sinuous and dragged process of gradual involvement of Romania in the Euro-Atlantic security structures and mechanisms, the political decision makers re-evaluated the relationships with the Soviet Union, showing their availability to perpetuate the contacts with the Kremlin officials. The performance of Romanian diplomacy issued credible messages, reshaping the entire strategy destined to the Eastern neighbour by a series of actions, demarches and dynamic initiatives, but especially constructive in this sense. With the intent to imprint a redefined form to these relations, the political decision makers promoted a policy based upon the inference of the consensus in relations with Moscow. The multiple contacts at high level and even the initiative of rescheduling the juridical frame under the format of the Treaty of Collaboration, Good Vicinity and Amity, obviously attest this reality. Not for a moment did the Romanian political leadership practice spacing in the bilateral dimension, but rather pleaded for a policy of substantial proximity. As a conclusion, Romania of the 1990-1991 cherished a harmonization of bilateral interests, still gravitating within the orbit of Moscow’s influence.

⁴⁵ The gradual decomposition of the Soviet Union had as a cause, beyond the economical explanation, one of internal nature, legitimated by the resurgence of the nationalist feeling in every component republic of USSR. As a consequence, the soviet republics and the other republics and autonomous regions started to claim their independency and autonomy, claiming to follow their own destiny, pledging for an official language, economical, political and even military independence. For further details concerning the collapse of the Soviet Union see the book of Vasile Buga, *Apusul unui imperiu: URSS în epoca Gorbaciov: 1985-1991*, București, Institutul Național pentru Studiul Totalitarismului, 2007.

ROMANIAN EAST-WEST MIGRATION. HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

This paper is structured in four parts, and deals with the multiple and complex dimensions of migration. Within the general context of the European population flux phenomenon of the last years, it draws attention on East-West migration, particularly regarding Romanians. Comparative statistical data are presented, causes and consequences of emigration are analyzed.

Keywords: East-West Migratory Flux, Romanian Emigration, Labour Force Market

1. Overlook upon the European international migration

On the European continent, since the '90, at the same time as the fall of the Block of the closed totalitarian regimes, a strong population flux from East towards West has been registered.

Migration refers to the number of migrants, people changing their residence to or from a given area (usually a country) during a given time period (usually one year).⁸⁶⁷ The emigrants are national citizens who settled their permanent residence abroad.

This migratory flux that aimed the Western Europe was part of a “situation overthrow” that has marked the Old Continent, which represented the departure point for the highest emigrants’ fluxes once.⁸⁶⁸ It was approximated that during 1850 – 1920, over 50 millions of Europeans emigrated towards America, Australia, India and other areas. Now the Western part was transformed in a *terminus point*. Since 1990, every year, Western Europe has recorded over 2 millions of immigrants. The decent life conditions, the observance of the fundamental freedoms of man, the huge demand of labour force, and the perspectives of socio-politic and economic development were the fundamental factors that determined Europe to be, particularly, the continent that absorbed till 2000, the higher number of immigrants in the world: approximately 60 millions⁸⁶⁹. Asia was next, with 50 millions, explainable by the huge surface of this continent, and by the numerous socio-political problems in certain countries, fact that determines massive population movements. Contrary to our expectations, North America was placed only on the third place, with over 40 millions of immigrants.

But it is only *recently* that *the migration towards the Western Europe has acquired such an extension*, demographic phenomenon in which the population of Romania is highly implied. The total number of non-

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⁸⁶⁷http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/statistics_explained/index.php/Glossary:Migration, accessed 16.11.2011

⁸⁶⁸ Maria Georgescu, *Provocări socioeconomice*, Cluj-Napoca, Editura Casa Cărții de Știință, 2005, p. 95.

⁸⁶⁹ It is shown in the Report of the International Organization for Migration, dated 5th May 2004.

nationals (people who are not citizens of their country of residence) living on the territory of the EU Member States on 1 January 2010 was 32.5 million, representing 6.5 % of the EU-27's population⁸⁷⁰. Across the EU as a whole, Turkish citizens made up the biggest group of non-nationals. This group comprised 2.4 million people in 2010, or 7.2 % of all non-nationals living in the EU. The second biggest group, was Romanians living in another EU Member State (6.6 % of the non-national population), followed by Moroccans.

<p>Main citizenships of foreigners residing in the EU-27 countries, 2010 - hierarchy</p> <p>Romania Poland Italy Portugal United Kingdom</p> <p>Main citizenships of foreigners residing in non-EU countries, 2010 - hierarchy</p> <p>Turkey Morocco Albania China Ukraine</p>
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Fig.1 Main citizenships of foreigners in the EU-27, 2010

Source: Eurostat, Migration⁸⁷¹

The group of non-nationals with the most significant increase over the period 2001 to 2010 was Romanians, whose number living in other Member States increased by seven times over the period considered (from 0.3 million in 2001 to 2.1 million people by 2010).

2. The escape from the totalitarian space

Romania represents now a country with a massive migration directed to the Western areas. But it was not the same situation under the communist regime. Table nr.1 shows that the official emigration was very low.

Table1. Romanian emigration before 1990

Period	Number of persons
1966 – 1970	22.800
1971 – 1975	45.400
1976 – 1980	59.600
1981 – 1985	96.900
1986 – 1989	84.900

Source: E. I. Gheorghiu⁸⁷²

⁸⁷⁰ <http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/portal/population/data/database>.

⁸⁷¹ Katya Vasileva, *Statistics in focus*, 34/2011, published on 14.07.2011

Other empirical sources are revealing the nationality criteria for the classification of the individuals overflowed. In particular, ethnic reasons and political asylum seeking were the main factors for the decision to go outside.

Table 2. Emigrants from Romania, by nationality, between 1975 and 1989

Period	Germans	Jews	Hungarian s	Romanian s	Others	Total
1975-1979	36 911	7 758	5 296	23 243	1 503	74 711
1980-1984	62 376	6 412	8 809	46 545	2 024	126 166
1985-1989	60 818	5 575	32 248	58 787	4 159	161 587

Source: Cornelia Mureșan⁸⁷³

By nationality, Germans were on the top of the external flow persons and, the idea of ancient regime administrators was to make them pay the scholar taxes before leaving Romania.

3. Recent Romanian emigration

Once *an option for living*, the circulatory migration of the labor force has been analyzed by the sociologists as, given the present situation, it represents the most dynamic form of social mobility in Romania.

For a comparative view, we can see the evolution of the number of emigrants, by nationality, after 1990 (Table Nr.3, Annex I). Immediately after the changing the political regime, in 1990, a large number of Germans and Hungarians left the country, having as destination Germany, respectively – Hungary. Also, a lot of Romanian nationals wanted to benefit the opportunity to get abroad. The presented data make us believe that East-West migration did not represent a genuine invasion of the Western countries. The presumed “demographic invasion” – with the foreseen consequent instabilities - seemed to be just a myth which the statistical available data do not confirm, the dynamic tendency of emigration flux being that of decreasing.

The actual reasons for emigration from Romania are:

a. The average net monthly salary in Romania is little (in 2006 it was 866 lei, in 2007 – 1042, in 2008 – 1309, in 2009 – 1361 and in 2010, it was 1391 lei⁸⁷⁴ - about 330 Euros) while in the EU it could be 3 or 4 times higher. Therefore, the salary is the main reason why the Romanians are attracted to

⁸⁷² *Migrația Est-Vest între mit și realitate*, Revista de cercetări sociale, București, Nr.1-2, 1999, pp.179-185

⁸⁷³ *Evoluția demografică a României*, Presa universitară clujeană, Cluj-Napoca, 1999, p.97

⁸⁷⁴ <http://www.insse.ro/cms/rw/pages/castiguri1938.ro.do>, accessed in 3.12.2011

working in the Western countries. Recently, doctors and nurses are flowing intensively abroad.

b. Another major cause of migration is related to the labor force market, mainly to the lack of jobs, not so much unemployment but more an ineffective correlation between professional training and the present market's demand for labor force. For example, at present most young people are choosing economics and law and the labor force market is fully covered in these areas. Thus, when they graduate and don't find jobs in their area of study, they chose to leave the country. Most legal emigrants have a high level of training and education, as proved by the selective character of the immigration policies of the countries of destination.

c. A significant number of Romanians have been emigrating because of their dissatisfaction with corruption at all levels, because of the political unrest, because of the laws' ambiguity that leaves room to interpretations, because of numerous legislative changes and because of the great number of taxes that place Romania on the first positions in the world and Europe (Romania is the fourth in the world and the first in the EU according to the number of taxes that a company has to pay for a year, with 96 taxes, a double number compared to that from other European countries such as Poland or Slovakia, as reported by PricewaterhouseCoopers and The World Bank which have analyzed 178 countries).

All these problems have a psychological effect on the citizens and they start thinking about leaving their country.

Table 4. Main countries of citizenship of the Romanian emigrants, 2010

(in absolute numbers and as a percentage of the total foreign population)

Country	1000	%
Italy	887.8	21.0
Spain	823.1	14.5
Hungary	72.8	36.4
Portugal	32.5	7.1
Ireland	11.8	3.1
Slovakia	5.4	8.6

Source: Eurostat, Migration,⁸⁷⁵

It is also important to underline that the pressure of the labor force migration to the European area has been (and it will be) attenuated also by the last years' option of an increasing part of the labor force to find work in countries outside the EU, mainly in the USA and Canada, which promote a more permissive policy for certain jobs and areas, even one that attracts

⁸⁷⁵ Katya Vasileva, *Statistics in focus*, 34/2011, published on 14.07.2011

young labor force. The distance is no longer a significant restriction and the modern transport and communication systems remove the barriers that seemed hard to be passed in the previous decades.

At the same time we have to mention that the employment of the overqualified people, with special performances, in our country, remains a delicate issue, of tensioning migration flows as long as the national economy doesn't offer attractive solutions. We appreciate that from the point of view of the brains' emigration, Romania will continue to represent an area of high interest for the transnational companies or for the international scientific research.

Yet the challenges that the national economy is faced with the loss of productive and creative potential are a too costly luxury for Romania for medium or long-term future.

4. Consequences of migration

For the external migration to represent a factor in stimulating the development of national economy, it is necessary for the policies pertaining to this area to find the balance between using the labor force on the national level and the migration for work (to avoid unemployment), and to do this by taking into consideration the costs, benefits, risks, the national and the EU interests. However, the two interest groups should not be divergent, but advantageous, beneficial to all.

A consideration of the positive and negative consequences of migration indicates that the negative ones weigh more in the balance. At the same time one can observe that the positive effects are for short term and can change into negative ones at any moment, while the negative effects are for long term and are difficult to change. Without overlooking the advantages, we have to underline that for long term the migration for work can have unexpected effects by means of the followings:

- The significant qualitative and quantitative decrease of national labor force offer;
- The low adjustment of the possibilities for reducing the inconsistencies regarding the competitiveness of the Romanian products on the foreign markets and as regards filling the necessary positions for highly competitive professions/ occupations;
- Limiting the possibilities of reducing income differences in comparison with the EU countries and implicitly the encouragement of migration for work;
- The emergence on the national level of ineffective segments for labor force training;
- Speeding up the process of demographic aging with all the implied social problems.
- The major problem of the country of origin is the loss of an important demographic potential, mainly represented by the young population, and on the other hand the loss of labor force into which money has been invested by education and training. Thus we have to do with an

investment that hasn't reached its purpose and which the developed countries benefit from. Within the same context we should mention that the migration for work of the Romanian human capital, mainly of the young population, represents the main form of the external flow. (See Table Nr.5, Annex II)

The questions that arise indicate that we are confronted with at least two fundamental issues:

The first is *whether we should focus or not on a strategy for keeping the labor force in the country?* Working abroad seems to have generated a real national satisfaction, so should we consider it as the fundamental option from now on or only a temporary one? Are we going to tacitly encourage an external flow of the individuals, or encourage the creation of jobs in the country with the immediate result of production development, a fact that would place Romania on another position rather than a simple sale market?

Another aspect to be considered at present - *if the pressure of immigration towards Romania is real?* As it has become the Eastern border of the EU, Romania has also turned to be a transit point for other immigrants and very frequently terminus point for Moldavian, Chinese, Turkish citizens. The number of immigrants that have received the right to have a residence in Romania is generating a constant decrease of the negative balance of migration (See Table Nr.6, Annex II).

Net migration is the difference between immigration to and emigration from a given area during the year (net migration is positive when there are more immigrants than emigrants and negative when there are more emigrants than immigrants)⁸⁷⁶. The very low fertility synthetic index and massive emigration could be compensated demographically by immigrants' flows. Thus, into a further future, Romania can become an immigration country, yet with a significant contingent of autochthonous population working abroad. It will also represent a *source* for West emigration and a beneficiary of East and South immigration. This status is not to be enjoyed and consequently we have to attenuate as much as possible the unfavorable effects on the national labor force market - the disorganization of the labor force offer and its deficient adjustment to the national market demand, on average, a lower level of the education and professional training of the labor force present on the labor market compared to the structure of the graduates coming from the initial education system and complementarily, a lower creative potential, precarious employability, the increase of job's insecurity, and rather modest productive performances.

We will end by making reference to the idea of J. C. Chesnais, who, in his book „Le crépuscule de l'Occident” (1995)⁸⁷⁷ predicted that more and more

⁸⁷⁶http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/statistics_explained/index.php/Glossary:Migration, accessed 16.11.2011

⁸⁷⁷ Apud Cornelia Mureșan, *Evoluția demografică a României*, Cluj-Napoca, Presa Universitară Clujeană, 1999, p. 101.

Eastern states will have to handle a massive establishment of emigrants coming from less advanced countries and foresaw a *demographic convergence between Eastern and Western Europe*.

Annex I

Table 3. The dynamics of emigrants' structure by nationality after 1990

Persons	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009
Romanians	23.888	19.307	18.104	8.814	10.146	18.706	16.767	16.883	15.202	11.283	13.438	9.023	7.465	9.886	11.890	10.301	13.296	8.589	8.485	10.052
Germans	60.072	15.567	8.852	5.945	4.065	2.906	2.315	1.273	775	390	374	143	67	20	36	93	85	12	18	15
Hungarians	11.040	7.494	3.523	3.206	2.509	3.608	2.105	1.459	1.217	696	788	647	489	661	1.062	460	693	167	194	103
Jews	745	516	224	221	177	131	191	136	198	111	66	72	28	24	36	48	54	21	27	27
Others	1.184	1.276	449	260	249	324	148	194	144	114	87	36	105	82	58	36	69	41	15	14
TOTAL	96.929	44.160	31.152	18.446	17.146	25.675	21.526	19.945	17.536	12.594	14.753	9.921	8.154	10.673	13.082	10.938	14.197	8.830	8.739	10211

%	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009
Romanians	25%	44%	58%	48%	59%	73%	78%	85%	87%	90%	91%	91%	92%	93%	91%	94%	94%	97%	97%	98%
Germans	62%	35%	28%	32%	24%	11%	11%	6%	4%	3%	3%	1%	1%	0%	0%	1%	1%	0%	0%	0%
Hungarians	11%	17%	11%	17%	15%	14%	10%	7%	7%	6%	5%	7%	6%	6%	8%	4%	5%	2%	2%	1%
Jews	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	0%	1%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Others	1%	3%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	0%	1%	1%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
TOTAL	100%																			

Source: National Institute of Statistics, Annual Statistical Yearbook/2010

Table 5. Emigrants by age group

Persons	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009
Under18 years	25298	14.83 7	5.540	4.119	4.597	5.137	4.198	4.145	6.371	4.290	4.372	2.860	1.233	1.677	1.417	765	963	1.003	1.214	1.316
18-25 years	13570	7.949	7.807	3.608	3.036	4.180	3.447	2.559	1.795	1.357	1.513	938	1.029	1.426	1.920	1.408	1.726	1.062	1.054	1.270
26-40 years	25.58 9	10.86 3	10.19 5	5.683	5.901	10.87 5	8.347	8.091	5.379	4.244	5.717	4.017	3.972	5.438	7.174	6.359	8.198	4.979	4.775	5.351
41-60 years	21.10 1	6.889	5.110	3.229	2.528	4.048	4.033	3.633	2.554	1.900	2.208	1.442	1.332	1.608	1.991	1.900	2.621	1.442	1.419	1.393
61 years and up	11.37 1	3.622	2.500	1.807	1.084	1.435	1.501	1.517	1.437	803	943	664	588	524	580	506	689	344	277	881
TOTAL	96.92 9	44.16 0	31.15 2	18.44 6	17.14 6	25.67 5	21.52 6	19.94 5	17.53 6	12.59 4	14.75 3	9.92 1	8.15 4	10.67 3	13.08 2	10.93 8	14.19 7	8.83 0	8.73 9	10.21 1

%	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009
Under18 years	26%	34%	18%	22%	27%	20%	20%	21%	36%	34%	30%	29%	15%	16%	11%	7%	7%	11%	14%	13%
18-25 years	14%	18%	25%	20%	18%	16%	16%	13%	10%	11%	10%	9%	13%	13%	15%	13%	12%	12%	12%	12%
26-40 years	26%	25%	33%	31%	34%	42%	39%	41%	31%	34%	39%	40%	49%	51%	55%	58%	58%	56%	55%	52%
41-60 years	22%	16%	16%	18%	15%	16%	19%	18%	15%	15%	15%	15%	16%	15%	15%	17%	18%	16%	16%	14%
61 years and up	12%	8%	8%	10%	6%	6%	7%	8%	8%	6%	6%	7%	7%	5%	4%	5%	5%	4%	3%	9%
	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Source: National Institute of Statistics, Annual Statistical Yearbook/2010

Table 6. Long term evolution of the total migration flows

Persons	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009
Emigrants	44.160	31.152	18.446	17.146	25.675	21.526	19.945	17.536	12.594	14.753	9.921	8.154	10.673	13.082	10.938	14.197	8.830	8.739	10.211
Immigrants	1.602	1.753	1.269	878	4.458	2.053	6.600	11.907	10.078	11.024	10.350	6.582	3.267	2.987	3.704	7.714	9.575	10.030	8.606
Net migration	-42.558	-29.399	-17.177	-16.268	-21.217	-19.473	-13.345	-5.629	-2.516	-3.729	429	-1.572	-7.406	-10.095	-7.234	-6.483	745	1.291	-1.472

Source: National Institute of Statistics, Annual Statistical Yearbook/2010

THE EU PERSPECTIVE FOR THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA AND THE EU POLITICAL MESSAGE IN 2011

Simion Costea*

Abstract

The Alliance for the European Integration won the parliamentary and local elections in 2009-2011, supports the pro-European Government that implements pro-European policies. Positive EU country reports mention the progress of the Republic of Moldova, but the European Neighbourhood Policy does not encourage a future EU Membership. However, Moldova is a European country and, when it will be prepared, it has the right to ask to become a candidate country.

Keywords: EU, Republic of Moldova, Communication, Country Reports, E.N.P., Eastern Partnership, Government, Crisis, European Integration

EU-Moldova Political Dialogue and Governance

The EU political communication¹ and message regarding the Republic of Moldova in 2011 (EC and High Representative, Joint Communication, Country Reports, public declaration of EU leaders etc) reveals a complex situation, but open the way for a future European integration of this country.

In 2011, the Republic of Moldova is the most democratic and the most pro-European country in the Eastern Partnership. The Alliance for the European Integration and its government won several successive elections in 2009-2011 and implements pro-European reforms. This evolution in Moldova is in contrast with the situation in other Eastern Partnership countries, where authoritarian tendencies increased in 2009-2011. As a result, the interest of EU and the USA for Moldova increased, and this is proved by the visits of several western leaders to Chisinau (including Joe Biden, Jerzy Buzek etc), by the conference of donors, by the progress in EU-Moldova negotiations. The Republic of Moldova benefits from a positive differentiation in the framework of the European Neighbourhood Policy and of EU's Eastern Partnership.

EU's Eastern Partnership, the Eastern dimension of the ENP framework², has as objective a substantially upgrading engagement with the 6 Eastern neighbours via:

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¹ Alex Mucchelli, Jean Antoine Corbalan, *Teoria comunicării*, Iaşi, Editura Institutului European, 2006; Jacques Gerstle, *Comunicarea politică*, Iasi, Editura Institutului European, 2002; Guy Lochard, Henry Boyer, *Comunicarea mediatică*, Iasi, Editura Institutului European, 1999; Denis Mcquail, *Comunicarea*, Iasi, Editura Institutului European, 1999.

² Sharon Pardo, Joel Peters, *Uneasy Neighbors. Israel and the European Union*, Plymouth, Lexington Books, 2010; Marise Cremona, "The European Neighbourhood Policy: More than

- Bilateral track, whose objectives include Association Agreements, Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Areas as well as progress on visa and mobility issues
- Multilateral track (i.e. intergovernmental platforms and Flagship Initiatives)³.

This approach allows for gradual political association and deeper economic integration. Moldova, Ukraine and Georgia are the most advanced Eastern European countries in this regard.

The EU-Moldova Action Plan was approved in 2005. A reform priorities matrix was tabled by the EU side in May 2010, and a yearly implementation tool was adopted at the EU-Republic of Moldova Cooperation Council of June 2010⁴.

Negotiations on a future EU- Moldova Association Agreement (AA) were launched in January 2010. „Negotiations since then have been progressing at a very good pace”, as the European Commission estimates, in 25 May 2011⁵. Association requires transposing large parts of the EU *acquis* into national law. Moldova (Ukraine and Georgia too) will then be anchored in the EU culture of law and policy. Meanwhile, the EU co-operation with Russia has never been more active⁶.

EU and Moldova established a regular human rights dialogue in 2009. In April 2010 a new law on freedom of expression was adopted, providing criteria for identifying and combating censorship and external interference in the editorial policy of media, including intimidation of journalists or obstruction to their activities. The Criminal code was updated accordingly⁷. This is a concrete progress in implementation of the Programme of the Government of the Alliance for the European Integration.

EU requests new concrete achievements in the field from the Republic of Moldova. As the Country Report mentions, further progress is needed to ensure implementation of the measures adopted in accordance with the EU-Moldova ENP Action Plan and, especially to strengthen the mechanisms for preventing violations of human rights and fundamental freedoms, to further reform the

a Partnership?”, in Eadem (ed.), *Developments in EU External Relations Law*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2008; Michele Comelli, Ettore Greco, Nathalie Tocci, *From Boundary to Borderland: Transforming the Meaning of Borders in Europe through the European Neighbourhood Policy*, in “European Foreign Affairs Review”, vol. 12, issue 2, summer 2007, pp. 203-218; Laure Delcour, Elsa Tulmets (eds), *Pioneer Europe? Testing EU Foreign Policy in the Neighbourhood*, Baden-Baden, Nomos, 2008; Roberto Albioni, *The Geopolitical Implications of the European Neighbourhood Policy*, in “European Foreign Affairs Review”, vol. 10, no. 1, Spring 2005, pp. 1-16; Krassimir Y. Nikolov (ed.), *The European Neighbourhood Policy: Time to Deliver*, in “BECSA”, May 2008; Leila Alieva, *EU and the South Caucasus*, in *CAP Discussion paper*, Berlin, Bertelsmann Stiftung, December 2006; Egidio Canciani, *European Financial Perspective and the European Neighbourhood and Partnership Instrument*, in “Mediterranean Yearbook 2007”, Barcelona, European Institute of the Mediterranean.

³ European Commission, *ENP Country Progress Report 2009 – Rep. of Moldova*, Memo 10/182, Brussels, 12 May 2010, http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/documents_en.htm

⁴ European Commission, *Country Report Moldova 2010*, Brussels, 25 May 2011, http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/pdf/progress2011/sec_11_643_en.pdf.

⁵ *Ibidem*.

⁶ Radosław Sikorski, Carl Bildt, Štefan Füle, *The new normal*, 29.09.2011, <http://www.europeanvoice.com/article/2011/september/the-new-normal-/72162.aspx>.

⁷ European Commission, *ENP Country Progress Report 2009 - Rep. of Moldova*, Memo 10/182, Brussels, 12 May 2010, http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/documents_en.htm

judiciary and to ensure the rule of law and the neutrality of the public media and to promote a pluralistic media environment, to enhance the fight against trafficking in human beings, and to improve matching labour market needs with skills development⁸.

The Council of Europe considers that Moldova has achieved good progress in fighting corruption. Moldova improved its ranking in the Transparency International Corruption Perception Index⁹. This is a progress, but corruption remains a serious and widespread phenomenon and there are many things to do to reduce it.

The reformist legislation was adopted, but its implementation was poor due to the lack of resources at local and central level, but also to the political uncertainty. During the parliamentary week, the majority of the Alliance for the European Integration, the failure of the Presidential election and of the referendum on the Constitutional Amendment, in September 2010, undermines the success of the pro-European policies. The weak implementation capacity is a real problem for the Moldovan institutions in all fields¹⁰.

The EU Common Foreign and Security Policy and the Transnistria Dilemma
Moldova cooperates actively with the EU on regional and international issues, and has aligned itself with nearly all EU Common Foreign and Security Policy (CFSP) declarations open for alignment. We should note that this alignment is an elementary necessity, but has little practical consequences.

Moldova cooperates with EU on all questions related to the Transnistria settlement efforts, including in the work of the EU Border Assistance Mission to Moldova and Ukraine (EUBAM) and in confidence-building efforts¹¹. As the Country Reports mention, the Republic of Moldova „continued to play a constructive part in the five informal meetings of the so-called “5+2” format”, despite the fact that these efforts did not bring real progress towards the resumption of official talks”¹². In Transnistria, there are no armed incidents any more, but the conflict persists and is far from being solved.

The negotiations in Moscow in 2011 did not bring any progress, because of the lack of political will. Russia uses the frozen conflicts as instruments for its projection of power and influence in the ex-Soviet area¹³. The existence of this fake state characterised by lawless and corruption is also a source of illegal fortunes and is in the interest of some powerful Russian Mafia groups.

⁸ Ibidem.

⁹ European Commission, *ENP Country Progress Report 2009 – Rep of Moldova*, Memo 10/182, Brussels, 12 May 2010, http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/documents_en.htm.

¹⁰ European Commission, *Country Report Moldova 2010*, Brussels, 25 May 2011, http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/pdf/progress2011/sec_11_643_en.pdf.

¹¹ European Commission, *ENP Country Progress Report 2009 – Rep. of Moldova*, Memo 10/182, Brussels, 12 May 2010, http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/documents_en.htm.

¹² European Commission, *Country Report Moldova 2010*, Brussels, 25 May 2011, http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/pdf/progress2011/sec_11_643_en.pdf.

¹³ Adrian Cioroianu, *Geopolitica Matrioșkai. Rusia postsovietica in noua ordine mondiala*, București, Editura Curtea Veche, 2009, *passim*.

Even the Russian press reveals the corruption of the pro-Russian leaders in Transnistria¹⁴.

Russia repeatedly rejected the idea to retreat the Russian troops from Transnistria. Moscow's position has been unchanged for 20 years. The Russian leaders and diplomats rejected this idea in many ways, in the last 20 years, even by using unusual gestures or jokes. As an example, "At a big conference convened in Istanbul, when the retreat of the Russian troops from Transnistria was in question, Yeltsin took off his headphones, he slammed them on the table and made a gesture of leaving the meeting. That is not a gesture for an ordinary diplomat"¹⁵. Another example: when a Romanian Minister of Foreign Affairs, Andrei Plesu, requested for the retreat of the Russian troops from Transnistria, a Russian diplomat answered with nonchalance: "Sir, we want to retreat, but, you know, the tanks are worn out and they do not work! They are, basically, a pile of junk".¹⁶

Kremlin repeatedly proposed a federalisation of the Republic of Moldova as a solution, and in that federation Transnistria would have the power of veto regarding the Moldova's way towards the EU. So the pro-Russian Transnistrian authorities would block the European destiny of the entire Republic of Moldova and would have an enormous influence on Moldova's policies. Even the pro-Russian regime of Voronin (the "Party of Communists") rejected such a solution¹⁷. In our opinion, this is a proof that the profound national interest emerges even in a pro-Russian regime.

The successive Governments in Chisinau do not accept a solution in which Transnistria would decide the major policies and the future of the Republic of Moldova. Also, the successive Moldovan Governments do not accept to abandon the principle of territorial integrity of the Republic of Moldova. However, Transnistria remains a catastrophic difficulty for the European future of the Republic of Moldova.

Some voices wondered whether accepting the clear separation of Transnistria is a solution or not, if it means making the least bad choice, regarding the European perspective of the Republic of Moldova¹⁸. This will remain a dilemma for the next years.

EU Financing for Moldova

2007-2010 the European Neighbourhood Policy Instrument (ENPI) budget for Moldova stands at € 209.7 million, plus € 16.6 million through the Governance Facility¹⁹.

¹⁴ Smirnov: *Cum nu s-ar comporta Rusia cu noi, noi vom continua sa o iubim*, in http://www.publika.md/smirnov--cum-nu-s-ar-comporta-rusia-cu-noi--vom-continua-s-o-iubim_587721.html; *Film despre Familia lui Smirnov: originea veniturilor, casele de milioane si crimele din stanga Nistrului*, in http://www.publika.md/film-despre-familia-lui-smirnov--originea-veniturilor--casele-de-milioane-si-crimele-din-stanga-nistrului-video_606451.html.

¹⁵ Andrei Pleșu, former Minister of Foreign Affairs, *Am dovada existentei lui Dumnezeu*, in "Adevarul", 4.11. 2011, in http://www.adevarul.ro/life/Andrei_Plesu-fost_ministru_de_Externe_-Am_dovada_existentei_lui_Dumnezeu_0_584941942.html

¹⁶ *Ibidem*.

¹⁷ Adrian Cioroianu, *op. cit.*, pp. 285-316.

¹⁸ *Ibidem*, pp. 351-353.

¹⁹ E.N.P. Country Progress Report 2009 – Rep. of Moldova, Memo 10/182, Brussels, May 12th 2010, http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/documents_en.htm.

2011-2013: An ENPI budget of € 273.1 million was announced by the Commission (an increase of nearly 75% annual average)²⁰.

2008-2009 – Neighbourhood Investment Facility (NIF) committed nearly € 20 million to 4 projects in Moldova (in the social sphere and transport sector), plus € 24 million for 3 NIF regional projects (in support of the energy and the private sectors)²¹.

The Republic of Moldova benefited from cooperation activities financed under horizontal instruments such as the European Instrument for Democracy and Human Rights (EIDHR) and the Development Cooperation Instrument (DCI) thematic programmes²².

On 29th January 2010, the IMF agreed to provide financial assistance of approximately USD 560 million (EUR 420 million) spread over 3 years. This was supplemented by EUR 90 million of EU macro-financial assistance²³. During the Moldova Partnership Forum organised in March 2010 by EU and the World Bank, more than 40 international donors, including EU, pledged over € 1.96 billion to support the Government's plan "Rethink Moldova"²⁴.

As several MEPs speeches emphasized, the donors support the pro-European policies of the Government of the Alliance for the European Integration.

However, the ENP financing are at far lower level than the EU financing for the “potential candidate countries”, for the “candidate countries” and for the EU “New Member States”.

Economic integration and trade

Moldova is one of the poorest countries in Europe and in EU's neighbourhood (with an average yearly income of only € 1100 per capita). The country was hit hard by the global financial and economic crisis, and “the GDP contracted by – 6.5% in 2009 (in sharp contrast with + 7.2% growth in 2008)”. The bilateral trade between UE and Moldova fell by 30% in 2009, from € 2.45 billion in 2008, due to the economic crisis. EU is Moldova's biggest trade partner (more than half of the external trade in 2009)²⁵.

The feasibility study on deep and comprehensive Free Trade Area (DCFTA) with EU concludes that it would bring long-lasting benefits for Moldova, but it also requires careful preparation and regulatory approximation in trade-related areas²⁶. Negotiations have not begun until the end of 2011.

The Republic of Moldova is on the position 111 (after Azerbaijan, Turkmenistan, China, Turkey), in the Human Development Index 2011. This is the lowest position of a European country. Moldova is in the third category of countries, with medium human development. The Human Development

²⁰ *Ibidem*.

²¹ ENP Country Progress Report 2009 –Rep of Moldova, Memo 10/182, Brussels, May 12th 2010, http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/documents_en.htm

²² European Commission, *Country Report Moldova 2010*, Brussels, 25 May 2011, http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/pdf/progress2011/sec_11_643_en.pdf

²³ *Ibidem*.

²⁴ ENP Country Progress Report 2009 –Rep of Moldova, Memo 10/182, Brussels, 12 May 2010, http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/documents_en.htm

²⁵ *Ibidem*.

²⁶ *Ibidem*

Index (HDI) is a comparative measure of life expectancy, literacy, education and standards of living for countries worldwide. It is a standard means of measuring well-being, especially child welfare²⁷. So, the EU and the Moldovan public policies should pay a special attention to human development.

EU-Moldova -Sector cooperation

The EU-Moldova cooperation in the field of Education should be very important. In 2007-2009, thanks to Erasmus Mundus grants, 211 Moldovan students and academics participated in exchange programmes with EU universities for up to three years²⁸. 6 Moldovan students were awarded scholarships for Erasmus Mundus Masters Courses under Action 1 in 2010. In 2010, Moldova State University became the first Moldovan University to be selected as a full partner in an Erasmus Mundus Action 1 project, delivering a masters course on migration with EU partner universities. Student and academic mobility was further enhanced under Action 2 Erasmus Mundus with 66 grants in 2010-2011²⁹.

The Academy of Economic Studies in Chisinau received 1 Jean Monnet project in 2010, to increase the understanding of the European integration and Eastern Partnership by public servants, students and academics³⁰.

Higher education reform continued to benefit from participation in Tempus, with 5 projects selected under the third Call for Proposals for Tempus IV in 2010, including support for the creation of doctoral studies in accordance with the policy commitments under the Bologna Process. The programme continues to facilitate implementation of Bologna reforms “with all 17 public universities taking part”³¹.

Youth in Action Programme and 2010 ENP Special Action under the Culture Programme are present in the country. “Opening of future new EU programmes such as Lifelong Learning to Eastern Partnership countries”³² should be an important step forward, especially for encouraging the Republic of Moldova.

In the sector of Health, Moldova continued its reform with substantial budget support from EU (€ 46.6 million) and pursued the fight against HIV/AIDS and tuberculosis³³.

In December 2009 Moldova was admitted to the Energy Community Treaty, which includes commitments for gradual convergence with EU’s internal energy market rules, and implements the Community *acquis* (new gas and

²⁷ *Human Development Index 2011*, in <http://hdr.undp.org/en/statistics/hdi/>

²⁸ European Commission, *ENP Country Progress Report 2009 –Rep of Moldova*, Memo 10/182, Brussels, 12 May 2010, http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/documents_en.htm

²⁹ European Commission, *Country Report Moldova 2010*, Brussels, 25 May 2011, http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/pdf/progress2011/sec_11_643_en.pdf

³⁰ *Ibidem*.

³¹ European Commission, *Country Report Moldova 2010*, Brussels, 25 May 2011, http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/pdf/progress2011/sec_11_643_en.pdf

³² EC and High Representative, *Joint Communication....”A new response to a changing Neighbourhood*”, Brussels 25 May 2011.

³³ European Commission, *ENP Country Progress Report 2009 –Rep of Moldova*, Memo 10/182, Brussels, 12 May 2010, http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/documents_en.htm

electricity laws were adopted in December 2009)³⁴. Moldova continues to be dependent on gas supplies from Russia, which uses the gas prices as an instrument of pressure on the government in Chisinau and on other European governments. The situation is exacerbated by the historical debts and energy inefficiency.

In the field of transport, Moldova is upgrading its road infrastructure (including with EU support) and adopting its regulatory framework in accordance with the international standards. It signed a working arrangement with the European Aviation Safety Agency and is a potential candidate for participation in the Common Aviation Area to be gradually integrated into the EU internal aviation market³⁵. However, the quality of the infrastructure is a real problem for the Republic of Moldova.

Promoting mobility, fighting irregular migration

In 2008, Visa facilitation and readmission agreements came into effect. A pilot Mobility Partnership is signed to strengthen capacities for migration management, to strengthen legal migration opportunities, and to fight illegal migration³⁶.

In order to combat irregular migration, EU demands the new law on asylum, largely in accordance with the international and EU standards, in effect in March 2009. In December 2009, EU and Moldova agreed to start up a visa dialogue in 2010, examining the necessary conditions for visa-free travel as a long-term goal³⁷. EU prepared an Action Plan on visa liberalisation and forwarded it to the Republic of Moldova in January 2011³⁸.

Trafficking in human beings is a major problem. The number of victims still remains high, and much greater efforts are required in order to tackle the organised trafficking networks and the related corruption activities³⁹. In the area of border management, the Republic of Moldova established a National Council on Border Management in September and adopted its Integrated Border Management strategy in November 2010⁴⁰. A constant effective action in the field is necessary, given the corruption and inefficiency found in customs operations.

The most important concrete and practical achievement on free movement is the Local border traffic Agreement (within a 50-km border strip), concluded between Moldova and Romania, in November 2009, that came into effect in February 2010⁴¹. In our opinion, this Agreement should be an example for a

³⁴ *Ibidem*.

³⁵ *Ibidem*.

³⁶ *Ibidem*.

³⁷ European Commission, *ENP Country Progress Report 2009 –Rep of Moldova*, Memo 10/182, Brussels, 12 May 2010, http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/documents_en.htm

³⁸ European Commission, *Country Report Moldova 2010*, Brussels, 25 May 2011, http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/pdf/progress2011/sec_11_643_en.pdf,

³⁹ *Ibidem*.

⁴⁰ *Ibidem*.

⁴¹ European Commission, *ENP Country Progress Report 2009 –Rep of Moldova*, Memo 10/182, Brussels, 12 May 2010, http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/documents_en.htm

future Ukraine-Romania border traffic Agreement. However, in order to be fruitful, this Agreement must be followed by a development of the infrastructure (bridges over the Prut river, good roads along the Prut).

The procedure of "repatriation" in which almost 1 million citizens of the Republic of Moldova have got Romanian citizenship, in the last 20 years, also contributed to a better free movement of persons. According to "jus sanguinis" implemented in the Romanian law, the grandchildren of the Romanian citizens abroad (in the Republic of Moldova, Ukraine, the Western countries), have the right to be Romanian citizens. These almost 1 million persons with Moldovan and Romanian citizenship are European citizens, work in the EU, come into contact with the European values and with the European system, and will contribute to a deep European process in the Republic of Moldova (a country with almost 4 million inhabitants)⁴².

Some anti-immigration articles in the international press criticised the double citizenship policy of Romania. However, the press is free to express any opinion. The legislation on citizenship is a competence of each state. Several Western states of EU (such as Germany, France, the UK, Belgium) have granted their citizenship to millions of persons from Africa, Asia, and America, for several decades. These EU countries accepted also millions of legal and illegal immigrants from Africa, Asia, and America. The Spanish law gives the Spanish citizenship to persons from Ibero-American states or from the Filipinas, after only 2 years of residence in Spain. Comparatively, for a person from any other country it is necessary to have 10 years residence in Spain to obtain the Spanish citizenship and that person must abandon the citizenship of its country of origin. So, the historical, political and cultural traditions are important for several countries in EU, not only in Moldova-Romania Relations.

Moldova, ENP and a future "potential candidate" status

Lady Ashton and The European Commission mentioned important EU objectives for Moldova on 25th May 2011, in the "Joint Communication to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions". The document promises EU support for the „encouraging progress" made by Moldova in its reform efforts, by Ukraine in the negotiations for the Association Agreement, by Morocco and Jordan in their announcement of constitutional reform⁴³. The "more for more" approach and EU cooperation not only with the neighbourhood governments, but also with the neighbourhood societies are crucial in this Communication.

As the president of the European Parliament, Jerzy Buzek, declared on 25th September 2011, "The European Parliament stands by the efforts of the Moldovan citizens. Today, we specifically underlined Moldova's EU perspectives. The perspective offered to Moldova by the Council, the Commission and the EEAS would encourage the country to pursue reforms. I strongly welcome the "more for more" approach. Greater political and financial support should be available for neighbourhood countries which undertake

⁴² Dan Dungaciu, *Basarabia e Romania?*, Bucuresti, Ed. Cartier, 2011, p 140.

⁴³ EC and High Representative, Joint Communication.... "A new response to a changing Neighbourhood", Brussels, 25 May 2011, in http://ec.europa.eu/world/enp/pdf/com_11_303_en.pdf

reforms with vigour and determination. Moldova has shown its strong commitment to reform in the last two years⁴⁴.

EU has included Moldova in ENP and EAP, while the Western Balkans states are included in the "Stabilization and Association Process" and enjoys the status of "candidate countries" (Croatia, Macedonia, Montenegro), or the status of "potential candidate countries" (Serbia, Albania, Bosnia, Kosovo). Bosnia and Kosovo have similar or even more serious problems comparing to Moldova: state-building, weak administrative capacity, poverty and weak economy, corruption, organised crime, inter-ethnic and inter-confessional conflicts. More than that, Kosovo is not even recognised as a state, by some EU states (Spain, Greece, Cyprus, Slovakia, and Romania) and by some Great Powers like Russia and China. However, Kosovo and Bosnia enjoy a superior status in relation to EU, they have the status of candidate countries, because this is the political will of EU, not because they are better prepared for this status. Moldova does not have this status; it is only part of the ENP, because this is the political will of EU.

There is no political will in EU for a better status for Moldova, even the French President (Nicolas Sarkozy) and the Romanian president (Traian Băsescu) made some statements in 2008, asserting the need to include the Republic of Moldova in the Stabilisation and Association Process, alongside the 'potential candidate countries' of the Western Balkans. Several MEPs supported this idea⁴⁵.

In fact, the Republic of Moldova is a European state situated on the border of the EU (like the countries of the Western Balkans) and it is a country with European aspirations and problems comparable with those of the 'potential candidate countries' of the Western Balkans (e.g. Albania, Bosnia and Kosovo, etc.). The Republic of Moldova has a population size comparable to that of the countries of the Western Balkans and belongs geographically, historically and culturally to South-East Europe and to Central-Eastern Europe, and the majority of its inhabitants are Moldovan Romanians. 70% of the Moldovan population supports accession to the EU (according to opinion polls). The Alliance for the European Integration, which won the parliamentary and local elections in 2009-2011, supports the pro-European Government that implements pro-European policies. EU would be able to integrate Moldova without major difficulties (after, of course, the Republic has fulfilled the accession criteria)⁴⁶.

Even though there is no political support for having the Republic of Moldova included in the Stabilisation and Association Process as a 'potential candidate country' for the accession to EU, we consider that the status of

⁴⁴ "Buzek on Moldova's Association Agreement", Strasbourg, 25 September 2011.

http://www.europarl.europa.eu/president/en/press/press_release/2011/2011September/press_release-2011-September-14.html

⁴⁵ *Motion for a Resolution*, PE 420.342, B6-0102/2009, Brussels, 12 February 2009, pursuant to Rule 113 of the Rules of Procedure, by Călin Cătălin Chiriță, on clear European prospects for the Republic of Moldova, in

<http://www.europarl.europa.eu/sidesSearch/search.do?type=MOTION&language=EN&term=6&author=95018>

⁴⁶ CC Chirita, *op cit.*, passim.

'potential candidate country' can be granted in the framework of the Eastern Partnership, according to the article 49 of the EU Treaty. This should be a concrete result of the positive differentiation of Moldova in the framework of the Eastern Partnership.

Some Resolutions and Reports proposed in the European Parliament in 2011 emphasised the article 49 of the EU Treaty, that allows to any European country (as Moldova) to become candidate to EU Membership.

"We understand how difficult and unpopular it can be [in some European capitals], but...why shouldn't Moldova have a European perspective if Bosnia and Albania have?" This is the question often raised by the pro-European Minister of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Moldova, Iurie Leanca. His strategy is a subtle one: diligence can shame Brussels into going further than it might otherwise want to. As „The European voice” remarks, „There is much frustration over the Eastern Partnership process in Moldova, with many asking why Moldova, a country with clear European aspirations, must be lumped in with the likes of Azerbaijan or Belarus.”⁴⁷

However, in our opinion, the Republic of Moldova will remain in the Eastern Partnership, it should make progresses and it should use the article 49 of the EU Treaty to become a candidate country. The EU and its Member states should encourage this evolution. A special support is necessary for the economic, social and “human development” in the Republic of Moldova.

⁴⁷ Thomas Escritt, *Moldovan optimist*, 29.09.2011, in
<http://www.europeanvoice.com/article/imported/moldovan-optimist/72131.aspx>
<http://www.europarl.europa.eu/sides/getDoc.do?type=REPORT&reference=A7-2011-0289&language=EN&mode=XML>

IL RISORGIMENTO IN ITALIA E IN EUROPA

Antonello Biagini*

Magnifico Rettore,
chiarissimi presidi e professori,
autorità,
signore e signori,
studenti,

la laurea *honoris causa* che l'Università "Petru Maior" di Tirgu Mureş mi ha attribuito è per me un grande onore che forse va al di là dei miei meriti e vorrei dedicarla a mia moglie, la professoressa Giovanna Motta, coordinatrice del dottorato in Storia d'Europa alla Sapienza Università di Roma, con la quale ho condiviso vita privata, impegno accademico e interessi scientifici. Mi auguro altresì che tale riconoscimento serva di stimolo per i tanti giovani studiosi presenti in questa sala, romeni e italiani, nella consapevolezza del dovere civile che ogni storico deve avere per avvicinarsi, con le sue ricerche, alla ricostruzione degli eventi anche per spiegare i fenomeni, i cambiamenti, le contraddizioni del passato che si riflettono sul presente: solo la dimensione storica ci consente di vivere il presente e immaginare il futuro. Dunque più che una *lectio magistralis* vorrei condividere con questo uditorio, con questa comunità accademica, alcune riflessioni che potranno poi essere oggetto di ulteriori approfondimenti negli incontri che ci ripromettiamo di fare nel vostro Ateneo, che questa mattina ha voluto inaugurare una sezione dell'Istituto di Studi Italo-Romeno fondato insieme ai colleghi dell'Università "Babeş-Bolyai" di Cluj-Napoca nel 2002. Condividere studi, ricerche, riflessioni, favorire gli scambi di giovani studiosi, sono questi gli obiettivi che ci hanno spinto a costruire, pur tra mille difficoltà e poche risorse economiche, una comunità di ricerca che ha già prodotto molti frutti e molti altri ne produrrà, a dimostrazione di come la volontà positiva e disinteressata degli studiosi di una generazione possa incidere sulle scelte e sul futuro di un'altra che si affaccia all'impegno professionale (tendenza oggi forse non molto diffusa nel panorama accademico) indicando uno stile di vita e di ricerca. Non mi dilungherò sulla lunga storia comune dei nostri popoli, sulle luci e sulle ombre che hanno caratterizzato i nostri rapporti internazionali (tutto ciò è contenuto nel mio volume *Storia della Romania contemporanea*, Bompiani RCS, 2004, molto bene accolto dai lettori specialisti e non, che è già alla terza edizione); voglio però ricordare che adesso i nostri due popoli vivono, finalmente, nella comune casa europea e devono sopportare il peso di ritardi e pregiudizi di cui solo parzialmente sono responsabili. Se possiamo affermare che i meccanismi economici che sono alla base del sistema europeo abbiano sostanzialmente funzionato, dobbiamo altresì constatare il drammatico ritardo dell'unificazione politica. Tutto ciò, complice una crisi economica mondiale, induce il riproporsi di fenomeni conflittuali e di forme di intolleranza che abbiamo il dovere morale e civile di combattere.

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Ecco dunque l'esigenza di "comprendere" la realtà di oggi, le cui origini profonde stanno nel divenire della storia. Per tale ragione ritengo che si debba tornare a riflettere sul secolo XIX, sul risveglio e sulla presa di coscienza dei popoli, quando le *élites* nazionali iniziarono la lunga lotta per disarticolare il "sistema" degli Imperi plurinazionali - risorto con il progetto reazionario elaborato al Congresso di Vienna del 1815 - chiedendo l'autodeterminazione e la libertà e utilizzando il grande patrimonio ideale della Rivoluzione francese. Quelle idee si sono estese in Europa, pure in maniera difforme, promuovendo lo sviluppo di movimenti politici liberal-democratici che hanno lottato per la realizzazione dello Stato nazionale come rappresentazione concreta dell'idea di nazione. La libertà dei popoli prefigura le più ampie libertà di una rappresentanza politica liberamente scelta attraverso l'identificazione di una cultura, di una lingua, di comuni tradizioni e di un territorio specifico. Un patrimonio di idee e di ideali che si era formato lentamente già nel corso dell'età moderna, con la progressiva separazione tra l'ambito religioso e la sfera civile e dunque giungendo alla formazione dello Stato accentrato e laico e alla divisione dei poteri. Sulla scia del lungo cammino della storia grandi pensatori come l'italiano Giuseppe Mazzini e il romeno Nicolae Bălcescu, immaginando un percorso sia pure diverso da quello che poi si sarebbe realizzato, affermarono che non esiste la libertà di un popolo, di una nazione, se non si rispetta e non si tutela quella degli altri popoli e delle altre nazioni. Sulla base di questa concezione, giovani di tutta Europa si mossero per andare a combattere per la libertà altrui, come ha mostrato l'ampia messe di studi sull'epopea garibaldina. La storiografia, pure di vario segno, che nel tempo si è occupata dell'interpretazione del Risorgimento, ha posto in luce come esso abbia creato indubbiamente un senso di appartenenza nazionale e popolare vivo fino a oggi, ma ha evidenziato pure come le classi dirigenti politiche postunitarie non abbiano saputo utilizzare quel sentimento come elemento fondante di un'identità nazionale. Oggi il dibattito sul Risorgimento riemerge come un fiume carsico dalle pieghe della storia e apre nuove riflessioni sul *come* e sul *perché* quel processo avviato centocinquanta anni fa sia rimasto incompiuto e incapace di resistere ai problemi della politica e alle crisi dell'economia.

Nella nostra analisi, però, ci sono tutti gli elementi per affermare che il Risorgimento è il primo movimento ad avere successo nell'Italia divisa in tanti piccoli Stati, spesso emanazione o sotto "protettorato" di potenze esterne. In questo senso il movimento unitario è stato un rilevante e indiscutibile movimento rivoluzionario che ha contribuito in maniera determinata a mettere in crisi l'intero assetto europeo che il Congresso di Vienna del 1815 aveva ricostruito - dopo la sconfitta di Napoleone - per bloccare i processi di trasformazione che le borghesie nazionali e protonazionali stavano perseguendo con l'obiettivo di mettere fine all'Antico Regime, basato sulla società di "ordini" (nobiltà, clero, "terzo stato"). La carboneria e la massoneria, prima nei moti del 1820-1821, poi nei moti del 1830, rivendicano nuovi spazi di libertà politica, sociale, economica, istituzionale. È la "religione della libertà" - per citare Benedetto Croce - che prende sempre di più il posto delle religioni tradizionali, *in primis* il cattolicesimo, fortemente legato ai poteri costituiti nel binomio trono-altare, che era stato il fondamento della Restaurazione.

Nell'intera Europa esplodono così manifestazioni e ribellioni, moti e rivolte finalizzate al riconoscimento da parte dei sovrani della concessione di "Statuti", un complesso di norme giuridiche costituzionali finalizzate a vincolare e garantire il rapporto tra sovrano e sudditi. Con il 1848 dunque si passa dalla "pace" della Santa Alleanza alla "rivoluzione europea" dei popoli, di ampio respiro continentale, sostenuta dai movimenti patriottici e nazionali di ispirazione liberale e democratica, ancora una volta irradiata da Parigi. Emergono anche modelli di rivoluzione "legalitaria": l'Assemblea di Francoforte in Germania, la rivoluzione "costituzionale" condotta nel regno d'Ungheria, la Repubblica Romana. Svanita la soluzione rivoluzionaria, rimanevano in campo gli esiti "moderati" per le grandi questioni nazionali o di "compromesso" con il potere in cambio di un'autonomia quasi assoluta, (l'Impero d'Austria diventa nel 1867 Impero austro-ungarico), o dell'unificazione intorno a nuclei statali (il regno di Prussia e il regno di Sardegna) più moderni e avanzati, capaci di mobilitare a favore della propria espansione un movimento di consenso popolare, nazionale e internazionale. Quest'ultimo modello, malgrado si realizzi in maniera diversa in Germania, dove si attua l'unificazione alla Prussia con il mantenimento delle altre istituzioni e autonomie locali, e in Italia - dove invece si arriva all'annessione *tout court* al regno sabauda - diventa comunque il modello ideale per le giovani nazioni emergenti dei Balcani (come il Montenegro e la Serbia che aspirano a divenire centri per l'aggregazione dei popoli slavi meridionali, o la Romania del "Vecchio Regno", che diventerà Grande Romania alla fine della prima guerra mondiale con l'annessione della Transilvania e del Banato sotto dominio ungherese, nonché della Bucovina austriaca, della Bessarabia russa).

Per tutti questi elementi e per molte altre ragioni politiche e culturali il Risorgimento rimane un grande movimento libertario e liberale, un importante esempio per altre regioni d'Europa in cui gli attori nazionali del complesso panorama internazionale sembrano capaci di far valere i propri processi di "risorgimento" nazionale e di proporsi, sull'esempio del Risorgimento italiano, dalla seconda metà del XIX secolo fino alla prima guerra mondiale, come i principali fattori di disgregazione dei grandi Imperi plurinazionali. Pur tuttavia è anche vero che il modello dello Stato-nazione che si impone drammaticamente nella storia specifica dell'Europa centrale e orientale (e che si connette fortemente ai fenomeni di nazionalismo, industrializzazione, urbanizzazione delle società continentali) è il nuovo laboratorio della "nazionalizzazione delle masse", che nelle società delle "piccole nazioni" est-europee ispira la costituzione di regimi autoritari su ispirazione del fascismo italiano.

Dobbiamo dunque riflettere ancora una volta su temi che sembravano trascurati e che l'anniversario dell'Unità ci ripropone per dare il nostro contributo sia come intellettuali che come cittadini, affinché oggi in tema di Unione Europea il processo di unificazione possa non essere più solo economica ma soprattutto politica per cominciare a dare i suoi frutti. Ciò che negli anni abbiamo fatto come docenti costruendo una casa comune per i nostri allievi e giovani studiosi di diversa estrazione disciplinare, italiani e romeni, va proprio in questa direzione, e credo che i primi, incoraggianti risultati, siano sotto gli occhi di tutti, speriamo che possano sempre meglio far crescere il loro futuro che sarà per noi motivo di soddisfazione e di orgoglio.

Nel rinnovare i ringraziamenti per l'alto onore che questa Università ha voluto farmi attribuendomi una laurea prestigiosa nell'anniversario dei suoi 50 anni di vita, assumo qui l'impegno a continuare sulla strada intrapresa.

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Alexandru-Florin Platon, Laurențiu Rădvan, Bogdan-Petru Maleon, **O istorie a Europei de Apus în Evul Mediu. De la Imperiul Roman târziu la marile descoperiri geografice**, Iași, Editura Polirom, 2010, 552 p.

The present book, written by the two scholars from Iasi overcomes one of the Romanian historiography's deficiencies: that is a compendium of European Medieval history. Such a book has indeed been absolutely necessary as a teaching support both for students and teachers. Our historiography needed such a thematic work as the „latest” book on this topic had been written three decades ago, in 1980 under the supervision of Professor Radu Manolescu (coord.), *Istorie medie universală*, București, Editura Didactică si Pedagogică, 1980.

Thus the book must be considered as an extremely valuable support for studying the Medieval history. Its importance in the Romanian historiographical field is doubled: first due to the fact that it overcomes the deficiency we had spoken about and secondly, due to the documentary sources but mostly to the historiographical ones used by the authors. They made possible for the Romanian readers to familiarize with the latest European studies on Medieval history, otherwise inaccessible for us. Despite that the book has mainly edited sources we are facing an original approach as the bibliographical and documentary resources are critically analyzed. Moreover the present book already has a documentary supplement edited by the same authors, Alexandru-Florin Platon, Laurentiu Radvan (eds), *De la Cetatea lui Dumnezeu la Editctul de la Nantes. Izvoare de istorie medievala (secolele V-XVI)*, Iasi, Editura Polirom, 2005, which comes as a compulsory instrument for the book's understanding.

The book consists of a critical analysis of the major events and phenomena of the Western Medieval Europe having as a starting point the transitory period of the III-VIII centuries up to the beginnings of the Modern Europe in the XVI century. There are indeed certain thematic and analytical limitations but they are legitimate as it is extremely difficult to write such an exhaustive approach on the Western European Medieval history with the documentary resources accessible from Romania. Thus (once more) the author's efforts are both very useful and valuable. Moreover, the book is the result of the author's professional experience both as historians and professors.

At a structural level, the book is organized from a chronological and thematic point of view. The first chapter analyses the transitory period from late Antiquity (the III century) to the beginnings of the Medieval Age (VIII). The authors insisted upon the period of the great invasions and also upon the barbarian kingdoms emphasizing the barbarians' heritage and their contribution to the Europe's foundations. The second chapter is a deep analysis of the first Medieval period (VIII-IX centuries). The entire chapters deals with the Carolingian Empire, considered as being the first

political unification of the Western Europe. Main attention was paid to the foreign policy of Charlemagne. The coronation moment, with its historical controversies, and the impact of the event upon the West and Byzantine Empire relations is also a subject discussed in the chapter. The authors deeply analyzed the elements which determined the success of the France royalty but also the real frontiers of the Carolingian Empire. The Carolingian Renaissance is also a subject of the chapter. One of the major ideas linked to this cultural phenomenon is the idea of continuity, several cultural transformations of the period being the result of the past transformation.

The third chapter, the most extended one, reveals in fact the basic features of what we know as being the Medieval Age. It is a deep analysis from an economical, social, religious and political perspective of the Western Europe between XI-XIII centuries. The authors started their analysis with the economical perspective considering that the economical expansion of the period is the most important aspect of the general development of the Western Medieval society that characterizes the period. One of the major ideas the authors insist upon is that this economical development was heterogeneous, different from one region to another. The chapter ends with a comparative analysis of the process which led to the formation of the centralized states of the Western Europe, that is France and England but also the Spanish Reconquista.

The fourth chapter deals with the relations between the Western and Eastern Europe, between the Catholic and Orthodox worlds. It makes reference mainly to the political and religious relations among the Byzantine Empire and the Western Europe thus events like the crusades are critically discussed.

The last chapter deals with the major phenomena that led to the transformation of Europe from a Medieval world to the Modern one. The first major issue the authors analyzed is the crisis of the Medieval Papality and the emergence of the movements claiming the Church's reformation - the so - called "The Pre-Reform Age". In the chapter's economy much space is given for profiling the main political entities of the Western Europe in the XVI century.

The conclusions are extremely valuable as they are in fact a comparative analysis between the modernity of the Western and Eastern Europe in an effort of understanding the differences and the gaps between the two parts of Europe. We must stress the fact that the book's conclusions could be a subject of an independent book as the subject in analysis is very complex. The authors' intention was that of clarifying the paradigm of the Western's supremacy over the East. They tried to identify the historical structural factors that could explain this primacy. And the final idea the authors insisted upon is that there are no historical reasons for denying the Eastern Europeanness' as West and East belong to the same cultural area.

Georgeta Fodor

Ioan-Aurel Pop, Sorin Şipoş, **Silviu Dragomir și dosarul Diplomei cavalerilor ioaniți**, Academia Română - Centrul de studii transilvane, Cluj-Napoca, 2009, 209 p.

For those still sceptical regarding the destiny of contemporary Romanian historiography, the publication of this volume is able to drive away the veil of distrust and the belief that there are still many design issues able to enrich the knowledge of history. With a dual load, meaning that is claimed both by the history of historiography and the medieval history, the volume is evidence of happy meeting between the two historians. More precisely a re-appointment, into the same interest for who was Silviu Dragomir, for the young historian Sorin Şipoş completed in 2001 a doctoral thesis entitled *Silviu Dragomir-historian*, led by professor Ioan-Aurel Pop.

If the monograph dedicated to the illustrious representative of the Transylvanian historiography, Silviu Dragomir was highly appreciated in scientific circles, has enjoyed so far by two editions in 2002 and 2009, and was rewarded with an Academy Award, not less true that the long effort to achieve this monograph has reserved the author many unknowns, which, with great perseverance, he tried to clear up afterwards. This explains the genesis of this book, which lies between which pages lies not only the odyssey of an unique manuscript of Silviu Dragomir, and especially the obstacles over which the two historians were forced to go, for years, until, finally, managed to consult and then be able to edit the manuscript of Dragomir about the Diploma of the Knights of St. John.

Committed himself to publish the “first systematic study on Silviu Dragomir’s research, so controversial, regarding the Diploma of the Knights of St. John, in the broader approach of life and work of the great historian” (p. 8), and Ioan-Aurel Pop and Sorin Şipoş propose a complex investigation, starting at the place of Professor Dragomir in the picture of Romanian historiography, only to reach in the end, in the documentary annex, at the transcription of the manuscript which bears the signature of the historian from Arad. So the authors have chosen two concentric analyses with millimetre precision, reserving the role of corollary documentary heritage, in this case of the refund.

The first chapter, *Silviu Dragomir-historiographical landmarks*, it is recommended as a synthetic presentation of how personality and work of the Transylvanian historian came to the attention of analysts, whether the purpose of editing and re-publishing its work or that of elucidating the biographical details, such as band related to intellectual, academic career, the years of imprisonment or Security reports on him.

Engaged in the monographic reconstruction of Silviu Dragomir, Sorin Şipoş managed to draw in the second chapter a biographical sketch, which turned to a voluminous documentary material, edited and unpublished sources, such as those from the archives of Deva, Sibiu, Bucharest or those kept in the personal collection of Enescu’s family, testamentary legatees of the historian. So, we discover lesser-known

aspects, as historian's face has been for long the shield of his work, especially on the details of the Caransebeş years imprisonment and Sighet times which reveal an existential Calvary, after the 1955 release. Exciting, these biographical reconstructions demonstrate the historian's efforts to remain in the scientific life agora, despite a modest living, which is consumed in an unpretentious place, but what was so familiar in the history of Cluj Institute building on the Napoca Street.

A very demanding connoisseur of Romanian medieval age, Academician Ioan-Aurel Pop, joined his professional pen at the younger colleague from Oradea, to describe in the third chapter, Silviu Dragomir's portrait as a historian of the Middle Ages. Ordered in three creative steps, the contribution of Silviu Dragomir to the development of Romanian medieval research, developed over more than four decades, breathing the spirit of critical school, geared both to refund documentation and for completion of lesser-known chapters of the Romanian Middle Ages. The authors reported Dragomir's constantly writing to the other contributions of that time, which were converging to the same thematic universe, such as those signed by Ioan Bogdan, Nicolae Iorga, Ioan Lupuş, Dimitrie Onciul.

Ioan-Aurel Pop and Sorin Şipoş carefully examined Silviu Dragomir's favourite themes that he has cultivated, and relations between Romanian and Saxons in medieval Transylvania, north-Balkan Romanity, Romanian lords status, etc., as they sought to analyze the historian concept and methodology, to explain his commitment to the positivist historiography through the formative environment, learnt in Austrian Chernivtsi and Vienna universities, in a time when the trend was still practiced with enthusiasm.

Fourth chapter, *St. John's Knights' Diploma (1247) and its historical implications*, it is recommended as a real investigation file, which, from Romanian historiographical history as found in works of Şerban Papacostea, Victor Spinei, Viorel Achim, Maria Holban, Tudor Sălăgean, Serban Turcuş, the two authors have analyzed the genesis of this document, and its distinct significance, both in terms of the Kingdom of Hungary, and in terms of papacy's policy in the thirteenth century. Characterized as "a historical document for understanding the fundamental realities of the Carpathians and the Lower Danube in the mid thirteenth century" (p.99), *St. John's Knights' Diploma* is actually a vital part not only when it comes to know pre-state political parties, but also when we think of Romanian space as one in which they have extended lines of force of the Hungarian crown and Catholicism which took control through its most powerful military-monks order at that time, Joannites.

Certainly the most surprising is the fifth chapter, entitled *A novel study on the St. John's Knights' Diploma (1247) and its fate*, in which the authors summarized an episode that seems plucked from ideological inventory rather of another historical era, in which censorship stroke on historians labour. It is somehow the strange story of the search of

Dragomir's manuscript, which lasted nearly a decade, since 1998 when Sorin Şipoş, then a doctoral student at the University of Cluj, has tried to identify it, first in archives and libraries in Cluj, Deva and Sibiu, until he found it at the Romanian Academy Library in Bucharest. But it passed years, until 2007, when he managed to go beyond what the administration of the prestigious institutions called "non-consultation clause" and finally got to read and photocopy Dragomir's manuscript. Odyssey through the historian from Oradea has gone through has all data for a psychological novel, for what could be more frustrating and inexplicable to a researcher, working in a democracy than to come up against barriers unexplained whispers and reserves without logic of a staff from specialized institution that houses a rich documentary treasure? Only replacement of Gabriel Ştrempel with Dan Horia Mazilu to rule the Romanian Academy Library finally brought a happy settlement of the approaches of the two researchers.

Finally, the last chapter, *Critics of the study issued by Silviu Dragomir on the St. John's Knights' Diploma*, based on the need to elucidate the reasons which led to the genesis of the concerns of positivist historian for this document from the diplomatic inventory of the thirteenth century. Ioan-Aurel Pop and Sorin Şipoş have linked this interest with the work carried out by Dragomir in order to question the authenticity for Transylvanian Romanians acts of religious union with the Church of Rome, because in this context he found a copy of the Diploma from 1247, in the archive of Gabriel Hevenesi. Subsequently, the historian reasoning was that the Jesuits would have been prepared an apocryphal text, and from here came quickly to put into question the authenticity of the text of the diploma which came to us. Whilst the authors recover the trajectory of Dragomir's syllogism, give him extenuating circumstances, judging him in line with the then state of historical knowledge.

From investigations of the two historians finally resulted a book written with very much professionalism, helpful not only for historians, who have the chance for an imaginary travel through the old historiography setting, have the chance of meeting an exemplary personality of Transylvanian historical writing, but also for those who are enthusiastic of the metamorphoses of our Transylvanian identity, for how can today someone can write history, without extravagance and with a tone that does not abandon the academic spirit.

Corina Teodor

Philippe Poirrier, *Introduction à l'historiographie*, Paris, Éditions Belin, 2009, 192 p.

It often happens to see that French historians express in a clear and concise language, a complex issue, able to rank and prioritize in summary manner, the knowledge we have in one area or another. It is also

the case of this summary, written by Philippe Poirrier, professor at the University of Bourgogne, which is addressed primarily to students and to all those interested to know the evolution of this historical discipline, the history of historiography, and the history of histories (*histoire des histoires*). A summary which balances titles in favour of more contemporary fate of this discipline, because the work is composed of two parts: the first one (*Savoirs*), dedicated to the chronological development of historiography, and a second one (*Savoir faire*) investigating new cases of success in the practice of history writing of the twentieth century, resulted from the methodological interferences of history with other sciences.

The historian begins the incursion in the evolution of historiography as science, totally ignoring the ancient times and giving the middle age only a transitional role. This option is justified by the fact that the historiography wasn't a genuine discipline, in these two periods, with its own rules and methodology, as it was demonstrated in recent years, convincingly, by one of the great theorists of historical science, Reinhart Koselleck. Therefore, the destiny of historical writing in the Middle Ages was only sketched, given that the history was then only a minor genre, an auxiliary science of morality, theology and law. Even the job of historian, as understood today, didn't exist.

In the Renaissance, by the examples that Philippe Poirrier offers, it is being outlined a growing interest in historical knowledge, Guillaume Budé, Jean Bodin, Lancelot du Voisin de La Popelinière, Paul Émile being some of those who put history in the service of princes, assuming the task of glorifying the past and the present.

The seventeenth century brought a major change in terms of historical discourse dissemination to the public. An observation in concordance with the way we look at today's historiography, not only as a quantification of historical production of an era, as a lexicon of the most important historians, but also in terms of reception of these works.

To analyze the evolution of historiography in the Enlightenment, Philippe Poirrier started from the observation of Chantal Grell in 1993, which had placed history under the sign of philosophy and scholarship. It is the time when the history books, from dictionaries to monographs, are well represented in the libraries of Parisian and provincial nobility, and periodicals also reserve great length for historical subjects. Of great public success, prove to be also the almanacs, which disseminate scholarly simplified versions of history.

The second chapter, *L'histoire comme discipline*, is inaugurated by analyzing the romantic generation, because in this "century of history" not only that history is professionalized, but becomes a subject of great interest to all engaged in the public life, whether they are in a monarchical or a republican group. The author seeks to identify in particular, the role assumed by the two great historians Jules Michelet, who made the French people the main actor of his historical syntheses, and François Guizot, liberal historian who sought to give political and intellectual legitimacy to

the bourgeois world, on which the regime was based on. The birth of Gabriel Monod's historical magazine in 1876 is a cornerstone of the second half of the XIX century by the reunion in the same framework, of the methodological background of French tradition and the scholarly literature. Gabriel Monod is not only the artisan of critical historiography, but also the one who, from Republican positions, established sustainable connections between history, the critical method, the image of the republic and the one of the nation. His initiatives were taken by Ernest Lavissee, "the national schoolmaster"; as Pierre Nora had called him (p. 41), who has kept the same innovative clothes of history for the didactic speech, also, teaching manuals which he has drawn, being equally civic textbooks, which put history in the generous framework of educational and cultural revolution in the 1880-1900.

The third chapter, *Les territoires de l'histoire*, dwell on present events, programmatically and methodologically, in the historiography of the '70-'80. Based on the economic and historical separation, then on the gradual fading of their domination and the unexpected revival of political history, Philippe Poirrier found that all historical periods, gradually pass through these metamorphoses, even if they are early, when it comes to medieval or modern history.

Biographies written with the methodology of the history of mentalities, as *Saint Louis*, that of Jacques Le Goff's (1996) or the of the histories of ideas, which reveals the impact of intellectual history on several generations, as François Furet ventured to show in his book *Penser la Révolution française* (1978), is recommended as indisputable successes, in an attempt to renew historiography.

The fourth chapter, *Les enjeux actuels de l'histoire*, based on media role in projecting some lights over the historiography, in presenting the most important public successes in a high-point which joins the literary production to the scientific historiographical one. A change in the reader's attitude can be observed starting from the '80, when not only they read less, but it is established a different relationship with specialized books, a fragmentary one, mediated by modern means of reproduction of texts, use of photocopies even in teaching. It is the moment when, more acutely than in the past, specialized magazines start being appreciated and are the subject of intellectual debates.

The author, passionate about cultural history, as demonstrated by papers published on this subject, has saved the second part of the book for major issues of contemporary historical research: integration in French historical writing of some successful foreign models, such as *British Cultural Studies* and *Micro-history*, which was added to the research by Italian historians, socio-historical assertion, balance of power between women's history and *Gender Studies*, relying on new information technologies, especially for subjects that require quantification and ranking, but also the documentation via the Internet, an increasingly common practice today.

Introduction in the historiography proves to be more than just a summary of the historiography, meaning that the author has crossed a complex route, passing from the territory of the history of historical writing to the methodology of contemporary historiography. Philippe Poirrier's book is a suggestive pattern, always followed by those who design such instruments for the use students, that doesn't lack of practical exercises. Each chapter of the first part, ends with a documentary record, which includes a representative text of that historiographical era, such as Gabriel Monod's manifesto or the program of the Annales school, followed by a very rigorous analysis of text, from which don't lack the interrogations, always challenging for those passionate about historiography, from other cultural areas.

Corina Teodor

Maria Berényi, ***Tales of Houses Romanians in Buda and Pest***, Budapest, 2011, 95 p.

The Romanian historian from Budapest is well known for her research upon the Romanians from Hungary. Studies like *Aspecte național-culturale din istoricul românilor din Ungaria (1785-1918)*, "Dunărea", Budapesta, Tankönyvkiadó, 1990, *Românii din Ungaria de azi în presa română din Transilvania și Ungaria secolului al XIX-lea (1821-1918). Documente*, Giula, Editura "NOI", 1994, *Istoria Fundației Gojdu (1870-1952) / A Gozsdu Alapítvány története (1870-1952)*, Budapesta-Budapest, Comp-Press Kft., 1995, *Cultură românească la Budapesta în secolul al XIX-lea*, Giula, 2000, *Viața și activitatea lui Emanuil Gojdu (1802-1870)*, Giula, 2002, prove her to be indeed an authority on the history of the Romanians from Hungary. In consequence, the present reviewed book must be considered as an outcome of her experience on this subject. It is in fact the indisputable evidence that history of a town can be written through its people and buildings as well as people's history could be written through the material testimonies. The author's intention was that of revealing the actual but also the cultural presence of the Romanians from Budapest using as the main historical tool the buildings once owned by some of the most prominent figures of the Romanians from Buda and Pest. Thus, the book should not be necessary considered only as a historical book. Its cultural dimension and importance must also be stressed. The book can indeed be taken as a guided tour for those interested in discovering the Romanian's presence in Budapest during the XVIII and the XIX centuries. The time period chosen, is of great relevance too. It represented in fact the time when the Macedo-Romanians and Romanians' presence in the cultural, artistic and ecclesiastical life of the city was very intense.

Each topic the author approaches is well represented through images. As indeed the image is a powerful historical tool. And this book has

magnificent photos of the buildings - not only - owned by the Macedo-Romanians and Romanians such as the Buildings from the East Side of Vörösmarty Square (No. 2 was owned by Mocioni family; No. 3 was owned by Gheorghe Sina; the Lica Palace etc.)

From a methodological point of view the author combines the historical with a geographical approach. She analyzes the history of the peoples and buildings all the same taking into consideration their location. First we have the buildings from Roosevelt Square, the splendid row of palaces from Kirkodó Square where a Macedo-Romanian family owned for almost forty years the palace, which is the Naco family. This family, as the author underlines, was one of the most influential families from Pest and Vienna. The second historical objective she analyzed is the Petöfi Square where Greeks and Macedo-Romanians built their Greek church. She also insisted upon the Nyáry Pál Street which is also of great relevance for the Romanian history as there was located the Editorial of "Familia" magazine, one of the most representatives journals Romanians had during the XIX century. Another important cultural location was on Veres Pálné Street where the Petru Maior Society and the "Luceafarul" literary magazine had their headquarters.

Also, a great extent of the book is rightly given to Emanuel Gojdu presence in Pest. Both, because the author had already researched the subject and he represents indeed the great Maecenas of the Romanians from Hungary. Overall, Maria Berényi's tales of the houses is indeed the story of the Romanian presence in Buda and Pest written with historical tools she masters so well. We must appreciate her effort in discovering and publishing the past history of the Romanian abroad.

Georgeta Fodor

Keith Hitchins, **Ion I.C. Brătianu. Romania**, London, Haus Publishing Ltd., 2011, 219 p.

Part of a series, *Makers of the Modern World. The peace conferences of 1919-23 and their aftermath*, Keith Hitchins' recent book analyses one of the most important Romanian personalities whose actions were decisive for the formation and affirmation of Romania as a national, modern state. Nevertheless, the book is once more a valuable proof of the author's deep knowledge and interest in the Romanian's history. Although the facts he analyses within the book's pages are not new we must stress the author's originality in constructing its discourse. We have in front of us a short history of Romania from the last decades of the XIX century up to the end of the interwar period viewed through one of the most prominent personalities of the Romanian political life that is Ionel Brătianu. The reasoning of such an historical approach resides mainly in that key role

that Brătianu had in structuring the Romanian's foreign and domestic affairs.

Three are the main aspects the author stressed upon. The first part of the book deals with a deep analysis of the key elements in Brătianu's intellectual and political formation: that is the family, the countryside and the land. Indeed Brătianu was well trained by his father, whose role in the emergence of the Romanian state was defining (Keith Hitchins noted indeed that much of the contours of modern Romania was due to Ionel Brătianu's father's congenial working relationship with Carol). Moreover, due to his father also, Ionel Brătianu spent his childhood and adolescence in that atmosphere of liberal challenges to tradition of dynamic nation building, and of political rivalries and gamesmanship. So the first part of the book represents an insight in the Brătianu family. It is to note the author's methods in revealing Ionel Brătianu's cultural background. Rather on insisting strictly upon the *cursus honorum*, Keith Hitchins placed Ionel Brătianu's formation on an historical background. But the first chapter, which is the most extended part in the book's economy, does not deal only with biographical references on Ionel Brătianu as much extent is given to his political activity. The author well revealed the politician that Ionel Brătianu had become and also the goals he intended to achieve in this quality: that was to bring Romania fully into the modern world at a European level of civilization and economic prosperity (p. 23). He was the exponent of an activist policy mainly in the decades before and after the First World War and Keith Hitchins deeply analyzes in the first chapter all the great dilemmas and the difficulties Brătianu, in particular, and Romanian political class, in general, had faced during this period of time.

Respecting the logic succession of events, the second part of the book is a thorough analysis of the Romania in the post-war decades. Much space is given to the Paris Conference and Brătianu's efforts to achieve the goals he so persistently pursued in his entire political career. And indeed, as the author stressed in the Introduction to the book, Paris, in a sense, was the culmination of a grand strategy Brătianu had worked out in the preceding quarter-century to raise the modest Romanian nation-state to a European level.

The book's final pages are in fact few reflections upon the effects that the war had upon the Romanian state and on the problems Brătianu had to deal with such as the agrarian and electoral reforms which he promised during the War, the economical progress, the multiplicity of political parties, the minorities and their status. Nevertheless, and the author insist on the idea, Brătianu's main goals remained unchanged, yet updated to the new international but also internal context, that was to consolidate Greater Romania as a unitary national state, to modernize the foundations of its economy, to mobilize its educational and cultural resources and to ensure the security of its expanded borders (p. 135).

Overall, we must appreciate the author's efforts in reinterpreting a fundamental period in our history, and express our hopes that soon enough we will have also a Romanian translation of the book.

Georgeta Fodor

Cornel Sigmirean, Corneliu Cezar Sigmirean, ***Relațiile româno-maghiare în perspectiva Conferinței de pace de la Paris***, Tîrgu Mureș, Editura Universității „Petru Maior”, 2010, 312 p.

The end of the Second World War and also the peace discussions ended with the Paris Peace Conference in 1947 represent a significant moment not only at a European or World level but also for the Romanian-Hungarian relations. The Peace Treaty of 1947 has ended a tormented period and deeply influenced the relations between Romania and Hungaria, which gradually stepped under the Soviet Union influence. The short interval which separated the war's end from the Treaty was a dynamic one from several points of view. Thus, this period must be analyzed from several perspectives: the international context, the relations between the Great Powers, their strategies in the effort of increasing their influence in this part of Europe (mainly from Soviet Union's part), respectively the efforts of the Romanian and Hungarian States in gaining support for their cause. In what the future of Transylvania is concerned, for solving this matter, several opinions – belonging to the interested parts, Romania, Hungaria, Great powers – coexisted. Memorandums and projects were elaborated by the Great Powers; several diplomatic initiatives were lead, all meant for reaching the best result, for one or the other parts. Taking this into account, it is not a surprise the fact that this sensitive mater has caused the interest of both the Hungarian (Romsics Ignác, *Az 1947-es parizsi békeszerződés*. Osiris Könyvkiadó, Budapest, 2006. Fülöp Mihály, *Pacea neterminată. Consiliul Miniștrilor Afacerilor Externe și tratatul de pace ungar 1947*, Institutul European, Iași, 2007) and the Romanian historians (Valeriu Florin Dobrinescu, *România și Ungaria de la Trianon la Paris (1920-1947). Bătălia diplomatică pentru Transilvania*, Editura Viitorul Românesc, București, 1996.) We must also mention Stefano Bottoni, *Transilvania roșie. Comunismul românesc și problema națională*. ISPMN, Cluj-Napoca, 2010, which analyses the present issue placing it on the background of the national problem in the context of instauration and the first decades of the Romanian communist regime.

Overall, it is obviously that much extent was given to this issue by both Romanian and Hungarian historiographies. The critical analyse of the documents regarding the preliminaries of the Peace Treaty found in the archives of the Romanian Foreign Minister the path of new research, interpretations and data about the real dimension of the diplomatic

activity and of the politic diplomatic efforts of the parts involved. The introductory study is a deep analyse of the diplomatic event of the 1945-1947 period. Sketching the international context of the period is followed by a description of the diplomatic activity of the two States. The authors researched the efforts of the two diplomatic offices in gaining the best result: journeys, formal and informal missions, private initiatives, opinions, suggestions, plans, personalities involved, proposals, etc. The second part of the volume has 90 documents referring to Peace Treaty preparations: the documents of the Romanian and Hungarian diplomatic services. These were selected from a wider documentary, found in archives, aiming at stressing the essence of these diplomatic efforts and the historical background they belonged to. These documents were not only selected but also work through (translated, edited). Moreover, due to their variety the authors captured the complexity and the dynamics of this historical process. The memorandums presented in the book, both the Romanian and Hungarian ones, reveal the great deep efforts that both sides had put for justifying their claims. For example we can point out the Romanian memorandums of 1946. (*Response* to His Eminence Cardinal Mindszent, Bishop of Hungary, *Memorandum* concerning Romanian legal position towards Transylvania issue, *Memorandum* concerning Romanian economic and financial contribution in the war against Germany and Hungary) or the memorandum presented by the Hungarians describing the Carpathian basin as a unity (geographically and economically) well formed across ages. Reading all this documents we can trace the dynamic of the diplomatic “confrontation”, the techniques and the answers of the two sides.

As stated above, the volume is based on documents from *The Archive of Foreign Affairs Minister, Paris Peace Conference*. The documents have been chosen with professionalism and with the common sense of the historian preoccupied of finding the relevant facts for reconstructing the historical process. The introductory study puts in historiographical context the selected documents and gives the reader the first landmarks for interpretation and analyze. The volume of documents edited by Cornel Sigmirean and Cornelius Caesar Sigmirean can be a useful tool not only for historians but also for those interested of this short, but extremely important period for the history of the two countries; for those who wish to travel back in time, to feel the atmosphere of the end of the war; for those who wish to live those moments of excitement that characterized the preparation of the Peace Conference. The book deals with a tense moment of the history of the two countries, a period in which the two sides resumed again, in Peace Times, the dispute for Transylvania. We consider that the presentation of such episodes from the history of the Central-East European area in a balanced tone, respecting the historiographical methodology helps us eliminate frustrations, tensions and to better understand certain facts, gestures of the past. Going over the introductory study and the edited documents reveals new perspectives, new research

topics for the history of the last century in order to complete the image given by these documents, such as: the Soviet game in the dispute for Transylvania and its consequences for Romanian Communist Party policy towards nationalities, the consequences of the diplomatic efforts from the perspective of the relation between the Hungarian elite and the Romanian State at the end of 1940'.

Csaba Zoltan Novak

Sharon Pardo and Joel Peters, *Uneasy Neighbors. Israel and the European Union*, Plymouth, Lexington Books, 2010, 155 p.

This book offers a deep and comprehensive analysis of EU-Israel relations. The authors, professors at Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Israel, a university in top 500, proved a remarkable capacity to understand the essence of the complex and sensible issues of EU-Israel relations in geopolitical context. The book is the result of the author's academic experience in Israel, Western Europe and USA, of their excellent documentation, of their professional method of analyzing, their penetrating reflection.

The book is organized in 5 chapters, plus the conclusion. The first chapter, "Israel, Europe and the Israeli-Palestinian Peace Process", treats the issues of Oslo Process, future of Jerusalem. Palestinian Statehood, the separation wall, Israeli settlements, the EUBAM and EUPOL-COPPS Missions. These are issues of crucial importance for the security of Israel and its citizens, but also for international relations at regional and world level. The following 2 chapters refer in a logical manner, to implementing European Neighborhood Policy and a Euro-Mediterranean Partnership.

The chapter 2 deals with Israeli-EU Relations in the Multilateral Context of Barcelona Process and of the Union for the Mediterranean. The chapter 3, "The Bilateral Nature of Israeli-EU Relations", refers to implementing of the ENP, EU-Israel Association Agreement and Action Plan.

The chapter 4 offers an interesting analysis of "Israeli Perception and Misperception of the EU", based on questionnaires, interviews and press and websites survey. In this chapter are analyzed the perceptions of political elites, public opinion, civil society, and media.

The chapter 5 made a reflection on a future model for Israeli-EU relations: "Integration without Membership". This model needs a strong institutional foundation: Euro-Israeli Partnership Council, EIP Joint Monitoring Committee, EIP Parliamentary Committee, EIP Court of Conciliation and Arbitration, the Israeli Standing Committee, an effective decision-making process. As Jean Monnet declared, "Nothing is possible without men; nothing is lasting without institutions".

In the concluding chapter, "Looking back, looking forward", the authors analyse the motives that make "uneasy" the EU-Israel relations, investigating with courage and professionalism the divergences between the two partners. This is a very interesting part and essential for avoiding of mutual miscommunications. However, there is still a large space for intense cooperation.

The EU-Israel cooperation was favored by the common historical and cultural traditions, the level of economic development of Israel's financial and technological and democratic values that share in this country in its parliamentary political system. Since 2000, it is implemented the Association Agreement between EU and Israel, which provides the reduction of customs duties on trade between the two sides and a gradual economic integration. Israel applies an "Action Plan", agreed with the EU to develop bilateral relations and common objectives.

EU-Israel cooperation in combating terrorism manifested, including exchanges at the level of experts, aiming to identify priority funding of international terrorism. Combating manifestations of anti-Semitism, racism and xenophobia is another common goal.

Israel is the first country outside the EU to successfully participate in the 7th Framework Program for research, especially accessing projects in IT and medicine. Joint Statement on the dialogue in education was followed by the implementation of concrete projects, especially Erasmus Mundus. The two sides signed an agreement on Israel's participation in community programs, which are discussed in the European Parliament.

In conclusion, this very valuable book is an essential reading for every person interested in European Neighborhood Policy and in the Israel's Foreign Affairs.

Simion Costea

Michel Labori and Simion Costea, ***Le management des politiques de l'Union Européenne***, Paris, Editions Prodifmultimedia, 2011, 304 p.

Classic Concerns

One does not pick up a book having such a title for a spot of light reading - but if it is a book that brings you up to speed on current EU concerns that you want, this book will not disappoint. It is a book that is very much the sum of its parts, inasmuch as each of its sixteen chapters fastens upon a different issue, or set of issues, confronting EU policy-makers within the present boundaries of the Union, and beyond those boundaries. At the same time, it does project a vision of the Union that transcends these parts and these issues: a Union conscious of itself as an organization whose destiny it is to grow.

This growth is not merely in numbers of members - though the book celebrates and reckons with a membership that few politicians in 1957 can have dreamt of; as the EU grows territorially, up to and perhaps beyond the limits of what might once have been thought of as the continent of Europe, so it grows in influence and ambition.

The first chapters focus on what might be called the 'classic' concerns of the Union: competition; regional policy (the systemic tension between the centre and the periphery); the Common Agricultural Policy; and the associated 'problem' of rural development. The reader of these chapters ought not to expect a fast-paced narrative - the text is marked by lists, by statistics, and by acronyms; it is eminently navigable, nevertheless. A plentiful provision of subheadings serve as groynes to break up the tide of facts; and emboldenings give prominence to salient points, for example "The Common Agricultural Policy in 2000 accounted for 44% of EU expenditure and the European Regional and Cohesion Policy accounted for 35%', or 'Romania is the country with the highest percentage of people actively involved in agriculture (40%)". For the student of EU institutions, in particular, there is a wealth of precise information concerning treaties, policies, and programmes; and an apparatus of references and bibliographic information rounds off every chapter.

Climate and Energy Policy

Beyond these classic concerns there follow chapters on EU policy relating to climate change and energy. Here, the authors begin to run on a rather longer leash: a recital of facts and figures and names and dates gives way to reasoned argument. Why, they ask, was the climate-conference held in Copenhagen just before Christmas in 2009 such a 'fiasco'? The reasons they give spare no-one:

1. The United States and China were not prepared to alter their positions;
2. Denmark's management of the conference was incompetent;
3. UN bureaucracy bore down too heavily on the proceedings;
4. The EU failed to play a leading role in the negotiations.

Since this is a book about the EU, though, it is the EU that comes in for particular criticism: in regard to the proposal that countries commit themselves to a reduction of 30% of greenhouse-gas emissions, for example, there was no progress at Copenhagen because the member countries of the EU could not, or would not, agree among themselves. No one member country is prepared to take the initiative for fear that its neighbours will enjoy an economic advantage. It is vital, say the authors, that the EU co-ordinate its efforts in the crusade against global warming if it is to influence world opinion, as it must.

The energy question is stated even more starkly, because concretely: the EU imports 80% of its oil and 50% of its natural gas. By 2030, it will need to import 90% of its oil (50% of it from OPEC countries) and 65% of its natural gas (42% of it from Russia). Dependency of this sort makes the EU very vulnerable to an interruption of supply such as that suffered by

Ukraine in January 2006, when Russia turned off the tap until its neighbour paid its dues. As in the global warming context, so in the related context of energy supply, EU members must act in concert if the lights are to remain on. The EU had its origins in a common coal and steel policy, but in recent years, member-states have marched under their own flags where energy policy is concerned. Labori and Costea are unequivocal in the warning that they issue, and in the course that they recommend: climate and energy policies must be combined in a practical policy binding all 27 member states. Where energy is concerned, this must involve a commitment to the Nabucco Project, to ensure the supply of gas from Central Asia in a pipeline that by-passes Russia; a parallel commitment to partnership with Russia in energy (and other) matters; and the opening-up of supply lines of gas from North and West Africa. Not the least laudable of the aims of this book is to put beyond doubt the importance of Europe's *being* Europe, of its *acting* as Europe, and of its speaking with one European voice, if the individual member states of Europe are to enjoy the benefits of membership, and Europe is to serve its own interests, and the interests of the world at large. This is the ideal, as the authors admit, but idealistic it is not.

Europe's Neighbours. It is acknowledged that the EU expanded a little too far, and a little too fast, for comfort: the Lisbon treaty is barely up to the huge task of adapting its 20th Century institutions to 21st Century needs. Nevertheless, the 12 new members of the EU, of 2004 and 2007, brought with them new neighbours. Thus, the 'neighbourhood' of Europe now includes Croatia and other Balkan countries, Turkey, Belarus, Russia, Ukraine, and Moldavia - and the Mediterranean, that until recently has been thought of as a natural European frontier, is perceived (not least as a result of what has happened in Tunisia and Libya this year) as just one more border to cross. Together with Russia - which already has a special relationship with the EU - no fewer than 16 nations, from Morocco to Azerbaijan, qualify as partners in the struggle against terrorism and human trafficking. The EU has an interest in their evolution as democracies with functioning market economies, and as societies in which human rights are both respected on paper, and protected on the ground. The EU has put mechanisms in place to facilitate dialogue and bilateral agreements with oriental and Mediterranean nations; but the Israel-Palestinian *impasse*, and the always delicate relationship between 'the West' and Russia, will place limits on the speed at which 'neighbours' can become colleagues.

Labori and Costea devote the longest chapter in the book (Chapter 10), and the following chapter, to EU relations with the countries in Eastern Europe that were satellites of the USSR until 1989, and that, to some extent, remain within the Russian sphere of influence; Ukraine, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, and Moldavia. One of the EU's most significant geopolitical objectives is to make of these six republics a 'circle of friends' that comes to respect European values and co-operates with the

EU in advancing security, stability and prosperity right across the region. This is the so-called 'Eastern partnership', launched in Prague in May 2009. It is a grand idea, just as the EU's overtures towards the countries of North Africa, and towards the Black Sea Forum, are grand ideas; but, the authors warn, the negotiations with the six republics are especially delicate for three reasons:

1. Each of the six republics is troubled by its own issues of democratic legitimacy, human rights, and energy dependence;
2. Russia is suspicious of, even hostile towards, any prejudice to what it perceives to be its own interests;
3. EU leaders themselves have different sets of priorities: thus, whilst Germany might be disposed to promote the Eastern Partnership, France is (as it always has been) more exercised by its relations with the countries of the Maghreb.

A Romanian Perspective

It will be of interest to readers of this book in Romania that the authors (both of them or, perhaps, Simion Costea in particular) see Romania as having its own grounds for anxiety about the Eastern Partnership. It was not consulted about the terms of the partnership in the first place; it fears that the EU's stance towards the six republics might compromise its own relations with its Black Sea partners; and - perhaps most significantly - Romania is worried that the Eastern Partnership says nothing about, and indeed may be a way of avoiding, the question of Moldavia's membership of the EU. To a non-Romanian, this may seem to be a small matter. (It may confuse, too, since the tiny republic which abuts the territory of Romania on its eastern border is referred to both as "la Moldova" and as "la Moldavie"; and the confusion is further compounded by the fact that the part of Romania that is abutted by this republic is, likewise - in English atlases - called either "Moldova" or "Moldavia"). To a Romanian, whose culture and language are the same as in the republic, the status of Moldavia/Moldova is not dust to be brushed under the carpet. Nevertheless, Romania supports the Eastern Partnership as the means by which old ghosts might be laid to rest.

The authors lay some emphasis on language: to speak of the 'Moldavian language' is to give credence to a Stalinist myth - the Moldavian language and the Romanian language are one and the same. Attention is drawn to the Romanian-speaking minority in Ukraine; and the hope is expressed that the same rights to speak and study in their language will be extended to this minority as are (now) extended to the Hungarian minority living in Romania. If this emphasis is thought to be misplaced, or exaggerated - if the Romanian perspective is put down, simply, to the fact that one of the authors is a Romanian national - it should be acknowledged that this perspective is a fitting case-study of many unresolved cultural-linguistic tensions persisting within and on and beyond the borders of the EU.

If the book focuses on Romania and its concerns in some detail (the involvement of its troops in Afghanistan; the situation of the Romanian

minority in Serbia) it does not shirk the big issues: in its final chapters, it turns its attention to the EU's relations with the USA, with China, and with the United Nations; to the accession to the Union of Turkey, Croatia, and other western Balkan nations (including newly-independent Kosovo); and to some of the likely consequences of this non-stop EU enlargement. It is difficult to think of any issue of importance that might have been left out of account. This, and the fact that the Conclusion at the end of each chapter gives a clear summary of the position of the two authors on each and every issue, makes this - for all its dry title and textbook layout - a book that all who seek an understanding of what the EU, and might be, should read.

Colin Swatridge

“Geostrategic Pulse” (Brasov), vol. 106, year 5, 20 September 2011

The publication “Geostrategic Pulse” (written in Romanian and in English) fulfilled 5 years of existence in 2011. As a journal specialized on International Relations, “Geostrategic Pulse” stands out by its extremely valuable articles, very relevant and up-to-date, as they provide both expert information and professional assessments on the contemporary developments and events. The high professional standard of the journal comes from its unique staff made of specialists with high level practical expertise in the field of international affairs.

On an exact two-week *cadenza*, the readers can have an appointment with this fine magazine and “Geostrategic Pulse” will help them gain a deep understanding of the crises in the Middle East, North Africa and the Caucasus, the foreign policy of Turkey, major events in the wider Black Sea area, the issues of energy security, newest developments in Intelligence, world security and military equipment, the geopolitical game of both the great powers and the regional actors.

As an example, in the volume 106, year 5, from 20 September 2011, Professor Vasile Pușcaș (the former Minister Negotiator with the EU) offers an interesting analyse of “the crises of European consciousness” in the context of world economic crisis, Professor Ilie Bădescu approaches the “Asymmetrical Disintegration” as a global problem, Dr. Octavian Dumitru studies the role of Crimea in the security of the Black Sea Area. The ex-diplomat Corneliu Pivariu analyses if Azerbaijan could be a N.A.T.O. member and estimates how much will resist the Assad regime in Syria, in the context of Arab Spring. The Ambassador Dumitru Chican writes about “the constructive anarchy” in the Middle East. The articles of Dr. Munir Salameh and of Reza Sahrestani are focused on Turkey-Israel Relations and on Iran-Syria relations. Scott Stewart emphasises the role of citizen in enforcing the security of a nation.

We perfectly agree with Dieter Farwick - Senior Vice President of the “World Security Network Foundation” Former Force Commander and Chief Operations at N.A.T.O. HQ, which declares that “Geostrategic Pulse is a source of finished intelligence. The facts are well-researched and the comments are value added for decision makers. The expertise on the Middle East, Eastern Europe and the Black Sea region is excellent”. In the specialized academic environment, “Geostrategic Pulse” is an extremely useful reader for the teaching activities and for the scientific papers as well. The partnerships with Harvard University and with “Petru Maior” University in Tirgu Mureş are just two aspects (among many others) confirming the magazine’s real worth and usefulness for the academic environment. “Geostrategic Pulse” is a must for the specialists in the field; it is a bulletin with critical information and analysis for the political and economic decision-makers who want to become full professionals in dealing with International Relations.

Simion Costea